

Different Digits Equivalent Fractions - II₁

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Abstract

*This work brings **equivalent fractions** for 10-digits without repetition of digits. Sometimes known as **pandigital**. For the 3 to 9 digits see first part of this work [17]. For repetition of digits, the number of equivalent fractions increases too much. These shall be dealt elsewhere.*

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¹This work is an extended and revised version of author's previous work <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a150.pdf> [8] done in 2016

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1 Introduction

Below is a little introduction on what we mean by **selfie fractions**, **equivalent selfie fractions** and **equivalent fractions**.

1.1 Selfie Fractions

The author [9, 10, 11, 12, 13] gave **selfie fractions**, recently summarized in [14]. By **selfie fractions** we understand that there are two fractions having same digits on both sides, where one of the side is with same digits in numerators and denominators, separated by certain operations. There are many ways of writing **selfie fractions**. See below some examples:

- **Addable Fractions**

$$\frac{96}{352} = \frac{9+6}{3+52}, \quad \frac{182}{6734} = \frac{18+2}{6+734}, \text{ etc.}$$

- **Subtractable Fractions**

$$\frac{204}{357} = \frac{20-4}{35-7}, \quad \frac{726}{1089} = \frac{72-6}{108-9}, \text{ etc.}$$

- **Dottable Fraction**

$$\frac{13}{624} = \frac{1 \times 3}{6 \times 24}, \quad \frac{416}{728} = \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8}, \text{ etc.}$$

- **Dottable with Potentiation Fractions**

$$\frac{95}{342} = \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2}, \quad \frac{728}{1456} = \frac{7^2 \times 8}{14 \times 56}, \text{ etc.}$$

- **Mixed Fractions: All Operations**

$$\frac{4980}{5312} = \frac{4-9+80}{5 \times (3+1)^2}, \quad \frac{3249}{5168} = \frac{(3+2^4) \times 9}{(5-1) \times 68}, \text{ etc.}$$

1.2 Equivalent Selfie Fractions

Still there are *selfie fractions* those can be written as equivalent forms, see below some examples,

- **Addable**

$$\frac{1453}{2906} = \frac{1+453}{2+906} = \frac{145+3}{290+6} = \frac{1+45+3}{2+90+6}.$$

• **Subtractable**

$$\frac{932}{1864} = \frac{9-32}{18-64} = \frac{93-2}{186-4}.$$

• **Dottable and Addable**

$$\frac{1680}{59472} = \frac{1 \times 6 \times 80}{59 \times 4 \times 72} = \frac{1+6+8+0}{59+472}.$$

• **Dottable, Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{302}{8154} = \frac{30 \times 2}{81 \times 5 \times 4} = \frac{3+02}{81+54} = \frac{3-02}{81-54}.$$

• **Symmetric Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{645}{1290} = \frac{6-45}{12-90} = \frac{6+45}{12+90}.$$

• **Dottable and Addable together**

$$\frac{284}{639} = \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{6 + 39} = \frac{28 + 4}{6 \times (3 + 9)}.$$

• **Mixed - All Operations**

$$\frac{73842}{90516} = \frac{7-3 \times (8-4^2)}{9 \times 05-1-6} = \frac{7 \times (3+8) + 4^2}{90+(5-1) \times 6} = \frac{738+4+2}{905+1+6}.$$

For more details on *equivalent* and *symmetric equivalent fractions* refer author's work, [14]. Above examples are with different digits. The work on repetition of digits shall be dealt elsewhere.

1.3 Equivalent Fraction

In this paper our aim is little different, i.e., we want to bring **equivalent fractions** without use of any operations, just with different digits. Below are some examples to understand the idea of *equivalent fractions* for different digits:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{24} = \frac{4}{32}, \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{4}{356} = \frac{6}{534}, \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{27}{3456} = \frac{42}{5376}, \\ &\quad \blacktriangleright \frac{315}{4620} = \frac{342}{5016}, \quad \blacktriangleright \frac{123}{58764} = \frac{164}{78352}, \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{26418} = \frac{618}{45732} = \frac{714}{52836} = \frac{732}{54168} = \frac{738}{54612}, \text{ etc.} \end{aligned}$$

Some studies in this direction can be seen in [3, 4, 5]. These authors concentrated on **equivalent fractions for the digits 1 to 9**, calling **pandigital fractions**. While, we worked for all digits, i.e., for 3 to 10 digits. The work for the 3 to 9 see [17]. This work is only for 10-digits. For more work on numbers in different situations refer summary of author's work [16, 17]. From historical point of view refer to classical books [1], [2].

2 10-Digits: Pandigital Equivalent Fractions

This section deals with equivalent fractions for 10 digits, 0 to 9 in each cases. Total we have 324374 for the digits 0 to 9, starting from 2 expressions. If we start from minimum 3 expressions, we have 9755 values. Since these numbers are high to put in a paper, we decided to put equivalent fractions those having more than 4 possibilities. For 2 and 3 equivalent fractions, only few values are written, as the quantity of equivalent fractions is too high. Instead starting from 4, 5 etc., we have started in reverse order, i.e., first for maximum number of expressions values. In this case we have 78. The details are given in following subsections.

2.1 78 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example, and in this situation it has maximum expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{16748}{20935} = \frac{18476}{23095} = \frac{18940}{23675} = \frac{18964}{23705} = \frac{19076}{23845} = \frac{19708}{24635} = \frac{24716}{30895} = \frac{24876}{31095} = \frac{25496}{31870} = \frac{28940}{36175} = \frac{29180}{36475} = \frac{29684}{37105} \\ & \quad = \frac{32716}{40895} = \frac{32876}{41095} = \frac{36712}{45890} = \frac{36728}{45910} = \frac{37512}{46890} = \frac{37528}{46910} = \frac{38092}{47615} = \frac{38152}{47690} = \frac{39012}{48765} = \frac{41896}{52370} = \frac{42968}{53710} \\ & \quad = \frac{46312}{46328} = \frac{46712}{46712} = \frac{47136}{47136} = \frac{47328}{47328} = \frac{47368}{47368} = \frac{48732}{48732} = \frac{49380}{49380} = \frac{49708}{49708} = \frac{51832}{51832} = \frac{53928}{53928} \\ & \quad = \frac{57890}{54312} = \frac{57910}{54328} = \frac{58390}{54712} = \frac{58920}{56984} = \frac{59160}{58496} = \frac{59210}{58912} = \frac{60915}{59328} = \frac{61725}{59368} = \frac{62135}{63124} = \frac{64790}{63140} = \frac{67410}{63152} \\ & \quad = \frac{67890}{63284} = \frac{67910}{63528} = \frac{68390}{64732} = \frac{71230}{65392} = \frac{73120}{65432} = \frac{73640}{67124} = \frac{74160}{67140} = \frac{74210}{67152} = \frac{78905}{67352} = \frac{78925}{67512} = \frac{78940}{71236} \\ & \quad = \frac{79105}{71364} = \frac{79410}{71456} = \frac{80915}{71460} = \frac{81740}{71536} = \frac{81790}{71624} = \frac{83905}{71632} = \frac{83925}{72836} = \frac{83940}{73248} = \frac{84190}{73264} = \frac{84390}{73284} = \frac{89045}{73456} \\ & \quad = \frac{89205}{73460} = \frac{89320}{73684} = \frac{89325}{74108} = \frac{89420}{74528} = \frac{89530}{74568} = \frac{89540}{74816} = \frac{91045}{75328} = \frac{91560}{75368} = \frac{91580}{76184} = \frac{91605}{76248} = \frac{91820}{76328} \\ & \quad = \frac{91825}{91825} = \frac{92105}{92105} = \frac{92635}{92635} = \frac{93160}{93160} = \frac{93210}{93210} = \frac{93520}{93520} = \frac{94160}{94160} = \frac{94210}{94210} = \frac{95230}{95230} = \frac{95310}{95310} = \frac{95410}{95410} \end{aligned}$$

2.2 48 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example with 48 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{13485}{26970} = \frac{13548}{27096} = \frac{13845}{27690} = \frac{14538}{29076} = \frac{14685}{29370} = \frac{14835}{29670} = \frac{14853}{29706} = \frac{14865}{29730} = \frac{15486}{30972} = \frac{16485}{32970} = \frac{18546}{37092} = \frac{18645}{37290} \\ & \quad = \frac{20679}{20769} = \frac{20769}{20769} = \frac{20793}{20793} = \frac{23079}{23079} = \frac{26709}{26709} = \frac{26907}{26907} = \frac{27069}{27069} = \frac{27093}{27093} = \frac{27309}{27309} = \frac{29067}{29067} = \frac{29073}{29073} \\ & \quad = \frac{41358}{29307} = \frac{41538}{30729} = \frac{41586}{30792} = \frac{46158}{30927} = \frac{53418}{31485} = \frac{53814}{32079} = \frac{54138}{32709} = \frac{54186}{32907} = \frac{54618}{34851} = \frac{58134}{35148} = \frac{58146}{35481} \\ & \quad = \frac{58614}{38145} = \frac{61458}{38451} = \frac{61584}{45138} = \frac{61854}{45186} = \frac{62970}{45381} = \frac{64158}{46185} = \frac{65418}{46851} = \frac{65814}{48135} = \frac{69702}{48351} = \frac{70296}{48513} = \frac{70962}{48516} \\ & \quad = \frac{76290}{48531} = \frac{76902}{48615} = \frac{90276}{48651} = \frac{90372}{90372} = \frac{90762}{90762} = \frac{92370}{92370} = \frac{93702}{93702} = \frac{96270}{96270} = \frac{96702}{96702} = \frac{97026}{97026} = \frac{97032}{97032} \\ & \quad = \frac{97062}{97062} = \frac{97230}{97230} = \frac{97302}{97302} \end{aligned}$$

2.3 46 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example with 46 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3187}{254960} &= \frac{4589}{367120} = \frac{4591}{367280} = \frac{4689}{375120} = \frac{4691}{375280} = \frac{4769}{381520} = \frac{5237}{418960} = \frac{5371}{429680} = \frac{5789}{463120} = \frac{5791}{463280} = \frac{5839}{467120} \\ &= \frac{5892}{471360} = \frac{5916}{473280} = \frac{5921}{473680} = \frac{6479}{518320} = \frac{6741}{539280} = \frac{6789}{543120} = \frac{6791}{543280} = \frac{6839}{547120} = \frac{7123}{569840} = \frac{7312}{584960} \\ &= \frac{7364}{589120} = \frac{7416}{593280} = \frac{7421}{593680} = \frac{7894}{631520} = \frac{7941}{635280} = \frac{8174}{653920} = \frac{8179}{654320} = \frac{8394}{671520} = \frac{8419}{673520} = \frac{8439}{675120} \\ &= \frac{8932}{714560} = \frac{8942}{715360} = \frac{8953}{716240} = \frac{8954}{716320} = \frac{9156}{732480} = \frac{9158}{732640} = \frac{9182}{734560} = \frac{9316}{745280} = \frac{9321}{745680} = \frac{9352}{748160} \\ &= \frac{9416}{753280} = \frac{9421}{753680} = \frac{9523}{761840} = \frac{9531}{762480} = \frac{9541}{763280} \end{aligned}$$

2.4 32 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example with 32 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1459}{208637} &= \frac{1649}{235807} = \frac{1658}{237094} = \frac{1706}{243958} = \frac{2756}{394108} = \frac{2837}{405691} = \frac{2851}{407693} = \frac{3189}{456027} = \frac{3196}{457028} = \frac{3649}{521807} = \frac{3918}{560274} \\ &= \frac{3928}{561704} = \frac{4103}{586729} = \frac{4132}{590876} = \frac{4237}{605891} = \frac{4251}{607893} = \frac{4253}{608179} = \frac{4952}{708136} = \frac{5034}{719862} = \frac{5168}{739024} = \frac{5196}{743028} \\ &= \frac{5328}{761904} = \frac{5461}{780923} = \frac{5463}{781209} = \frac{5741}{820963} = \frac{5763}{824109} = \frac{5921}{846703} = \frac{6378}{912054} = \frac{6518}{932074} = \frac{6701}{958243} = \frac{6801}{972543} \\ &= \frac{6821}{975403} \end{aligned}$$

2.5 28 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 2 examples, each one with 28 expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2469}{153078} &= \frac{2587}{160394} = \frac{2734}{169508} = \frac{2845}{176390} = \frac{3056}{189472} = \frac{3469}{215078} = \frac{3508}{217496} = \frac{4178}{259036} = \frac{4309}{267158} = \frac{4358}{270196} = \frac{4503}{279186} \\ &= \frac{4513}{279806} = \frac{4703}{291586} = \frac{4961}{307582} = \frac{4976}{308512} = \frac{5048}{312976} = \frac{5069}{314278} = \frac{5169}{320478} = \frac{6245}{387190} = \frac{6915}{428730} = \frac{8237}{510694} \\ &= \frac{8306}{514972} = \frac{8372}{519064} = \frac{8397}{520614} = \frac{8701}{539462} = \frac{8716}{540392} = \frac{9372}{581064} = \frac{9406}{583172} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2469}{130857} &= \frac{2839}{150467} = \frac{2843}{150679} = \frac{2968}{157304} = \frac{3492}{185076} = \frac{3708}{196524} = \frac{3867}{204951} = \frac{3897}{206541} = \frac{3916}{207548} = \frac{3918}{207654} = \frac{4073}{215869} \\ &= \frac{5078}{269134} = \frac{5168}{273904} = \frac{5397}{286041} = \frac{5694}{301782} = \frac{5716}{302948} = \frac{5864}{310792} = \frac{5926}{314078} = \frac{5982}{317046} = \frac{6984}{370152} = \frac{7406}{392518} \\ &= \frac{7832}{415096} = \frac{7853}{416209} = \frac{8037}{425961} = \frac{8219}{435607} = \frac{8623}{457019} = \frac{8703}{461259} = \frac{9201}{487653} \end{aligned}$$

2.6 27 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 2 examples, each one with 27 expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15790}{26843} &= \frac{16790}{28543} = \frac{17380}{29546} = \frac{21740}{36958} = \frac{26890}{45713} = \frac{26930}{45781} = \frac{32170}{54689} = \frac{34780}{59126} = \frac{38210}{64957} = \frac{38410}{65297} = \frac{39520}{67184} = \frac{39540}{67218} \\ &= \frac{45190}{45230} = \frac{45960}{45960} = \frac{46190}{46230} = \frac{47960}{47960} = \frac{49160}{49160} = \frac{49210}{49210} = \frac{52610}{52610} = \frac{52630}{52630} = \frac{52730}{52730} \\ &= \frac{76823}{76823} = \frac{76891}{76891} = \frac{78132}{78132} = \frac{78523}{78523} = \frac{78591}{78591} = \frac{81532}{81532} = \frac{83572}{83572} = \frac{83657}{83657} = \frac{89437}{89437} = \frac{89471}{89471} = \frac{89641}{89641} \\ &= \frac{53780}{91426} = \frac{54610}{92837} = \frac{54630}{92871} = \frac{54780}{93126} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1579}{268430} &= \frac{1679}{285430} = \frac{1738}{295460} = \frac{2174}{369580} = \frac{2689}{457130} = \frac{2693}{457810} = \frac{3217}{546890} = \frac{3478}{591260} = \frac{3821}{649570} = \frac{3841}{652970} = \frac{3952}{671840} \\ &= \frac{3954}{672180} = \frac{4519}{768230} = \frac{4523}{768910} = \frac{4596}{781320} = \frac{4619}{785230} = \frac{4623}{785910} = \frac{4796}{815320} = \frac{4916}{835720} = \frac{4921}{836570} = \frac{5261}{894370} \\ &= \frac{5263}{894710} = \frac{5273}{896410} = \frac{5378}{914260} = \frac{5461}{928370} = \frac{5463}{928710} = \frac{5478}{931260}. \end{aligned}$$

2.7 21 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example with 21 expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1567}{280493} &= \frac{1724}{308596} = \frac{1726}{308954} = \frac{1978}{354062} = \frac{2096}{375184} = \frac{2176}{389504} = \frac{2831}{506749} = \frac{2847}{509613} = \frac{3068}{549172} = \frac{3186}{570294} = \frac{3196}{572084} \\ &= \frac{3452}{617908} = \frac{3942}{705618} = \frac{3956}{708124} = \frac{4069}{728351} = \frac{4192}{750368} = \frac{4359}{780261} = \frac{4369}{782051} = \frac{4523}{809617} = \frac{4601}{823579} = \frac{5206}{931874}. \end{aligned}$$

2.8 20 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have only one example with 20 expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10345}{26897} &= \frac{14265}{37089} = \frac{14695}{38207} = \frac{16530}{42978} = \frac{17805}{46293} = \frac{21730}{56498} = \frac{23415}{60879} = \frac{23495}{61087} = \frac{23790}{61854} = \frac{25890}{67314} = \frac{25930}{67418} = \frac{29385}{76401} \\ &= \frac{29430}{76518} = \frac{30165}{78429} = \frac{30485}{79261} = \frac{31695}{82407} = \frac{31790}{82654} = \frac{34510}{89726} = \frac{35710}{92846} = \frac{37085}{96421}. \end{aligned}$$

2.9 19 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 3 examples, each one with with 19 expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10542}{36897} &= \frac{10654}{37289} = \frac{13790}{48265} = \frac{13902}{48657} = \frac{16298}{57043} = \frac{17254}{60389} = \frac{17298}{60543} = \frac{18074}{63259} = \frac{18270}{63945} = \frac{18370}{64295} = \frac{19258}{67403} = \frac{20534}{71869} \\ &= \frac{20986}{73451} = \frac{21054}{73689} = \frac{21390}{74865} = \frac{25034}{87619} = \frac{26710}{93485} = \frac{27018}{94563} = \frac{27458}{96103}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1398}{275406} &= \frac{1572}{309684} = \frac{1798}{354206} = \frac{1906}{375482} = \frac{2014}{396758} = \frac{2018}{397546} = \frac{2381}{469057} = \frac{2531}{498607} = \frac{2694}{530718} = \frac{3457}{681029} = \frac{3596}{708412} \\ &= \frac{3812}{750964} = \frac{3962}{780514} = \frac{4028}{793516} = \frac{4391}{865027} = \frac{4521}{890637} = \frac{4531}{892607} = \frac{4673}{920581} = \frac{5012}{987364}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{6234}{105978} &= \frac{6352}{107984} = \frac{7408}{125936} = \frac{7459}{126803} = \frac{7682}{130594} = \frac{7946}{135082} = \frac{8027}{136459} = \frac{8092}{137564} = \frac{8257}{140369} = \frac{8267}{140539} = \frac{8269}{140573} \\ &= \frac{8357}{142069} = \frac{8659}{147203} = \frac{9028}{153476} = \frac{9046}{153782} = \frac{9078}{154326} = \frac{9238}{157046} = \frac{9534}{162078} = \frac{9724}{165308}. \end{aligned}$$

2.10 17 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 3 examples, each one with with 17 expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10356}{28479} &= \frac{10536}{28974} = \frac{12876}{35409} = \frac{12948}{35607} = \frac{12984}{35706} = \frac{15672}{43098} = \frac{16392}{45078} = \frac{17052}{46893} = \frac{18936}{52074} = \frac{19068}{52437} = \frac{21036}{57849} = \frac{21468}{59037} \\ &= \frac{21948}{60357} = \frac{25836}{71049} = \frac{29364}{80751} = \frac{32784}{90156} = \frac{34608}{95172}. \end{aligned}$$

2.11 16 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 5 examples, each one with with 16 expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10459}{83672} &= \frac{10469}{83752} = \frac{10537}{84296} = \frac{10579}{84632} = \frac{10592}{84736} = \frac{10674}{85392} = \frac{10679}{85432} = \frac{10742}{85936} = \frac{10794}{86352} = \frac{10932}{87456} = \frac{10942}{87536} = \frac{10953}{87624} \\ &= \frac{10954}{87632} = \frac{12073}{96584} = \frac{12307}{98456} = \frac{12345}{98760} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15078}{23694} &= \frac{24857}{39061} = \frac{25697}{40381} = \frac{29071}{45683} = \frac{29106}{45738} = \frac{30912}{48576} = \frac{31052}{48796} = \frac{31976}{50248} = \frac{36974}{58102} = \frac{39487}{62051} = \frac{45136}{70928} = \frac{45906}{72138} \\ &= \frac{48503}{76219} = \frac{49651}{78023} = \frac{51394}{80762} = \frac{54901}{86273} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1639}{204875} &= \frac{1894}{236750} = \frac{2894}{361750} = \frac{2918}{364750} = \frac{3809}{476125} = \frac{3901}{487625} = \frac{4819}{602375} = \frac{4873}{609125} = \frac{4903}{612875} = \frac{4938}{617250} = \frac{6314}{789250} \\ &= \frac{6419}{802375} = \frac{6473}{809125} = \frac{6714}{839250} = \frac{7146}{893250} = \frac{7346}{918250} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2954}{316078} &= \frac{3756}{401892} = \frac{4689}{501723} = \frac{4769}{510283} = \frac{4829}{516703} = \frac{4961}{530827} = \frac{5807}{621349} = \frac{5904}{631728} = \frac{6902}{738514} = \frac{7523}{804961} = \frac{7562}{809134} \\ &= \frac{7563}{809241} = \frac{7903}{845621} = \frac{7963}{852041} = \frac{8461}{905327} = \frac{8706}{931542} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4806}{153792} &= \frac{5304}{169728} = \frac{5307}{169824} = \frac{5328}{170496} = \frac{5394}{172608} = \frac{5403}{172896} = \frac{5604}{179328} = \frac{5697}{182304} = \frac{5703}{182496} = \frac{6054}{193728} = \frac{6057}{193824} \\ &= \frac{6537}{209184} = \frac{7938}{254016} = \frac{9612}{307584} = \frac{9765}{312480} = \frac{9846}{315072} \end{aligned}$$

2.12 15 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 6 examples, each one with with 15 expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1538}{240697} &= \frac{1958}{306427} = \frac{2504}{391876} = \frac{2518}{394067} = \frac{2810}{439765} = \frac{3648}{570912} = \frac{3816}{597204} = \frac{4290}{671385} = \frac{4526}{708319} = \frac{4806}{752139} = \frac{5068}{793142} \\ &= \frac{5102}{798463} = \frac{5206}{814739} = \frac{5862}{917403} = \frac{6052}{947138} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1846}{239057} &= \frac{2470}{319865} = \frac{2910}{376845} = \frac{2946}{381507} = \frac{2970}{384615} = \frac{3876}{501942} = \frac{3926}{508417} = \frac{4086}{529137} = \frac{5204}{673918} = \frac{5312}{687904} = \frac{5892}{763014} \\ &= \frac{6124}{793058} = \frac{6294}{815073} = \frac{6370}{824915} = \frac{7430}{962185} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2630}{174895} &= \frac{3156}{209874} = \frac{3618}{240597} = \frac{3918}{260547} = \frac{4190}{278635} = \frac{5126}{340879} = \frac{5418}{360297} = \frac{5746}{382109} = \frac{5874}{390621} = \frac{7642}{508193} = \frac{7834}{520961} \\ &= \frac{7836}{521094} = \frac{8074}{536921} = \frac{8126}{540379} = \frac{9702}{645183} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2764}{158930} &= \frac{2930}{168475} = \frac{2934}{168705} = \frac{3456}{198720} = \frac{4156}{238970} = \frac{4698}{270135} = \frac{6082}{349715} = \frac{6172}{354890} = \frac{6712}{385940} = \frac{6872}{395140} = \frac{6978}{401235} \\ &= \frac{7302}{419865} = \frac{8132}{467590} = \frac{8576}{493120} = \frac{9248}{531760} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3472}{105896} &= \frac{3572}{108946} = \frac{4058}{123769} = \frac{4986}{152073} = \frac{5378}{164029} = \frac{5926}{180743} = \frac{6370}{194285} = \frac{6504}{198372} = \frac{7036}{214598} = \frac{7038}{214659} = \frac{7930}{241865} \\ &= \frac{8130}{247965} = \frac{8394}{256017} = \frac{9130}{278465} = \frac{9430}{287615}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3587}{416092} &= \frac{4837}{561092} = \frac{4921}{570836} = \frac{4923}{571068} = \frac{5413}{627908} = \frac{6203}{719548} = \frac{6395}{741820} = \frac{7029}{815364} = \frac{7039}{816524} = \frac{7195}{834620} = \frac{7215}{836940} \\ &= \frac{7329}{850164} = \frac{7865}{912340} = \frac{8041}{932756} = \frac{8057}{934612}. \end{aligned}$$

2.13 14 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 2 examples, each one with with 14 expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1509}{274638} &= \frac{1794}{326508} = \frac{1896}{345072} = \frac{1908}{347256} = \frac{1962}{357084} = \frac{2019}{367458} = \frac{2097}{381654} = \frac{2973}{541086} = \frac{3018}{549276} = \frac{4056}{738192} = \frac{5043}{917826} \\ &= \frac{5046}{918372} = \frac{5103}{928746} = \frac{5301}{964782}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2967}{103845} &= \frac{3654}{127890} = \frac{3674}{128590} = \frac{3687}{129045} = \frac{5342}{186970} = \frac{6709}{234815} = \frac{7418}{259630} = \frac{7483}{261905} = \frac{8627}{301945} = \frac{8649}{302715} = \frac{8749}{306215} \\ &= \frac{9167}{320845} = \frac{9786}{342510} = \frac{9862}{345170}. \end{aligned}$$

2.14 13 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 9 examples, each one with 13 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1347}{289605} &= \frac{1376}{295840} = \frac{1384}{297560} = \frac{1627}{349805} = \frac{1672}{359480} = \frac{1873}{402695} = \frac{2138}{459670} = \frac{2158}{463970} = \frac{2189}{470635} = \frac{2716}{583940} = \frac{2813}{604795} \\ &= \frac{3247}{698105} = \frac{4013}{862795}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1357}{426098} &= \frac{1509}{473826} = \frac{1563}{490782} = \frac{1567}{492038} = \frac{1572}{493608} = \frac{1583}{497062} = \frac{1829}{574306} = \frac{2389}{750146} = \frac{2736}{859104} = \frac{2745}{861930} = \frac{3012}{945768} \\ &= \frac{3018}{947652} = \frac{3106}{975284}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1378}{259064} &= \frac{1435}{269780} = \frac{1547}{290836} = \frac{1583}{297604} = \frac{1894}{356072} = \frac{3021}{567948} = \frac{3042}{571896} = \frac{3082}{579416} = \frac{3094}{581672} = \frac{3715}{698420} = \frac{4235}{796180} \\ &= \frac{5164}{970832} = \frac{5203}{978164}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1596}{247380} &= \frac{1803}{279465} = \frac{2514}{389670} = \frac{2697}{418035} = \frac{2703}{418965} = \frac{2973}{460815} = \frac{3027}{469185} = \frac{3879}{601245} = \frac{3954}{612870} = \frac{3984}{617520} = \frac{4218}{653790} \\ &= \frac{4596}{712380} = \frac{6027}{934185}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2043}{187956} &= \frac{4086}{375912} = \frac{5091}{468372} = \frac{5196}{478032} = \frac{5208}{479136} = \frac{5301}{487692} = \frac{5316}{489072} = \frac{5328}{490176} = \frac{8196}{754032} = \frac{8295}{763140} = \frac{8631}{794052} \\ &= \frac{9153}{842076} = \frac{9312}{856704}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2086}{157493} &= \frac{3416}{257908} = \frac{3458}{261079} = \frac{3470}{261985} = \frac{3790}{286145} = \frac{4718}{356209} = \frac{4912}{370856} = \frac{5028}{379614} = \frac{5172}{390486} = \frac{7082}{534691} = \frac{8930}{674215} \\ &= \frac{9104}{687352} = \frac{9830}{742165}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2306}{194857} &= \frac{4716}{398502} = \frac{6278}{530491} = \frac{7014}{592683} = \frac{7214}{609583} = \frac{7598}{642031} = \frac{8172}{690534} = \frac{8210}{693745} = \frac{8462}{715039} = \frac{8652}{731094} = \frac{8912}{753064} \\ &= \frac{8916}{753402} = \frac{9512}{803764}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2397}{105468} &= \frac{2967}{130548} = \frac{2974}{130856} = \frac{3297}{145068} = \frac{3429}{150876} = \frac{4083}{179652} = \frac{4739}{208516} = \frac{5917}{260348} = \frac{6345}{279180} = \frac{6948}{305712} = \frac{7915}{348260} \\ &= \frac{7961}{350284} = \frac{9172}{403568}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3906}{154287} &= \frac{4328}{170956} = \frac{4870}{192365} = \frac{5032}{198764} = \frac{5164}{203978} = \frac{5846}{230917} = \frac{6938}{274051} = \frac{7358}{290641} = \frac{7514}{296803} = \frac{7642}{301859} = \frac{7658}{302491} \\ &= \frac{7862}{310549} = \frac{8042}{317659}. \end{aligned}$$

2.15 12 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 12 examples, each one with 12 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13458}{67290} &= \frac{13584}{67920} = \frac{13854}{69270} = \frac{14538}{72690} = \frac{14586}{72930} = \frac{14658}{73290} = \frac{15384}{76920} = \frac{15846}{79230} = \frac{15864}{79320} = \frac{18534}{92670} = \frac{18546}{92730} = \frac{18654}{93270}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14835}{20769} &= \frac{16485}{23079} = \frac{18390}{25746} = \frac{19560}{27384} = \frac{28695}{40173} = \frac{29670}{41538} = \frac{32970}{46158} = \frac{36780}{51492} = \frac{39120}{54768} = \frac{43980}{61572} = \frac{47130}{65982} = \frac{60195}{84273}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15479}{20863} &= \frac{27094}{36518} = \frac{30958}{41726} = \frac{35627}{48019} = \frac{37812}{50964} = \frac{38617}{52049} = \frac{42803}{57691} = \frac{45287}{61039} = \frac{52394}{70618} = \frac{53406}{71982} = \frac{53498}{72106} = \frac{71254}{96038}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16375}{24890} &= \frac{26150}{39748} = \frac{31975}{48602} = \frac{32175}{48906} = \frac{41375}{62890} = \frac{41975}{63802} = \frac{48625}{73910} = \frac{61075}{92834} = \frac{62375}{94810} = \frac{63825}{97014} = \frac{64025}{97318} = \frac{64350}{97812}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1057}{293846} &= \frac{1402}{389756} = \frac{1785}{496230} = \frac{1823}{506794} = \frac{1873}{520694} = \frac{2041}{567398} = \frac{2137}{594086} = \frac{2341}{650798} = \frac{2541}{706398} = \frac{2568}{713904} = \frac{3064}{851792} = \frac{3207}{891546}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1594}{263807} &= \frac{1694}{280357} = \frac{1968}{325704} = \frac{2178}{360459} = \frac{2536}{419708} = \frac{3194}{528607} = \frac{3608}{597124} = \frac{3902}{645781} = \frac{4356}{720918} = \frac{5072}{839416} = \frac{5682}{940371} = \frac{5702}{943681}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{387695} &= \frac{2968}{571340} = \frac{3490}{671825} = \frac{3528}{679140} = \frac{3928}{756140} = \frac{4062}{781935} = \frac{4102}{789635} = \frac{4310}{829675} = \frac{4630}{891275} = \frac{4738}{912065} = \frac{4786}{921305} = \frac{5124}{986370}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2578}{310649} &= \frac{2654}{319807} = \frac{4238}{510679} = \frac{4806}{579123} = \frac{5094}{613827} = \frac{5842}{703961} = \frac{5926}{714083} = \frac{5932}{714806} = \frac{6158}{742039} = \frac{6502}{783491} = \frac{7132}{859406} = \frac{8104}{976532}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{2697}{134850} &= \frac{2769}{138450} = \frac{2937}{146850} = \frac{2967}{148350} = \frac{2973}{148650} = \frac{3297}{164850} = \frac{3729}{186450} = \frac{6297}{314850} = \frac{7629}{381450} = \frac{9237}{461850} = \frac{9627}{481350} = \frac{9723}{486150}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3205}{146789} &= \frac{3470}{158926} = \frac{3805}{174269} = \frac{3820}{174956} = \frac{4320}{197856} = \frac{6410}{293578} = \frac{6415}{293807} = \frac{6485}{297013} = \frac{6745}{308921} = \frac{6940}{317852} = \frac{8640}{395712} = \frac{9185}{420673}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{6729}{134580} &= \frac{6792}{135840} = \frac{6927}{138540} = \frac{7269}{145380} = \frac{7293}{145860} = \frac{7329}{146580} = \frac{7692}{153840} = \frac{7923}{158460} = \frac{7932}{158640} = \frac{9267}{185340} = \frac{9273}{185460} = \frac{9327}{186540}. \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1835796} &= \frac{206}{1853794} = \frac{402}{3617598} = \frac{408}{3671592} = \frac{429}{3860571} = \frac{602}{5417398} = \frac{608}{5471392} = \frac{759}{6830241} = \frac{804}{7235196} = \frac{806}{7253194} = \frac{924}{8315076} = \frac{957}{8612043}. \end{aligned}$$

2.16 11 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 6 examples, each one with 11 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{14756}{20398} = \frac{17068}{23594} = \frac{31076}{42958} = \frac{36278}{50149} = \frac{37604}{51982} = \frac{41038}{56729} = \frac{42806}{59173} = \frac{50184}{69372} = \frac{65314}{90287} = \frac{68170}{94235} = \frac{71230}{98465}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{15079}{24836} = \frac{18054}{29736} = \frac{19856}{32704} = \frac{30158}{49672} = \frac{36108}{59472} = \frac{39712}{65408} = \frac{41038}{67592} = \frac{43809}{72156} = \frac{50371}{82964} = \frac{52904}{87136} = \frac{56712}{93408}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1452}{370986} = \frac{1972}{503846} = \frac{1986}{507423} = \frac{2034}{519687} = \frac{2916}{745038} = \frac{2930}{748615} = \frac{2936}{750148} = \frac{3502}{894761} = \frac{3682}{940751} = \frac{3702}{945861} = \frac{3742}{956081}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2079}{153846} = \frac{2385}{176490} = \frac{4158}{307692} = \frac{5673}{419802} = \frac{6207}{459318} = \frac{6783}{501942} = \frac{6942}{513708} = \frac{7284}{539016} = \frac{9102}{673548} = \frac{9543}{706182} = \frac{9642}{713508}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3804}{295761} = \frac{4072}{316598} = \frac{5192}{403678} = \frac{5308}{412697} = \frac{6312}{490758} = \frac{6472}{503198} = \frac{6912}{537408} = \frac{7852}{610493} = \frac{9340}{726185} = \frac{9364}{728051} = \frac{9648}{750132}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3970}{124658} = \frac{4980}{156372} = \frac{5490}{172386} = \frac{6205}{194837} = \frac{6785}{213049} = \frac{6945}{218073} = \frac{7490}{235186} = \frac{7610}{238954} = \frac{7685}{241309} = \frac{7835}{246019} = \frac{8405}{263917}. \end{aligned}$$

2.17 10 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 9 examples, each one with 10 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{10598}{23467} = \frac{13076}{28954} = \frac{18326}{40579} = \frac{20398}{45167} = \frac{21630}{47895} = \frac{27034}{59861} = \frac{27930}{61845} = \frac{30492}{67518} = \frac{39074}{86521} = \frac{39410}{87265}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12804}{39576} = \frac{15873}{49062} = \frac{16027}{49538} = \frac{16038}{49572} = \frac{16478}{50932} = \frac{17094}{52836} = \frac{21835}{67490} = \frac{21945}{67830} = \frac{31207}{96458} = \frac{31724}{98056}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{13290}{58476} = \frac{13470}{59268} = \frac{15430}{67892} = \frac{15780}{69432} = \frac{16385}{72094} = \frac{16805}{73942} = \frac{16905}{74382} = \frac{20835}{91674} = \frac{21670}{95348} = \frac{21835}{96074}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{13680}{24795} = \frac{19072}{34568} = \frac{21504}{38976} = \frac{23056}{41789} = \frac{31408}{56927} = \frac{31904}{57826} = \frac{32096}{58174} = \frac{41952}{76038} = \frac{45072}{81693} = \frac{50672}{91843}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{15496}{32780} = \frac{18564}{39270} = \frac{21736}{45980} = \frac{31902}{67485} = \frac{31928}{67540} = \frac{35984}{76120} = \frac{41392}{87560} = \frac{42718}{90365} = \frac{43576}{92180} = \frac{43810}{92675}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{36025}{41789} = \frac{39725}{46081} = \frac{63950}{74182} = \frac{69175}{80243} = \frac{69325}{80417} = \frac{70425}{81693} = \frac{71950}{83462} = \frac{72150}{83694} = \frac{78650}{91234} = \frac{80725}{93641}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1784}{239056} = \frac{3079}{412586} = \frac{3185}{426790} = \frac{3658}{490172} = \frac{3768}{504912} = \frac{4027}{539618} = \frac{5172}{693048} = \frac{5329}{714086} = \frac{5462}{731908} = \frac{6845}{917230}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{204953} = \frac{3780}{412965} = \frac{5784}{631902} = \frac{5892}{643701} = \frac{5932}{648071} = \frac{6584}{719302} = \frac{7692}{840351} = \frac{7904}{863512} = \frac{8276}{904153} = \frac{8620}{941735}. \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2538}{164970} = \frac{3876}{251940} = \frac{3918}{254670} = \frac{4137}{268905} = \frac{4518}{293670} = \frac{6279}{408135} = \frac{6972}{453180} = \frac{7203}{468195} = \frac{7896}{513240} = \frac{8196}{532740}. \end{aligned}$$

2.18 9 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 20 examples, each one with 9 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{12584}{30976} = \frac{18603}{45792} = \frac{20137}{49568} = \frac{21697}{53408} = \frac{24037}{59168} = \frac{29861}{73504} = \frac{37206}{91584} = \frac{37245}{91680} = \frac{38701}{95264} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{15893}{27640} = \frac{19872}{34560} = \frac{23897}{41560} = \frac{35489}{61720} = \frac{38594}{67120} = \frac{39514}{68720} = \frac{46759}{81320} = \frac{49312}{85760} = \frac{53176}{92480} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{16907}{38425} = \frac{17963}{40825} = \frac{27918}{63450} = \frac{28193}{64075} = \frac{30129}{68475} = \frac{30481}{69275} = \frac{34826}{79150} = \frac{36047}{81925} = \frac{36971}{84025} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{17596}{24380} = \frac{26809}{37145} = \frac{28967}{40135} = \frac{35192}{48760} = \frac{39176}{54280} = \frac{41832}{57960} = \frac{45318}{62790} = \frac{45982}{63710} = \frac{53618}{74290} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{18359}{26704} = \frac{27401}{39856} = \frac{32901}{47856} = \frac{40821}{59376} = \frac{41063}{59728} = \frac{49203}{71568} = \frac{50963}{74128} = \frac{51293}{74608} = \frac{59147}{86032} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1098}{243756} = \frac{1485}{329670} = \frac{1782}{395604} = \frac{1836}{407592} = \frac{1908}{423576} = \frac{2079}{461538} = \frac{3564}{791208} = \frac{3627}{805194} = \frac{4158}{923076} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1378}{209456} = \frac{2567}{390184} = \frac{2615}{397480} = \frac{3109}{472568} = \frac{3129}{475608} = \frac{4179}{635208} = \frac{4639}{705128} = \frac{5273}{801496} = \frac{6435}{978120} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1596}{237804} = \frac{1704}{253896} = \frac{2541}{378609} = \frac{2601}{387549} = \frac{2697}{401853} = \frac{3069}{457281} = \frac{3192}{475608} = \frac{3198}{476502} = \frac{5316}{792084} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1653}{429780} = \frac{2173}{564980} = \frac{2379}{618540} = \frac{2589}{673140} = \frac{2593}{674180} = \frac{2943}{765180} = \frac{3179}{826540} = \frac{3451}{897260} = \frac{3571}{928460} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2768}{143590} = \frac{2976}{154380} = \frac{3456}{179280} = \frac{3672}{190485} = \frac{4976}{258130} = \frac{6072}{314985} = \frac{6184}{320795} = \frac{6728}{349015} = \frac{6784}{351920} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2945}{108376} = \frac{3960}{145728} = \frac{3975}{146280} = \frac{4320}{158976} = \frac{4865}{179032} = \frac{5360}{197248} = \frac{8415}{309672} = \frac{8640}{317952} = \frac{8675}{319240} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2976}{135408} = \frac{3276}{149058} = \frac{4830}{219765} = \frac{6354}{289107} = \frac{7068}{321594} = \frac{7518}{342069} = \frac{7602}{345891} = \frac{8190}{372645} = \frac{8952}{407316} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3108}{425796} = \frac{3291}{450867} = \frac{3681}{504297} = \frac{5031}{689247} = \frac{5208}{713496} = \frac{6102}{835974} = \frac{6201}{849537} = \frac{6273}{859401} = \frac{6582}{901734} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3470}{168295} = \frac{3502}{169847} = \frac{3754}{182069} = \frac{4870}{236195} = \frac{4890}{237165} = \frac{7210}{349685} = \frac{8170}{396245} = \frac{8790}{426315} = \frac{9286}{450371} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3548}{196027} = \frac{3940}{217685} = \frac{5628}{310947} = \frac{5908}{326417} = \frac{6804}{375921} = \frac{7352}{406198} = \frac{9308}{514267} = \frac{9376}{518024} = \frac{9468}{523107} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3652}{407198} = \frac{4608}{513792} = \frac{5498}{613027} = \frac{6390}{712485} = \frac{7196}{802354} = \frac{7234}{806591} = \frac{7296}{813504} = \frac{7356}{820194} = \frac{8230}{917645} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{4293}{510867} = \frac{4362}{519078} = \frac{6759}{804321} = \frac{6903}{821457} = \frac{7029}{836451} = \frac{7506}{893214} = \frac{7824}{931056} = \frac{8103}{964257} = \frac{8154}{970326} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{4653}{120978} = \frac{4765}{123890} = \frac{7943}{206518} = \frac{8345}{216970} = \frac{8365}{217490} = \frac{9071}{235846} = \frac{9531}{247806} = \frac{9643}{250718} = \frac{9781}{254306} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4920}{358176} &= \frac{4975}{362180} = \frac{5470}{398216} = \frac{5760}{419328} = \frac{6015}{437892} = \frac{6510}{473928} = \frac{9635}{701428} = \frac{9830}{715624} = \frac{9840}{716352} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{507}{1824693} &= \frac{526}{1893074} = \frac{569}{2047831} = \frac{594}{2137806} = \frac{597}{2148603} = \frac{607}{2184593} = \frac{841}{3026759} = \frac{851}{3062749} = \frac{894}{3217506} \end{aligned}$$

2.19 8 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 39 examples, each one with 8 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12860}{73945} &= \frac{12980}{74635} = \frac{13208}{75946} = \frac{13820}{79465} = \frac{13956}{80247} = \frac{15604}{89723} = \frac{15728}{90436} = \frac{15736}{90482} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{12908}{53476} &= \frac{12964}{53708} = \frac{14308}{59276} = \frac{15407}{63829} = \frac{16954}{70238} = \frac{16982}{70354} = \frac{18249}{75603} = \frac{20167}{83549} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13698}{20547} &= \frac{16938}{25407} = \frac{18306}{27459} = \frac{18630}{27945} = \frac{30186}{45279} = \frac{30618}{45927} = \frac{61830}{92745} = \frac{63018}{94527} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14350}{26978} &= \frac{16425}{30879} = \frac{32175}{60489} = \frac{37150}{69842} = \frac{42350}{79618} = \frac{43675}{82109} = \frac{46325}{87091} = \frac{48725}{91603} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15237}{60948} &= \frac{17235}{68940} = \frac{17352}{69408} = \frac{20394}{81576} = \frac{20439}{81756} = \frac{21735}{86940} = \frac{23517}{94068} = \frac{23715}{94860} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17936}{25840} &= \frac{18703}{26945} = \frac{19647}{28305} = \frac{26019}{37485} = \frac{39412}{56780} = \frac{39648}{57120} = \frac{42598}{61370} = \frac{65372}{94180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19458}{32706} &= \frac{26837}{45109} = \frac{28059}{47163} = \frac{34028}{57196} = \frac{39104}{65728} = \frac{42159}{70863} = \frac{50196}{84372} = \frac{53674}{90218} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26047}{31598} &= \frac{28914}{35076} = \frac{39162}{47508} = \frac{51972}{63048} = \frac{59048}{71632} = \frac{65148}{79032} = \frac{78324}{95016} = \frac{80154}{97236} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27508}{39146} &= \frac{30186}{42957} = \frac{40976}{58312} = \frac{53482}{76109} = \frac{56342}{80179} = \frac{57694}{82103} = \frac{60372}{85914} = \frac{64870}{92315} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1045}{267938} &= \frac{1780}{456392} = \frac{1795}{460238} = \frac{1825}{467930} = \frac{2395}{614078} = \frac{2940}{753816} = \frac{3560}{912784} = \frac{3745}{960218} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1046}{257839} &= \frac{1490}{367285} = \frac{2316}{570894} = \frac{2418}{596037} = \frac{2490}{613785} = \frac{2846}{701539} = \frac{2904}{715836} = \frac{3672}{905148} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1209}{368745} &= \frac{1269}{387045} = \frac{1396}{425780} = \frac{1397}{426085} = \frac{1736}{529480} = \frac{1768}{539240} = \frac{1926}{587430} = \frac{2089}{637145} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1283}{460597} &= \frac{1308}{469572} = \frac{1627}{584093} = \frac{1962}{704358} = \frac{2369}{850471} = \frac{2379}{854061} = \frac{2439}{875601} = \frac{2734}{981506} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{1590}{267438} &= \frac{2145}{360789} = \frac{2730}{459186} = \frac{3460}{581972} = \frac{4215}{708963} = \frac{4915}{826703} = \frac{5460}{918372} = \frac{5480}{921736} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{1768}{392054} = \frac{1784}{395602} = \frac{2156}{478093} = \frac{3028}{671459} = \frac{3428}{760159} = \frac{3568}{791204} = \frac{3904}{865712} = \frac{4380}{971265} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1830}{256749} = \frac{2580}{361974} = \frac{3290}{461587} = \frac{3870}{542961} = \frac{5160}{723948} = \frac{5430}{761829} = \frac{6580}{923174} = \frac{6780}{951234} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1839}{257460} = \frac{1956}{273840} = \frac{2967}{415380} = \frac{3297}{461580} = \frac{3678}{514920} = \frac{3912}{547680} = \frac{4398}{615720} = \frac{4713}{659820} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2016}{375984} = \frac{2046}{381579} = \frac{3108}{579642} = \frac{3594}{670281} = \frac{3708}{691542} = \frac{4032}{751968} = \frac{4092}{763158} = \frac{5274}{983601} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2037}{149865} = \frac{3598}{264710} = \frac{3689}{271405} = \frac{3801}{279645} = \frac{5124}{376980} = \frac{8372}{615940} = \frac{8932}{657140} = \frac{9247}{680315} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2037}{156849} = \frac{4167}{320859} = \frac{5283}{406791} = \frac{5691}{438207} = \frac{6351}{489027} = \frac{6807}{524139} = \frac{7038}{541926} = \frac{8247}{635019} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2041}{359687} = \frac{2054}{361978} = \frac{3081}{542967} = \frac{4108}{723956} = \frac{4693}{827051} = \frac{5148}{907236} = \frac{5278}{930146} = \frac{5603}{987421} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2508}{134976} = \frac{2794}{150368} = \frac{2937}{158064} = \frac{6501}{349872} = \frac{7953}{428016} = \frac{8096}{435712} = \frac{9053}{487216} = \frac{9867}{531024} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2964}{137085} = \frac{5184}{239760} = \frac{6140}{283975} = \frac{6308}{291745} = \frac{6724}{310985} = \frac{6748}{312095} = \frac{8460}{391275} = \frac{8476}{392015} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2970}{164835} = \frac{3564}{197802} = \frac{4158}{230769} = \frac{7128}{395604} = \frac{7236}{401598} = \frac{7362}{408591} = \frac{7902}{438561} = \frac{9702}{538461} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3056}{271984} = \frac{4021}{357869} = \frac{4168}{370952} = \frac{6172}{549308} = \frac{7408}{659312} = \frac{8321}{740569} = \frac{8461}{753029} = \frac{9507}{846123} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3408}{172956} = \frac{3528}{179046} = \frac{3872}{196504} = \frac{5304}{269178} = \frac{6812}{345709} = \frac{6912}{350784} = \frac{8612}{437059} = \frac{9268}{470351} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3648}{105792} = \frac{3756}{108924} = \frac{5934}{172086} = \frac{6048}{175392} = \frac{6702}{194358} = \frac{6708}{194532} = \frac{6738}{195402} = \frac{8769}{254301} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3705}{149682} = \frac{4380}{176952} = \frac{5370}{216948} = \frac{5740}{231896} = \frac{5910}{238764} = \frac{6935}{280174} = \frac{7960}{321584} = \frac{9105}{367842} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3720}{156984} = \frac{4580}{193276} = \frac{4985}{210367} = \frac{5490}{231678} = \frac{5780}{243916} = \frac{7065}{298143} = \frac{7690}{324518} = \frac{9765}{412083} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3904}{127856} = \frac{5032}{164798} = \frac{5436}{178029} = \frac{5824}{190736} = \frac{6032}{197548} = \frac{7380}{241695} = \frac{7980}{261345} = \frac{8304}{271956} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4095}{371826} = \frac{6310}{572948} = \frac{8190}{743652} = \frac{9105}{826734} = \frac{9325}{846710} = \frac{9605}{872134} = \frac{9615}{873042} = \frac{9640}{875312} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4826}{103759} = \frac{6298}{135407} = \frac{7086}{152349} = \frac{8230}{176945} = \frac{9376}{201584} = \frac{9384}{201756} = \frac{9518}{204637} = \frac{9784}{210356} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5038}{291746} = \frac{5918}{342706} = \frac{6127}{354809} = \frac{9108}{527436} = \frac{9328}{540176} = \frac{9361}{542087} = \frac{9702}{561834} = \frac{9724}{563108} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{5302}{176894} = \frac{5632}{187904} = \frac{5764}{192308} = \frac{5786}{193042} = \frac{8019}{267543} = \frac{9218}{307546} = \frac{9251}{308647} = \frac{9614}{320758} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5418}{273609} = \frac{5814}{293607} = \frac{7092}{358146} = \frac{7218}{364509} = \frac{7290}{368145} = \frac{7812}{394506} = \frac{9072}{458136} = \frac{9270}{468135} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{2567490} = \frac{258}{3619740} = \frac{329}{4615870} = \frac{387}{5429610} = \frac{516}{7239480} = \frac{543}{7618290} = \frac{658}{9231740} = \frac{678}{9512340} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{295}{1703684} = \frac{325}{1876940} = \frac{365}{2107948} = \frac{380}{2194576} = \frac{415}{2396708} = \frac{570}{3291864} = \frac{730}{4215896} = \frac{760}{4389152} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{521}{3867904} = \frac{524}{3890176} = \frac{608}{4513792} = \frac{692}{5137408} = \frac{803}{5961472} = \frac{921}{6837504} = \frac{984}{7305216} = \frac{985}{7312640} \end{aligned}$$

2.20 7 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 52 examples, each one with 7 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{13984}{25760} = \frac{21584}{39760} = \frac{29184}{53760} = \frac{31426}{57890} = \frac{43168}{79520} = \frac{53124}{97860} = \frac{53276}{98140} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{15908}{36472} = \frac{17589}{40326} = \frac{19762}{45308} = \frac{21607}{49538} = \frac{21976}{50384} = \frac{35219}{80746} = \frac{42107}{96538} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{23760} = \frac{25974}{38610} = \frac{27639}{41085} = \frac{28971}{43065} = \frac{31968}{47520} = \frac{41958}{62370} = \frac{57942}{86130} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{16092}{37548} = \frac{19602}{45738} = \frac{21843}{50967} = \frac{25893}{60417} = \frac{32184}{75096} = \frac{32589}{76041} = \frac{41067}{95823} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{16497}{25380} = \frac{25194}{38760} = \frac{25467}{39180} = \frac{29367}{45180} = \frac{45318}{69720} = \frac{51324}{78960} = \frac{53274}{81960} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{23940} = \frac{18459}{26370} = \frac{31689}{45270} = \frac{36918}{52740} = \frac{37926}{54180} = \frac{41832}{59760} = \frac{53298}{76140} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{19647}{25308} = \frac{19706}{25384} = \frac{32509}{41876} = \frac{39412}{50768} = \frac{39648}{51072} = \frac{47318}{60952} = \frac{71685}{92340} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{19720}{34568} = \frac{21590}{37846} = \frac{28305}{49617} = \frac{32470}{56918} = \frac{43180}{75692} = \frac{52360}{91784} = \frac{53720}{94168} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{25396}{48071} = \frac{28476}{53901} = \frac{41860}{79235} = \frac{42756}{80931} = \frac{43092}{81567} = \frac{47628}{90153} = \frac{51268}{97043} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{26871}{35490} = \frac{28461}{37590} = \frac{36729}{48510} = \frac{38796}{51240} = \frac{47859}{63210} = \frac{63759}{84210} = \frac{72186}{95340} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{27168}{39054} = \frac{27936}{40158} = \frac{31728}{45609} = \frac{49536}{71208} = \frac{63504}{91287} = \frac{64752}{93081} = \frac{65184}{93702} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{358976} = \frac{1920}{485376} = \frac{2735}{691408} = \frac{2910}{735648} = \frac{3095}{782416} = \frac{3725}{941680} = \frac{3845}{972016} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1472}{309856} = \frac{1704}{358692} = \frac{1854}{390267} = \frac{1872}{394056} = \frac{1936}{407528} = \frac{3094}{651287} = \frac{3562}{749801} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1548}{273609} = \frac{1984}{350672} = \frac{2780}{491365} = \frac{3096}{547218} = \frac{3548}{627109} = \frac{4516}{798203} = \frac{5128}{906374} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1572}{304968} = \frac{1584}{307296} = \frac{1785}{346290} = \frac{2397}{465018} = \frac{3651}{708294} = \frac{4173}{809562} = \frac{5073}{984162} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{289536} = \frac{1745}{290368} = \frac{1975}{328640} = \frac{3725}{619840} = \frac{4290}{713856} = \frac{4325}{719680} = \frac{5240}{871936} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1870}{253946} = \frac{3165}{429807} = \frac{3790}{514682} = \frac{6785}{921403} = \frac{6830}{927514} = \frac{7085}{962143} = \frac{7130}{968254} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{305824} = \frac{2054}{317896} = \frac{3692}{571408} = \frac{4108}{635792} = \frac{4589}{710236} = \frac{5824}{901376} = \frac{5863}{907412} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2043}{175698} = \frac{3471}{298506} = \frac{5091}{437826} = \frac{7203}{619458} = \frac{7935}{682410} = \frac{8169}{702534} = \frac{8415}{723690} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2305}{196847} = \frac{4180}{356972} = \frac{4190}{357826} = \frac{5780}{493612} = \frac{8540}{729316} = \frac{8610}{735294} = \frac{9210}{786534} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2394}{167580} = \frac{2637}{184590} = \frac{4527}{316890} = \frac{5274}{369180} = \frac{5418}{379260} = \frac{5976}{418320} = \frac{7614}{532980} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{175960} = \frac{4876}{351920} = \frac{5428}{391760} = \frac{5796}{418320} = \frac{6279}{453180} = \frac{6371}{459820} = \frac{7429}{536180} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{137984} = \frac{2870}{154693} = \frac{4710}{253869} = \frac{4890}{263571} = \frac{7160}{385924} = \frac{7680}{413952} = \frac{8570}{461923} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2576}{139840} = \frac{3976}{215840} = \frac{5376}{291840} = \frac{5789}{314260} = \frac{7952}{431680} = \frac{9786}{531240} = \frac{9814}{532760} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2586}{140937} = \frac{3042}{165789} = \frac{3624}{197508} = \frac{5904}{321768} = \frac{7092}{386514} = \frac{7248}{395016} = \frac{9408}{512736} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2705}{138496} = \frac{2905}{148736} = \frac{3295}{168704} = \frac{7215}{369408} = \frac{7460}{381952} = \frac{8930}{457216} = \frac{9280}{475136} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2716}{308945} = \frac{2796}{318045} = \frac{5432}{617890} = \frac{5928}{674310} = \frac{8136}{925470} = \frac{8216}{934570} = \frac{8416}{957320} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2790}{143685} = \frac{3048}{156972} = \frac{3768}{194052} = \frac{3984}{205176} = \frac{7968}{410352} = \frac{8310}{427965} = \frac{9102}{468753} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3270}{196854} = \frac{3280}{197456} = \frac{4590}{276318} = \frac{4835}{291067} = \frac{5810}{349762} = \frac{8670}{521934} = \frac{9670}{582134} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3278}{154960} = \frac{3927}{185640} = \frac{4598}{217360} = \frac{6754}{319280} = \frac{7612}{359840} = \frac{8756}{413920} = \frac{9218}{435760} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3458}{107692} = \frac{4039}{125786} = \frac{6342}{197508} = \frac{6895}{214730} = \frac{7581}{236094} = \frac{7819}{243506} = \frac{9716}{302584} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3549}{268710} = \frac{3759}{284610} = \frac{4851}{367290} = \frac{5124}{387960} = \frac{6321}{478590} = \frac{8421}{637590} = \frac{9534}{721860} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3570}{294168} = \frac{4590}{378216} = \frac{7830}{645192} = \frac{9015}{742836} = \frac{9180}{756432} = \frac{9510}{783624} = \frac{9735}{802164} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3645}{107892} = \frac{4705}{139268} = \frac{4725}{139860} = \frac{6045}{178932} = \frac{8135}{240796} = \frac{8310}{245976} = \frac{9410}{278536} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3752}{140968} = \frac{4508}{169372} = \frac{5047}{189623} = \frac{5376}{201984} = \frac{7504}{281936} = \frac{9478}{356102} = \frac{9702}{364518} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{3980}{275416} = \frac{4130}{285796} = \frac{4590}{317628} = \frac{5480}{379216} = \frac{7690}{532148} = \frac{7860}{543912} = \frac{9275}{641830} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{4176}{305892} = \frac{5428}{397601} = \frac{5908}{432761} = \frac{6924}{507183} = \frac{7248}{530916} = \frac{9152}{670384} = \frac{9180}{672435} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{7083}{269154} = \frac{7641}{290358} = \frac{7653}{290814} = \frac{7803}{296514} = \frac{8952}{340176} = \frac{9102}{345876} = \frac{9165}{348270} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{193}{2478506} = \frac{359}{4610278} = \frac{386}{4957012} = \frac{612}{7859304} = \frac{627}{8051934} = \frac{746}{9580132} = \frac{765}{9824130} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1345798} = \frac{407}{2658931} = \frac{689}{4501237} = \frac{713}{4658029} = \frac{751}{4906283} = \frac{812}{5304796} = \frac{871}{5690243} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1346587} = \frac{302}{1945786} = \frac{304}{1958672} = \frac{409}{2635187} = \frac{489}{3150627} = \frac{604}{3891572} = \frac{978}{6301254} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1947680} = \frac{358}{2967104} = \frac{506}{4193728} = \frac{689}{5710432} = \frac{716}{5934208} = \frac{849}{7036512} = \frac{945}{7832160} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{248}{3075169} = \frac{280}{3471965} = \frac{328}{4067159} = \frac{392}{4860751} = \frac{568}{7043129} = \frac{608}{7539124} = \frac{768}{9523104} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1470689} = \frac{283}{1645079} = \frac{407}{2365891} = \frac{481}{2796053} = \frac{506}{2941378} = \frac{607}{3528491} = \frac{916}{5324708} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1379840} = \frac{287}{1546930} = \frac{471}{2538690} = \frac{489}{2635710} = \frac{716}{3859240} = \frac{768}{4139520} = \frac{857}{4619230} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{263}{1895704} = \frac{395}{2847160} = \frac{487}{3510296} = \frac{526}{3791408} = \frac{587}{4231096} = \frac{731}{5269048} = \frac{839}{6047512} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{274}{1360958} = \frac{307}{1524869} = \frac{362}{1798054} = \frac{543}{2697081} = \frac{573}{2846091} = \frac{724}{3596108} = \frac{876}{4351092} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1076958} = \frac{483}{1520967} = \frac{749}{2358601} = \frac{804}{2531796} = \frac{849}{2673501} = \frac{907}{2856143} = \frac{958}{3016742} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{427}{1056398} = \frac{529}{1308746} = \frac{593}{1467082} = \frac{643}{1590782} = \frac{729}{1803546} = \frac{749}{1853026} = \frac{965}{2387410} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{1937052} = \frac{472}{1953608} = \frac{487}{2015693} = \frac{601}{2487539} = \frac{603}{2495817} = \frac{704}{2913856} = \frac{756}{3129084} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{5791032} = \frac{518}{6409732} = \frac{543}{6719082} = \frac{645}{7981230} = \frac{671}{8302954} = \frac{734}{9082516} = \frac{745}{9218630} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24680753} = \frac{31}{40268597} = \frac{37}{48062519} = \frac{47}{61052389} = \frac{62}{80537194} = \frac{73}{94826051} = \frac{74}{96125038} \end{aligned}$$

2.21 6 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 132 examples, each one with 6 expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{47952} = \frac{10536}{48729} = \frac{10672}{49358} = \frac{12736}{58904} = \frac{16952}{78403} = \frac{21056}{97384} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{10736}{25498} = \frac{17256}{40983} = \frac{17896}{42503} = \frac{19720}{46835} = \frac{21368}{50749} = \frac{29536}{70148} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12047}{65398} = \frac{12495}{67830} = \frac{12845}{69730} = \frac{13685}{74290} = \frac{13902}{75468} = \frac{14098}{76532} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12056}{34798} = \frac{12804}{36957} = \frac{12980}{37465} = \frac{25608}{73914} = \frac{25916}{74803} = \frac{32780}{94615} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{36540} = \frac{12859}{36740} = \frac{18697}{53420} = \frac{25963}{74180} = \frac{34251}{97860} = \frac{34517}{98620} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{13048}{26795} = \frac{13608}{27945} = \frac{18256}{37490} = \frac{36512}{74980} = \frac{40376}{82915} = \frac{47152}{96830} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{13409}{28567} = \frac{18952}{40376} = \frac{28359}{60417} = \frac{29578}{63014} = \frac{43056}{91728} = \frac{43516}{92708} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{13760}{29584} = \frac{13840}{29756} = \frac{16720}{35948} = \frac{21380}{45967} = \frac{21580}{46397} = \frac{27160}{58394} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14679}{20853} = \frac{28659}{40713} = \frac{29358}{41706} = \frac{50328}{71496} = \frac{67104}{95328} = \frac{68502}{97314} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14796}{32058} = \frac{19872}{43056} = \frac{20196}{43758} = \frac{28134}{60957} = \frac{37152}{80496} = \frac{40392}{87516} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14798}{20536} = \frac{36897}{51204} = \frac{54831}{76092} = \frac{59143}{82076} = \frac{61397}{85204} = \frac{65807}{91324} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{14806}{27593} = \frac{19470}{36285} = \frac{26730}{49815} = \frac{31064}{57892} = \frac{31768}{59204} = \frac{32758}{61049} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{15368}{49720} = \frac{16932}{54780} = \frac{18462}{59730} = \frac{24769}{80135} = \frac{27863}{90145} = \frac{28356}{91740} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{15760}{23984} = \frac{20685}{31479} = \frac{25610}{38974} = \frac{31520}{47968} = \frac{41370}{62958} = \frac{57130}{86942} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{15768}{39420} = \frac{17568}{43920} = \frac{23184}{57960} = \frac{24318}{60795} = \frac{31824}{79560} = \frac{31842}{79605} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{15960}{24738} = \frac{25140}{38967} = \frac{39540}{61287} = \frac{39840}{61752} = \frac{42180}{65379} = \frac{45960}{71238} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{16794}{50382} = \frac{17694}{53082} = \frac{20583}{61749} = \frac{23058}{69174} = \frac{30582}{91746} = \frac{32058}{96174} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{16975}{38024} = \frac{17625}{39480} = \frac{18275}{40936} = \frac{39025}{87416} = \frac{39125}{87640} = \frac{41375}{92680} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{17658}{29430} = \frac{18279}{30465} = \frac{20817}{34695} = \frac{27918}{46530} = \frac{34182}{56970} = \frac{41823}{69705} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{17690}{23485} = \frac{45298}{60137} = \frac{59102}{78463} = \frac{68730}{91245} = \frac{71804}{95326} = \frac{71862}{95403} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{18042}{39576} = \frac{18569}{40732} = \frac{30814}{67592} = \frac{36084}{79152} = \frac{36549}{80172} = \frac{45012}{98736} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{19468}{37052} = \frac{20584}{39176} = \frac{27869}{53041} = \frac{30721}{58469} = \frac{39618}{75402} = \frac{47368}{90152} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{51678} = \frac{23069}{58174} = \frac{24173}{60958} = \frac{27485}{69310} = \frac{31947}{80562} = \frac{34615}{87290} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{21679}{34580} = \frac{37164}{59280} = \frac{38957}{62140} = \frac{41239}{65780} = \frac{46129}{73580} = \frac{54931}{87620} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{21746}{39508} = \frac{30261}{54978} = \frac{31964}{58072} = \frac{41396}{75208} = \frac{42051}{76398} = \frac{45719}{83062} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{25947}{31806} = \frac{35061}{42978} = \frac{38502}{47196} = \frac{65379}{80142} = \frac{67053}{82194} = \frac{73842}{90516} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{27508}{31694} = \frac{29670}{34185} = \frac{46782}{53901} = \frac{53728}{61904} = \frac{78246}{90153} = \frac{84502}{97361} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{28569}{34710} = \frac{39162}{47580} = \frac{42693}{51870} = \frac{57138}{69420} = \frac{64521}{78390} = \frac{78324}{95160} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{40851} = \frac{29760}{41385} = \frac{38976}{54201} = \frac{48320}{67195} = \frac{64832}{90157} = \frac{65728}{91403} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{29516}{34780} = \frac{35796}{42180} = \frac{39721}{46805} = \frac{52438}{61790} = \frac{71592}{84360} = \frac{72063}{84915} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{31692}{50874} = \frac{43928}{70516} = \frac{50692}{81374} = \frac{54302}{87169} = \frac{56278}{90341} = \frac{58026}{93147} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{32015}{49876} = \frac{45980}{71632} = \frac{49305}{76812} = \frac{56430}{87912} = \frac{62510}{97384} = \frac{63175}{98420} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{36102}{47589} = \frac{38742}{51069} = \frac{39204}{51678} = \frac{45738}{60291} = \frac{60258}{79431} = \frac{60324}{79518} \\ &\triangleright \frac{48739}{60512} = \frac{59126}{73408} = \frac{64719}{80352} = \frac{67915}{84320} = \frac{73508}{91264} = \frac{75106}{93248} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1047}{385296} = \frac{1372}{504896} = \frac{1728}{635904} = \frac{2063}{759184} = \frac{2145}{789360} = \frac{2156}{793408} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1068}{479532} = \frac{1358}{609742} = \frac{1502}{674398} = \frac{1543}{692807} = \frac{1907}{856243} = \frac{2084}{935716} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1259}{304678} = \frac{1738}{420596} = \frac{1935}{468270} = \frac{3149}{762058} = \frac{3701}{895642} = \frac{4018}{972356} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1392}{407856} = \frac{1842}{539706} = \frac{2037}{596841} = \frac{2937}{860541} = \frac{3156}{924708} = \frac{3246}{951078} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1406}{327598} = \frac{1584}{369072} = \frac{2751}{640983} = \frac{3627}{845091} = \frac{3649}{850217} = \frac{4016}{935728} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1506}{237948} = \frac{1857}{293406} = \frac{2985}{471630} = \frac{3012}{475896} = \frac{3702}{584916} = \frac{5634}{890172} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1526}{307489} = \frac{3052}{614978} = \frac{3190}{642785} = \frac{3526}{710489} = \frac{4106}{827359} = \frac{4618}{930527} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1584}{239760} = \frac{2079}{314685} = \frac{2574}{389610} = \frac{3168}{479520} = \frac{4158}{629370} = \frac{5742}{869130} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1728}{349056} = \frac{1827}{369054} = \frac{1845}{372690} = \frac{2718}{549036} = \frac{2817}{569034} = \frac{4815}{972630} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1740}{263958} = \frac{3210}{486957} = \frac{3480}{527916} = \frac{4170}{632589} = \frac{5370}{814629} = \frac{5730}{869241} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1742}{386590} = \frac{1976}{438520} = \frac{2678}{594310} = \frac{3627}{804915} = \frac{4173}{926085} = \frac{4316}{957820} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1745}{230689} = \frac{2845}{376109} = \frac{4290}{567138} = \frac{4310}{569782} = \frac{7130}{942586} = \frac{7415}{980263} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1748}{302956} = \frac{1786}{309542} = \frac{2831}{490657} = \frac{2964}{513708} = \frac{3572}{619084} = \frac{5643}{978021} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1764}{208593} = \frac{3812}{450769} = \frac{5304}{627198} = \frac{6308}{745921} = \frac{6792}{803154} = \frac{7624}{901538} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1809}{372654} = \frac{2315}{476890} = \frac{2365}{487190} = \frac{3945}{812670} = \frac{4503}{927618} = \frac{4613}{950278} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1824}{305976} = \frac{3408}{571692} = \frac{4236}{710589} = \frac{5376}{901824} = \frac{5412}{907863} = \frac{5804}{973621} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1845}{269370} = \frac{2541}{370986} = \frac{3285}{479610} = \frac{4173}{609258} = \frac{5091}{743286} = \frac{5619}{820374} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{1859}{203476} = \frac{2794}{305816} = \frac{2904}{317856} = \frac{3718}{406952} = \frac{3729}{408156} = \frac{8701}{952364} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1864}{253970} = \frac{5816}{792430} = \frac{5832}{794610} = \frac{5976}{814230} = \frac{6172}{840935} = \frac{6740}{918325} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1935}{247680} = \frac{3192}{408576} = \frac{3765}{481920} = \frac{3972}{508416} = \frac{5304}{678912} = \frac{7518}{962304} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1965}{270384} = \frac{2985}{410736} = \frac{3510}{482976} = \frac{5230}{719648} = \frac{6045}{831792} = \frac{6870}{945312} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1972}{345680} = \frac{2159}{378460} = \frac{3247}{569180} = \frac{4318}{756920} = \frac{5236}{917840} = \frac{5372}{941680} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2076}{359148} = \frac{2109}{364857} = \frac{2619}{453087} = \frac{3126}{540798} = \frac{5013}{867249} = \frac{5238}{906174} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2079}{146853} = \frac{4059}{286713} = \frac{4158}{293706} = \frac{7128}{503496} = \frac{9504}{671328} = \frac{9702}{685314} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2097}{184536} = \frac{5319}{468072} = \frac{6489}{571032} = \frac{6714}{590832} = \frac{6741}{593208} = \frac{7398}{651024} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2384}{159760} = \frac{3874}{259610} = \frac{4768}{319520} = \frac{6258}{419370} = \frac{7301}{489265} = \frac{8642}{579130} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2385}{160749} = \frac{3810}{256794} = \frac{4065}{273981} = \frac{4865}{327901} = \frac{7810}{526394} = \frac{8130}{547962} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2416}{308795} = \frac{2480}{316975} = \frac{2896}{370145} = \frac{4832}{617590} = \frac{5312}{678940} = \frac{5632}{719840} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2476}{159083} = \frac{2548}{163709} = \frac{5096}{327418} = \frac{5924}{380617} = \frac{7516}{482903} = \frac{7912}{508346} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2485}{301679} = \frac{3805}{461927} = \frac{6210}{753894} = \frac{6435}{781209} = \frac{7610}{923854} = \frac{7645}{928103} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2508}{173964} = \frac{2673}{185409} = \frac{4697}{325801} = \frac{5016}{347928} = \frac{5027}{348691} = \frac{5819}{403627} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2530}{197846} = \frac{3185}{249067} = \frac{4190}{327658} = \frac{5290}{413678} = \frac{9410}{735862} = \frac{9510}{743682} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2570}{196348} = \frac{3495}{267018} = \frac{3560}{271984} = \frac{4780}{365192} = \frac{7120}{543968} = \frac{9245}{706318} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2730}{154986} = \frac{2835}{160947} = \frac{3045}{172869} = \frac{3780}{214596} = \frac{4935}{280167} = \frac{5670}{321894} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2793}{156408} = \frac{5679}{318024} = \frac{5841}{327096} = \frac{6915}{387240} = \frac{8307}{465192} = \frac{9243}{517608} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2890}{137564} = \frac{3795}{180642} = \frac{4975}{236810} = \frac{7590}{361284} = \frac{8675}{412930} = \frac{9185}{437206} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{2940}{163758} = \frac{4630}{257891} = \frac{5780}{321946} = \frac{6210}{345897} = \frac{7120}{396584} = \frac{8290}{461753} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2981}{350674} = \frac{3509}{412786} = \frac{5137}{604298} = \frac{5962}{701348} = \frac{7106}{835924} = \frac{7304}{859216} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2985}{364170} = \frac{5097}{621834} = \frac{5172}{630984} = \frac{7341}{895602} = \frac{7431}{906582} = \frac{7812}{953064} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3018}{295764} = \frac{6013}{589274} = \frac{6014}{589372} = \frac{6038}{591724} = \frac{7123}{698054} = \frac{8123}{796054} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3165}{427908} = \frac{4230}{571896} = \frac{4380}{592176} = \frac{5340}{721968} = \frac{5460}{738192} = \frac{7140}{965328} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3195}{278604} = \frac{4265}{371908} = \frac{7490}{653128} = \frac{8305}{724196} = \frac{8405}{732916} = \frac{9635}{840172} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3270}{514698} = \frac{3290}{517846} = \frac{3760}{591824} = \frac{4180}{657932} = \frac{4835}{761029} = \frac{5830}{917642} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3276}{185094} = \frac{4806}{271539} = \frac{5472}{309168} = \frac{8190}{462735} = \frac{9612}{543078} = \frac{9702}{548163} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3276}{490581} = \frac{3612}{540897} = \frac{5084}{761329} = \frac{5108}{764923} = \frac{5236}{784091} = \frac{5612}{840397} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3458}{216790} = \frac{5928}{371640} = \frac{6214}{389570} = \frac{6578}{412390} = \frac{7358}{461290} = \frac{8762}{549310} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3471}{285690} = \frac{4758}{391620} = \frac{5187}{426930} = \frac{6942}{571380} = \frac{7839}{645210} = \frac{9516}{783240} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3476}{285901} = \frac{4596}{378021} = \frac{7428}{610953} = \frac{7820}{643195} = \frac{9340}{768215} = \frac{9756}{802431} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3504}{127896} = \frac{4398}{160527} = \frac{4830}{176295} = \frac{5694}{207831} = \frac{8130}{296745} = \frac{8796}{321054} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3507}{164829} = \frac{5067}{238149} = \frac{6051}{284397} = \frac{7014}{329658} = \frac{8736}{410592} = \frac{9831}{462057} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3568}{209174} = \frac{5168}{302974} = \frac{5296}{310478} = \frac{6504}{381297} = \frac{9072}{531846} = \frac{9832}{576401} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3576}{210984} = \frac{4539}{267801} = \frac{6702}{395418} = \frac{7839}{462501} = \frac{7851}{463209} = \frac{8934}{527106} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3760}{219584} = \frac{4915}{287036} = \frac{6805}{397412} = \frac{7520}{439168} = \frac{9210}{537864} = \frac{9270}{541368} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3870}{129645} = \frac{5682}{190347} = \frac{5802}{194367} = \frac{7854}{263109} = \frac{7890}{264315} = \frac{8190}{274365} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3928}{106547} = \frac{4568}{123907} = \frac{5048}{136927} = \frac{7240}{196385} = \frac{7856}{213094} = \frac{9368}{254107} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{4576}{391820} = \frac{8216}{703495} = \frac{8296}{710345} = \frac{9152}{783640} = \frac{9160}{784325} = \frac{9432}{807615} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4965}{138027} = \frac{5320}{147896} = \frac{5370}{149286} = \frac{5890}{163742} = \frac{7495}{208361} = \frac{9510}{264378} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5064}{182937} = \frac{5376}{194208} = \frac{8512}{307496} = \frac{8904}{321657} = \frac{9056}{327148} = \frac{9712}{350846} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5769}{103842} = \frac{5796}{104328} = \frac{5832}{104976} = \frac{7956}{143208} = \frac{8307}{149526} = \frac{9603}{172854} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{6039}{487512} = \frac{7326}{591408} = \frac{8019}{647352} = \frac{8415}{679320} = \frac{9108}{735264} = \frac{9306}{751248} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{6435}{120978} = \frac{6805}{127934} = \frac{8340}{156792} = \frac{8470}{159236} = \frac{9245}{173806} = \frac{9745}{183206} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{6895}{142037} = \frac{6930}{142758} = \frac{6970}{143582} = \frac{7890}{162534} = \frac{7905}{162843} = \frac{9045}{186327} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7356}{102984} = \frac{7824}{109536} = \frac{8934}{125076} = \frac{9648}{135072} = \frac{9672}{135408} = \frac{9804}{137256} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7980}{145236} = \frac{8460}{153972} = \frac{8760}{159432} = \frac{8970}{163254} = \frac{9480}{172536} = \frac{9540}{173628} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{8294}{103675} = \frac{8634}{107925} = \frac{8746}{109325} = \frac{9638}{120475} = \frac{9846}{123075} = \frac{9876}{123450} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2754986} = \frac{135}{2860947} = \frac{145}{3072869} = \frac{235}{4980167} = \frac{290}{6145738} = \frac{435}{9218607} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{2486709} = \frac{281}{4567093} = \frac{423}{6875019} = \frac{534}{8679102} = \frac{568}{9231704} = \frac{571}{9280463} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2639580} = \frac{321}{4869570} = \frac{348}{5279160} = \frac{417}{6325890} = \frac{537}{8146290} = \frac{573}{8692410} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{3024756} = \frac{219}{3504876} = \frac{378}{6049512} = \frac{381}{6097524} = \frac{543}{8690172} = \frac{576}{9218304} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1709584} = \frac{249}{1803756} = \frac{498}{3607512} = \frac{719}{5208436} = \frac{871}{6309524} = \frac{932}{6751408} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{278}{1530946} = \frac{374}{2059618} = \frac{561}{3089427} = \frac{702}{3865914} = \frac{718}{3954026} = \frac{981}{5402367} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{279}{1064385} = \frac{283}{1079645} = \frac{386}{1472590} = \frac{703}{2681945} = \frac{763}{2910845} = \frac{947}{3612805} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1357496} = \frac{435}{2108967} = \frac{490}{2375618} = \frac{645}{3127089} = \frac{905}{4387621} = \frac{980}{4751236} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1397640} = \frac{326}{1598704} = \frac{348}{1706592} = \frac{652}{3197408} = \frac{671}{3290584} = \frac{751}{3682904} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1637580} = \frac{463}{2578910} = \frac{578}{3219460} = \frac{621}{3458970} = \frac{712}{3965840} = \frac{829}{4617530} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{1572896} = \frac{342}{1769508} = \frac{349}{1805726} = \frac{608}{3145792} = \frac{819}{4237506} = \frac{873}{4516902} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1762845} = \frac{378}{2156490} = \frac{516}{2943780} = \frac{756}{4312980} = \frac{792}{4518360} = \frac{984}{5613720} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{1079568} = \frac{327}{1089564} = \frac{504}{1679328} = \frac{507}{1689324} = \frac{543}{1809276} = \frac{738}{2459016} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{1968540} = \frac{328}{1974560} = \frac{459}{2763180} = \frac{581}{3497620} = \frac{867}{5219340} = \frac{967}{5821340} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{1279508} = \frac{504}{1863792} = \frac{563}{2081974} = \frac{651}{2407398} = \frac{864}{3195072} = \frac{974}{3601852} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{1589260} = \frac{382}{1749560} = \frac{432}{1978560} = \frac{641}{2935780} = \frac{694}{3178520} = \frac{864}{3957120} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{1682950} = \frac{487}{2361950} = \frac{489}{2371650} = \frac{721}{3496850} = \frac{817}{3962450} = \frac{879}{4263150} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{361}{2085497} = \frac{374}{2160598} = \frac{491}{2836507} = \frac{508}{2934716} = \frac{561}{3240897} = \frac{982}{5673014} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{365}{2749180} = \frac{504}{3796128} = \frac{579}{4361028} = \frac{581}{4376092} = \frac{851}{6409732} = \frac{907}{6831524} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{365}{4917280} = \frac{378}{5092416} = \frac{539}{7261408} = \frac{672}{9053184} = \frac{715}{9632480} = \frac{732}{9861504} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{381}{2657094} = \frac{617}{4302958} = \frac{732}{5104968} = \frac{895}{6241730} = \frac{901}{6283574} = \frac{907}{6325418} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{384}{1507296} = \frac{432}{1695708} = \frac{504}{1978326} = \frac{768}{3014592} = \frac{896}{3517024} = \frac{908}{3564127} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{398}{2754160} = \frac{413}{2857960} = \frac{459}{3176280} = \frac{548}{3792160} = \frac{769}{5321480} = \frac{786}{5439120} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{1376592} = \frac{468}{1579032} = \frac{502}{1693748} = \frac{583}{1967042} = \frac{781}{2635094} = \frac{951}{3208674} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{3569720} = \frac{419}{3578260} = \frac{578}{4936120} = \frac{854}{7293160} = \frac{861}{7352940} = \frac{921}{7865340} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{1357902} = \frac{472}{1369508} = \frac{508}{1473962} = \frac{630}{1827945} = \frac{936}{2715804} = \frac{954}{2768031} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{476}{1893052} = \frac{617}{2453809} = \frac{631}{2509487} = \frac{649}{2581073} = \frac{689}{2740153} = \frac{952}{3786104} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{479}{3521608} = \frac{509}{3742168} = \frac{871}{6403592} = \frac{927}{6815304} = \frac{935}{6874120} = \frac{958}{7043216} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{3581760} = \frac{547}{3982160} = \frac{576}{4193280} = \frac{651}{4739280} = \frac{983}{7156240} = \frac{984}{7163520} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{568}{2713904} = \frac{615}{2938470} = \frac{659}{3148702} = \frac{827}{3951406} = \frac{865}{4132970} = \frac{895}{4276310} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{798}{1452360} = \frac{846}{1539720} = \frac{876}{1594320} = \frac{897}{1632540} = \frac{948}{1725360} = \frac{954}{1736280} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13069485} = \frac{32}{15489760} = \frac{36}{17425980} = \frac{54}{26138970} = \frac{68}{32915740} = \frac{72}{34851960} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14806935} = \frac{32}{17548960} = \frac{36}{19742580} = \frac{54}{29613870} = \frac{68}{37291540} = \frac{72}{39485160} \end{aligned}$$

2.22 5 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 295 examples, each one with 5 expressions.

$\blacktriangleright \frac{10296}{43758} = \frac{12684}{53907} = \frac{13428}{57069} = \frac{14076}{59823} = \frac{16548}{70329}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{27048} = \frac{17860}{34592} = \frac{35720}{69184} = \frac{41230}{79856} = \frac{46835}{90712}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10675}{34892} = \frac{12075}{39468} = \frac{19075}{62348} = \frac{21350}{69784} = \frac{24150}{78936}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13978}{25064} = \frac{14935}{26780} = \frac{31842}{57096} = \frac{38715}{69420} = \frac{45907}{82316}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10726}{35984} = \frac{13702}{45968} = \frac{13795}{46280} = \frac{19437}{65208} = \frac{25079}{84136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13984}{27056} = \frac{16790}{32485} = \frac{28106}{54379} = \frac{45126}{87309} = \frac{46782}{90513}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12360}{47895} = \frac{14976}{58032} = \frac{19056}{73842} = \frac{19320}{74865} = \frac{23160}{89745}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{25704} = \frac{21645}{39780} = \frac{25197}{46308} = \frac{43068}{79152} = \frac{52836}{97104}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12397}{58604} = \frac{13794}{65208} = \frac{13904}{65728} = \frac{20174}{95368} = \frac{20548}{97136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{25398} = \frac{27186}{49053} = \frac{38502}{69471} = \frac{50784}{91632} = \frac{54372}{98106}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12596}{34780} = \frac{15678}{43290} = \frac{18023}{49765} = \frac{19832}{54760} = \frac{23718}{65490}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14359}{27680} = \frac{15438}{29760} = \frac{17928}{34560} = \frac{25813}{49760} = \frac{35192}{67840}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13694}{20875} = \frac{24190}{36875} = \frac{40918}{62375} = \frac{41902}{63875} = \frac{64370}{98125}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14365}{29087} = \frac{18590}{37642} = \frac{35490}{71862} = \frac{43095}{87261} = \frac{47320}{95816}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13795}{20648} = \frac{17360}{25984} = \frac{34720}{51968} = \frac{52390}{78416} = \frac{56730}{84912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{26973} = \frac{26580}{49173} = \frac{28740}{53169} = \frac{31620}{58497} = \frac{41580}{76923}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13825}{67940} = \frac{14035}{68972} = \frac{14385}{70692} = \frac{15960}{78432} = \frac{16975}{83420}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14670}{32985} = \frac{17604}{39582} = \frac{20538}{46179} = \frac{35208}{79164} = \frac{41076}{92358}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13862}{54970} = \frac{15834}{62790} = \frac{17458}{69230} = \frac{20967}{83145} = \frac{21634}{85790}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14685}{30972} = \frac{16940}{35728} = \frac{21780}{45936} = \frac{39105}{82476} = \frac{43560}{91872}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13902}{45678} = \frac{18543}{60927} = \frac{19047}{62583} = \frac{19572}{64308} = \frac{27804}{91356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14965}{23780} = \frac{32704}{51968} = \frac{46501}{73892} = \frac{51903}{82476} = \frac{56137}{89204}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15028}{47396} = \frac{24063}{75891} = \frac{25467}{80319} = \frac{26793}{84501} = \frac{28743}{90651}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15067}{34892} = \frac{19703}{45628} = \frac{21793}{50468} = \frac{25973}{60148} = \frac{42351}{98076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15084}{26397} = \frac{29376}{51408} = \frac{30168}{52794} = \frac{41508}{72639} = \frac{45792}{80136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15308}{27946} = \frac{21586}{39407} = \frac{31906}{58247} = \frac{37410}{68295} = \frac{53148}{97026}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15840}{23976} = \frac{25740}{38961} = \frac{31680}{47952} = \frac{41580}{62937} = \frac{57420}{86913}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15974}{28036} = \frac{28714}{50396} = \frac{30184}{52976} = \frac{31948}{56072} = \frac{46795}{82130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15976}{23840} = \frac{25961}{38740} = \frac{31952}{47680} = \frac{41937}{62580} = \frac{57913}{86420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{25974} = \frac{24570}{38961} = \frac{32760}{51948} = \frac{45360}{71928} = \frac{48510}{76923}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16470}{29835} = \frac{19764}{35802} = \frac{23058}{41769} = \frac{39528}{71604} = \frac{53802}{97461}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16470}{39528} = \frac{19530}{46872} = \frac{29835}{71604} = \frac{30195}{72468} = \frac{31095}{74628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16480}{53972} = \frac{18240}{59736} = \frac{19720}{64583} = \frac{23160}{75849} = \frac{25640}{83971}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{32490} = \frac{16954}{32870} = \frac{23618}{45790} = \frac{23716}{45980} = \frac{47236}{91580}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16958}{23074} = \frac{17568}{23904} = \frac{38064}{51792} = \frac{42639}{58017} = \frac{60573}{82419}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17458}{26390} = \frac{24596}{37180} = \frac{34916}{52780} = \frac{41538}{62790} = \frac{62307}{94185}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17649}{28305} = \frac{26871}{43095} = \frac{27189}{43605} = \frac{30687}{49215} = \frac{53742}{86190}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17940}{28635} = \frac{31824}{50796} = \frac{53924}{86071} = \frac{56472}{90138} = \frac{57408}{91632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17964}{35820} = \frac{21956}{43780} = \frac{35928}{71640} = \frac{39421}{78605} = \frac{43912}{87560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18096}{52374} = \frac{18304}{52976} = \frac{20176}{58394} = \frac{30264}{87591} = \frac{32760}{94815}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19208}{35476} = \frac{30478}{56291} = \frac{32046}{59187} = \frac{38416}{70952} = \frac{41062}{75839}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19275}{40863} = \frac{28950}{61374} = \frac{41025}{86973} = \frac{41325}{87609} = \frac{46275}{98103}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19580}{23674} = \frac{62810}{75943} = \frac{67430}{81529} = \frac{75460}{91238} = \frac{78210}{94563}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{23058} = \frac{35802}{41769} = \frac{52974}{61803} = \frac{54702}{63819} = \frac{70254}{81963}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21735}{49680} = \frac{29358}{67104} = \frac{35217}{80496} = \frac{35469}{81072} = \frac{41706}{95328}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24817}{35690} = \frac{25714}{36980} = \frac{32591}{46870} = \frac{51428}{73960} = \frac{65182}{93740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25086}{34917} = \frac{41736}{58092} = \frac{50172}{69834} = \frac{51948}{72306} = \frac{56832}{79104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26071}{54839} = \frac{28739}{60451} = \frac{30972}{65148} = \frac{35612}{74908} = \frac{43152}{90768}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28576}{39104} = \frac{41097}{56238} = \frac{43168}{59072} = \frac{49058}{67132} = \frac{65873}{90142}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28630}{59714} = \frac{28945}{60371} = \frac{32410}{67598} = \frac{32795}{68401} = \frac{36190}{75482}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28710}{45936} = \frac{29385}{47016} = \frac{41895}{67032} = \frac{45810}{73296} = \frac{61470}{98352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28917}{34506} = \frac{57834}{69012} = \frac{63189}{75402} = \frac{75684}{90312} = \frac{78064}{93152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28946}{31570} = \frac{57892}{63140} = \frac{68129}{74305} = \frac{84367}{92015} = \frac{85426}{93170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36018}{57942} = \frac{38571}{62049} = \frac{40917}{65823} = \frac{54027}{86913} = \frac{61203}{98457}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36972}{51480} = \frac{37841}{52690} = \frac{47321}{65890} = \frac{49217}{68530} = \frac{59724}{83160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38160}{45792} = \frac{38925}{46710} = \frac{61290}{73548} = \frac{74610}{89532} = \frac{76320}{91584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38796}{50142} = \frac{40386}{52197} = \frac{56498}{73021} = \frac{72610}{93845} = \frac{76214}{98503}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43680}{51792} = \frac{63420}{75198} = \frac{63490}{75281} = \frac{71960}{85324} = \frac{78540}{93126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54320}{61789} = \frac{59280}{67431} = \frac{81360}{92547} = \frac{82160}{93457} = \frac{84160}{95732}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1026}{437589} = \frac{1092}{465738} = \frac{1384}{590276} = \frac{1936}{825704} = \frac{2104}{897356}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{1026}{548397} = \frac{1092}{583674} = \frac{1274}{680953} = \frac{1364}{729058} = \frac{1730}{924685} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1047}{265938} = \frac{1524}{387096} = \frac{1803}{457962} = \frac{2094}{531876} = \frac{2901}{736854} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1069}{345287} = \frac{1638}{529074} = \frac{2138}{690574} = \frac{2158}{697034} = \frac{2497}{806531} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1078}{463295} = \frac{1276}{548390} = \frac{1694}{728035} = \frac{2046}{879315} = \frac{2178}{936045} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1092}{367458} = \frac{2430}{817695} = \frac{2654}{893071} = \frac{2730}{918645} = \frac{2854}{960371} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1096}{437852} = \frac{1274}{508963} = \frac{1954}{780623} = \frac{2194}{876503} = \frac{2370}{946815} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1209}{357864} = \frac{1673}{495208} = \frac{2079}{615384} = \frac{2941}{870536} = \frac{3185}{942760} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1236}{849750} = \frac{1348}{926750} = \frac{1402}{963875} = \frac{1426}{980375} = \frac{1436}{987250} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1290}{387645} = \frac{1678}{504239} = \frac{1784}{536092} = \frac{3164}{950782} = \frac{3214}{965807} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1296}{345708} = \frac{1536}{409728} = \frac{1576}{420398} = \frac{3072}{819456} = \frac{3152}{840796} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1304}{579628} = \frac{1326}{589407} = \frac{1372}{609854} = \frac{1532}{680974} = \frac{2130}{946785} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1305}{247689} = \frac{1870}{354926} = \frac{2510}{476398} = \frac{2610}{495378} = \frac{3540}{671892} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1329}{584760} = \frac{1347}{592680} = \frac{1543}{678920} = \frac{1578}{694320} = \frac{2167}{953480} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1340}{279658} = \frac{1580}{329746} = \frac{1670}{348529} = \frac{1720}{358964} = \frac{2940}{613578} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1369}{204758} = \frac{2738}{409516} = \frac{3478}{520196} = \frac{5476}{819032} = \frac{6401}{957382} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1370}{264958} = \frac{1540}{297836} = \frac{1860}{359724} = \frac{1905}{368427} = \frac{3205}{619847} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1379}{482650} = \frac{1827}{639450} = \frac{1837}{642950} = \frac{2139}{748650} = \frac{2671}{934850} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1380}{274965} = \frac{1752}{349086} = \frac{3504}{698172} = \frac{3568}{710924} = \frac{4392}{875106} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1392}{405768} = \frac{2690}{784135} = \frac{2694}{785301} = \frac{2796}{815034} = \frac{3176}{925804} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{1436}{208579} = \frac{4172}{605983} = \frac{4892}{710563} = \frac{5412}{786093} = \frac{5716}{830249} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1452}{736890} = \frac{1456}{738920} = \frac{1498}{760235} = \frac{1764}{895230} = \frac{1782}{904365} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1460}{579328} = \frac{1470}{583296} = \frac{1845}{732096} = \frac{1925}{763840} = \frac{1930}{765824} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1470}{253869} = \frac{2140}{369578} = \frac{3820}{659714} = \frac{4280}{739156} = \frac{5320}{918764} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1495}{326807} = \frac{2630}{574918} = \frac{2890}{631754} = \frac{3910}{854726} = \frac{4285}{936701} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1496}{230758} = \frac{1576}{243098} = \frac{1708}{263459} = \frac{1740}{268395} = \frac{4592}{708316} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1496}{235807} = \frac{1704}{268593} = \frac{1952}{307684} = \frac{2408}{379561} = \frac{5064}{798213} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1504}{279368} = \frac{3712}{689504} = \frac{3904}{725168} = \frac{4356}{809127} = \frac{5312}{986704} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1539}{204687} = \frac{1908}{253764} = \frac{3519}{468027} = \frac{4581}{609273} = \frac{6543}{870219} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1539}{264708} = \frac{2853}{490716} = \frac{3078}{529416} = \frac{4536}{780192} = \frac{5706}{981432} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1548}{379260} = \frac{1782}{436590} = \frac{2364}{579180} = \frac{2487}{609315} = \frac{2493}{610785} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1576}{239840} = \frac{2561}{389740} = \frac{3152}{479680} = \frac{4137}{629580} = \frac{5713}{869420} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1584}{329670} = \frac{1728}{359640} = \frac{3456}{719280} = \frac{3816}{794205} = \frac{3960}{824175} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1590}{324678} = \frac{3045}{621789} = \frac{3490}{712658} = \frac{4265}{870913} = \frac{4715}{962803} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1635}{490827} = \frac{1920}{576384} = \frac{2190}{657438} = \frac{2730}{819546} = \frac{3270}{981654} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1638}{259740} = \frac{2457}{389610} = \frac{3276}{519480} = \frac{4536}{719280} = \frac{4851}{769230} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1638}{290745} = \frac{2094}{371685} = \frac{3276}{581490} = \frac{4152}{736980} = \frac{4236}{751890} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1640}{398725} = \frac{1792}{435680} = \frac{2384}{579610} = \frac{2416}{587390} = \frac{3128}{760495} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1645}{378209} = \frac{2135}{490867} = \frac{2380}{547196} = \frac{3290}{756418} = \frac{3745}{861029} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{1645}{720839} = \frac{1930}{845726} = \frac{1970}{863254} = \frac{2085}{913647} = \frac{2165}{948703} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1648}{539720} = \frac{1824}{597360} = \frac{1972}{645830} = \frac{2316}{758490} = \frac{2564}{839710} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1670}{325984} = \frac{3915}{764208} = \frac{3920}{765184} = \frac{4715}{920368} = \frac{4765}{930128} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1692}{358704} = \frac{2397}{508164} = \frac{2439}{517068} = \frac{2895}{613740} = \frac{3519}{746028} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1698}{520437} = \frac{2316}{709854} = \frac{2490}{763185} = \frac{3072}{941568} = \frac{3216}{985704} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1706}{589423} = \frac{1732}{598406} = \frac{1904}{657832} = \frac{2014}{695837} = \frac{2708}{935614} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1708}{325496} = \frac{1946}{370852} = \frac{2513}{478906} = \frac{4865}{927130} = \frac{5103}{972486} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1760}{395824} = \frac{2630}{591487} = \frac{3420}{769158} = \frac{3520}{791648} = \frac{4320}{971568} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1795}{234068} = \frac{3805}{496172} = \frac{5210}{679384} = \frac{7215}{940836} = \frac{7540}{983216} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1856}{407392} = \frac{2638}{579041} = \frac{2910}{638745} = \frac{3504}{769128} = \frac{4136}{907852} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1863}{429705} = \frac{1978}{456230} = \frac{2783}{641905} = \frac{3542}{816970} = \frac{3726}{859410} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1920}{384576} = \frac{2190}{438657} = \frac{2730}{546819} = \frac{3270}{654981} = \frac{3840}{769152} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1930}{284675} = \frac{1946}{287035} = \frac{2564}{378190} = \frac{2610}{384975} = \frac{2786}{410935} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1935}{264708} = \frac{3870}{529416} = \frac{3960}{541728} = \frac{6390}{874152} = \frac{6840}{935712} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1952}{364780} = \frac{2576}{481390} = \frac{3704}{692185} = \frac{3968}{741520} = \frac{5264}{983710} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1956}{320784} = \frac{1986}{325704} = \frac{2109}{345876} = \frac{3972}{651408} = \frac{5361}{879204} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1958}{236740} = \frac{6281}{759430} = \frac{6743}{815290} = \frac{7546}{912380} = \frac{7821}{945630} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1965}{428370} = \frac{3018}{657924} = \frac{3528}{769104} = \frac{3714}{809652} = \frac{4107}{895326} \\ &\triangleright \frac{1985}{237406} = \frac{4910}{587236} = \frac{6915}{827034} = \frac{6975}{834210} = \frac{7630}{912548} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{2034}{176958} = \frac{6192}{538704} = \frac{6201}{539487} = \frac{6723}{584901} = \frac{7254}{631098} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2058}{371469} = \frac{2670}{481935} = \frac{4206}{759183} = \frac{5136}{927048} = \frac{5328}{961704} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2068}{137945} = \frac{2376}{158490} = \frac{2684}{179035} = \frac{4136}{275890} = \frac{4752}{316980} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2076}{189435} = \frac{4172}{380695} = \frac{4276}{390185} = \frac{5128}{467930} = \frac{7012}{639845} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2304}{158976} = \frac{4608}{317952} = \frac{4761}{328509} = \frac{7398}{510462} = \frac{9423}{650187} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2350}{194768} = \frac{2375}{196840} = \frac{4725}{391608} = \frac{8375}{694120} = \frac{9450}{783216} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2376}{159840} = \frac{3861}{259740} = \frac{4752}{319680} = \frac{6237}{419580} = \frac{8613}{579420} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2390}{156784} = \frac{4530}{297168} = \frac{4905}{321768} = \frac{4985}{327016} = \frac{8190}{537264} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2394}{106875} = \frac{3290}{146875} = \frac{3948}{176250} = \frac{8764}{391250} = \frac{9268}{413750} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2406}{318795} = \frac{3612}{478590} = \frac{4812}{637590} = \frac{5124}{678930} = \frac{7284}{965130} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2436}{158079} = \frac{3976}{258014} = \frac{5964}{387021} = \frac{7812}{506943} = \frac{8036}{521479} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2465}{107938} = \frac{3825}{167490} = \frac{4930}{215876} = \frac{6715}{294038} = \frac{9860}{431752} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2490}{356817} = \frac{2580}{369714} = \frac{3270}{468591} = \frac{5160}{739428} = \frac{6540}{937182} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2509}{146873} = \frac{2964}{173508} = \frac{5018}{293746} = \frac{5928}{347016} = \frac{8021}{469537} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2570}{418396} = \frac{2895}{471306} = \frac{2970}{483516} = \frac{3490}{568172} = \frac{5140}{836792} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2584}{179360} = \frac{5678}{394120} = \frac{5712}{396480} = \frac{6137}{425980} = \frac{9418}{653720} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2705}{381946} = \frac{2765}{390418} = \frac{4160}{587392} = \frac{4315}{609278} = \frac{5410}{763892} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2740}{381956} = \frac{5190}{723486} = \frac{5480}{763912} = \frac{6035}{841279} = \frac{6780}{945132} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2758}{163904} = \frac{5194}{308672} = \frac{6258}{371904} = \frac{7056}{419328} = \frac{8365}{497120} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{2784}{136590} = \frac{3792}{186045} = \frac{6480}{317925} = \frac{6704}{328915} = \frac{9312}{456870} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2835}{197640} = \frac{4039}{281576} = \frac{8204}{571936} = \frac{8743}{609512} = \frac{9058}{631472} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2856}{174930} = \frac{5712}{349860} = \frac{7068}{432915} = \frac{7128}{436590} = \frac{7368}{451290} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2890}{163574} = \frac{4805}{271963} = \frac{7215}{408369} = \frac{7530}{426198} = \frac{8315}{470629} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2890}{371654} = \frac{4370}{561982} = \frac{4735}{608921} = \frac{4805}{617923} = \frac{6390}{821754} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{2951}{473068} = \frac{3172}{508496} = \frac{3718}{596024} = \frac{4615}{739820} = \frac{6084}{975312} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3024}{189756} = \frac{3504}{219876} = \frac{6048}{379512} = \frac{7860}{493215} = \frac{9216}{578304} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3059}{247618} = \frac{3078}{249156} = \frac{7429}{601358} = \frac{9082}{735164} = \frac{9652}{781304} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3094}{185276} = \frac{4539}{271806} = \frac{5168}{309472} = \frac{9078}{543612} = \frac{9163}{548702} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3108}{257964} = \frac{5106}{423798} = \frac{7104}{589632} = \frac{8103}{672549} = \frac{8952}{743016} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3108}{264957} = \frac{3504}{298716} = \frac{7380}{629145} = \frac{7512}{640398} = \frac{8940}{762135} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3190}{246587} = \frac{5670}{438291} = \frac{6230}{481579} = \frac{9460}{731258} = \frac{9610}{742853} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3249}{167580} = \frac{3287}{169540} = \frac{4579}{236180} = \frac{4598}{237160} = \frac{9158}{472360} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3456}{187920} = \frac{3816}{207495} = \frac{4968}{270135} = \frac{6840}{371925} = \frac{6912}{375840} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3465}{129780} = \frac{4906}{183752} = \frac{5203}{194876} = \frac{5379}{201468} = \frac{9812}{367504} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3507}{281694} = \frac{3674}{295108} = \frac{4509}{362178} = \frac{7348}{590216} = \frac{9018}{724356} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3508}{462179} = \frac{3712}{489056} = \frac{5328}{701964} = \frac{7016}{924358} = \frac{7156}{942803} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3549}{261807} = \frac{6721}{495803} = \frac{7098}{523614} = \frac{7163}{528409} = \frac{8047}{593621} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3564}{179820} = \frac{4356}{219780} = \frac{7128}{359640} = \frac{7821}{394605} = \frac{8712}{439560} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{3569}{248170} = \frac{3698}{257140} = \frac{4687}{325910} = \frac{7396}{514280} = \frac{9374}{651820} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3570}{419628} = \frac{6930}{814572} = \frac{7035}{826914} = \frac{7140}{839256} = \frac{7840}{921536} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3587}{190264} = \frac{3798}{201456} = \frac{5697}{302184} = \frac{9073}{481256} = \frac{9706}{514832} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3780}{215649} = \frac{5160}{294378} = \frac{7560}{431298} = \frac{7920}{451836} = \frac{9840}{561372} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3840}{192576} = \frac{4380}{219657} = \frac{5460}{273819} = \frac{6540}{327981} = \frac{9120}{457368} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3890}{125647} = \frac{4260}{137598} = \frac{4290}{138567} = \frac{8190}{264537} = \frac{9760}{315248} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3906}{182745} = \frac{4956}{231870} = \frac{7812}{365490} = \frac{8106}{379245} = \frac{9156}{428370} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3927}{140658} = \frac{4389}{157206} = \frac{5874}{210396} = \frac{8954}{320716} = \frac{8976}{321504} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3960}{428175} = \frac{5728}{619340} = \frac{5872}{634910} = \frac{8472}{916035} = \frac{8752}{946310} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4096}{138752} = \frac{4872}{165039} = \frac{5632}{190784} = \frac{5728}{194036} = \frac{9608}{325471} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4207}{358196} = \frac{6083}{517924} = \frac{6804}{579312} = \frac{7504}{638912} = \frac{9765}{831420} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4290}{385671} = \frac{5210}{468379} = \frac{7590}{682341} = \frac{8390}{754261} = \frac{8490}{763251} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4368}{517920} = \frac{6342}{751980} = \frac{6349}{752810} = \frac{7196}{853240} = \frac{7854}{931260} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4706}{325981} = \frac{5642}{390817} = \frac{5746}{398021} = \frac{5798}{401623} = \frac{8970}{621345} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4823}{106795} = \frac{5796}{128340} = \frac{6209}{137485} = \frac{6972}{154380} = \frac{8673}{192045} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4852}{137069} = \frac{4860}{137295} = \frac{6392}{180574} = \frac{7032}{198654} = \frac{9564}{270183} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4905}{163827} = \frac{5760}{192384} = \frac{6570}{219438} = \frac{8190}{273546} = \frac{9810}{327654} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4910}{538627} = \frac{5910}{648327} = \frac{6830}{749251} = \frac{7490}{821653} = \frac{7620}{835914} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5072}{194638} = \frac{5416}{207839} = \frac{7584}{291036} = \frac{7640}{293185} = \frac{8576}{329104} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{5136}{487920} = \frac{5238}{497610} = \frac{7254}{689130} = \frac{8031}{762945} = \frac{9132}{867540}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6294}{173085} = \frac{6492}{178530} = \frac{7614}{209385} = \frac{7836}{215490} = \frac{8706}{239415}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5148}{369720} = \frac{5269}{378410} = \frac{6589}{473210} = \frac{6853}{492170} = \frac{8316}{597240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6370}{125489} = \frac{6490}{127853} = \frac{7560}{148932} = \frac{7580}{149326} = \frac{8490}{167253}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5170}{329846} = \frac{5710}{364298} = \frac{6315}{402897} = \frac{8420}{537196} = \frac{9830}{627154}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6495}{387102} = \frac{7035}{419286} = \frac{8310}{495276} = \frac{8325}{496170} = \frac{8970}{534612}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5267}{340981} = \frac{6509}{421387} = \frac{7521}{486903} = \frac{8901}{576243} = \frac{9384}{607512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6580}{147392} = \frac{7295}{163408} = \frac{8675}{194320} = \frac{9570}{214368} = \frac{9735}{218064}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5368}{127490} = \frac{5864}{139270} = \frac{5872}{139460} = \frac{7092}{168435} = \frac{9860}{234175}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6784}{130592} = \frac{7064}{135982} = \frac{8956}{172403} = \frac{9056}{174328} = \frac{9364}{180257}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5480}{196732} = \frac{6830}{245197} = \frac{6890}{247351} = \frac{9520}{341768} = \frac{9680}{347512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6795}{103284} = \frac{8395}{127604} = \frac{8975}{136420} = \frac{9380}{142576} = \frac{9760}{148352}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{5786}{432109} = \frac{6842}{510973} = \frac{6974}{520831} = \frac{7216}{538904} = \frac{9548}{713062}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{6027}{458913} = \frac{6839}{520741} = \frac{7042}{536198} = \frac{9408}{716352} = \frac{9506}{723814}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{6834}{105927} = \frac{7968}{123504} = \frac{8790}{136245} = \frac{9270}{143685} = \frac{9732}{150846}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{2983570} = \frac{328}{5967140} = \frac{398}{7240615} = \frac{432}{7859160} = \frac{532}{9678410}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{6840}{123975} = \frac{7856}{142390} = \frac{9536}{172840} = \frac{9568}{173420} = \frac{9632}{174580}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{167}{2805934} = \frac{182}{3057964} = \frac{239}{4015678} = \frac{415}{6972830} = \frac{465}{7812930}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{124}{3675980} = \frac{128}{3794560} = \frac{248}{7351960} = \frac{249}{7381605} = \frac{294}{8715630}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{3958240} = \frac{263}{5914870} = \frac{342}{7691580} = \frac{352}{7916480} = \frac{432}{9715680}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{128}{5047936} = \frac{137}{5402869} = \frac{154}{6073298} = \frac{159}{6270483} = \frac{207}{8163459}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{5374096} = \frac{268}{7913504} = \frac{293}{8651704} = \frac{302}{8917456} = \frac{304}{8976512}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2586974} = \frac{260}{5173948} = \frac{380}{7561924} = \frac{395}{7860421} = \frac{420}{8357916}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{2357960} = \frac{187}{2396405} = \frac{368}{4715920} = \frac{438}{5612970} = \frac{647}{8291305}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{134}{2796580} = \frac{158}{3297460} = \frac{167}{3485290} = \frac{172}{3589640} = \frac{294}{6135780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3507648} = \frac{196}{3580724} = \frac{294}{5371086} = \frac{384}{7015296} = \frac{401}{7325869}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{146}{2379508} = \frac{147}{2395806} = \frac{265}{4318970} = \frac{312}{5084976} = \frac{436}{7105928}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3845760} = \frac{219}{4386570} = \frac{273}{5468190} = \frac{327}{6549810} = \frac{384}{7691520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2538690} = \frac{214}{3695780} = \frac{382}{6597140} = \frac{428}{7391560} = \frac{532}{9187640}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1587936} = \frac{381}{2965704} = \frac{749}{5830216} = \frac{762}{5931408} = \frac{952}{7410368}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2659083} = \frac{163}{2948507} = \frac{279}{5046831} = \frac{326}{5897014} = \frac{401}{7253689}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1498753} = \frac{270}{1964385} = \frac{482}{3506791} = \frac{602}{4379851} = \frac{964}{7013582}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{4286907} = \frac{162}{4539078} = \frac{213}{5968047} = \frac{324}{9078156} = \frac{348}{9750612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1543976} = \frac{364}{2701958} = \frac{416}{3087952} = \frac{728}{5403916} = \frac{832}{6175904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{2674380} = \frac{273}{4591860} = \frac{346}{5819720} = \frac{546}{9183720} = \frac{548}{9217360}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1547936} = \frac{416}{3095872} = \frac{481}{3579602} = \frac{609}{4532178} = \frac{704}{5239168}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{2864703} = \frac{267}{4810539} = \frac{318}{5729406} = \frac{514}{9260738} = \frac{534}{9621078}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1378564} = \frac{259}{1708364} = \frac{693}{4571028} = \frac{917}{6048532} = \frac{937}{6180452}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1867945} = \frac{306}{2485179} = \frac{452}{3670918} = \frac{518}{4206937} = \frac{612}{4970358}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1076985} = \frac{468}{2153970} = \frac{516}{2374890} = \frac{678}{3120495} = \frac{792}{3645180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1580746} = \frac{279}{1845306} = \frac{391}{2586074} = \frac{735}{4861290} = \frac{816}{5397024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{1538069} = \frac{617}{3842059} = \frac{691}{4302857} = \frac{841}{5236907} = \frac{943}{5872061}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{3198650} = \frac{291}{3768450} = \frac{297}{3846150} = \frac{637}{8249150} = \frac{743}{9621850}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{249}{3568170} = \frac{258}{3697140} = \frac{327}{4685910} = \frac{516}{7394280} = \frac{654}{9371820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{3478609} = \frac{376}{5210984} = \frac{418}{5793062} = \frac{579}{8024361} = \frac{631}{8745029}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1978460} = \frac{419}{3276580} = \frac{529}{4136780} = \frac{941}{7358620} = \frac{951}{7436820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{1673098} = \frac{381}{2509647} = \frac{562}{3701894} = \frac{869}{5724103} = \frac{983}{6475021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{257}{1896403} = \frac{514}{3792806} = \frac{651}{4803729} = \frac{804}{5932716} = \frac{841}{6205739}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1340697} = \frac{396}{2057814} = \frac{594}{3086721} = \frac{608}{3159472} = \frac{802}{4167593}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{1093587} = \frac{384}{1590672} = \frac{432}{1789506} = \frac{728}{3015649} = \frac{864}{3579012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{265}{1437890} = \frac{493}{2675018} = \frac{509}{2761834} = \frac{571}{3098246} = \frac{937}{5084162}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{265}{1809473} = \frac{285}{1946037} = \frac{380}{2594716} = \frac{760}{5189432} = \frac{915}{6247803}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{268}{1534970} = \frac{792}{4536180} = \frac{810}{4639275} = \frac{826}{4730915} = \frac{862}{4937105}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{268}{3579140} = \frac{367}{4901285} = \frac{394}{5261870} = \frac{546}{7291830} = \frac{642}{8573910}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{268}{4590371} = \frac{412}{7056839} = \frac{420}{7193865} = \frac{528}{9043716} = \frac{536}{9180742}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{269}{1437805} = \frac{489}{2613705} = \frac{546}{2918370} = \frac{672}{3591840} = \frac{798}{4265310}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1839564} = \frac{390}{2657148} = \frac{540}{3679128} = \frac{780}{5314296} = \frac{915}{6234078}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{271}{3904568} = \frac{287}{4135096} = \frac{389}{5604712} = \frac{508}{7319264} = \frac{542}{7809136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1589406} = \frac{293}{1705846} = \frac{469}{2730518} = \frac{527}{3068194} = \frac{823}{4791506}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{1503986} = \frac{726}{3985014} = \frac{839}{4605271} = \frac{924}{5071836} = \frac{942}{5170638}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{1630985} = \frac{438}{2607195} = \frac{548}{3261970} = \frac{876}{5214390} = \frac{964}{5738210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{1539804} = \frac{324}{1807596} = \frac{549}{3062871} = \frac{702}{3916458} = \frac{934}{5210786}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{3459170} = \frac{438}{5297610} = \frac{572}{6918340} = \frac{697}{8430215} = \frac{756}{9143820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1035496} = \frac{482}{1739056} = \frac{509}{1836472} = \frac{965}{3481720} = \frac{976}{3521408}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{295}{4367180} = \frac{329}{4870516} = \frac{531}{7860924} = \frac{613}{9074852} = \frac{658}{9741032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1563408} = \frac{534}{2810976} = \frac{597}{3142608} = \frac{607}{3195248} = \frac{745}{3921680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{1698752} = \frac{345}{1927860} = \frac{549}{3067812} = \frac{706}{3945128} = \frac{897}{5012436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1245879} = \frac{398}{1620457} = \frac{538}{2190467} = \frac{784}{3192056} = \frac{790}{3216485}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1574982} = \frac{694}{3572018} = \frac{758}{3901426} = \frac{807}{4153629} = \frac{923}{4750681}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{308}{1496572} = \frac{356}{1729804} = \frac{489}{2376051} = \frac{712}{3459608} = \frac{968}{4703512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{319}{2465870} = \frac{567}{4382910} = \frac{623}{4815790} = \frac{946}{7312580} = \frac{961}{7428530}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1548976} = \frac{360}{1742598} = \frac{540}{2613897} = \frac{680}{3291574} = \frac{720}{3485196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1754896} = \frac{360}{1974258} = \frac{540}{2961387} = \frac{680}{3729154} = \frac{720}{3948516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{1506489} = \frac{453}{2086971} = \frac{641}{2953087} = \frac{654}{3012978} = \frac{758}{3492106}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{5146980} = \frac{329}{5178460} = \frac{376}{5918240} = \frac{418}{6579320} = \frac{583}{9176420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{1457960} = \frac{426}{1893570} = \frac{489}{2173605} = \frac{631}{2804795} = \frac{769}{3418205}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{4106578} = \frac{512}{6390784} = \frac{593}{7401826} = \frac{604}{7539128} = \frac{715}{8924630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{4096872} = \frac{461}{5380792} = \frac{582}{6793104} = \frac{817}{9536024} = \frac{835}{9746120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2941680} = \frac{459}{3782160} = \frac{783}{6451920} = \frac{918}{7564320} = \frac{951}{7836240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{361}{4580729} = \frac{543}{6890127} = \frac{643}{8159027} = \frac{712}{9034568} = \frac{716}{9085324}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{362}{1097584} = \frac{496}{1503872} = \frac{562}{1703984} = \frac{765}{2319480} = \frac{895}{2713640} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{2751904} = \frac{469}{3507182} = \frac{504}{3768912} = \frac{718}{5369204} = \frac{915}{6842370} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{368}{2917504} = \frac{531}{4209768} = \frac{718}{5692304} = \frac{809}{6413752} = \frac{935}{7412680} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{372}{1569840} = \frac{458}{1932760} = \frac{549}{2316780} = \frac{578}{2439160} = \frac{769}{3245180} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2951608} = \frac{481}{3796052} = \frac{502}{3961784} = \frac{674}{5319208} = \frac{748}{5903216} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1425980} = \frac{456}{1729380} = \frac{564}{2138970} = \frac{798}{3026415} = \frac{912}{3458760} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{376}{5014289} = \frac{384}{5120976} = \frac{432}{5761098} = \frac{536}{7148029} = \frac{736}{9815204} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{384}{1925760} = \frac{438}{2196570} = \frac{546}{2738190} = \frac{654}{3279810} = \frac{912}{4573680} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{384}{5761920} = \frac{438}{6572190} = \frac{546}{8192730} = \frac{627}{9408135} = \frac{654}{9813270} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{386}{2514790} = \frac{431}{2807965} = \frac{479}{3120685} = \frac{619}{4032785} = \frac{958}{6241370} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{389}{1256470} = \frac{426}{1375980} = \frac{429}{1385670} = \frac{819}{2645370} = \frac{976}{3152480} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{389}{1526047} = \frac{406}{1592738} = \frac{589}{2310647} = \frac{761}{2985403} = \frac{894}{3507162} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{392}{1876504} = \frac{508}{2431796} = \frac{796}{3810452} = \frac{867}{4150329} = \frac{983}{4705621} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{397}{1246580} = \frac{498}{1563720} = \frac{549}{1723860} = \frac{749}{2351860} = \frac{761}{2389540} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{423}{5718960} = \frac{438}{5921760} = \frac{534}{7219680} = \frac{546}{7381920} = \frac{714}{9653280} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{429}{3856710} = \frac{521}{4683790} = \frac{759}{6823410} = \frac{839}{7542610} = \frac{849}{7632510} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{436}{5187092} = \frac{632}{7518904} = \frac{659}{7840123} = \frac{702}{8351694} = \frac{786}{9351042} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{1596072} = \frac{468}{1705392} = \frac{538}{1960472} = \frac{657}{2394108} = \frac{816}{2973504} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{1769520} = \frac{537}{2169480} = \frac{574}{2318960} = \frac{591}{2387640} = \frac{796}{3215840} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{438}{1970562} = \frac{587}{2640913} = \frac{647}{2910853} = \frac{679}{3054821} = \frac{796}{3581204} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{458}{3126079} = \frac{572}{3904186} = \frac{730}{4982615} = \frac{746}{5091823} = \frac{914}{6238507} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{468}{1073592} = \frac{478}{1096532} = \frac{607}{1392458} = \frac{608}{1394752} = \frac{945}{2167830} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{482}{3107695} = \frac{596}{3842710} = \frac{612}{3945870} = \frac{670}{4319825} = \frac{718}{4629305} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{486}{1257039} = \frac{490}{1267385} = \frac{794}{2053681} = \frac{830}{2146795} = \frac{896}{2317504} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{491}{5386270} = \frac{591}{6483270} = \frac{683}{7492510} = \frac{749}{8216530} = \frac{762}{8359140} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{492}{1730856} = \frac{593}{2086174} = \frac{598}{2103764} = \frac{857}{3014926} = \frac{869}{3057142} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{529}{4308176} = \frac{673}{5480912} = \frac{732}{5961408} = \frac{891}{7256304} = \frac{931}{7582064} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{531}{2890764} = \frac{685}{3729140} = \frac{715}{3892460} = \frac{829}{4513076} = \frac{938}{5106472} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{548}{1967320} = \frac{683}{2451970} = \frac{689}{2473510} = \frac{952}{3417680} = \frac{968}{3475120} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{623}{4170985} = \frac{639}{4278105} = \frac{678}{4539210} = \frac{798}{5342610} = \frac{842}{5637190} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{637}{1254890} = \frac{649}{1278530} = \frac{756}{1489320} = \frac{758}{1493260} = \frac{849}{1672530} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{637}{1942850} = \frac{793}{2418650} = \frac{813}{2479650} = \frac{913}{2784650} = \frac{943}{2876150} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{638}{7429510} = \frac{681}{7930245} = \frac{721}{8396045} = \frac{801}{9327645} = \frac{827}{9630415} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{647}{5210938} = \frac{721}{5806934} = \frac{724}{5831096} = \frac{758}{6104932} = \frac{813}{6547902} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{648}{1597320} = \frac{693}{1708245} = \frac{784}{1932560} = \frac{876}{2159340} = \frac{958}{2361470} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{672}{1583904} = \frac{704}{1659328} = \frac{836}{1970452} = \frac{867}{2043519} = \frac{978}{2305146} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20475863} = \frac{28}{30174956} = \frac{38}{40951726} = \frac{49}{52806173} = \frac{76}{81903452} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{26}{15498730} = \frac{27}{16094835} = \frac{36}{21459780} = \frac{47}{28016935} = \frac{54}{32189670} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14569038} = \frac{47}{25360918} = \frac{54}{29138076} = \frac{94}{50721836} = \frac{97}{52340618} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{41}{23078695} = \frac{46}{25893170} = \frac{58}{32647910} = \frac{82}{46157390} = \frac{92}{51786340} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{2}{197530864} = \frac{4}{395061728} = \frac{5}{493827160} = \frac{7}{691358024} = \frac{8}{790123456} \end{aligned}$$

2.23 4 Equivalent Expressions

In this case we have 866 examples, each one with 4 expressions.

▶ $\frac{10392}{67548} = \frac{10452}{67938} = \frac{12396}{80574} = \frac{13524}{87906}$	▶ $\frac{12546}{39780} = \frac{16974}{53820} = \frac{23698}{75140} = \frac{26937}{85410}$
▶ $\frac{10437}{25986} = \frac{15827}{39406} = \frac{23716}{59048} = \frac{29645}{73810}$	▶ $\frac{12597}{34086} = \frac{18734}{50692} = \frac{29053}{78614} = \frac{34187}{92506}$
▶ $\frac{10527}{46893} = \frac{10923}{48657} = \frac{19536}{87024} = \frac{21054}{93786}$	▶ $\frac{12670}{39458} = \frac{17290}{53846} = \frac{25340}{78916} = \frac{31605}{98427}$
▶ $\frac{10537}{28946} = \frac{26985}{74130} = \frac{28013}{76954} = \frac{31097}{85426}$	▶ $\frac{12780}{64539} = \frac{14580}{73629} = \frac{18540}{93627} = \frac{18720}{94536}$
▶ $\frac{10634}{29857} = \frac{24830}{69715} = \frac{24986}{70153} = \frac{34502}{96871}$	▶ $\frac{12903}{47685} = \frac{17043}{62985} = \frac{18239}{67405} = \frac{26358}{97410}$
▶ $\frac{10659}{34782} = \frac{17309}{56482} = \frac{28063}{91574} = \frac{30172}{98456}$	▶ $\frac{12903}{48576} = \frac{13974}{52608} = \frac{19465}{73280} = \frac{24718}{93056}$
▶ $\frac{10675}{39284} = \frac{10725}{39468} = \frac{21450}{78936} = \frac{23075}{84916}$	▶ $\frac{13286}{74095} = \frac{13624}{75980} = \frac{14976}{83520} = \frac{15236}{84970}$
▶ $\frac{10695}{23784} = \frac{17825}{39640} = \frac{21390}{47568} = \frac{42780}{95136}$	▶ $\frac{13547}{26809} = \frac{27094}{53618} = \frac{38502}{76194} = \frac{47058}{93126}$
▶ $\frac{10728}{46935} = \frac{13248}{57960} = \frac{20376}{89145} = \frac{21456}{93870}$	▶ $\frac{13572}{49608} = \frac{17893}{65402} = \frac{19256}{70384} = \frac{19836}{72504}$
▶ $\frac{10795}{24638} = \frac{15980}{36472} = \frac{34680}{79152} = \frac{37910}{86524}$	▶ $\frac{13690}{24578} = \frac{27380}{49156} = \frac{47915}{86023} = \frac{54760}{98312}$
▶ $\frac{10965}{24378} = \frac{21930}{48756} = \frac{43215}{96078} = \frac{43860}{97512}$	▶ $\frac{13804}{27956} = \frac{20587}{41693} = \frac{24871}{50369} = \frac{46172}{93508}$
▶ $\frac{10974}{32568} = \frac{13578}{40296} = \frac{18972}{56304} = \frac{20739}{61548}$	▶ $\frac{13960}{42578} = \frac{17360}{52948} = \frac{17680}{53924} = \frac{19260}{58743}$
▶ $\frac{10975}{32486} = \frac{12975}{38406} = \frac{30275}{89614} = \frac{31850}{94276}$	▶ $\frac{13974}{26580} = \frac{25619}{48730} = \frac{27948}{53160} = \frac{51238}{97460}$
▶ $\frac{12360}{84975} = \frac{13480}{92675} = \frac{14352}{98670} = \frac{14360}{98725}$	▶ $\frac{13980}{26574} = \frac{25630}{48719} = \frac{27960}{53148} = \frac{51260}{97438}$
▶ $\frac{12374}{65098} = \frac{12489}{65703} = \frac{15709}{82643} = \frac{17802}{93654}$	▶ $\frac{14053}{28769} = \frac{17296}{35408} = \frac{34592}{70816} = \frac{42159}{86307}$
▶ $\frac{12390}{48675} = \frac{18564}{72930} = \frac{18690}{73425} = \frac{21630}{84975}$	▶ $\frac{14239}{78560} = \frac{17284}{95360} = \frac{17342}{95680} = \frac{17458}{96320}$
▶ $\frac{12430}{65879} = \frac{14320}{75896} = \frac{15920}{84376} = \frac{17460}{92538}$	▶ $\frac{14365}{20978} = \frac{28730}{41956} = \frac{37180}{54296} = \frac{57460}{83912}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14385}{20769} = \frac{18495}{26703} = \frac{41785}{60329} = \frac{48635}{70219}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14396}{57820} = \frac{17324}{69580} = \frac{21594}{86730} = \frac{23607}{94815}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14398}{56027} = \frac{18630}{72495} = \frac{20516}{79834} = \frac{24058}{93617}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14586}{39270} = \frac{25194}{67830} = \frac{32097}{86415} = \frac{35724}{96180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14652}{30789} = \frac{18056}{37942} = \frac{27084}{56913} = \frac{29304}{61578}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14730}{26985} = \frac{21604}{39578} = \frac{43208}{79156} = \frac{53028}{97146}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14760}{39852} = \frac{18360}{49572} = \frac{25830}{69741} = \frac{35820}{96714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{39627} = \frac{19740}{52836} = \frac{23970}{64158} = \frac{28435}{76109}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15087}{42693} = \frac{18706}{52934} = \frac{28106}{79534} = \frac{30926}{87514}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15096}{24378} = \frac{29156}{47083} = \frac{30192}{48756} = \frac{60384}{97512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15096}{47328} = \frac{18093}{56724} = \frac{24531}{76908} = \frac{30784}{96512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{24786} = \frac{25137}{40698} = \frac{30618}{49572} = \frac{50274}{81396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15347}{28906} = \frac{27398}{51604} = \frac{30179}{56842} = \frac{30694}{57812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15407}{38269} = \frac{32054}{79618} = \frac{32457}{80619} = \frac{35092}{87164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15478}{30629} = \frac{17892}{35406} = \frac{19028}{37654} = \frac{40186}{79523}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15486}{29370} = \frac{18792}{35640} = \frac{40281}{76395} = \frac{45936}{87120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15694}{23807} = \frac{25016}{37948} = \frac{29736}{45108} = \frac{60534}{91827}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15698}{20374} = \frac{26978}{35014} = \frac{28059}{36417} = \frac{48927}{63501}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15730}{28496} = \frac{21780}{39456} = \frac{32670}{59184} = \frac{43560}{78912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15780}{24936} = \frac{28930}{45716} = \frac{31560}{49872} = \frac{57860}{91432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15792}{34860} = \frac{17860}{39425} = \frac{31584}{69720} = \frac{32148}{70965}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15870}{36294} = \frac{19780}{45236} = \frac{23690}{54178} = \frac{41860}{95732}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16037}{25984} = \frac{32074}{51968} = \frac{57038}{92416} = \frac{60751}{98432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{27459} = \frac{20196}{34578} = \frac{30294}{51867} = \frac{32076}{54918}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{45927} = \frac{20196}{57834} = \frac{30294}{86751} = \frac{32076}{91854}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16082}{39457} = \frac{16598}{40723} = \frac{25714}{63089} = \frac{40162}{98537}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16354}{20978} = \frac{18759}{24063} = \frac{32708}{41956} = \frac{53872}{69104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16974}{25830} = \frac{52164}{79380} = \frac{57132}{86940} = \frac{62307}{94815}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{16983}{27540} = \frac{21978}{35640} = \frac{43956}{71280} = \frac{45621}{73980}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17094}{32856} = \frac{18249}{35076} = \frac{36498}{70152} = \frac{50127}{96348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17264}{39508} = \frac{17420}{39865} = \frac{26104}{59738} = \frac{34528}{79016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{34965} = \frac{20736}{41958} = \frac{23680}{47915} = \frac{27136}{54908}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17385}{20496} = \frac{26790}{31584} = \frac{28975}{34160} = \frac{82365}{97104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17420}{38659} = \frac{19760}{43852} = \frac{26780}{59431} = \frac{43160}{95782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17493}{28560} = \frac{34986}{57120} = \frac{43659}{71280} = \frac{45129}{73680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{32805} = \frac{17568}{32940} = \frac{19584}{36720} = \frac{31824}{59670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17549}{30268} = \frac{41965}{72380} = \frac{42619}{73508} = \frac{47306}{81592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17640}{35982} = \frac{21560}{43978} = \frac{35280}{71964} = \frac{43120}{87956}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17682}{54309} = \frac{19026}{58437} = \frac{20958}{64371} = \frac{31206}{95847}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{35964} = \frac{21780}{43956} = \frac{35640}{71928} = \frac{43560}{87912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17869}{24503} = \frac{37408}{51296} = \frac{52438}{71906} = \frac{67134}{92058}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17954}{30268} = \frac{42593}{71806} = \frac{52143}{87906} = \frac{53671}{90482}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17956}{23048} = \frac{24857}{31906} = \frac{38257}{49106} = \frac{62913}{80754}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17956}{30284} = \frac{37051}{62489} = \frac{43081}{72659} = \frac{56213}{94807}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17982}{35640} = \frac{21978}{43560} = \frac{35964}{71280} = \frac{43956}{87120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18067}{23954} = \frac{37914}{50268} = \frac{54913}{72806} = \frac{62745}{83190}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18096}{23754} = \frac{36192}{47508} = \frac{39208}{51467} = \frac{72384}{95016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18270}{39564} = \frac{23780}{51496} = \frac{26390}{57148} = \frac{36540}{79128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18270}{45936} = \frac{19320}{48576} = \frac{36540}{91872} = \frac{38640}{97152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{20769} = \frac{35986}{40721} = \frac{39786}{45021} = \frac{39862}{45107}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18370}{46259} = \frac{19360}{48752} = \frac{25410}{63987} = \frac{36740}{92518}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18479}{20653} = \frac{53941}{60287} = \frac{63512}{70984} = \frac{75106}{83942}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18640}{25397} = \frac{58160}{79243} = \frac{58320}{79461} = \frac{59760}{81423}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18675}{23904} = \frac{19350}{24768} = \frac{37650}{48192} = \frac{48375}{61920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18745}{23690} = \frac{27058}{34196} = \frac{49715}{62830} = \frac{65037}{82194}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18763}{45290} = \frac{18792}{45360} = \frac{27318}{65940} = \frac{29638}{71540}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{18963}{42570} = \frac{34251}{76890} = \frac{37926}{85140} = \frac{43512}{97680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{28647} = \frac{25740}{38196} = \frac{38610}{57294} = \frac{51480}{76392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19380}{25764} = \frac{35190}{46782} = \frac{53890}{71642} = \frac{74120}{98536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19470}{32568} = \frac{21945}{36708} = \frac{27390}{45816} = \frac{54780}{91632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19520}{36478} = \frac{25760}{48139} = \frac{39680}{74152} = \frac{52640}{98371}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19576}{23804} = \frac{39152}{47608} = \frac{73410}{89265} = \frac{78304}{95216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19630}{28574} = \frac{27180}{39564} = \frac{39260}{57148} = \frac{54360}{79128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19685}{42037} = \frac{21390}{45678} = \frac{32705}{69841} = \frac{42780}{91356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19734}{25806} = \frac{37518}{49062} = \frac{49803}{65127} = \frac{75036}{98124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19750}{32864} = \frac{37250}{61984} = \frac{43250}{71968} = \frac{49375}{82160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19760}{25384} = \frac{43810}{56279} = \frac{48230}{61957} = \frac{72540}{93186}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{36504} = \frac{30912}{56784} = \frac{39468}{72501} = \frac{47012}{86359}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20176}{35984} = \frac{40352}{71968} = \frac{42389}{75601} = \frac{52186}{93074}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20586}{31974} = \frac{46389}{72051} = \frac{52734}{81906} = \frac{61053}{94827}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{20895}{43176} = \frac{31840}{65792} = \frac{34825}{71960} = \frac{41790}{86352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21087}{43956} = \frac{27903}{58164} = \frac{34506}{71928} = \frac{40257}{83916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21375}{40698} = \frac{40125}{76398} = \frac{42750}{81396} = \frac{48375}{92106}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21408}{36795} = \frac{27936}{48015} = \frac{42816}{73590} = \frac{57216}{98340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{21836}{59740} = \frac{32701}{89465} = \frac{32754}{89610} = \frac{34768}{95120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{24178}{30569} = \frac{32970}{41685} = \frac{42076}{53198} = \frac{63742}{80591}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25109}{34867} = \frac{32916}{45708} = \frac{36714}{50982} = \frac{50218}{69734}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25974}{30186} = \frac{51948}{60372} = \frac{54279}{63081} = \frac{74259}{86301}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26471}{35980} = \frac{37698}{51240} = \frac{61594}{83720} = \frac{65714}{89320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26549}{30178} = \frac{59214}{67308} = \frac{63245}{71890} = \frac{85346}{97012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{26598}{37014} = \frac{28457}{39601} = \frac{53196}{74028} = \frac{64207}{89351}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27168}{59430} = \frac{31728}{69405} = \frac{32496}{71085} = \frac{36912}{80745}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{40698} = \frac{29601}{43758} = \frac{48369}{71502} = \frac{59064}{87312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27935}{46810} = \frac{38295}{64170} = \frac{40293}{67518} = \frac{56203}{94178}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{27965}{40138} = \frac{31790}{45628} = \frac{31960}{45872} = \frac{49215}{70638}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28364}{90157} = \frac{28476}{90513} = \frac{28756}{91403} = \frac{30128}{95764}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{28379}{40651} = \frac{42513}{60897} = \frac{50394}{72186} = \frac{57461}{82309}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29078}{31465} = \frac{38592}{41760} = \frac{38726}{41905} = \frac{65928}{71340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29087}{46315} = \frac{38947}{62015} = \frac{42398}{67510} = \frac{58174}{92630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29406}{37518} = \frac{40629}{51837} = \frac{46023}{58719} = \frac{54027}{68931}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29605}{38471} = \frac{36290}{47158} = \frac{48705}{63291} = \frac{72580}{94316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29680}{34715} = \frac{42896}{50173} = \frac{63952}{74801} = \frac{74032}{86591}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{29680}{57134} = \frac{35280}{67914} = \frac{39280}{75614} = \frac{51240}{98637}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30528}{41976} = \frac{49320}{67815} = \frac{51624}{70983} = \frac{60912}{83754}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{30962}{41785} = \frac{37968}{51240} = \frac{54692}{73810} = \frac{61924}{83570}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31089}{42657} = \frac{62049}{85137} = \frac{62307}{85491} = \frac{67854}{93102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{31682}{40579} = \frac{39712}{50864} = \frac{54896}{70312} = \frac{64970}{83215}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34921}{56870} = \frac{42351}{68970} = \frac{51267}{83490} = \frac{53496}{87120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35417}{62890} = \frac{42693}{75810} = \frac{45796}{81320} = \frac{47936}{85120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35706}{42198} = \frac{48312}{57096} = \frac{54087}{63921} = \frac{73194}{86502}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36120}{47859} = \frac{48120}{63759} = \frac{51240}{67893} = \frac{72840}{96513}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36218}{40795} = \frac{69342}{78105} = \frac{69524}{78310} = \frac{72436}{81590}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37128}{56049} = \frac{45032}{67981} = \frac{49816}{75203} = \frac{60528}{91374}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37521}{64809} = \frac{38049}{65721} = \frac{45309}{78261} = \frac{52734}{91086}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37820}{65941} = \frac{45260}{78913} = \frac{51460}{89723} = \frac{56420}{98371}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46127}{59830} = \frac{48517}{62930} = \frac{52341}{67890} = \frac{73612}{95480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48792}{51360} = \frac{49761}{52380} = \frac{68913}{72540} = \frac{86754}{91320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1026}{534789} = \frac{1406}{732859} = \frac{1824}{950736} = \frac{1862}{970543}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1027}{645983} = \frac{1423}{895067} = \frac{1527}{960483} = \frac{1538}{967402}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1035}{268479} = \frac{1680}{435792} = \frac{1785}{463029} = \frac{3540}{918276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1043}{796852} = \frac{1079}{824356} = \frac{1237}{945068} = \frac{1257}{960348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1057}{269384} = \frac{1708}{435296} = \frac{2107}{536984} = \frac{3416}{870592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1058}{627394} = \frac{1078}{639254} = \frac{1342}{795806} = \frac{1532}{908476}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1065}{274983} = \frac{1540}{397628} = \frac{2705}{698431} = \frac{3045}{786219}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1065}{437928} = \frac{1830}{752496} = \frac{2175}{894360} = \frac{2305}{947816}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1067}{253849} = \frac{2134}{507698} = \frac{2948}{701356} = \frac{3762}{895014}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1078}{253946} = \frac{1736}{408952} = \frac{3052}{718964} = \frac{3507}{826149}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1087}{429365} = \frac{1754}{692830} = \frac{1839}{726405} = \frac{1862}{735490}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1092}{347865} = \frac{1248}{397560} = \frac{1872}{596340} = \frac{2184}{695730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1093}{628475} = \frac{1286}{739450} = \frac{1298}{746350} = \frac{1382}{794650}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1095}{326748} = \frac{1260}{375984} = \frac{1605}{478932} = \frac{3210}{957864}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1208}{376594} = \frac{1708}{532469} = \frac{1804}{562397} = \frac{2380}{741965}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1209}{437658} = \frac{1356}{490872} = \frac{1632}{590784} = \frac{2109}{763458}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1240}{367598} = \frac{1280}{379456} = \frac{2480}{735196} = \frac{2940}{871563}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1243}{658790} = \frac{1432}{758960} = \frac{1592}{843760} = \frac{1746}{925380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1248}{359760} = \frac{1872}{539640} = \frac{2418}{697035} = \frac{3042}{876915}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1248}{507936} = \frac{1572}{639804} = \frac{1704}{693528} = \frac{2079}{846153}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1258}{309764} = \frac{1547}{380926} = \frac{3094}{761852} = \frac{3706}{912548}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1265}{793408} = \frac{1370}{859264} = \frac{1425}{893760} = \frac{1560}{978432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1269}{437805} = \frac{1692}{583740} = \frac{2169}{748305} = \frac{2601}{897345}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1270}{659384} = \frac{1325}{687940} = \frac{1340}{695728} = \frac{1425}{739860}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1274}{396508} = \frac{1807}{562394} = \frac{1937}{602854} = \frac{2548}{793016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1274}{635089} = \frac{1298}{647053} = \frac{1370}{682945} = \frac{1670}{832495}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1275}{349860} = \frac{1960}{537824} = \frac{2975}{816340} = \frac{3470}{952168}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1278}{645390} = \frac{1458}{736290} = \frac{1854}{936270} = \frac{1872}{945360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1286}{479035} = \frac{1948}{725630} = \frac{1962}{730845} = \frac{2138}{796405}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1305}{286947} = \frac{1740}{382596} = \frac{2610}{573894} = \frac{3480}{765192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1309}{246785} = \frac{2618}{493570} = \frac{5168}{974320} = \frac{5236}{987140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1348}{562790} = \frac{1432}{597860} = \frac{1528}{637940} = \frac{1842}{769035}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1349}{256807} = \frac{1463}{278509} = \frac{3249}{618507} = \frac{4237}{806591}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1358}{740692} = \frac{1435}{782690} = \frac{1645}{897230} = \frac{1743}{950682}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1365}{207948} = \frac{2415}{367908} = \frac{2730}{415896} = \frac{5460}{831792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1378}{290546} = \frac{2067}{435819} = \frac{3458}{729106} = \frac{4251}{896307}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1379}{245068} = \frac{2758}{490136} = \frac{2765}{491380} = \frac{3801}{675492}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1395}{402876} = \frac{1520}{438976} = \frac{3105}{896724} = \frac{3145}{908276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1398}{265740} = \frac{2563}{487190} = \frac{2796}{531480} = \frac{5126}{974380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{357698} = \frac{1540}{387926} = \frac{2840}{715396} = \frac{3540}{891726}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1430}{295867} = \frac{1680}{347592} = \frac{2860}{591734} = \frac{3180}{657942}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1430}{296857} = \frac{2860}{593714} = \frac{3510}{728649} = \frac{4680}{971532}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1470}{359268} = \frac{2340}{571896} = \frac{2940}{718536} = \frac{3240}{791856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1476}{398520} = \frac{1836}{495720} = \frac{2583}{697410} = \frac{3582}{967140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1485}{269730} = \frac{2178}{395604} = \frac{4356}{791208} = \frac{5346}{971028}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1485}{307692} = \frac{2190}{453768} = \frac{2970}{615384} = \frac{3615}{749028}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1486}{259307} = \frac{3542}{618079} = \frac{4528}{790136} = \frac{5174}{902863}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1504}{387296} = \frac{1692}{435708} = \frac{1974}{508326} = \frac{2914}{750386}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1547}{263809} = \frac{2108}{359476} = \frac{3094}{527618} = \frac{5372}{916084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1547}{362089} = \frac{1598}{374026} = \frac{3196}{748052} = \frac{3502}{819674}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{249378} = \frac{2860}{457193} = \frac{3120}{498756} = \frac{5720}{914386}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{284973} = \frac{2160}{394578} = \frac{3240}{591867} = \frac{4320}{789156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{392478} = \frac{2860}{719543} = \frac{3120}{784956} = \frac{3640}{915782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1564}{203987} = \frac{1768}{230594} = \frac{5304}{691782} = \frac{6052}{789341}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1570}{362984} = \frac{3140}{725968} = \frac{3295}{761804} = \frac{3425}{791860}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1573}{284960} = \frac{2178}{394560} = \frac{3267}{591840} = \frac{4356}{789120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{246039} = \frac{3156}{492078} = \frac{3682}{574091} = \frac{5786}{902143}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{249360} = \frac{2893}{457160} = \frac{3156}{498720} = \frac{5786}{914320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{230967} = \frac{4032}{587916} = \frac{4208}{613579} = \frac{6032}{879541}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1587}{203964} = \frac{1794}{230568} = \frac{5382}{691704} = \frac{7406}{951832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1587}{209346} = \frac{3726}{491508} = \frac{3864}{509712} = \frac{7452}{983016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1587}{362940} = \frac{1978}{452360} = \frac{2369}{541780} = \frac{4186}{957320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1596}{378024} = \frac{1932}{457608} = \frac{2835}{671490} = \frac{3192}{756048}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1598}{207364} = \frac{2465}{319870} = \frac{3978}{516204} = \frac{5321}{690478}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1605}{249738} = \frac{4095}{637182} = \frac{4905}{763218} = \frac{6325}{984170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1608}{347529} = \frac{1624}{350987} = \frac{2840}{613795} = \frac{4176}{902538}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1620}{349758} = \frac{1840}{397256} = \frac{2130}{459867} = \frac{3680}{794512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1640}{298357} = \frac{3280}{596714} = \frac{4320}{785916} = \frac{5320}{967841}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1640}{372895} = \frac{3480}{791265} = \frac{4120}{936785} = \frac{4280}{973165}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1645}{389207} = \frac{2730}{645918} = \frac{3210}{759486} = \frac{3870}{915642}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1670}{258349} = \frac{3210}{496587} = \frac{3860}{597142} = \frac{5410}{836927}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1674}{293508} = \frac{2079}{364518} = \frac{4158}{729036} = \frac{5103}{894726}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1683}{209457} = \frac{4851}{603729} = \frac{4983}{620157} = \frac{5049}{628371}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{235708} = \frac{4529}{630178} = \frac{5012}{697384} = \frac{6531}{908742}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{307582} = \frac{2653}{481709} = \frac{3094}{561782} = \frac{3864}{701592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1708}{463295} = \frac{1732}{469805} = \frac{1820}{493675} = \frac{3584}{972160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{259408} = \frac{3619}{540782} = \frac{5012}{748936} = \frac{6251}{934078}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{259840} = \frac{3472}{519680} = \frac{5239}{784160} = \frac{5673}{849120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{289540} = \frac{2086}{347915} = \frac{4172}{695830} = \frac{5824}{971360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{239685} = \frac{3768}{519042} = \frac{5904}{813276} = \frac{6804}{937251}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{235980} = \frac{3087}{412965} = \frac{3528}{471960} = \frac{6174}{825930}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{359820} = \frac{2156}{439780} = \frac{3528}{719640} = \frac{4312}{879560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{359640} = \frac{2178}{439560} = \frac{3564}{719280} = \frac{4356}{879120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1784}{596302} = \frac{2368}{791504} = \frac{2516}{840973} = \frac{2736}{914508}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1790}{328465} = \frac{2610}{478935} = \frac{2734}{501689} = \frac{2746}{503891}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{236054} = \frac{2697}{354081} = \frac{3596}{472108} = \frac{5394}{708162}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1809}{263547} = \frac{2546}{370918} = \frac{3618}{527094} = \frac{5092}{741836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1827}{395640} = \frac{2378}{514960} = \frac{2639}{571480} = \frac{3654}{791280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1827}{453096} = \frac{1839}{456072} = \frac{1965}{487320} = \frac{3165}{784920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1827}{459360} = \frac{1932}{485760} = \frac{3654}{918720} = \frac{3864}{971520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1830}{247965} = \frac{4578}{620319} = \frac{5304}{718692} = \frac{5862}{794301}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1837}{462590} = \frac{1936}{487520} = \frac{2541}{639870} = \frac{3674}{925180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1840}{365792} = \frac{1940}{385672} = \frac{3415}{678902} = \frac{3820}{759416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1852}{769043} = \frac{1976}{820534} = \frac{2176}{903584} = \frac{2340}{971685}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1853}{270946} = \frac{3706}{541892} = \frac{5123}{749086} = \frac{5341}{780962}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1853}{472906} = \frac{2507}{639814} = \frac{2943}{751086} = \frac{3706}{945812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1854}{367092} = \frac{3609}{714582} = \frac{3942}{780516} = \frac{4302}{851796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1860}{349275} = \frac{1984}{372560} = \frac{3472}{651980} = \frac{3968}{745120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1864}{390275} = \frac{1928}{403675} = \frac{4328}{906175} = \frac{4360}{912875}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{324950} = \frac{3892}{674150} = \frac{4690}{812375} = \frac{4732}{819650}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1890}{473256} = \frac{2190}{548376} = \frac{3645}{912708} = \frac{3780}{946512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1892}{453607} = \frac{2468}{591703} = \frac{3204}{768159} = \frac{4028}{965713}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1896}{473052} = \frac{1926}{480537} = \frac{3708}{925146} = \frac{3852}{961074}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1925}{367840} = \frac{1960}{374528} = \frac{2135}{407968} = \frac{4270}{815936}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1935}{280647} = \frac{2580}{374196} = \frac{3870}{561294} = \frac{5160}{748392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1938}{257640} = \frac{3519}{467820} = \frac{5389}{716420} = \frac{7412}{985360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1945}{603728} = \frac{2390}{741856} = \frac{2635}{817904} = \frac{3145}{976208}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1947}{280635} = \frac{2596}{374180} = \frac{3894}{561270} = \frac{5192}{748360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1947}{286305} = \frac{2596}{381740} = \frac{3894}{572610} = \frac{5192}{763480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1963}{285740} = \frac{2718}{395640} = \frac{3926}{571480} = \frac{5436}{791280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{302586} = \frac{2086}{319754} = \frac{3948}{605172} = \frac{4172}{639508}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{536082} = \frac{2149}{583607} = \frac{2163}{587409} = \frac{2583}{701469}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1975}{342860} = \frac{4510}{782936} = \frac{4910}{852376} = \frac{5670}{984312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{253840} = \frac{4381}{562790} = \frac{4823}{619570} = \frac{7254}{931860}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{236054} = \frac{2967}{354081} = \frac{3956}{472108} = \frac{5934}{708162}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{360254} = \frac{2967}{540381} = \frac{3128}{569704} = \frac{4163}{758209}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{379586} = \frac{2869}{540731} = \frac{4579}{863021} = \frac{5168}{974032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{165798} = \frac{3051}{248697} = \frac{3164}{257908} = \frac{5198}{423706}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2048}{175936} = \frac{4096}{351872} = \frac{4512}{387609} = \frac{9120}{783465}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{183976} = \frac{3081}{275964} = \frac{4108}{367952} = \frac{8216}{735904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{198376} = \frac{3081}{297564} = \frac{4108}{396752} = \frac{8216}{793504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{376198} = \frac{3081}{564297} = \frac{3172}{580964} = \frac{4108}{752396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2064}{379518} = \frac{3960}{728145} = \frac{4128}{759036} = \frac{4632}{851709}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2067}{345189} = \frac{2718}{453906} = \frac{3921}{654807} = \frac{5436}{907812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{148953} = \frac{2340}{167895} = \frac{5712}{409836} = \frac{7416}{532098}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2079}{164835} = \frac{3654}{289710} = \frac{4158}{329670} = \frac{7182}{569430}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2079}{483516} = \frac{2184}{507936} = \frac{2751}{639804} = \frac{4158}{967032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2108}{476935} = \frac{2984}{675130} = \frac{3456}{781920} = \frac{4216}{953870}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2136}{504897} = \frac{2584}{610793} = \frac{2704}{639158} = \frac{4120}{973865}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2160}{347598} = \frac{3720}{598641} = \frac{3840}{617952} = \frac{4680}{753129}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2180}{463795} = \frac{2384}{507196} = \frac{3516}{748029} = \frac{4308}{916527}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2190}{537864} = \frac{2905}{713468} = \frac{3215}{789604} = \frac{3725}{914860}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2304}{175896} = \frac{4608}{351792} = \frac{9216}{703584} = \frac{9536}{728014}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2316}{584790} = \frac{3162}{798405} = \frac{3726}{940815} = \frac{3768}{951420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{165978} = \frac{3510}{248967} = \frac{6370}{451829} = \frac{7930}{562481}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2358}{109647} = \frac{5094}{236871} = \frac{6498}{302157} = \frac{6894}{320571}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2370}{648195} = \frac{2946}{805731} = \frac{3190}{872465} = \frac{3602}{985147}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{180954} = \frac{4752}{361908} = \frac{5148}{392067} = \frac{9504}{723816}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{195804} = \frac{4752}{391608} = \frac{8910}{734265} = \frac{9504}{783216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2394}{156807} = \frac{4536}{297108} = \frac{5904}{386712} = \frac{9702}{635481}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2407}{539168} = \frac{2671}{598304} = \frac{2917}{653408} = \frac{3759}{842016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2430}{196587} = \frac{3410}{275869} = \frac{6420}{519378} = \frac{6710}{542839}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{175398} = \frac{3780}{269514} = \frac{7380}{526194} = \frac{9570}{682341}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2465}{189370} = \frac{5168}{397024} = \frac{6783}{521094} = \frac{7684}{590312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2478}{156039} = \frac{4956}{312078} = \frac{5782}{364091} = \frac{9086}{572143}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2489}{163750} = \frac{6289}{413750} = \frac{7391}{486250} = \frac{9481}{623750}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2490}{168573} = \frac{3570}{241689} = \frac{7920}{536184} = \frac{9510}{643827}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2496}{375180} = \frac{3120}{468975} = \frac{4816}{723905} = \frac{5312}{798460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2508}{391476} = \frac{2981}{465307} = \frac{5632}{879104} = \frac{5786}{903142}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2537}{184906} = \frac{5074}{369812} = \frac{6751}{492038} = \frac{9245}{673810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{174398} = \frac{3840}{261597} = \frac{5120}{348796} = \frac{7680}{523194}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{197438} = \frac{3840}{296157} = \frac{5120}{394876} = \frac{7680}{592314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{106938} = \frac{3047}{126589} = \frac{4356}{180972} = \frac{6094}{253178}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2583}{149076} = \frac{2709}{156348} = \frac{6741}{389052} = \frac{8736}{504192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2596}{413708} = \frac{2937}{468051} = \frac{2981}{475063} = \frac{5874}{936102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2597}{314608} = \frac{2961}{358704} = \frac{7483}{906512} = \frac{7861}{952304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2603}{189745} = \frac{4826}{351790} = \frac{7296}{531840} = \frac{9823}{716045}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2639}{174580} = \frac{3718}{245960} = \frac{5278}{349160} = \frac{6279}{415380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2640}{137895} = \frac{4576}{239018} = \frac{7920}{413685} = \frac{9152}{478036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2658}{139740} = \frac{4873}{256190} = \frac{5316}{279480} = \frac{9746}{512380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2670}{485139} = \frac{4230}{768591} = \frac{4690}{852173} = \frac{5310}{964827}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2680}{357914} = \frac{3940}{526187} = \frac{5460}{729183} = \frac{6420}{857391}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2685}{409731} = \frac{2730}{416598} = \frac{4530}{691278} = \frac{5370}{819462}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2695}{184730} = \frac{5412}{370968} = \frac{6908}{473512} = \frac{7821}{536094}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2703}{149685} = \frac{5194}{287630} = \frac{5724}{316980} = \frac{8321}{460795}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2705}{318649} = \frac{5410}{637298} = \frac{6940}{817532} = \frac{7230}{851694}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2706}{395814} = \frac{2761}{403859} = \frac{3916}{572804} = \frac{4829}{706351}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2730}{158496} = \frac{3780}{219456} = \frac{5670}{329184} = \frac{7560}{438912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2730}{165984} = \frac{3975}{241680} = \frac{4965}{301872} = \frac{7920}{481536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2730}{468195} = \frac{2976}{510384} = \frac{4038}{692517} = \frac{5094}{873621}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2754}{169830} = \frac{3564}{219780} = \frac{7128}{439560} = \frac{7398}{456210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2765}{349180} = \frac{3619}{457028} = \frac{6195}{782340} = \frac{7238}{914056}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2783}{140965} = \frac{3864}{195720} = \frac{6279}{318045} = \frac{8671}{439205}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2790}{386415} = \frac{3582}{496107} = \frac{5042}{698317} = \frac{6518}{902743}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2796}{108345} = \frac{4380}{169725} = \frac{6180}{239475} = \frac{8076}{312945}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2804}{167539} = \frac{3260}{194785} = \frac{6908}{412753} = \frac{9012}{538467}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2805}{136947} = \frac{3740}{182596} = \frac{5610}{273894} = \frac{7480}{365192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2805}{193647} = \frac{3740}{258196} = \frac{5610}{387294} = \frac{7480}{516392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2806}{137954} = \frac{2867}{140953} = \frac{5063}{248917} = \frac{5734}{281906}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2856}{431970} = \frac{5496}{831270} = \frac{5712}{863940} = \frac{6180}{934725}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2860}{345917} = \frac{4380}{529761} = \frac{5720}{691834} = \frac{7560}{914382}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2871}{435609} = \frac{3201}{485679} = \frac{4851}{736029} = \frac{6402}{971358}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2915}{347680} = \frac{4279}{510368} = \frac{7634}{910528} = \frac{8162}{973504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2938}{467051} = \frac{3164}{502978} = \frac{3842}{610759} = \frac{5876}{934102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2943}{615087} = \frac{3108}{649572} = \frac{3609}{754281} = \frac{3612}{754908}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2968}{104357} = \frac{3640}{127985} = \frac{5376}{189024} = \frac{5936}{208714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2970}{153846} = \frac{3570}{184926} = \frac{5730}{296814} = \frac{7140}{369852}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2970}{418635} = \frac{3718}{524069} = \frac{5742}{809361} = \frac{5962}{840371}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3024}{185976} = \frac{3546}{218079} = \frac{6048}{371952} = \frac{7092}{436158}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3056}{247918} = \frac{4016}{325798} = \frac{6384}{517902} = \frac{9104}{738562}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3094}{167258} = \frac{3672}{198504} = \frac{3978}{215046} = \frac{5627}{304189}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3097}{215486} = \frac{4579}{318602} = \frac{8094}{563172} = \frac{9158}{637204}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3107}{624985} = \frac{3471}{698205} = \frac{4732}{951860} = \frac{4823}{970165}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3108}{495726} = \frac{3708}{591426} = \frac{5316}{847902} = \frac{6132}{978054}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3128}{496570} = \frac{3648}{579120} = \frac{4812}{763905} = \frac{4952}{786130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3168}{297504} = \frac{5236}{491708} = \frac{6083}{571249} = \frac{7304}{685912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3186}{294705} = \frac{6372}{589410} = \frac{7128}{659340} = \frac{7452}{689310}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3195}{472860} = \frac{3798}{562104} = \frac{5346}{791208} = \frac{5427}{803196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3201}{478695} = \frac{3476}{519820} = \frac{5324}{796180} = \frac{6512}{973840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3276}{150948} = \frac{5863}{270149} = \frac{6058}{279134} = \frac{8502}{391746}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3289}{170456} = \frac{6578}{340912} = \frac{7429}{385016} = \frac{9315}{482760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3297}{186045} = \frac{4809}{271365} = \frac{4893}{276105} = \frac{9618}{542730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3456}{129708} = \frac{4096}{153728} = \frac{8192}{307456} = \frac{9728}{365104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3458}{107926} = \frac{6859}{214073} = \frac{6954}{217038} = \frac{8493}{265071}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3458}{176092} = \frac{3549}{180726} = \frac{6708}{341592} = \frac{7098}{361452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3458}{216970} = \frac{4921}{308765} = \frac{8246}{517390} = \frac{9842}{617530}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3478}{125960} = \frac{4329}{156780} = \frac{5476}{198320} = \frac{6549}{237180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3478}{295160} = \frac{4218}{357960} = \frac{6179}{524380} = \frac{8436}{715920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3507}{169428} = \frac{4509}{217836} = \frac{9018}{435672} = \frac{9853}{476012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3509}{214687} = \frac{5918}{362074} = \frac{6589}{403127} = \frac{8327}{509461}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3510}{297648} = \frac{6390}{541872} = \frac{8175}{693240} = \frac{8295}{703416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3528}{169407} = \frac{3584}{172096} = \frac{4536}{217809} = \frac{9072}{435618}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3542}{180796} = \frac{7084}{361592} = \frac{7245}{369810} = \frac{7912}{403856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3562}{148097} = \frac{4290}{178365} = \frac{5746}{238901} = \frac{5798}{241063}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3568}{417902} = \frac{4328}{506917} = \frac{4608}{539712} = \frac{7856}{920134}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3570}{291648} = \frac{4675}{381920} = \frac{7140}{583296} = \frac{7395}{604128}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3582}{179640} = \frac{4378}{219560} = \frac{7164}{359280} = \frac{8756}{439120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3584}{172960} = \frac{4368}{210795} = \frac{7168}{345920} = \frac{8736}{421590}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3591}{240786} = \frac{3819}{256074} = \frac{4617}{309582} = \frac{7809}{523614}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3657}{148029} = \frac{6187}{250439} = \frac{7314}{296058} = \frac{7682}{310954}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3679}{480251} = \frac{4368}{570192} = \frac{5213}{680497} = \frac{5629}{734801}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3690}{214758} = \frac{4590}{267138} = \frac{7380}{429516} = \frac{9180}{534276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3690}{451287} = \frac{6210}{759483} = \frac{6970}{852431} = \frac{7460}{912358}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3724}{159068} = \frac{3794}{162058} = \frac{5691}{243087} = \frac{5831}{249067}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3728}{596014} = \frac{4912}{785306} = \frac{5096}{814723} = \frac{6120}{978435}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3752}{109648} = \frac{5829}{170346} = \frac{5896}{172304} = \frac{9514}{278036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3760}{142598} = \frac{4560}{172938} = \frac{5640}{213897} = \frac{9120}{345876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3780}{125496} = \frac{5240}{173968} = \frac{9165}{304278} = \frac{9540}{316728}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3780}{192564} = \frac{4970}{253186} = \frac{7245}{369081} = \frac{7490}{381562}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3782}{196054} = \frac{5673}{294081} = \frac{7564}{392108} = \frac{9672}{501384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3782}{659410} = \frac{4526}{789130} = \frac{5146}{897230} = \frac{5642}{983710}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3810}{279654} = \frac{4065}{298371} = \frac{7380}{541692} = \frac{8130}{596742}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3816}{457920} = \frac{6129}{735480} = \frac{7461}{895320} = \frac{7632}{915840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3825}{469710} = \frac{3915}{480762} = \frac{6435}{790218} = \frac{7830}{961524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3840}{576192} = \frac{4380}{657219} = \frac{5460}{819273} = \frac{6540}{981327}$$

$\triangleright \frac{3874}{165092} = \frac{4082}{173956} = \frac{7982}{340156} = \frac{9685}{412730}$	$\triangleright \frac{4257}{189630} = \frac{7689}{342510} = \frac{8514}{379260} = \frac{9768}{435120}$
$\triangleright \frac{3920}{174685} = \frac{4576}{203918} = \frac{8240}{367195} = \frac{9152}{407836}$	$\triangleright \frac{4285}{103697} = \frac{4985}{120637} = \frac{9035}{218647} = \frac{9705}{234861}$
$\triangleright \frac{3924}{176580} = \frac{6093}{274185} = \frac{7596}{341820} = \frac{8937}{402165}$	$\triangleright \frac{4308}{296175} = \frac{7180}{493625} = \frac{8932}{614075} = \frac{9140}{628375}$
$\triangleright \frac{3942}{157680} = \frac{4392}{175680} = \frac{5796}{231840} = \frac{7956}{318240}$	$\triangleright \frac{4319}{562087} = \frac{4396}{572108} = \frac{4837}{629501} = \frac{6013}{782549}$
$\triangleright \frac{3945}{206718} = \frac{5340}{279816} = \frac{7695}{403218} = \frac{9015}{472386}$	$\triangleright \frac{4328}{107659} = \frac{4856}{120793} = \frac{6328}{157409} = \frac{7256}{180493}$
$\triangleright \frac{3948}{270156} = \frac{5096}{348712} = \frac{5712}{390864} = \frac{7896}{540312}$	$\triangleright \frac{4368}{107952} = \frac{6027}{148953} = \frac{8463}{209157} = \frac{8736}{215904}$
$\triangleright \frac{3956}{178204} = \frac{7568}{340912} = \frac{7912}{356408} = \frac{8256}{371904}$	$\triangleright \frac{4382}{175906} = \frac{5908}{237164} = \frac{7091}{284653} = \frac{7546}{302918}$
$\triangleright \frac{3975}{180624} = \frac{7150}{324896} = \frac{7950}{361248} = \frac{9075}{412368}$	$\triangleright \frac{4508}{167923} = \frac{5476}{203981} = \frac{9612}{358047} = \frac{9740}{362815}$
$\triangleright \frac{3978}{125460} = \frac{5382}{169740} = \frac{7514}{236980} = \frac{8541}{269370}$	$\triangleright \frac{4510}{283679} = \frac{5980}{376142} = \frac{8970}{564213} = \frac{9120}{573648}$
$\triangleright \frac{4016}{287395} = \frac{6752}{483190} = \frac{7264}{519830} = \frac{9184}{657230}$	$\triangleright \frac{4521}{369078} = \frac{8074}{659132} = \frac{9042}{738156} = \frac{9328}{761504}$
$\triangleright \frac{4017}{253689} = \frac{7293}{460581} = \frac{8307}{524619} = \frac{8931}{564027}$	$\triangleright \frac{4528}{176309} = \frac{7456}{290318} = \frac{7968}{310254} = \frac{9184}{357602}$
$\triangleright \frac{4028}{157396} = \frac{4876}{190532} = \frac{8056}{314792} = \frac{9752}{381064}$	$\triangleright \frac{4529}{187630} = \frac{4536}{187920} = \frac{6594}{273180} = \frac{7154}{296380}$
$\triangleright \frac{4031}{278695} = \frac{4582}{316790} = \frac{5278}{364910} = \frac{8932}{617540}$	$\triangleright \frac{4572}{310896} = \frac{5409}{367812} = \frac{7251}{493068} = \frac{8934}{607512}$
$\triangleright \frac{4087}{256139} = \frac{4891}{306527} = \frac{4958}{310726} = \frac{9782}{613054}$	$\triangleright \frac{4572}{380619} = \frac{7128}{593406} = \frac{7812}{650349} = \frac{9180}{764235}$
$\triangleright \frac{4095}{173862} = \frac{4235}{179806} = \frac{6405}{271938} = \frac{8470}{359612}$	$\triangleright \frac{4576}{103928} = \frac{6708}{152349} = \frac{8476}{192503} = \frac{9568}{217304}$
$\triangleright \frac{4095}{182637} = \frac{4905}{218763} = \frac{8190}{365274} = \frac{9810}{437526}$	$\triangleright \frac{4576}{183920} = \frac{7046}{283195} = \frac{9152}{367840} = \frac{9516}{382470}$
$\triangleright \frac{4170}{328596} = \frac{6015}{473982} = \frac{8190}{645372} = \frac{8340}{657192}$	$\triangleright \frac{4716}{259380} = \frac{7803}{429165} = \frac{9432}{518760} = \frac{9486}{521730}$
$\triangleright \frac{4185}{206739} = \frac{6285}{310479} = \frac{7180}{354692} = \frac{7480}{369512}$	$\triangleright \frac{4738}{690512} = \frac{5704}{831296} = \frac{6371}{928504} = \frac{6417}{935208}$
$\triangleright \frac{4256}{198037} = \frac{8512}{396074} = \frac{8672}{403519} = \frac{9056}{421387}$	$\triangleright \frac{4756}{192038} = \frac{5986}{241703} = \frac{6970}{281435} = \frac{9512}{384076}$

▶ $\frac{4760}{139825} = \frac{6752}{198340} = \frac{7384}{216905} = \frac{9640}{283175}$	▶ $\frac{5421}{703896} = \frac{6123}{795048} = \frac{6279}{815304} = \frac{7215}{936840}$
▶ $\frac{4829}{370516} = \frac{6138}{470952} = \frac{7931}{608524} = \frac{9658}{741032}$	▶ $\frac{5472}{103968} = \frac{5697}{108243} = \frac{7398}{140562} = \frac{9603}{182457}$
▶ $\frac{4851}{230769} = \frac{5481}{260739} = \frac{9072}{431568} = \frac{9702}{461538}$	▶ $\frac{5497}{138620} = \frac{6279}{158340} = \frac{6923}{174580} = \frac{8579}{216340}$
▶ $\frac{4876}{130592} = \frac{6509}{174328} = \frac{7406}{198352} = \frac{9637}{258104}$	▶ $\frac{5687}{349210} = \frac{6897}{423510} = \frac{8349}{512670} = \frac{8712}{534960}$
▶ $\frac{4896}{175032} = \frac{5328}{190476} = \frac{7104}{253968} = \frac{8592}{307164}$	▶ $\frac{5740}{216398} = \frac{6830}{257491} = \frac{7590}{286143} = \frac{8610}{324597}$
▶ $\frac{4902}{157638} = \frac{5092}{163748} = \frac{6479}{208351} = \frac{9804}{315276}$	▶ $\frac{5760}{384192} = \frac{6570}{438219} = \frac{8190}{546273} = \frac{9810}{654327}$
▶ $\frac{4905}{168732} = \frac{5430}{186792} = \frac{9240}{317856} = \frac{9540}{328176}$	▶ $\frac{5786}{230914} = \frac{7106}{283594} = \frac{9284}{370516} = \frac{9526}{380174}$
▶ $\frac{4932}{567180} = \frac{4968}{571320} = \frac{6129}{704835} = \frac{8127}{934605}$	▶ $\frac{5786}{301924} = \frac{7502}{391468} = \frac{8195}{427630} = \frac{9713}{506842}$
▶ $\frac{4972}{153680} = \frac{5478}{169320} = \frac{5973}{184620} = \frac{9174}{283560}$	▶ $\frac{5860}{379142} = \frac{6140}{397258} = \frac{7560}{489132} = \frac{9540}{617238}$
▶ $\frac{5028}{436179} = \frac{6204}{538197} = \frac{6308}{547219} = \frac{8692}{754031}$	▶ $\frac{5896}{401732} = \frac{6930}{472185} = \frac{8712}{593604} = \frac{9174}{625083}$
▶ $\frac{5031}{268749} = \frac{7869}{420351} = \frac{9804}{523716} = \frac{9847}{526013}$	▶ $\frac{5943}{108672} = \frac{7084}{129536} = \frac{9037}{165248} = \frac{9506}{173824}$
▶ $\frac{5096}{174832} = \frac{6357}{218094} = \frac{7098}{243516} = \frac{9204}{315768}$	▶ $\frac{5962}{140378} = \frac{6358}{149702} = \frac{8679}{204351} = \frac{8943}{210567}$
▶ $\frac{5192}{678304} = \frac{5369}{701428} = \frac{5428}{709136} = \frac{5841}{763092}$	▶ $\frac{5967}{143208} = \frac{6408}{153792} = \frac{7596}{182304} = \frac{8235}{197640}$
▶ $\frac{5196}{470238} = \frac{6402}{579381} = \frac{8430}{762915} = \frac{8502}{769431}$	▶ $\frac{5983}{461270} = \frac{6293}{485170} = \frac{6789}{523410} = \frac{9548}{736120}$
▶ $\frac{5260}{378194} = \frac{6590}{473821} = \frac{7360}{529184} = \frac{8270}{594613}$	▶ $\frac{6058}{237194} = \frac{6357}{248901} = \frac{7163}{280459} = \frac{8697}{340521}$
▶ $\frac{5310}{478962} = \frac{8310}{749562} = \frac{9270}{836154} = \frac{9570}{863214}$	▶ $\frac{6184}{279053} = \frac{6584}{297103} = \frac{7024}{316958} = \frac{9720}{438615}$
▶ $\frac{5346}{102789} = \frac{7326}{140859} = \frac{9504}{182736} = \frac{9702}{186543}$	▶ $\frac{6201}{374985} = \frac{6254}{378190} = \frac{7261}{439085} = \frac{8162}{493570}$
▶ $\frac{5368}{109472} = \frac{6893}{140572} = \frac{7259}{148036} = \frac{8235}{167940}$	▶ $\frac{6289}{354170} = \frac{7581}{426930} = \frac{8132}{457960} = \frac{8512}{479360}$
▶ $\frac{5418}{297603} = \frac{7014}{385269} = \frac{8610}{472935} = \frac{9478}{520613}$	▶ $\frac{6384}{105792} = \frac{6489}{107532} = \frac{6573}{108924} = \frac{8295}{137460}$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{6475}{398120} = \frac{7910}{486352} = \frac{9170}{563824} = \frac{9835}{604712} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{6480}{159732} = \frac{7840}{193256} = \frac{8760}{215934} = \frac{9580}{236147} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{6570}{139284} = \frac{8205}{173946} = \frac{8325}{176490} = \frac{8460}{179352} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{6794}{138250} = \frac{6923}{140875} = \frac{8342}{169750} = \frac{9073}{184625} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7294}{138065} = \frac{7602}{143895} = \frac{9268}{175430} = \frac{9702}{183645} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7420}{691385} = \frac{8064}{751392} = \frac{9072}{845316} = \frac{9352}{871406} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7462}{150839} = \frac{8092}{163574} = \frac{8456}{170932} = \frac{9254}{187063} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7462}{381095} = \frac{8610}{439725} = \frac{8932}{456170} = \frac{9170}{468325} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7530}{819264} = \frac{8315}{904672} = \frac{8470}{921536} = \frac{8570}{932416} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2593786} = \frac{108}{2693547} = \frac{216}{5387094} = \frac{364}{9078251} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{3987256} = \frac{127}{4869053} = \frac{172}{6594308} = \frac{254}{9738106} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3478692} = \frac{120}{3975648} = \frac{180}{5963472} = \frac{210}{6957384} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2697435} = \frac{176}{4395820} = \frac{216}{5394870} = \frac{352}{8791640} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{3796524} = \frac{143}{5026879} = \frac{216}{7593048} = \frac{239}{8401567} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{109}{3684527} = \frac{129}{4360587} = \frac{136}{4597208} = \frac{218}{7369054} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{124}{3597860} = \frac{127}{3684905} = \frac{234}{6789510} = \frac{254}{7369810} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2467985} = \frac{162}{3075489} = \frac{210}{3986745} = \frac{324}{6150978} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2486975} = \frac{156}{2984370} = \frac{312}{5968740} = \frac{416}{7958320} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2598674} = \frac{260}{5197348} = \frac{380}{7596124} = \frac{420}{8395716} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2894567} = \frac{210}{4675839} = \frac{260}{5789134} = \frac{420}{9351678} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2649780} = \frac{168}{3297504} = \frac{195}{3827460} = \frac{349}{6850172} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2678940} = \frac{317}{6290548} = \frac{348}{6905712} = \frac{429}{8513076} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2806947} = \frac{180}{3742596} = \frac{270}{5613894} = \frac{360}{7485192} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{136}{4708592} = \frac{197}{6820534} = \frac{265}{9174830} = \frac{273}{9451806} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{136}{5794280} = \frac{186}{7924530} = \frac{194}{8265370} = \frac{213}{9074865} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2504976} = \frac{259}{4701368} = \frac{435}{7896120} = \frac{518}{9402736} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2674509} = \frac{170}{3294685} = \frac{276}{5349018} = \frac{304}{5891672} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3576980} = \frac{154}{3879260} = \frac{284}{7153960} = \frac{354}{8917260} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2870956} = \frac{208}{4175936} = \frac{273}{5480916} = \frac{351}{7046892} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2958670} = \frac{168}{3475920} = \frac{286}{5917340} = \frac{318}{6579420} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2968570} = \frac{286}{5937140} = \frac{351}{7286490} = \frac{468}{9715320} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2690835} = \frac{294}{5381670} = \frac{381}{6974205} = \frac{389}{7120645} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2806935} = \frac{196}{3742580} = \frac{294}{5613870} = \frac{392}{7485160} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2869305} = \frac{196}{3825740} = \frac{294}{5738610} = \frac{392}{7651480} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{147}{3592680} = \frac{234}{5718960} = \frac{294}{7185360} = \frac{324}{7918560} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{2093756} = \frac{409}{5786123} = \frac{451}{6380297} = \frac{567}{8021349} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{148}{3609572} = \frac{168}{4097352} = \frac{279}{6804531} = \frac{326}{7950814} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{149}{2368057} = \frac{156}{2479308} = \frac{219}{3480567} = \frac{614}{9758302} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{149}{2673805} = \frac{217}{3894065} = \frac{271}{4863095} = \frac{298}{5347610}$
► $\frac{154}{2379608} = \frac{207}{3198564} = \frac{308}{4759216} = \frac{392}{6057184}$
► $\frac{156}{2347980} = \frac{273}{4108965} = \frac{481}{7239605} = \frac{546}{8217930}$
► $\frac{156}{2478039} = \frac{312}{4956078} = \frac{364}{5782091} = \frac{572}{9086143}$
► $\frac{156}{2493780} = \frac{286}{4571930} = \frac{312}{4987560} = \frac{572}{9143860}$
► $\frac{156}{2739048} = \frac{287}{5039146} = \frac{312}{5478096} = \frac{419}{7356802}$
► $\frac{156}{2849730} = \frac{216}{3945780} = \frac{324}{5918670} = \frac{432}{7891560}$
► $\frac{156}{3924780} = \frac{286}{7195430} = \frac{312}{7849560} = \frac{364}{9157820}$
► $\frac{157}{2048693} = \frac{261}{3405789} = \frac{284}{3705916} = \frac{561}{7320489}$
► $\frac{158}{3429706} = \frac{182}{3950674} = \frac{263}{5708941} = \frac{418}{9073526}$
► $\frac{159}{2743068} = \frac{238}{4105976} = \frac{532}{9178064} = \frac{564}{9730128}$
► $\frac{159}{3764802} = \frac{241}{5706398} = \frac{318}{7529604} = \frac{415}{9826370}$
► $\frac{160}{2379458} = \frac{240}{3569187} = \frac{320}{4758916} = \frac{640}{9517832}$
► $\frac{160}{2394578} = \frac{240}{3591867} = \frac{320}{4789156} = \frac{640}{9578312}$
► $\frac{162}{3497580} = \frac{184}{3972560} = \frac{213}{4598670} = \frac{368}{7945120}$
► $\frac{162}{4583790} = \frac{254}{7186930} = \frac{297}{8403615} = \frac{324}{9167580}$
► $\frac{164}{3728950} = \frac{348}{7912650} = \frac{412}{9367850} = \frac{428}{9731650}$
► $\frac{167}{2583490} = \frac{321}{4965870} = \frac{386}{5971420} = \frac{541}{8369270}$
► $\frac{168}{3507294} = \frac{216}{4509378} = \frac{348}{7265109} = \frac{432}{9018756}$

► $\frac{170}{3285964} = \frac{180}{3479256} = \frac{190}{3672548} = \frac{340}{6571928}$
► $\frac{172}{3459608} = \frac{207}{4163598} = \frac{368}{7401952} = \frac{483}{9715062}$
► $\frac{173}{2684095} = \frac{256}{3971840} = \frac{512}{7943680} = \frac{562}{8719430}$
► $\frac{173}{6420895} = \frac{182}{6754930} = \frac{183}{6792045} = \frac{236}{8759140}$
► $\frac{174}{2093568} = \frac{379}{4560128} = \frac{418}{5029376} = \frac{783}{9421056}$
► $\frac{176}{2053984} = \frac{352}{4107968} = \frac{462}{5391708} = \frac{704}{8215936}$
► $\frac{176}{2395804} = \frac{308}{4192657} = \frac{352}{4791608} = \frac{704}{9583216}$
► $\frac{176}{3829540} = \frac{248}{5396170} = \frac{364}{7920185} = \frac{420}{9138675}$
► $\frac{179}{2053846} = \frac{357}{4096218} = \frac{358}{4107692} = \frac{367}{4210958}$
► $\frac{179}{2540368} = \frac{187}{2653904} = \frac{416}{5903872} = \frac{513}{7280496}$
► $\frac{179}{2580643} = \frac{496}{7150832} = \frac{573}{8260941} = \frac{576}{8304192}$
► $\frac{180}{2745639} = \frac{360}{5491278} = \frac{520}{7931846} = \frac{540}{8236917}$
► $\frac{180}{3276594} = \frac{190}{3458627} = \frac{230}{4186759} = \frac{380}{6917254}$
► $\frac{182}{3675490} = \frac{356}{7189420} = \frac{407}{8219365} = \frac{478}{9653210}$
► $\frac{182}{6394570} = \frac{183}{6429705} = \frac{218}{7659430} = \frac{267}{9381045}$
► $\frac{184}{3056792} = \frac{316}{5249708} = \frac{571}{9486023} = \frac{578}{9602314}$
► $\frac{186}{2409537} = \frac{392}{5078164} = \frac{416}{5389072} = \frac{738}{9560421}$
► $\frac{187}{2350964} = \frac{278}{3495016} = \frac{408}{5129376} = \frac{582}{7316904}$
► $\frac{187}{2539460} = \frac{379}{5146820} = \frac{683}{9275140} = \frac{713}{9682540}$

▶ $\frac{187}{3549260} = \frac{251}{4763980} = \frac{261}{4953780} = \frac{354}{6718920}$

▶ $\frac{189}{3026457} = \frac{219}{3506847} = \frac{378}{6052914} = \frac{456}{7301928}$

▶ $\frac{192}{3840576} = \frac{219}{4380657} = \frac{273}{5460819} = \frac{327}{6540981}$

▶ $\frac{192}{5760384} = \frac{219}{6570438} = \frac{273}{8190546} = \frac{327}{9810654}$

▶ $\frac{192}{5763840} = \frac{219}{6574380} = \frac{273}{8195460} = \frac{327}{9816540}$

▶ $\frac{194}{2063578} = \frac{381}{4052697} = \frac{582}{6190734} = \frac{762}{8105394}$

▶ $\frac{196}{2407538} = \frac{392}{4815076} = \frac{602}{7394581} = \frac{784}{9630152}$

▶ $\frac{196}{3504872} = \frac{208}{3719456} = \frac{306}{5471892} = \frac{524}{9370168}$

▶ $\frac{196}{4230758} = \frac{218}{4705639} = \frac{236}{5094178} = \frac{430}{9281765}$

▶ $\frac{196}{5048372} = \frac{219}{5640783} = \frac{293}{7546801} = \frac{372}{9581604}$

▶ $\frac{197}{2650438} = \frac{309}{4157286} = \frac{368}{4951072} = \frac{703}{9458162}$

▶ $\frac{198}{5032764} = \frac{309}{7854162} = \frac{345}{8769210} = \frac{384}{9760512}$

▶ $\frac{204}{1385976} = \frac{365}{2479810} = \frac{607}{4123958} = \frac{695}{4721830}$

▶ $\frac{204}{1395768} = \frac{249}{1703658} = \frac{408}{2791536} = \frac{867}{5932014}$

▶ $\frac{206}{1478359} = \frac{426}{3057189} = \frac{736}{5281904} = \frac{934}{6702851}$

▶ $\frac{207}{3561849} = \frac{354}{6091278} = \frac{476}{8190532} = \frac{502}{8637914}$

▶ $\frac{209}{1436875} = \frac{718}{4936250} = \frac{879}{6043125} = \frac{914}{6283750}$

▶ $\frac{214}{3065978} = \frac{398}{5702146} = \frac{567}{8123409} = \frac{609}{8725143}$

▶ $\frac{216}{3475980} = \frac{372}{5986410} = \frac{384}{6179520} = \frac{468}{7531290}$

▶ $\frac{230}{1576489} = \frac{460}{3152978} = \frac{670}{4592381} = \frac{870}{5963241}$

▶ $\frac{231}{4096785} = \frac{354}{6278190} = \frac{429}{7608315} = \frac{462}{8193570}$

▶ $\frac{231}{4850769} = \frac{261}{5480739} = \frac{432}{9071568} = \frac{462}{9701538}$

▶ $\frac{234}{1059786} = \frac{348}{1576092} = \frac{762}{3451098} = \frac{897}{4062513}$

▶ $\frac{234}{1659780} = \frac{351}{2489670} = \frac{637}{4518290} = \frac{793}{5624810}$

▶ $\frac{234}{1798056} = \frac{351}{2697084} = \frac{702}{5394168} = \frac{945}{7261380}$

▶ $\frac{235}{1786940} = \frac{376}{2859104} = \frac{568}{4319072} = \frac{962}{7315048}$

▶ $\frac{236}{1798054} = \frac{354}{2697081} = \frac{472}{3596108} = \frac{708}{5394162}$

▶ $\frac{236}{1975084} = \frac{472}{3950168} = \frac{587}{4912603} = \frac{906}{7582314}$

▶ $\frac{236}{1978054} = \frac{354}{2967081} = \frac{472}{3956108} = \frac{708}{5934162}$

▶ $\frac{236}{1985704} = \frac{512}{4307968} = \frac{732}{6159048} = \frac{735}{6184290}$

▶ $\frac{237}{1059864} = \frac{349}{1560728} = \frac{657}{2938104} = \frac{841}{3760952}$

▶ $\frac{238}{1054697} = \frac{486}{2153709} = \frac{630}{2791845} = \frac{634}{2809571}$

▶ $\frac{240}{1835976} = \frac{480}{3671952} = \frac{690}{5278431} = \frac{760}{5813924}$

▶ $\frac{243}{1589706} = \frac{302}{1975684} = \frac{504}{3297168} = \frac{529}{3460718}$

▶ $\frac{243}{1965870} = \frac{341}{2758690} = \frac{642}{5193780} = \frac{671}{5428390}$

▶ $\frac{245}{1378069} = \frac{280}{1574936} = \frac{490}{2756138} = \frac{560}{3149872}$

▶ $\frac{245}{1607893} = \frac{490}{3215786} = \frac{945}{6201873} = \frac{980}{6431572}$

▶ $\frac{245}{1796830} = \frac{653}{4789102} = \frac{724}{5309816} = \frac{845}{6197230}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1573908} = \frac{472}{3019856} = \frac{671}{4293058} = \frac{709}{4536182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1578039} = \frac{492}{3156078} = \frac{574}{3682091} = \frac{902}{5786143}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1753980} = \frac{378}{2695140} = \frac{738}{5261940} = \frac{957}{6823410}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1795308} = \frac{419}{3057862} = \frac{504}{3678192} = \frac{509}{3714682}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{3510789} = \frac{438}{6250917} = \frac{504}{7192836} = \frac{534}{7620981}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{3758019} = \frac{256}{3910784} = \frac{492}{7516038} = \frac{642}{9807513}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{1089365} = \frac{598}{2637410} = \frac{637}{2809415} = \frac{741}{3268095}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{1386905} = \frac{352}{1976480} = \frac{516}{2897340} = \frac{584}{3279160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{249}{1685730} = \frac{357}{2416890} = \frac{792}{5361840} = \frac{951}{6438270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1708946} = \frac{506}{3417892} = \frac{561}{3789402} = \frac{715}{4829630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{1039876} = \frac{367}{1502498} = \frac{384}{1572096} = \frac{804}{3291576}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{1837690} = \frac{586}{4239710} = \frac{681}{4927035} = \frac{942}{6815370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1387904} = \frac{284}{1539706} = \frac{568}{3079412} = \frac{710}{3849265}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1743980} = \frac{384}{2615970} = \frac{512}{3487960} = \frac{768}{5231940}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1974380} = \frac{384}{2961570} = \frac{512}{3948760} = \frac{768}{5923140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{257}{1963480} = \frac{356}{2719840} = \frac{478}{3651920} = \frac{712}{5439680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{257}{4183960} = \frac{297}{4835160} = \frac{349}{5681720} = \frac{514}{8367920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1673904} = \frac{507}{3289416} = \frac{604}{3918752} = \frac{715}{4638920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{259}{1374086} = \frac{296}{1570384} = \frac{592}{3140768} = \frac{962}{5103748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{260}{1584973} = \frac{360}{2194578} = \frac{540}{3291867} = \frac{720}{4389156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{263}{4085179} = \frac{419}{6508327} = \frac{581}{9024673} = \frac{607}{9428531}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{264}{3579180} = \frac{362}{4907815} = \frac{642}{8703915} = \frac{724}{9815630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{267}{3981504} = \frac{315}{4697280} = \frac{541}{8067392} = \frac{543}{8097216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{267}{4851390} = \frac{423}{7685910} = \frac{469}{8521730} = \frac{531}{9648270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{268}{1395074} = \frac{536}{2790148} = \frac{596}{3102478} = \frac{786}{4091523}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{268}{1793054} = \frac{430}{2876915} = \frac{436}{2917058} = \frac{804}{5379162}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{270}{3941865} = \frac{396}{5781402} = \frac{576}{8409312} = \frac{594}{8672103}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1058694} = \frac{615}{2384970} = \frac{807}{3129546} = \frac{845}{3276910}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1584960} = \frac{378}{2194560} = \frac{567}{3291840} = \frac{756}{4389120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{1365890} = \frac{287}{1430695} = \frac{574}{2861390} = \frac{918}{4576230}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{3819560} = \frac{519}{7234860} = \frac{548}{7639120} = \frac{678}{9451320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{278}{4031695} = \frac{316}{4582790} = \frac{364}{5278910} = \frac{516}{7483290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{279}{1608435} = \frac{723}{4168095} = \frac{726}{4185390} = \frac{786}{4531290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{281}{4703659} = \frac{459}{7683201} = \frac{536}{8972104} = \frac{562}{9407318}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{283}{1749506} = \frac{297}{1836054} = \frac{435}{2689170} = \frac{594}{3672108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{284}{3569170} = \frac{472}{5931860} = \frac{476}{5982130} = \frac{718}{9023465}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1306947} = \frac{380}{1742596} = \frac{570}{2613894} = \frac{760}{3485192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1739640} = \frac{459}{2801736} = \frac{621}{3790584} = \frac{918}{5603472}$$

▶ $\frac{285}{1930647} = \frac{380}{2574196} = \frac{570}{3861294} = \frac{760}{5148392}$
▶ $\frac{285}{3146970} = \frac{287}{3169054} = \frac{371}{4096582} = \frac{571}{6304982}$
▶ $\frac{285}{4367910} = \frac{315}{4827690} = \frac{539}{8260714} = \frac{603}{9241578}$
▶ $\frac{287}{1360954} = \frac{309}{1465278} = \frac{509}{2413678} = \frac{652}{3091784}$
▶ $\frac{290}{3618475} = \frac{368}{4591720} = \frac{746}{9308215} = \frac{764}{9532810}$
▶ $\frac{293}{1407865} = \frac{516}{2479380} = \frac{603}{2897415} = \frac{758}{3642190}$
▶ $\frac{293}{1845607} = \frac{506}{3187294} = \frac{824}{5190376} = \frac{957}{6028143}$
▶ $\frac{294}{1376508} = \frac{396}{1854072} = \frac{615}{2879430} = \frac{651}{3047982}$
▶ $\frac{294}{1587306} = \frac{506}{2731894} = \frac{576}{3109824} = \frac{596}{3217804}$
▶ $\frac{294}{1680357} = \frac{378}{2160459} = \frac{756}{4320918} = \frac{906}{5178243}$
▶ $\frac{295}{3617408} = \frac{380}{4659712} = \frac{590}{7234816} = \frac{735}{9012864}$
▶ $\frac{297}{1538460} = \frac{357}{1849260} = \frac{573}{2968140} = \frac{714}{3698520}$
▶ $\frac{297}{1806354} = \frac{324}{1970568} = \frac{594}{3612708} = \frac{927}{5638014}$
▶ $\frac{297}{3618054} = \frac{504}{6139728} = \frac{594}{7236108} = \frac{651}{7930482}$
▶ $\frac{298}{1574036} = \frac{596}{3148072} = \frac{681}{3597042} = \frac{798}{4215036}$
▶ $\frac{301}{2586794} = \frac{617}{5302498} = \frac{793}{6815042} = \frac{845}{7261930}$
▶ $\frac{301}{2849567} = \frac{418}{3957206} = \frac{421}{3985607} = \frac{612}{5793804}$
▶ $\frac{301}{4269857} = \frac{567}{8043219} = \frac{602}{8539714} = \frac{651}{9234807}$
▶ $\frac{301}{4569782} = \frac{429}{6513078} = \frac{469}{7120358} = \frac{523}{7940186}$

▶ $\frac{304}{2198756} = \frac{428}{3095617} = \frac{608}{4397512} = \frac{632}{4571098}$
▶ $\frac{305}{2618974} = \frac{510}{4379268} = \frac{610}{5237948} = \frac{805}{6912374}$
▶ $\frac{305}{2746891} = \frac{610}{5493782} = \frac{845}{7610239} = \frac{915}{8240673}$
▶ $\frac{306}{2179485} = \frac{406}{2891735} = \frac{612}{4358970} = \frac{948}{6752130}$
▶ $\frac{308}{1679524} = \frac{576}{3140928} = \frac{647}{3528091} = \frac{827}{4509631}$
▶ $\frac{308}{1694572} = \frac{469}{2580371} = \frac{924}{5083716} = \frac{938}{5160742}$
▶ $\frac{308}{1697542} = \frac{792}{4365108} = \frac{862}{4750913} = \frac{974}{5368201}$
▶ $\frac{308}{4157692} = \frac{417}{5629083} = \frac{421}{5683079} = \frac{471}{6358029}$
▶ $\frac{309}{1478256} = \frac{501}{2396784} = \frac{681}{3257904} = \frac{879}{4205136}$
▶ $\frac{309}{1487526} = \frac{379}{1824506} = \frac{758}{3649012} = \frac{879}{4231506}$
▶ $\frac{309}{1728546} = \frac{354}{1980276} = \frac{504}{2819376} = \frac{618}{3457092}$
▶ $\frac{309}{1865742} = \frac{347}{2095186} = \frac{598}{3610724} = \frac{863}{5210794}$
▶ $\frac{309}{2614758} = \frac{471}{3985602} = \frac{639}{5407218} = \frac{951}{8047362}$
▶ $\frac{309}{6245817} = \frac{397}{8024561} = \frac{421}{8509673} = \frac{427}{8630951}$
▶ $\frac{310}{2849675} = \frac{410}{3768925} = \frac{536}{4927180} = \frac{932}{8567410}$
▶ $\frac{312}{4590768} = \frac{318}{4679052} = \frac{458}{6739012} = \frac{485}{7136290}$
▶ $\frac{312}{4850976} = \frac{315}{4897620} = \frac{327}{5084196} = \frac{504}{7836192}$
▶ $\frac{315}{2648709} = \frac{630}{5297418} = \frac{935}{7862041} = \frac{970}{8156342}$
▶ $\frac{317}{2864095} = \frac{429}{3876015} = \frac{634}{5728190} = \frac{754}{6812390}$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1679584} = \frac{480}{2519376} = \frac{490}{2571863} = \frac{980}{5143726} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{321}{5098764} = \frac{327}{5194068} = \frac{395}{6274180} = \frac{549}{8720316} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{1578690} = \frac{406}{1978235} = \frac{810}{3946725} = \frac{812}{3956470} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{1098457} = \frac{576}{1940832} = \frac{870}{2931465} = \frac{970}{3268415} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{5048176} = \frac{489}{7503216} = \frac{539}{8270416} = \frac{613}{9405872} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2197658} = \frac{510}{3296487} = \frac{610}{3942857} = \frac{870}{5623419} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{341}{2709586} = \frac{351}{2789046} = \frac{513}{4076298} = \frac{643}{5109278} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1705896} = \frac{369}{1840572} = \frac{435}{2169780} = \frac{621}{3097548} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{5016798} = \frac{389}{5706241} = \frac{413}{6058297} = \frac{498}{7305162} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{1295078} = \frac{389}{1456027} = \frac{528}{1976304} = \frac{827}{3095461} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{5109728} = \frac{384}{5670912} = \frac{549}{8107632} = \frac{613}{9052784} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{2619850} = \frac{379}{2861450} = \frac{893}{6742150} = \frac{983}{7421650} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{347}{6158209} = \frac{423}{7506981} = \frac{503}{8926741} = \frac{528}{9370416} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{2715096} = \frac{354}{2761908} = \frac{506}{3947812} = \frac{615}{4798230} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{2940678} = \frac{641}{5370298} = \frac{708}{5931624} = \frac{804}{6735912} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{1849760} = \frac{372}{1954860} = \frac{618}{3247590} = \frac{803}{4219765} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{1978064} = \frac{610}{3427895} = \frac{704}{3956128} = \frac{806}{4529317} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{356}{1072984} = \frac{648}{1953072} = \frac{836}{2519704} = \frac{934}{2815076} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{356}{1492708} = \frac{491}{2058763} = \frac{591}{2478063} = \frac{892}{3740156} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{356}{1749028} = \frac{439}{2156807} = \frac{539}{2648107} = \frac{712}{3498056} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{4196280} = \frac{693}{8145720} = \frac{714}{8392560} = \frac{784}{9215360} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{1046792} = \frac{583}{1704692} = \frac{716}{2093584} = \frac{945}{2763180} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{1472096} = \frac{359}{1476208} = \frac{915}{3762480} = \frac{978}{4021536} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{1670249} = \frac{426}{1987503} = \frac{514}{2398067} = \frac{516}{2407398} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{4817062} = \frac{536}{7192048} = \frac{619}{8305742} = \frac{639}{8574102} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1849275} = \frac{384}{1972560} = \frac{672}{3451980} = \frac{768}{3945120} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{361}{2049758} = \frac{659}{3741802} = \frac{761}{4320958} = \frac{894}{5076132} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{361}{4259078} = \frac{579}{6831042} = \frac{785}{9261430} = \frac{814}{9603572} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1509872} = \frac{749}{3106852} = \frac{895}{3712460} = \frac{972}{4031856} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1527890} = \frac{402}{1687395} = \frac{428}{1796530} = \frac{902}{3786145} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1059472} = \frac{592}{1704368} = \frac{859}{2473061} = \frac{879}{2530641} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{4570192} = \frac{542}{6731098} = \frac{679}{8432501} = \frac{758}{9413602} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{369}{1208475} = \frac{603}{1974825} = \frac{738}{2416950} = \frac{798}{2613450} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{369}{2015478} = \frac{534}{2916708} = \frac{587}{3206194} = \frac{597}{3260814} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{369}{2147580} = \frac{459}{2671380} = \frac{738}{4295160} = \frac{918}{5342760} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{369}{4512870} = \frac{621}{7594830} = \frac{697}{8524310} = \frac{746}{9123580} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1098625} = \frac{476}{1398250} = \frac{890}{2614375} = \frac{964}{2831750} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1052894} = \frac{384}{1075296} = \frac{856}{2397014} = \frac{876}{2453019} \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{376}{1928504} = \frac{567}{2908143} = \frac{598}{3067142} = \frac{908}{4657132}$	▶ $\frac{419}{5603287} = \frac{459}{6138207} = \frac{526}{7034198} = \frac{641}{8572093}$
▶ $\frac{376}{2195840} = \frac{752}{4391680} = \frac{921}{5378640} = \frac{927}{5413680}$	▶ $\frac{423}{1075689} = \frac{432}{1098576} = \frac{768}{1953024} = \frac{813}{2067459}$
▶ $\frac{378}{2540916} = \frac{415}{2789630} = \frac{564}{3791208} = \frac{806}{5417932}$	▶ $\frac{426}{1709538} = \frac{607}{2435891} = \frac{809}{3246517} = \frac{852}{3419076}$
▶ $\frac{380}{4692715} = \frac{492}{6075831} = \frac{508}{6273419} = \frac{780}{9632415}$	▶ $\frac{426}{3158790} = \frac{512}{3796480} = \frac{612}{4537980} = \frac{829}{6147035}$
▶ $\frac{384}{1920576} = \frac{438}{2190657} = \frac{546}{2730819} = \frac{654}{3270981}$	▶ $\frac{429}{3760185} = \frac{452}{3961780} = \frac{709}{6214385} = \frac{732}{6415980}$
▶ $\frac{384}{5760192} = \frac{438}{6570219} = \frac{546}{8190273} = \frac{654}{9810327}$	▶ $\frac{429}{3857061} = \frac{759}{6824031} = \frac{924}{8307516} = \frac{957}{8604213}$
▶ $\frac{385}{1297604} = \frac{645}{2173908} = \frac{715}{2409836} = \frac{975}{3286140}$	▶ $\frac{430}{1785962} = \frac{435}{1806729} = \frac{785}{3260419} = \frac{860}{3571924}$
▶ $\frac{387}{5294160} = \frac{396}{5417280} = \frac{639}{8741520} = \frac{684}{9357120}$	▶ $\frac{432}{1079865} = \frac{576}{1439820} = \frac{816}{2039745} = \frac{864}{2159730}$
▶ $\frac{390}{1756248} = \frac{405}{1823796} = \frac{780}{3512496} = \frac{810}{3647592}$	▶ $\frac{432}{1508976} = \frac{459}{1603287} = \frac{864}{3017952} = \frac{918}{3206574}$
▶ $\frac{392}{1675408} = \frac{607}{2594318} = \frac{798}{3410652} = \frac{973}{4158602}$	▶ $\frac{432}{1750896} = \frac{459}{1860327} = \frac{864}{3501792} = \frac{918}{3720654}$
▶ $\frac{396}{1457280} = \frac{432}{1589760} = \frac{536}{1972480} = \frac{864}{3179520}$	▶ $\frac{435}{1762098} = \frac{780}{3159624} = \frac{870}{3524196} = \frac{915}{3706482}$
▶ $\frac{406}{1789532} = \frac{791}{3486502} = \frac{812}{3579064} = \frac{861}{3795042}$	▶ $\frac{435}{2986710} = \frac{571}{3920486} = \frac{721}{4950386} = \frac{879}{6035214}$
▶ $\frac{407}{1396528} = \frac{594}{2038176} = \frac{814}{2793056} = \frac{891}{3057264}$	▶ $\frac{437}{2980156} = \frac{456}{3109728} = \frac{589}{4016732} = \frac{874}{5960312}$
▶ $\frac{408}{2359176} = \frac{493}{2850671} = \frac{867}{5013249} = \frac{986}{5701342}$	▶ $\frac{451}{2836790} = \frac{598}{3761420} = \frac{897}{5642130} = \frac{912}{5736480}$
▶ $\frac{408}{2953716} = \frac{498}{3605271} = \frac{602}{4358179} = \frac{816}{5907432}$	▶ $\frac{457}{1068923} = \frac{463}{1082957} = \frac{834}{1950726} = \frac{984}{2301576}$
▶ $\frac{409}{3275681} = \frac{638}{5109742} = \frac{738}{5910642} = \frac{823}{6591407}$	▶ $\frac{459}{1603827} = \frac{578}{2019634} = \frac{867}{3029451} = \frac{918}{3207654}$
▶ $\frac{410}{2938675} = \frac{596}{4271830} = \frac{748}{5361290} = \frac{784}{5619320}$	▶ $\frac{459}{2716038} = \frac{578}{3420196} = \frac{867}{5130294} = \frac{918}{5432076}$
▶ $\frac{412}{3095768} = \frac{835}{6274190} = \frac{903}{6785142} = \frac{953}{7160842}$	▶ $\frac{460}{2589317} = \frac{580}{3264791} = \frac{820}{4615739} = \frac{920}{5178634}$
▶ $\frac{417}{3685029} = \frac{602}{5319874} = \frac{782}{6910534} = \frac{849}{7502613}$	▶ $\frac{465}{1209837} = \frac{705}{1834269} = \frac{795}{2068431} = \frac{915}{2380647}$

$$\begin{aligned}&\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{2107938} = \frac{480}{2175936} = \frac{930}{4215876} = \frac{960}{4351872} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{2937051} = \frac{504}{3162978} = \frac{612}{3840759} = \frac{936}{5874102} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{3709251} = \frac{732}{5801649} = \frac{812}{6435709} = \frac{936}{7418502} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{470}{1562938} = \frac{785}{2610439} = \frac{810}{2693574} = \frac{940}{3125876} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{3560289} = \frac{502}{3794618} = \frac{578}{4369102} = \frac{851}{6432709} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{6235098} = \frac{509}{6738142} = \frac{603}{7982514} = \frac{745}{9862310} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{476}{3925810} = \frac{628}{5179430} = \frac{862}{7109345} = \frac{946}{7802135} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{478}{6301952} = \frac{549}{7238016} = \frac{601}{7923584} = \frac{704}{9281536} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{479}{3150862} = \frac{482}{3170596} = \frac{732}{4815096} = \frac{958}{6301724} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{1592736} = \frac{485}{1609327} = \frac{960}{3185472} = \frac{970}{3218654} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{3617952} = \frac{570}{4296318} = \frac{580}{4371692} = \frac{905}{6821347} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{487}{3519062} = \frac{623}{4501798} = \frac{817}{5903642} = \frac{859}{6207134} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{490}{2815736} = \frac{560}{3217984} = \frac{830}{4769512} = \frac{980}{5631472} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{498}{2301756} = \frac{672}{3105984} = \frac{906}{4187532} = \frac{978}{4520316} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{506}{4382719} = \frac{532}{4607918} = \frac{682}{5907143} = \frac{954}{8263071} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{508}{1439672} = \frac{645}{1827930} = \frac{945}{2678130} = \frac{965}{2734810} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{509}{4681273} = \frac{832}{7651904} = \frac{931}{8562407} = \frac{932}{8571604} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{3697408} = \frac{572}{4130698} = \frac{802}{5791643} = \frac{890}{6427135} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{514}{2978630} = \frac{601}{3482795} = \frac{758}{4392610} = \frac{782}{4531690}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}&\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{4392708} = \frac{571}{4860923} = \frac{753}{6410289} = \frac{952}{8104376} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{3298460} = \frac{571}{3642980} = \frac{842}{5371960} = \frac{983}{6271540} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{6304298} = \frac{601}{7328594} = \frac{608}{7413952} = \frac{765}{9328410} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{2409736} = \frac{806}{3749512} = \frac{918}{4270536} = \frac{928}{4317056} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{524}{1378906} = \frac{562}{1478903} = \frac{876}{2305194} = \frac{974}{2563081} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{524}{3710968} = \frac{761}{5389402} = \frac{794}{5623108} = \frac{843}{5970126} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{526}{3781940} = \frac{659}{4738210} = \frac{736}{5291840} = \frac{827}{5946130} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{529}{4817603} = \frac{714}{6502398} = \frac{823}{7495061} = \frac{923}{8405761} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{531}{4789620} = \frac{831}{7495620} = \frac{927}{8361540} = \frac{957}{8632140} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{532}{1064798} = \frac{652}{1304978} = \frac{726}{1453089} = \frac{732}{1465098} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{532}{1478960} = \frac{537}{1492860} = \frac{589}{1637420} = \frac{951}{2643780} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{1297086} = \frac{578}{1403962} = \frac{638}{1549702} = \frac{867}{2105943} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{548}{1390276} = \frac{758}{1923046} = \frac{961}{2438057} = \frac{973}{2468501} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{560}{4378192} = \frac{590}{4612738} = \frac{670}{5238194} = \frac{760}{5941832} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{574}{2163980} = \frac{683}{2574910} = \frac{759}{2861430} = \frac{861}{3245970} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{1098432} = \frac{789}{1504623} = \frac{809}{1542763} = \frac{972}{1853604} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{1920384} = \frac{657}{2190438} = \frac{819}{2730546} = \frac{981}{3270654} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{1923840} = \frac{657}{2194380} = \frac{819}{2735460} = \frac{981}{3276540} \\&\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{3840192} = \frac{657}{4380219} = \frac{819}{5460273} = \frac{981}{6540327}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{576}{3841920} = \frac{657}{4382190} = \frac{819}{5462730} = \frac{981}{6543270} \\ &\triangleright \frac{586}{3791420} = \frac{614}{3972580} = \frac{756}{4891320} = \frac{954}{6172380} \\ &\triangleright \frac{589}{4213706} = \frac{712}{5093648} = \frac{726}{5193804} = \frac{938}{6710452} \\ &\triangleright \frac{597}{1348026} = \frac{678}{1530924} = \frac{704}{1589632} = \frac{853}{1926074} \\ &\triangleright \frac{598}{1673204} = \frac{653}{1827094} = \frac{753}{2106894} = \frac{785}{2196430} \\ &\triangleright \frac{605}{4372819} = \frac{760}{5493128} = \frac{930}{6721854} = \frac{945}{6830271} \\ &\triangleright \frac{609}{2378145} = \frac{617}{2409385} = \frac{741}{2893605} = \frac{942}{3678510} \\ &\triangleright \frac{632}{7459180} = \frac{690}{8143725} = \frac{784}{9253160} = \frac{814}{9607235} \\ &\triangleright \frac{635}{1249807} = \frac{760}{1495832} = \frac{865}{1702493} = \frac{935}{1840267} \\ &\triangleright \frac{652}{3179804} = \frac{657}{3204189} = \frac{708}{3452916} = \frac{951}{4638027} \\ &\triangleright \frac{659}{1280437} = \frac{674}{1309582} = \frac{763}{1482509} = \frac{964}{1873052} \\ &\triangleright \frac{681}{7942503} = \frac{764}{8910532} = \frac{812}{9470356} = \frac{827}{9645301} \\ &\triangleright \frac{695}{1247803} = \frac{740}{1328596} = \frac{905}{1624837} = \frac{960}{1723584} \\ &\triangleright \frac{736}{1025984} = \frac{753}{1049682} = \frac{895}{1247630} = \frac{907}{1264358} \\ &\triangleright \frac{762}{3150489} = \frac{826}{3415097} = \frac{896}{3704512} = \frac{908}{3754126} \\ &\triangleright \frac{762}{5910834} = \frac{809}{6275413} = \frac{827}{6415039} = \frac{958}{7431206} \\ &\triangleright \frac{796}{4851023} = \frac{892}{5436071} = \frac{924}{5631087} = \frac{936}{5704218} \\ &\triangleright \frac{810}{2437695} = \frac{910}{2738645} = \frac{914}{2750683} = \frac{954}{2871063} \\ &\triangleright \frac{13}{25869740} = \frac{26}{51739480} = \frac{38}{75619240} = \frac{42}{83579160} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{13}{25986740} = \frac{26}{51973480} = \frac{38}{75961240} = \frac{42}{83957160} \\ &\triangleright \frac{13}{28790645} = \frac{19}{42078635} = \frac{34}{75298610} = \frac{37}{81942605} \\ &\triangleright \frac{13}{28945670} = \frac{21}{46758390} = \frac{26}{57891340} = \frac{42}{93516780} \\ &\triangleright \frac{14}{20753698} = \frac{28}{41507396} = \frac{56}{83014792} = \frac{59}{87462013} \\ &\triangleright \frac{14}{26583970} = \frac{19}{36078245} = \frac{28}{53167940} = \frac{38}{72156490} \\ &\triangleright \frac{15}{23984760} = \frac{37}{59162408} = \frac{49}{78350216} = \frac{61}{97538024} \\ &\triangleright \frac{16}{23794580} = \frac{24}{35691870} = \frac{32}{47589160} = \frac{64}{95178320} \\ &\triangleright \frac{16}{23945780} = \frac{24}{35918670} = \frac{32}{47891560} = \frac{64}{95783120} \\ &\triangleright \frac{16}{29583704} = \frac{26}{48073519} = \frac{32}{59167408} = \frac{52}{96147038} \\ &\triangleright \frac{16}{34905728} = \frac{23}{50176984} = \frac{27}{58903416} = \frac{45}{98172360} \\ &\triangleright \frac{17}{28450639} = \frac{27}{45186309} = \frac{34}{56901278} = \frac{54}{90372618} \\ &\triangleright \frac{17}{32859640} = \frac{18}{34792560} = \frac{19}{36725480} = \frac{34}{65719280} \\ &\triangleright \frac{18}{23754096} = \frac{36}{47508192} = \frac{39}{51467208} = \frac{72}{95016384} \\ &\triangleright \frac{18}{23760954} = \frac{36}{47521908} = \frac{39}{51482067} = \frac{72}{95043816} \\ &\triangleright \frac{18}{23794056} = \frac{27}{35691084} = \frac{31}{40978652} = \frac{62}{81957304} \\ &\triangleright \frac{18}{24607539} = \frac{36}{49215078} = \frac{62}{84759301} = \frac{72}{98430156} \\ &\triangleright \frac{18}{27456390} = \frac{36}{54912780} = \frac{52}{79318460} = \frac{54}{82369170} \\ &\triangleright \frac{18}{32765940} = \frac{19}{34586270} = \frac{23}{41867590} = \frac{38}{69172540} \\ &\triangleright \frac{20}{14365798} = \frac{30}{21548697} = \frac{40}{28731596} = \frac{80}{57463192} \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{20}{14365978} = \frac{30}{21548967} = \frac{40}{28731956} = \frac{80}{57463912}$
▶ $\frac{20}{17639458} = \frac{30}{26459187} = \frac{40}{35278916} = \frac{60}{52918374}$
▶ $\frac{20}{17985634} = \frac{30}{26978451} = \frac{40}{35971268} = \frac{80}{71942536}$
▶ $\frac{20}{18379456} = \frac{30}{27569184} = \frac{40}{36758912} = \frac{95}{87302416}$
▶ $\frac{20}{19457638} = \frac{30}{29186457} = \frac{40}{38915276} = \frac{60}{58372914}$
▶ $\frac{20}{19785634} = \frac{30}{29678451} = \frac{40}{39571268} = \frac{80}{79142536}$
▶ $\frac{21}{30789465} = \frac{24}{35187960} = \frac{36}{52781940} = \frac{42}{61578930}$
▶ $\frac{21}{34890765} = \frac{24}{39875160} = \frac{36}{59812740} = \frac{42}{69781530}$
▶ $\frac{23}{14567809} = \frac{41}{25968703} = \frac{82}{51937406} = \frac{98}{62071534}$
▶ $\frac{23}{15764890} = \frac{46}{31529780} = \frac{67}{45923810} = \frac{87}{59632410}$
▶ $\frac{23}{18079564} = \frac{37}{29084516} = \frac{59}{46378012} = \frac{74}{58169032}$
▶ $\frac{23}{18907564} = \frac{63}{51790284} = \frac{84}{69053712} = \frac{89}{73164052}$
▶ $\frac{24}{10375968} = \frac{43}{18590276} = \frac{48}{20751936} = \frac{96}{41503872}$
▶ $\frac{24}{10397568} = \frac{37}{16029584} = \frac{48}{20795136} = \frac{74}{32059168}$
▶ $\frac{24}{13695780} = \frac{26}{14837095} = \frac{48}{27391560} = \frac{96}{54783120}$
▶ $\frac{24}{17539608} = \frac{48}{35079216} = \frac{89}{65042713} = \frac{96}{70158432}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18359760} = \frac{48}{36719520} = \frac{69}{52784310} = \frac{76}{58139240}$
▶ $\frac{24}{19853076} = \frac{46}{38051729} = \frac{48}{39706152} = \frac{92}{76103458}$
▶ $\frac{24}{39857160} = \frac{26}{43178590} = \frac{29}{48160735} = \frac{58}{96321470}$

▶ $\frac{26}{15849730} = \frac{36}{21945780} = \frac{54}{32918670} = \frac{72}{43891560}$
▶ $\frac{26}{19473805} = \frac{52}{38947610} = \frac{84}{62915370} = \frac{98}{73401265}$
▶ $\frac{27}{13694805} = \frac{36}{18259740} = \frac{54}{27389610} = \frac{72}{36519480}$
▶ $\frac{27}{14869305} = \frac{36}{19825740} = \frac{54}{29738610} = \frac{72}{39651480}$
▶ $\frac{27}{14930865} = \frac{32}{17695840} = \frac{54}{29861730} = \frac{72}{39815640}$
▶ $\frac{27}{16038459} = \frac{34}{20196578} = \frac{51}{30294867} = \frac{54}{32076918}$
▶ $\frac{27}{18395640} = \frac{39}{26571480} = \frac{54}{36791280} = \frac{78}{53142960}$
▶ $\frac{27}{19306485} = \frac{36}{25741980} = \frac{54}{38612970} = \frac{72}{51483960}$
▶ $\frac{27}{19364805} = \frac{36}{25819740} = \frac{54}{38729610} = \frac{72}{51639480}$
▶ $\frac{27}{19480635} = \frac{36}{25974180} = \frac{54}{38961270} = \frac{72}{51948360}$
▶ $\frac{27}{19486305} = \frac{36}{25981740} = \frac{54}{38972610} = \frac{72}{51963480}$
▶ $\frac{27}{45916038} = \frac{34}{57820196} = \frac{51}{86730294} = \frac{54}{91832076}$
▶ $\frac{29}{18604573} = \frac{43}{27586091} = \frac{58}{37209146} = \frac{79}{50681423}$
▶ $\frac{30}{19285476} = \frac{40}{25713968} = \frac{75}{48213690} = \frac{80}{51427936}$
▶ $\frac{32}{15679840} = \frac{43}{21069785} = \frac{48}{23519760} = \frac{86}{42139570}$
▶ $\frac{32}{16795840} = \frac{48}{25193760} = \frac{49}{25718630} = \frac{98}{51437260}$
▶ $\frac{34}{19026587} = \frac{36}{20145798} = \frac{54}{30218697} = \frac{92}{51483706}$
▶ $\frac{34}{21976580} = \frac{51}{32964870} = \frac{61}{39428570} = \frac{87}{56234190}$
▶ $\frac{35}{17062948} = \frac{45}{21938076} = \frac{70}{34125896} = \frac{90}{43876152}$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{36}{19054728} = \frac{37}{19584026} = \frac{72}{38109456} = \frac{74}{39168052} \\ &\triangleright \frac{36}{19084752} = \frac{39}{20675148} = \frac{72}{38169504} = \frac{78}{41350296} \\ &\triangleright \frac{36}{19452870} = \frac{48}{25937160} = \frac{90}{48632175} = \frac{96}{51874320} \\ &\triangleright \frac{37}{28196405} = \frac{48}{36579120} = \frac{74}{56392810} = \frac{96}{73158240} \\ &\triangleright \frac{38}{21945760} = \frac{57}{32918640} = \frac{73}{42158960} = \frac{76}{43891520} \\ &\triangleright \frac{39}{42857061} = \frac{69}{75824031} = \frac{84}{92307516} = \frac{87}{95604213} \\ &\triangleright \frac{39}{42860571} = \frac{69}{75830241} = \frac{84}{92315076} = \frac{87}{95612043} \\ &\triangleright \frac{40}{25397168} = \frac{65}{41270398} = \frac{90}{57143628} = \frac{95}{60318274} \\ &\triangleright \frac{43}{18027965} = \frac{46}{19285730} = \frac{58}{24316790} = \frac{92}{38571460} \\ &\triangleright \frac{43}{26850791} = \frac{62}{38715094} = \frac{87}{54326019} = \frac{93}{58072641} \\ &\triangleright \frac{43}{52186907} = \frac{52}{63109748} = \frac{58}{70391642} = \frac{61}{74032589} \\ &\triangleright \frac{48}{25739160} = \frac{74}{39681205} = \frac{82}{43971065} = \frac{96}{51478320} \\ &\triangleright \frac{49}{28157360} = \frac{56}{32179840} = \frac{83}{47695120} = \frac{98}{56314720} \\ &\triangleright \frac{49}{36207815} = \frac{62}{45813970} = \frac{91}{67243085} = \frac{98}{72415630} \\ &\triangleright \frac{56}{43781920} = \frac{59}{46127380} = \frac{67}{52381940} = \frac{76}{59418320} \\ &\triangleright \frac{57}{36098214} = \frac{76}{48130952} = \frac{82}{51930764} = \frac{91}{57630482} \\ &\triangleright \frac{57}{39842601} = \frac{69}{48230517} = \frac{71}{49628503} = \frac{73}{51026489} \\ &\triangleright \frac{58}{26041739} = \frac{70}{31429685} = \frac{78}{35021649} = \frac{92}{41307586} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \frac{2}{107653948} = \frac{4}{215307896} = \frac{5}{269134870} = \frac{8}{430615792} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{136507948} = \frac{4}{273015896} = \frac{5}{341269870} = \frac{8}{546031792} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{136759048} = \frac{4}{273518096} = \frac{5}{341897620} = \frac{8}{547036192} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{143657980} = \frac{3}{215486970} = \frac{4}{287315960} = \frac{8}{574631920} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{143659780} = \frac{3}{215489670} = \frac{4}{287319560} = \frac{8}{574639120} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{147936508} = \frac{4}{295873016} = \frac{5}{369841270} = \frac{8}{591746032} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{150793648} = \frac{4}{301587296} = \frac{5}{376984120} = \frac{8}{603174592} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{154397608} = \frac{4}{308795216} = \frac{7}{540391628} = \frac{8}{617590432} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{176394580} = \frac{3}{264591870} = \frac{4}{352789160} = \frac{6}{529183740} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{179856340} = \frac{3}{269784510} = \frac{4}{359712680} = \frac{8}{719425360} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{183976054} = \frac{3}{275964081} = \frac{4}{367952108} = \frac{8}{735904216} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{186309754} = \frac{4}{372619508} = \frac{7}{652084139} = \frac{8}{745239016} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{190384756} = \frac{4}{380769512} = \frac{8}{761539024} = \frac{9}{856731402} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{194576380} = \frac{3}{291864570} = \frac{4}{389152760} = \frac{6}{583729140} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{197856340} = \frac{3}{296784510} = \frac{4}{395712680} = \frac{8}{791425360} \\ &\triangleright \frac{2}{198376054} = \frac{3}{297564081} = \frac{4}{396752108} = \frac{8}{793504216} \end{aligned}$$

2.24 3 Equivalent Expressions

In this case, there are more than 8000 equivalent expressions. We have divided it in number of digits in numerator.

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{14580}{23976} = \frac{21870}{35964} = \frac{53460}{87912}$ | ▶ $\frac{14703}{59826} = \frac{17052}{69384} = \frac{20967}{85314}$ | ▶ $\frac{14865}{29307} = \frac{29730}{58614} = \frac{39640}{78152}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14586}{23970} = \frac{26598}{43710} = \frac{53196}{87420}$ | ▶ $\frac{14725}{39680} = \frac{19760}{53248} = \frac{30495}{82176}$ | ▶ $\frac{14869}{20753} = \frac{29738}{41506} = \frac{59476}{83012}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14586}{30927} = \frac{17952}{38064} = \frac{35904}{76128}$ | ▶ $\frac{14725}{80693} = \frac{14975}{82063} = \frac{16475}{90283}$ | ▶ $\frac{14896}{50372} = \frac{19304}{65278} = \frac{23408}{79156}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14590}{23678} = \frac{29180}{47356} = \frac{58360}{94712}$ | ▶ $\frac{14728}{36590} = \frac{29456}{73180} = \frac{36820}{91475}$ | ▶ $\frac{14920}{35768} = \frac{16785}{40239} = \frac{29840}{71536}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14590}{36728} = \frac{29180}{73456} = \frac{36475}{91820}$ | ▶ $\frac{14753}{20869} = \frac{29506}{41738} = \frac{59012}{83476}$ | ▶ $\frac{14973}{25806} = \frac{47523}{81906} = \frac{50127}{86394}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14592}{30768} = \frac{17024}{35896} = \frac{46512}{98073}$ | ▶ $\frac{14758}{20369} = \frac{29516}{40738} = \frac{59032}{81476}$ | ▶ $\frac{14985}{37260} = \frac{18537}{46092} = \frac{37185}{92460}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14596}{23780} = \frac{18067}{29435} = \frac{21894}{35670}$ | ▶ $\frac{14759}{20368} = \frac{29518}{40736} = \frac{59036}{81472}$ | ▶ $\frac{14986}{27305} = \frac{29736}{54180} = \frac{41890}{76325}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14607}{28539} = \frac{19476}{38052} = \frac{38952}{76104}$ | ▶ $\frac{14760}{23985} = \frac{29160}{47385} = \frac{45096}{73281}$ | ▶ $\frac{15078}{23946} = \frac{30156}{47892} = \frac{60312}{95784}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14607}{38952} = \frac{20169}{53784} = \frac{28539}{76104}$ | ▶ $\frac{14768}{20359} = \frac{29536}{40718} = \frac{59072}{81436}$ | ▶ $\frac{15078}{24396} = \frac{30156}{48792} = \frac{60312}{97584}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14630}{28975} = \frac{38192}{75640} = \frac{42196}{83570}$ | ▶ $\frac{14768}{39052} = \frac{26980}{71345} = \frac{29536}{78104}$ | ▶ $\frac{15084}{37296} = \frac{30168}{74592} = \frac{35196}{87024}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14678}{23509} = \frac{29356}{47018} = \frac{58712}{94036}$ | ▶ $\frac{14769}{20358} = \frac{29538}{40716} = \frac{59076}{81432}$ | ▶ $\frac{15086}{27493} = \frac{19056}{34728} = \frac{30172}{54986}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14678}{23590} = \frac{29356}{47180} = \frac{58712}{94360}$ | ▶ $\frac{14769}{20853} = \frac{29538}{41706} = \frac{59076}{83412}$ | ▶ $\frac{15087}{24396} = \frac{46389}{75012} = \frac{61053}{98724}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14679}{23085} = \frac{29358}{46170} = \frac{58716}{92340}$ | ▶ $\frac{14790}{28536} = \frac{17085}{32964} = \frac{34170}{65928}$ | ▶ $\frac{15096}{23784} = \frac{25789}{40631} = \frac{30192}{47568}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14679}{23508} = \frac{29358}{47016} = \frac{58716}{94032}$ | ▶ $\frac{14793}{20865} = \frac{29586}{41730} = \frac{59172}{83460}$ | ▶ $\frac{15096}{27438} = \frac{30192}{54876} = \frac{43512}{79086}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14679}{23580} = \frac{29358}{47160} = \frac{58716}{94320}$ | ▶ $\frac{14805}{36792} = \frac{29610}{73584} = \frac{31490}{78256}$ | ▶ $\frac{15096}{42738} = \frac{25308}{71649} = \frac{30192}{85476}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14680}{23579} = \frac{29360}{47158} = \frac{58720}{94316}$ | ▶ $\frac{14835}{20679} = \frac{29670}{41358} = \frac{59340}{82716}$ | ▶ $\frac{15204}{63987} = \frac{15928}{67034} = \frac{23168}{97504}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14685}{23079} = \frac{29370}{46158} = \frac{58740}{92316}$ | ▶ $\frac{14835}{27069} = \frac{29670}{54138} = \frac{39560}{72184}$ | ▶ $\frac{15248}{37906} = \frac{30496}{75812} = \frac{38120}{94765}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14685}{37290} = \frac{27145}{68930} = \frac{27501}{69834}$ | ▶ $\frac{14853}{20769} = \frac{29706}{41538} = \frac{59412}{83076}$ | ▶ $\frac{15264}{37098} = \frac{30528}{74196} = \frac{38160}{92745}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14690}{23578} = \frac{29380}{47156} = \frac{58760}{94312}$ | ▶ $\frac{14865}{20793} = \frac{29730}{41586} = \frac{59460}{83172}$ | ▶ $\frac{15309}{48762} = \frac{18954}{60372} = \frac{30618}{97524}$ |

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17906}{23845} &= \frac{35812}{47690} = \frac{71624}{95380} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17908}{23645} &= \frac{35816}{47290} = \frac{71632}{94580} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17908}{24635} &= \frac{35816}{49270} = \frac{71632}{98540} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17920}{43568} &= \frac{23840}{57961} = \frac{24160}{58739} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17936}{54280} &= \frac{25916}{78430} = \frac{32186}{97405} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17940}{25638} &= \frac{26910}{38457} = \frac{53820}{76914} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17940}{58236} &= \frac{24765}{80391} = \frac{26910}{87354} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17948}{23506} &= \frac{35896}{47012} = \frac{60254}{78913} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17954}{26038} &= \frac{31706}{45982} = \frac{36481}{52907} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17956}{23840} &= \frac{35912}{47680} = \frac{71824}{95360} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17958}{20364} &= \frac{35916}{40728} = \frac{53874}{61092} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17958}{23640} &= \frac{35916}{47280} = \frac{71832}{94560} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17962}{38054} &= \frac{26943}{57081} = \frac{35924}{76108} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17963}{24085} &= \frac{35926}{48170} = \frac{71852}{96340} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17964}{20358} &= \frac{35928}{40716} = \frac{53892}{61074} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17964}{23085} &= \frac{35928}{46170} = \frac{71856}{92340} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17964}{23508} &= \frac{35928}{47016} = \frac{71856}{94032} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17964}{23580} &= \frac{35928}{47160} = \frac{71856}{94320} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17982}{36054} &= \frac{26973}{54081} = \frac{35964}{72108} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17982}{40635} &= \frac{23976}{54180} = \frac{35964}{81270} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17982}{43605} &= \frac{23976}{58140} = \frac{35964}{87210} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17984}{20635} &= \frac{35968}{41270} = \frac{71936}{82540} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17985}{20634} &= \frac{35970}{41268} = \frac{71940}{82536} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17985}{40632} &= \frac{23980}{54176} = \frac{35970}{81264} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{17985}{43062} &= \frac{23980}{57416} = \frac{35970}{86124} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18027}{39564} &= \frac{26039}{57148} = \frac{36054}{79128} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18036}{25974} &= \frac{27054}{38961} = \frac{36072}{51948} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18039}{24576} &= \frac{36078}{49152} = \frac{72156}{98304} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18046}{23759} &= \frac{36092}{47518} = \frac{72184}{95036} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18054}{23796} &= \frac{27081}{35694} = \frac{36108}{47592} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18054}{23976} &= \frac{27081}{35964} = \frac{36108}{47952} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18054}{37962} &= \frac{27081}{56943} = \frac{36108}{75924} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18054}{39762} &= \frac{27081}{59643} = \frac{36108}{79524} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18076}{23954} &= \frac{36152}{47908} = \frac{72304}{95816} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18076}{24539} &= \frac{36152}{49078} = \frac{72304}{98156} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18079}{23645} &= \frac{36158}{47290} = \frac{72316}{94580} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18079}{24635} &= \frac{36158}{49270} = \frac{72316}{98540} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18097}{25436} &= \frac{36194}{50872} = \frac{54291}{76308} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18240}{35796} &= \frac{36480}{71592} = \frac{48720}{95613} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18256}{39740} &= \frac{27384}{59610} = \frac{36512}{79480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18279}{45630} &= \frac{18956}{47320} = \frac{34527}{86190} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18326}{57409} &= \frac{20874}{65391} = \frac{27146}{85039} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18352}{40796} &= \frac{36704}{81592} = \frac{42180}{93765} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18357}{46209} &= \frac{29058}{73146} = \frac{34017}{85629} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{25974} &= \frac{27540}{38961} = \frac{36720}{51948} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18369}{24570} &= \frac{26847}{35910} = \frac{53694}{71820} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18370}{49265} &= \frac{21604}{57938} = \frac{30426}{81597} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18374}{25960} &= \frac{27561}{38940} = \frac{36748}{51920} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18376}{20549} &= \frac{36752}{41098} = \frac{73504}{82196} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18379}{24506} &= \frac{36758}{49012} = \frac{73516}{98024} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18379}{24560} &= \frac{36758}{49120} = \frac{73516}{98240} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18379}{24605} &= \frac{36758}{49210} = \frac{73516}{98420} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18392}{45760} &= \frac{36784}{91520} = \frac{38247}{95160} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18394}{25670} &= \frac{49231}{68705} = \frac{51936}{72480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18396}{25740} &= \frac{27594}{38610} = \frac{36792}{51480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18396}{40572} &= \frac{30514}{67298} = \frac{39201}{86457} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18405}{23796} &= \frac{36810}{47592} = \frac{73620}{95184} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18406}{23795} &= \frac{36812}{47590} = \frac{73624}{95180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18437}{26059} &= \frac{65872}{93104} = \frac{67304}{95128} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18456}{23790} &= \frac{36912}{47580} = \frac{73824}{95160} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18456}{37920} &= \frac{31529}{64780} = \frac{36912}{75840} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18476}{20539} &= \frac{36952}{41078} = \frac{73904}{82156} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18479}{20635} &= \frac{36958}{41270} = \frac{73916}{82540} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18506}{47239} &= \frac{23104}{58976} = \frac{29830}{76145} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18549}{20763} &= \frac{37098}{41526} = \frac{74196}{83052} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18564}{32970} &= \frac{37128}{65940} = \frac{49062}{87135} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18579}{24630} &= \frac{37158}{49260} = \frac{74316}{98520} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18590}{23764} &= \frac{19305}{24678} = \frac{47905}{61238} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18594}{32760} &= \frac{19627}{34580} = \frac{23759}{41860} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18605}{37942} &= \frac{23790}{48516} = \frac{36295}{74018} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18630}{24579} &= \frac{37260}{49158} = \frac{74520}{98316} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18645}{23079} &= \frac{37290}{46158} = \frac{74580}{92316} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18645}{39270} &= \frac{23165}{48790} = \frac{26103}{54978} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18649}{20753} &= \frac{37298}{41506} = \frac{74596}{83012} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18690}{32574} &= \frac{20895}{36417} = \frac{26985}{47031} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18730}{29564} &= \frac{37460}{59128} = \frac{46825}{73910} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18734}{26095} &= \frac{37468}{52190} = \frac{68324}{95170} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18753}{24096} &= \frac{37506}{48192} = \frac{75012}{96384} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18753}{24609} &= \frac{37506}{49218} = \frac{75012}{98436} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18754}{23096} &= \frac{37508}{46192} = \frac{75016}{92384} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18756}{20349} &= \frac{37512}{40698} = \frac{75024}{81396} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18759}{23046} &= \frac{37518}{46092} = \frac{75036}{92184} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18759}{24603} &= \frac{37518}{49206} = \frac{75036}{98412} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18759}{43602} &= \frac{29415}{68370} = \frac{34965}{81270} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18760}{32495} &= \frac{38920}{67415} = \frac{47320}{81965} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18790}{23456} &= \frac{37580}{46912} = \frac{75160}{93824} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18795}{23406} &= \frac{37590}{46812} = \frac{75180}{93624} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18796}{23405} &= \frac{37592}{46810} = \frac{75184}{93620} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18903}{24576} &= \frac{37806}{49152} = \frac{75612}{98304} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18924}{35607} &= \frac{25308}{47619} = \frac{42180}{79365} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18930}{24756} &= \frac{37860}{49512} = \frac{47325}{61890} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18942}{70356} &= \frac{21693}{80574} = \frac{23415}{86970} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18953}{24076} &= \frac{37906}{48152} = \frac{75812}{96304} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18954}{23076} &= \frac{37908}{46152} = \frac{75816}{92304} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18956}{32704} &= \frac{37912}{65408} = \frac{46713}{80592} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18963}{40572} &= \frac{27391}{58604} = \frac{32981}{70564} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18975}{30624} &= \frac{24150}{38976} = \frac{37950}{61248} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18976}{20534} &= \frac{37952}{41068} = \frac{75904}{82136} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19038}{24576} &= \frac{38076}{49152} = \frac{76152}{98304} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19038}{25764} &= \frac{67134}{90852} = \frac{72645}{98310} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19046}{23758} &= \frac{38092}{47516} = \frac{76184}{95032} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19046}{27358} &= \frac{28569}{41037} = \frac{38092}{54716} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19046}{35728} &= \frac{38092}{71456} = \frac{47615}{89320} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19048}{35726} &= \frac{38096}{71452} = \frac{47620}{89315} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19052}{48763} &= \frac{20784}{53196} = \frac{38104}{97526} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19054}{32768} &= \frac{47635}{81920} = \frac{57162}{98304} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19063}{48752} &= \frac{20796}{53184} = \frac{38126}{97504} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19076}{24538} &= \frac{38152}{49076} = \frac{76304}{98152} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19078}{23645} &= \frac{38156}{47290} = \frac{76312}{94580} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19078}{24635} &= \frac{38156}{49270} = \frac{76312}{98540} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19082}{35467} &= \frac{26978}{50143} = \frac{30926}{57481} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19203}{58647} &= \frac{19758}{60342} = \frac{25641}{78309} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19208}{47536} &= \frac{21609}{53478} = \frac{38416}{95072} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19236}{47508} &= \frac{20839}{51467} = \frac{38472}{95016} \end{aligned}$$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{28614}{30597} = \frac{38152}{40796} = \frac{76304}{81592}$ | ▶ $\frac{29315}{47806} = \frac{36270}{59148} = \frac{41925}{68370}$ | ▶ $\frac{30857}{49162} = \frac{37819}{60254} = \frac{61537}{98042}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28617}{35940} = \frac{38156}{47920} = \frac{76312}{95840}$ | ▶ $\frac{29315}{48607} = \frac{54120}{89736} = \frac{58630}{97214}$ | ▶ $\frac{30912}{74865} = \frac{35712}{86490} = \frac{37824}{91605}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28679}{34510} = \frac{59286}{71340} = \frac{63142}{75980}$ | ▶ $\frac{29407}{35168} = \frac{37809}{45216} = \frac{75618}{90432}$ | ▶ $\frac{30927}{48516} = \frac{38064}{59712} = \frac{61854}{97032}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28690}{37145} = \frac{62514}{80937} = \frac{76104}{98532}$ | ▶ $\frac{29541}{37068} = \frac{49235}{61780} = \frac{59082}{74136}$ | ▶ $\frac{31280}{49657} = \frac{36480}{57912} = \frac{49520}{78613}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28731}{56049} = \frac{40321}{78659} = \frac{41297}{80563}$ | ▶ $\frac{29561}{43870} = \frac{43981}{65270} = \frac{54796}{81320}$ | ▶ $\frac{31504}{87296} = \frac{35084}{97216} = \frac{35621}{98704}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28791}{46053} = \frac{42501}{67983} = \frac{53012}{84796}$ | ▶ $\frac{29568}{37041} = \frac{49280}{61735} = \frac{59136}{74082}$ | ▶ $\frac{31590}{62478} = \frac{36045}{71289} = \frac{45360}{89712}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28905}{46371} = \frac{52170}{83694} = \frac{56870}{91234}$ | ▶ $\frac{29568}{41370} = \frac{54912}{76830} = \frac{59136}{82740}$ | ▶ $\frac{31605}{42987} = \frac{54180}{73692} = \frac{63210}{85974}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28907}{41356} = \frac{37812}{54096} = \frac{47539}{68012}$ | ▶ $\frac{29610}{37458} = \frac{36190}{45782} = \frac{72380}{91564}$ | ▶ $\frac{31679}{45820} = \frac{36491}{52780} = \frac{61754}{89320}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28910}{57643} = \frac{43120}{85976} = \frac{48510}{96723}$ | ▶ $\frac{29706}{31854} = \frac{59412}{63708} = \frac{84167}{90253}$ | ▶ $\frac{31692}{45870} = \frac{41268}{59730} = \frac{53124}{76890}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28943}{51706} = \frac{30629}{54718} = \frac{51704}{92368}$ | ▶ $\frac{29754}{31806} = \frac{46893}{50127} = \frac{75429}{80631}$ | ▶ $\frac{31758}{62094} = \frac{34907}{68251} = \frac{39128}{76504}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28956}{41730} = \frac{57912}{83460} = \frac{62738}{90415}$ | ▶ $\frac{29835}{40716} = \frac{59670}{81432} = \frac{60945}{83172}$ | ▶ $\frac{31790}{65824} = \frac{35190}{72864} = \frac{38165}{79024}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28960}{34571} = \frac{49120}{58637} = \frac{59680}{71243}$ | ▶ $\frac{29840}{67513} = \frac{34560}{78192} = \frac{42160}{95387}$ | ▶ $\frac{32058}{46917} = \frac{43018}{62957} = \frac{67130}{98245}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{28971}{36540} = \frac{32967}{41580} = \frac{56943}{71820}$ | ▶ $\frac{29845}{67310} = \frac{34592}{78016} = \frac{37694}{85012}$ | ▶ $\frac{32085}{64791} = \frac{40765}{82319} = \frac{42935}{86701}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{29053}{48671} = \frac{49561}{83027} = \frac{58106}{97342}$ | ▶ $\frac{30127}{46859} = \frac{32691}{50847} = \frac{60254}{93718}$ | ▶ $\frac{32617}{45890} = \frac{52689}{74130} = \frac{65234}{91780}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{29058}{36714} = \frac{39746}{50218} = \frac{70641}{89253}$ | ▶ $\frac{30162}{47985} = \frac{38214}{60795} = \frac{54912}{87360}$ | ▶ $\frac{32691}{48075} = \frac{42891}{63075} = \frac{60741}{89325}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{29078}{45136} = \frac{30619}{47528} = \frac{32897}{51064}$ | ▶ $\frac{30472}{59186} = \frac{39208}{76154} = \frac{50128}{97364}$ | ▶ $\frac{32760}{58149} = \frac{41520}{73698} = \frac{42360}{75189}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{29087}{41536} = \frac{37961}{54208} = \frac{68034}{97152}$ | ▶ $\frac{30685}{47291} = \frac{37910}{58426} = \frac{61370}{94582}$ | ▶ $\frac{32760}{59418} = \frac{34580}{62719} = \frac{41860}{75923}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{29145}{30687} = \frac{58290}{61374} = \frac{87435}{92061}$ | ▶ $\frac{30691}{45872} = \frac{34609}{51728} = \frac{50934}{76128}$ | ▶ $\frac{32806}{45719} = \frac{60254}{83971} = \frac{65142}{90783}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{29145}{30867} = \frac{58290}{61734} = \frac{87435}{92601}$ | ▶ $\frac{30798}{46152} = \frac{32509}{48716} = \frac{65018}{97432}$ | ▶ $\frac{32809}{64715} = \frac{43709}{86215} = \frac{48723}{96105}$ |

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32865}{40971} = \frac{65730}{81942} = \frac{75120}{93648}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{32984}{65170} = \frac{36084}{71295} = \frac{38192}{75460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34760}{51982} = \frac{53240}{79618} = \frac{65120}{97384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34768}{51092} = \frac{57236}{84109} = \frac{63140}{92785}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{34891}{52670} = \frac{56129}{84730} = \frac{65231}{98470}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35208}{46197} = \frac{36512}{47908} = \frac{73024}{95816}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35217}{48069} = \frac{45279}{61803} = \frac{65403}{89271}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35708}{49612} = \frac{48251}{67039} = \frac{54918}{76302}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35862}{91740} = \frac{36851}{94270} = \frac{37582}{96140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{35972}{40618} = \frac{46138}{52097} = \frac{59432}{67108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36192}{47580} = \frac{38976}{51240} = \frac{72384}{95160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36570}{49128} = \frac{73140}{98256} = \frac{73405}{98612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36597}{40128} = \frac{73194}{80256} = \frac{76521}{83904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36708}{45129} = \frac{47196}{58023} = \frac{73416}{90258}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36851}{40279} = \frac{83506}{91274} = \frac{87204}{95316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36917}{45820} = \frac{52193}{64780} = \frac{59831}{74260}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36972}{50481} = \frac{37128}{50694} = \frac{38064}{51972}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{36975}{42108} = \frac{73950}{84216} = \frac{80325}{91476}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37018}{45269} = \frac{38512}{47096} = \frac{57104}{69832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37196}{40528} = \frac{74392}{81056} = \frac{79315}{86420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37260}{41958} = \frac{74520}{83916} = \frac{75210}{84693}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37590}{46182} = \frac{67095}{82431} = \frac{75180}{92364}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37596}{48012} = \frac{56394}{72018} = \frac{65793}{84021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37596}{48120} = \frac{56394}{72180} = \frac{65793}{84210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{37942}{68015} = \frac{39186}{70245} = \frac{54736}{98120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38052}{71946} = \frac{39562}{74801} = \frac{50132}{94786}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38076}{41952} = \frac{73146}{80592} = \frac{76152}{83904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38097}{54162} = \frac{52041}{73986} = \frac{65487}{93102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38467}{52910} = \frac{39812}{54760} = \frac{62139}{85470}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38590}{47216} = \frac{59160}{72384} = \frac{59840}{73216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38610}{45279} = \frac{73260}{85914} = \frac{83160}{97524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38720}{51964} = \frac{43120}{57869} = \frac{65120}{87394}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38752}{69104} = \frac{46710}{83295} = \frac{47056}{83912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38764}{51920} = \frac{43169}{57820} = \frac{65194}{87320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{38962}{45701} = \frac{60984}{71532} = \frac{76230}{89415}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39028}{64751} = \frac{50732}{84169} = \frac{54736}{90812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39215}{47608} = \frac{42780}{51936} = \frac{78430}{95216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39402}{57816} = \frac{57312}{84096} = \frac{59103}{86724}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39420}{57816} = \frac{49815}{73062} = \frac{59130}{86724}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39615}{80427} = \frac{42395}{86071} = \frac{45870}{93126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39756}{48012} = \frac{59634}{72018} = \frac{69573}{84021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39756}{48120} = \frac{59634}{72180} = \frac{69573}{84210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39816}{47502} = \frac{65412}{78039} = \frac{70152}{83694}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39867}{45210} = \frac{65184}{73920} = \frac{82547}{93610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40139}{56782} = \frac{49651}{70238} = \frac{51906}{73428}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40236}{58917} = \frac{49056}{71832} = \frac{67032}{98154}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40391}{62857} = \frac{51038}{79426} = \frac{58136}{90472}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42398}{60157} = \frac{50286}{71349} = \frac{67048}{95132}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{42679}{50183} = \frac{42861}{50397} = \frac{53417}{62809}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43795}{68210} = \frac{45639}{71082} = \frac{57164}{89032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{43862}{71095} = \frac{54236}{87910} = \frac{57148}{92630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{45103}{69782} = \frac{45368}{70192} = \frac{61427}{95038}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46231}{50879} = \frac{73524}{80916} = \frac{84107}{92563}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46718}{59032} = \frac{50197}{63428} = \frac{71568}{90432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46870}{53192} = \frac{63425}{71980} = \frac{69015}{78324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47608}{59312} = \frac{74658}{93012} = \frac{76281}{95034}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47982}{50163} = \frac{49038}{51267} = \frac{59048}{61732}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{48319}{52670} = \frac{68153}{74290} = \frac{86721}{94530} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{48319}{67520} = \frac{51983}{72640} = \frac{65723}{91840} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{48320}{61759} = \frac{53120}{67894} = \frac{56320}{71984} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{48930}{51726} = \frac{68145}{72039} = \frac{69510}{73482} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{50463}{72891} = \frac{52893}{76401} = \frac{63504}{91728} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{50463}{89712} = \frac{52407}{93168} = \frac{53217}{94608} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{50964}{87132} = \frac{51243}{87609} = \frac{53847}{92061} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{51026}{74893} = \frac{52018}{76349} = \frac{57164}{83902} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{51039}{64872} = \frac{59813}{76024} = \frac{70513}{89624} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{51728}{69430} = \frac{67832}{91045} = \frac{71248}{95630} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{51840}{67392} = \frac{62730}{81549} = \frac{72810}{94653} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{52089}{63147} = \frac{61934}{75082} = \frac{67304}{81592} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{52437}{61908} = \frac{69235}{81740} = \frac{78315}{92460} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{53240}{81796} = \frac{53790}{82641} = \frac{64130}{98527} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{53298}{71064} = \frac{67014}{89352} = \frac{70146}{93528} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{53418}{79206} = \frac{59102}{87634} = \frac{60523}{89741} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{71928} = \frac{65340}{87912} = \frac{68475}{92130} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{53820}{64791} = \frac{59280}{71364} = \frac{69420}{83571} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{53928}{71460} = \frac{65912}{87340} = \frac{67410}{89325} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{54230}{61897} = \frac{63510}{72489} = \frac{85260}{97314} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{54910}{62738} = \frac{73695}{84201} = \frac{82365}{94107} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{57102}{63984} = \frac{63549}{71208} = \frac{74601}{83592} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{57280}{61934} = \frac{58720}{63491} = \frac{87520}{94631} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{57429}{63810} = \frac{58239}{64710} = \frac{75249}{83610} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{58293}{67014} = \frac{69723}{80154} = \frac{73152}{84096} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{58632}{70149} = \frac{69720}{83415} = \frac{78120}{93465} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{58941}{63720} = \frac{65934}{71280} = \frac{68931}{74520} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{59182}{73406} = \frac{60813}{75429} = \frac{65473}{81209} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{63125}{80497} = \frac{63750}{81294} = \frac{64375}{82091} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{64321}{75980} = \frac{73159}{86420} = \frac{75614}{89320} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{64952}{78013} = \frac{74152}{89063} = \frac{75624}{90831} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{65128}{70943} = \frac{69048}{75213} = \frac{79240}{86315} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{65431}{72098} = \frac{73194}{80652} = \frac{75412}{83096} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{69174}{82350} = \frac{69741}{83025} = \frac{78246}{93150} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{76314}{82950} = \frac{79143}{86025} = \frac{83421}{90675} \end{aligned}$$

• **4-Digits Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1026}{345978} = \frac{1064}{358792} = \frac{2641}{890573} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1029}{534786} = \frac{1526}{793084} = \frac{1743}{905862} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1032}{495876} = \frac{1206}{579483} = \frac{1246}{598703} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1032}{579468} = \frac{1046}{587329} = \frac{1348}{756902} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1034}{296758} = \frac{1508}{432796} = \frac{2037}{584619} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1035}{274689} = \frac{2645}{701983} = \frac{2945}{781603} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1038}{245769} = \frac{2076}{491538} = \frac{4152}{983076} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1038}{246759} = \frac{2076}{493518} = \frac{4152}{987036} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1038}{629547} = \frac{1406}{852739} = \frac{1430}{867295} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1039}{245768} = \frac{2078}{491536} = \frac{4156}{983072} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1039}{246758} = \frac{2078}{493516} = \frac{4156}{987032} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1039}{475862} = \frac{1539}{704862} = \frac{2153}{986074} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{1039}{625478} = \frac{1092}{657384} = \frac{1635}{984270} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1052}{346897} = \frac{1508}{497263} = \frac{2748}{906153} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1053}{267489} = \frac{2106}{534978} = \frac{3159}{802467} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1053}{268749} = \frac{2106}{537498} = \frac{3159}{806247} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1053}{274689} = \frac{2106}{549378} = \frac{3159}{824067} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{1053}{274869} = \frac{2106}{549738} = \frac{3159}{824607} \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{1053}{286749} = \frac{2106}{573498} = \frac{3159}{860247}$	▶ $\frac{1067}{452893} = \frac{1408}{597632} = \frac{2134}{905786}$	▶ $\frac{1092}{738465} = \frac{1256}{849370} = \frac{1460}{987325}$
▶ $\frac{1053}{287469} = \frac{2106}{574938} = \frac{3159}{862407}$	▶ $\frac{1068}{235479} = \frac{1780}{392465} = \frac{2136}{470958}$	▶ $\frac{1092}{745836} = \frac{1249}{853067} = \frac{1432}{978056}$
▶ $\frac{1054}{298367} = \frac{2046}{579183} = \frac{2108}{596734}$	▶ $\frac{1068}{352974} = \frac{2136}{705948} = \frac{2406}{795183}$	▶ $\frac{1093}{268547} = \frac{2186}{537094} = \frac{3279}{805641}$
▶ $\frac{1056}{237984} = \frac{2079}{468531} = \frac{4158}{937062}$	▶ $\frac{1069}{237845} = \frac{2138}{475690} = \frac{4276}{951380}$	▶ $\frac{1093}{285467} = \frac{2186}{570934} = \frac{3279}{856401}$
▶ $\frac{1056}{284739} = \frac{1408}{379652} = \frac{2816}{759304}$	▶ $\frac{1069}{285473} = \frac{2138}{570946} = \frac{3207}{856419}$	▶ $\frac{1095}{234768} = \frac{1725}{369840} = \frac{4605}{987312}$
▶ $\frac{1059}{427836} = \frac{1468}{593072} = \frac{1537}{620948}$	▶ $\frac{1069}{328547} = \frac{2138}{657094} = \frac{3207}{985641}$	▶ $\frac{1096}{257834} = \frac{3056}{718924} = \frac{3856}{907124}$
▶ $\frac{1059}{643872} = \frac{1308}{795264} = \frac{1584}{963072}$	▶ $\frac{1072}{693584} = \frac{1307}{845629} = \frac{1506}{974382}$	▶ $\frac{1098}{254736} = \frac{3456}{801792} = \frac{3672}{851904}$
▶ $\frac{1062}{375948} = \frac{1908}{675432} = \frac{2547}{901638}$	▶ $\frac{1073}{268549} = \frac{2146}{537098} = \frac{3219}{805647}$	▶ $\frac{1098}{367452} = \frac{2501}{836974} = \frac{2745}{918630}$
▶ $\frac{1064}{379582} = \frac{1468}{523709} = \frac{2536}{904718}$	▶ $\frac{1073}{285469} = \frac{2146}{570938} = \frac{3219}{856407}$	▶ $\frac{1098}{426573} = \frac{1278}{496503} = \frac{1890}{734265}$
▶ $\frac{1065}{273489} = \frac{2130}{546978} = \frac{3195}{820467}$	▶ $\frac{1078}{239465} = \frac{2156}{478930} = \frac{4312}{957860}$	▶ $\frac{1208}{573649} = \frac{1536}{729408} = \frac{2016}{957348}$
▶ $\frac{1065}{283947} = \frac{1420}{378596} = \frac{2130}{567894}$	▶ $\frac{1078}{243965} = \frac{2156}{487930} = \frac{4312}{975860}$	▶ $\frac{1209}{348657} = \frac{2483}{716059} = \frac{3146}{907258}$
▶ $\frac{1065}{287349} = \frac{2130}{574698} = \frac{3195}{862047}$	▶ $\frac{1085}{346297} = \frac{1240}{395768} = \frac{2480}{791536}$	▶ $\frac{1209}{543678} = \frac{1352}{607984} = \frac{2158}{970436}$
▶ $\frac{1065}{289347} = \frac{1420}{385796} = \frac{2130}{578694}$	▶ $\frac{1085}{346927} = \frac{1860}{594732} = \frac{2170}{693854}$	▶ $\frac{1209}{854763} = \frac{1278}{903546} = \frac{1308}{924756}$
▶ $\frac{1065}{382974} = \frac{1305}{469278} = \frac{2130}{765948}$	▶ $\frac{1086}{357294} = \frac{1983}{652407} = \frac{2451}{806379}$	▶ $\frac{1230}{587694} = \frac{1640}{783592} = \frac{1730}{826594}$
▶ $\frac{1065}{437982} = \frac{1420}{583976} = \frac{2130}{875964}$	▶ $\frac{1086}{472953} = \frac{1304}{567892} = \frac{2154}{938067}$	▶ $\frac{1236}{478950} = \frac{1932}{748650} = \frac{2316}{897450}$
▶ $\frac{1065}{483297} = \frac{1605}{728349} = \frac{2085}{946173}$	▶ $\frac{1089}{246753} = \frac{2178}{493506} = \frac{4356}{987012}$	▶ $\frac{1239}{475068} = \frac{2478}{950136} = \frac{2534}{971608}$
▶ $\frac{1067}{285493} = \frac{2134}{570986} = \frac{3201}{856479}$	▶ $\frac{1089}{267345} = \frac{1936}{475280} = \frac{2178}{534690}$	▶ $\frac{1239}{486750} = \frac{1869}{734250} = \frac{2163}{849750}$
▶ $\frac{1067}{328549} = \frac{2134}{657098} = \frac{3201}{985647}$	▶ $\frac{1089}{345267} = \frac{1694}{537082} = \frac{2178}{690534}$	▶ $\frac{1239}{586047} = \frac{1359}{642807} = \frac{2061}{974853}$
▶ $\frac{1067}{342895} = \frac{2134}{685790} = \frac{2189}{703465}$	▶ $\frac{1089}{452673} = \frac{1936}{804752} = \frac{2178}{905346}$	▶ $\frac{1240}{359786} = \frac{2340}{678951} = \frac{2540}{736981}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1248}{365079} = \frac{2016}{589743} = \frac{2496}{730158}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1248}{375960} = \frac{1872}{563940} = \frac{2184}{657930}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1254}{390786} = \frac{2071}{645389} = \frac{2451}{763809}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1258}{369704} = \frac{2516}{739408} = \frac{2907}{854316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1260}{358974} = \frac{2610}{743589} = \frac{2970}{846153}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1267}{308549} = \frac{2534}{617098} = \frac{3801}{925647}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1267}{394580} = \frac{1729}{538460} = \frac{2534}{789160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1268}{394570} = \frac{2536}{789140} = \frac{3170}{986425}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1269}{308547} = \frac{2538}{617094} = \frac{3807}{925641}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1269}{345087} = \frac{1974}{536802} = \frac{2538}{690174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1269}{348570} = \frac{2397}{658410} = \frac{2538}{697140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1269}{370548} = \frac{1746}{509832} = \frac{2538}{741096}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1269}{384507} = \frac{1746}{529038} = \frac{2538}{769014}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1270}{356984} = \frac{2540}{713968} = \frac{3175}{892460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1270}{394568} = \frac{2540}{789136} = \frac{3175}{986420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1276}{349508} = \frac{3476}{952108} = \frac{3542}{970186}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1276}{349580} = \frac{2146}{587930} = \frac{2378}{651490}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1285}{609347} = \frac{1580}{749236} = \frac{1760}{834592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1287}{309465} = \frac{2574}{618930} = \frac{2871}{690345}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1287}{350649} = \frac{2178}{593406} = \frac{3564}{971028}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1290}{437568} = \frac{1690}{573248} = \frac{2180}{739456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1293}{708564} = \frac{1352}{740896} = \frac{1497}{820356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12947}{36058} = \frac{15729}{43806} = \frac{20437}{56918}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1296}{538407} = \frac{2160}{897345} = \frac{2304}{957168}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1298}{356704} = \frac{2596}{713408} = \frac{3245}{891760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1298}{536074} = \frac{1904}{786352} = \frac{2073}{856149}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1305}{267489} = \frac{2610}{534978} = \frac{3915}{802467}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1305}{268749} = \frac{2610}{537498} = \frac{3915}{806247}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1305}{274689} = \frac{2610}{549378} = \frac{3915}{824067}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1305}{274869} = \frac{2610}{549738} = \frac{3915}{824607}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1305}{286749} = \frac{2610}{573498} = \frac{3915}{860247}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1305}{287469} = \frac{2610}{574938} = \frac{3915}{862407}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1307}{268549} = \frac{2614}{537098} = \frac{3921}{805647}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1307}{285469} = \frac{2614}{570938} = \frac{3921}{856407}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1308}{459762} = \frac{2130}{748695} = \frac{2754}{968031}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1309}{268547} = \frac{2618}{537094} = \frac{3927}{805641}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1309}{285467} = \frac{2618}{570934} = \frac{3927}{856401}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1309}{427856} = \frac{2135}{697840} = \frac{2415}{789360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1309}{467852} = \frac{2618}{935704} = \frac{2635}{941780}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1320}{495768} = \frac{1980}{743652} = \frac{2310}{867594}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1325}{649780} = \frac{1385}{679204} = \frac{1740}{853296}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1340}{267598} = \frac{3580}{714926} = \frac{4290}{856713}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1347}{285069} = \frac{2694}{570138} = \frac{3592}{760184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1347}{285690} = \frac{2694}{571380} = \frac{3592}{761840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1347}{286905} = \frac{1796}{382540} = \frac{2694}{573810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1347}{289065} = \frac{1796}{385420} = \frac{2694}{578130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1348}{729605} = \frac{1380}{746925} = \frac{1780}{963425}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1349}{206785} = \frac{2698}{413570} = \frac{5396}{827140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1349}{270865} = \frac{2698}{541730} = \frac{3097}{621845}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1352}{746980} = \frac{1634}{902785} = \frac{1738}{960245}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1354}{207698} = \frac{2708}{415396} = \frac{5416}{830792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1354}{209768} = \frac{2708}{419536} = \frac{5416}{839072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1354}{729806} = \frac{1536}{827904} = \frac{1804}{972356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1357}{246089} = \frac{2783}{504691} = \frac{5382}{976014}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1358}{204769} = \frac{2716}{409538} = \frac{5432}{819076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1358}{246790} = \frac{2716}{493580} = \frac{5432}{987160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1358}{264907} = \frac{3290}{641785} = \frac{3612}{704598}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1359}{204768} = \frac{2718}{409536} = \frac{5436}{819072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1359}{246780} = \frac{2718}{493560} = \frac{5436}{987120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1360}{248795} = \frac{3072}{561984} = \frac{3264}{597108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1360}{579428} = \frac{1860}{792453} = \frac{1940}{826537}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1362}{495087} = \frac{2370}{861495} = \frac{2610}{948735}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1362}{795408} = \frac{1536}{897024} = \frac{1576}{920384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1364}{259780} = \frac{2398}{456710} = \frac{3916}{745820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1365}{209478} = \frac{2730}{418956} = \frac{5460}{837912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1365}{280947} = \frac{1820}{374596} = \frac{2730}{561894}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1365}{407982} = \frac{1820}{543976} = \frac{2730}{815964}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1365}{492870} = \frac{2041}{736958} = \frac{2587}{934106}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{204759} = \frac{2736}{409518} = \frac{5472}{819036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{207549} = \frac{2736}{415098} = \frac{5472}{830196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{209475} = \frac{2736}{418950} = \frac{3928}{601475}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{209754} = \frac{2736}{419508} = \frac{5472}{839016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{240795} = \frac{2736}{481590} = \frac{5472}{963180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{245079} = \frac{2736}{490158} = \frac{5472}{980316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{245790} = \frac{2736}{491580} = \frac{5472}{983160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{247590} = \frac{2736}{495180} = \frac{3420}{618975}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{247950} = \frac{1804}{326975} = \frac{3420}{619875}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1368}{290745} = \frac{2736}{581490} = \frac{3192}{678405}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1369}{207548} = \frac{2738}{415096} = \frac{5476}{830192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1369}{245078} = \frac{2738}{490156} = \frac{5476}{980312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1369}{245780} = \frac{2738}{491560} = \frac{5476}{983120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1374}{265980} = \frac{2519}{487630} = \frac{2748}{531960}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1375}{264890} = \frac{1925}{370846} = \frac{3850}{741692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1376}{285904} = \frac{1806}{375249} = \frac{3612}{750498}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1378}{204659} = \frac{2756}{409318} = \frac{6042}{897351}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1378}{406952} = \frac{1908}{563472} = \frac{2756}{813904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1380}{265974} = \frac{2530}{487619} = \frac{2760}{531948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1380}{269457} = \frac{1840}{359276} = \frac{2760}{538914}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1380}{294567} = \frac{1840}{392756} = \frac{2760}{589134}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1380}{564972} = \frac{1840}{753296} = \frac{2135}{874069}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1384}{205697} = \frac{2416}{359078} = \frac{6024}{895317}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1386}{207459} = \frac{1584}{237096} = \frac{6534}{978021}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1390}{247568} = \frac{2780}{495136} = \frac{3475}{618920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1390}{264875} = \frac{1946}{370825} = \frac{3892}{741650}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1392}{478065} = \frac{1728}{593460} = \frac{2784}{956130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1394}{205768} = \frac{2419}{357068} = \frac{3198}{472056}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1398}{270654} = \frac{2796}{541308} = \frac{3029}{586417}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1398}{527046} = \frac{1802}{679354} = \frac{2137}{805649}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1402}{365798} = \frac{2103}{548697} = \frac{2804}{731596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1402}{365978} = \frac{2103}{548967} = \frac{2804}{731956}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1402}{376598} = \frac{2103}{564897} = \frac{2804}{753196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1402}{379658} = \frac{2103}{569487} = \frac{2804}{759316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1402}{396578} = \frac{2103}{594867} = \frac{2804}{793156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1402}{397658} = \frac{2103}{596487} = \frac{2804}{795316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1403}{289567} = \frac{2806}{579134} = \frac{4163}{859207}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1407}{682395} = \frac{1498}{726530} = \frac{1697}{823045}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1408}{236795} = \frac{2816}{473590} = \frac{5632}{947180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{365798} = \frac{2130}{548697} = \frac{2840}{731596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{365978} = \frac{2130}{548967} = \frac{2840}{731956}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{376598} = \frac{2130}{564897} = \frac{2840}{753196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{379658} = \frac{2130}{569487} = \frac{2840}{759316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{396578} = \frac{2130}{594867} = \frac{2840}{793156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1420}{397658} = \frac{2130}{596487} = \frac{2840}{795316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1428}{376950} = \frac{1870}{493625} = \frac{3094}{816725}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1430}{298675} = \frac{2948}{615730} = \frac{3102}{647895}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1430}{678925} = \frac{1452}{689370} = \frac{2046}{971385}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1432}{897506} = \frac{1476}{925083} = \frac{1564}{980237}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1435}{298067} = \frac{2870}{596134} = \frac{4510}{936782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1439}{607258} = \frac{2037}{859614} = \frac{2314}{976508}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{267089} = \frac{2906}{534178} = \frac{4359}{801267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{268709} = \frac{2906}{537418} = \frac{4359}{806127}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{268907} = \frac{2906}{537814} = \frac{4359}{806721}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{269087} = \frac{2906}{538174} = \frac{4359}{807261}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{270689} = \frac{2906}{541378} = \frac{4359}{812067}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{270869} = \frac{2906}{541738} = \frac{4359}{812607}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{286709} = \frac{2906}{573418} = \frac{4359}{860127}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{286907} = \frac{2906}{573814} = \frac{4359}{860721}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{287069} = \frac{2906}{574138} = \frac{4359}{861207}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{289067} = \frac{2906}{578134} = \frac{4359}{867201}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{290687} = \frac{2906}{581374} = \frac{4359}{872061}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1453}{290867} = \frac{2906}{581734} = \frac{4359}{872601}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1456}{207389} = \frac{3216}{458079} = \frac{3280}{467195}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1456}{289730} = \frac{3952}{786410} = \frac{4680}{931275}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1456}{309728} = \frac{1547}{329086} = \frac{3094}{658172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1456}{397280} = \frac{1974}{538620} = \frac{2149}{586370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1457}{629083} = \frac{1692}{730548} = \frac{1974}{852306}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1458}{236790} = \frac{2916}{473580} = \frac{5832}{947160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1458}{239760} = \frac{2187}{359640} = \frac{5346}{879120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1459}{236780} = \frac{2918}{473560} = \frac{5836}{947120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1463}{250987} = \frac{1596}{273804} = \frac{3192}{547608}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1468}{235079} = \frac{2936}{470158} = \frac{5872}{940316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1468}{235790} = \frac{2936}{471580} = \frac{5872}{943160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1468}{392570} = \frac{2936}{785140} = \frac{3670}{981425}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1469}{230785} = \frac{2938}{461570} = \frac{5876}{923140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1469}{235078} = \frac{2938}{470156} = \frac{5876}{940312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1469}{235780} = \frac{2938}{471560} = \frac{5876}{943120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1470}{236985} = \frac{4158}{670329} = \frac{5628}{907314}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1470}{283569} = \frac{2940}{567138} = \frac{3920}{756184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1470}{365928} = \frac{2940}{731856} = \frac{3675}{914820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1470}{369852} = \frac{2715}{683094} = \frac{3645}{917082}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1470}{392568} = \frac{2940}{785136} = \frac{3675}{981420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1476}{239850} = \frac{1806}{293475} = \frac{2916}{473850}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1476}{352980} = \frac{1927}{460835} = \frac{3854}{921670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1478}{209365} = \frac{2956}{418730} = \frac{5912}{837460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1479}{206835} = \frac{2958}{413670} = \frac{5916}{827340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1479}{235068} = \frac{2465}{391780} = \frac{2958}{470136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1482}{369075} = \frac{1638}{407925} = \frac{2964}{738150}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1482}{605397} = \frac{2046}{835791} = \frac{2370}{968145}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1485}{230769} = \frac{2970}{461538} = \frac{4590}{713286}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1485}{769230} = \frac{1785}{924630} = \frac{1854}{960372}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1490}{235867} = \frac{3690}{584127} = \frac{3970}{628451}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1493}{207865} = \frac{2986}{415730} = \frac{5972}{831460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1506}{284397} = \frac{3012}{568794} = \frac{4016}{758392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1506}{284937} = \frac{3012}{569874} = \frac{4016}{759832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1506}{293847} = \frac{3012}{587694} = \frac{4016}{783592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1506}{294738} = \frac{3012}{589476} = \frac{4267}{835091}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1506}{298437} = \frac{3012}{596874} = \frac{4016}{795832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1506}{372984} = \frac{3012}{745968} = \frac{3514}{870296}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1506}{379248} = \frac{3012}{758496} = \frac{3765}{948120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1508}{237946} = \frac{3016}{475892} = \frac{6032}{951784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1508}{243796} = \frac{3016}{487592} = \frac{6032}{975184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1508}{274369} = \frac{1872}{340596} = \frac{4732}{860951}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1520}{379468} = \frac{2360}{589174} = \frac{2380}{594167}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1524}{378096} = \frac{3048}{756192} = \frac{3429}{850716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1526}{370984} = \frac{3052}{741968} = \frac{3815}{927460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1526}{497803} = \frac{2058}{671349} = \frac{2506}{817493}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1534}{207896} = \frac{3068}{415792} = \frac{5192}{703648}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1536}{287904} = \frac{3280}{614795} = \frac{4592}{860713}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1537}{290864} = \frac{1798}{340256} = \frac{2697}{510384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1538}{209476} = \frac{3076}{418952} = \frac{6152}{837904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1538}{409726} = \frac{2307}{614589} = \frac{3076}{819452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1539}{204768} = \frac{1957}{260384} = \frac{3914}{520768}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1540}{278936} = \frac{1925}{348670} = \frac{5170}{936428}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1540}{382976} = \frac{2170}{539648} = \frac{3185}{792064}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1540}{792638} = \frac{1820}{936754} = \frac{1860}{957342}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1543}{208976} = \frac{3086}{417952} = \frac{6172}{835904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1543}{209876} = \frac{3086}{419752} = \frac{6172}{839504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1547}{293608} = \frac{3094}{587216} = \frac{5083}{964712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1547}{390286} = \frac{2751}{694038} = \frac{3815}{962470}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1548}{209376} = \frac{3096}{418752} = \frac{6192}{837504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{237984} = \frac{3120}{475968} = \frac{4680}{713952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{239784} = \frac{3120}{479568} = \frac{4680}{719352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{247839} = \frac{3120}{495678} = \frac{3640}{578291}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{249873} = \frac{2160}{345978} = \frac{3240}{518967}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{284397} = \frac{3120}{568794} = \frac{4160}{758392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{284937} = \frac{3120}{569874} = \frac{4160}{759832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{293847} = \frac{3120}{587694} = \frac{4160}{783592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{298437} = \frac{3120}{596874} = \frac{4160}{795832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{329784} = \frac{3210}{678594} = \frac{3910}{826574}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1560}{493728} = \frac{1690}{534872} = \frac{3120}{987456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1562}{438709} = \frac{2310}{648795} = \frac{2970}{834165}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1563}{402897} = \frac{2084}{537196} = \frac{3126}{805794}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1564}{298730} = \frac{3128}{597460} = \frac{3910}{746825}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1564}{329870} = \frac{3128}{659740} = \frac{3910}{824675}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1564}{380972} = \frac{1972}{480356} = \frac{2703}{658419}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1564}{398072} = \frac{1587}{403926} = \frac{2346}{597108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1568}{204379} = \frac{3872}{504691} = \frac{3968}{517204}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1568}{347920} = \frac{2156}{478390} = \frac{4312}{956780}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1569}{370284} = \frac{3189}{752604} = \frac{3609}{851724}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1573}{249860} = \frac{2178}{345960} = \frac{3267}{518940}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1576}{203948} = \frac{3152}{407896} = \frac{6304}{815792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1576}{204398} = \frac{3152}{408796} = \frac{6304}{817592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1576}{204893} = \frac{3152}{409786} = \frac{6304}{819572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1576}{204938} = \frac{3152}{409876} = \frac{6304}{819752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{239460} = \frac{3156}{478920} = \frac{6312}{957840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{243960} = \frac{3156}{487920} = \frac{6312}{975840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{246390} = \frac{3156}{492780} = \frac{3682}{574910}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{362940} = \frac{3549}{816270} = \frac{3564}{819720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{390246} = \frac{3156}{780492} = \frac{3682}{910574}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1578}{392460} = \frac{3156}{784920} = \frac{3682}{915740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1580}{237946} = \frac{3160}{475892} = \frac{6320}{951784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1580}{239476} = \frac{2765}{419083} = \frac{3160}{478952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1580}{243796} = \frac{3160}{487592} = \frac{6320}{975184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1580}{274396} = \frac{2765}{480193} = \frac{3160}{548792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1580}{294736} = \frac{1975}{368420} = \frac{3160}{589472}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1580}{493276} = \frac{1720}{536984} = \frac{2390}{746158}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{203796} = \frac{3168}{407592} = \frac{7524}{968031}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{372960} = \frac{3168}{745920} = \frac{3641}{857290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1584}{390672} = \frac{1782}{439506} = \frac{3564}{879012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1586}{249730} = \frac{2196}{345780} = \frac{3294}{518670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1590}{273648} = \frac{3180}{547296} = \frac{3975}{684120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1590}{273846} = \frac{2385}{410769} = \frac{3180}{547692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1590}{462738} = \frac{2385}{694107} = \frac{3180}{925476}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1592}{607348} = \frac{1962}{748503} = \frac{2374}{905681}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1593}{204876} = \frac{3186}{409752} = \frac{6372}{819504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1596}{243780} = \frac{3192}{487560} = \frac{6384}{975120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1596}{274380} = \frac{2793}{480165} = \frac{3192}{548760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1596}{287034} = \frac{3192}{574068} = \frac{3458}{621907}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1598}{204376} = \frac{3196}{408752} = \frac{6392}{817504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1598}{270436} = \frac{1645}{278390} = \frac{3196}{540872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1598}{364720} = \frac{3468}{791520} = \frac{3791}{865240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1602}{379458} = \frac{2403}{569187} = \frac{3204}{758916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1602}{394578} = \frac{2403}{591867} = \frac{3204}{789156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1603}{457289} = \frac{2061}{587943} = \frac{3206}{914578}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1605}{283947} = \frac{2140}{378596} = \frac{3210}{567894}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1605}{289347} = \frac{2140}{385796} = \frac{3210}{578694}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1605}{374928} = \frac{2130}{497568} = \frac{3210}{749856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1605}{437982} = \frac{2140}{583976} = \frac{3210}{875964}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1608}{235974} = \frac{1956}{287043} = \frac{3912}{574086}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1608}{237945} = \frac{3216}{475890} = \frac{6432}{951780}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1608}{243795} = \frac{3216}{487590} = \frac{6432}{975180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1608}{392754} = \frac{1756}{428903} = \frac{3728}{910564}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1620}{379458} = \frac{2430}{569187} = \frac{3240}{758916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1620}{394578} = \frac{2430}{591867} = \frac{3240}{789156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1620}{458379} = \frac{2540}{718693} = \frac{3240}{916758}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1628}{493570} = \frac{3182}{964705} = \frac{3256}{987140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1632}{407985} = \frac{2176}{543980} = \frac{3264}{815970}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1632}{584970} = \frac{1824}{653790} = \frac{2064}{739815}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1632}{708594} = \frac{1680}{729435} = \frac{2160}{937845}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1635}{207948} = \frac{3270}{415896} = \frac{6540}{831792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1635}{209478} = \frac{3270}{418956} = \frac{6540}{837912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1635}{280947} = \frac{2180}{374596} = \frac{3270}{561894}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1635}{407982} = \frac{2180}{543976} = \frac{3270}{815964}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1638}{254709} = \frac{2970}{461835} = \frac{3276}{509418}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1638}{452907} = \frac{2430}{671895} = \frac{3276}{905814}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1638}{475209} = \frac{1872}{543096} = \frac{3276}{950418}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1638}{492570} = \frac{2709}{814635} = \frac{3276}{985140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1639}{254870} = \frac{3129}{486570} = \frac{6258}{973140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1640}{257398} = \frac{3280}{514796} = \frac{3640}{571298}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1640}{279538} = \frac{1740}{296583} = \frac{2580}{439761}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1643}{207985} = \frac{3286}{415970} = \frac{6572}{831940}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1643}{209785} = \frac{3286}{419570} = \frac{6572}{839140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1643}{579820} = \frac{1798}{634520} = \frac{2139}{754860}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1647}{280935} = \frac{2196}{374580} = \frac{3294}{561870}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1647}{283905} = \frac{2196}{378540} = \frac{3294}{567810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1647}{285093} = \frac{3172}{549068} = \frac{3294}{570186}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1647}{289305} = \frac{2196}{385740} = \frac{3294}{578610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1647}{293085} = \frac{3294}{586170} = \frac{4392}{781560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1648}{207935} = \frac{3296}{415870} = \frac{6592}{831740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1648}{273590} = \frac{3296}{547180} = \frac{4120}{683975}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1650}{329748} = \frac{1925}{384706} = \frac{3850}{769412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1653}{208974} = \frac{6194}{783052} = \frac{6574}{831092}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1674}{235980} = \frac{1798}{253460} = \frac{5921}{834670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1674}{253890} = \frac{1809}{274365} = \frac{4698}{712530}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1674}{258093} = \frac{3162}{487509} = \frac{6324}{975018}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1680}{234759} = \frac{1760}{245938} = \frac{3520}{491876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1680}{294357} = \frac{2160}{378459} = \frac{4320}{756918}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1680}{357294} = \frac{2160}{459378} = \frac{4320}{918756}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1680}{359472} = \frac{4095}{876213} = \frac{4270}{913658}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1683}{420597} = \frac{2739}{684501} = \frac{3762}{940158}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1687}{395402} = \frac{2169}{508374} = \frac{3615}{847290}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1690}{247385} = \frac{2704}{395816} = \frac{5408}{791632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{280735} = \frac{2178}{360945} = \frac{4356}{721890}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{283507} = \frac{2178}{364509} = \frac{4356}{729018}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{283570} = \frac{2178}{364590} = \frac{4356}{729180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{350728} = \frac{2178}{450936} = \frac{4356}{901872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{352807} = \frac{2178}{453609} = \frac{4356}{907218}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{357028} = \frac{2178}{459036} = \frac{4356}{918072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1694}{357280} = \frac{2178}{459360} = \frac{4356}{918720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1695}{247380} = \frac{4068}{593712} = \frac{5763}{841092}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1698}{403275} = \frac{1938}{460275} = \frac{1972}{468350}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1702}{364598} = \frac{2369}{507481} = \frac{3289}{704561}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1703}{296584} = \frac{3549}{618072} = \frac{5213}{907864}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1704}{382956} = \frac{2130}{478695} = \frac{3408}{765912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1705}{482639} = \frac{1870}{529346} = \frac{3410}{965278}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1706}{392548} = \frac{3412}{785096} = \frac{4265}{981370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1708}{243695} = \frac{4872}{695130} = \frac{6132}{874905}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1708}{392546} = \frac{3416}{785092} = \frac{4270}{981365}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1708}{394526} = \frac{3416}{789052} = \frac{4270}{986315}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1725}{380946} = \frac{2875}{634910} = \frac{3450}{761892}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1726}{359048} = \frac{3452}{718096} = \frac{4315}{897620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1726}{394508} = \frac{3452}{789016} = \frac{4315}{986270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1726}{409538} = \frac{2589}{614307} = \frac{3452}{819076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1728}{349650} = \frac{1824}{369075} = \frac{2368}{479150}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1728}{356940} = \frac{3248}{670915} = \frac{4256}{879130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1728}{359046} = \frac{3456}{718092} = \frac{4320}{897615}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1728}{493560} = \frac{1872}{534690} = \frac{3456}{987120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{308465} = \frac{2639}{470815} = \frac{5278}{941630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{384560} = \frac{3458}{769120} = \frac{4368}{971520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1729}{458360} = \frac{1976}{523840} = \frac{3458}{916720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1734}{298605} = \frac{3468}{597210} = \frac{5712}{983640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{250984} = \frac{3472}{501968} = \frac{4123}{596087}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{290458} = \frac{3472}{580916} = \frac{4216}{705398}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1736}{458290} = \frac{1984}{523760} = \frac{3472}{916580}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1738}{290546} = \frac{2607}{435819} = \frac{3476}{581092}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1739}{280645} = \frac{3478}{561290} = \frac{3854}{621970}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1739}{406852} = \frac{1927}{450836} = \frac{3854}{901672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{256398} = \frac{2610}{384597} = \frac{3480}{512796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{258396} = \frac{2610}{387594} = \frac{3480}{516792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{259638} = \frac{2610}{389457} = \frac{3480}{519276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{259836} = \frac{2610}{389754} = \frac{3480}{519672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{362598} = \frac{2610}{543897} = \frac{3480}{725196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{386952} = \frac{2175}{483690} = \frac{3915}{870642}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{396258} = \frac{2610}{594387} = \frac{3480}{792516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1740}{398256} = \frac{2610}{597384} = \frac{3480}{796512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1746}{290538} = \frac{2619}{435807} = \frac{3492}{581076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1746}{325089} = \frac{3298}{614057} = \frac{3492}{650178}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1746}{380925} = \frac{2910}{634875} = \frac{3492}{761850}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1746}{392508} = \frac{3492}{785016} = \frac{4365}{981270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1748}{260935} = \frac{3496}{521870} = \frac{4180}{623975}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1748}{360295} = \frac{1824}{375960} = \frac{3648}{751920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1748}{390526} = \frac{3496}{781052} = \frac{4186}{935207}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1748}{392506} = \frac{3496}{785012} = \frac{4370}{981265}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1750}{249368} = \frac{2750}{391864} = \frac{6375}{908412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1752}{386940} = \frac{2190}{483675} = \frac{3942}{870615}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1753}{208649} = \frac{3506}{417298} = \frac{7012}{834596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1753}{209864} = \frac{3506}{419728} = \frac{7012}{839456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1753}{240896} = \frac{3506}{481792} = \frac{7012}{963584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1753}{246089} = \frac{3506}{492178} = \frac{7012}{984356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1754}{209863} = \frac{3508}{419726} = \frac{7016}{839452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1754}{230896} = \frac{3508}{461792} = \frac{7016}{923584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1754}{238096} = \frac{3508}{476192} = \frac{7016}{952384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1754}{239608} = \frac{3508}{479216} = \frac{7016}{958432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1756}{203489} = \frac{3512}{406978} = \frac{7024}{813956}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1756}{203849} = \frac{3512}{407698} = \frac{7024}{815396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1756}{203984} = \frac{3512}{407968} = \frac{7024}{815936}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1756}{204839} = \frac{3512}{409678} = \frac{7024}{819356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1756}{243980} = \frac{3512}{487960} = \frac{5268}{731940}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1758}{203649} = \frac{3516}{407298} = \frac{7032}{814596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1758}{239046} = \frac{3516}{478092} = \frac{7032}{956184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1758}{239604} = \frac{3516}{479208} = \frac{7032}{958416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1758}{240396} = \frac{3516}{480792} = \frac{7032}{961584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1758}{246039} = \frac{3516}{492078} = \frac{7032}{984156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1759}{203648} = \frac{3518}{407296} = \frac{7036}{814592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1759}{204863} = \frac{3518}{409726} = \frac{7036}{819452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1759}{238046} = \frac{3518}{476092} = \frac{7036}{952184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1759}{246038} = \frac{3518}{492076} = \frac{7036}{984152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1760}{239458} = \frac{2640}{359187} = \frac{3520}{478916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1760}{254398} = \frac{2640}{381597} = \frac{5280}{763194}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1760}{348592} = \frac{3520}{697184} = \frac{4510}{893267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1760}{394582} = \frac{2640}{591873} = \frac{3520}{789164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1760}{438592} = \frac{3180}{792456} = \frac{3510}{874692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1760}{439582} = \frac{2160}{539487} = \frac{3520}{879164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1762}{394580} = \frac{2643}{591870} = \frac{3524}{789160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1762}{398054} = \frac{2643}{597081} = \frac{3524}{796108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1763}{204859} = \frac{3526}{409718} = \frac{7052}{819436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1763}{208549} = \frac{3526}{417098} = \frac{7052}{834196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1763}{209854} = \frac{3526}{419708} = \frac{7052}{839416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{203598} = \frac{3528}{407196} = \frac{7056}{814392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{209853} = \frac{3528}{419706} = \frac{7056}{839412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{239580} = \frac{3087}{419265} = \frac{3528}{479160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{305928} = \frac{2835}{491670} = \frac{3927}{681054}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{308952} = \frac{3528}{617904} = \frac{5236}{917048}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{358092} = \frac{2706}{549318} = \frac{4239}{860517}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1764}{382095} = \frac{3528}{764190} = \frac{4172}{903685}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1768}{549302} = \frac{1836}{570429} = \frac{2108}{654937}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1780}{235964} = \frac{3560}{471928} = \frac{7120}{943856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1780}{236459} = \frac{3560}{472918} = \frac{7120}{945836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1780}{239456} = \frac{2670}{359184} = \frac{3560}{478912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1780}{239564} = \frac{3560}{479128} = \frac{5340}{718692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1780}{239654} = \frac{2670}{359481} = \frac{5340}{718962}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1780}{246359} = \frac{3560}{492718} = \frac{7120}{985436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1780}{256394} = \frac{2670}{384591} = \frac{5340}{769182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1780}{394562} = \frac{2670}{591843} = \frac{3560}{789124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{305694} = \frac{4653}{798201} = \frac{5346}{917082}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{364905} = \frac{3410}{698275} = \frac{3564}{729810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{394560} = \frac{2673}{591840} = \frac{3564}{789120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{396054} = \frac{2673}{594081} = \frac{3564}{792108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1782}{439560} = \frac{2187}{539460} = \frac{3564}{879120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1784}{239506} = \frac{3568}{479012} = \frac{7136}{958024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1784}{239560} = \frac{3568}{479120} = \frac{7136}{958240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1784}{239605} = \frac{3568}{479210} = \frac{7136}{958420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{206349} = \frac{3570}{412698} = \frac{7140}{825396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{230964} = \frac{3570}{461928} = \frac{7140}{923856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{234906} = \frac{3570}{469812} = \frac{7230}{951468}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{240963} = \frac{3570}{481926} = \frac{7140}{963852}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{246309} = \frac{3570}{492618} = \frac{7140}{985236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{309264} = \frac{1890}{327456} = \frac{3780}{654912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1785}{326094} = \frac{1890}{345276} = \frac{4725}{863190}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1786}{230945} = \frac{2914}{376805} = \frac{3572}{461890}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1786}{235094} = \frac{5396}{710284} = \frac{6042}{795318}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1786}{249053} = \frac{3572}{498106} = \frac{4902}{683571}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1786}{342095} = \frac{3572}{684190} = \frac{3948}{756210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1786}{345920} = \frac{3572}{691840} = \frac{4123}{798560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1789}{234506} = \frac{3578}{469012} = \frac{7156}{938024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1789}{234560} = \frac{3578}{469120} = \frac{7156}{938240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1789}{234605} = \frac{3578}{469210} = \frac{7156}{938420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1790}{236458} = \frac{3580}{472916} = \frac{7160}{945832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1790}{238456} = \frac{3580}{476912} = \frac{7160}{953824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1790}{245863} = \frac{3580}{491726} = \frac{7160}{983452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1790}{246358} = \frac{3580}{492716} = \frac{7160}{985432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1790}{326854} = \frac{1895}{346027} = \frac{2530}{461978}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1790}{536284} = \frac{2735}{819406} = \frac{3065}{918274}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1792}{384560} = \frac{3248}{697015} = \frac{3584}{769120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1792}{386540} = \frac{4032}{869715} = \frac{4160}{897325}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1792}{450863} = \frac{2304}{579681} = \frac{3584}{901726}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1792}{458360} = \frac{3584}{916720} = \frac{3680}{941275}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1792}{803456} = \frac{1904}{853672} = \frac{1946}{872503}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1794}{203658} = \frac{2691}{305487} = \frac{5382}{610974}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1794}{238056} = \frac{2691}{357084} = \frac{7245}{961380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1794}{256380} = \frac{2691}{384570} = \frac{5382}{769140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1794}{305682} = \frac{3289}{560417} = \frac{5382}{917046}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1795}{230864} = \frac{3590}{461728} = \frac{7180}{923456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1795}{236408} = \frac{3590}{472816} = \frac{7180}{945632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1795}{238406} = \frac{3590}{476812} = \frac{7180}{953624}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1795}{240863} = \frac{3590}{481726} = \frac{7180}{963452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1796}{203584} = \frac{3592}{407168} = \frac{8531}{967024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1796}{205438} = \frac{2694}{308157} = \frac{3592}{410876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1796}{238054} = \frac{2694}{357081} = \frac{3592}{476108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1796}{238405} = \frac{3592}{476810} = \frac{7184}{953620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1796}{380542} = \frac{2694}{570813} = \frac{3592}{761084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1796}{382054} = \frac{2694}{573081} = \frac{3592}{764108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{205436} = \frac{2697}{308154} = \frac{3596}{410872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{234056} = \frac{2697}{351084} = \frac{5394}{702168}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{235406} = \frac{3596}{470812} = \frac{5394}{706218}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{235604} = \frac{3596}{471208} = \frac{5394}{706812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{240356} = \frac{3596}{480712} = \frac{5394}{721068}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{240536} = \frac{3596}{481072} = \frac{5394}{721608}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{254036} = \frac{2697}{381054} = \frac{5394}{762108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{256034} = \frac{2697}{384051} = \frac{5394}{768102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{360542} = \frac{2697}{540813} = \frac{3596}{721084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{362054} = \frac{2697}{543081} = \frac{3596}{724108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1798}{405623} = \frac{3410}{769285} = \frac{4278}{965103}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1802}{359764} = \frac{3145}{627890} = \frac{3604}{719528}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1802}{379456} = \frac{2703}{569184} = \frac{3604}{758912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1802}{394576} = \frac{2703}{591864} = \frac{3604}{789152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1804}{237596} = \frac{3608}{475192} = \frac{7216}{950384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1804}{239576} = \frac{3608}{479152} = \frac{7216}{958304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1804}{567932} = \frac{2673}{841509} = \frac{3058}{962714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1806}{253974} = \frac{3612}{507948} = \frac{3741}{526089}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1806}{273945} = \frac{3268}{495710} = \frac{3612}{547890}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1809}{237546} = \frac{3618}{475092} = \frac{7236}{950184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1809}{245376} = \frac{3618}{490752} = \frac{7236}{981504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1820}{367549} = \frac{3560}{718942} = \frac{4780}{965321}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1820}{379456} = \frac{2730}{569184} = \frac{3640}{758912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1820}{394576} = \frac{2730}{591864} = \frac{3640}{789152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1820}{457639} = \frac{3160}{794582} = \frac{3640}{915278}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1820}{576394} = \frac{2430}{769581} = \frac{2730}{864591}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1824}{357960} = \frac{3648}{715920} = \frac{4872}{956130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1824}{359760} = \frac{3648}{719520} = \frac{4370}{861925}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1824}{709536} = \frac{2154}{837906} = \frac{2463}{958107}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1825}{349670} = \frac{4195}{803762} = \frac{4310}{825796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1825}{796430} = \frac{2015}{879346} = \frac{2145}{936078}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1829}{346507} = \frac{3069}{581427} = \frac{5084}{963172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1835}{206479} = \frac{3670}{412958} = \frac{7340}{825916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1836}{240975} = \frac{3672}{481950} = \frac{3780}{496125}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1836}{259740} = \frac{2754}{389610} = \frac{3672}{519480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1836}{457029} = \frac{2856}{710934} = \frac{3672}{914058}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1839}{204756} = \frac{3678}{409512} = \frac{7356}{819024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1839}{205476} = \frac{3678}{410952} = \frac{7356}{821904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1840}{235796} = \frac{3680}{471592} = \frac{4380}{561297}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1840}{235976} = \frac{3680}{471952} = \frac{5290}{678431}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1840}{237956} = \frac{3680}{475912} = \frac{7360}{951824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1840}{293756} = \frac{4820}{769513} = \frac{5160}{823794}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1845}{237906} = \frac{3690}{475812} = \frac{7380}{951624}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1846}{237905} = \frac{3692}{475810} = \frac{7384}{951620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1846}{273590} = \frac{2769}{410385} = \frac{3692}{547180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1849}{203756} = \frac{3698}{407512} = \frac{7396}{815024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1849}{205376} = \frac{3698}{410752} = \frac{7396}{821504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1852}{340976} = \frac{3241}{596708} = \frac{3704}{681952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1853}{207649} = \frac{3706}{415298} = \frac{7412}{830596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1853}{209764} = \frac{3706}{419528} = \frac{7412}{839056}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1854}{209763} = \frac{3708}{419526} = \frac{7416}{839052}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1854}{267903} = \frac{3924}{567018} = \frac{6210}{897345}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1856}{304792} = \frac{3016}{495287} = \frac{3712}{609584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1859}{204763} = \frac{3718}{409526} = \frac{7436}{819052}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1859}{320476} = \frac{2145}{369780} = \frac{3718}{640952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1859}{376420} = \frac{3549}{718620} = \frac{4732}{958160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1860}{459327} = \frac{3560}{879142} = \frac{3720}{918654}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{204759} = \frac{3726}{409518} = \frac{7452}{819036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{207549} = \frac{3726}{415098} = \frac{7452}{830196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{209754} = \frac{3726}{419508} = \frac{7452}{839016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{240795} = \frac{3726}{481590} = \frac{7452}{963180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{240975} = \frac{2691}{348075} = \frac{3726}{481950}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{245079} = \frac{3726}{490158} = \frac{7452}{980316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{245790} = \frac{3726}{491580} = \frac{7452}{983160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{257094} = \frac{5031}{694278} = \frac{6741}{930258}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1864}{209753} = \frac{3728}{419506} = \frac{7456}{839012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1864}{230795} = \frac{3728}{461590} = \frac{7456}{923180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1864}{235097} = \frac{3296}{415708} = \frac{3720}{469185}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1865}{273409} = \frac{2985}{437601} = \frac{4865}{713209}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1869}{375402} = \frac{3241}{650978} = \frac{4319}{867502}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1869}{730245} = \frac{1932}{754860} = \frac{2436}{951780}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1870}{329564} = \frac{3740}{659128} = \frac{4675}{823910}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1870}{432956} = \frac{3520}{814976} = \frac{3740}{865912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1872}{359064} = \frac{3016}{578492} = \frac{3692}{708154}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1875}{246093} = \frac{3750}{492186} = \frac{6875}{902341}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{205349} = \frac{3752}{410698} = \frac{7504}{821396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{230459} = \frac{3752}{460918} = \frac{7504}{921836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{230954} = \frac{3752}{461908} = \frac{7504}{923816}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{240953} = \frac{3752}{481906} = \frac{7504}{963812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{245309} = \frac{3752}{490618} = \frac{7504}{981236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1876}{245903} = \frac{3752}{491806} = \frac{7504}{983612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1879}{234506} = \frac{3758}{469012} = \frac{7516}{938024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1879}{234560} = \frac{3758}{469120} = \frac{7516}{938240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1879}{234605} = \frac{3758}{469210} = \frac{7516}{938420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1890}{265734} = \frac{1905}{267843} = \frac{6345}{892107}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1890}{274563} = \frac{3780}{549126} = \frac{5460}{793182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1890}{342657} = \frac{2970}{538461} = \frac{4590}{832167}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1890}{347625} = \frac{3906}{718425} = \frac{3948}{726150}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1896}{230754} = \frac{3792}{461508} = \frac{7584}{923016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1896}{240753} = \frac{3792}{481506} = \frac{7584}{963012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1896}{340752} = \frac{3792}{681504} = \frac{5214}{937068}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1896}{437502} = \frac{3268}{754091} = \frac{3420}{789165}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1903}{245876} = \frac{3806}{491752} = \frac{7612}{983504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1903}{267458} = \frac{2189}{307654} = \frac{6215}{873490}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1905}{237846} = \frac{3810}{475692} = \frac{7620}{951384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1905}{238476} = \frac{2540}{317968} = \frac{3810}{476952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1905}{283647} = \frac{2540}{378196} = \frac{3810}{567294}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1905}{286347} = \frac{2540}{381796} = \frac{3810}{572694}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1905}{427863} = \frac{2985}{670431} = \frac{4170}{936582}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1906}{237845} = \frac{3812}{475690} = \frac{7624}{951380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1906}{375248} = \frac{3812}{750496} = \frac{4765}{938120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1908}{235476} = \frac{3816}{470952} = \frac{7314}{902658}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1908}{237546} = \frac{3816}{475092} = \frac{7632}{950184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1908}{245376} = \frac{3816}{490752} = \frac{7632}{981504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1908}{364752} = \frac{2067}{395148} = \frac{3816}{729504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1908}{453627} = \frac{3024}{718956} = \frac{3816}{907254}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1908}{475236} = \frac{2067}{514839} = \frac{3816}{950472}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1920}{354768} = \frac{3120}{576498} = \frac{3240}{598671}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1920}{387456} = \frac{3405}{687129} = \frac{4095}{826371}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1924}{365708} = \frac{2704}{513968} = \frac{2873}{546091}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1924}{368705} = \frac{4316}{827095} = \frac{4732}{906815}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1926}{370458} = \frac{3852}{740916} = \frac{4173}{802659}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1926}{370548} = \frac{3852}{741096} = \frac{4815}{926370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1926}{374508} = \frac{3852}{749016} = \frac{4815}{936270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1927}{480356} = \frac{3572}{890416} = \frac{3854}{960712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1935}{760842} = \frac{2195}{863074} = \frac{2480}{975136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1936}{257840} = \frac{4598}{612370} = \frac{5368}{714920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1936}{475208} = \frac{2178}{534609} = \frac{3872}{950416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1936}{480752} = \frac{2541}{630987} = \frac{3872}{961504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1937}{458026} = \frac{3198}{756204} = \frac{3874}{916052}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1938}{462570} = \frac{3781}{902465} = \frac{3876}{925140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1940}{256378} = \frac{2910}{384567} = \frac{5820}{769134}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1943}{206857} = \frac{8576}{913024} = \frac{8643}{920157}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1946}{237580} = \frac{3892}{475160} = \frac{5143}{627890}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1946}{253708} = \frac{3892}{507416} = \frac{4309}{561782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1946}{372508} = \frac{3892}{745016} = \frac{4865}{931270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1947}{238065} = \frac{3861}{472095} = \frac{3927}{480165}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1947}{283605} = \frac{2596}{378140} = \frac{3894}{567210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1947}{325680} = \frac{2739}{458160} = \frac{5478}{916320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1948}{370526} = \frac{3896}{741052} = \frac{4870}{926315}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1948}{372506} = \frac{3896}{745012} = \frac{4870}{931265}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1952}{347680} = \frac{3172}{564980} = \frac{3294}{586710}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1953}{240876} = \frac{3906}{481752} = \frac{7812}{963504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1953}{286407} = \frac{3472}{509168} = \frac{3906}{572814}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1953}{482670} = \frac{2184}{539760} = \frac{2597}{641830}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1954}{230876} = \frac{3908}{461752} = \frac{7816}{923504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1954}{237608} = \frac{3908}{475216} = \frac{7816}{950432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1954}{238076} = \frac{3908}{476152} = \frac{7816}{952304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1956}{237840} = \frac{3912}{475680} = \frac{7824}{951360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1958}{237604} = \frac{3916}{475208} = \frac{7832}{950416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1958}{240376} = \frac{3916}{480752} = \frac{7832}{961504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1958}{376420} = \frac{3916}{752840} = \frac{4539}{872610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1960}{257348} = \frac{6490}{852137} = \frac{7120}{934856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1960}{257438} = \frac{2940}{386157} = \frac{3920}{514876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1960}{258374} = \frac{2940}{387561} = \frac{3920}{516748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1960}{374258} = \frac{2940}{561387} = \frac{3920}{748516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1960}{382574} = \frac{2940}{573861} = \frac{3920}{765148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1960}{475328} = \frac{3675}{891240} = \frac{3745}{908216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1962}{378054} = \frac{2943}{567081} = \frac{3924}{756108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1963}{240785} = \frac{3926}{481570} = \frac{7852}{963140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1964}{203578} = \frac{3928}{407156} = \frac{5892}{610734}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1964}{230785} = \frac{3928}{461570} = \frac{7856}{923140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1964}{235078} = \frac{3928}{470156} = \frac{7856}{940312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1964}{235780} = \frac{3928}{471560} = \frac{7856}{943120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1965}{408327} = \frac{3295}{684701} = \frac{3920}{814576}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1965}{430728} = \frac{2730}{598416} = \frac{3615}{792408}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1968}{307254} = \frac{4392}{685701} = \frac{4920}{768135}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1968}{350427} = \frac{2016}{358974} = \frac{5184}{923076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1968}{470352} = \frac{3459}{826701} = \frac{3726}{890514}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{256038} = \frac{2961}{384057} = \frac{3948}{512076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{256380} = \frac{2961}{384570} = \frac{3948}{512760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{258036} = \frac{2961}{387054} = \frac{3948}{516072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{258360} = \frac{2961}{387540} = \frac{3948}{516720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{358260} = \frac{3948}{716520} = \frac{5217}{946830}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{360258} = \frac{2961}{540387} = \frac{3948}{720516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{362580} = \frac{2961}{543870} = \frac{3948}{725160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{380256} = \frac{2961}{570384} = \frac{3948}{760512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1974}{382560} = \frac{2961}{573840} = \frac{3948}{765120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{203458} = \frac{2964}{305187} = \frac{5928}{610374}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{204358} = \frac{3952}{408716} = \frac{5928}{613074}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{205384} = \frac{3952}{410768} = \frac{7904}{821536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{205438} = \frac{2964}{308157} = \frac{3952}{410876}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{235840} = \frac{3952}{471680} = \frac{7163}{854920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{238054} = \frac{2964}{357081} = \frac{3952}{476108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{254380} = \frac{2964}{381570} = \frac{5928}{763140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{280345} = \frac{3016}{427895} = \frac{5936}{842170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{380542} = \frac{2964}{570813} = \frac{3952}{761084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{382054} = \frac{2964}{573081} = \frac{3952}{764108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{384052} = \frac{3458}{672091} = \frac{3952}{768104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{450832} = \frac{4108}{937256} = \frac{4173}{952086}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1976}{480532} = \frac{3496}{850172} = \frac{3724}{905618}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{205436} = \frac{2967}{308154} = \frac{3956}{410872}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{234056} = \frac{2967}{351084} = \frac{5934}{702168}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{235406} = \frac{3956}{470812} = \frac{5934}{706218}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{235604} = \frac{3956}{471208} = \frac{5934}{706812}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{240356} = \frac{3956}{480712} = \frac{5934}{721068}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1984}{203756} = \frac{3968}{407512} = \frac{7936}{815024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{178596} = \frac{3051}{267894} = \frac{4068}{357192}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{240536} = \frac{3956}{481072} = \frac{5934}{721608}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1984}{205376} = \frac{3968}{410752} = \frac{7936}{821504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{179658} = \frac{3051}{269487} = \frac{6102}{538974}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{254036} = \frac{2967}{381054} = \frac{5934}{762108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1984}{235760} = \frac{3968}{471520} = \frac{7192}{854630}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{179856} = \frac{3051}{269784} = \frac{4068}{359712}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{256034} = \frac{2967}{384051} = \frac{5934}{768102}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1984}{273056} = \frac{4092}{563178} = \frac{5146}{708239}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{185796} = \frac{3051}{278694} = \frac{4068}{371592}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{263504} = \frac{4301}{572968} = \frac{6854}{913072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1984}{376052} = \frac{3472}{658091} = \frac{3968}{752104}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{185976} = \frac{3051}{278964} = \frac{4068}{371952}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{360542} = \frac{2967}{540813} = \frac{3956}{721084}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1986}{274305} = \frac{3972}{548610} = \frac{5296}{731480}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{189756} = \frac{4068}{379512} = \frac{8136}{759024}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{362054} = \frac{2967}{543081} = \frac{3956}{724108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{365798} = \frac{3021}{548697} = \frac{4028}{731596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{196578} = \frac{3051}{294867} = \frac{6102}{589734}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{435206} = \frac{2107}{463589} = \frac{3956}{870412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{365978} = \frac{3021}{548967} = \frac{4028}{731956}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{197856} = \frac{3051}{296784} = \frac{4068}{395712}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1978}{435620} = \frac{3612}{795480} = \frac{3956}{871240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{376598} = \frac{3021}{564897} = \frac{4028}{753196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{198576} = \frac{3051}{297864} = \frac{4068}{397152}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1980}{235764} = \frac{3960}{471528} = \frac{6930}{825174}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{379658} = \frac{3021}{569487} = \frac{4028}{759316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{198756} = \frac{4068}{397512} = \frac{8136}{795024}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1980}{237456} = \frac{2970}{356184} = \frac{5940}{712368}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{396578} = \frac{3021}{594867} = \frac{4028}{793156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2036}{157984} = \frac{4072}{315968} = \frac{6108}{473952}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1980}{237564} = \frac{3960}{475128} = \frac{6105}{732489}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2014}{397658} = \frac{3021}{596487} = \frac{4028}{795316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2036}{159784} = \frac{4072}{319568} = \frac{6108}{479352}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1980}{243756} = \frac{3960}{487512} = \frac{5940}{731268}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2016}{345879} = \frac{4032}{691758} = \frac{4256}{730189}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2036}{174598} = \frac{3054}{261897} = \frac{6108}{523794}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1980}{254376} = \frac{2970}{381564} = \frac{5940}{763128}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2016}{379458} = \frac{3024}{569187} = \frac{4032}{758916}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2036}{179458} = \frac{3054}{269187} = \frac{4072}{358916}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1980}{256374} = \frac{2970}{384561} = \frac{3960}{512748}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2016}{394578} = \frac{3024}{591867} = \frac{4032}{789156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2036}{179584} = \frac{4072}{359168} = \frac{9671}{853024}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1980}{257436} = \frac{2970}{386154} = \frac{3960}{514872}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2018}{379456} = \frac{3027}{569184} = \frac{4036}{758912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2036}{194578} = \frac{3054}{291867} = \frac{4072}{389156}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1980}{362574} = \frac{2970}{543861} = \frac{3960}{725148}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2018}{394576} = \frac{3027}{591864} = \frac{4036}{789152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2036}{197458} = \frac{3054}{296187} = \frac{6108}{592374}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1980}{374256} = \frac{2970}{561384} = \frac{3960}{748512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{157986} = \frac{4068}{315972} = \frac{6102}{473958}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2037}{159468} = \frac{3801}{297564} = \frac{9408}{736512}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1982}{376054} = \frac{2973}{564081} = \frac{3964}{752108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2034}{159786} = \frac{4068}{319572} = \frac{6102}{479358}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2038}{159476} = \frac{4076}{318952} = \frac{8152}{637904}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2038}{179456} = \frac{3057}{269184} = \frac{4076}{358912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2038}{194576} = \frac{3057}{291864} = \frac{4076}{389152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2039}{184756} = \frac{4078}{369512} = \frac{8156}{739024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2041}{369578} = \frac{2158}{390764} = \frac{4082}{739156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2043}{158976} = \frac{4086}{317952} = \frac{8172}{635904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2043}{159876} = \frac{4086}{319752} = \frac{8172}{639504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2046}{157938} = \frac{4092}{315876} = \frac{8091}{624573}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2046}{183579} = \frac{4092}{367158} = \frac{7192}{645308}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2046}{187953} = \frac{5126}{470893} = \frac{9152}{840736}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2048}{135769} = \frac{4096}{271538} = \frac{8192}{543076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2048}{136759} = \frac{4096}{273518} = \frac{8192}{547036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2048}{159376} = \frac{4096}{318752} = \frac{8192}{637504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2048}{176359} = \frac{4096}{352718} = \frac{8192}{705436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2049}{135768} = \frac{4098}{271536} = \frac{8196}{543072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2049}{136758} = \frac{4098}{273516} = \frac{8196}{547032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2049}{175863} = \frac{4098}{351726} = \frac{8196}{703452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2049}{176358} = \frac{4098}{352716} = \frac{8196}{705432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2049}{183756} = \frac{4098}{367512} = \frac{8196}{735024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2049}{185763} = \frac{4098}{371526} = \frac{8196}{743052}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{163798} = \frac{3081}{245697} = \frac{4108}{327596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{163978} = \frac{3081}{245967} = \frac{4108}{327956}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{176398} = \frac{3081}{264597} = \frac{4108}{352796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{178396} = \frac{3081}{267594} = \frac{4108}{356792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{179638} = \frac{3081}{269457} = \frac{4108}{359276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{179836} = \frac{3081}{269754} = \frac{4108}{359672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{183796} = \frac{3081}{275694} = \frac{4108}{367592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{196378} = \frac{3081}{294567} = \frac{4108}{392756}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{197638} = \frac{3081}{296457} = \frac{4108}{395276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{197836} = \frac{3081}{296754} = \frac{4108}{395672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{361798} = \frac{3081}{542697} = \frac{4108}{723596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{378196} = \frac{3081}{567294} = \frac{4108}{756392}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{379618} = \frac{3081}{569427} = \frac{4108}{759236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{379816} = \frac{3081}{569724} = \frac{4108}{759632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{381796} = \frac{3081}{572694} = \frac{4108}{763592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{381976} = \frac{3081}{572964} = \frac{4108}{763952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{396178} = \frac{3081}{594267} = \frac{4108}{792356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{396817} = \frac{3042}{587691} = \frac{3068}{592714}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{397618} = \frac{3081}{596427} = \frac{4108}{795236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{397816} = \frac{3081}{596724} = \frac{4108}{795632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2054}{398176} = \frac{3081}{597264} = \frac{4108}{796352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2058}{179634} = \frac{3087}{269451} = \frac{6174}{538902}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2058}{197436} = \frac{3087}{296154} = \frac{6174}{592308}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2058}{367941} = \frac{3192}{570684} = \frac{4536}{810972}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2064}{139578} = \frac{4760}{321895} = \frac{5608}{379241}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2064}{179835} = \frac{4128}{359670} = \frac{8256}{719340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2064}{197835} = \frac{4128}{395670} = \frac{8256}{791340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2065}{479381} = \frac{3540}{821796} = \frac{4130}{958762}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2067}{918543} = \frac{2106}{935874} = \frac{2184}{970536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2069}{134785} = \frac{4138}{269570} = \frac{8276}{539140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2069}{147835} = \frac{4138}{295670} = \frac{8276}{591340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2075}{493186} = \frac{3150}{748692} = \frac{4150}{986372}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{153948} = \frac{4152}{307896} = \frac{8304}{615792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{154398} = \frac{4152}{308796} = \frac{8304}{617592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{154893} = \frac{4152}{309786} = \frac{8304}{619572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{154938} = \frac{4152}{309876} = \frac{8304}{619752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{391845} = \frac{4152}{783690} = \frac{4860}{917325}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{431895} = \frac{3460}{719825} = \frac{4152}{863790}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{491835} = \frac{3460}{819725} = \frac{4152}{983670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2076}{493185} = \frac{3460}{821975} = \frac{4152}{986370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2078}{149365} = \frac{4156}{298730} = \frac{8312}{597460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2078}{164935} = \frac{4156}{329870} = \frac{8312}{659740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2078}{549631} = \frac{2654}{701983} = \frac{3270}{864915}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2079}{148365} = \frac{2574}{183690} = \frac{4158}{296730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2079}{164538} = \frac{3108}{245976} = \frac{4158}{329076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2079}{183546} = \frac{4158}{367092} = \frac{7308}{645192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2079}{183645} = \frac{4158}{367290} = \frac{9234}{815670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2079}{451836} = \frac{3645}{792180} = \frac{4158}{903672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2085}{164793} = \frac{4170}{329586} = \frac{8340}{659172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2085}{493176} = \frac{3475}{821960} = \frac{4170}{986352}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2091}{368754} = \frac{2159}{380746} = \frac{3417}{602598}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2093}{147865} = \frac{4186}{295730} = \frac{8372}{591460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2093}{154876} = \frac{4186}{309752} = \frac{8372}{619504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2093}{164785} = \frac{4186}{329570} = \frac{8372}{659140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2093}{174685} = \frac{4576}{381920} = \frac{9152}{763840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2093}{175864} = \frac{6923}{581704} = \frac{8694}{730512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2093}{546871} = \frac{2198}{574306} = \frac{2583}{674901}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2098}{136754} = \frac{4196}{273508} = \frac{8392}{547016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2098}{154376} = \frac{4196}{308752} = \frac{8392}{617504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2098}{175364} = \frac{4196}{350728} = \frac{8392}{701456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2098}{176354} = \frac{4196}{352708} = \frac{8392}{705416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2106}{487539} = \frac{2196}{508374} = \frac{2598}{601437}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2109}{346875} = \frac{3021}{496875} = \frac{4218}{693750}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2109}{485736} = \frac{3021}{695784} = \frac{3591}{827064}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2134}{809756} = \frac{2365}{897410} = \frac{2376}{901584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2140}{365798} = \frac{3210}{548697} = \frac{4280}{731596}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2140}{365978} = \frac{3210}{548967} = \frac{4280}{731956}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2140}{376598} = \frac{3210}{564897} = \frac{4280}{753196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2140}{379658} = \frac{3210}{569487} = \frac{4280}{759316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2140}{396578} = \frac{3210}{594867} = \frac{4280}{793156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2140}{397658} = \frac{3210}{596487} = \frac{4280}{795316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2145}{607893} = \frac{2540}{719836} = \frac{2810}{796354}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2146}{537980} = \frac{2378}{596140} = \frac{3567}{894210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2146}{809375} = \frac{2436}{918750} = \frac{2610}{984375}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2156}{379048} = \frac{2695}{473810} = \frac{4312}{758096}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2158}{346970} = \frac{5146}{827390} = \frac{6142}{987530}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2158}{396740} = \frac{2639}{485170} = \frac{3419}{628570}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2160}{379458} = \frac{3240}{569187} = \frac{4320}{758916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2163}{478950} = \frac{2793}{618450} = \frac{3941}{872650}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2173}{584906} = \frac{2385}{641970} = \frac{2915}{784630}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2175}{348609} = \frac{3075}{492861} = \frac{4350}{697218}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2176}{304895} = \frac{2816}{394570} = \frac{5632}{789140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2176}{394580} = \frac{3264}{591870} = \frac{4352}{789160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2176}{398054} = \frac{3264}{597081} = \frac{4352}{796108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2178}{396054} = \frac{3267}{594081} = \frac{4356}{792108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2180}{379456} = \frac{3270}{569184} = \frac{4360}{758912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2180}{394576} = \frac{3270}{591864} = \frac{4360}{789152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2184}{375960} = \frac{4368}{751920} = \frac{5418}{932670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2189}{347056} = \frac{5731}{908624} = \frac{5742}{910368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2190}{568743} = \frac{2370}{615489} = \frac{2940}{763518}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2193}{460785} = \frac{3612}{758940} = \frac{4386}{921570}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2196}{378054} = \frac{3294}{567081} = \frac{4392}{756108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2198}{376054} = \frac{3297}{564081} = \frac{4396}{752108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2304}{169578} = \frac{6912}{508734} = \frac{7936}{584102}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2304}{187596} = \frac{4608}{375192} = \frac{9216}{750384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2304}{189576} = \frac{4608}{379152} = \frac{9216}{758304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2304}{195876} = \frac{4608}{391752} = \frac{9216}{783504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2304}{197856} = \frac{4608}{395712} = \frac{6048}{519372}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2309}{146785} = \frac{4618}{293570} = \frac{9236}{587140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2309}{178645} = \frac{4618}{357290} = \frac{9236}{714580}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2309}{187546} = \frac{4618}{375092} = \frac{9236}{750184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{157896} = \frac{4095}{276318} = \frac{4680}{315792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{175968} = \frac{7140}{536928} = \frac{9615}{723048}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{178596} = \frac{3510}{267894} = \frac{4680}{357192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{178956} = \frac{4680}{357912} = \frac{9360}{715824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{179586} = \frac{2470}{189563} = \frac{4680}{359172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{179856} = \frac{3510}{269784} = \frac{4680}{359712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{185796} = \frac{3510}{278694} = \frac{4680}{371592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{185976} = \frac{3510}{278964} = \frac{4680}{371952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{187956} = \frac{4680}{375912} = \frac{9360}{751824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{197856} = \frac{3510}{296784} = \frac{4680}{395712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{198576} = \frac{3510}{297864} = \frac{4680}{397152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2340}{597168} = \frac{3015}{769428} = \frac{3825}{976140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2345}{106789} = \frac{4690}{213578} = \frac{9380}{427156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2345}{106879} = \frac{4690}{213758} = \frac{9380}{427516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2345}{167098} = \frac{3045}{216978} = \frac{9170}{653428}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2345}{178906} = \frac{4690}{357812} = \frac{9380}{715624}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2345}{180967} = \frac{6370}{491582} = \frac{8295}{640137}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2345}{187906} = \frac{4690}{375812} = \frac{9380}{751624}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2346}{178905} = \frac{4692}{357810} = \frac{9384}{715620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2346}{187905} = \frac{4692}{375810} = \frac{9384}{751620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2349}{167508} = \frac{9512}{678304} = \frac{9541}{680372}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2351}{907486} = \frac{2463}{950718} = \frac{2471}{953806}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2354}{178690} = \frac{5786}{439210} = \frac{6842}{519370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2354}{179806} = \frac{4708}{359612} = \frac{7062}{539418}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2354}{197806} = \frac{4708}{395612} = \frac{7062}{593418}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2356}{179804} = \frac{4712}{359608} = \frac{7068}{539412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2356}{197804} = \frac{4712}{395608} = \frac{7068}{593412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2358}{146790} = \frac{4716}{293580} = \frac{9432}{587160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2358}{179640} = \frac{4716}{359280} = \frac{9432}{718560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2358}{197640} = \frac{4716}{395280} = \frac{8253}{691740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2359}{146780} = \frac{4718}{293560} = \frac{9436}{587120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2360}{179458} = \frac{3540}{269187} = \frac{4720}{358916}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2360}{194578} = \frac{3540}{291867} = \frac{4720}{389156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{105789} = \frac{7164}{320589} = \frac{9132}{408657}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{175980} = \frac{4728}{351960} = \frac{8274}{615930}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{178095} = \frac{4728}{356190} = \frac{9456}{712380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{179508} = \frac{4728}{359016} = \frac{9456}{718032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{179580} = \frac{4728}{359160} = \frac{9456}{718320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{180795} = \frac{4728}{361590} = \frac{9456}{723180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{195078} = \frac{4728}{390156} = \frac{9456}{780312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{195780} = \frac{4728}{391560} = \frac{9456}{783120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{197580} = \frac{4728}{395160} = \frac{8274}{691530}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2365}{419078} = \frac{3720}{659184} = \frac{3985}{706142}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2368}{140795} = \frac{4736}{281590} = \frac{9472}{563180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2368}{145079} = \frac{4736}{290158} = \frac{9472}{580316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2368}{145790} = \frac{4736}{291580} = \frac{9472}{583160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2369}{107548} = \frac{2987}{135604} = \frac{4738}{215096}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2369}{145078} = \frac{4738}{290156} = \frac{9476}{580312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2369}{145780} = \frac{4738}{291560} = \frac{9476}{583120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2369}{147805} = \frac{4738}{295610} = \frac{8326}{519470}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{180459} = \frac{4752}{360918} = \frac{9504}{721836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{190458} = \frac{4752}{380916} = \frac{9504}{761832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{194508} = \frac{4752}{389016} = \frac{6138}{502479}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{194580} = \frac{3564}{291870} = \frac{4752}{389160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{194805} = \frac{3168}{259740} = \frac{4752}{389610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{195408} = \frac{4752}{390816} = \frac{9504}{781632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{198054} = \frac{3564}{297081} = \frac{4752}{396108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{491508} = \frac{2970}{614385} = \frac{4752}{983016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{109465} = \frac{4756}{218930} = \frac{9512}{437860}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{150946} = \frac{4756}{301892} = \frac{9512}{603784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{159460} = \frac{4756}{318920} = \frac{9512}{637840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{160945} = \frac{4756}{321890} = \frac{9512}{643780}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{194560} = \frac{3567}{291840} = \frac{4756}{389120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{195406} = \frac{4756}{390812} = \frac{9164}{753028}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{195640} = \frac{4756}{391280} = \frac{7134}{586920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{196054} = \frac{3567}{294081} = \frac{4756}{392108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{196504} = \frac{4715}{389620} = \frac{7093}{586124}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2378}{196540} = \frac{3567}{294810} = \frac{7134}{589620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2379}{104568} = \frac{3965}{174280} = \frac{4758}{209136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2379}{106845} = \frac{4758}{213690} = \frac{9516}{427380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2379}{145068} = \frac{3965}{241780} = \frac{4758}{290136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2379}{164508} = \frac{3965}{274180} = \frac{4758}{329016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2379}{184506} = \frac{4758}{369012} = \frac{9516}{738024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2379}{184560} = \frac{4758}{369120} = \frac{9516}{738240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2379}{184605} = \frac{4758}{369210} = \frac{9516}{738420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{157946} = \frac{4760}{315892} = \frac{9520}{631784}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{159476} = \frac{4165}{279083} = \frac{4760}{318952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{169745} = \frac{5628}{401397} = \frac{5908}{421367}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{179456} = \frac{3570}{269184} = \frac{4760}{358912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{179564} = \frac{4760}{359128} = \frac{7140}{538692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{179654} = \frac{3570}{269481} = \frac{7140}{538962}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{194576} = \frac{3570}{291864} = \frac{4760}{389152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{197456} = \frac{3570}{296184} = \frac{7140}{592368}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2380}{495176} = \frac{3465}{720918} = \frac{4130}{859276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2384}{106795} = \frac{4768}{213590} = \frac{9536}{427180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2384}{179506} = \frac{4768}{359012} = \frac{9536}{718024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2384}{179560} = \frac{4768}{359120} = \frac{9536}{718240}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2384}{179605} = \frac{4768}{359210} = \frac{9536}{718420}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2385}{167904} = \frac{4170}{293568} = \frac{8730}{614592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2390}{178456} = \frac{4780}{356912} = \frac{9560}{713824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2395}{106784} = \frac{4790}{213568} = \frac{9580}{427136}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2395}{178406} = \frac{4790}{356812} = \frac{9580}{713624}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{23951}{40678} = \frac{47902}{81356} = \frac{53472}{90816}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2396}{175408} = \frac{4792}{350816} = \frac{9584}{701632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2396}{175804} = \frac{4792}{351608} = \frac{9584}{703216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2396}{178054} = \frac{3594}{267081} = \frac{4792}{356108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2396}{178405} = \frac{4792}{356810} = \frac{9584}{713620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2396}{180754} = \frac{4792}{361508} = \frac{9584}{723016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2397}{106845} = \frac{6439}{287015} = \frac{9682}{431570}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2397}{145860} = \frac{4371}{265980} = \frac{8742}{531960}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2397}{514086} = \frac{2941}{630758} = \frac{4165}{893270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2398}{174560} = \frac{3597}{261840} = \frac{7194}{523680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2398}{176054} = \frac{3597}{264081} = \frac{4796}{352108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2398}{541076} = \frac{3146}{709852} = \frac{4103}{925786}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2401}{358967} = \frac{3087}{461529} = \frac{6174}{923058}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2403}{175896} = \frac{4806}{351792} = \frac{9612}{703584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2403}{187596} = \frac{4806}{375192} = \frac{9612}{750384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2403}{189576} = \frac{4806}{379152} = \frac{9612}{758304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2403}{195876} = \frac{4806}{391752} = \frac{9612}{783504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2405}{178396} = \frac{4810}{356792} = \frac{9620}{713584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2405}{183796} = \frac{4810}{367592} = \frac{9620}{735184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2406}{178395} = \frac{4812}{356790} = \frac{9624}{713580}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2406}{183795} = \frac{4812}{367590} = \frac{9624}{735180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2407}{198536} = \frac{7163}{590824} = \frac{9251}{763048}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2408}{136795} = \frac{4816}{273590} = \frac{9632}{547180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2408}{175396} = \frac{4816}{350792} = \frac{9632}{701584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2408}{179536} = \frac{4816}{359072} = \frac{8127}{605934}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2408}{179635} = \frac{4816}{359270} = \frac{9632}{718540}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2408}{195376} = \frac{4816}{390752} = \frac{9632}{781504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2408}{195736} = \frac{3654}{297018} = \frac{9352}{760184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2408}{367951} = \frac{4816}{735902} = \frac{4928}{753016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2409}{165783} = \frac{5247}{361089} = \frac{7128}{490536}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2409}{175638} = \frac{5709}{416238} = \frac{6501}{473982}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2415}{307986} = \frac{2760}{351984} = \frac{4830}{615972}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2416}{798035} = \frac{2704}{893165} = \frac{2768}{914305}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2430}{157896} = \frac{4860}{315792} = \frac{9720}{631584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2430}{158796} = \frac{4860}{317592} = \frac{9720}{635184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2430}{586197} = \frac{3240}{781596} = \frac{3510}{846729}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2435}{186970} = \frac{3409}{261758} = \frac{9253}{710486}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2435}{196870} = \frac{3409}{275618} = \frac{9253}{748106}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2436}{105879} = \frac{3780}{164295} = \frac{6804}{295731}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2436}{159780} = \frac{4872}{319560} = \frac{5278}{346190}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2436}{175980} = \frac{4872}{351960} = \frac{5916}{427380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{106795} = \frac{4876}{213590} = \frac{7912}{346580}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{107965} = \frac{4876}{215930} = \frac{9752}{431860}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{150796} = \frac{4876}{301592} = \frac{9752}{603184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{157960} = \frac{4876}{315920} = \frac{9752}{631840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{160795} = \frac{4876}{321590} = \frac{9752}{643180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2438}{197560} = \frac{4876}{395120} = \frac{7314}{592680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2439}{106587} = \frac{3794}{165802} = \frac{5691}{248703}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2439}{175608} = \frac{8046}{579312} = \frac{9072}{653184}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2450}{139876} = \frac{3675}{209814} = \frac{7350}{419628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2453}{107689} = \frac{4906}{215378} = \frac{9812}{430756}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2453}{108769} = \frac{4906}{217538} = \frac{9812}{435076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2453}{176089} = \frac{4906}{352178} = \frac{9812}{704356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2453}{187609} = \frac{4906}{375218} = \frac{9812}{750436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2453}{189076} = \frac{4906}{378152} = \frac{9812}{756304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2453}{190876} = \frac{4906}{381752} = \frac{9812}{763504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2456}{178390} = \frac{4912}{356780} = \frac{9824}{713560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2456}{183790} = \frac{4912}{367580} = \frac{9824}{735160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2457}{103896} = \frac{3507}{148296} = \frac{8904}{376512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2457}{160839} = \frac{4563}{298701} = \frac{7683}{502941}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2457}{183690} = \frac{3591}{268470} = \frac{7182}{536940}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2458}{103769} = \frac{4916}{207538} = \frac{9832}{415076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2458}{136790} = \frac{4916}{273580} = \frac{9832}{547160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2458}{176039} = \frac{4916}{352078} = \frac{9832}{704156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2458}{190376} = \frac{4916}{380752} = \frac{9832}{761504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2459}{103768} = \frac{4918}{207536} = \frac{9836}{415072}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2459}{178630} = \frac{4918}{357260} = \frac{9836}{714520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2459}{180376} = \frac{4918}{360752} = \frac{9836}{721504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2459}{187603} = \frac{4918}{375206} = \frac{9836}{750412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{157839} = \frac{4920}{315678} = \frac{5740}{368291}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{157893} = \frac{4920}{315786} = \frac{9840}{631572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{157938} = \frac{4920}{315876} = \frac{9840}{631752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{158793} = \frac{4920}{317586} = \frac{9840}{635172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{159378} = \frac{4920}{318756} = \frac{9840}{637512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2460}{391578} = \frac{4920}{783156} = \frac{5740}{913682}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2463}{178590} = \frac{4926}{357180} = \frac{9852}{714360}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2463}{185079} = \frac{4926}{370158} = \frac{9852}{740316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2463}{185790} = \frac{4926}{371580} = \frac{9852}{743160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2463}{190785} = \frac{4926}{381570} = \frac{9852}{763140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2465}{107893} = \frac{4930}{215786} = \frac{9860}{431572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2465}{108793} = \frac{4930}{217586} = \frac{9860}{435172}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2465}{109378} = \frac{4930}{218756} = \frac{9860}{437512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2465}{139780} = \frac{3485}{197620} = \frac{5627}{319084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2468}{103759} = \frac{4936}{207518} = \frac{9872}{415036}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2468}{135079} = \frac{4936}{270158} = \frac{9872}{540316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2468}{135790} = \frac{4936}{271580} = \frac{9872}{543160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2469}{103758} = \frac{4938}{207516} = \frac{9876}{415032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2469}{107538} = \frac{4938}{215076} = \frac{9876}{430152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2469}{108753} = \frac{4938}{217506} = \frac{9876}{435012}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2469}{135780} = \frac{4938}{271560} = \frac{9876}{543120}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2471}{305698} = \frac{5684}{703192} = \frac{7245}{896310}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2475}{318690} = \frac{2695}{347018} = \frac{7480}{963152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2476}{193508} = \frac{4952}{387016} = \frac{6809}{532147}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2479}{160358} = \frac{4958}{320716} = \frac{9715}{628430}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2480}{367195} = \frac{2576}{381409} = \frac{3712}{549608}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2485}{176309} = \frac{4970}{352618} = \frac{6035}{428179}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2485}{179630} = \frac{5726}{413908} = \frac{6531}{472098}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2486}{301597} = \frac{3916}{475082} = \frac{7832}{950164}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2490}{157368} = \frac{6915}{437028} = \frac{9120}{576384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2490}{315786} = \frac{2905}{368417} = \frac{4980}{631572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2490}{365781} = \frac{3960}{581724} = \frac{4980}{731562}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2517}{460938} = \frac{4195}{768230} = \frac{5034}{921876}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2546}{187093} = \frac{5092}{374186} = \frac{6834}{502197}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2548}{370916} = \frac{2793}{406581} = \frac{5096}{741832}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{198374} = \frac{3840}{297561} = \frac{5120}{396748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{374198} = \frac{3840}{561297} = \frac{5120}{748396}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2560}{381974} = \frac{3840}{572961} = \frac{5120}{763948}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2573}{168490} = \frac{3689}{241570} = \frac{9827}{643510}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{103698} = \frac{5148}{207396} = \frac{9152}{368704}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{160398} = \frac{3861}{240597} = \frac{5148}{320796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{163980} = \frac{3861}{245970} = \frac{5148}{327960}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{198036} = \frac{3861}{297054} = \frac{5148}{396072}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2580}{396174} = \frac{3870}{594261} = \frac{5160}{792348}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2580}{397416} = \frac{3870}{596124} = \frac{5160}{794832}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2584}{371960} = \frac{4921}{708365} = \frac{5168}{743920}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2596}{374018} = \frac{3894}{561027} = \frac{5192}{748036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2596}{380174} = \frac{3894}{570261} = \frac{5192}{760348}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2598}{374016} = \frac{3897}{561024} = \frac{5196}{748032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2598}{374160} = \frac{3897}{561240} = \frac{5196}{748320}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2607}{143859} = \frac{5049}{278613} = \frac{9174}{506238}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2608}{195437} = \frac{2640}{197835} = \frac{5216}{390874}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2610}{453879} = \frac{2970}{516483} = \frac{5160}{897324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2618}{354970} = \frac{6103}{827495} = \frac{6817}{924305}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2618}{379540} = \frac{5423}{786190} = \frac{6358}{921740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2618}{394570} = \frac{5236}{789140} = \frac{6258}{943170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2635}{498170} = \frac{3162}{597804} = \frac{5134}{970628}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2639}{148057} = \frac{3596}{201748} = \frac{8961}{502743}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2649}{351807} = \frac{5298}{703614} = \frac{7064}{938152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2650}{137894} = \frac{3975}{206841} = \frac{7950}{413682}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2654}{137098} = \frac{3981}{205647} = \frac{5308}{274196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2670}{138594} = \frac{3560}{184792} = \frac{7120}{369584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2670}{139485} = \frac{3916}{204578} = \frac{7832}{409156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2671}{308549} = \frac{5342}{617098} = \frac{8013}{925647}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2673}{108549} = \frac{5346}{217098} = \frac{8019}{325647}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2673}{108945} = \frac{4752}{193680} = \frac{5346}{217890}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2673}{145089} = \frac{5346}{290178} = \frac{8019}{435267}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2673}{451089} = \frac{4752}{801936} = \frac{5346}{902178}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2673}{541890} = \frac{2783}{564190} = \frac{4532}{918760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2679}{184053} = \frac{3807}{261549} = \frac{7614}{523098}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2684}{139570} = \frac{5368}{279140} = \frac{6710}{348925}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2684}{351970} = \frac{3652}{478910} = \frac{5324}{698170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2685}{301794} = \frac{3725}{418690} = \frac{6245}{701938}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2685}{317904} = \frac{2970}{351648} = \frac{7305}{864912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2687}{145093} = \frac{5374}{290186} = \frac{8061}{435279}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2687}{145309} = \frac{5374}{290618} = \frac{8061}{435927}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2687}{309145} = \frac{5374}{618290} = \frac{8061}{927435}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2687}{314509} = \frac{5374}{629018} = \frac{8061}{943527}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2689}{145073} = \frac{5378}{290146} = \frac{8067}{435219}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2689}{145307} = \frac{5378}{290614} = \frac{8067}{435921}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2689}{307145} = \frac{5378}{614290} = \frac{8067}{921435}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2689}{314507} = \frac{5378}{629014} = \frac{8067}{943521}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2691}{308547} = \frac{5382}{617094} = \frac{8073}{925641}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2693}{108547} = \frac{5386}{217094} = \frac{8079}{325641}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2693}{145087} = \frac{5386}{290174} = \frac{8079}{435261}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2694}{138570} = \frac{3592}{184760} = \frac{7184}{369520}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2695}{108374} = \frac{5390}{216748} = \frac{9240}{371568}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2695}{471380} = \frac{5104}{892736} = \frac{5643}{987012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2697}{138054} = \frac{3596}{184072} = \frac{5394}{276108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2697}{140853} = \frac{5301}{276849} = \frac{5394}{281706}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2697}{154380} = \frac{2784}{159360} = \frac{9831}{562740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2697}{384105} = \frac{5146}{732890} = \frac{5394}{768210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2698}{410735} = \frac{3268}{497510} = \frac{5396}{821470}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2704}{139568} = \frac{5408}{279136} = \frac{8736}{450912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2704}{351689} = \frac{4720}{613895} = \frac{6192}{805347}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2706}{134589} = \frac{3608}{179452} = \frac{7216}{358904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2706}{148953} = \frac{2970}{163485} = \frac{3718}{204659}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2706}{189543} = \frac{5412}{379086} = \frac{6270}{439185}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2708}{391546} = \frac{4062}{587319} = \frac{5416}{783092}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2709}{153846} = \frac{3096}{175824} = \frac{5418}{307692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2709}{346185} = \frac{5418}{692370} = \frac{7482}{956130}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2709}{364518} = \frac{4386}{590172} = \frac{5418}{729036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2709}{465381} = \frac{5031}{864279} = \frac{5418}{930762}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2716}{354908} = \frac{4753}{621089} = \frac{5432}{709816}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2730}{158964} = \frac{5460}{317928} = \frac{6825}{397410}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2730}{186459} = \frac{5460}{372918} = \frac{6710}{458293}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2730}{189564} = \frac{5460}{379128} = \frac{6825}{473910}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2730}{194586} = \frac{5460}{389172} = \frac{8905}{634721}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2730}{195468} = \frac{3975}{284610} = \frac{4605}{329718}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2730}{451698} = \frac{2835}{469071} = \frac{5670}{938142}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2736}{159804} = \frac{5472}{319608} = \frac{9804}{572631}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2736}{419805} = \frac{4896}{751230} = \frac{5472}{839610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2738}{159046} = \frac{4107}{238569} = \frac{5476}{318092}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2738}{195064} = \frac{5476}{390128} = \frac{9435}{672180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2738}{461590} = \frac{4107}{692385} = \frac{5476}{923180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2739}{140685} = \frac{4598}{236170} = \frac{6974}{358210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2739}{501486} = \frac{3102}{567948} = \frac{3179}{582046}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2740}{136589} = \frac{5740}{286139} = \frac{9180}{457623}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2745}{180639} = \frac{5490}{361278} = \frac{7930}{521846}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2745}{189063} = \frac{5490}{378126} = \frac{7930}{546182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2745}{193086} = \frac{5490}{386172} = \frac{7320}{514896}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2745}{306891} = \frac{3720}{415896} = \frac{5490}{613782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2748}{159036} = \frac{5267}{304819} = \frac{5496}{318072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2748}{365910} = \frac{5496}{731820} = \frac{6412}{853790}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2790}{153864} = \frac{4185}{230796} = \frac{8370}{461592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2790}{186345} = \frac{3596}{240178} = \frac{7192}{480356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2790}{581436} = \frac{4305}{897162} = \frac{4680}{975312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2794}{156083} = \frac{7810}{436295} = \frac{8976}{501432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2795}{364081} = \frac{3705}{482619} = \frac{7410}{965238}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2805}{137496} = \frac{3795}{186024} = \frac{8910}{436752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2805}{163947} = \frac{3740}{218596} = \frac{5610}{327894}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2805}{413967} = \frac{5610}{827934} = \frac{6380}{941572}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2806}{397415} = \frac{4370}{618925} = \frac{5612}{794830}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2807}{169435} = \frac{3609}{217845} = \frac{7218}{435690}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{2807}{351694} = \frac{3609}{452178} = \frac{7218}{904356}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{2817}{360954} = \frac{4069}{521378} = \frac{5634}{721908}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2849}{157360} = \frac{3256}{179840} = \frac{5698}{314720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2867}{314509} = \frac{5734}{629018} = \frac{8601}{943527}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2835}{106947} = \frac{3780}{142596} = \frac{5670}{213894}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2853}{196407} = \frac{5072}{349168} = \frac{5706}{392814}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2869}{145073} = \frac{5738}{290146} = \frac{8607}{435219}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2835}{147069} = \frac{5670}{294138} = \frac{7560}{392184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2856}{170349} = \frac{4760}{283915} = \frac{5712}{340698}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2869}{145307} = \frac{5738}{290614} = \frac{8607}{435921}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2835}{169407} = \frac{3645}{217809} = \frac{7290}{435618}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2856}{370419} = \frac{3128}{405697} = \frac{5304}{687921}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2869}{307145} = \frac{5738}{614290} = \frac{8607}{921435}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2835}{174069} = \frac{5910}{362874} = \frac{6180}{379452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2859}{170346} = \frac{4765}{283910} = \frac{5718}{340692}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2869}{314507} = \frac{5738}{629014} = \frac{8607}{943521}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2835}{190647} = \frac{3780}{254196} = \frac{5670}{381294}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2860}{154973} = \frac{3960}{214578} = \frac{5940}{321867}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2870}{139564} = \frac{7910}{384652} = \frac{8960}{435712}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2839}{451067} = \frac{5627}{894031} = \frac{5678}{902134}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2860}{173459} = \frac{5720}{346918} = \frac{8760}{531294}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2870}{439561} = \frac{4270}{653981} = \frac{5320}{814796}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2840}{173596} = \frac{5680}{347192} = \frac{9230}{564187}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2860}{459173} = \frac{5720}{918346} = \frac{5840}{937612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2870}{463915} = \frac{3724}{601958} = \frac{4396}{710582}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2840}{356917} = \frac{4720}{593186} = \frac{4760}{598213}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2863}{597140} = \frac{3241}{675980} = \frac{3619}{754820}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2871}{369054} = \frac{4917}{632058} = \frac{6435}{827190}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{106935} = \frac{3796}{142580} = \frac{5694}{213870}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2863}{759104} = \frac{3416}{905728} = \frac{3465}{918720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2871}{459360} = \frac{4581}{732960} = \frac{6147}{983520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{109365} = \frac{3796}{145820} = \frac{5694}{218730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2864}{195730} = \frac{5728}{391460} = \frac{7160}{489325}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2873}{145069} = \frac{5746}{290138} = \frac{8619}{435207}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{135069} = \frac{5694}{270138} = \frac{7592}{360184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2865}{109347} = \frac{3820}{145796} = \frac{5730}{218694}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2873}{154960} = \frac{3978}{214560} = \frac{5967}{321840}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{135690} = \frac{5694}{271380} = \frac{7592}{361840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2865}{130947} = \frac{3820}{174596} = \frac{5730}{261894}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2873}{164905} = \frac{5746}{329810} = \frac{7293}{418605}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{136905} = \frac{3796}{182540} = \frac{5694}{273810}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2865}{143097} = \frac{5730}{286194} = \frac{7640}{381592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2873}{419560} = \frac{3718}{542960} = \frac{5746}{839120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{139065} = \frac{3796}{185420} = \frac{5694}{278130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2865}{149307} = \frac{5730}{298614} = \frac{7640}{398152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2873}{450619} = \frac{5369}{842107} = \frac{5746}{901238}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{160935} = \frac{3796}{214580} = \frac{5694}{321870}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2867}{145093} = \frac{5734}{290186} = \frac{8601}{435279}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2873}{451906} = \frac{5491}{863702} = \frac{5746}{903812}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{163905} = \frac{3796}{218540} = \frac{5694}{327810}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2867}{145309} = \frac{5734}{290618} = \frac{8601}{435927}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2874}{319506} = \frac{5748}{639012} = \frac{8143}{905267}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{190635} = \frac{3796}{254180} = \frac{5694}{381270}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2867}{153049} = \frac{3572}{190684} = \frac{3948}{210756}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2875}{164390} = \frac{3450}{197268} = \frac{8625}{493170}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2847}{193605} = \frac{3796}{258140} = \frac{5694}{387210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2867}{309145} = \frac{5734}{618290} = \frac{8601}{927435}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2875}{641930} = \frac{3650}{814972} = \frac{4350}{971268}$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{2890}{134657} = \frac{4590}{213867} = \frac{5780}{269314}$ | ▶ $\frac{2943}{176580} = \frac{4653}{279180} = \frac{5697}{341820}$ | ▶ $\frac{2967}{405318} = \frac{3519}{480726} = \frac{7038}{961452}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2890}{145367} = \frac{3290}{165487} = \frac{9120}{458736}$ | ▶ $\frac{2945}{307861} = \frac{8645}{903721} = \frac{8740}{913652}$ | ▶ $\frac{2968}{150374} = \frac{3604}{182597} = \frac{7208}{365194}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2890}{164375} = \frac{3468}{197250} = \frac{8670}{493125}$ | ▶ $\frac{2945}{317680} = \frac{5921}{638704} = \frac{6851}{739024}$ | ▶ $\frac{2970}{134865} = \frac{4356}{197802} = \frac{8712}{395604}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2891}{576430} = \frac{4312}{859760} = \frac{4851}{967230}$ | ▶ $\frac{2946}{318570} = \frac{5892}{637140} = \frac{8347}{902615}$ | ▶ $\frac{2970}{341685} = \frac{5478}{630219} = \frac{7392}{850416}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2893}{145067} = \frac{5786}{290134} = \frac{8679}{435201}$ | ▶ $\frac{2946}{370518} = \frac{5401}{679283} = \frac{5892}{741036}$ | ▶ $\frac{2970}{548163} = \frac{3510}{647829} = \frac{5130}{946827}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2896}{345710} = \frac{4912}{586370} = \frac{5968}{712430}$ | ▶ $\frac{2947}{153608} = \frac{5894}{307216} = \frac{9683}{504712}$ | ▶ $\frac{2985}{164307} = \frac{5970}{328614} = \frac{7960}{438152}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2906}{174538} = \frac{4359}{261807} = \frac{5812}{349076}$ | ▶ $\frac{2947}{186503} = \frac{4781}{302569} = \frac{5194}{328706}$ | ▶ $\frac{3015}{642798} = \frac{3185}{679042} = \frac{4305}{917826}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2907}{318546} = \frac{5814}{637092} = \frac{7695}{843210}$ | ▶ $\frac{2948}{157036} = \frac{4891}{260537} = \frac{5896}{314072}$ | ▶ $\frac{3016}{485927} = \frac{3712}{598064} = \frac{6032}{971854}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2907}{384516} = \frac{5491}{726308} = \frac{5814}{769032}$ | ▶ $\frac{2948}{357016} = \frac{5896}{714032} = \frac{6901}{835742}$ | ▶ $\frac{3021}{458679} = \frac{4293}{651807} = \frac{6042}{917358}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2908}{736451} = \frac{3516}{890427} = \frac{3820}{967415}$ | ▶ $\frac{2951}{467038} = \frac{3178}{502964} = \frac{3859}{610742}$ | ▶ $\frac{3024}{157896} = \frac{6048}{315792} = \frac{8190}{427635}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2910}{365748} = \frac{5820}{731496} = \frac{6790}{853412}$ | ▶ $\frac{2954}{167083} = \frac{5486}{310297} = \frac{6752}{381904}$ | ▶ $\frac{3024}{158796} = \frac{6048}{317592} = \frac{6804}{357291}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2914}{680357} = \frac{3290}{768145} = \frac{4230}{987615}$ | ▶ $\frac{2954}{367108} = \frac{5908}{734216} = \frac{6752}{839104}$ | ▶ $\frac{3024}{159768} = \frac{4806}{253917} = \frac{9612}{507834}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2937}{154860} = \frac{3564}{187920} = \frac{8712}{459360}$ | ▶ $\frac{2958}{173604} = \frac{5916}{347208} = \frac{8352}{490176}$ | ▶ $\frac{3024}{159876} = \frac{6048}{319752} = \frac{6804}{359721}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2940}{138567} = \frac{3920}{184756} = \frac{7840}{369512}$ | ▶ $\frac{2958}{460317} = \frac{4182}{650793} = \frac{4692}{730158}$ | ▶ $\frac{3042}{187956} = \frac{6084}{375912} = \frac{6591}{407238}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2940}{168357} = \frac{3780}{216459} = \frac{7560}{432918}$ | ▶ $\frac{2961}{374580} = \frac{3619}{457820} = \frac{7238}{915640}$ | ▶ $\frac{3051}{267489} = \frac{6102}{534978} = \frac{9153}{802467}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2940}{316785} = \frac{4836}{521079} = \frac{8376}{902514}$ | ▶ $\frac{2964}{130758} = \frac{4056}{178932} = \frac{7410}{326895}$ | ▶ $\frac{3051}{268749} = \frac{6102}{537498} = \frac{9153}{806247}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2940}{357168} = \frac{3780}{459216} = \frac{7560}{918432}$ | ▶ $\frac{2964}{138057} = \frac{3952}{184076} = \frac{7904}{368152}$ | ▶ $\frac{3051}{274689} = \frac{6102}{549378} = \frac{9153}{824067}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2940}{358617} = \frac{3920}{478156} = \frac{7840}{956312}$ | ▶ $\frac{2964}{158730} = \frac{5928}{317460} = \frac{7410}{396825}$ | ▶ $\frac{3051}{274869} = \frac{6102}{549738} = \frac{9153}{824607}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2940}{367815} = \frac{3276}{409851} = \frac{7140}{893265}$ | ▶ $\frac{2967}{138054} = \frac{3956}{184072} = \frac{5934}{276108}$ | ▶ $\frac{3051}{286749} = \frac{6102}{573498} = \frac{9153}{860247}$ |

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{3107}{285469} = \frac{6214}{570938} = \frac{9321}{856407} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{287069} = \frac{6290}{574138} = \frac{9435}{861207} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3192}{547086} = \frac{4620}{791835} = \frac{5376}{921408} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3108}{957264} = \frac{3156}{972048} = \frac{3165}{974820} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{289067} = \frac{6290}{578134} = \frac{9435}{867201} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3192}{584706} = \frac{3780}{692415} = \frac{5124}{938607} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3109}{268547} = \frac{6218}{537094} = \frac{9327}{805641} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{290687} = \frac{6290}{581374} = \frac{9435}{872061} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3194}{205768} = \frac{4791}{308652} = \frac{9582}{617304} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3109}{285467} = \frac{6218}{570934} = \frac{9327}{856401} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{290867} = \frac{6290}{581734} = \frac{9435}{872601} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3196}{240875} = \frac{6392}{481750} = \frac{9860}{743125} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3120}{479856} = \frac{4390}{675182} = \frac{6230}{958174} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3146}{527098} = \frac{4213}{705869} = \frac{5071}{849623} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3198}{250674} = \frac{4056}{317928} = \frac{6981}{547203} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3120}{647985} = \frac{3568}{741029} = \frac{4512}{937086} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3156}{402897} = \frac{4208}{537196} = \frac{6312}{805794} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3198}{267540} = \frac{3567}{298410} = \frac{7134}{596820} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3128}{457096} = \frac{3496}{510872} = \frac{5014}{732698} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3157}{289460} = \frac{6314}{578920} = \frac{9317}{854260} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3198}{450762} = \frac{5904}{832176} = \frac{6027}{849513} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3128}{467590} = \frac{3672}{548910} = \frac{4692}{701385} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3159}{407862} = \frac{3807}{491526} = \frac{7614}{983052} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3204}{159876} = \frac{5874}{293106} = \frac{6408}{319752} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3129}{405876} = \frac{5691}{738204} = \frac{6132}{795408} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3160}{284795} = \frac{5208}{469371} = \frac{9376}{845012} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3204}{167958} = \frac{4806}{251937} = \frac{9612}{503874} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3129}{460857} = \frac{3297}{485601} = \frac{5649}{832017} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3160}{458279} = \frac{3640}{527891} = \frac{5160}{748329} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3204}{195678} = \frac{4806}{293517} = \frac{9612}{587034} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3140}{257968} = \frac{4710}{386952} = \frac{8635}{709412} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3168}{205794} = \frac{4752}{308691} = \frac{9504}{617382} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3204}{198756} = \frac{6408}{397512} = \frac{9078}{563142} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{267089} = \frac{6290}{534178} = \frac{9435}{801267} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3172}{506849} = \frac{4628}{739501} = \frac{6084}{972153} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3206}{185479} = \frac{5038}{291467} = \frac{6412}{370958} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{268709} = \frac{6290}{537418} = \frac{9435}{806127} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3179}{240856} = \frac{5678}{430192} = \frac{9316}{705824} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3240}{189756} = \frac{6480}{379512} = \frac{9180}{537642} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{268907} = \frac{6290}{537814} = \frac{9435}{806721} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3186}{205497} = \frac{3870}{249615} = \frac{9810}{632745} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3245}{619087} = \frac{4235}{807961} = \frac{5170}{986342} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{269087} = \frac{6290}{538174} = \frac{9435}{807261} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3186}{294570} = \frac{6372}{589140} = \frac{9027}{834615} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3248}{109756} = \frac{5684}{192073} = \frac{7308}{246951} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{270689} = \frac{6290}{541378} = \frac{9435}{812067} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3186}{297054} = \frac{6372}{594108} = \frac{9027}{841653} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3248}{176059} = \frac{5376}{291408} = \frac{7280}{394615} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{270869} = \frac{6290}{541738} = \frac{9435}{812607} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3190}{264857} = \frac{4290}{356187} = \frac{6380}{529714} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3249}{156807} = \frac{7106}{342958} = \frac{9367}{452081} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{286709} = \frac{6290}{573418} = \frac{9435}{860127} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3190}{428765} = \frac{5962}{801347} = \frac{6490}{872315} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3256}{178904} = \frac{7659}{420831} = \frac{7918}{435062} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{3145}{286907} = \frac{6290}{573814} = \frac{9435}{860721} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3190}{648527} = \frac{3540}{719682} = \frac{4120}{837596} & \blacktriangleright \frac{3258}{106497} = \frac{4706}{153829} = \frac{9412}{307658} \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{3264}{105978} = \frac{3904}{126758} = \frac{5248}{170396}$	▶ $\frac{3289}{406571} = \frac{3718}{459602} = \frac{4693}{580127}$	▶ $\frac{3420}{185976} = \frac{5130}{278964} = \frac{6840}{371952}$
▶ $\frac{3264}{158970} = \frac{6528}{317940} = \frac{8160}{397425}$	▶ $\frac{3289}{617045} = \frac{3956}{742180} = \frac{4761}{893205}$	▶ $\frac{3420}{195786} = \frac{6270}{358941} = \frac{6840}{391572}$
▶ $\frac{3264}{189570} = \frac{6528}{379140} = \frac{8160}{473925}$	▶ $\frac{3290}{176485} = \frac{5418}{290637} = \frac{5768}{309412}$	▶ $\frac{3420}{197856} = \frac{5130}{296784} = \frac{6840}{395712}$
▶ $\frac{3264}{190587} = \frac{3456}{201798} = \frac{5184}{302697}$	▶ $\frac{3294}{175680} = \frac{3672}{195840} = \frac{5967}{318240}$	▶ $\frac{3420}{198576} = \frac{5130}{297864} = \frac{6840}{397152}$
▶ $\frac{3267}{108549} = \frac{6534}{217098} = \frac{9801}{325647}$	▶ $\frac{3401}{269857} = \frac{5012}{397684} = \frac{6802}{539714}$	▶ $\frac{3420}{597816} = \frac{3540}{618792} = \frac{5130}{896724}$
▶ $\frac{3267}{145089} = \frac{6534}{290178} = \frac{9801}{435267}$	▶ $\frac{3402}{178596} = \frac{5103}{267894} = \frac{6804}{357192}$	▶ $\frac{3421}{508796} = \frac{5467}{813092} = \frac{6523}{970148}$
▶ $\frac{3269}{108547} = \frac{6538}{217094} = \frac{9807}{325641}$	▶ $\frac{3402}{179856} = \frac{5103}{269784} = \frac{6804}{359712}$	▶ $\frac{3425}{187690} = \frac{6805}{372914} = \frac{8270}{453196}$
▶ $\frac{3269}{145087} = \frac{6538}{290174} = \frac{9807}{435261}$	▶ $\frac{3402}{185796} = \frac{5103}{278694} = \frac{6804}{371592}$	▶ $\frac{3451}{286790} = \frac{7134}{592860} = \frac{7598}{631420}$
▶ $\frac{3270}{416598} = \frac{5430}{691782} = \frac{6510}{829374}$	▶ $\frac{3402}{185976} = \frac{5103}{278964} = \frac{6804}{371952}$	▶ $\frac{3465}{108927} = \frac{5940}{186732} = \frac{6930}{217854}$
▶ $\frac{3276}{180594} = \frac{3458}{190627} = \frac{4186}{230759}$	▶ $\frac{3402}{197856} = \frac{5103}{296784} = \frac{6804}{395712}$	▶ $\frac{3465}{129087} = \frac{3960}{147528} = \frac{6930}{258174}$
▶ $\frac{3276}{185940} = \frac{3458}{196270} = \frac{4186}{237590}$	▶ $\frac{3402}{198576} = \frac{5103}{297864} = \frac{6804}{397152}$	▶ $\frac{3465}{187209} = \frac{7210}{389546} = \frac{7805}{421693}$
▶ $\frac{3276}{195804} = \frac{5148}{307692} = \frac{6903}{412587}$	▶ $\frac{3402}{597618} = \frac{4671}{820539} = \frac{5103}{896427}$	▶ $\frac{3465}{219780} = \frac{4851}{307692} = \frac{9702}{615384}$
▶ $\frac{3276}{594018} = \frac{3458}{627019} = \frac{4186}{759023}$	▶ $\frac{3409}{158762} = \frac{8407}{391526} = \frac{9702}{451836}$	▶ $\frac{3465}{289107} = \frac{4510}{376298} = \frac{6930}{578214}$
▶ $\frac{3276}{594180} = \frac{3458}{627190} = \frac{4186}{759230}$	▶ $\frac{3410}{278659} = \frac{6710}{548329} = \frac{8470}{692153}$	▶ $\frac{3468}{125970} = \frac{5984}{217360} = \frac{8670}{314925}$
▶ $\frac{3278}{504961} = \frac{5148}{793026} = \frac{5302}{816749}$	▶ $\frac{3410}{598672} = \frac{3520}{617984} = \frac{4290}{753168}$	▶ $\frac{3475}{298016} = \frac{7450}{638912} = \frac{9725}{834016}$
▶ $\frac{3286}{157940} = \frac{3596}{172840} = \frac{7192}{345680}$	▶ $\frac{3420}{178596} = \frac{5130}{267894} = \frac{6840}{357192}$	▶ $\frac{3479}{162085} = \frac{3976}{185240} = \frac{6958}{324170}$
▶ $\frac{3287}{140695} = \frac{6401}{273985} = \frac{6574}{281390}$	▶ $\frac{3420}{178695} = \frac{5796}{302841} = \frac{7620}{398145}$	▶ $\frac{3479}{185206} = \frac{5467}{291038} = \frac{6958}{370412}$
▶ $\frac{3287}{145069} = \frac{6574}{290138} = \frac{9861}{435207}$	▶ $\frac{3420}{179856} = \frac{5130}{269784} = \frac{6840}{359712}$	▶ $\frac{3480}{125976} = \frac{4860}{175932} = \frac{9720}{351864}$
▶ $\frac{3289}{145067} = \frac{6578}{290134} = \frac{9867}{435201}$	▶ $\frac{3420}{185796} = \frac{5130}{278694} = \frac{6840}{371592}$	▶ $\frac{3480}{172695} = \frac{7216}{358094} = \frac{7864}{390251}$

▶ $\frac{3608}{154297} = \frac{7216}{308594} = \frac{9512}{406783}$	▶ $\frac{3648}{157920} = \frac{7296}{315840} = \frac{9652}{417830}$	▶ $\frac{3706}{281945} = \frac{7412}{563890} = \frac{9810}{746325}$
▶ $\frac{3608}{154792} = \frac{5617}{240983} = \frac{7216}{309584}$	▶ $\frac{3649}{105287} = \frac{7503}{216489} = \frac{9307}{268541}$	▶ $\frac{3706}{291584} = \frac{4578}{360192} = \frac{9156}{720384}$
▶ $\frac{3608}{297154} = \frac{7216}{594308} = \frac{9512}{783406}$	▶ $\frac{3654}{179802} = \frac{5481}{269703} = \frac{8352}{410976}$	▶ $\frac{3708}{154296} = \frac{4635}{192870} = \frac{7416}{308592}$
▶ $\frac{3615}{870492} = \frac{3705}{892164} = \frac{4035}{971628}$	▶ $\frac{3654}{297108} = \frac{7308}{594216} = \frac{8352}{679104}$	▶ $\frac{3708}{192546} = \frac{7416}{385092} = \frac{9270}{481365}$
▶ $\frac{3618}{259740} = \frac{5427}{389610} = \frac{7236}{519480}$	▶ $\frac{3658}{120497} = \frac{5782}{190463} = \frac{6490}{213785}$	▶ $\frac{3708}{194526} = \frac{7416}{389052} = \frac{9270}{486315}$
▶ $\frac{3618}{457029} = \frac{5628}{710934} = \frac{7236}{914058}$	▶ $\frac{3670}{145928} = \frac{7340}{291856} = \frac{9175}{364820}$	▶ $\frac{3710}{289645} = \frac{8092}{631754} = \frac{9310}{726845}$
▶ $\frac{3618}{592704} = \frac{5092}{834176} = \frac{5293}{867104}$	▶ $\frac{3674}{159280} = \frac{8517}{369240} = \frac{9853}{427160}$	▶ $\frac{3712}{548096} = \frac{4901}{723658} = \frac{6583}{972014}$
▶ $\frac{3619}{504827} = \frac{4081}{569273} = \frac{5621}{784093}$	▶ $\frac{3674}{280951} = \frac{6012}{459738} = \frac{7348}{561902}$	▶ $\frac{3716}{450928} = \frac{6503}{789124} = \frac{7432}{901856}$
▶ $\frac{3620}{179458} = \frac{5430}{269187} = \frac{7240}{358916}$	▶ $\frac{3675}{198240} = \frac{7245}{390816} = \frac{9870}{532416}$	▶ $\frac{3720}{418965} = \frac{4712}{530689} = \frac{7512}{846039}$
▶ $\frac{3620}{194578} = \frac{5430}{291867} = \frac{7240}{389156}$	▶ $\frac{3675}{421890} = \frac{4890}{561372} = \frac{6135}{704298}$	▶ $\frac{3726}{190458} = \frac{7452}{380916} = \frac{8073}{412659}$
▶ $\frac{3624}{158097} = \frac{4032}{175896} = \frac{8064}{351792}$	▶ $\frac{3681}{479052} = \frac{6135}{798420} = \frac{7362}{958104}$	▶ $\frac{3726}{194508} = \frac{7452}{389016} = \frac{9315}{486270}$
▶ $\frac{3624}{159780} = \frac{7248}{319560} = \frac{7852}{346190}$	▶ $\frac{3682}{157094} = \frac{4208}{179536} = \frac{8416}{359072}$	▶ $\frac{3726}{194580} = \frac{5346}{279180} = \frac{7452}{389160}$
▶ $\frac{3627}{409851} = \frac{4716}{532908} = \frac{7164}{809532}$	▶ $\frac{3682}{170954} = \frac{4208}{195376} = \frac{8416}{390752}$	▶ $\frac{3726}{401598} = \frac{7452}{803196} = \frac{7613}{820549}$
▶ $\frac{3627}{480519} = \frac{3906}{517482} = \frac{7254}{961038}$	▶ $\frac{3685}{147290} = \frac{6901}{275834} = \frac{9514}{380276}$	▶ $\frac{3726}{419580} = \frac{7452}{839160} = \frac{7521}{846930}$
▶ $\frac{3640}{195728} = \frac{4830}{259716} = \frac{7280}{391456}$	▶ $\frac{3690}{187452} = \frac{5310}{269748} = \frac{8370}{425196}$	▶ $\frac{3726}{509841} = \frac{6102}{834957} = \frac{6210}{849735}$
▶ $\frac{3640}{278915} = \frac{4856}{372091} = \frac{5608}{429713}$	▶ $\frac{3692}{154780} = \frac{5694}{238710} = \frac{9217}{386405}$	▶ $\frac{3728}{140965} = \frac{7456}{281930} = \frac{9472}{358160}$
▶ $\frac{3640}{298571} = \frac{5720}{469183} = \frac{7240}{593861}$	▶ $\frac{3698}{214570} = \frac{3784}{219560} = \frac{7568}{439120}$	▶ $\frac{3728}{195064} = \frac{7456}{390128} = \frac{9786}{512043}$
▶ $\frac{3645}{128790} = \frac{5967}{210834} = \frac{7965}{281430}$	▶ $\frac{3705}{162849} = \frac{7410}{325698} = \frac{9165}{402837}$	▶ $\frac{3728}{450916} = \frac{6524}{789103} = \frac{7456}{901832}$
▶ $\frac{3645}{290871} = \frac{4095}{326781} = \frac{9180}{732564}$	▶ $\frac{3706}{192548} = \frac{7412}{385096} = \frac{9265}{481370}$	▶ $\frac{3740}{162598} = \frac{5610}{243897} = \frac{7480}{325196}$

$$\begin{aligned}&▶ \frac{3740}{196258} = \frac{5610}{294387} = \frac{7480}{392516} \\&▶ \frac{3740}{198256} = \frac{5610}{297384} = \frac{7480}{396512} \\&▶ \frac{3740}{256198} = \frac{5610}{384297} = \frac{7480}{512396} \\&▶ \frac{3740}{259618} = \frac{5610}{389427} = \frac{7480}{519236} \\&▶ \frac{3740}{259816} = \frac{5610}{389724} = \frac{7480}{519632} \\&▶ \frac{3740}{598162} = \frac{5610}{897243} = \frac{5720}{914836} \\&▶ \frac{3741}{295068} = \frac{6235}{491780} = \frac{7482}{590136} \\&▶ \frac{3745}{108926} = \frac{7945}{231086} = \frac{9345}{271806} \\&▶ \frac{3745}{160928} = \frac{4970}{213568} = \frac{7490}{321856} \\&▶ \frac{3745}{182609} = \frac{7490}{365218} = \frac{8560}{417392} \\&▶ \frac{3746}{192508} = \frac{7492}{385016} = \frac{9365}{481270} \\&▶ \frac{3748}{192506} = \frac{7496}{385012} = \frac{9370}{481265} \\&▶ \frac{3749}{182560} = \frac{7498}{365120} = \frac{9683}{471520} \\&▶ \frac{375}{4916082} = \frac{625}{8193470} = \frac{750}{9832164} \\&▶ \frac{3752}{140896} = \frac{8174}{306952} = \frac{9715}{364820} \\&▶ \frac{3752}{198064} = \frac{6097}{321854} = \frac{7504}{396128} \\&▶ \frac{3756}{129408} = \frac{4382}{150976} = \frac{8764}{301952} \\&▶ \frac{3756}{190248} = \frac{4695}{237810} = \frac{7512}{380496} \\&▶ \frac{3756}{219048} = \frac{4695}{273810} = \frac{7512}{438096}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}&▶ \frac{3760}{158249} = \frac{4720}{198653} = \frac{7520}{316498} \\&▶ \frac{3760}{194582} = \frac{5640}{291873} = \frac{7520}{389164} \\&▶ \frac{3760}{219458} = \frac{5640}{329187} = \frac{7520}{438916} \\&▶ \frac{3762}{194580} = \frac{5643}{291870} = \frac{7524}{389160} \\&▶ \frac{3762}{198054} = \frac{5643}{297081} = \frac{7524}{396108} \\&▶ \frac{3762}{450918} = \frac{4389}{526071} = \frac{7524}{901836} \\&▶ \frac{3768}{140952} = \frac{5024}{187936} = \frac{7536}{281904} \\&▶ \frac{3768}{149052} = \frac{5024}{198736} = \frac{7536}{298104} \\&▶ \frac{3768}{410952} = \frac{6908}{753412} = \frac{7536}{821904} \\&▶ \frac{3768}{459012} = \frac{6594}{803271} = \frac{7536}{918024} \\&▶ \frac{3780}{149625} = \frac{4860}{192375} = \frac{9612}{380475} \\&▶ \frac{3780}{156492} = \frac{4680}{193752} = \frac{7560}{312984} \\&▶ \frac{3780}{165942} = \frac{4230}{185697} = \frac{5670}{248913} \\&▶ \frac{3780}{194562} = \frac{5670}{291843} = \frac{7560}{389124} \\&▶ \frac{3780}{196452} = \frac{5740}{298316} = \frac{6580}{341972} \\&▶ \frac{3780}{215964} = \frac{6210}{354798} = \frac{7560}{431928} \\&▶ \frac{3780}{216594} = \frac{5670}{324891} = \frac{7920}{453816} \\&▶ \frac{3780}{219564} = \frac{4095}{237861} = \frac{7560}{439128} \\&▶ \frac{3780}{465912} = \frac{6930}{854172} = \frac{7560}{931824}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}&▶ \frac{3780}{549612} = \frac{4920}{715368} = \frac{6405}{931287} \\&▶ \frac{3781}{426059} = \frac{4712}{530968} = \frac{6251}{704389} \\&▶ \frac{3782}{160549} = \frac{3904}{165728} = \frac{7564}{321098} \\&▶ \frac{3782}{194560} = \frac{5673}{291840} = \frac{7564}{389120} \\&▶ \frac{3782}{510694} = \frac{3904}{527168} = \frac{4819}{650723} \\&▶ \frac{3784}{150629} = \frac{5896}{234701} = \frac{9240}{367815} \\&▶ \frac{3784}{205196} = \frac{7568}{410392} = \frac{8690}{471235} \\&▶ \frac{3784}{209516} = \frac{4730}{261895} = \frac{7568}{419032} \\&▶ \frac{3792}{184560} = \frac{6478}{315290} = \frac{7584}{369120} \\&▶ \frac{3796}{180542} = \frac{5694}{270813} = \frac{7592}{361084} \\&▶ \frac{3796}{182054} = \frac{5694}{273081} = \frac{7592}{364108} \\&▶ \frac{3796}{205418} = \frac{5694}{308127} = \frac{7592}{410836} \\&▶ \frac{3796}{208415} = \frac{5824}{319760} = \frac{7592}{416830} \\&▶ \frac{3796}{214058} = \frac{5694}{321087} = \frac{6278}{354019} \\&▶ \frac{3796}{218054} = \frac{5694}{327081} = \frac{7592}{436108} \\&▶ \frac{3798}{140526} = \frac{5346}{197802} = \frac{5643}{208791} \\&▶ \frac{3798}{160542} = \frac{5697}{240813} = \frac{7596}{321084} \\&▶ \frac{3798}{162054} = \frac{5697}{243081} = \frac{7596}{324108} \\&▶ \frac{3798}{205416} = \frac{5697}{308124} = \frac{7596}{410832}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{4062}{179835} = \frac{5416}{239780} = \frac{8124}{359670} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4065}{137982} = \frac{5420}{183976} = \frac{8130}{275964} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4068}{137295} = \frac{6984}{235710} = \frac{8136}{274590} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4081}{276395} = \frac{4378}{296510} = \frac{8294}{561730} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4089}{236175} = \frac{4698}{271350} = \frac{8091}{467325} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4092}{175863} = \frac{4356}{187209} = \frac{6380}{274195} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4095}{132867} = \frac{6435}{208791} = \frac{8190}{265734} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4095}{281736} = \frac{8190}{563472} = \frac{9315}{640872} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4095}{328671} = \frac{8190}{657342} = \frac{9360}{751248} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4095}{673218} = \frac{5310}{872964} = \frac{5670}{932148} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4097}{358126} = \frac{5389}{471062} = \frac{8619}{753402} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4098}{153726} = \frac{6147}{230589} = \frac{8196}{307452} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4120}{379658} = \frac{6480}{597132} = \frac{8240}{759316} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4136}{780952} = \frac{5104}{963728} = \frac{5148}{972036} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4137}{295680} = \frac{7683}{549120} = \frac{8274}{591360} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4150}{836972} = \frac{4650}{937812} = \frac{4825}{973106} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4152}{378096} = \frac{8304}{756192} = \frac{9342}{850716} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4158}{396270} = \frac{8019}{764235} = \frac{8316}{792540} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4172}{386059} = \frac{5012}{463789} = \frac{8204}{759163} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{4175}{382096} = \frac{8325}{761904} = \frac{8350}{764192} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4176}{235980} = \frac{7308}{412965} = \frac{8352}{471960} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4176}{239580} = \frac{7308}{419265} = \frac{8352}{479160} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4180}{326975} = \frac{4712}{368590} = \frac{5928}{463710} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4186}{352079} = \frac{4508}{379162} = \frac{9016}{758324} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4186}{572390} = \frac{6049}{827135} = \frac{6854}{937210} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4208}{197536} = \frac{8416}{395072} = \frac{9731}{456802} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4209}{135786} = \frac{5037}{162498} = \frac{9752}{314608} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4209}{518673} = \frac{6527}{804319} = \frac{7564}{932108} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4230}{187956} = \frac{8460}{375912} = \frac{9165}{407238} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4235}{180796} = \frac{7425}{316980} = \frac{8470}{361592} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4235}{698170} = \frac{4823}{795106} = \frac{4956}{817032} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4251}{396708} = \frac{6213}{579804} = \frac{8502}{793416} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4257}{196380} = \frac{7568}{349120} = \frac{8514}{392760} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4257}{601398} = \frac{5049}{713286} = \frac{6732}{951048} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4260}{315879} = \frac{5120}{379648} = \frac{6120}{453798} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4263}{590817} = \frac{4312}{597608} = \frac{4851}{672309} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4270}{396158} = \frac{8235}{764019} = \frac{8540}{792316} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4275}{198360} = \frac{5370}{249168} = \frac{6780}{314592} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{4290}{136578} = \frac{7590}{241638} = \frac{8415}{267903} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4290}{168375} = \frac{7436}{291850} = \frac{9724}{381650} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4290}{531687} = \frac{4730}{586219} = \frac{5940}{736182} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4290}{583176} = \frac{6175}{839420} = \frac{7085}{963124} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4293}{186705} = \frac{6413}{278905} = \frac{8162}{354970} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4298}{365701} = \frac{8596}{731402} = \frac{9210}{783645} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4305}{179862} = \frac{5740}{239816} = \frac{8610}{359724} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4305}{219876} = \frac{5740}{293168} = \frac{8610}{439752} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4316}{270985} = \frac{4980}{312675} = \frac{8632}{541970} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4362}{179805} = \frac{5816}{239740} = \frac{8724}{359610} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4365}{107982} = \frac{5820}{143976} = \frac{8730}{215964} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4370}{129865} = \frac{5842}{173609} = \frac{9614}{285703} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4378}{195206} = \frac{5174}{230698} = \frac{8756}{390412} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4379}{510682} = \frac{7395}{862410} = \frac{8352}{974016} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4380}{176295} = \frac{7104}{285936} = \frac{9072}{365148} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4382}{697051} = \frac{5614}{893027} = \frac{5726}{910843} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4386}{125970} = \frac{7654}{219830} = \frac{9761}{280345} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4386}{517290} = \frac{7293}{860145} = \frac{7854}{926310} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4387}{192065} = \frac{4879}{213605} = \frac{8241}{360795} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4387}{295610} &= \frac{6527}{439810} = \frac{8132}{547960} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4392}{768051} &= \frac{4512}{789036} = \frac{5376}{940128} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4396}{158270} &= \frac{8792}{316540} = \frac{9106}{327845} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4508}{173926} &= \frac{5978}{230641} = \frac{9016}{347852} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4509}{163728} &= \frac{8517}{309264} = \frac{9018}{327456} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4509}{172638} &= \frac{8517}{326094} = \frac{9018}{345276} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4509}{381762} &= \frac{8154}{690372} = \frac{9018}{763524} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4521}{398670} &= \frac{7392}{651840} = \frac{9361}{825470} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4521}{769803} &= \frac{4752}{809136} = \frac{5346}{910278} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4528}{190736} &= \frac{6509}{274183} = \frac{9056}{381472} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4531}{268709} &= \frac{8471}{502369} = \frac{9062}{537418} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4536}{179820} &= \frac{8190}{324675} = \frac{9702}{384615} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4536}{198072} &= \frac{6507}{284139} = \frac{8451}{369027} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4539}{218076} &= \frac{7921}{380564} = \frac{9078}{436152} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4539}{280617} &= \frac{8364}{517092} = \frac{9078}{561234} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4563}{182790} &= \frac{4732}{189560} = \frac{8619}{345270} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4571}{302869} &= \frac{7836}{519204} = \frac{9142}{605738} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4582}{369170} &= \frac{6478}{521930} = \frac{7426}{598310} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4587}{316920} &= \frac{5973}{412680} = \frac{7689}{531240} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4589}{326170} &= \frac{7413}{526890} = \frac{9178}{652340} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4590}{182763} &= \frac{4760}{189532} = \frac{8670}{345219} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4590}{187623} &= \frac{7820}{319654} = \frac{9180}{375246} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4592}{360178} &= \frac{9184}{720356} = \frac{9512}{746083} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4592}{367108} &= \frac{4756}{380219} = \frac{9512}{760438} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4598}{371602} &= \frac{6402}{517398} = \frac{9284}{750316} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4598}{716320} &= \frac{5643}{879120} = \frac{6251}{973840} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4608}{253917} &= \frac{7680}{423195} = \frac{9216}{507834} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4615}{237809} &= \frac{8165}{420739} = \frac{9230}{475618} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4617}{250938} &= \frac{7695}{418230} = \frac{9234}{501876} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4617}{253908} &= \frac{7695}{423180} = \frac{9234}{507816} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4617}{380295} &= \frac{4826}{397510} = \frac{7809}{643215} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4618}{273590} &= \frac{6927}{410385} = \frac{9236}{547180} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4620}{157839} &= \frac{8540}{291763} = \frac{9240}{315678} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4620}{197835} &= \frac{6804}{291357} = \frac{8652}{370491} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4620}{379158} &= \frac{8470}{695123} = \frac{9240}{758316} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4620}{397815} &= \frac{7420}{638915} = \frac{9436}{812507} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4623}{501897} &= \frac{6532}{709148} = \frac{7429}{806531} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4628}{153970} &= \frac{5824}{193760} = \frac{7098}{236145} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4628}{379051} &= \frac{5096}{417382} = \frac{7852}{643109} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4658}{302719} &= \frac{6028}{391754} = \frac{9042}{587631} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4671}{325809} &= \frac{7612}{530948} = \frac{8304}{579216} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4680}{215397} &= \frac{5160}{237489} = \frac{7920}{364518} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4683}{129507} &= \frac{5798}{160342} = \frac{8697}{240513} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4706}{389512} &= \frac{7046}{583192} = \frac{8541}{706932} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4715}{236980} &= \frac{6509}{327148} = \frac{7061}{354892} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4718}{392605} &= \frac{5796}{482310} = \frac{9436}{785210} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4725}{380916} &= \frac{6125}{493780} = \frac{9450}{761832} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4725}{389610} &= \frac{6930}{571428} = \frac{8190}{675324} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4726}{351809} &= \frac{8024}{597316} = \frac{9452}{703618} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4732}{159068} &= \frac{5304}{178296} = \frac{9152}{307648} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4736}{190528} &= \frac{8954}{360217} = \frac{9472}{381056} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4752}{190836} &= \frac{5148}{206739} = \frac{9504}{381672} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4752}{190863} &= \frac{8096}{325174} = \frac{9504}{381726} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4752}{193608} &= \frac{5346}{217809} = \frac{9504}{387216} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4752}{368091} &= \frac{7920}{613485} = \frac{9504}{736182} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4758}{130296} &= \frac{5369}{147028} = \frac{7358}{201496} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4758}{361920} &= \frac{5124}{389760} = \frac{9516}{723840} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4785}{129630} &= \frac{5049}{136782} = \frac{8745}{236910} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4785}{139260} &= \frac{7453}{216908} = \frac{8091}{235476} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4785}{260913} &= \frac{7590}{413862} = \frac{7920}{431856} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4785}{361920} &= \frac{6732}{509184} = \frac{7029}{531648} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4791}{368052} &= \frac{7985}{613420} = \frac{9582}{736104} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4792}{358016} &= \frac{5391}{402768} = \frac{9584}{716032} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4795}{261380} &= \frac{7261}{395804} = \frac{9316}{507824} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4805}{172639} &= \frac{5270}{189346} = \frac{9610}{345278} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4812}{375960} &= \frac{7218}{563940} = \frac{8421}{657930} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4812}{397560} &= \frac{7218}{596340} = \frac{8421}{695730} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4812}{590673} &= \frac{5204}{638791} = \frac{5964}{732081} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4836}{209157} &= \frac{7896}{341502} = \frac{8592}{371604} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4836}{519207} &= \frac{5704}{612398} = \frac{7564}{812093} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{1960273} &= \frac{815}{3294067} = \frac{920}{3718456} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{2106937} &= \frac{935}{4061827} = \frac{980}{4257316} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{2369710} &= \frac{569}{2780134} = \frac{963}{4705218} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{485}{3679210} &= \frac{509}{3861274} = \frac{563}{4270918} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4851}{309672} &= \frac{5782}{369104} = \frac{7203}{459816} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4890}{125673} &= \frac{7620}{195834} = \frac{9780}{251346} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4895}{201763} &= \frac{7590}{312846} = \frac{8910}{367254} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4901}{267358} &= \frac{7685}{419230} = \frac{9802}{534716} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4908}{351762} &= \frac{5726}{410389} = \frac{9816}{703524} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4913}{256870} &= \frac{7514}{392860} = \frac{9826}{513740} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4917}{256038} &= \frac{8195}{426730} = \frac{9834}{512076} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4917}{650832} &= \frac{5093}{674128} = \frac{7315}{968240} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4920}{135768} &= \frac{8610}{237594} = \frac{9840}{271536} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4921}{365708} &= \frac{5092}{378416} = \frac{6973}{518204} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4927}{380516} &= \frac{7839}{605412} = \frac{9854}{761032} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4928}{157360} &= \frac{5632}{179840} = \frac{9856}{314720} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4928}{310576} &= \frac{8316}{524097} = \frac{9064}{571238} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4928}{701536} &= \frac{5208}{741396} = \frac{5642}{803179} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4930}{172856} &= \frac{9715}{340628} = \frac{9860}{345712} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4932}{175086} &= \frac{5814}{206397} = \frac{9864}{350172} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4938}{250617} &= \frac{8230}{417695} = \frac{9876}{501234} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4956}{710832} &= \frac{5901}{846372} = \frac{6132}{879504} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4956}{870132} &= \frac{5208}{914376} = \frac{5481}{962307} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4960}{138725} &= \frac{6592}{184370} = \frac{7648}{213905} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4960}{517328} &= \frac{5890}{614327} = \frac{5980}{623714} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4962}{315087} &= \frac{6270}{398145} = \frac{9018}{572643} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4978}{360512} &= \frac{7429}{538016} = \frac{8493}{615072} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4986}{521037} &= \frac{6930}{724185} = \frac{7956}{831402} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5018}{274639} &= \frac{5642}{308791} = \frac{9802}{536471} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5024}{138796} &= \frac{6280}{173495} = \frac{7536}{208194} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5032}{174896} &= \frac{5476}{190328} = \frac{6845}{237910} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5032}{194768} &= \frac{5083}{196742} = \frac{7514}{290836} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5036}{482197} &= \frac{6072}{581394} = \frac{9152}{876304} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5049}{618732} &= \frac{7315}{896420} = \frac{7513}{920684} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5071}{243869} &= \frac{6809}{327451} = \frac{8371}{402569} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5074}{219386} &= \frac{6431}{278059} = \frac{9853}{426017} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5092}{183647} &= \frac{7068}{254913} = \frac{9652}{348107} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5094}{371862} &= \frac{5796}{423108} = \frac{8937}{652401} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5096}{317824} &= \frac{8134}{507296} = \frac{8673}{540912} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5103}{486972} &= \frac{7245}{691380} = \frac{9051}{863724} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5124}{379680} &= \frac{7381}{546920} = \frac{8357}{619240} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5140}{297863} &= \frac{7580}{439261} = \frac{7820}{453169} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5148}{307296} &= \frac{5187}{309624} = \frac{7059}{421368} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5184}{290736} &= \frac{7236}{405819} = \frac{8964}{502731} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{5184}{673920} = \frac{6273}{815490} = \frac{7281}{946530} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5192}{387640} = \frac{5782}{431690} = \frac{8732}{651940} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5243}{178690} = \frac{5684}{193720} = \frac{6958}{237140} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5246}{310978} = \frac{6837}{405291} = \frac{8901}{527643} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5267}{348910} = \frac{8473}{561290} = \frac{9847}{652310} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5267}{483190} = \frac{7429}{681530} = \frac{9453}{867210} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5280}{147936} = \frac{6435}{180297} = \frac{9570}{268134} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5280}{149376} = \frac{6325}{178940} = \frac{7315}{206948} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5291}{384670} = \frac{5476}{398120} = \frac{8547}{621390} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5302}{148697} = \frac{7458}{209163} = \frac{8690}{243715} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5304}{198276} = \frac{7854}{293601} = \frac{9418}{352067} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5307}{614829} = \frac{6832}{791504} = \frac{7503}{869241} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5310}{486927} = \frac{6370}{584129} = \frac{8230}{754691} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{534}{1627098} = \frac{549}{1672803} = \frac{798}{2431506} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5346}{207198} = \frac{5643}{218709} = \frac{9207}{356841} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5376}{291480} = \frac{6048}{327915} = \frac{7968}{432015} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5382}{490176} = \frac{6409}{583712} = \frac{9165}{834720} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5382}{647910} = \frac{5928}{713640} = \frac{6942}{835710} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5384}{127096} = \frac{6057}{142983} = \frac{8749}{206531} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{5396}{274018} = \frac{7952}{403816} = \frac{9230}{468715} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5401}{396728} = \frac{5731}{420968} = \frac{9845}{723160} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5423}{618970} = \frac{6351}{724890} = \frac{8526}{973140} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5460}{291837} = \frac{6720}{359184} = \frac{7980}{426531} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5472}{198360} = \frac{6984}{253170} = \frac{7308}{264915} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5472}{319086} = \frac{7920}{461835} = \frac{9216}{537408} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5480}{326197} = \frac{8760}{521439} = \frac{9640}{573821} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5487}{263190} = \frac{7198}{345260} = \frac{9853}{472610} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5490}{378261} = \frac{7890}{543621} = \frac{9480}{653172} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5629}{103487} = \frac{6578}{120934} = \frac{7046}{129538} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5629}{384071} = \frac{7462}{509138} = \frac{9048}{617352} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5643}{197802} = \frac{5814}{203796} = \frac{8721}{305694} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5671}{409382} = \frac{6731}{485902} = \frac{8745}{631290} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5687}{310294} = \frac{7865}{429130} = \frac{9801}{534762} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5704}{163928} = \frac{6279}{180453} = \frac{9154}{263078} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5709}{648231} = \frac{6512}{739408} = \frac{8206}{931754} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5720}{193864} = \frac{6370}{215894} = \frac{6435}{218097} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5736}{418920} = \frac{8126}{593470} = \frac{9321}{680745} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5738}{120649} = \frac{7296}{153408} = \frac{9576}{201348} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{5760}{329184} = \frac{6120}{349758} = \frac{9180}{524637} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5760}{491328} = \frac{7380}{629514} = \frac{9540}{813762} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5763}{290184} = \frac{6154}{309872} = \frac{9537}{480216} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5782}{143960} = \frac{6958}{173240} = \frac{8673}{215940} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5792}{186430} = \frac{9840}{316725} = \frac{9856}{317240} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5796}{342180} = \frac{6923}{408715} = \frac{8694}{513270} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5803}{479162} = \frac{8519}{703426} = \frac{8904}{735216} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5819}{670243} = \frac{6149}{708253} = \frac{7403}{852691} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5829}{134067} = \frac{7098}{163254} = \frac{8763}{201549} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5829}{460317} = \frac{8241}{650793} = \frac{9246}{730158} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5830}{429671} = \frac{5870}{432619} = \frac{8490}{625713} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5832}{176904} = \frac{7614}{230958} = \frac{9018}{273546} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5837}{491206} = \frac{7241}{609358} = \frac{7358}{619204} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5872}{413609} = \frac{5968}{420371} = \frac{9328}{657041} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5907}{163248} = \frac{9306}{257184} = \frac{9361}{258704} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5907}{614328} = \frac{5943}{618072} = \frac{7914}{823056} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5908}{214376} = \frac{6587}{239014} = \frac{9674}{351028} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5913}{204768} = \frac{6789}{235104} = \frac{7519}{260384} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{5916}{307284} = \frac{7514}{390286} = \frac{9826}{510374} \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{5940}{183276} = \frac{6270}{193458} = \frac{7590}{234186}$

▶ $\frac{5940}{327618} = \frac{6270}{345819} = \frac{7590}{418623}$

▶ $\frac{5960}{427183} = \frac{7480}{536129} = \frac{7840}{561932}$

▶ $\frac{5964}{173208} = \frac{6532}{189704} = \frac{9514}{276308}$

▶ $\frac{5970}{142683} = \frac{6270}{149853} = \frac{9840}{235176}$

▶ $\frac{5974}{218360} = \frac{8961}{327540} = \frac{9512}{347680}$

▶ $\frac{5976}{203184} = \frac{6435}{218790} = \frac{8145}{276930}$

▶ $\frac{5980}{724316} = \frac{6045}{732189} = \frac{7540}{913268}$

▶ $\frac{5984}{123760} = \frac{6952}{143780} = \frac{8492}{175630}$

▶ $\frac{6014}{379852} = \frac{7936}{501248} = \frac{9703}{612854}$

▶ $\frac{6018}{275943} = \frac{7854}{360129} = \frac{9078}{416253}$

▶ $\frac{6032}{791584} = \frac{7215}{946830} = \frac{7501}{984362}$

▶ $\frac{6120}{387945} = \frac{6392}{405187} = \frac{7208}{456913}$

▶ $\frac{6120}{753984} = \frac{6415}{790328} = \frac{7480}{921536}$

▶ $\frac{6123}{509847} = \frac{9106}{758234} = \frac{9734}{810526}$

▶ $\frac{6142}{307598} = \frac{7289}{365041} = \frac{9287}{465103}$

▶ $\frac{6150}{293847} = \frac{8650}{413297} = \frac{8950}{427631}$

▶ $\frac{6174}{358092} = \frac{7812}{453096} = \frac{7902}{458316}$

▶ $\frac{6193}{708254} = \frac{7359}{841602} = \frac{8415}{962370}$

▶ $\frac{6195}{480732} = \frac{7905}{613428} = \frac{8370}{649512}$

▶ $\frac{6204}{397518} = \frac{8742}{560139} = \frac{9870}{632415}$

▶ $\frac{6357}{204891} = \frac{8047}{259361} = \frac{9854}{317602}$

▶ $\frac{6370}{519428} = \frac{7385}{602194} = \frac{9345}{762018}$

▶ $\frac{6372}{504981} = \frac{6804}{539217} = \frac{7980}{632415}$

▶ $\frac{6381}{574290} = \frac{6471}{582390} = \frac{8361}{752490}$

▶ $\frac{6384}{579120} = \frac{8043}{729615} = \frac{8421}{763905}$

▶ $\frac{6394}{182507} = \frac{9016}{257348} = \frac{9568}{273104}$

▶ $\frac{6394}{801752} = \frac{6739}{845012} = \frac{7521}{943068}$

▶ $\frac{6409}{752318} = \frac{7215}{846930} = \frac{7345}{862190}$

▶ $\frac{6417}{539028} = \frac{8235}{691740} = \frac{9315}{782460}$

▶ $\frac{6420}{375891} = \frac{6540}{382917} = \frac{9840}{576132}$

▶ $\frac{6431}{285907} = \frac{7906}{351482} = \frac{8201}{364597}$

▶ $\frac{6435}{187902} = \frac{7380}{215496} = \frac{8730}{254916}$

▶ $\frac{6450}{182793} = \frac{9450}{267813} = \frac{9650}{273481}$

▶ $\frac{6478}{529310} = \frac{7821}{639045} = \frac{8532}{697140}$

▶ $\frac{6480}{193752} = \frac{8610}{257439} = \frac{9570}{286143}$

▶ $\frac{6498}{731025} = \frac{7146}{803925} = \frac{8370}{941625}$

▶ $\frac{6504}{298371} = \frac{7104}{325896} = \frac{8952}{410673}$

▶ $\frac{6528}{719304} = \frac{7392}{814506} = \frac{7632}{840951}$

▶ $\frac{6534}{120879} = \frac{7290}{134865} = \frac{8274}{153069}$

▶ $\frac{6578}{123409} = \frac{7452}{139806} = \frac{9384}{176052}$

▶ $\frac{6704}{389251} = \frac{9312}{540678} = \frac{9328}{541607}$

▶ $\frac{6723}{580419} = \frac{8154}{703962} = \frac{8451}{729603}$

▶ $\frac{6731}{508429} = \frac{7239}{546801} = \frac{8509}{642731}$

▶ $\frac{6780}{453921} = \frac{7980}{534261} = \frac{8420}{563719}$

▶ $\frac{6783}{124950} = \frac{6973}{128450} = \frac{7429}{136850}$

▶ $\frac{6785}{124903} = \frac{7820}{143956} = \frac{9085}{167243}$

▶ $\frac{6785}{139240} = \frac{7843}{160952} = \frac{7935}{162840}$

▶ $\frac{6804}{137592} = \frac{7938}{160524} = \frac{9072}{183456}$

▶ $\frac{6831}{257094} = \frac{9207}{346518} = \frac{9702}{365148}$

▶ $\frac{6831}{742095} = \frac{8327}{904615} = \frac{8426}{915370}$

▶ $\frac{6840}{159372} = \frac{7230}{168459} = \frac{7920}{184536}$

▶ $\frac{6849}{102735} = \frac{7263}{108945} = \frac{8469}{127035}$

▶ $\frac{6894}{172350} = \frac{8694}{217350} = \frac{9486}{237150}$

▶ $\frac{6903}{124785} = \frac{7956}{143820} = \frac{9243}{167085}$

▶ $\frac{6923}{107548} = \frac{8729}{135604} = \frac{9503}{147628}$

▶ $\frac{6924}{813570} = \frac{6930}{814275} = \frac{8310}{976425}$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{6930}{271845} = \frac{8976}{352104} = \frac{9504}{372816} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{6942}{351078} = \frac{7209}{364581} = \frac{9523}{481607} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{6970}{382415} = \frac{7052}{386914} = \frac{8610}{472395} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{6985}{147320} = \frac{9548}{201376} = \frac{9713}{204856} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7018}{245369} = \frac{8470}{296135} = \frac{8712}{304596} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7018}{635492} = \frac{8091}{732654} = \frac{8294}{751036} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7029}{154638} = \frac{9387}{206514} = \frac{9765}{214830} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7032}{649581} = \frac{7504}{693182} = \frac{8032}{741956} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7035}{129846} = \frac{8925}{164730} = \frac{9765}{180234} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7062}{498513} = \frac{7216}{509384} = \frac{8954}{632071} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7064}{159823} = \frac{7480}{169235} = \frac{8576}{194032} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7128}{539460} = \frac{8712}{659340} = \frac{8910}{674325} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7140}{398265} = \frac{7820}{436195} = \frac{8092}{451367} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7208}{135694} = \frac{7420}{139685} = \frac{9328}{175604} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{7409}{685213} = \frac{7502}{693814} = \frac{9052}{837164} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7420}{315986} = \frac{7560}{321948} = \frac{8120}{345796} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7425}{163890} = \frac{8745}{193026} = \frac{9845}{217306} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7426}{350918} = \frac{7614}{359802} = \frac{9071}{428653} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7460}{851932} = \frac{8360}{954712} = \frac{8530}{974126} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7482}{509163} = \frac{9048}{615732} = \frac{9512}{647308} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7524}{130986} = \frac{8602}{149753} = \frac{9482}{165073} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7536}{140829} = \frac{7952}{148603} = \frac{9536}{178204} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7598}{136240} = \frac{8352}{149760} = \frac{8497}{152360} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7598}{643210} = \frac{8642}{731590} = \frac{8932}{756140} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7632}{581940} = \frac{7932}{604815} = \frac{9864}{752130} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7690}{345281} = \frac{7860}{352914} = \frac{7890}{354261} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7695}{243810} = \frac{8645}{273910} = \frac{9063}{287154} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7905}{382416} = \frac{8160}{394752} = \frac{8925}{431760} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{7925}{408613} = \frac{8025}{413769} = \frac{8925}{460173} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7940}{213586} = \frac{8790}{236451} = \frac{9360}{251784} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7945}{312806} = \frac{9415}{370682} = \frac{9520}{374816} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{7964}{213580} = \frac{9614}{257830} = \frac{9713}{260485} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{8132}{679450} = \frac{8930}{746125} = \frac{9614}{803275} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{8375}{296140} = \frac{8950}{316472} = \frac{9675}{342108} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{8742}{365190} = \frac{9021}{376845} = \frac{9207}{384615} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{9086}{347215} = \frac{9268}{354170} = \frac{9842}{376105} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{9174}{358620} = \frac{9427}{368510} = \frac{9614}{375820} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{9372}{105648} = \frac{9526}{107384} = \frac{9548}{107632} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{9435}{120768} = \frac{9675}{123840} = \frac{9735}{124608} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{9465}{831027} = \frac{9540}{837612} = \frac{9720}{853416} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{9526}{103487} = \frac{9548}{103726} = \frac{9724}{105638} \end{aligned}$$

• **3-Digits Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{3574896} = \frac{174}{6098352} = \frac{273}{9568104} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{3594678} = \frac{187}{6590243} = \frac{204}{7189356} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{102}{4875396} = \frac{154}{7360892} = \frac{173}{8269054} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{2457689} = \frac{206}{4915378} = \frac{412}{9830756} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{2458769} = \frac{206}{4917538} = \frac{412}{9835076} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{2467589} = \frac{206}{4935178} = \frac{412}{9870356} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{2468759} = \frac{206}{4937518} = \frac{412}{9875036} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{2478695} = \frac{274}{6593810} = \frac{326}{7845190} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{103}{6845792} = \frac{135}{8972640} = \frac{145}{9637280} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2375968} = \frac{208}{4751936} = \frac{416}{9503872} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2376958} = \frac{208}{4753916} = \frac{416}{9507832} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2395768} = \frac{208}{4791536} = \frac{416}{9583072} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2396758} = \frac{208}{4793516} = \frac{416}{9587032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2746893} = \frac{210}{5493786} = \frac{315}{8240679}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{2365984} = \frac{213}{4709856} = \frac{435}{9618720}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2587936} = \frac{302}{7514968} = \frac{378}{9406152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2748693} = \frac{210}{5497386} = \frac{315}{8246079}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{2486359} = \frac{157}{3648209} = \frac{249}{5786013}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2859376} = \frac{216}{5938704} = \frac{301}{8275694}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2836947} = \frac{140}{3782596} = \frac{210}{5673894}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{2685493} = \frac{214}{5370986} = \frac{321}{8056479}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2956738} = \frac{208}{5913476} = \frac{260}{7391845}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2867493} = \frac{210}{5734986} = \frac{315}{8602479}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{2836549} = \frac{214}{5673098} = \frac{321}{8509647}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2957368} = \frac{169}{4805723} = \frac{208}{5914736}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2869347} = \frac{140}{3825796} = \frac{210}{5738694}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{2854693} = \frac{214}{5709386} = \frac{321}{8564079}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2967358} = \frac{208}{5934716} = \frac{260}{7418395}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2874693} = \frac{210}{5749386} = \frac{315}{8624079}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{2865349} = \frac{214}{5730698} = \frac{321}{8596047}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{2973568} = \frac{208}{5947136} = \frac{306}{8749152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2967384} = \frac{210}{5934768} = \frac{325}{9184760}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{3259648} = \frac{236}{7189504} = \frac{312}{9504768}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{3572698} = \frac{208}{7145396} = \frac{260}{8931745}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3267489} = \frac{210}{6534978} = \frac{315}{9802467}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{3268549} = \frac{214}{6537098} = \frac{321}{9805647}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{104}{3965728} = \frac{208}{7931456} = \frac{238}{9075416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3268749} = \frac{210}{6537498} = \frac{315}{9806247}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{3285469} = \frac{214}{6570938} = \frac{321}{9856407}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2346789} = \frac{210}{4693578} = \frac{420}{9387156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3274689} = \frac{210}{6549378} = \frac{315}{9824067}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{3285649} = \frac{137}{4206859} = \frac{263}{8075941}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2346879} = \frac{210}{4693758} = \frac{420}{9387516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3274869} = \frac{210}{6549738} = \frac{315}{9824607}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{3894265} = \frac{246}{8953170} = \frac{271}{9863045}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2378469} = \frac{210}{4756938} = \frac{420}{9513876}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3286749} = \frac{210}{6573498} = \frac{315}{9860247}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{4269835} = \frac{214}{8539670} = \frac{236}{9417580}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2379684} = \frac{210}{4759368} = \frac{420}{9518736}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3287469} = \frac{210}{6574938} = \frac{315}{9862407}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{107}{4683925} = \frac{139}{6084725} = \frac{214}{9367850}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2384679} = \frac{210}{4769358} = \frac{420}{9538716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3468927} = \frac{180}{5946732} = \frac{210}{6937854}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2375469} = \frac{216}{4750938} = \frac{432}{9501876}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2396784} = \frac{210}{4793568} = \frac{420}{9587136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3827469} = \frac{210}{7654938} = \frac{245}{8930761}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2376954} = \frac{216}{4753908} = \frac{432}{9507816}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2467839} = \frac{210}{4935678} = \frac{420}{9871356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3846297} = \frac{120}{4395768} = \frac{240}{8791536}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2379465} = \frac{216}{4758930} = \frac{432}{9517860}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2468379} = \frac{210}{4936758} = \frac{420}{9873516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3846927} = \frac{180}{6594732} = \frac{210}{7693854}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2396754} = \frac{216}{4793508} = \frac{432}{9587016}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2478693} = \frac{195}{4603287} = \frac{210}{4957386}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{3962847} = \frac{140}{5283796} = \frac{180}{6793452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2437965} = \frac{216}{4875930} = \frac{432}{9751860}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2674893} = \frac{210}{5349786} = \frac{315}{8024679}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{4367982} = \frac{140}{5823976} = \frac{210}{8735964}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2453769} = \frac{216}{4907538} = \frac{432}{9815076}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2687493} = \frac{210}{5374986} = \frac{315}{8062479}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{2743598} = \frac{108}{2795364} = \frac{312}{8075496}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2459376} = \frac{159}{3620748} = \frac{357}{8129604}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{105}{2698437} = \frac{210}{5396874} = \frac{360}{9251784}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{106}{4279538} = \frac{136}{5490728} = \frac{237}{9568401}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{108}{2467539} = \frac{216}{4935078} = \frac{432}{9870156}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2574689} = \frac{260}{5149378} = \frac{430}{8516279}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2068479} = \frac{270}{4136958} = \frac{540}{8273916}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{137}{5298064} = \frac{194}{7502368} = \frac{253}{9784016}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2746985} = \frac{208}{4395176} = \frac{416}{8790352}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2069784} = \frac{270}{4139568} = \frac{540}{8279136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2049576} = \frac{429}{6371508} = \frac{654}{9713208}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2758964} = \frac{325}{6897410} = \frac{420}{8913576}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2096874} = \frac{315}{4892706} = \frac{630}{9785412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2546790} = \frac{258}{4761390} = \frac{471}{8692305}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{2859467} = \frac{260}{5718934} = \frac{360}{7918524}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2407968} = \frac{270}{4815936} = \frac{540}{9631872}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2549067} = \frac{176}{3250984} = \frac{276}{5098134}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{4298567} = \frac{240}{7935816} = \frac{260}{8597134}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2409678} = \frac{270}{4819356} = \frac{540}{9638712}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2640597} = \frac{184}{3520796} = \frac{368}{7041592}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{130}{4798625} = \frac{172}{6348950} = \frac{196}{7234850}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2467809} = \frac{270}{4935618} = \frac{540}{9871236}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2659740} = \frac{253}{4876190} = \frac{276}{5319480}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1302}{458769} = \frac{1932}{680754} = \frac{2604}{917538}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2467908} = \frac{270}{4935816} = \frac{540}{9871632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2694570} = \frac{184}{3592760} = \frac{276}{5389140}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{132}{4067985} = \frac{176}{5423980} = \frac{264}{8135970}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2468079} = \frac{270}{4936158} = \frac{540}{9872316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2697054} = \frac{184}{3596072} = \frac{276}{5394108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{132}{4075698} = \frac{138}{4260957} = \frac{186}{5743029}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2469078} = \frac{270}{4938156} = \frac{540}{9876312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2705964} = \frac{184}{3607952} = \frac{368}{7215904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{132}{4079658} = \frac{138}{4265097} = \frac{276}{8530194}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2674809} = \frac{270}{5349618} = \frac{430}{8519762}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2740956} = \frac{156}{3098472} = \frac{301}{5978462}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{132}{4079865} = \frac{176}{5439820} = \frac{264}{8159730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2746980} = \frac{304}{6185792} = \frac{369}{7508412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2945670} = \frac{184}{3927560} = \frac{276}{5891340}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{132}{4957680} = \frac{198}{7436520} = \frac{231}{8675940}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2847069} = \frac{270}{5694138} = \frac{360}{7592184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2964057} = \frac{184}{3952076} = \frac{368}{7904152}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{132}{7580496} = \frac{138}{7925064} = \frac{158}{9073624}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2897640} = \frac{137}{2940568} = \frac{179}{3842056}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2967054} = \frac{184}{3956072} = \frac{276}{5934108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{134}{2067985} = \frac{268}{4135970} = \frac{536}{8271940}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2907468} = \frac{270}{5814936} = \frac{315}{6784092}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{2970564} = \frac{184}{3960752} = \frac{368}{7921504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{134}{2068759} = \frac{270}{4168395} = \frac{410}{6329785}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2964708} = \frac{370}{8125496} = \frac{390}{8564712}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{4902657} = \frac{206}{7318459} = \frac{276}{9805314}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{134}{2069785} = \frac{268}{4139570} = \frac{536}{8279140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{4067982} = \frac{180}{5423976} = \frac{270}{8135964}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{138}{5920476} = \frac{164}{7035928} = \frac{169}{7250438}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{134}{2076598} = \frac{316}{4897052} = \frac{562}{8709314}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{136}{2790584} = \frac{247}{5068193} = \frac{403}{8269157}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{2406785} = \frac{439}{7601285} = \frac{469}{8120735}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{134}{2675980} = \frac{358}{7149260} = \frac{429}{8567130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{136}{2795480} = \frac{158}{3247690} = \frac{297}{6104835}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{2458076} = \frac{504}{8912736} = \frac{526}{9301784}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{134}{2896075} = \frac{142}{3068975} = \frac{284}{6137950}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{136}{2975408} = \frac{159}{3478602} = \frac{318}{6957204}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{139}{2684507} = \frac{239}{4615807} = \frac{278}{5369014}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2067849} = \frac{270}{4135698} = \frac{540}{8271396}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{136}{5974208} = \frac{153}{6720984} = \frac{218}{9576304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2357968} = \frac{280}{4715936} = \frac{560}{9431872}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{135}{2067984} = \frac{270}{4135968} = \frac{540}{8271936}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{137}{2649580} = \frac{154}{2978360} = \frac{186}{3597240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2359678} = \frac{280}{4719356} = \frac{560}{9438712}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2365798} = \frac{210}{3548697} = \frac{280}{4731596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3598067} = \frac{270}{6841395} = \frac{290}{7348165}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2687093} = \frac{290}{5374186} = \frac{435}{8061279}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2365978} = \frac{210}{3548967} = \frac{280}{4731956}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3657980} = \frac{213}{5486970} = \frac{284}{7315960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2687309} = \frac{290}{5374618} = \frac{435}{8061927}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2367958} = \frac{280}{4735916} = \frac{560}{9471832}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3659780} = \frac{213}{5489670} = \frac{284}{7319560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2689073} = \frac{290}{5378146} = \frac{435}{8067219}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2369578} = \frac{280}{4739156} = \frac{560}{9478312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3765980} = \frac{213}{5648970} = \frac{284}{7531960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2689307} = \frac{290}{5378614} = \frac{435}{8067921}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2376598} = \frac{210}{3564897} = \frac{280}{4753196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3796580} = \frac{213}{5694870} = \frac{284}{7593160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2690873} = \frac{290}{5381746} = \frac{435}{8072619}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2379658} = \frac{210}{3569487} = \frac{280}{4759316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3965780} = \frac{213}{5948670} = \frac{284}{7931560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2693087} = \frac{290}{5386174} = \frac{435}{8079261}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2379856} = \frac{210}{3569784} = \frac{420}{7139568}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3976580} = \frac{213}{5964870} = \frac{284}{7953160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2706893} = \frac{290}{5413786} = \frac{435}{8120679}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2389576} = \frac{275}{4693810} = \frac{395}{6742018}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2079865} = \frac{286}{4159730} = \frac{572}{8319460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2708693} = \frac{290}{5417386} = \frac{435}{8126079}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2396578} = \frac{210}{3594867} = \frac{280}{4793156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2097865} = \frac{286}{4195730} = \frac{572}{8391460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2730689} = \frac{290}{5461378} = \frac{435}{8192067}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2397658} = \frac{210}{3596487} = \frac{280}{4795316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2560987} = \frac{156}{2793804} = \frac{439}{7862051}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2730869} = \frac{290}{5461738} = \frac{435}{8192607}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2397856} = \frac{210}{3596784} = \frac{420}{7193568}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2568709} = \frac{196}{3520748} = \frac{296}{5317048}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2798036} = \frac{315}{6078492} = \frac{465}{8973012}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2637985} = \frac{304}{5728196} = \frac{524}{9873601}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{143}{2786905} = \frac{182}{3546970} = \frac{429}{8360715}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2867093} = \frac{290}{5734186} = \frac{435}{8601279}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2658397} = \frac{280}{5316794} = \frac{380}{7215649}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2307869} = \frac{290}{4615738} = \frac{580}{9231476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2867309} = \frac{290}{5734618} = \frac{435}{8601927}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{2736895} = \frac{184}{3597062} = \frac{384}{7506912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2308679} = \frac{290}{4617358} = \frac{580}{9234716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2869073} = \frac{290}{5738146} = \frac{435}{8607219}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{3657982} = \frac{210}{5486973} = \frac{280}{7315964}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2367809} = \frac{290}{4735618} = \frac{580}{9471236}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2869307} = \frac{290}{5738614} = \frac{435}{8607921}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{3659782} = \frac{210}{5489673} = \frac{280}{7319564}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2367908} = \frac{290}{4735816} = \frac{580}{9471632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2870693} = \frac{290}{5741386} = \frac{435}{8612079}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{3765982} = \frac{210}{5648973} = \frac{280}{7531964}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2368079} = \frac{290}{4736158} = \frac{580}{9472316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2873069} = \frac{290}{5746138} = \frac{435}{8619207}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{3796582} = \frac{210}{5694873} = \frac{280}{7593164}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2369078} = \frac{290}{4738156} = \frac{580}{9476312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2890673} = \frac{290}{5781346} = \frac{435}{8672019}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{3965782} = \frac{210}{5948673} = \frac{280}{7931564}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2380697} = \frac{285}{4679301} = \frac{485}{7963021}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2893067} = \frac{290}{5786134} = \frac{435}{8679201}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{140}{3976582} = \frac{210}{5964873} = \frac{280}{7953164}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2670893} = \frac{290}{5341786} = \frac{435}{8012679}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2906873} = \frac{290}{5813746} = \frac{435}{8720619}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{142}{3589760} = \frac{192}{4853760} = \frac{291}{7356480}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2673089} = \frac{290}{5346178} = \frac{435}{8019267}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2908673} = \frac{290}{5817346} = \frac{435}{8726019}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2930687} &= \frac{290}{5861374} = \frac{435}{8792061} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{2930867} &= \frac{290}{5861734} = \frac{435}{8792601} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3067289} &= \frac{290}{6134578} = \frac{435}{9201867} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3068729} &= \frac{290}{6137458} = \frac{435}{9206187} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3068927} &= \frac{290}{6137854} = \frac{435}{9206781} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3069287} &= \frac{290}{6138574} = \frac{435}{9207861} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3072689} &= \frac{290}{6145378} = \frac{435}{9218067} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3086729} &= \frac{290}{6173458} = \frac{435}{9260187} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3086927} &= \frac{290}{6173854} = \frac{435}{9260781} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3087269} &= \frac{290}{6174538} = \frac{435}{9261807} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3089267} &= \frac{290}{6178534} = \frac{435}{9267801} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3092687} &= \frac{290}{6185374} = \frac{435}{9278061} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3092867} &= \frac{290}{6185734} = \frac{435}{9278601} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3260789} &= \frac{240}{5397168} = \frac{285}{6409137} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3267089} &= \frac{290}{6534178} = \frac{435}{9801267} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3268709} &= \frac{290}{6537418} = \frac{435}{9806127} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3268907} &= \frac{290}{6537814} = \frac{435}{9806721} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3269087} &= \frac{290}{6538174} = \frac{435}{9807261} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3270689} &= \frac{290}{6541378} = \frac{435}{9812067} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3270869} &= \frac{290}{6541738} = \frac{435}{9812607} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3286709} &= \frac{290}{6573418} = \frac{435}{9860127} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3286907} &= \frac{290}{6573814} = \frac{435}{9860721} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3287069} &= \frac{290}{6574138} = \frac{435}{9861207} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3289067} &= \frac{290}{6578134} = \frac{435}{9867201} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3290687} &= \frac{290}{6581374} = \frac{435}{9872061} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3290867} &= \frac{290}{6581734} = \frac{435}{9872601} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{145}{3869702} &= \frac{170}{4536892} = \frac{185}{4937206} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{2035897} &= \frac{524}{7306918} = \frac{670}{9342815} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{2508937} &= \frac{270}{4639815} = \frac{528}{9073416} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{146}{5793280} &= \frac{147}{5832960} = \frac{193}{7658240} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2506938} &= \frac{294}{5013876} = \frac{576}{9823104} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2508639} &= \frac{273}{4658901} = \frac{546}{9317802} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2603958} &= \frac{459}{8130726} = \frac{543}{9618702} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2805396} &= \frac{196}{3740528} = \frac{392}{7481056} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2809365} &= \frac{196}{3745820} = \frac{294}{5618730} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2835069} &= \frac{294}{5670138} = \frac{392}{7560184} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2835609} &= \frac{154}{2970638} = \frac{308}{5941276} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2835690} &= \frac{294}{5671380} = \frac{392}{7561840} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2836905} &= \frac{196}{3782540} = \frac{294}{5673810} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2839065} &= \frac{196}{3785420} = \frac{294}{5678130} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2865093} &= \frac{294}{5730186} = \frac{504}{9823176} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2893065} &= \frac{196}{3857420} = \frac{294}{5786130} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{2930865} &= \frac{294}{5861730} = \frac{392}{7815640} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{3058629} &= \frac{291}{6054837} = \frac{436}{9071852} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{3062598} &= \frac{362}{7541908} = \frac{468}{9750312} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{3560928} &= \frac{195}{4723680} = \frac{309}{7485216} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{3962805} &= \frac{196}{5283740} = \frac{238}{6415970} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{147}{8290653} &= \frac{153}{8629047} = \frac{168}{9475032} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{2035769} &= \frac{296}{4071538} = \frac{592}{8143076} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{2036759} &= \frac{296}{4073518} = \frac{592}{8147036} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{2053796} &= \frac{483}{6702591} = \frac{681}{9450237} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{2075369} &= \frac{296}{4150738} = \frac{592}{8301476} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{2079365} &= \frac{296}{4158730} = \frac{592}{8317460} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{2753096} &= \frac{308}{5729416} = \frac{382}{7105964} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{3509672} &= \frac{193}{4576802} = \frac{408}{9675312} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{3602579} &= \frac{284}{6913057} = \frac{340}{8276195} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{3752096} &= \frac{157}{3980264} = \frac{314}{7960528} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{148}{3926570} &= \frac{296}{7853140} = \frac{370}{9816425} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{2035768} &= \frac{298}{4071536} = \frac{596}{8143072} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{2036758} &= \frac{298}{4073516} = \frac{596}{8147032} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{2067835} &= \frac{298}{4135670} = \frac{596}{8271340} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{2075368} &= \frac{298}{4150736} = \frac{596}{8301472} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{149}{2076853} &= \frac{298}{4153706} = \frac{596}{8307412} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{149}{2083765} = \frac{287}{4013695} = \frac{298}{4167530}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{2079836} = \frac{308}{4159672} = \frac{651}{8792034}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2870349} = \frac{260}{4783915} = \frac{312}{5740698}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{149}{2086753} = \frac{298}{4173506} = \frac{596}{8347012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{2308796} = \frac{308}{4617592} = \frac{319}{4782506}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2897304} = \frac{312}{5794608} = \frac{507}{9416238}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{149}{2358670} = \frac{369}{5841270} = \frac{397}{6284510}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{2638097} = \frac{308}{5276194} = \frac{568}{9730124}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2904738} = \frac{312}{5809476} = \frac{390}{7261845}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{149}{3750628} = \frac{346}{8709512} = \frac{382}{9615704}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{2963807} = \frac{308}{5927614} = \frac{354}{6812907}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2938470} = \frac{312}{5876940} = \frac{416}{7835920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{149}{3827065} = \frac{286}{7345910} = \frac{298}{7654130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{2973608} = \frac{308}{5947216} = \frac{406}{7839512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3072498} = \frac{390}{7681245} = \frac{486}{9572013}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3607948} = \frac{156}{3702894} = \frac{304}{7215896}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{3608297} = \frac{308}{7216594} = \frac{406}{9512783}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3297840} = \frac{321}{6785940} = \frac{391}{8265740}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3709864} = \frac{156}{3807492} = \frac{186}{4539702}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{154}{7926380} = \frac{182}{9367540} = \frac{186}{9573420}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3402789} = \frac{236}{5147809} = \frac{376}{8201594}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3740986} = \frac{368}{9057124} = \frac{376}{9254018}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2037948} = \frac{312}{4075896} = \frac{741}{9680253}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3402897} = \frac{208}{4537196} = \frac{312}{6805794}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3780964} = \frac{304}{7561928} = \frac{342}{8507169}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2037984} = \frac{312}{4075968} = \frac{561}{7328904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3702948} = \frac{273}{6480159} = \frac{312}{7405896}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3790648} = \frac{247}{6159803} = \frac{304}{7581296}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2048793} = \frac{312}{4097586} = \frac{728}{9561034}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3702984} = \frac{195}{4628730} = \frac{312}{7405968}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{3794680} = \frac{236}{5891740} = \frac{238}{5941670}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2379840} = \frac{312}{4759680} = \frac{468}{7139520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3704298} = \frac{206}{4891573} = \frac{312}{7408596}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{152}{4378096} = \frac{304}{8756192} = \frac{342}{9850716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2394780} = \frac{273}{4190865} = \frac{312}{4789560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3729408} = \frac{182}{4350976} = \frac{364}{8701952}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{2069478} = \frac{431}{5829706} = \frac{437}{5910862}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2397840} = \frac{312}{4795680} = \frac{468}{7193520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{3902478} = \frac{312}{7804956} = \frac{364}{9105782}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{2074986} = \frac{187}{2536094} = \frac{657}{8910234}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2437890} = \frac{218}{3406795} = \frac{430}{6719825}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{4028973} = \frac{208}{5371964} = \frac{312}{8057946}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{2089476} = \frac{306}{4178952} = \frac{612}{8357904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2478390} = \frac{312}{4956780} = \frac{364}{5782910}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{4793802} = \frac{176}{5408392} = \frac{312}{9587604}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{2094876} = \frac{306}{4189752} = \frac{612}{8379504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2498730} = \frac{216}{3459780} = \frac{324}{5189670}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{4937280} = \frac{169}{5348720} = \frac{312}{9874560}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{2486097} = \frac{216}{3509784} = \frac{432}{7019568}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2703948} = \frac{312}{5407896} = \frac{463}{8025179}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{157}{3026489} = \frac{314}{6052978} = \frac{456}{8790312}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{2496807} = \frac{174}{2839506} = \frac{348}{5679012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2743980} = \frac{273}{4801965} = \frac{312}{5487960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{2039476} = \frac{316}{4078952} = \frac{632}{8157904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{2804796} = \frac{186}{3409752} = \frac{372}{6819504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2803749} = \frac{192}{3450768} = \frac{312}{5607498}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{2043976} = \frac{316}{4087952} = \frac{632}{8175904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{4296087} = \frac{201}{5643879} = \frac{306}{8592174}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2843970} = \frac{312}{5687940} = \frac{416}{7583920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{2049376} = \frac{316}{4098752} = \frac{632}{8197504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{153}{7869402} = \frac{154}{7920836} = \frac{176}{9052384}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{156}{2849370} = \frac{312}{5698740} = \frac{416}{7598320}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{2379460} = \frac{316}{4758920} = \frac{632}{9517840}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{2437960} = \frac{316}{4875920} = \frac{632}{9751840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2574398} = \frac{240}{3861597} = \frac{320}{5148796}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{5803974} = \frac{243}{8705961} = \frac{261}{9350847}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{2639074} = \frac{291}{4860573} = \frac{409}{6831527}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2583974} = \frac{240}{3875961} = \frac{320}{5167948}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{163}{2079485} = \frac{326}{4158970} = \frac{652}{8317940}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{2739046} = \frac{237}{4108569} = \frac{316}{5478092}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2597438} = \frac{240}{3896157} = \frac{320}{5194876}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{163}{2094785} = \frac{326}{4189570} = \frac{652}{8379140}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{2904736} = \frac{316}{5809472} = \frac{395}{7261840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2598374} = \frac{240}{3897561} = \frac{320}{5196748}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{2035978} = \frac{328}{4071956} = \frac{638}{7920451}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{4379602} = \frac{216}{5987304} = \frac{316}{8759204}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3742598} = \frac{240}{5613897} = \frac{320}{7485196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{2390587} = \frac{196}{2857043} = \frac{392}{5714086}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{4627390} = \frac{237}{6941085} = \frac{316}{9254780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3759824} = \frac{310}{7284659} = \frac{320}{7519648}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{2573980} = \frac{328}{5147960} = \frac{364}{5712980}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{4932760} = \frac{172}{5369840} = \frac{239}{7461580}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3794582} = \frac{240}{5691873} = \frac{320}{7589164}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{2795380} = \frac{174}{2965830} = \frac{258}{4397610}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{158}{4937026} = \frac{169}{5280743} = \frac{316}{9874052}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3825974} = \frac{240}{5738961} = \frac{320}{7651948}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{2958730} = \frac{328}{5917460} = \frac{410}{7396825}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{2473086} = \frac{381}{5926074} = \frac{504}{7839216}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3895472} = \frac{190}{4625873} = \frac{380}{9251746}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{3087952} = \frac{287}{5403916} = \frac{328}{6175904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{2604738} = \frac{318}{5209476} = \frac{483}{7912506}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3945728} = \frac{230}{5671984} = \frac{320}{7891456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{3279508} = \frac{208}{4159376} = \frac{314}{6279058}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{2870346} = \frac{265}{4783910} = \frac{318}{5740692}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3945782} = \frac{240}{5918673} = \frac{320}{7891564}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{3295870} = \frac{328}{6591740} = \frac{410}{8239675}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{159}{3067428} = \frac{471}{9086532} = \frac{504}{9723168}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3957824} = \frac{320}{7915648} = \frac{370}{9152468}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{164}{3780952} = \frac{328}{7561904} = \frac{369}{8507142}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2379854} = \frac{240}{3569781} = \frac{480}{7139562}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3974258} = \frac{240}{5961387} = \frac{320}{7948516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{165}{2037849} = \frac{195}{2408367} = \frac{290}{3581674}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2397854} = \frac{240}{3596781} = \frac{480}{7193562}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{3982574} = \frac{240}{5973861} = \frac{320}{7965148}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{165}{2370489} = \frac{265}{3807149} = \frac{530}{7614298}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2437958} = \frac{320}{4875916} = \frac{640}{9751832}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{3794580} = \frac{243}{5691870} = \frac{324}{7589160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{165}{2840739} = \frac{285}{4906731} = \frac{570}{9813462}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2439578} = \frac{320}{4879156} = \frac{640}{9758312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{3798054} = \frac{243}{5697081} = \frac{324}{7596108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{165}{2983470} = \frac{319}{5768042} = \frac{517}{9348206}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2457893} = \frac{320}{4915786} = \frac{640}{9831572}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{3945780} = \frac{243}{5918670} = \frac{324}{7891560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{165}{3097248} = \frac{175}{3284960} = \frac{475}{8916320}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2457938} = \frac{320}{4915876} = \frac{640}{9831752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{3978054} = \frac{243}{5967081} = \frac{324}{7956108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{165}{7280493} = \frac{180}{7942356} = \frac{215}{9486703}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2458793} = \frac{320}{4917586} = \frac{640}{9835172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{4079835} = \frac{216}{5439780} = \frac{324}{8159670}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{167}{2385094} = \frac{394}{5627108} = \frac{572}{8169304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2459378} = \frac{320}{4918756} = \frac{640}{9837512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{4307985} = \frac{216}{5743980} = \frac{324}{8615970}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{167}{2509843} = \frac{381}{5726049} = \frac{452}{6793108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{160}{2573984} = \frac{320}{5147968} = \frac{430}{6917582}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{162}{4379805} = \frac{216}{5839740} = \frac{324}{8759610}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{2347590} = \frac{176}{2459380} = \frac{352}{4918760}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{2493750} = \frac{264}{3918750} = \frac{612}{9084375}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{5849632} = \frac{190}{6537824} = \frac{215}{7398064}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3802596} = \frac{261}{5703894} = \frac{348}{7605192}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{2579304} = \frac{258}{3961074} = \frac{403}{6187259}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{3409685} = \frac{368}{7295140} = \frac{472}{9356810}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3825960} = \frac{261}{5738940} = \frac{348}{7651920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{2940357} = \frac{216}{3780459} = \frac{432}{7560918}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{6350498} = \frac{204}{7531986} = \frac{254}{9378061}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3960258} = \frac{261}{5940387} = \frac{348}{7920516}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{2940735} = \frac{216}{3780945} = \frac{432}{7561890}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{172}{6508394} = \frac{214}{8097653} = \frac{246}{9308517}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3962580} = \frac{261}{5943870} = \frac{348}{7925160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{2943507} = \frac{216}{3784509} = \frac{432}{7569018}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2089653} = \frac{652}{7830194} = \frac{692}{8310574}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3980256} = \frac{261}{5970384} = \frac{348}{7960512}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{2943570} = \frac{216}{3784590} = \frac{432}{7569180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2390586} = \frac{516}{7089324} = \frac{678}{9315042}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3982560} = \frac{261}{5973840} = \frac{348}{7965120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3097542} = \frac{260}{4793815} = \frac{432}{7965108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2509863} = \frac{270}{3894615} = \frac{348}{5019726}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{5238096} = \frac{176}{5298304} = \frac{315}{9482760}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3254790} = \frac{368}{7129540} = \frac{420}{8136975}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2560398} = \frac{261}{3840597} = \frac{348}{5120796}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{2486309} = \frac{350}{4972618} = \frac{425}{6038179}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3259704} = \frac{236}{4579108} = \frac{308}{5976124}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2563980} = \frac{261}{3845970} = \frac{348}{5127960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{3240986} = \frac{325}{6018974} = \frac{350}{6481972}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3279054} = \frac{420}{8197635} = \frac{504}{9837162}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2580396} = \frac{261}{3870594} = \frac{348}{5160792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{175}{3289640} = \frac{210}{3947568} = \frac{420}{7895136}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3529407} = \frac{216}{4537809} = \frac{432}{9075618}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2583960} = \frac{261}{3875940} = \frac{348}{5167920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2034598} = \frac{264}{3051897} = \frac{528}{6103794}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3570294} = \frac{216}{4590378} = \frac{432}{9180756}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2596038} = \frac{261}{3894057} = \frac{348}{5192076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2039458} = \frac{264}{3059187} = \frac{352}{4078916}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3572940} = \frac{216}{4593780} = \frac{432}{9187560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2596380} = \frac{261}{3894570} = \frac{348}{5192760}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2043598} = \frac{352}{4087196} = \frac{528}{6130794}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{3954027} = \frac{216}{5083749} = \frac{360}{8472915}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2598036} = \frac{261}{3897054} = \frac{348}{5196072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2053489} = \frac{352}{4106978} = \frac{704}{8213956}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{7395402} = \frac{180}{7923645} = \frac{216}{9508374}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2598360} = \frac{261}{3897540} = \frac{348}{5196720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2053849} = \frac{352}{4107698} = \frac{704}{8215396}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{168}{7539420} = \frac{194}{8706235} = \frac{214}{9603785}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2895360} = \frac{429}{7138560} = \frac{524}{8719360}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2054398} = \frac{264}{3081597} = \frac{352}{4108796}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{169}{4237805} = \frac{182}{4563790} = \frac{364}{9127580}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{2930856} = \frac{513}{8640972} = \frac{519}{8742036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2054839} = \frac{352}{4109678} = \frac{704}{8219356}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{2456398} = \frac{190}{2745386} = \frac{480}{6935712}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3052986} = \frac{348}{6105972} = \frac{493}{8650127}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2304589} = \frac{352}{4609178} = \frac{704}{9218356}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{2639845} = \frac{602}{9348157} = \frac{610}{9472385}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3280596} = \frac{201}{3789654} = \frac{403}{7598162}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2308954} = \frac{352}{4617908} = \frac{704}{9235816}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{3296485} = \frac{238}{4615079} = \frac{476}{9230158}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3602598} = \frac{261}{5403897} = \frac{348}{7205196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2358904} = \frac{418}{5602397} = \frac{682}{9140753}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{170}{3692485} = \frac{218}{4735069} = \frac{416}{9035728}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{174}{3625980} = \frac{261}{5438970} = \frac{348}{7251960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2359048} = \frac{352}{4718096} = \frac{418}{5602739}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2359804} = \frac{308}{4129657} = \frac{352}{4719608}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2380459} = \frac{352}{4760918} = \frac{704}{9521836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2380954} = \frac{352}{4761908} = \frac{704}{9523816}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2390458} = \frac{352}{4780916} = \frac{704}{9561832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2394580} = \frac{264}{3591870} = \frac{352}{4789160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2395408} = \frac{352}{4790816} = \frac{704}{9581632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2398054} = \frac{264}{3597081} = \frac{352}{4796108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2403958} = \frac{352}{4807916} = \frac{704}{9615832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2408953} = \frac{352}{4817906} = \frac{704}{9635812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2409538} = \frac{352}{4819076} = \frac{704}{9638152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2439580} = \frac{352}{4879160} = \frac{604}{8372195}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2453089} = \frac{352}{4906178} = \frac{704}{9812356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2453809} = \frac{352}{4907618} = \frac{704}{9815236}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2453908} = \frac{352}{4907816} = \frac{704}{9815632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2458039} = \frac{352}{4916078} = \frac{704}{9832156}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2458903} = \frac{352}{4917806} = \frac{704}{9835612}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2459038} = \frac{352}{4918076} = \frac{704}{9836152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{2543980} = \frac{264}{3815970} = \frac{528}{7631940}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{3945802} = \frac{264}{5918703} = \frac{352}{7891604}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{3945820} = \frac{264}{5918730} = \frac{352}{7891640}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{3980542} = \frac{264}{5970813} = \frac{352}{7961084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{3982054} = \frac{264}{5973081} = \frac{352}{7964108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{4235980} = \frac{308}{7412965} = \frac{352}{8471960}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{4239580} = \frac{308}{7419265} = \frac{352}{8479160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{176}{4385920} = \frac{318}{7924560} = \frac{351}{8746920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2035964} = \frac{356}{4071928} = \frac{534}{6107892}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2036594} = \frac{267}{3054891} = \frac{534}{6109782}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2039456} = \frac{267}{3059184} = \frac{356}{4078912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2054396} = \frac{267}{3081594} = \frac{356}{4108792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2059634} = \frac{267}{3089451} = \frac{534}{6178902}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2350964} = \frac{356}{4701928} = \frac{712}{9403856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2359640} = \frac{356}{4719280} = \frac{712}{9438560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2364095} = \frac{356}{4728190} = \frac{712}{9456380}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2364509} = \frac{356}{4729018} = \frac{712}{9458036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2364590} = \frac{356}{4729180} = \frac{712}{9458360}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2394560} = \frac{267}{3591840} = \frac{356}{4789120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2395640} = \frac{356}{4791280} = \frac{534}{7186920}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2396054} = \frac{267}{3594081} = \frac{356}{4792108}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2563940} = \frac{267}{3845910} = \frac{534}{7691820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2569430} = \frac{483}{6972105} = \frac{643}{9281705}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{2906534} = \frac{267}{4359801} = \frac{534}{8719602}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{3065249} = \frac{218}{3754069} = \frac{504}{8679132}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{3962054} = \frac{267}{5943081} = \frac{356}{7924108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{4563920} = \frac{294}{7538160} = \frac{356}{9127840}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{4953206} = \frac{187}{5203649} = \frac{217}{6038459}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{178}{5324069} = \frac{194}{5802637} = \frac{230}{6879415}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{2063485} = \frac{358}{4126970} = \frac{716}{8253940}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{2308645} = \frac{358}{4617290} = \frac{716}{9234580}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{2463580} = \frac{358}{4927160} = \frac{716}{9854320}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{3260485} = \frac{419}{7632085} = \frac{534}{9726810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{179}{4256083} = \frac{347}{8250619} = \frac{376}{8940152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2357964} = \frac{360}{4715928} = \frac{720}{9431856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2359764} = \frac{360}{4719528} = \frac{630}{8259174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2364579} = \frac{360}{4729158} = \frac{720}{9458316}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2379456} = \frac{270}{3569184} = \frac{360}{4758912}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2379465} = \frac{384}{5076192} = \frac{492}{6503871}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2379564} = \frac{360}{4759128} = \frac{540}{7138692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2379654} = \frac{270}{3569481} = \frac{540}{7138962}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2394576} = \frac{270}{3591864} = \frac{360}{4789152}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2435976} = \frac{360}{4871952} = \frac{430}{5819276}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2439756} = \frac{360}{4879512} = \frac{540}{7319268}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2563974} = \frac{270}{3845961} = \frac{360}{5127948}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2574396} = \frac{270}{3861594} = \frac{360}{5148792}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2594736} = \frac{275}{3964180} = \frac{360}{5189472}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2596374} = \frac{270}{3894561} = \frac{360}{5192748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2597436} = \frac{270}{3896154} = \frac{360}{5194872}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{2759436} = \frac{285}{4369107} = \frac{615}{9428073}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{3425796} = \frac{270}{5138694} = \frac{485}{9230617}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{3794562} = \frac{270}{5691843} = \frac{360}{7589124}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{5742396} = \frac{245}{7816039} = \frac{270}{8613594}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{180}{5943276} = \frac{190}{6273458} = \frac{230}{7594186}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{3657094} = \frac{208}{4179536} = \frac{416}{8359072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{3670954} = \frac{208}{4195376} = \frac{416}{8390752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{3794560} = \frac{273}{5691840} = \frac{364}{7589120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{3796054} = \frac{273}{5694081} = \frac{364}{7592108}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{5763940} = \frac{243}{7695810} = \frac{273}{8645910}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{182}{7639450} = \frac{201}{8436975} = \frac{213}{8940675}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{2647095} = \frac{249}{3601785} = \frac{396}{5728140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{183}{2905674} = \frac{192}{3048576} = \frac{384}{6097152}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{2039756} = \frac{368}{4079512} = \frac{736}{8159024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{2053976} = \frac{368}{4107952} = \frac{736}{8215904}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{2359760} = \frac{368}{4719520} = \frac{529}{6784310}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{2375960} = \frac{368}{4751920} = \frac{713}{9206845}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{184}{2379560} = \frac{368}{4759120} = \frac{736}{9518240}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{2475093} = \frac{372}{4950186} = \frac{682}{9075341}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{2597304} = \frac{372}{5194608} = \frac{408}{5697312}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{3254907} = \frac{210}{3674895} = \frac{372}{6509814}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{3902745} = \frac{236}{4951870} = \frac{394}{8267105}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{4079352} = \frac{297}{6513804} = \frac{324}{7105968}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{4309527} = \frac{324}{7506918} = \frac{372}{8619054}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{4593270} = \frac{356}{8791420} = \frac{372}{9186540}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{186}{4920537} = \frac{204}{5396718} = \frac{356}{9417802}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{187}{2630954} = \frac{374}{5261908} = \frac{429}{6035718}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{187}{2945063} = \frac{302}{4756198} = \frac{374}{5890126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{187}{3049256} = \frac{374}{6098512} = \frac{517}{8430296}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{187}{3590264} = \frac{473}{9081256} = \frac{506}{9714832}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{187}{4329560} = \frac{352}{8149760} = \frac{374}{8659120}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{2435076} = \frac{285}{3671940} = \frac{402}{5179368}$$

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$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{2706345} = \frac{287}{4109635} = \frac{378}{5412690}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{2745063} = \frac{378}{5490126} = \frac{546}{7930182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{2745630} = \frac{378}{5491260} = \frac{546}{7931820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{3075462} = \frac{245}{3986710} = \frac{378}{6150924}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{3250746} = \frac{357}{6140298} = \frac{378}{6501492}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{3426570} = \frac{297}{5384610} = \frac{459}{8321670}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{3457026} = \frac{378}{6914052} = \frac{504}{9218736}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{3475206} = \frac{297}{5461038} = \frac{378}{6950412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{4572603} = \frac{243}{5879061} = \frac{378}{9145206}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{189}{4732560} = \frac{219}{5483760} = \frac{378}{9465120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2364578} = \frac{380}{4729156} = \frac{760}{9458312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2378456} = \frac{380}{4756912} = \frac{760}{9513824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2435876} = \frac{480}{6153792} = \frac{530}{6794812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2457863} = \frac{380}{4915726} = \frac{760}{9831452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2463578} = \frac{380}{4927156} = \frac{760}{9854312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2483756} = \frac{380}{4967512} = \frac{735}{9608214}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2735648} = \frac{380}{5471296} = \frac{475}{6839120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2735846} = \frac{285}{4103769} = \frac{380}{5471692}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{2745638} = \frac{380}{5491276} = \frac{570}{8236914}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{3572648} = \frac{380}{7145296} = \frac{475}{8931620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{4627358} = \frac{285}{6941037} = \frac{380}{9254716}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{190}{6427358} = \frac{205}{6934781} = \frac{285}{9641037}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1904}{326587} = \frac{2016}{345798} = \frac{3024}{518697}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1904}{536872} = \frac{2516}{709438} = \frac{3502}{987461}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{1904}{627538} = \frac{2408}{793651} = \frac{2856}{941307}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3048756} = \frac{384}{6097512} = \frac{432}{6859701}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3506784} = \frac{416}{7598032} = \frac{506}{9241837}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3547680} = \frac{312}{5764980} = \frac{324}{5986710}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3576048} = \frac{384}{7152096} = \frac{504}{9387126}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3647508} = \frac{208}{3951467} = \frac{384}{7295016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{3804576} = \frac{384}{7609152} = \frac{402}{7965831}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{4378560} = \frac{407}{9281635} = \frac{432}{9851760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{4735680} = \frac{309}{7621485} = \frac{312}{7695480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{4750836} = \frac{208}{5146739} = \frac{384}{9501672}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{4753608} = \frac{216}{5347809} = \frac{384}{9507216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{4780536} = \frac{304}{7569182} = \frac{384}{9561072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{4805376} = \frac{376}{9410528} = \frac{384}{9610752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{5084736} = \frac{213}{5640879} = \frac{342}{9057186}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{192}{8547360} = \frac{196}{8725430} = \frac{210}{9348675}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{2036578} = \frac{291}{3054867} = \frac{582}{6109734}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{2563780} = \frac{291}{3845670} = \frac{582}{7691340}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{2673805} = \frac{412}{5678390} = \frac{596}{8214370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{194}{3065782} = \frac{219}{3460857} = \frac{532}{8407196}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2307864} = \frac{390}{4615728} = \frac{780}{9231456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2364078} = \frac{390}{4728156} = \frac{780}{9456312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2378406} = \frac{390}{4756812} = \frac{780}{9513624}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2407863} = \frac{390}{4815726} = \frac{780}{9631452}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2607384} = \frac{390}{5214768} = \frac{635}{8490712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2743086} = \frac{390}{5486172} = \frac{520}{7314896}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2743806} = \frac{390}{5487612} = \frac{435}{6120798}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2746380} = \frac{274}{3859016} = \frac{281}{3957604}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2786043} = \frac{320}{4571968} = \frac{680}{9715432}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2836470} = \frac{513}{7462098} = \frac{645}{9382170}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2837640} = \frac{408}{5937216} = \frac{508}{7392416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{195}{2843607} = \frac{295}{4301867} = \frac{390}{5687214}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2054378} = \frac{294}{3081567} = \frac{392}{4108756}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2085734} = \frac{694}{7385201} = \frac{754}{8023691}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2308754} = \frac{392}{4617508} = \frac{784}{9235016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2375408} = \frac{392}{4750816} = \frac{784}{9501632}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2375804} = \frac{392}{4751608} = \frac{784}{9503216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2378054} = \frac{294}{3567081} = \frac{392}{4756108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2378405} = \frac{392}{4756810} = \frac{784}{9513620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2380754} = \frac{392}{4761508} = \frac{784}{9523016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2385740} = \frac{294}{3578610} = \frac{609}{7412835}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2403758} = \frac{392}{4807516} = \frac{784}{9615032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2408753} = \frac{392}{4817506} = \frac{784}{9635012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2508734} = \frac{392}{5017468} = \frac{490}{6271835}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2530874} = \frac{392}{5061748} = \frac{490}{6327185}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2573480} = \frac{649}{8521370} = \frac{712}{9348560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2574038} = \frac{294}{3861057} = \frac{392}{5148076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2574380} = \frac{294}{3861570} = \frac{392}{5148760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2580374} = \frac{294}{3870561} = \frac{392}{5160748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2583740} = \frac{294}{3875610} = \frac{392}{5167480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2587403} = \frac{392}{5174806} = \frac{728}{9610354}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2730854} = \frac{392}{5461708} = \frac{490}{6827135}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2850734} = \frac{392}{5701468} = \frac{490}{7126835}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2853074} = \frac{392}{5706148} = \frac{490}{7132685}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{2873054} = \frac{392}{5746108} = \frac{490}{7182635}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3052874} = \frac{392}{6105748} = \frac{490}{7632185}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3072854} = \frac{392}{6145708} = \frac{490}{7682135}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3275804} = \frac{308}{5147692} = \frac{413}{6902587}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3287054} = \frac{392}{6574108} = \frac{490}{8217635}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3547208} = \frac{327}{5918046} = \frac{419}{7583062}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3740258} = \frac{294}{5610387} = \frac{392}{7480516}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3780542} = \frac{294}{5670813} = \frac{392}{7561084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3782054} = \frac{294}{5673081} = \frac{392}{7564108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3802574} = \frac{294}{5703861} = \frac{392}{7605148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3807524} = \frac{301}{5847269} = \frac{392}{7615048}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{3850742} = \frac{238}{4675901} = \frac{476}{9351802}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{4308752} = \frac{315}{6924780} = \frac{392}{8617504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{4378052} = \frac{316}{7058492} = \frac{392}{8756104}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{4730852} = \frac{254}{6130798} = \frac{273}{6589401}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{196}{5074832} = \frac{219}{5670348} = \frac{295}{7638140}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{2430586} = \frac{609}{7513842} = \frac{659}{8130742}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{197}{2543608} = \frac{394}{5087216} = \frac{591}{7630824}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2034576} = \frac{297}{3051864} = \frac{594}{6103728}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2035764} = \frac{396}{4071528} = \frac{792}{8143056}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2043576} = \frac{396}{4087152} = \frac{594}{6130728}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2054376} = \frac{297}{3081564} = \frac{396}{4108752}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2057436} = \frac{297}{3086154} = \frac{594}{6172308}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2075364} = \frac{396}{4150728} = \frac{792}{8301456}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2075634} = \frac{387}{4056921} = \frac{864}{9057312}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2076354} = \frac{396}{4152708} = \frac{792}{8305416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2357640} = \frac{396}{4715280} = \frac{693}{8251740}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2374560} = \frac{297}{3561840} = \frac{594}{7123680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2376054} = \frac{297}{3564081} = \frac{396}{4752108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2437560} = \frac{396}{4875120} = \frac{594}{7312680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2540637} = \frac{396}{5081274} = \frac{438}{5620197}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2543607} = \frac{396}{5087214} = \frac{594}{7630821}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2543760} = \frac{297}{3815640} = \frac{594}{7631280}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2560374} = \frac{297}{3840561} = \frac{396}{5120748}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2563740} = \frac{297}{3845610} = \frac{396}{5127480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2573604} = \frac{246}{3197508} = \frac{396}{5147208}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2574036} = \frac{297}{3861054} = \frac{396}{5148072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{2574360} = \frac{297}{3861540} = \frac{396}{5148720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3042567} = \frac{246}{3780159} = \frac{492}{7560318}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3602574} = \frac{297}{5403861} = \frac{396}{7205148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3605274} = \frac{396}{7210548} = \frac{506}{9213478}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3625740} = \frac{297}{5438610} = \frac{396}{7251480}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3642507} = \frac{396}{7285014} = \frac{504}{9271836}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3740256} = \frac{297}{5610384} = \frac{396}{7480512}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3742560} = \frac{297}{5613840} = \frac{396}{7485120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3760542} = \frac{297}{5640813} = \frac{396}{7521084}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{3762054} = \frac{297}{5643081} = \frac{396}{7524108}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{4075236} = \frac{391}{8047562} = \frac{396}{8150472}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{4375206} = \frac{234}{5170698} = \frac{396}{8750412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{6073452} = \frac{207}{6349518} = \frac{231}{7085694}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{198}{7325604} = \frac{201}{7436598} = \frac{247}{9138506}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{201}{3456798} = \frac{359}{6174082} = \frac{379}{6518042}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{201}{5637849} = \frac{243}{6815907} = \frac{348}{9761052}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1468579} = \frac{406}{2937158} = \frac{928}{6713504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1475869} = \frac{406}{2951738} = \frac{812}{5903476}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1476859} = \frac{406}{2953718} = \frac{812}{5907436}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1485769} = \frac{406}{2971538} = \frac{812}{5943076}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1486759} = \frac{406}{2973518} = \frac{812}{5947036}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1486975} = \frac{391}{2864075} = \frac{918}{6724350}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1589476} = \frac{406}{3178952} = \frac{812}{6357904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1763598} = \frac{408}{3527196} = \frac{816}{7054392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1483679} = \frac{410}{2967358} = \frac{820}{5934716}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1594876} = \frac{406}{3189752} = \frac{812}{6379504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1793568} = \frac{315}{2769480} = \frac{916}{8053472}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1783649} = \frac{410}{3567298} = \frac{820}{7134596}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1758649} = \frac{406}{3517298} = \frac{812}{7034596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1796358} = \frac{408}{3592716} = \frac{612}{5389074}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1786349} = \frac{410}{3572698} = \frac{820}{7145396}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1758946} = \frac{319}{2764058} = \frac{406}{3517892}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1839756} = \frac{408}{3679512} = \frac{816}{7359024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1786493} = \frac{410}{3572986} = \frac{970}{8453162}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1759864} = \frac{406}{3519728} = \frac{812}{7039456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1859763} = \frac{408}{3719526} = \frac{816}{7439052}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1798364} = \frac{410}{3596728} = \frac{820}{7193456}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1764859} = \frac{406}{3529718} = \frac{812}{7059436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1963578} = \frac{408}{3927156} = \frac{612}{5890734}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1798634} = \frac{410}{3597268} = \frac{820}{7194536}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1857649} = \frac{406}{3715298} = \frac{812}{7430596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1975863} = \frac{408}{3951726} = \frac{816}{7903452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1836479} = \frac{410}{3672958} = \frac{820}{7345916}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1859764} = \frac{406}{3719528} = \frac{812}{7439056}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1976358} = \frac{408}{3952716} = \frac{816}{7905432}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1863479} = \frac{410}{3726958} = \frac{820}{7453916}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1864759} = \frac{406}{3729518} = \frac{812}{7459036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1983756} = \frac{408}{3967512} = \frac{816}{7935024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1978364} = \frac{410}{3956728} = \frac{820}{7913456}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1975864} = \frac{406}{3951728} = \frac{812}{7903456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1985763} = \frac{408}{3971526} = \frac{816}{7943052}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1978634} = \frac{410}{3957268} = \frac{820}{7914536}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{203}{1985764} = \frac{406}{3971528} = \frac{812}{7943056}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{3198756} = \frac{408}{6397512} = \frac{578}{9063142}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1348579} = \frac{498}{3260157} = \frac{692}{4530178}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1357698} = \frac{408}{2715396} = \frac{816}{5430792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{3589176} = \frac{207}{3641958} = \frac{561}{9870234}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1753489} = \frac{412}{3506978} = \frac{824}{7013956}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1359768} = \frac{408}{2719536} = \frac{816}{5439072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{3615798} = \frac{408}{7231596} = \frac{548}{9713026}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1753849} = \frac{412}{3507698} = \frac{824}{7015396}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1367598} = \frac{408}{2735196} = \frac{816}{5470392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{3781956} = \frac{209}{3874651} = \frac{408}{7563912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1753984} = \frac{412}{3507968} = \frac{824}{7015936}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1369758} = \frac{408}{2739516} = \frac{816}{5479032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1347869} = \frac{410}{2695738} = \frac{820}{5391476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1754839} = \frac{412}{3509678} = \frac{824}{7019356}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1536987} = \frac{492}{3706851} = \frac{628}{4731509}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1348679} = \frac{410}{2697358} = \frac{820}{5394716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1837549} = \frac{412}{3675098} = \frac{824}{7350196}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1579836} = \frac{408}{3159672} = \frac{612}{4739508}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1367849} = \frac{410}{2735698} = \frac{820}{5471396}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1839754} = \frac{412}{3679508} = \frac{824}{7359016}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1597836} = \frac{408}{3195672} = \frac{612}{4793508}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1367984} = \frac{410}{2735968} = \frac{820}{5471936}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1847539} = \frac{412}{3695078} = \frac{824}{7390156}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1635978} = \frac{408}{3271956} = \frac{672}{5389104}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1368479} = \frac{410}{2736958} = \frac{820}{5473916}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1875349} = \frac{412}{3750698} = \frac{824}{7501396}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1679583} = \frac{612}{5038749} = \frac{780}{6421935}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1369784} = \frac{410}{2739568} = \frac{820}{5479136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1897534} = \frac{412}{3795068} = \frac{824}{7590136}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{204}{1759863} = \frac{408}{3519726} = \frac{816}{7039452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{205}{1478369} = \frac{410}{2956738} = \frac{820}{5913476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1975384} = \frac{412}{3950768} = \frac{824}{7901536}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1983754} = \frac{412}{3967508} = \frac{824}{7935016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1975364} = \frac{416}{3950728} = \frac{832}{7901456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{4513678} = \frac{352}{7601984} = \frac{418}{9027356}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{1987534} = \frac{412}{3975068} = \frac{824}{7950136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1976354} = \frac{416}{3952708} = \frac{832}{7905416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{4783516} = \frac{407}{9315268} = \frac{418}{9567032}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{3781954} = \frac{267}{4901853} = \frac{412}{7563908}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{3617549} = \frac{416}{7235098} = \frac{512}{8904736}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{3478965} = \frac{408}{6759132} = \frac{582}{9641703}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{206}{7139548} = \frac{261}{9045738} = \frac{265}{9184370}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{4519376} = \frac{403}{8756291} = \frac{416}{9038752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{3497865} = \frac{216}{3597804} = \frac{432}{7195608}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{207}{1546893} = \frac{253}{1890647} = \frac{506}{3781294}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{4917536} = \frac{298}{7045316} = \frac{416}{9835072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{3645789} = \frac{380}{6597142} = \frac{470}{8159623}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{207}{1583964} = \frac{234}{1790568} = \frac{918}{7024536}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1354768} = \frac{418}{2709536} = \frac{836}{5419072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{3794658} = \frac{405}{7318269} = \frac{420}{7589316}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{207}{1596384} = \frac{528}{4071936} = \frac{635}{4897120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1367548} = \frac{418}{2735096} = \frac{836}{5470192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{4396875} = \frac{436}{9128750} = \frac{438}{9170625}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{207}{1685394} = \frac{243}{1978506} = \frac{486}{3957012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1435678} = \frac{374}{2569108} = \frac{781}{5364902}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{210}{4963875} = \frac{386}{9124075} = \frac{412}{9738650}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{207}{1689534} = \frac{519}{4236078} = \frac{915}{7468230}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1438756} = \frac{729}{5018436} = \frac{981}{6753204}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{3657980} = \frac{321}{5486970} = \frac{428}{7315960}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1354769} = \frac{416}{2709538} = \frac{832}{5419076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1475368} = \frac{418}{2950736} = \frac{836}{5901472}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{3659780} = \frac{321}{5489670} = \frac{428}{7319560}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1367549} = \frac{416}{2735098} = \frac{832}{5470196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1476853} = \frac{418}{2953706} = \frac{836}{5907412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{3765980} = \frac{321}{5648970} = \frac{428}{7531960}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1369754} = \frac{416}{2739508} = \frac{832}{5479016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1486753} = \frac{418}{2973506} = \frac{836}{5947012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{3796580} = \frac{321}{5694870} = \frac{428}{7593160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1379456} = \frac{679}{4503128} = \frac{751}{4980632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1753648} = \frac{418}{3507296} = \frac{836}{7014592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{3965780} = \frac{321}{5948670} = \frac{428}{7931560}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1475369} = \frac{416}{2950738} = \frac{832}{5901476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1754863} = \frac{418}{3509726} = \frac{836}{7019452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{3976580} = \frac{321}{5964870} = \frac{428}{7953160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1479365} = \frac{416}{2958730} = \frac{832}{5917460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1763548} = \frac{418}{3527096} = \frac{836}{7054192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{214}{5970386} = \frac{247}{6891053} = \frac{269}{7504831}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1539476} = \frac{416}{3078952} = \frac{832}{6157904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1764853} = \frac{418}{3529706} = \frac{836}{7059412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{3469780} = \frac{301}{4857692} = \frac{602}{9715384}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1549376} = \frac{416}{3098752} = \frac{832}{6197504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1854763} = \frac{418}{3709526} = \frac{836}{7419052}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{3476980} = \frac{372}{6015984} = \frac{517}{8360924}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1647935} = \frac{416}{3295870} = \frac{832}{6591740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{1864753} = \frac{418}{3729506} = \frac{836}{7459012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{215}{3879460} = \frac{216}{3897504} = \frac{408}{7361952}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1753649} = \frac{416}{3507298} = \frac{832}{7014596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{3467158} = \frac{253}{4197086} = \frac{506}{8394172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{3094875} = \frac{432}{6189750} = \frac{680}{9743125}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1763549} = \frac{416}{3527098} = \frac{832}{7054196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{3756148} = \frac{419}{7530268} = \frac{514}{9237608}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{3547098} = \frac{420}{6897135} = \frac{512}{8407936}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{208}{1794536} = \frac{416}{3589072} = \frac{936}{8075412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{209}{4356187} = \frac{263}{5481709} = \frac{392}{8170456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{3794580} = \frac{324}{5691870} = \frac{432}{7589160}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{3798054} = \frac{324}{5697081} = \frac{432}{7596108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1578946} = \frac{460}{3157892} = \frac{920}{6315784}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1857960} = \frac{351}{2786940} = \frac{468}{3715920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{3907548} = \frac{294}{5318607} = \frac{432}{7815096}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1587946} = \frac{460}{3175892} = \frac{920}{6351784}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1859760} = \frac{351}{2789640} = \frac{468}{3719520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{3978054} = \frac{324}{5967081} = \frac{432}{7956108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1675849} = \frac{390}{2841657} = \frac{740}{5391862}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1879506} = \frac{468}{3759012} = \frac{936}{7518024}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{3978504} = \frac{261}{4807359} = \frac{504}{9283176}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1785964} = \frac{460}{3571928} = \frac{920}{7143856}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1879560} = \frac{468}{3759120} = \frac{936}{7518240}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{4037958} = \frac{284}{5309167} = \frac{432}{8075916}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1786459} = \frac{460}{3572918} = \frac{920}{7145836}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1879605} = \frac{468}{3759210} = \frac{936}{7518420}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{216}{4578390} = \frac{284}{6019735} = \frac{432}{9156780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1795864} = \frac{460}{3591728} = \frac{920}{7183456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1956078} = \frac{507}{4238169} = \frac{754}{6302918}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{217}{3548069} = \frac{279}{4561803} = \frac{403}{6589271}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1857964} = \frac{460}{3715928} = \frac{920}{7431856}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1978056} = \frac{351}{2967084} = \frac{702}{5934168}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{217}{4089365} = \frac{312}{5879640} = \frac{416}{7839520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1864579} = \frac{460}{3729158} = \frac{920}{7458316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1978560} = \frac{351}{2967840} = \frac{468}{3957120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{217}{4580963} = \frac{231}{4876509} = \frac{462}{9753018}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1956748} = \frac{715}{6082934} = \frac{895}{7614302}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1985760} = \frac{351}{2978640} = \frac{468}{3971520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{217}{4806935} = \frac{279}{6180345} = \frac{403}{8927165}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1957864} = \frac{460}{3915728} = \frac{920}{7831456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{5690178} = \frac{241}{5860397} = \frac{312}{7586904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{218}{3794560} = \frac{327}{5691840} = \frac{436}{7589120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{231}{4786509} = \frac{297}{6154083} = \frac{462}{9573018}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1079684} = \frac{470}{2159368} = \frac{915}{4203876}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{218}{3796054} = \frac{327}{5694081} = \frac{436}{7592108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1067895} = \frac{468}{2135790} = \frac{936}{4271580}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1407968} = \frac{470}{2815936} = \frac{940}{5631872}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{218}{3945760} = \frac{327}{5918640} = \frac{436}{7891520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1068795} = \frac{468}{2137590} = \frac{936}{4275180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1409678} = \frac{470}{2819356} = \frac{940}{5638712}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{218}{3976054} = \frac{327}{5964081} = \frac{436}{7952108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1507896} = \frac{468}{3015792} = \frac{792}{5103648}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1467809} = \frac{470}{2935618} = \frac{940}{5871236}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{219}{4087635} = \frac{329}{6140785} = \frac{419}{7820635}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1760598} = \frac{351}{2640897} = \frac{507}{3814629}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1467908} = \frac{470}{2935816} = \frac{940}{5871632}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{219}{4805736} = \frac{291}{6385704} = \frac{324}{7109856}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1785960} = \frac{351}{2678940} = \frac{468}{3571920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1468079} = \frac{470}{2936158} = \frac{940}{5872316}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{219}{5687430} = \frac{237}{6154890} = \frac{294}{7635180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1789506} = \frac{468}{3579012} = \frac{936}{7158024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1469078} = \frac{470}{2938156} = \frac{940}{5876312}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1457869} = \frac{460}{2915738} = \frac{920}{5831476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1789560} = \frac{468}{3579120} = \frac{936}{7158240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1780964} = \frac{470}{3561928} = \frac{940}{7123856}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1458679} = \frac{460}{2917358} = \frac{920}{5834716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1789605} = \frac{468}{3579210} = \frac{936}{7158420}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1786094} = \frac{710}{5396284} = \frac{795}{6042318}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1467859} = \frac{460}{2935718} = \frac{920}{5871436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1795860} = \frac{247}{1895630} = \frac{468}{3591720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1796408} = \frac{470}{3592816} = \frac{940}{7185632}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{230}{1468579} = \frac{460}{2937158} = \frac{920}{5874316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{234}{1798560} = \frac{351}{2697840} = \frac{468}{3597120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1807964} = \frac{470}{3615928} = \frac{940}{7231856}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{235}{1964078} = \frac{470}{3928156} = \frac{940}{7856312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1607945} = \frac{476}{3215890} = \frac{952}{6431780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1976054} = \frac{357}{2964081} = \frac{476}{3952108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1047958} = \frac{370}{1642985} = \frac{982}{4360571}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1609475} = \frac{286}{1934075} = \frac{476}{3218950}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{4507916} = \frac{391}{7405862} = \frac{476}{9015832}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1457890} = \frac{670}{4138925} = \frac{936}{5782140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1754096} = \frac{476}{3508192} = \frac{952}{7016384}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{5640719} = \frac{290}{6873145} = \frac{296}{7015348}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1489750} = \frac{348}{2196750} = \frac{390}{2461875}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1754609} = \frac{476}{3509218} = \frac{952}{7018436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{5796014} = \frac{241}{5869073} = \frac{357}{8694021}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1547098} = \frac{670}{4392185} = \frac{982}{6437501}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1756049} = \frac{476}{3512098} = \frac{504}{3718692}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1045768} = \frac{478}{2091536} = \frac{956}{4183072}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1547980} = \frac{413}{2708965} = \frac{826}{5417930}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1759046} = \frac{476}{3518092} = \frac{952}{7036184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1046758} = \frac{478}{2093516} = \frac{956}{4187032}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1594780} = \frac{413}{2790865} = \frac{472}{3189560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1759604} = \frac{476}{3519208} = \frac{952}{7038416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1067845} = \frac{478}{2135690} = \frac{956}{4271380}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1794580} = \frac{354}{2691870} = \frac{472}{3589160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1760459} = \frac{476}{3520918} = \frac{952}{7041836}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1075468} = \frac{478}{2150936} = \frac{956}{4301872}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1879504} = \frac{578}{4603192} = \frac{906}{7215384}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1760954} = \frac{476}{3521908} = \frac{952}{7043816}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1567840} = \frac{453}{2971680} = \frac{819}{5372640}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{236}{1945780} = \frac{354}{2918670} = \frac{472}{3891560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1794560} = \frac{357}{2691840} = \frac{476}{3589120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1754608} = \frac{478}{3509216} = \frac{956}{7018432}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1045769} = \frac{476}{2091538} = \frac{952}{4183076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1795640} = \frac{476}{3591280} = \frac{714}{5386920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1758046} = \frac{478}{3516092} = \frac{956}{7032184}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1046759} = \frac{476}{2093518} = \frac{952}{4187036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1796054} = \frac{357}{2694081} = \frac{476}{3592108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1760458} = \frac{478}{3520916} = \frac{956}{7041832}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1067549} = \frac{430}{1928765} = \frac{476}{2135098}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1796540} = \frac{357}{2694810} = \frac{714}{5389620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1784506} = \frac{478}{3569012} = \frac{956}{7138024}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1069754} = \frac{476}{2139508} = \frac{782}{3514906}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1904576} = \frac{476}{3809152} = \frac{952}{7618304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1784560} = \frac{478}{3569120} = \frac{956}{7138240}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1075469} = \frac{476}{2150938} = \frac{952}{4301876}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1907546} = \frac{476}{3815092} = \frac{952}{7630184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1784605} = \frac{478}{3569210} = \frac{956}{7138420}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1076954} = \frac{476}{2153908} = \frac{952}{4307816}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1945076} = \frac{476}{3890152} = \frac{918}{7502436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1804576} = \frac{478}{3609152} = \frac{956}{7218304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1079465} = \frac{476}{2158930} = \frac{952}{4317860}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1945760} = \frac{357}{2918640} = \frac{476}{3891520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{239}{1807546} = \frac{478}{3615092} = \frac{956}{7230184}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1096754} = \frac{476}{2193508} = \frac{952}{4387016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1954076} = \frac{476}{3908152} = \frac{952}{7816304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1357968} = \frac{480}{2715936} = \frac{960}{5431872}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1507946} = \frac{476}{3015892} = \frac{952}{6031784}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1957604} = \frac{476}{3915208} = \frac{952}{7830416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1359678} = \frac{480}{2719356} = \frac{960}{5438712}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1579460} = \frac{476}{3158920} = \frac{952}{6317840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1960754} = \frac{476}{3921508} = \frac{952}{7843016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1367958} = \frac{480}{2735916} = \frac{960}{5471832}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1597064} = \frac{731}{4905268} = \frac{935}{6274180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{238}{1974560} = \frac{357}{2961840} = \frac{714}{5923680}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1369578} = \frac{480}{2739156} = \frac{960}{5478312}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1379568} = \frac{480}{2759136} = \frac{670}{3851294}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3875196} = \frac{360}{5812794} = \frac{420}{6781593}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1306879} = \frac{280}{1493576} = \frac{490}{2613758}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1579368} = \frac{780}{5132946} = \frac{820}{5396174}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3879516} = \frac{360}{5819274} = \frac{420}{6789153}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1307869} = \frac{490}{2615738} = \frac{980}{5231476}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1597836} = \frac{480}{3195672} = \frac{520}{3461978}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3951876} = \frac{360}{5927814} = \frac{420}{6915783}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1308679} = \frac{490}{2617358} = \frac{980}{5234716}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1763598} = \frac{480}{3527196} = \frac{840}{6172593}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3985716} = \frac{260}{4317859} = \frac{580}{9632147}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1308769} = \frac{280}{1495736} = \frac{490}{2617538}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1783956} = \frac{480}{3567912} = \frac{960}{7135824}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3987516} = \frac{360}{5981274} = \frac{420}{6978153}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1367809} = \frac{490}{2735618} = \frac{980}{5471236}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1785963} = \frac{480}{3571926} = \frac{960}{7143852}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{241}{3608975} = \frac{261}{3908475} = \frac{321}{4806975}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1367908} = \frac{490}{2735816} = \frac{980}{5471632}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1789536} = \frac{425}{3168970} = \frac{910}{6785324}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1078965} = \frac{486}{2157930} = \frac{972}{4315860}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1368079} = \frac{490}{2736158} = \frac{980}{5472316}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1795638} = \frac{480}{3591276} = \frac{720}{5386914}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1085967} = \frac{402}{1796538} = \frac{789}{3526041}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1369078} = \frac{490}{2738156} = \frac{980}{5476312}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1795863} = \frac{480}{3591726} = \frac{960}{7183452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1087965} = \frac{486}{2175930} = \frac{972}{4351860}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1376809} = \frac{280}{1573496} = \frac{490}{2753618}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1796358} = \frac{480}{3592716} = \frac{960}{7185432}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1507896} = \frac{486}{3015792} = \frac{972}{6031584}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1607938} = \frac{490}{3215876} = \frac{980}{6431752}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1837956} = \frac{480}{3675912} = \frac{960}{7351824}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1508796} = \frac{486}{3017592} = \frac{972}{6035184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1608793} = \frac{490}{3217586} = \frac{980}{6435172}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1857963} = \frac{480}{3715926} = \frac{960}{7431852}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1578960} = \frac{486}{3157920} = \frac{972}{6315840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1609378} = \frac{490}{3218756} = \frac{980}{6437512}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1956378} = \frac{480}{3912756} = \frac{720}{5869134}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1580796} = \frac{378}{2459016} = \frac{756}{4918032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1783906} = \frac{490}{3567812} = \frac{980}{7135624}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1957863} = \frac{480}{3915726} = \frac{960}{7831452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1587960} = \frac{486}{3175920} = \frac{972}{6351840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1786309} = \frac{490}{3572618} = \frac{980}{7145236}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1963578} = \frac{480}{3927156} = \frac{960}{7854312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1607895} = \frac{486}{3215790} = \frac{972}{6431580}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1790863} = \frac{490}{3581726} = \frac{980}{7163452}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{1976358} = \frac{480}{3952716} = \frac{840}{6917253}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1608795} = \frac{486}{3217590} = \frac{972}{6435180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1836079} = \frac{480}{3597216} = \frac{490}{3672158}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3158976} = \frac{480}{6317952} = \frac{580}{7634192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{1968057} = \frac{751}{6082349} = \frac{758}{6139042}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1837906} = \frac{490}{3675812} = \frac{980}{7351624}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3175968} = \frac{510}{6748932} = \frac{675}{8932410}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{5086719} = \frac{327}{6845091} = \frac{342}{7159086}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1863079} = \frac{490}{3726158} = \frac{980}{7452316}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3518796} = \frac{360}{5278194} = \frac{420}{6157893}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{243}{5861970} = \frac{324}{7815960} = \frac{351}{8467290}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1907863} = \frac{490}{3815726} = \frac{980}{7631452}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3519876} = \frac{360}{5279814} = \frac{420}{6159783}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1067839} = \frac{490}{2135678} = \frac{980}{4271356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1370589} = \frac{576}{3209184} = \frac{612}{3409758}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{240}{3615978} = \frac{480}{7231956} = \frac{520}{7834619}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{245}{1068379} = \frac{490}{2136758} = \frac{980}{4273516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1507893} = \frac{492}{3015786} = \frac{984}{6031572}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1507938} = \frac{492}{3015876} = \frac{984}{6031752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1890753} = \frac{492}{3781506} = \frac{984}{7563012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{3094867} = \frac{502}{6189734} = \frac{753}{9284601}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1508793} = \frac{492}{3017586} = \frac{984}{6035172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1903758} = \frac{492}{3807516} = \frac{984}{7615032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{4876930} = \frac{451}{8762930} = \frac{461}{8957230}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1509378} = \frac{492}{3018756} = \frac{984}{6037512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1907538} = \frac{492}{3815076} = \frac{984}{7630152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1068947} = \frac{506}{2137894} = \frac{759}{3206841}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1578390} = \frac{492}{3156780} = \frac{574}{3682910}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1907853} = \frac{492}{3815706} = \frac{942}{7305681}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1069487} = \frac{506}{2138974} = \frac{759}{3208461}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1578930} = \frac{492}{3157860} = \frac{984}{6315720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1908753} = \frac{492}{3817506} = \frac{984}{7635012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1074689} = \frac{483}{2051679} = \frac{506}{2149378}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1579380} = \frac{492}{3158760} = \frac{984}{6317520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{3179058} = \frac{487}{6293501} = \frac{561}{7249803}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1086947} = \frac{506}{2173894} = \frac{759}{3260841}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1587930} = \frac{492}{3175860} = \frac{984}{6351720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{3901578} = \frac{492}{7803156} = \frac{574}{9103682}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1089467} = \frac{506}{2178934} = \frac{759}{3268401}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1593780} = \frac{492}{3187560} = \frac{984}{6375120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{3915780} = \frac{492}{7831560} = \frac{574}{9136820}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1094687} = \frac{506}{2189374} = \frac{759}{3284061}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1753089} = \frac{492}{3506178} = \frac{984}{7012356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{3917058} = \frac{519}{8264037} = \frac{567}{9028341}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1094867} = \frac{506}{2189734} = \frac{759}{3284601}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1753809} = \frac{492}{3507618} = \frac{984}{7015236}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{247}{3098615} = \frac{538}{6749210} = \frac{652}{8179340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{253}{1648709} = \frac{506}{3297418} = \frac{627}{4085931}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1753908} = \frac{492}{3507816} = \frac{984}{7015632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{1367590} = \frac{496}{2735180} = \frac{620}{3418975}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{1063879} = \frac{462}{1935087} = \frac{826}{3459701}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1758039} = \frac{492}{3516078} = \frac{984}{7032156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{3591760} = \frac{496}{7183520} = \frac{651}{9428370}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{1796380} = \frac{381}{2694570} = \frac{762}{5389140}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1758903} = \frac{492}{3517806} = \frac{984}{7035612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{248}{5031796} = \frac{310}{6289745} = \frac{402}{8156379}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{1798036} = \frac{381}{2697054} = \frac{762}{5394108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1759038} = \frac{492}{3518076} = \frac{984}{7036152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{249}{3657810} = \frac{396}{5817240} = \frac{498}{7315620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{1963780} = \frac{381}{2945670} = \frac{762}{5891340}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1783905} = \frac{492}{3567810} = \frac{984}{7135620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{250}{1387964} = \frac{375}{2081946} = \frac{750}{4163892}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{1978036} = \frac{381}{2967054} = \frac{762}{5934108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1803759} = \frac{492}{3607518} = \frac{984}{7215036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{250}{1389746} = \frac{375}{2084619} = \frac{750}{4169238}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{254}{3719068} = \frac{493}{7218506} = \frac{627}{9180534}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1807539} = \frac{492}{3615078} = \frac{984}{7230156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{3068947} = \frac{502}{6137894} = \frac{753}{9206841}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1397840} = \frac{496}{2708315} = \frac{768}{4193520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1837905} = \frac{492}{3675810} = \frac{984}{7351620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{3069487} = \frac{502}{6138974} = \frac{753}{9208461}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1740398} = \frac{384}{2610597} = \frac{512}{3480796}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1875093} = \frac{492}{3750186} = \frac{902}{6875341}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{3086947} = \frac{502}{6173894} = \frac{753}{9260841}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1798034} = \frac{384}{2697051} = \frac{768}{5394102}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1875309} = \frac{492}{3750618} = \frac{984}{7501236}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{3089467} = \frac{502}{6178934} = \frac{753}{9268401}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1803974} = \frac{384}{2705961} = \frac{512}{3607948}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{246}{1875903} = \frac{492}{3751806} = \frac{984}{7503612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{251}{3094687} = \frac{502}{6189374} = \frac{753}{9284061}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1839740} = \frac{384}{2759610} = \frac{512}{3679480}$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1970384} = \frac{512}{3940768} = \frac{528}{4063917} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1973408} = \frac{824}{6351907} = \frac{928}{7153604} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1974038} = \frac{384}{2961057} = \frac{512}{3948076} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1978034} = \frac{384}{2967051} = \frac{768}{5934102} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1980374} = \frac{384}{2970561} = \frac{512}{3960748} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1983740} = \frac{384}{2975610} = \frac{512}{3967480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{1987304} = \frac{480}{3726195} = \frac{512}{3974608} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3719048} = \frac{480}{6973215} = \frac{512}{7438096} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3740198} = \frac{384}{5610297} = \frac{512}{7480396} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3741980} = \frac{384}{5612970} = \frac{512}{7483960} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3801974} = \frac{384}{5702961} = \frac{512}{7603948} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3819740} = \frac{384}{5729610} = \frac{512}{7639480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3974018} = \frac{384}{5961027} = \frac{512}{7948036} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3974180} = \frac{384}{5961270} = \frac{512}{7948360} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3980174} = \frac{384}{5970261} = \frac{512}{7960348} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{256}{3981740} = \frac{384}{5972610} = \frac{512}{7963480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{257}{1068349} = \frac{601}{2498357} = \frac{708}{2943156} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{257}{4813096} = \frac{382}{7154096} = \frac{487}{9120536} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1367490} = \frac{516}{2734980} = \frac{903}{4786215} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1603974} = \frac{387}{2405961} = \frac{516}{3207948} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1639074} = \frac{308}{1956724} = \frac{406}{2579318} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1639740} = \frac{387}{2459610} = \frac{516}{3279480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1740396} = \frac{387}{2610594} = \frac{516}{3480792} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1743960} = \frac{387}{2615940} = \frac{516}{3487920} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1960374} = \frac{387}{2940561} = \frac{516}{3920748} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1963740} = \frac{387}{2945610} = \frac{516}{3927480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1974036} = \frac{387}{2961054} = \frac{516}{3948072} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{1974360} = \frac{387}{2961540} = \frac{516}{3948720} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3016794} = \frac{528}{6173904} = \frac{807}{9436251} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3601974} = \frac{387}{5402961} = \frac{516}{7203948} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3740196} = \frac{387}{5610294} = \frac{516}{7480392} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3741960} = \frac{387}{5612940} = \frac{516}{7483920} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3940176} = \frac{301}{4596872} = \frac{387}{5910264} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3960174} = \frac{387}{5940261} = \frac{516}{7920348} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3961740} = \frac{387}{5942610} = \frac{516}{7923480} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3974016} = \frac{387}{5961024} = \frac{516}{7948032} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{3974160} = \frac{387}{5961240} = \frac{516}{7948320} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{4017936} = \frac{301}{4687592} = \frac{602}{9375184} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{4193706} = \frac{301}{4892657} = \frac{602}{9785314} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{4903617} = \frac{430}{8172695} = \frac{516}{9807234} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{258}{4963017} = \frac{354}{6809721} = \frac{430}{8271695} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{1304768} = \frac{329}{1657408} = \frac{378}{1904256} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{259}{4708361} = \frac{471}{8562309} = \frac{512}{9307648} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{1387945} = \frac{328}{1750946} = \frac{352}{1879064} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{1549873} = \frac{360}{2145978} = \frac{540}{3218967} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{1573984} = \frac{325}{1967480} = \frac{520}{3147968} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{1597384} = \frac{520}{3194768} = \frac{715}{4392806} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{1895374} = \frac{620}{4519738} = \frac{680}{4957132} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{260}{3197584} = \frac{725}{8916340} = \frac{745}{9162308} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{3957804} = \frac{347}{5261908} = \frac{536}{8127904} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{3974508} = \frac{315}{4796820} = \frac{549}{8360172} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{261}{4538790} = \frac{297}{5164830} = \frac{516}{8973240} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{263}{1457809} = \frac{342}{1895706} = \frac{536}{2971048} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{263}{5749180} = \frac{289}{6317540} = \frac{391}{8547260} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{264}{1380597} = \frac{352}{1840796} = \frac{704}{3681592} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{264}{1508397} = \frac{528}{3016794} = \frac{576}{3291048} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{264}{1597380} = \frac{286}{1730495} = \frac{528}{3194760} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{264}{1759380} = \frac{462}{3078915} = \frac{924}{6157830} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{264}{3519807} = \frac{528}{7039614} = \frac{704}{9386152} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{264}{5193870} = \frac{456}{8971230} = \frac{468}{9207315} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{1074893} = \frac{530}{2149786} = \frac{745}{3021869} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{1089347} = \frac{530}{2178694} = \frac{795}{3268041} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{1093487} = \frac{530}{2186974} = \frac{795}{3280461} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{1938740} &= \frac{529}{3870164} = \frac{573}{4192068} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{3709841} &= \frac{305}{4269817} = \frac{530}{7419682} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{265}{3841970} &= \frac{396}{5741208} = \frac{501}{7263498} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{1085493} &= \frac{534}{2170986} = \frac{801}{3256479} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{1308549} &= \frac{534}{2617098} = \frac{801}{3925647} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{1345089} &= \frac{534}{2690178} = \frac{712}{3586904} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{1385940} &= \frac{356}{1847920} = \frac{712}{3695840} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{1450893} &= \frac{534}{2901786} = \frac{801}{4352679} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{1453089} &= \frac{534}{2906178} = \frac{801}{4359267} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{3085491} &= \frac{534}{6170982} = \frac{801}{9256473} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{3089145} &= \frac{534}{6178290} = \frac{801}{9267435} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{3108549} &= \frac{534}{6217098} = \frac{801}{9325647} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{3145089} &= \frac{534}{6290178} = \frac{801}{9435267} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{3508914} &= \frac{459}{6032178} = \frac{531}{6978402} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{267}{4180953} &= \frac{417}{6529803} = \frac{504}{7892136} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{1057394} &= \frac{518}{2043769} = \frac{534}{2106897} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{1730945} &= \frac{712}{4598630} = \frac{952}{6148730} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{3571904} &= \frac{372}{4958016} = \frac{713}{9502864} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{268}{4735091} &= \frac{460}{8127395} = \frac{536}{9470182} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{1085473} &= \frac{538}{2170946} = \frac{807}{3256419} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{1308547} &= \frac{538}{2617094} = \frac{807}{3925641} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{1345807} &= \frac{581}{2906743} = \frac{906}{4532718} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{1408753} &= \frac{581}{3042697} = \frac{651}{3409287} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{1450873} &= \frac{538}{2901746} = \frac{807}{4352619} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{1453087} &= \frac{538}{2906174} = \frac{807}{4359261} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{3085471} &= \frac{538}{6170942} = \frac{807}{9256413} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{3087145} &= \frac{538}{6174290} = \frac{807}{9261435} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{3108547} &= \frac{538}{6217094} = \frac{807}{9325641} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{269}{3145087} &= \frac{538}{6290174} = \frac{807}{9435261} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1345869} &= \frac{540}{2691738} = \frac{960}{4785312} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1348569} &= \frac{540}{2697138} = \frac{720}{3596184} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1385694} &= \frac{360}{1847592} = \frac{720}{3695184} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1395684} &= \frac{540}{2791368} = \frac{675}{3489210} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1483569} &= \frac{540}{2967138} = \frac{720}{3956184} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1593648} &= \frac{540}{3187296} = \frac{675}{3984120} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1654398} &= \frac{285}{1746309} = \frac{570}{3492618} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1846935} &= \frac{576}{3940128} = \frac{984}{6731052} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1856493} &= \frac{540}{3712986} = \frac{860}{5913274} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{1935648} &= \frac{540}{3871296} = \frac{675}{4839120} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{3586194} &= \frac{360}{4781592} = \frac{720}{9563184} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{3914865} &= \frac{396}{5741802} = \frac{594}{8612703} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{3956418} &= \frac{390}{5714826} = \frac{540}{7912836} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{4961385} &= \frac{384}{7056192} = \frac{402}{7386951} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{270}{5861943} &= \frac{360}{7815924} = \frac{390}{8467251} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{271}{3068549} &= \frac{542}{6137098} = \frac{813}{9205647} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{271}{3085469} &= \frac{542}{6170938} = \frac{813}{9256407} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{271}{3804569} &= \frac{371}{5208469} = \frac{542}{7609138} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{271}{4563098} &= \frac{398}{6701524} = \frac{547}{9210386} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1068549} &= \frac{546}{2137098} = \frac{819}{3205647} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1085469} &= \frac{546}{2170938} = \frac{819}{3256407} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1450689} &= \frac{546}{2901378} = \frac{819}{4352067} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1450869} &= \frac{546}{2901738} = \frac{819}{4352607} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1549860} &= \frac{378}{2145960} = \frac{567}{3218940} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1864590} &= \frac{546}{3729180} = \frac{671}{4582930} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1865409} &= \frac{843}{5760219} = \frac{864}{5903712} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1896405} &= \frac{546}{3792810} = \frac{897}{6231045} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{1980654} &= \frac{651}{4723098} = \frac{693}{5027814} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{4015869} &= \frac{406}{5972318} = \frac{413}{6075289} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{4058691} &= \frac{327}{4861509} = \frac{654}{9723018} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{4165980} &= \frac{453}{6912780} = \frac{537}{8194620} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{273}{6459180} &= \frac{321}{7594860} = \frac{387}{9156420} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{274}{1095863} &= \frac{392}{1567804} = \frac{710}{2839645} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{274}{1396508} &= \frac{548}{2793016} = \frac{685}{3491270} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{1589063} = \frac{564}{3270918} = \frac{758}{4396021}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{3571694} = \frac{360}{4592178} = \frac{720}{9184356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1947063} = \frac{540}{3689172} = \frac{570}{3894126}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{274}{1603859} = \frac{526}{3078941} = \frac{670}{3921845}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{3591746} = \frac{420}{5387619} = \frac{560}{7183492}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1960743} = \frac{405}{2786319} = \frac{570}{3921486}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{275}{6938140} = \frac{285}{7190436} = \frac{290}{7316584}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{3714956} = \frac{470}{6235819} = \frac{730}{9685421}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1976304} = \frac{470}{3259168} = \frac{680}{4715392}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{3098514} = \frac{632}{7095148} = \frac{726}{8150439}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{3915746} = \frac{420}{5873619} = \frac{560}{7831492}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{3694170} = \frac{387}{5016294} = \frac{534}{6921708}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{3589104} = \frac{473}{6150892} = \frac{756}{9831024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{4915736} = \frac{320}{5617984} = \frac{560}{9831472}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{3901764} = \frac{480}{6571392} = \frac{540}{7392816}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{276}{4391850} = \frac{378}{6014925} = \frac{612}{9738450}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{281}{4637905} = \frac{283}{4670915} = \frac{362}{5974810}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{4706319} = \frac{540}{8917236} = \frac{570}{9412638}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{278}{3406195} = \frac{476}{5832190} = \frac{612}{7498530}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{283}{1069457} = \frac{534}{2017986} = \frac{798}{3015642}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{1035749} = \frac{506}{1832479} = \frac{854}{3092761}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{278}{6019534} = \frac{372}{8054916} = \frac{403}{8726159}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{284}{1396570} = \frac{402}{1976835} = \frac{568}{2793140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{1397045} = \frac{374}{1826905} = \frac{814}{3976205}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{278}{6954031} = \frac{316}{7904582} = \frac{364}{9105278}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{284}{1509673} = \frac{356}{1892407} = \frac{504}{2679138}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{1549730} = \frac{396}{2145780} = \frac{594}{3218670}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{279}{1540638} = \frac{327}{1805694} = \frac{561}{3097842}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{284}{1539067} = \frac{536}{2904718} = \frac{936}{5072418}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{1734590} = \frac{572}{3469180} = \frac{876}{5312940}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{279}{3156048} = \frac{398}{4502176} = \frac{532}{6017984}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{284}{1735960} = \frac{568}{3471920} = \frac{923}{5641870}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{1759043} = \frac{290}{1783645} = \frac{304}{1869752}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{279}{3815046} = \frac{432}{5907168} = \frac{531}{7260894}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1069347} = \frac{380}{1425796} = \frac{570}{2138694}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{1957304} = \frac{572}{3914608} = \frac{715}{4893260}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{279}{5340618} = \frac{298}{5704316} = \frac{508}{9724136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1347069} = \frac{570}{2694138} = \frac{760}{3592184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{3759041} = \frac{458}{6019723} = \frac{534}{7018629}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1346975} = \frac{408}{1962735} = \frac{816}{3925470}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1460739} = \frac{380}{1947652} = \frac{920}{4715368}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{4531709} = \frac{374}{5926081} = \frac{572}{9063418}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1349576} = \frac{490}{2361758} = \frac{980}{4723516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1609347} = \frac{380}{2145796} = \frac{570}{3218694}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{4591730} = \frac{572}{9183460} = \frac{584}{9376120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1573649} = \frac{320}{1798456} = \frac{560}{3147298}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1630947} = \frac{380}{2174596} = \frac{570}{3261894}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{286}{7103954} = \frac{326}{8097514} = \frac{368}{9140752}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1694357} = \frac{360}{2178459} = \frac{720}{4356918}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1640973} = \frac{510}{2936478} = \frac{570}{3281946}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1054396} = \frac{492}{1807536} = \frac{984}{3615072}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1745639} = \frac{560}{3491278} = \frac{840}{5236917}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1643097} = \frac{570}{3286194} = \frac{760}{4381592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1346509} = \frac{574}{2693018} = \frac{861}{4039527}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1793645} = \frac{408}{2613597} = \frac{712}{4560983}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1649307} = \frac{570}{3298614} = \frac{760}{4398152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1395640} = \frac{791}{3846520} = \frac{896}{4357120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1934765} = \frac{832}{5749016} = \frac{864}{5970132}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1906347} = \frac{380}{2541796} = \frac{570}{3812694}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1450693} = \frac{574}{2901386} = \frac{861}{4352079}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{280}{1947365} = \frac{680}{4729315} = \frac{728}{5063149}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{285}{1940736} = \frac{510}{3472896} = \frac{915}{6230784}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1453069} = \frac{574}{2906138} = \frac{861}{4359207}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1465093} = \frac{574}{2930186} = \frac{984}{5023176}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1365784} = \frac{910}{4285736} = \frac{970}{4568312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{3068547} = \frac{582}{6137094} = \frac{873}{9205641}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1634509} = \frac{574}{3269018} = \frac{861}{4903527}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1374658} = \frac{435}{2061987} = \frac{580}{2749316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{3085467} = \frac{582}{6170934} = \frac{873}{9256401}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{1940653} = \frac{371}{2508649} = \frac{784}{5301296}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1376485} = \frac{408}{1936572} = \frac{652}{3094718}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{3546708} = \frac{417}{5082396} = \frac{582}{7093416}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{3069145} = \frac{574}{6138290} = \frac{861}{9207435}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1378654} = \frac{435}{2067981} = \frac{870}{4135962}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{3657480} = \frac{582}{7314960} = \frac{679}{8534120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{3091564} = \frac{746}{8035912} = \frac{857}{9231604}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1465738} = \frac{435}{2198607} = \frac{580}{2931476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{291}{5476038} = \frac{309}{5814762} = \frac{485}{9126730}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{3145069} = \frac{574}{6290138} = \frac{861}{9435207}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1483756} = \frac{570}{2916348} = \frac{680}{3479152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{1068547} = \frac{586}{2137094} = \frac{879}{3205641}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{3450916} = \frac{574}{6901832} = \frac{615}{7394820}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1584736} = \frac{580}{3169472} = \frac{725}{3961840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{1085467} = \frac{586}{2170934} = \frac{879}{3256401}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{4315906} = \frac{291}{4376058} = \frac{615}{9248370}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1634875} = \frac{830}{4679125} = \frac{836}{4712950}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{1450687} = \frac{586}{2901374} = \frac{879}{4352061}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{287}{4395610} = \frac{427}{6539810} = \frac{532}{8147960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1643875} = \frac{348}{1972650} = \frac{870}{4931625}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{1450867} = \frac{586}{2901734} = \frac{879}{4352601}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1067345} = \frac{493}{1820765} = \frac{578}{2134690}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1734586} = \frac{435}{2601879} = \frac{580}{3469172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{293}{4817506} = \frac{429}{7053618} = \frac{438}{7201596}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1346507} = \frac{578}{2693014} = \frac{867}{4039521}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1745638} = \frac{580}{3491276} = \frac{870}{5236914}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1385670} = \frac{392}{1847560} = \frac{784}{3695120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1346570} = \frac{459}{2138670} = \frac{578}{2693140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1746538} = \frac{435}{2619807} = \frac{870}{5239614}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1680735} = \frac{378}{2160945} = \frac{756}{4321890}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1450673} = \frac{578}{2901346} = \frac{867}{4352019}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1843675} = \frac{468}{2975310} = \frac{916}{5823470}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1683507} = \frac{378}{2164509} = \frac{756}{4329018}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1453067} = \frac{578}{2906134} = \frac{867}{4359201}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1847356} = \frac{580}{3694712} = \frac{725}{4618390}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1683570} = \frac{378}{2164590} = \frac{756}{4329180}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1453670} = \frac{329}{1654870} = \frac{912}{4587360}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{1857346} = \frac{435}{2786019} = \frac{580}{3714692}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1736805} = \frac{298}{1760435} = \frac{912}{5387640}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1470653} = \frac{493}{2508761} = \frac{578}{2941306}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{3164857} = \frac{390}{4256187} = \frac{580}{6329714}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1853670} = \frac{438}{2761590} = \frac{681}{4293705}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1547306} = \frac{578}{3094612} = \frac{594}{3180276}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{3647185} = \frac{472}{5936108} = \frac{724}{9105386}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{1865073} = \frac{504}{3197268} = \frac{798}{5062341}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{1634507} = \frac{578}{3269014} = \frac{867}{4903521}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{290}{4563817} = \frac{460}{7239158} = \frac{580}{9127634}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3507168} = \frac{378}{4509216} = \frac{756}{9018432}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{3067145} = \frac{578}{6134290} = \frac{867}{9201435}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2905}{136784} = \frac{3920}{184576} = \frac{7840}{369152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3516807} = \frac{378}{4521609} = \frac{756}{9043218}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{3145067} = \frac{578}{6290134} = \frac{867}{9435201}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2905}{148673} = \frac{5810}{297346} = \frac{9130}{467258}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3570168} = \frac{378}{4590216} = \frac{756}{9180432}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{289}{3716540} = \frac{437}{5619820} = \frac{639}{8217540}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2905}{478163} = \frac{4085}{672391} = \frac{4235}{697081}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3571680} = \frac{378}{4592160} = \frac{756}{9184320}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3586170} = \frac{392}{4781560} = \frac{784}{9563120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{3058614} = \frac{396}{4078152} = \frac{792}{8156304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{1957286} = \frac{608}{3914572} = \frac{760}{4893215}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3708516} = \frac{513}{6470982} = \frac{693}{8741502}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{3608154} = \frac{594}{7216308} = \frac{783}{9512406}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{2157896} = \frac{608}{4315792} = \frac{874}{6203951}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{294}{3801567} = \frac{396}{5120478} = \frac{762}{9853041}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{3805164} = \frac{594}{7610328} = \frac{735}{9416820}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{2189576} = \frac{608}{4379152} = \frac{874}{6295031}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{295}{1637840} = \frac{357}{1982064} = \frac{579}{3214608}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{4013658} = \frac{309}{4175826} = \frac{594}{8027316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{2619587} = \frac{608}{5239174} = \frac{976}{8410253}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{295}{4871630} = \frac{521}{8603794} = \frac{543}{8967102}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{4036581} = \frac{429}{5830617} = \frac{594}{8073162}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{1267489} = \frac{610}{2534978} = \frac{915}{3802467}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{295}{7834610} = \frac{341}{9056278} = \frac{357}{9481206}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{4360158} = \frac{594}{8720316} = \frac{648}{9513072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{1268749} = \frac{610}{2537498} = \frac{915}{3806247}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{295}{7843106} = \frac{360}{9571248} = \frac{365}{9704182}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{5401836} = \frac{395}{7184260} = \frac{469}{8530172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{1274689} = \frac{610}{2549378} = \frac{915}{3824067}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{295}{8467031} = \frac{320}{9184576} = \frac{340}{9758612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{5481630} = \frac{351}{6478290} = \frac{513}{9468270}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{1274869} = \frac{610}{2549738} = \frac{915}{3824607}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{1583704} = \frac{592}{3167408} = \frac{962}{5147038}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2976}{108345} = \frac{3872}{140965} = \frac{9728}{354160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{1286749} = \frac{610}{2573498} = \frac{915}{3860247}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{296}{5047318} = \frac{416}{7093528} = \frac{512}{8730496}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2976}{413850} = \frac{4832}{671950} = \frac{4912}{683075}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{1287469} = \frac{610}{2574938} = \frac{915}{3862407}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1043658} = \frac{594}{2087316} = \frac{972}{3415608}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{3506417} = \frac{596}{7012834} = \frac{630}{7412895}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{1892647} = \frac{470}{2916538} = \frac{610}{3785294}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1380564} = \frac{396}{1840752} = \frac{792}{3681504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{298}{5071364} = \frac{534}{9087612} = \frac{541}{9206738}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{2674891} = \frac{610}{5349782} = \frac{915}{8024673}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1430865} = \frac{594}{2861730} = \frac{792}{3815640}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{301}{4572869} = \frac{516}{7839204} = \frac{602}{9145738}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{2687491} = \frac{610}{5374982} = \frac{915}{8062473}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1506384} = \frac{309}{1567248} = \frac{594}{3012768}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{302}{1498675} = \frac{348}{1726950} = \frac{970}{4813625}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{2748691} = \frac{610}{5497382} = \frac{915}{8246073}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1543608} = \frac{594}{3087216} = \frac{783}{4069512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{302}{1567984} = \frac{362}{1879504} = \frac{591}{3068472}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{2867491} = \frac{610}{5734982} = \frac{915}{8602473}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1543806} = \frac{594}{3087612} = \frac{987}{5130426}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{302}{4758916} = \frac{369}{5814702} = \frac{604}{9517832}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{305}{2874691} = \frac{610}{5749382} = \frac{915}{8624073}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1563804} = \frac{324}{1705968} = \frac{594}{3127608}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{1275698} = \frac{728}{3054961} = \frac{760}{3189245}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1548792} = \frac{357}{1806924} = \frac{612}{3097584}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1583604} = \frac{378}{2015496} = \frac{594}{3167208}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{1562978} = \frac{352}{1809764} = \frac{704}{3619528}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1729854} = \frac{612}{3459708} = \frac{867}{4901253}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1643085} = \frac{594}{3286170} = \frac{792}{4381560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{1598672} = \frac{342}{1798506} = \frac{684}{3597012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1789524} = \frac{561}{3280794} = \frac{612}{3579048}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1648053} = \frac{369}{2047581} = \frac{738}{4095162}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{1876592} = \frac{397}{2450681} = \frac{697}{4302581}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1792548} = \frac{358}{2097164} = \frac{591}{3462078}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{297}{1805436} = \frac{594}{3610872} = \frac{902}{5483176}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{304}{1928576} = \frac{439}{2785016} = \frac{596}{3781024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1894752} = \frac{612}{3789504} = \frac{981}{6074352}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1928547} = \frac{408}{2571396} = \frac{612}{3857094}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1268547} = \frac{618}{2537094} = \frac{927}{3805641}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{315}{2960748} = \frac{735}{6908412} = \frac{930}{8741256}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1945287} = \frac{408}{2593716} = \frac{612}{3890574}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1285467} = \frac{618}{2570934} = \frac{927}{3856401}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{315}{4289607} = \frac{630}{8579214} = \frac{640}{8715392}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1947852} = \frac{408}{2597136} = \frac{612}{3895704}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1452687} = \frac{618}{2905374} = \frac{927}{4358061}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{315}{7826490} = \frac{351}{8720946} = \frac{387}{9615402}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{1982574} = \frac{814}{5273906} = \frac{871}{5643209}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1452867} = \frac{618}{2905734} = \frac{927}{4358601}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{316}{2740589} = \frac{572}{4960813} = \frac{836}{7250419}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{2145978} = \frac{378}{2650914} = \frac{726}{5091438}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1457862} = \frac{465}{2193870} = \frac{852}{4019736}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{316}{2754098} = \frac{412}{3590786} = \frac{864}{7530192}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{2159748} = \frac{465}{3281970} = \frac{564}{3980712}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1587642} = \frac{465}{2389170} = \frac{879}{4516302}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{316}{2850794} = \frac{642}{5791803} = \frac{842}{7596103}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{306}{4578219} = \frac{418}{6253907} = \frac{492}{7361058}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{1752648} = \frac{387}{2195064} = \frac{735}{4168920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{316}{5408972} = \frac{317}{5426089} = \frac{512}{8763904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{1268549} = \frac{614}{2537098} = \frac{921}{3805647}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{2685471} = \frac{618}{5370942} = \frac{927}{8056413}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{318}{2096574} = \frac{459}{3026187} = \frac{918}{6052374}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{1285469} = \frac{614}{2570938} = \frac{921}{3856407}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{2687145} = \frac{618}{5374290} = \frac{927}{8061435}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{318}{4902765} = \frac{402}{6197835} = \frac{468}{7215390}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{1452689} = \frac{614}{2905378} = \frac{921}{4358067}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{2854671} = \frac{618}{5709342} = \frac{927}{8564013}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{319}{2078546} = \frac{407}{2651938} = \frac{638}{4157092}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{1452869} = \frac{614}{2905738} = \frac{921}{4358607}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{309}{2867145} = \frac{618}{5734290} = \frac{927}{8601435}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{319}{2648570} = \frac{429}{3561870} = \frac{638}{5297140}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{2469815} = \frac{807}{6492315} = \frac{938}{7546210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{2648795} = \frac{602}{5143789} = \frac{856}{7314092}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{319}{6485270} = \frac{354}{7196820} = \frac{412}{8375960}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{2685491} = \frac{614}{5370982} = \frac{921}{8056473}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{2698457} = \frac{410}{3568927} = \frac{670}{5832149}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1497568} = \frac{510}{2386749} = \frac{610}{2854739}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{2689145} = \frac{614}{5378290} = \frac{921}{8067435}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{4285967} = \frac{520}{7189364} = \frac{620}{8571934}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1567984} = \frac{480}{2351976} = \frac{860}{4213957}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{2854691} = \frac{614}{5709382} = \frac{921}{8564073}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{310}{4592867} = \frac{590}{8741263} = \frac{620}{9185734}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1578496} = \frac{870}{4291536} = \frac{920}{4538176}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{307}{2869145} = \frac{614}{5738290} = \frac{921}{8607435}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{4798560} = \frac{439}{6751820} = \frac{623}{9581740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1596784} = \frac{480}{2395176} = \frac{860}{4291357}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{308}{1652497} = \frac{468}{2510937} = \frac{936}{5021874}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{312}{5706948} = \frac{394}{7206851} = \frac{412}{7536098}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1769584} = \frac{540}{2986173} = \frac{720}{3981564}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{308}{1672594} = \frac{396}{2150478} = \frac{536}{2910748}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{314}{2675908} = \frac{508}{4329176} = \frac{956}{8147032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{320}{1954768} = \frac{520}{3176498} = \frac{540}{3298671}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{308}{1794562} = \frac{672}{3915408} = \frac{874}{5092361}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{315}{2089647} = \frac{560}{3714928} = \frac{820}{5439716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{1789506} = \frac{594}{3280761} = \frac{648}{3579012}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{308}{1956427} = \frac{756}{4802139} = \frac{952}{6047138}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{315}{2407986} = \frac{360}{2751984} = \frac{630}{4815972}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{1795608} = \frac{504}{2793168} = \frac{981}{5436702}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{308}{5716249} = \frac{312}{5790486} = \frac{432}{8017596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{315}{2786490} = \frac{609}{5387214} = \frac{715}{6324890}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{1895076} = \frac{648}{3790152} = \frac{903}{5281647}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{1897506} = \frac{648}{3795012} = \frac{876}{5130294}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{5046918} = \frac{427}{6590318} = \frac{601}{9275834}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2197856} = \frac{510}{3296784} = \frac{680}{4395712}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{1897560} = \frac{648}{3795120} = \frac{918}{5376420}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{1596704} = \frac{561}{2730948} = \frac{815}{3967420}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2198576} = \frac{510}{3297864} = \frac{680}{4397152}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{324}{1908576} = \frac{459}{2703816} = \frac{918}{5407632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{1679054} = \frac{820}{4197635} = \frac{984}{5037162}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2571896} = \frac{345}{2609718} = \frac{680}{5143792}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{1068947} = \frac{650}{2137894} = \frac{975}{3206841}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{1759064} = \frac{481}{2579603} = \frac{801}{4295763}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2587196} = \frac{680}{5174392} = \frac{940}{7152836}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{1069487} = \frac{650}{2138974} = \frac{975}{3208461}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{328}{4950176} = \frac{349}{5267108} = \frac{485}{7319620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2619785} = \frac{508}{3914267} = \frac{684}{5270391}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{1086947} = \frac{650}{2173894} = \frac{975}{3260841}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{1047865} = \frac{678}{2159430} = \frac{798}{2541630}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2759168} = \frac{640}{5193728} = \frac{895}{7263104}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{1089467} = \frac{650}{2178934} = \frac{975}{3268401}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{1068547} = \frac{658}{2137094} = \frac{987}{3205641}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2971856} = \frac{680}{5943712} = \frac{935}{8172604}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{1094687} = \frac{650}{2189374} = \frac{975}{3284061}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{1085467} = \frac{658}{2170934} = \frac{987}{3256401}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{341}{2786590} = \frac{671}{5483290} = \frac{847}{6921530}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{1094867} = \frac{650}{2189734} = \frac{975}{3284601}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{1450687} = \frac{658}{2901374} = \frac{987}{4352061}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{341}{5809276} = \frac{471}{8023956} = \frac{509}{8671324}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{1789640} = \frac{390}{2147568} = \frac{780}{4295136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{329}{1450867} = \frac{658}{2901734} = \frac{987}{4352601}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{341}{5986720} = \frac{352}{6179840} = \frac{429}{7531680}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{4601987} = \frac{425}{6017983} = \frac{450}{6371982}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{1768952} = \frac{760}{3954128} = \frac{765}{3980142}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1508796} = \frac{684}{3017592} = \frac{741}{3269058}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{325}{4906187} = \frac{450}{6793182} = \frac{650}{9812374}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{1785962} = \frac{510}{2678943} = \frac{680}{3571924}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1785960} = \frac{513}{2678940} = \frac{684}{3571920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{1589704} = \frac{652}{3179408} = \frac{815}{3974260}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{1798562} = \frac{510}{2697843} = \frac{680}{3597124}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1786095} = \frac{684}{3572190} = \frac{756}{3948210}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{1749805} = \frac{368}{1975240} = \frac{498}{2673015}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{1857962} = \frac{510}{2786943} = \frac{680}{3715924}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1798560} = \frac{513}{2697840} = \frac{684}{3597120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{1895704} = \frac{652}{3791408} = \frac{815}{4739260}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{1859762} = \frac{510}{2789643} = \frac{680}{3719524}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1857960} = \frac{513}{2786940} = \frac{684}{3715920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{326}{4501897} = \frac{536}{7401892} = \frac{610}{8423795}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{1978562} = \frac{510}{2967843} = \frac{680}{3957124}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1859760} = \frac{513}{2789640} = \frac{684}{3719520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{1068549} = \frac{654}{2137098} = \frac{981}{3205647}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{1985762} = \frac{510}{2978643} = \frac{680}{3971524}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1890576} = \frac{591}{3267048} = \frac{936}{5174208}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{1085469} = \frac{654}{2170938} = \frac{981}{3256407}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2178596} = \frac{510}{3267894} = \frac{680}{4357192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1957608} = \frac{648}{3709152} = \frac{927}{5306148}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{1450689} = \frac{654}{2901378} = \frac{981}{4352067}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2179856} = \frac{510}{3269784} = \frac{680}{4359712}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1957860} = \frac{627}{3589410} = \frac{684}{3915720}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{1450869} = \frac{654}{2901738} = \frac{981}{4352607}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2185796} = \frac{510}{3278694} = \frac{680}{4371592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1978560} = \frac{513}{2967840} = \frac{684}{3957120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{327}{4165980} = \frac{543}{6917820} = \frac{651}{8293740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{340}{2185976} = \frac{510}{3278964} = \frac{680}{4371952}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{1985760} = \frac{513}{2978640} = \frac{684}{3971520}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{342}{5978160} = \frac{354}{6187920} = \frac{513}{8967240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{1784096} = \frac{374}{1895602} = \frac{704}{3568192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2940168} = \frac{459}{3780216} = \frac{918}{7560432}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{1609287} = \frac{510}{2378946} = \frac{690}{3218574}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{1906784} = \frac{493}{2670581} = \frac{712}{3856904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{4296180} = \frac{527}{6341980} = \frac{714}{8592360}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{1860792} = \frac{690}{3721584} = \frac{710}{3829456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{1947680} = \frac{572}{3164980} = \frac{594}{3286710}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{4296801} = \frac{392}{4718056} = \frac{714}{8593602}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{345}{2167980} = \frac{729}{4581036} = \frac{798}{5014632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{4678091} = \frac{480}{6379215} = \frac{704}{9356182}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{4902681} = \frac{497}{6825301} = \frac{714}{9805362}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{1095782} = \frac{496}{1570832} = \frac{901}{2853467}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{354}{2091786} = \frac{504}{2978136} = \frac{948}{5601732}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{1269704} = \frac{716}{2539408} = \frac{895}{3174260}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{1850927} = \frac{692}{3701854} = \frac{948}{5071326}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{356}{1478290} = \frac{452}{1876930} = \frac{576}{2391840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{1296704} = \frac{716}{2593408} = \frac{895}{3241760}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{346}{2507981} = \frac{370}{2681945} = \frac{902}{6538147}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{356}{1849270} = \frac{712}{3698540} = \frac{890}{4623175}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{358}{2197046} = \frac{587}{3602419} = \frac{738}{4529106}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{1069752} = \frac{642}{1973508} = \frac{645}{1982730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{356}{2079841} = \frac{604}{3528719} = \frac{652}{3809147}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{1482670} = \frac{426}{1759380} = \frac{718}{2965340}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{1259760} = \frac{486}{1759320} = \frac{972}{3518640}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{356}{2109478} = \frac{846}{5012973} = \frac{926}{5487013}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{4170862} = \frac{432}{5018976} = \frac{693}{8051274}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{348}{1602975} = \frac{396}{1824075} = \frac{792}{3648150}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{356}{4192078} = \frac{628}{7395014} = \frac{726}{8549013}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{359}{6481027} = \frac{406}{7329518} = \frac{471}{8502963}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{349}{1026758} = \frac{503}{1479826} = \frac{743}{2185906}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{1680294} = \frac{459}{2160378} = \frac{918}{4320756}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1527948} = \frac{460}{1952378} = \frac{870}{3692541}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{349}{6718250} = \frac{431}{8296750} = \frac{463}{8912750}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{1682940} = \frac{459}{2163780} = \frac{918}{4327560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1572984} = \frac{720}{3145968} = \frac{790}{3451826}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{350}{1496278} = \frac{450}{1923786} = \frac{975}{4168203}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{1694028} = \frac{459}{2178036} = \frac{918}{4356072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1574928} = \frac{395}{1728046} = \frac{720}{3149856}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{2069847} = \frac{687}{4051239} = \frac{912}{5378064}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{1694280} = \frac{459}{2178360} = \frac{918}{4356720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1597824} = \frac{720}{3195648} = \frac{780}{3461952}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{2849067} = \frac{702}{5698134} = \frac{752}{6103984}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2601984} = \frac{714}{5203968} = \frac{935}{6814720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1794582} = \frac{540}{2691873} = \frac{720}{3589164}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{2876094} = \frac{648}{5309712} = \frac{783}{6415902}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2604819} = \frac{561}{4093287} = \frac{714}{5209638}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1795248} = \frac{765}{3814902} = \frac{975}{4862130}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{4098276} = \frac{765}{8932140} = \frac{801}{9352476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2648019} = \frac{714}{5296038} = \frac{952}{7061384}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1825974} = \frac{540}{2738961} = \frac{720}{3651948}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{4296708} = \frac{513}{6279804} = \frac{702}{8593416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2801694} = \frac{459}{3602178} = \frac{918}{7204356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1845792} = \frac{720}{3691584} = \frac{805}{4127396}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{4829760} = \frac{523}{7196480} = \frac{687}{9453120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2814690} = \frac{714}{5629380} = \frac{819}{6457230}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1945287} = \frac{480}{2593716} = \frac{960}{5187432}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{351}{4907682} = \frac{561}{7843902} = \frac{702}{9815364}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2816940} = \frac{459}{3621780} = \frac{918}{7243560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1945782} = \frac{540}{2918673} = \frac{720}{3891564}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{352}{1609784} = \frac{704}{3219568} = \frac{856}{3914702}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{357}{2861940} = \frac{476}{3815920} = \frac{952}{7631840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{1982574} = \frac{540}{2973861} = \frac{720}{3965148}$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{2147598} = \frac{640}{3817952} = \frac{780}{4653129}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{2985710} = \frac{572}{4691830} = \frac{724}{5938610}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{2459168} = \frac{560}{3721984} = \frac{980}{6513472}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{2179458} = \frac{540}{3269187} = \frac{720}{4358916}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{365}{1792480} = \frac{438}{2150976} = \frac{876}{4301952}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{2469158} = \frac{680}{4537912} = \frac{860}{5739124}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{2197584} = \frac{495}{3021678} = \frac{720}{4395168}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{365}{2418709} = \frac{495}{3280167} = \frac{635}{4207891}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{2945681} = \frac{520}{4139876} = \frac{740}{5891362}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{2415978} = \frac{720}{4831956} = \frac{780}{5234619}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1204579} = \frac{736}{2409158} = \frac{768}{2513904}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{5429861} = \frac{570}{8364921} = \frac{670}{9832451}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{2419758} = \frac{720}{4839516} = \frac{940}{6318257}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1209754} = \frac{736}{2419508} = \frac{840}{2761395}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{371}{2084596} = \frac{679}{3815204} = \frac{735}{4129860}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{2574198} = \frac{540}{3861297} = \frac{720}{5148396}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1259470} = \frac{736}{2518940} = \frac{920}{3148675}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{371}{5064892} = \frac{534}{7290168} = \frac{641}{8750932}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{2581974} = \frac{540}{3872961} = \frac{720}{5163948}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1274590} = \frac{736}{2549180} = \frac{920}{3186475}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{371}{5084926} = \frac{431}{5907286} = \frac{607}{8319542}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{2597418} = \frac{540}{3896127} = \frac{720}{5194836}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1459270} = \frac{736}{2918540} = \frac{920}{3648175}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{372}{1495068} = \frac{408}{1639752} = \frac{816}{3279504}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{2598174} = \frac{540}{3897261} = \frac{720}{5196348}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1472590} = \frac{736}{2945180} = \frac{920}{3681475}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{372}{1584069} = \frac{604}{2571983} = \frac{820}{3491765}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{360}{4971528} = \frac{615}{8493027} = \frac{645}{8907321}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1592704} = \frac{402}{1739856} = \frac{503}{2176984}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{372}{1584906} = \frac{478}{2036519} = \frac{970}{4132685}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{361}{4570982} = \frac{397}{5026814} = \frac{471}{5963802}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{1957024} = \frac{572}{3041896} = \frac{791}{4206538}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{372}{4096185} = \frac{648}{7135290} = \frac{864}{9513720}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{362}{1794580} = \frac{543}{2691870} = \frac{724}{3589160}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{368}{4509127} = \frac{736}{9018254} = \frac{768}{9410352}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{372}{4598106} = \frac{508}{6279134} = \frac{518}{6402739}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{362}{1945780} = \frac{543}{2918670} = \frac{724}{3891560}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{369}{1580427} = \frac{394}{1687502} = \frac{726}{3109458}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{372}{4891056} = \frac{613}{8059724} = \frac{639}{8401572}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{362}{1978054} = \frac{543}{2967081} = \frac{724}{3956108}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{369}{1874520} = \frac{531}{2697480} = \frac{837}{4251960}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1596028} = \frac{385}{1642970} = \frac{748}{3192056}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{362}{4705819} = \frac{396}{5147802} = \frac{754}{9801623}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{369}{7041258} = \frac{456}{8701392} = \frac{504}{9617328}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1602598} = \frac{561}{2403897} = \frac{748}{3205196}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1507298} = \frac{728}{3014596} = \frac{910}{3768245}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{1259468} = \frac{740}{2518936} = \frac{925}{3148670}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1625980} = \frac{561}{2438970} = \frac{748}{3251960}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1908725} = \frac{908}{4761325} = \frac{916}{4803275}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{1265948} = \frac{740}{2531896} = \frac{925}{3164870}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1690582} = \frac{814}{3679502} = \frac{891}{4027563}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{1957280} = \frac{483}{2597160} = \frac{728}{3914560}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{1459268} = \frac{740}{2918536} = \frac{925}{3648170}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1802596} = \frac{561}{2703894} = \frac{748}{3605192}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{2019758} = \frac{728}{4039516} = \frac{938}{5204761}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{1465829} = \frac{630}{2495871} = \frac{740}{2931658}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1825960} = \frac{561}{2738940} = \frac{748}{3651920}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{2501798} = \frac{602}{4137589} = \frac{924}{6350718}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{1469825} = \frac{548}{2176930} = \frac{782}{3106495}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1960258} = \frac{561}{2940387} = \frac{748}{3920516}$ |
| $\blacktriangleright \frac{364}{2951078} = \frac{406}{3291587} = \frac{476}{3859102}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{370}{1982645} = \frac{910}{4876235} = \frac{978}{5240613}$ | $\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1962580} = \frac{561}{2943870} = \frac{748}{3925160}$ |

$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1980256} = \frac{561}{2970384} = \frac{748}{3960512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{2019458} = \frac{564}{3029187} = \frac{752}{4038916}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2105946} = \frac{763}{4250891} = \frac{973}{5420861}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{1982560} = \frac{561}{2973840} = \frac{748}{3965120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{2054198} = \frac{564}{3081297} = \frac{752}{4108396}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2159640} = \frac{621}{3547980} = \frac{756}{4319280}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2560198} = \frac{561}{3840297} = \frac{748}{5120396}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{2194580} = \frac{564}{3291870} = \frac{752}{4389160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2165940} = \frac{567}{3248910} = \frac{792}{4538160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2561980} = \frac{561}{3842970} = \frac{748}{5123960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{2198054} = \frac{564}{3297081} = \frac{752}{4396108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2196054} = \frac{567}{3294081} = \frac{756}{4392108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2580196} = \frac{561}{3870294} = \frac{748}{5160392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1046952} = \frac{931}{2578604} = \frac{945}{2617380}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2546019} = \frac{786}{5294103} = \frac{894}{6021537}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2581960} = \frac{561}{3872940} = \frac{748}{5163920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1069524} = \frac{756}{2139048} = \frac{945}{2673810}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2560194} = \frac{567}{3840291} = \frac{576}{3901248}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2596018} = \frac{561}{3894027} = \frac{748}{5192036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1254960} = \frac{524}{1739680} = \frac{954}{3167280}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{4129650} = \frac{769}{8401325} = \frac{862}{9417350}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2596180} = \frac{561}{3894270} = \frac{748}{5192360}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1509624} = \frac{469}{1873052} = \frac{756}{3019248}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{4659120} = \frac{693}{8541720} = \frac{756}{9318240}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2598016} = \frac{561}{3897024} = \frac{748}{5196032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1564920} = \frac{468}{1937520} = \frac{756}{3129840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{379}{2568104} = \frac{829}{5617304} = \frac{907}{6145832}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{2598160} = \frac{561}{3897240} = \frac{748}{5196320}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1609254} = \frac{742}{3158906} = \frac{847}{3605921}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{1625974} = \frac{570}{2438961} = \frac{760}{3251948}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{5021698} = \frac{429}{5760183} = \frac{543}{7290861}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1640952} = \frac{504}{2187936} = \frac{756}{3281904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{1729456} = \frac{760}{3458912} = \frac{795}{3618204}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{5960218} = \frac{561}{8940327} = \frac{612}{9753084}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1649052} = \frac{504}{2198736} = \frac{756}{3298104}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{1794265} = \frac{604}{2851937} = \frac{980}{4627315}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{5981620} = \frac{561}{8972430} = \frac{572}{9148360}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1659420} = \frac{423}{1856970} = \frac{567}{2489130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{1794562} = \frac{570}{2691843} = \frac{760}{3589124}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{374}{6029815} = \frac{418}{6739205} = \frac{610}{9834725}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1925640} = \frac{497}{2531860} = \frac{749}{3815620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{1945762} = \frac{570}{2918643} = \frac{760}{3891524}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1582490} = \frac{472}{1986530} = \frac{752}{3164980}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1945602} = \frac{567}{2918403} = \frac{756}{3891204}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{1962574} = \frac{570}{2943861} = \frac{760}{3925148}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1854902} = \frac{436}{2150897} = \frac{728}{3591406}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1945620} = \frac{567}{2918430} = \frac{756}{3891240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{1974256} = \frac{570}{2961384} = \frac{760}{3948512}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1945802} = \frac{564}{2918703} = \frac{752}{3891604}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1960542} = \frac{567}{2940813} = \frac{756}{3921084}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{2179456} = \frac{570}{3269184} = \frac{760}{4358912}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1945820} = \frac{564}{2918730} = \frac{752}{3891640}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1962054} = \frac{567}{2943081} = \frac{756}{3924108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{2419765} = \frac{456}{2903718} = \frac{912}{5807436}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1980542} = \frac{564}{2970813} = \frac{752}{3961084}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{1964520} = \frac{574}{2983160} = \frac{658}{3419720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{2561974} = \frac{570}{3842961} = \frac{760}{5123948}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1982054} = \frac{564}{2973081} = \frac{752}{3964108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2019456} = \frac{567}{3029184} = \frac{756}{4038912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{2596174} = \frac{570}{3894261} = \frac{760}{5192348}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{376}{1984052} = \frac{658}{3472091} = \frac{752}{3968104}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{378}{2054196} = \frac{567}{3081294} = \frac{756}{4108392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{380}{2597416} = \frac{570}{3896124} = \frac{760}{5194832}$

▶ $\frac{380}{2974165} = \frac{492}{3850761} = \frac{820}{6417935}$

▶ $\frac{381}{2506974} = \frac{635}{4178290} = \frac{762}{5013948}$

▶ $\frac{381}{2509674} = \frac{635}{4182790} = \frac{762}{5019348}$

▶ $\frac{381}{2567940} = \frac{781}{5263940} = \frac{813}{5479620}$

▶ $\frac{381}{2607945} = \frac{387}{2649015} = \frac{798}{5462310}$

▶ $\frac{381}{2647950} = \frac{681}{4732950} = \frac{897}{6234150}$

▶ $\frac{381}{2796540} = \frac{738}{5416920} = \frac{813}{5967420}$

▶ $\frac{381}{4765092} = \frac{635}{7941820} = \frac{762}{9530184}$

▶ $\frac{381}{4907652} = \frac{635}{8179420} = \frac{762}{9815304}$

▶ $\frac{381}{7245096} = \frac{435}{8271960} = \frac{457}{8690312}$

▶ $\frac{382}{1740965} = \frac{392}{1786540} = \frac{614}{2798305}$

▶ $\frac{382}{1794560} = \frac{573}{2691840} = \frac{764}{3589120}$

▶ $\frac{382}{1796054} = \frac{573}{2694081} = \frac{764}{3592108}$

▶ $\frac{382}{1945760} = \frac{573}{2918640} = \frac{764}{3891520}$

▶ $\frac{382}{1976054} = \frac{573}{2964081} = \frac{764}{3952108}$

▶ $\frac{384}{1065792} = \frac{578}{1604239} = \frac{914}{2536807}$

▶ $\frac{384}{1527096} = \frac{768}{3054192} = \frac{816}{3245079}$

▶ $\frac{384}{1572960} = \frac{432}{1769580} = \frac{768}{3145920}$

▶ $\frac{384}{1607952} = \frac{752}{3148906} = \frac{768}{3215904}$

▶ $\frac{384}{1657920} = \frac{684}{2953170} = \frac{714}{3082695}$

▶ $\frac{384}{1709526} = \frac{768}{3419052} = \frac{960}{4273815}$

▶ $\frac{384}{1752960} = \frac{792}{3615480} = \frac{879}{4012635}$

▶ $\frac{384}{1902576} = \frac{648}{3210597} = \frac{952}{4716803}$

▶ $\frac{384}{1976052} = \frac{672}{3458091} = \frac{768}{3952104}$

▶ $\frac{384}{2017596} = \frac{608}{3194527} = \frac{768}{4035192}$

▶ $\frac{384}{2150976} = \frac{516}{2890374} = \frac{768}{4301952}$

▶ $\frac{384}{2970156} = \frac{480}{3712695} = \frac{768}{5940312}$

▶ $\frac{384}{2970516} = \frac{672}{5198403} = \frac{768}{5941032}$

▶ $\frac{385}{1724690} = \frac{392}{1756048} = \frac{784}{3512096}$

▶ $\frac{385}{4271960} = \frac{817}{9065432} = \frac{845}{9376120}$

▶ $\frac{386}{4712095} = \frac{602}{7348915} = \frac{690}{8423175}$

▶ $\frac{387}{1054962} = \frac{903}{2461578} = \frac{943}{2570618}$

▶ $\frac{387}{1260459} = \frac{763}{2485091} = \frac{972}{3165804}$

▶ $\frac{387}{1296450} = \frac{789}{2643150} = \frac{819}{2743650}$

▶ $\frac{387}{2061549} = \frac{503}{2679481} = \frac{863}{4597201}$

▶ $\frac{387}{4025961} = \frac{578}{6012934} = \frac{683}{7105249}$

▶ $\frac{387}{4965210} = \frac{657}{8429310} = \frac{726}{9314580}$

▶ $\frac{389}{1207456} = \frac{593}{1840672} = \frac{914}{2837056}$

▶ $\frac{389}{1624075} = \frac{674}{2813950} = \frac{829}{3461075}$

▶ $\frac{389}{2765401} = \frac{568}{4037912} = \frac{857}{6092413}$

▶ $\frac{390}{1274568} = \frac{780}{2549136} = \frac{975}{3186420}$

▶ $\frac{390}{1456728} = \frac{780}{2913456} = \frac{975}{3641820}$

▶ $\frac{390}{1472568} = \frac{780}{2945136} = \frac{975}{3681420}$

▶ $\frac{390}{1562478} = \frac{780}{3124956} = \frac{910}{3645782}$

▶ $\frac{390}{1578246} = \frac{780}{3156492} = \frac{910}{3682574}$

▶ $\frac{390}{1687452} = \frac{960}{4153728} = \frac{975}{4218630}$

▶ $\frac{390}{1824576} = \frac{780}{3649152} = \frac{915}{4280736}$

▶ $\frac{390}{1874652} = \frac{795}{3821406} = \frac{820}{3941576}$

▶ $\frac{390}{2164578} = \frac{590}{3274618} = \frac{780}{4329156}$

▶ $\frac{390}{2458716} = \frac{495}{3120678} = \frac{720}{4539168}$

▶ $\frac{390}{2461578} = \frac{780}{4923156} = \frac{910}{5743682}$

▶ $\frac{390}{2478156} = \frac{780}{4956312} = \frac{910}{5782364}$

▶ $\frac{390}{2865174} = \frac{870}{6391542} = \frac{985}{7236401}$

▶ $\frac{390}{4178265} = \frac{482}{5163907} = \frac{578}{6192403}$

▶ $\frac{390}{4216875} = \frac{396}{4281750} = \frac{834}{9017625}$

▶ $\frac{390}{4527861} = \frac{740}{8591326} = \frac{840}{9752316}$

▶ $\frac{391}{2706548} = \frac{782}{5413096} = \frac{935}{6472180}$

▶ $\frac{392}{1047865} = \frac{496}{1325870} = \frac{728}{1946035}$

▶ $\frac{392}{1075648} = \frac{504}{1382976} = \frac{736}{2019584}$

▶ $\frac{392}{1467508} = \frac{756}{2830194} = \frac{784}{2935016}$

▶ $\frac{392}{1745086} = \frac{420}{1869735} = \frac{980}{4362715}$

▶ $\frac{392}{1746850} = \frac{824}{3671950} = \frac{980}{4367125}$

▶ $\frac{392}{4580716} = \frac{462}{5398701} = \frac{762}{8904351}$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{392}{4718560} = \frac{427}{5139860} = \frac{742}{8931560}$ | ▶ $\frac{396}{2574180} = \frac{594}{3861270} = \frac{792}{5148360}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{2574016} = \frac{597}{3861024} = \frac{796}{5148032}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{392}{4780615} = \frac{672}{8195340} = \frac{784}{9561230}$ | ▶ $\frac{396}{2580174} = \frac{594}{3870261} = \frac{792}{5160348}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{2574160} = \frac{597}{3861240} = \frac{796}{5148320}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{394}{1068725} = \frac{724}{1963850} = \frac{910}{2468375}$ | ▶ $\frac{396}{2581740} = \frac{594}{3872610} = \frac{792}{5163480}$ | ▶ $\frac{401}{5239867} = \frac{407}{5318269} = \frac{708}{9251436}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{394}{2701658} = \frac{748}{5129036} = \frac{862}{5910734}$ | ▶ $\frac{396}{2758140} = \frac{768}{5349120} = \frac{824}{5739160}$ | ▶ $\frac{401}{8596237} = \frac{423}{9067851} = \frac{428}{9175036}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{394}{8075621} = \frac{406}{8321579} = \frac{426}{8731509}$ | ▶ $\frac{396}{4021578} = \frac{496}{5037128} = \frac{792}{8043156}$ | ▶ $\frac{402}{1379865} = \frac{524}{1798630} = \frac{956}{3281470}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{395}{1086724} = \frac{465}{1279308} = \frac{780}{2145936}$ | ▶ $\frac{396}{4105728} = \frac{693}{7185024} = \frac{873}{9051264}$ | ▶ $\frac{402}{1965378} = \frac{729}{3564081} = \frac{831}{4062759}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{1457820} = \frac{528}{1943760} = \frac{594}{2186730}$ | ▶ $\frac{396}{4180257} = \frac{572}{6038149} = \frac{792}{8360514}$ | ▶ $\frac{403}{1259687} = \frac{651}{2034879} = \frac{806}{2519374}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{1740258} = \frac{594}{2610387} = \frac{792}{3480516}$ | ▶ $\frac{397}{1825406} = \frac{451}{2073698} = \frac{794}{3650812}$ | ▶ $\frac{403}{1286597} = \frac{651}{2078349} = \frac{806}{2573194}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{1742580} = \frac{594}{2613870} = \frac{792}{3485160}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{1507624} = \frac{406}{1537928} = \frac{796}{3015248}$ | ▶ $\frac{403}{1628957} = \frac{806}{3257914} = \frac{871}{3520649}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{1758240} = \frac{792}{3516480} = \frac{972}{4315680}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{1602574} = \frac{597}{2403861} = \frac{796}{3205148}$ | ▶ $\frac{403}{6981572} = \frac{501}{8679324} = \frac{504}{8731296}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{1780542} = \frac{594}{2670813} = \frac{792}{3561084}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{1625740} = \frac{597}{2438610} = \frac{796}{3251480}$ | ▶ $\frac{405}{1367982} = \frac{540}{1823976} = \frac{810}{2735964}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{1782054} = \frac{594}{2673081} = \frac{792}{3564108}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{1706425} = \frac{796}{3412850} = \frac{938}{4021675}$ | ▶ $\frac{405}{1637982} = \frac{540}{2183976} = \frac{810}{3275964}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{1802574} = \frac{594}{2703861} = \frac{792}{3605148}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{1740256} = \frac{597}{2610384} = \frac{796}{3480512}$ | ▶ $\frac{405}{1739826} = \frac{540}{2319768} = \frac{810}{3479652}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{1807542} = \frac{792}{3615084} = \frac{810}{3697245}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{1742560} = \frac{597}{2613840} = \frac{796}{3485120}$ | ▶ $\frac{405}{1798362} = \frac{540}{2397816} = \frac{810}{3596724}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{1825740} = \frac{594}{2738610} = \frac{792}{3651480}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{1760542} = \frac{597}{2640813} = \frac{796}{3521084}$ | ▶ $\frac{405}{1798632} = \frac{540}{2398176} = \frac{810}{3597264}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{2017584} = \frac{627}{3194508} = \frac{792}{4035168}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{1762054} = \frac{597}{2643081} = \frac{796}{3524108}$ | ▶ $\frac{405}{3169287} = \frac{480}{3756192} = \frac{960}{7512384}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{2054178} = \frac{594}{3081267} = \frac{792}{4108356}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{2054176} = \frac{597}{3081264} = \frac{796}{4108352}$ | ▶ $\frac{406}{1258397} = \frac{596}{1847302} = \frac{658}{2039471}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{2075148} = \frac{704}{3689152} = \frac{781}{4092653}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{2057461} = \frac{678}{3504921} = \frac{756}{3908142}$ | ▶ $\frac{406}{3952178} = \frac{714}{6950382} = \frac{812}{7904356}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{2178054} = \frac{594}{3267081} = \frac{792}{4356108}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{2176054} = \frac{597}{3264081} = \frac{796}{4352108}$ | ▶ $\frac{407}{2895361} = \frac{429}{3051867} = \frac{803}{5712469}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{2417580} = \frac{792}{4835160} = \frac{936}{5714280}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{2560174} = \frac{597}{3840261} = \frac{796}{5120348}$ | ▶ $\frac{407}{6391528} = \frac{459}{7208136} = \frac{529}{8307416}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{396}{2574018} = \frac{594}{3861027} = \frac{792}{5148036}$ | ▶ $\frac{398}{2561740} = \frac{597}{3842610} = \frac{796}{5123480}$ | ▶ $\frac{407}{8269315} = \frac{429}{8716305} = \frac{473}{9610285}$ |

$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{1293756} = \frac{476}{1509382} = \frac{952}{3018764}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{415}{3260987} = \frac{610}{4793258} = \frac{830}{6521974}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{427}{1859036} = \frac{728}{3169504} = \frac{756}{3291408}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{1357926} = \frac{420}{1397865} = \frac{804}{2675913}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{3780952} = \frac{832}{7561904} = \frac{936}{8507142}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{427}{3086951} = \frac{671}{4850923} = \frac{854}{6173902}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{1572936} = \frac{476}{1835092} = \frac{952}{3670184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{3789520} = \frac{702}{6394815} = \frac{806}{7342195}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{428}{3705196} = \frac{801}{6934257} = \frac{856}{7410392}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{2179536} = \frac{567}{3028914} = \frac{816}{4359072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{416}{7350928} = \frac{506}{8941273} = \frac{514}{9082637}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{3105687} = \frac{627}{4539081} = \frac{891}{6450273}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{2537196} = \frac{612}{3805794} = \frac{816}{5074392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{417}{2509638} = \frac{695}{4182730} = \frac{834}{5019276}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{5310786} = \frac{462}{5719308} = \frac{495}{6127830}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{2539716} = \frac{612}{3809574} = \frac{816}{5079432}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{417}{2580396} = \frac{435}{2691780} = \frac{834}{5160792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{5316870} = \frac{473}{5862190} = \frac{594}{7361820}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{3169752} = \frac{792}{6153048} = \frac{948}{7365012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{417}{3285960} = \frac{819}{6453720} = \frac{834}{6571920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{5671380} = \frac{431}{5697820} = \frac{713}{9425860}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{3769512} = \frac{501}{4628739} = \frac{816}{7539024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{417}{5039862} = \frac{537}{6490182} = \frac{615}{7432890}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{429}{7806513} = \frac{457}{8316029} = \frac{521}{9480637}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{6517392} = \frac{439}{7012586} = \frac{458}{7316092}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{3750296} = \frac{835}{7491620} = \frac{846}{7590312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{431}{6752908} = \frac{452}{7081936} = \frac{549}{8601732}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{408}{6719352} = \frac{409}{6735821} = \frac{583}{9601427}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{3952076} = \frac{803}{7592146} = \frac{836}{7904152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{1067985} = \frac{576}{1423980} = \frac{864}{2135970}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{409}{1376285} = \frac{546}{1837290} = \frac{576}{1938240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{418}{6370529} = \frac{532}{8107946} = \frac{628}{9571034}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{1578096} = \frac{436}{1592708} = \frac{713}{2604589}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{2583697} = \frac{780}{4915326} = \frac{820}{5167394}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{1958376} = \frac{840}{3916752} = \frac{895}{4173206}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{1607985} = \frac{576}{2143980} = \frac{864}{3215970}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{2639785} = \frac{610}{3927485} = \frac{682}{4391057}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{3157896} = \frac{495}{3721806} = \frac{840}{6315792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{1759860} = \frac{460}{1873925} = \frac{864}{3519720}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{2956387} = \frac{610}{4398527} = \frac{890}{6417523}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{3897516} = \frac{510}{4732698} = \frac{920}{8537416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{432}{1798605} = \frac{576}{2398140} = \frac{864}{3597210}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{3258967} = \frac{820}{6517934} = \frac{830}{6597421}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{3957618} = \frac{810}{7632549} = \frac{840}{7915236}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{1067982} = \frac{580}{1423976} = \frac{870}{2135964}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{3827965} = \frac{418}{3902657} = \frac{532}{4967018}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{420}{5197836} = \frac{610}{7549238} = \frac{780}{9653124}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{1607982} = \frac{580}{2143976} = \frac{870}{3215964}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{410}{3926857} = \frac{610}{5842397} = \frac{620}{5938174}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{421}{5307968} = \frac{619}{7804352} = \frac{726}{9153408}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{1798062} = \frac{580}{2397416} = \frac{870}{3596124}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{3796580} = \frac{648}{5971320} = \frac{824}{7593160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{426}{1735098} = \frac{852}{3470196} = \frac{864}{3519072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{1962807} = \frac{465}{2098173} = \frac{870}{3925614}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{3970856} = \frac{516}{4973208} = \frac{601}{5792438}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{426}{1739805} = \frac{568}{2319740} = \frac{852}{3479610}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{1978206} = \frac{815}{3706294} = \frac{870}{3956412}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{5073986} = \frac{482}{5936071} = \frac{726}{8941053}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{426}{1890375} = \frac{918}{4073625} = \frac{930}{4126875}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{2796180} = \frac{582}{3741096} = \frac{618}{3972504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{412}{7539806} = \frac{430}{7869215} = \frac{432}{7905816}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{426}{3510879} = \frac{612}{5043798} = \frac{618}{5093247}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{2871609} = \frac{485}{3201679} = \frac{830}{5479162}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{2961708} = \frac{725}{4936180} = \frac{870}{5923416}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{435}{6891270} = \frac{501}{7936842} = \frac{615}{9742830}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{437}{1509628} = \frac{589}{2034716} = \frac{874}{3019256}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{438}{1096752} = \frac{756}{1893024} = \frac{876}{2193504}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{438}{1697250} = \frac{618}{2394750} = \frac{879}{3406125}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{438}{2509617} = \frac{730}{4182695} = \frac{876}{5019234}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{438}{2970516} = \frac{798}{5412036} = \frac{876}{5941032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{438}{6195072} = \frac{516}{7298304} = \frac{543}{7680192}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{439}{2781065} = \frac{678}{4295130} = \frac{761}{4820935}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{451}{7829360} = \frac{491}{8523760} = \frac{567}{9843120}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{452}{1067398} = \frac{608}{1435792} = \frac{874}{2063951}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{452}{1693870} = \frac{490}{1836275} = \frac{926}{3470185}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{453}{2718906} = \frac{645}{3871290} = \frac{906}{5437812}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{456}{3018792} = \frac{627}{4150839} = \frac{912}{6037584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{456}{3189720} = \frac{546}{3819270} = \frac{603}{4217985}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{456}{3912708} = \frac{618}{5302749} = \frac{846}{7259103}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{458}{1376290} = \frac{769}{2310845} = \frac{781}{2346905}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{458}{1739026} = \frac{847}{3216059} = \frac{916}{3478052}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{459}{1827630} = \frac{476}{1895320} = \frac{867}{3452190}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{459}{1876230} = \frac{782}{3196540} = \frac{918}{3752460}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{459}{3071628} = \frac{735}{4918620} = \frac{798}{5340216}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{460}{1928573} = \frac{580}{2431679} = \frac{920}{3857146}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{460}{3815792} = \frac{910}{7548632} = \frac{920}{7631584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{461}{5023978} = \frac{753}{8206194} = \frac{794}{8653012}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{462}{1578390} = \frac{854}{2917630} = \frac{924}{3156780}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{462}{1583790} = \frac{847}{2903615} = \frac{924}{3167580}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{462}{1785903} = \frac{792}{3061548} = \frac{924}{3571806}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{462}{3791580} = \frac{847}{6951230} = \frac{924}{7583160}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{462}{3918075} = \frac{814}{6903275} = \frac{924}{7836150}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{462}{5307918} = \frac{804}{9237156} = \frac{816}{9375024}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{463}{2758091} = \frac{831}{4950267} = \frac{976}{5814032}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{463}{5108279} = \frac{473}{5218609} = \frac{482}{5317906}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{2718390} = \frac{693}{4051278} = \frac{735}{4296810}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{2719380} = \frac{527}{3081964} = \frac{806}{4713592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{2891370} = \frac{934}{5807612} = \frac{985}{6124730}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{3081927} = \frac{495}{3280761} = \frac{690}{4573182}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{465}{3812907} = \frac{920}{7543816} = \frac{930}{7625814}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{468}{3205917} = \frac{628}{4301957} = \frac{980}{6713245}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{3527081} = \frac{749}{5632801} = \frac{938}{7054162}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{469}{3712805} = \frac{672}{5319840} = \frac{938}{7425610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{470}{1329865} = \frac{594}{1680723} = \frac{938}{2654071}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{470}{2631859} = \frac{530}{2967841} = \frac{940}{5263718}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{2598036} = \frac{491}{2708356} = \frac{581}{3204796}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{2693805} = \frac{628}{3591740} = \frac{942}{5387610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{2936805} = \frac{628}{3915740} = \frac{942}{5873610}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{471}{5026983} = \frac{571}{6094283} = \frac{792}{8453016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{472}{3890165} = \frac{824}{6791305} = \frac{840}{6923175}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{473}{1892605} = \frac{817}{3269045} = \frac{946}{3785210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{473}{5980612} = \frac{561}{7093284} = \frac{673}{8509412}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{475}{3129680} = \frac{780}{5139264} = \frac{930}{6127584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{476}{1823590} = \frac{910}{3486275} = \frac{952}{3647180}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{476}{1930852} = \frac{901}{3654827} = \frac{952}{3861704}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{476}{2018359} = \frac{704}{2985136} = \frac{952}{4036718}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{476}{2195380} = \frac{784}{3615920} = \frac{791}{3648205}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{476}{2391508} = \frac{901}{4526783} = \frac{952}{4783016}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{476}{3981502} = \frac{758}{6340291} = \frac{782}{6541039}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{1237596} = \frac{720}{1856394} = \frac{840}{2165793}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{1239756} = \frac{720}{1859634} = \frac{840}{2169573}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{1357692} = \frac{840}{2375961} = \frac{960}{2715384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{1673952} = \frac{940}{3278156} = \frac{980}{3417652}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{1729356} = \frac{520}{1873469} = \frac{960}{3458712}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{3561792} = \frac{730}{5416892} = \frac{960}{7123584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{3657912} = \frac{740}{5639281} = \frac{960}{7315824}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{3759612} = \frac{720}{5639418} = \frac{840}{6579321}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{1357680} = \frac{861}{2375940} = \frac{984}{2715360}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{503}{1298746} = \frac{609}{1572438} = \frac{897}{2316054}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{3769152} = \frac{830}{6517492} = \frac{940}{7381256}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{1750836} = \frac{697}{2480351} = \frac{984}{3501672}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{1376928} = \frac{672}{1835904} = \frac{708}{1934256}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{3975612} = \frac{720}{5963418} = \frac{840}{6957321}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{3075186} = \frac{902}{5637841} = \frac{984}{6150372}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{1389276} = \frac{756}{2083914} = \frac{918}{2530467}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{6175392} = \frac{580}{7461932} = \frac{765}{9842031}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{3187506} = \frac{902}{5843761} = \frac{984}{6375012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{504}{2916837} = \frac{648}{3750219} = \frac{792}{4583601}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{480}{7521936} = \frac{620}{9715834} = \frac{630}{9872541}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{3615708} = \frac{516}{3792084} = \frac{843}{6195207}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{506}{1297384} = \frac{794}{2035816} = \frac{904}{2317856}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{481}{5976203} = \frac{741}{9206583} = \frac{754}{9368102}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{3617508} = \frac{697}{5124803} = \frac{984}{7235016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{506}{8137492} = \frac{574}{9231068} = \frac{604}{9713528}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{482}{1693507} = \frac{534}{1876209} = \frac{714}{2508639}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{5871036} = \frac{691}{8245703} = \frac{756}{9021348}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{507}{1328496} = \frac{702}{1839456} = \frac{897}{2350416}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{483}{1507926} = \frac{635}{1982470} = \frac{907}{2831654}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{493}{1086572} = \frac{592}{1304768} = \frac{937}{2065148}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{507}{1392846} = \frac{741}{2035698} = \frac{936}{2571408}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{483}{2710596} = \frac{765}{4293180} = \frac{948}{5320176}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{493}{1860752} = \frac{957}{3612048} = \frac{986}{3721504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{507}{2149368} = \frac{819}{3472056} = \frac{871}{3692504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{1509273} = \frac{528}{1639704} = \frac{972}{3018546}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{1280763} = \frac{680}{1759432} = \frac{835}{2160479}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{507}{2498613} = \frac{702}{3459618} = \frac{806}{3972154}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{486}{3750219} = \frac{702}{5416983} = \frac{952}{7346108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{1678230} = \frac{539}{1827406} = \frac{594}{2013876}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{507}{2849613} = \frac{702}{3945618} = \frac{897}{5041623}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{1256730} = \frac{762}{1958340} = \frac{978}{2513460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{1836720} = \frac{693}{2571408} = \frac{759}{2816304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{508}{2317496} = \frac{685}{3124970} = \frac{791}{3608542}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{489}{2075316} = \frac{504}{2138976} = \frac{978}{4150632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{3172680} = \frac{594}{3807216} = \frac{803}{5146792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{508}{3471926} = \frac{716}{4893502} = \frac{924}{6315078}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{490}{1573628} = \frac{560}{1798432} = \frac{980}{3147256}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{495}{8031276} = \frac{540}{8761392} = \frac{570}{9248136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{510}{3247986} = \frac{735}{4680921} = \frac{945}{6018327}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{490}{1725836} = \frac{560}{1972384} = \frac{980}{3451672}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{1085372} = \frac{728}{1593046} = \frac{820}{1794365}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{512}{6937408} = \frac{672}{9105348} = \frac{680}{9213745}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{490}{1873256} = \frac{945}{3612708} = \frac{980}{3746512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{496}{5173280} = \frac{589}{6143270} = \frac{598}{6237140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{514}{6283907} = \frac{730}{8924615} = \frac{782}{9560341}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{490}{3716258} = \frac{510}{3867942} = \frac{980}{7432516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{497}{2081365} = \frac{826}{3459170} = \frac{917}{3840265}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{516}{4387290} = \frac{894}{7601235} = \frac{924}{7856310}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{490}{3728165} = \frac{502}{3819467} = \frac{718}{5462903}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{498}{3570162} = \frac{687}{4925103} = \frac{801}{5742369}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{517}{2938064} = \frac{836}{4750912} = \frac{891}{5063472}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{491}{5306728} = \frac{742}{8019536} = \frac{845}{9132760}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{501}{2674839} = \frac{801}{4276539} = \frac{948}{5061372}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{518}{4906237} = \frac{734}{6952081} = \frac{802}{7596143}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{1035768} = \frac{574}{1208396} = \frac{984}{2071536}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{501}{2937864} = \frac{561}{3289704} = \frac{906}{5312784}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{2068734} = \frac{941}{3750826} = \frac{957}{3814602}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{492}{1305768} = \frac{759}{2014386} = \frac{981}{2603574}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{502}{3674891} = \frac{512}{3748096} = \frac{834}{6105297}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{519}{4376208} = \frac{704}{5936128} = \frac{836}{7049152}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{1893476} = \frac{590}{2148367} = \frac{730}{2658149}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{1937468} = \frac{710}{2645389} = \frac{840}{3129756}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{520}{4369781} = \frac{640}{5378192} = \frac{680}{5714329}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{523}{1086794} = \frac{736}{1529408} = \frac{902}{1874356}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{523}{1698704} = \frac{536}{1740928} = \frac{673}{2185904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{524}{3169807} = \frac{796}{4815203} = \frac{928}{5613704}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{527}{1469803} = \frac{642}{1790538} = \frac{903}{2518467}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{527}{4083196} = \frac{609}{4718532} = \frac{945}{7321860}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{528}{3916704} = \frac{684}{5073912} = \frac{819}{6075342}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{528}{4190736} = \frac{683}{5420971} = \frac{759}{6024183}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{528}{7390416} = \frac{579}{8104263} = \frac{609}{8524173}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{531}{4028697} = \frac{567}{4301829} = \frac{783}{5940621}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{531}{4869270} = \frac{637}{5841290} = \frac{823}{7546910}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{532}{4986170} = \frac{730}{6841925} = \frac{930}{8716425}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5324}{817960} = \frac{5379}{826410} = \frac{6413}{985270}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{1270984} = \frac{603}{1429857} = \frac{871}{2065349}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{4091728} = \frac{804}{6137592} = \frac{938}{7160524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{536}{4281970} = \frac{924}{7381605} = \frac{928}{7413560}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{538}{2490671} = \frac{704}{3259168} = \frac{710}{3286945}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{1208746} = \frac{735}{1648290} = \frac{917}{2056438}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{539}{2701468} = \frac{876}{4390512} = \frac{938}{4701256}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{2730968} = \frac{754}{3806192} = \frac{965}{4871320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{541}{6372980} = \frac{694}{8175320} = \frac{723}{8516940}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{542}{3609178} = \frac{586}{3902174} = \frac{821}{5467039}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{543}{1072968} = \frac{807}{1594632} = \frac{945}{1867320}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{543}{1867920} = \frac{924}{3178560} = \frac{954}{3281760}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{543}{1890726} = \frac{715}{2489630} = \frac{853}{2970146}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{543}{2198607} = \frac{758}{3069142} = \frac{809}{3275641}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{546}{1937208} = \frac{651}{2309748} = \frac{918}{3257064}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{546}{1938027} = \frac{872}{3095164} = \frac{906}{3215847}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{546}{3291078} = \frac{689}{4153027} = \frac{832}{5014976}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{549}{3782610} = \frac{789}{5436210} = \frac{948}{6531720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{549}{6381027} = \frac{684}{7950132} = \frac{702}{8159346}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{560}{1893472} = \frac{615}{2079438} = \frac{895}{3026174}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{560}{1943872} = \frac{805}{2794316} = \frac{895}{3106724}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{560}{3197824} = \frac{715}{4082936} = \frac{730}{4168592}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{561}{4270893} = \frac{713}{5428069} = \frac{819}{6235047}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{564}{1087392} = \frac{783}{1509624} = \frac{834}{1607952}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{564}{3102987} = \frac{780}{4291365} = \frac{924}{5083617}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{568}{1047392} = \frac{908}{1674352} = \frac{924}{1703856}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{568}{1079342} = \frac{572}{1086943} = \frac{940}{1786235}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{568}{4370192} = \frac{698}{5370412} = \frac{936}{7201584}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{570}{1694382} = \frac{605}{1798423} = \frac{930}{2764518}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{570}{1893426} = \frac{705}{2341869} = \frac{795}{2640831}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{570}{4832916} = \frac{730}{6189524} = \frac{890}{7546132}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{572}{1084369} = \frac{872}{1653094} = \frac{964}{1827503}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{572}{1609348} = \frac{583}{1640297} = \frac{638}{1795042}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{572}{3814096} = \frac{798}{5321064} = \frac{978}{6521304}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{572}{6301984} = \frac{649}{7150328} = \frac{682}{7513904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{574}{3290168} = \frac{612}{3507984} = \frac{672}{3851904}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{2038194} = \frac{864}{3057291} = \frac{896}{3170524}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{3291840} = \frac{612}{3497580} = \frac{918}{5246370}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{3491280} = \frac{612}{3709485} = \frac{708}{4291365}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{4893120} = \frac{731}{6209845} = \frac{758}{6439210}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{4913280} = \frac{738}{6295140} = \frac{954}{8137620}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{576}{8413920} = \frac{618}{9027435} = \frac{642}{9378015}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{579}{1260483} = \frac{657}{1430289} = \frac{953}{2074681}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{579}{4013628} = \frac{831}{5760492} = \frac{915}{6342780}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{580}{1469372} = \frac{735}{1862049} = \frac{760}{1925384}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{580}{3967142} = \frac{710}{4856329} = \frac{760}{5198324}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{581}{3607429} = \frac{836}{5190724} = \frac{972}{6035148}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{582}{4367910} = \frac{834}{6259170} = \frac{981}{7362405}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{583}{1470962} = \frac{693}{1748502} = \frac{814}{2053796}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{583}{4296710} = \frac{587}{4326190} = \frac{849}{6257130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{609}{3821475} = \frac{687}{4310925} = \frac{786}{4932150}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{642}{5973810} = \frac{821}{7639405} = \frac{942}{8765310}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{586}{1497230} = \frac{726}{1854930} = \frac{973}{2486015}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{609}{3841572} = \frac{615}{3879420} = \frac{954}{6017832}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{642}{7091853} = \frac{742}{8196503} = \frac{754}{8329061}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{586}{4730192} = \frac{681}{5497032} = \frac{832}{6715904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{610}{2873954} = \frac{895}{4216703} = \frac{905}{4263817}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{645}{1037289} = \frac{780}{1254396} = \frac{960}{1543872}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{590}{1784632} = \frac{635}{1920748} = \frac{640}{1935872}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{613}{2095847} = \frac{749}{2560831} = \frac{853}{2916407}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{645}{7129830} = \frac{735}{8124690} = \frac{873}{9650142}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{1368704} = \frac{597}{1380264} = \frac{796}{1840352}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{614}{2839750} = \frac{809}{3741625} = \frac{846}{3912750}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{648}{1937520} = \frac{861}{2574390} = \frac{957}{2861430}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{592}{4301768} = \frac{874}{6350921} = \frac{984}{7150236}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{615}{2038479} = \frac{730}{2419658} = \frac{790}{2618534}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{649}{2573108} = \frac{781}{3096452} = \frac{902}{3576184}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{1078326} = \frac{693}{1258047} = \frac{902}{1637458}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{615}{3708942} = \frac{640}{3859712} = \frac{890}{5367412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{653}{1409827} = \frac{697}{1504823} = \frac{736}{1589024}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{1803276} = \frac{627}{1903458} = \frac{759}{2304186}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{615}{7390824} = \frac{710}{8532496} = \frac{810}{9734256}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{653}{2408917} = \frac{679}{2504831} = \frac{869}{3205741}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{1832760} = \frac{627}{1934580} = \frac{759}{2341860}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{617}{2359408} = \frac{824}{3150976} = \frac{916}{3502784}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{654}{3879201} = \frac{762}{4519803} = \frac{894}{5302761}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{3276018} = \frac{627}{3458019} = \frac{759}{4186023}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{621}{5038794} = \frac{753}{6109842} = \frac{906}{7351284}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{670}{2584391} = \frac{760}{2931548} = \frac{920}{3548716}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{3276180} = \frac{627}{3458190} = \frac{759}{4186230}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{623}{4871059} = \frac{637}{4980521} = \frac{819}{6403527}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{672}{1039584} = \frac{798}{1234506} = \frac{972}{1503684}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{594}{3760218} = \frac{891}{5640327} = \frac{972}{6153084}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{630}{1795248} = \frac{675}{1923480} = \frac{915}{2607384}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{674}{5382901} = \frac{734}{5862091} = \frac{952}{7603148}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{596}{3142708} = \frac{892}{4703516} = \frac{964}{5083172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{630}{2795814} = \frac{695}{3084271} = \frac{705}{3128649}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{675}{1328940} = \frac{690}{1358472} = \frac{840}{1653792}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{597}{1426830} = \frac{627}{1498530} = \frac{984}{2351760}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{630}{4198572} = \frac{680}{4531792} = \frac{725}{4831690}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{679}{1325408} = \frac{692}{1350784} = \frac{765}{1493280}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{597}{1862043} = \frac{657}{2049183} = \frac{903}{2816457}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{631}{5729480} = \frac{819}{7436520} = \frac{964}{8753120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{679}{5402318} = \frac{903}{7184526} = \frac{924}{7351608}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{598}{2130674} = \frac{657}{2340891} = \frac{659}{2348017}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{634}{2875190} = \frac{671}{3042985} = \frac{826}{3745910}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{680}{7913245} = \frac{704}{8192536} = \frac{784}{9123506}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{603}{5241879} = \frac{842}{7319506} = \frac{951}{8267043}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{634}{2980751} = \frac{672}{3159408} = \frac{910}{4278365}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{684}{1239750} = \frac{894}{1620375} = \frac{902}{1634875}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{605}{1748329} = \frac{930}{2687514} = \frac{945}{2730861}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{637}{5824091} = \frac{914}{8356702} = \frac{952}{8704136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{684}{1593720} = \frac{723}{1684590} = \frac{792}{1845360}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{609}{2835417} = \frac{784}{3650192} = \frac{854}{3976102}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{638}{1297054} = \frac{684}{1390572} = \frac{706}{1435298}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{684}{5271930} = \frac{732}{5641890} = \frac{814}{6273905}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{609}{3271548} = \frac{741}{3980652} = \frac{987}{5302164}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{641}{5802973} = \frac{643}{5821079} = \frac{823}{7450619}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{684}{5732091} = \frac{752}{6301948} = \frac{972}{8145603}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{609}{3521847} = \frac{792}{4580136} = \frac{927}{5360841}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{642}{3758910} = \frac{654}{3829170} = \frac{984}{5761320}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{685}{1324790} = \frac{853}{1649702} = \frac{945}{1827630}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{685}{7921340} = \frac{729}{8430156} = \frac{783}{9054612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{708}{4123569} = \frac{924}{5381607} = \frac{984}{5731062}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{753}{4618902} = \frac{819}{5023746} = \frac{843}{5170962}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{690}{3817425} = \frac{852}{4713690} = \frac{936}{5178420}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{709}{1862543} = \frac{783}{2056941} = \frac{891}{2340657}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{753}{8192640} = \frac{847}{9215360} = \frac{857}{9324160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{690}{4173258} = \frac{705}{4263981} = \frac{870}{5261934}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{712}{3089546} = \frac{852}{3697041} = \frac{976}{4235108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{769}{3452810} = \frac{786}{3529140} = \frac{789}{3542610}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{690}{7824531} = \frac{740}{8391526} = \frac{860}{9752314}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{716}{8394205} = \frac{820}{9613475} = \frac{832}{9754160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{780}{6349512} = \frac{785}{6390214} = \frac{810}{6593724}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{693}{1427580} = \frac{697}{1435820} = \frac{789}{1625340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{718}{3269054} = \frac{794}{3615082} = \frac{891}{4056723}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{781}{5063294} = \frac{792}{5134608} = \frac{957}{6204318}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{694}{5823701} = \frac{836}{7015294} = \frac{912}{7653048}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{720}{1953648} = \frac{790}{2143586} = \frac{865}{2347091}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{786}{5210394} = \frac{804}{5329716} = \frac{927}{6145083}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{694}{7813052} = \frac{695}{7824310} = \frac{713}{8026954}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{723}{1085946} = \frac{728}{1093456} = \frac{936}{1405872}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{794}{2135860} = \frac{879}{2364510} = \frac{936}{2517840}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{695}{2784031} = \frac{790}{3164582} = \frac{910}{3645278}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{724}{8013956} = \frac{761}{8423509} = \frac{827}{9154063}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{795}{1302846} = \frac{840}{1376592} = \frac{960}{1573248}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{695}{3104287} = \frac{790}{3528614} = \frac{815}{3640279}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{734}{1089256} = \frac{839}{1245076} = \frac{967}{1435028}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{802}{4961573} = \frac{908}{5617342} = \frac{982}{6075143}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{695}{4031278} = \frac{790}{4582316} = \frac{910}{5278364}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{734}{8065192} = \frac{742}{8153096} = \frac{874}{9603512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{810}{3547962} = \frac{820}{3591764} = \frac{845}{3701269}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{697}{1235084} = \frac{709}{1256348} = \frac{835}{1479620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{1268904} = \frac{780}{1346592} = \frac{975}{1683240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{814}{2603579} = \frac{846}{2705931} = \frac{946}{3025781}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{698}{1073524} = \frac{849}{1305762} = \frac{956}{1470328}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{735}{4296180} = \frac{791}{4623508} = \frac{903}{5278164}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{839}{5247106} = \frac{912}{5703648} = \frac{973}{6085142}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{698}{5103427} = \frac{726}{5308149} = \frac{874}{6390251}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{1549280} = \frac{852}{1793460} = \frac{973}{2048165}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{853}{1427069} = \frac{873}{1460529} = \frac{958}{1602734}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{702}{8146359} = \frac{736}{8540912} = \frac{742}{8610539}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{736}{5901248} = \frac{785}{6294130} = \frac{918}{7360524}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{908}{7435612} = \frac{926}{7583014} = \frac{954}{7812306}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{704}{1329856} = \frac{836}{1579204} = \frac{932}{1760548}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{742}{3159860} = \frac{756}{3219480} = \frac{812}{3457960}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{705}{4839261} = \frac{915}{6280743} = \frac{935}{6418027}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{746}{3819520} = \frac{893}{4572160} = \frac{928}{4751360}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{706}{3951482} = \frac{712}{3985064} = \frac{856}{4791032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{746}{8519320} = \frac{836}{9547120} = \frac{853}{9741260}$	

• **2-Digits Numerator**

$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23456789} = \frac{20}{46913578} = \frac{40}{93827156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23489765} = \frac{34}{79865201} = \frac{42}{98657013}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23784569} = \frac{20}{47569138} = \frac{40}{95138276}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23456879} = \frac{20}{46913758} = \frac{40}{93827516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23498765} = \frac{16}{37598024} = \frac{32}{75196048}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23794658} = \frac{20}{47589316} = \frac{40}{95178632}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23795684} = \frac{20}{47591368} = \frac{40}{95182736}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{34765892} = \frac{20}{69531784} = \frac{25}{86914730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{36750984} = \frac{17}{52063894} = \frac{24}{73501968}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23845679} = \frac{20}{47691358} = \frac{40}{95382716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{35726984} = \frac{20}{71453968} = \frac{25}{89317460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{36975840} = \frac{24}{73951680} = \frac{27}{83195640}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23946578} = \frac{20}{47893156} = \frac{40}{95786312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{35784692} = \frac{20}{71569384} = \frac{25}{89461730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{37596048} = \frac{18}{56394072} = \frac{21}{65793084}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{23956784} = \frac{20}{47913568} = \frac{40}{95827136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{37259468} = \frac{20}{74518936} = \frac{25}{93148670}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{37596480} = \frac{18}{56394720} = \frac{21}{65793840}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24379658} = \frac{20}{48759316} = \frac{40}{97518632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{37265948} = \frac{20}{74531896} = \frac{25}{93164870}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{39756048} = \frac{18}{59634072} = \frac{21}{69573084}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24396578} = \frac{20}{48793156} = \frac{40}{97586312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{37459268} = \frac{20}{74918536} = \frac{25}{93648170}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{39756480} = \frac{18}{59634720} = \frac{21}{69573840}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24567839} = \frac{20}{49135678} = \frac{40}{98271356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{39257468} = \frac{20}{78514936} = \frac{25}{98143670}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{40679835} = \frac{16}{54239780} = \frac{24}{81359670}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24568379} = \frac{20}{49136758} = \frac{40}{98273516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{39265748} = \frac{20}{78531496} = \frac{25}{98164370}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{40798365} = \frac{16}{54397820} = \frac{24}{81596730}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24657893} = \frac{20}{49315786} = \frac{40}{98631572}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{39457268} = \frac{20}{78914536} = \frac{25}{98643170}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{43067985} = \frac{16}{57423980} = \frac{24}{86135970}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24657938} = \frac{20}{49315876} = \frac{40}{98631752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{30568794} = \frac{16}{40758392} = \frac{30}{76421985}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{43079865} = \frac{16}{57439820} = \frac{24}{86159730}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24658793} = \frac{20}{49317586} = \frac{40}{98635172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{30587964} = \frac{16}{40783952} = \frac{32}{81567904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{43679805} = \frac{16}{58239740} = \frac{24}{87359610}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24659378} = \frac{20}{49318756} = \frac{40}{98637512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{30596874} = \frac{16}{40795832} = \frac{30}{76492185}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{43798065} = \frac{16}{58397420} = \frac{24}{87596130}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24853976} = \frac{15}{37280964} = \frac{30}{74561928}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{30598764} = \frac{16}{40798352} = \frac{32}{81596704}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{45937680} = \frac{13}{49765820} = \frac{24}{91875360}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{24873965} = \frac{30}{74621895} = \frac{38}{94521067}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{34567890} = \frac{24}{69135780} = \frac{30}{86419725}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{48037596} = \frac{18}{72056394} = \frac{21}{84065793}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{25374986} = \frac{15}{38062479} = \frac{30}{76124958}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{34568790} = \frac{24}{69137580} = \frac{30}{86421975}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{48039756} = \frac{18}{72059634} = \frac{21}{84069573}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{25497386} = \frac{15}{38246079} = \frac{30}{76492158}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{34765890} = \frac{24}{69531780} = \frac{30}{86914725}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{48375960} = \frac{18}{72563940} = \frac{21}{84657930}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{26574938} = \frac{15}{39862407} = \frac{20}{53149876}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{34768590} = \frac{24}{69537180} = \frac{30}{86921475}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{48397560} = \frac{18}{72596340} = \frac{21}{84695730}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{28674395} = \frac{16}{45879032} = \frac{32}{91758064}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{35687940} = \frac{16}{47583920} = \frac{32}{95167840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{49035768} = \frac{14}{57208396} = \frac{24}{98071536}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{29567384} = \frac{20}{59134768} = \frac{25}{73918460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{35690478} = \frac{24}{71380956} = \frac{32}{95174608}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{49357680} = \frac{21}{86375940} = \frac{24}{98715360}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{29673584} = \frac{20}{59347168} = \frac{25}{74183960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{35784690} = \frac{24}{71569380} = \frac{30}{89461725}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{53470896} = \frac{13}{57926804} = \frac{21}{93574068}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10}{34567892} = \frac{20}{69135784} = \frac{25}{86419730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{35876940} = \frac{16}{47835920} = \frac{32}{95671840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12}{65987340} = \frac{14}{76985230} = \frac{17}{93482065}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20475869} = \frac{26}{40951738} = \frac{52}{81903476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24586790} = \frac{26}{49173580} = \frac{52}{98347160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{27068549} = \frac{26}{54137098} = \frac{39}{81205647}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20476859} = \frac{26}{40953718} = \frac{52}{81907436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24678509} = \frac{26}{49357018} = \frac{52}{98714036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{27069458} = \frac{29}{60385714} = \frac{41}{85372906}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20485769} = \frac{26}{40971538} = \frac{52}{81943076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24678590} = \frac{26}{49357180} = \frac{52}{98714360}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{27085469} = \frac{26}{54170938} = \frac{39}{81256407}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20486759} = \frac{26}{40973518} = \frac{52}{81947036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24679085} = \frac{26}{49358170} = \frac{52}{98716340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{27468905} = \frac{26}{54937810} = \frac{39}{82406715}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20754869} = \frac{26}{41509738} = \frac{52}{83019476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24685079} = \frac{26}{49370158} = \frac{52}{98740316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{27486905} = \frac{26}{54973810} = \frac{39}{82460715}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20768549} = \frac{26}{41537098} = \frac{52}{83074196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24685790} = \frac{26}{49371580} = \frac{52}{98743160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28496507} = \frac{18}{39456702} = \frac{23}{50416897}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20769854} = \frac{26}{41539708} = \frac{52}{83079416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24690785} = \frac{26}{49381570} = \frac{52}{98763140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28546709} = \frac{26}{57093418} = \frac{39}{85640127}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20794865} = \frac{26}{41589730} = \frac{52}{83179460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{25068947} = \frac{26}{50137894} = \frac{39}{75206841}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28546907} = \frac{26}{57093814} = \frac{39}{85640721}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20854769} = \frac{26}{41709538} = \frac{52}{83419076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{25069487} = \frac{26}{50138974} = \frac{39}{75208461}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28547069} = \frac{26}{57094138} = \frac{39}{85641207}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20867549} = \frac{26}{41735098} = \frac{52}{83470196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{25086947} = \frac{26}{50173894} = \frac{39}{75260841}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28549067} = \frac{26}{57098134} = \frac{39}{85647201}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20869754} = \frac{26}{41739508} = \frac{52}{83479016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{25089467} = \frac{26}{50178934} = \frac{39}{75268401}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28594670} = \frac{26}{57189340} = \frac{36}{79185240}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20947865} = \frac{26}{41895730} = \frac{52}{83791460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{25094687} = \frac{26}{50189374} = \frac{39}{75284061}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28650947} = \frac{18}{39670542} = \frac{26}{57301894}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20976854} = \frac{26}{41953708} = \frac{52}{83907416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{25094867} = \frac{26}{50189734} = \frac{39}{75284601}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28674905} = \frac{26}{57349810} = \frac{39}{86024715}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{20986754} = \frac{26}{41973508} = \frac{52}{83947016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{25746890} = \frac{26}{51493780} = \frac{43}{85162790}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28695407} = \frac{26}{57390814} = \frac{31}{68427509}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24078695} = \frac{26}{48157390} = \frac{52}{96314780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{26708549} = \frac{26}{53417098} = \frac{39}{80125647}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{28746905} = \frac{26}{57493810} = \frac{39}{86240715}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24079685} = \frac{26}{48159370} = \frac{52}{96318740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{26748905} = \frac{26}{53497810} = \frac{39}{80246715}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{29046875} = \frac{39}{87140625} = \frac{43}{96078125}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24086795} = \frac{26}{48173590} = \frac{52}{96347180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{26854709} = \frac{26}{53709418} = \frac{39}{80564127}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{29068547} = \frac{26}{58137094} = \frac{39}{87205641}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24096785} = \frac{26}{48193570} = \frac{52}{96387140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{26854907} = \frac{26}{53709814} = \frac{39}{80564721}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{29085467} = \frac{26}{58170934} = \frac{39}{87256401}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24507869} = \frac{26}{49015738} = \frac{52}{98031476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{26874905} = \frac{26}{53749810} = \frac{39}{80624715}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{29865407} = \frac{26}{59730814} = \frac{34}{78109526}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24508679} = \frac{26}{49017358} = \frac{52}{98034716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{26908547} = \frac{26}{53817094} = \frac{39}{80725641}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{40259687} = \frac{21}{65034879} = \frac{26}{80519374}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{24578690} = \frac{26}{49157380} = \frac{52}{98314760}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{26945087} = \frac{26}{53890174} = \frac{43}{89126057}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{40286597} = \frac{21}{65078349} = \frac{26}{80573194}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{42985670} = \frac{24}{79358160} = \frac{26}{85971340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20857396} = \frac{39}{58102746} = \frac{53}{78960142}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23695780} = \frac{28}{47391560} = \frac{56}{94783120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13}{50728496} = \frac{18}{70239456} = \frac{23}{89750416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20869753} = \frac{28}{41739506} = \frac{56}{83479012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23765980} = \frac{21}{35648970} = \frac{28}{47531960}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20357698} = \frac{28}{40715396} = \frac{56}{81430792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20975368} = \frac{28}{41950736} = \frac{56}{83901472}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23796580} = \frac{21}{35694870} = \frac{28}{47593160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20359768} = \frac{28}{40719536} = \frac{56}{81439072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20976853} = \frac{28}{41953706} = \frac{56}{83907412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23798560} = \frac{21}{35697840} = \frac{42}{71395680}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20365798} = \frac{21}{30548697} = \frac{28}{40731596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20986753} = \frac{28}{41973506} = \frac{56}{83947012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23965780} = \frac{21}{35948670} = \frac{28}{47931560}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20365978} = \frac{21}{30548967} = \frac{28}{40731956}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23078695} = \frac{28}{46157390} = \frac{56}{92314780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23976580} = \frac{21}{35964870} = \frac{28}{47953160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20367598} = \frac{28}{40735196} = \frac{56}{81470392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23079685} = \frac{28}{46159370} = \frac{56}{92318740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23978560} = \frac{21}{35967840} = \frac{42}{71935680}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20369758} = \frac{28}{40739516} = \frac{56}{81479032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23086795} = \frac{28}{46173590} = \frac{56}{92347180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{26537098} = \frac{21}{39805647} = \frac{28}{53074196}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20376598} = \frac{21}{30564897} = \frac{28}{40753196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23096785} = \frac{28}{46193570} = \frac{56}{92387140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{27096853} = \frac{28}{54193706} = \frac{46}{89032517}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20378596} = \frac{21}{30567894} = \frac{49}{71325086}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23506798} = \frac{28}{47013596} = \frac{52}{87310964}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{27396508} = \frac{28}{54793016} = \frac{35}{68491270}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20379658} = \frac{21}{30569487} = \frac{28}{40759316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23507968} = \frac{28}{47015936} = \frac{56}{94031872}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{27536908} = \frac{27}{53106894} = \frac{31}{60974582}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20385796} = \frac{21}{30578694} = \frac{49}{71350286}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23509678} = \frac{28}{47019356} = \frac{56}{94038712}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{29863750} = \frac{23}{49061875} = \frac{46}{98123750}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20396578} = \frac{21}{30594867} = \frac{28}{40793156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23579680} = \frac{28}{47159360} = \frac{56}{94318720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{30785692} = \frac{15}{32984670} = \frac{39}{85760142}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20397658} = \frac{21}{30596487} = \frac{28}{40795316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23596780} = \frac{28}{47193560} = \frac{56}{94387120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{35089726} = \frac{17}{42608953} = \frac{34}{85217906}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20579836} = \frac{21}{30869754} = \frac{42}{61739508}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23657980} = \frac{21}{35486970} = \frac{28}{47315960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{35902678} = \frac{19}{48725063} = \frac{38}{97450126}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20597836} = \frac{21}{30896754} = \frac{42}{61793508}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23659780} = \frac{21}{35489670} = \frac{28}{47319560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{36579802} = \frac{21}{54869703} = \frac{28}{73159604}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20657938} = \frac{17}{25084639} = \frac{34}{50169278}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23678095} = \frac{28}{47356190} = \frac{56}{94712380}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{36579820} = \frac{21}{54869730} = \frac{28}{73159640}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20679835} = \frac{28}{41359670} = \frac{56}{82719340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23679508} = \frac{28}{47359016} = \frac{56}{94718032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{36597802} = \frac{21}{54896703} = \frac{28}{73195604}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20697835} = \frac{28}{41395670} = \frac{56}{82791340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23679580} = \frac{28}{47359160} = \frac{56}{94718320}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{36597820} = \frac{21}{54896730} = \frac{28}{73195640}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20769853} = \frac{28}{41539706} = \frac{56}{83079412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23680795} = \frac{28}{47361590} = \frac{56}{94723180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{37096528} = \frac{15}{39746280} = \frac{28}{74193056}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{20796853} = \frac{28}{41593706} = \frac{64}{95071328}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{23695078} = \frac{28}{47390156} = \frac{56}{94780312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14}{37659802} = \frac{21}{56489703} = \frac{28}{75319604}$

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|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{14}{37659820} = \frac{21}{56489730} = \frac{28}{75319640}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{23794608} = \frac{30}{47589216} = \frac{60}{95178432}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{27894630} = \frac{31}{57648902} = \frac{52}{96701384}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14}{37965802} = \frac{21}{56948703} = \frac{28}{75931604}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{23794680} = \frac{32}{50761984} = \frac{41}{65038792}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28063947} = \frac{20}{37418596} = \frac{30}{56127894}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14}{37965820} = \frac{21}{56948730} = \frac{28}{75931640}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{23807946} = \frac{30}{47615892} = \frac{60}{95231784}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28093647} = \frac{20}{37458196} = \frac{30}{56187294}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14}{39628057} = \frac{30}{84917265} = \frac{32}{90578416}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{23809476} = \frac{20}{31745968} = \frac{30}{47618952}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28360947} = \frac{20}{37814596} = \frac{30}{56721894}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14}{39657802} = \frac{21}{59486703} = \frac{28}{79315604}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{23894607} = \frac{20}{31859476} = \frac{40}{63718952}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28390647} = \frac{20}{37854196} = \frac{30}{56781294}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14}{39657820} = \frac{21}{59486730} = \frac{28}{79315640}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{23946078} = \frac{30}{47892156} = \frac{60}{95784312}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28439706} = \frac{30}{56879412} = \frac{40}{75839216}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14}{39765802} = \frac{21}{59648703} = \frac{28}{79531604}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24307896} = \frac{30}{48615792} = \frac{60}{97231584}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28493706} = \frac{30}{56987412} = \frac{40}{75983216}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{14}{39765820} = \frac{21}{59648730} = \frac{28}{79531640}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24308796} = \frac{30}{48617592} = \frac{60}{97235184}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28609347} = \frac{20}{38145796} = \frac{30}{57218694}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{20687439} = \frac{35}{48270691} = \frac{70}{96541382}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24378096} = \frac{30}{48756192} = \frac{60}{97512384}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28630947} = \frac{20}{38174596} = \frac{30}{57261894}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{20786493} = \frac{30}{41572986} = \frac{60}{83145972}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24379608} = \frac{30}{48759216} = \frac{60}{97518432}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28643097} = \frac{30}{57286194} = \frac{40}{76381592}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{20793648} = \frac{30}{41587296} = \frac{60}{83174592}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24380796} = \frac{30}{48761592} = \frac{60}{97523184}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28649307} = \frac{30}{57298614} = \frac{40}{76398152}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{20794863} = \frac{30}{41589726} = \frac{60}{83179452}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24389760} = \frac{27}{43901568} = \frac{45}{73169280}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28906347} = \frac{20}{38541796} = \frac{30}{57812694}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{20798643} = \frac{30}{41597286} = \frac{60}{83194572}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24396078} = \frac{30}{48792156} = \frac{60}{97584312}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{28930647} = \frac{20}{38574196} = \frac{30}{57861294}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{20864793} = \frac{30}{41729586} = \frac{60}{83459172}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24607893} = \frac{30}{49215786} = \frac{60}{98431572}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{29307486} = \frac{30}{58614972} = \frac{40}{78153296}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{20936478} = \frac{30}{41872956} = \frac{60}{83745912}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24607938} = \frac{30}{49215876} = \frac{60}{98431752}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{29308647} = \frac{30}{58617294} = \frac{40}{78156392}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{20947863} = \frac{30}{41895726} = \frac{60}{83791452}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24608793} = \frac{30}{49217586} = \frac{60}{98435172}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{29367480} = \frac{18}{35240976} = \frac{36}{70481952}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{20978643} = \frac{30}{41957286} = \frac{60}{83914572}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24609378} = \frac{30}{49218756} = \frac{60}{98437512}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{29384706} = \frac{30}{58769412} = \frac{40}{78359216}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{23078946} = \frac{30}{46157892} = \frac{60}{92315784}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{24796380} = \frac{43}{71082956} = \frac{51}{84307692}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{29843706} = \frac{30}{59687412} = \frac{40}{79583216}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{23087946} = \frac{30}{46175892} = \frac{60}{92351784}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{26074398} = \frac{30}{52148796} = \frac{40}{69531728}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{29864307} = \frac{30}{59728614} = \frac{40}{79638152}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{23498760} = \frac{24}{37598016} = \frac{48}{75196032}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{26089437} = \frac{20}{34785916} = \frac{40}{69571832}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{36072984} = \frac{30}{72145968} = \frac{35}{84170296}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{15}{23780946} = \frac{30}{47561892} = \frac{60}{95123784}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{26984730} = \frac{17}{30582694} = \frac{28}{50371496}$ | ▶ $\frac{15}{37296084} = \frac{30}{74592168} = \frac{35}{87024196}$ |

$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{37298406} = \frac{30}{74596812} = \frac{35}{87029614}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20487593} = \frac{32}{40975186} = \frac{64}{81950372}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23579480} = \frac{32}{47158960} = \frac{62}{91370485}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{38092746} = \frac{25}{63487910} = \frac{30}{76185492}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20493758} = \frac{32}{40987516} = \frac{64}{81975032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23780945} = \frac{32}{47561890} = \frac{64}{95123780}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{38270946} = \frac{25}{63784910} = \frac{30}{76541892}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20543798} = \frac{24}{30815697} = \frac{32}{41087596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23794508} = \frac{32}{47589016} = \frac{64}{95178032}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{38407296} = \frac{30}{76814592} = \frac{35}{89617024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20543978} = \frac{24}{30815967} = \frac{32}{41087956}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23798054} = \frac{24}{35697081} = \frac{32}{47596108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{40637982} = \frac{20}{54183976} = \frac{30}{81275964}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20579834} = \frac{24}{30869751} = \frac{48}{61739502}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23798540} = \frac{24}{35697810} = \frac{48}{71395620}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{40739826} = \frac{20}{54319768} = \frac{30}{81479652}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20597834} = \frac{24}{30896751} = \frac{48}{61793502}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23807945} = \frac{32}{47615890} = \frac{64}{95231780}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{40798362} = \frac{20}{54397816} = \frac{30}{81596724}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20753948} = \frac{32}{41507896} = \frac{64}{83015792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23897504} = \frac{34}{50782196} = \frac{53}{79160482}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{40798632} = \frac{20}{54398176} = \frac{30}{81597264}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20754398} = \frac{32}{41508796} = \frac{64}{83017592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23945078} = \frac{32}{47890156} = \frac{64}{95780312}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{43079862} = \frac{20}{57439816} = \frac{30}{86159724}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20754893} = \frac{32}{41509786} = \frac{64}{83019572}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23978054} = \frac{24}{35967081} = \frac{32}{47956108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{43607982} = \frac{20}{58143976} = \frac{30}{87215964}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20754938} = \frac{32}{41509876} = \frac{64}{83019752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23978540} = \frac{24}{35967810} = \frac{48}{71935620}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15}{43798062} = \frac{20}{58397416} = \frac{30}{87596124}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20875493} = \frac{32}{41750986} = \frac{64}{83501972}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24307895} = \frac{32}{48615790} = \frac{64}{97231580}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20357984} = \frac{32}{40715968} = \frac{48}{61073952}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20894753} = \frac{32}{41789506} = \frac{64}{83579012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24308795} = \frac{32}{48617590} = \frac{64}{97235180}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20359784} = \frac{32}{40719568} = \frac{48}{61079352}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20897543} = \frac{32}{41795086} = \frac{64}{83590172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24378095} = \frac{32}{48756190} = \frac{64}{97512380}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20375948} = \frac{32}{40751896} = \frac{64}{81503792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20937548} = \frac{32}{41875096} = \frac{64}{83750192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24379508} = \frac{32}{48759016} = \frac{64}{97518032}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20379458} = \frac{24}{30569187} = \frac{32}{40758916}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20947538} = \frac{32}{41895076} = \frac{64}{83790152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24379580} = \frac{32}{48759160} = \frac{64}{97518320}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20394578} = \frac{24}{30591867} = \frac{32}{40789156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20948753} = \frac{32}{41897506} = \frac{64}{83795012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24380795} = \frac{32}{48761590} = \frac{64}{97523180}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20394758} = \frac{32}{40789516} = \frac{64}{81579032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20975438} = \frac{32}{41950876} = \frac{64}{83901752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24395078} = \frac{32}{48790156} = \frac{64}{97580312}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20437598} = \frac{32}{40875196} = \frac{64}{81750392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20987543} = \frac{32}{41975086} = \frac{64}{83950172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24395780} = \frac{32}{48791560} = \frac{64}{97583120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20439758} = \frac{32}{40879516} = \frac{64}{81759032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23078945} = \frac{32}{46157890} = \frac{64}{92315780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24507893} = \frac{32}{49015786} = \frac{64}{98031572}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20475893} = \frac{32}{40951786} = \frac{64}{81903572}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23087945} = \frac{32}{46175890} = \frac{64}{92351780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24507938} = \frac{32}{49015876} = \frac{64}{98031752}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{20475938} = \frac{32}{40951876} = \frac{64}{81903752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{23509784} = \frac{32}{47019568} = \frac{36}{52897014}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16}{24508793} = \frac{32}{49017586} = \frac{64}{98035172}$

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{16}{24509378} = \frac{32}{49018756} = \frac{64}{98037512}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{29735408} = \frac{32}{59470816} = \frac{38}{70621594}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39457802} = \frac{24}{59186703} = \frac{32}{78915604}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{24578930} = \frac{32}{49157860} = \frac{64}{98315720}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{30879524} = \frac{28}{54039167} = \frac{32}{61759048}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39457820} = \frac{24}{59186730} = \frac{32}{78915640}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{24579380} = \frac{32}{49158760} = \frac{64}{98317520}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{34890752} = \frac{32}{69781504} = \frac{36}{78504192}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39578240} = \frac{32}{79156480} = \frac{37}{91524680}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{24587930} = \frac{32}{49175860} = \frac{64}{98351720}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{35097824} = \frac{32}{70195648} = \frac{45}{98712630}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39705428} = \frac{20}{49631785} = \frac{32}{79410856}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{24593780} = \frac{32}{49187560} = \frac{64}{98375120}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{35702984} = \frac{26}{58017349} = \frac{32}{71405968}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39740258} = \frac{24}{59610387} = \frac{32}{79480516}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{24758930} = \frac{32}{49517860} = \frac{40}{61897325}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{35849270} = \frac{32}{71698540} = \frac{40}{89623175}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39742508} = \frac{20}{49678135} = \frac{32}{79485016}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25739840} = \frac{32}{51479680} = \frac{43}{69175820}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37259480} = \frac{32}{74518960} = \frac{42}{97806135}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39742580} = \frac{24}{59613870} = \frac{32}{79485160}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25740398} = \frac{24}{38610597} = \frac{32}{51480796}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37402598} = \frac{24}{56103897} = \frac{32}{74805196}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39780542} = \frac{24}{59670813} = \frac{32}{79561084}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25743980} = \frac{24}{38615970} = \frac{32}{51487960}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37425980} = \frac{24}{56138970} = \frac{32}{74851960}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39782054} = \frac{24}{59673081} = \frac{32}{79564108}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25803974} = \frac{24}{38705961} = \frac{32}{51607948}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37598240} = \frac{31}{72846590} = \frac{32}{75196480}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39802574} = \frac{24}{59703861} = \frac{32}{79605148}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25839740} = \frac{24}{38759610} = \frac{32}{51679480}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37809524} = \frac{32}{75619048} = \frac{36}{85071429}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39825740} = \frac{24}{59738610} = \frac{32}{79651480}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25974038} = \frac{24}{38961057} = \frac{32}{51948076}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37905248} = \frac{21}{49750638} = \frac{32}{75810496}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39852704} = \frac{19}{47325086} = \frac{38}{94650172}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25974380} = \frac{24}{38961570} = \frac{32}{51948760}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37908452} = \frac{32}{75816904} = \frac{36}{85294017}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{40953728} = \frac{32}{81907456} = \frac{38}{97265104}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25980374} = \frac{24}{38970561} = \frac{32}{51960748}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37945802} = \frac{24}{56918703} = \frac{32}{75891604}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{43087952} = \frac{28}{75403916} = \frac{32}{86175904}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25983740} = \frac{24}{38975610} = \frac{32}{51967480}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37945820} = \frac{24}{56918730} = \frac{32}{75891640}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{43780952} = \frac{32}{87561904} = \frac{36}{98507142}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{25987304} = \frac{30}{48726195} = \frac{32}{51974608}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37980542} = \frac{24}{56970813} = \frac{32}{75961084}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{45083792} = \frac{23}{64807951} = \frac{32}{90167584}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{29047358} = \frac{32}{58094716} = \frac{40}{72618395}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{37982054} = \frac{24}{56973081} = \frac{32}{75964108}$ | ▶ $\frac{17}{20539468} = \frac{59}{71284036} = \frac{76}{91823504}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{29357480} = \frac{32}{58714960} = \frac{38}{69724015}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{38025974} = \frac{24}{57038961} = \frac{32}{76051948}$ | ▶ $\frac{17}{20945683} = \frac{49}{60372851} = \frac{51}{62837049}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{29473580} = \frac{20}{36841975} = \frac{32}{58947160}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{38259740} = \frac{24}{57389610} = \frac{32}{76519480}$ | ▶ $\frac{17}{24563980} = \frac{19}{27453860} = \frac{48}{69357120}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{29570384} = \frac{32}{59140768} = \frac{52}{96103748}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{38954720} = \frac{19}{46258730} = \frac{38}{92517460}$ | ▶ $\frac{17}{24860953} = \frac{24}{35097816} = \frac{48}{70195632}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{16}{29587340} = \frac{20}{36984175} = \frac{32}{59174680}$ | ▶ $\frac{16}{39457280} = \frac{23}{56719840} = \frac{32}{78914560}$ | ▶ $\frac{17}{25436098} = \frac{34}{50872196} = \frac{51}{76308294}$ |

$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{26403958} = \frac{32}{49701568} = \frac{34}{52807916}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20597436} = \frac{27}{30896154} = \frac{54}{61792308}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23904576} = \frac{36}{47809152} = \frac{72}{95618304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{28354096} = \frac{34}{56708192} = \frac{56}{93401728}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20753649} = \frac{36}{41507298} = \frac{72}{83014596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23907546} = \frac{36}{47815092} = \frac{72}{95630184}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{30926485} = \frac{18}{32745690} = \frac{34}{61852970}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20763549} = \frac{36}{41527098} = \frac{72}{83054196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23945760} = \frac{27}{35918640} = \frac{36}{47891520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{32609485} = \frac{18}{34527690} = \frac{34}{65218970}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20975364} = \frac{36}{41950728} = \frac{72}{83901456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23954076} = \frac{36}{47908152} = \frac{72}{95816304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{32946085} = \frac{34}{65892170} = \frac{47}{91086235}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20976354} = \frac{36}{41952708} = \frac{72}{83905416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23957604} = \frac{36}{47915208} = \frac{72}{95830416}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{36095284} = \frac{29}{61574308} = \frac{34}{72190568}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23507964} = \frac{36}{47015928} = \frac{72}{94031856}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23960754} = \frac{36}{47921508} = \frac{72}{95843016}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17}{42869053} = \frac{18}{45390762} = \frac{36}{90781524}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23579640} = \frac{36}{47159280} = \frac{72}{94318560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23974560} = \frac{27}{35961840} = \frac{54}{71923680}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20345976} = \frac{27}{30518964} = \frac{54}{61037928}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23597640} = \frac{36}{47195280} = \frac{63}{82591740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23976054} = \frac{27}{35964081} = \frac{36}{47952108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20357649} = \frac{36}{40715298} = \frac{72}{81430596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23605974} = \frac{26}{34097518} = \frac{27}{35408961}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24037596} = \frac{36}{48075192} = \frac{72}{96150384}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20357964} = \frac{36}{40715928} = \frac{54}{61073892}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23640795} = \frac{36}{47281590} = \frac{72}{94563180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24039576} = \frac{36}{48079152} = \frac{72}{96158304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20359764} = \frac{36}{40719528} = \frac{72}{81439056}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23645079} = \frac{36}{47290158} = \frac{72}{94580316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24075396} = \frac{36}{48150792} = \frac{72}{96301584}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20364759} = \frac{36}{40729518} = \frac{72}{81459036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23645790} = \frac{36}{47291580} = \frac{72}{94583160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24079635} = \frac{36}{48159270} = \frac{72}{96318540}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20365794} = \frac{27}{30548691} = \frac{54}{61097382}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23674905} = \frac{26}{34197085} = \frac{52}{68394170}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24095376} = \frac{36}{48190752} = \frac{72}{96381504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20379456} = \frac{27}{30569184} = \frac{36}{40758912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23754609} = \frac{36}{47509218} = \frac{72}{95018436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24359760} = \frac{36}{48719520} = \frac{43}{58192760}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20394576} = \frac{27}{30591864} = \frac{36}{40789152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23759046} = \frac{36}{47518092} = \frac{72}{95036184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24397560} = \frac{36}{48795120} = \frac{54}{73192680}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20435976} = \frac{36}{40871952} = \frac{54}{61307928}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23759604} = \frac{36}{47519208} = \frac{72}{95038416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24537609} = \frac{36}{49075218} = \frac{72}{98150436}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20476359} = \frac{36}{40952718} = \frac{72}{81905436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23760459} = \frac{36}{47520918} = \frac{72}{95041836}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24539076} = \frac{36}{49078152} = \frac{72}{98156304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20536479} = \frac{36}{41072958} = \frac{64}{73018592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23794560} = \frac{27}{35691840} = \frac{36}{47589120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24576039} = \frac{36}{49152078} = \frac{72}{98304156}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20543796} = \frac{27}{30815694} = \frac{36}{41087592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23795640} = \frac{36}{47591280} = \frac{54}{71386920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24590376} = \frac{36}{49180752} = \frac{72}{98361504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20543976} = \frac{27}{30815964} = \frac{36}{41087952}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23796054} = \frac{27}{35694081} = \frac{36}{47592108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24603759} = \frac{36}{49207518} = \frac{72}{98415036}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{20579634} = \frac{27}{30869451} = \frac{54}{61738902}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{23796540} = \frac{27}{35694810} = \frac{54}{71389620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24635079} = \frac{36}{49270158} = \frac{72}{98540316}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24635790} = \frac{36}{49271580} = \frac{72}{98543160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{29047356} = \frac{36}{58094712} = \frac{45}{72618390}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37960542} = \frac{27}{56940813} = \frac{36}{75921084}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{24935076} = \frac{36}{49870152} = \frac{51}{70649382}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{29053746} = \frac{27}{43580619} = \frac{36}{58107492}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37962054} = \frac{27}{56943081} = \frac{36}{75924108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25370946} = \frac{27}{38056419} = \frac{36}{50741892}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{29457036} = \frac{36}{58914072} = \frac{57}{93280614}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39457602} = \frac{27}{59186403} = \frac{36}{78915204}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25436097} = \frac{36}{50872194} = \frac{54}{76308291}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{29457360} = \frac{36}{58914720} = \frac{57}{93281640}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39457620} = \frac{27}{59186430} = \frac{36}{78915240}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25439760} = \frac{27}{38159640} = \frac{54}{76319280}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{32760594} = \frac{19}{34580627} = \frac{23}{41860759}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39564027} = \frac{26}{57148039} = \frac{36}{79128054}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25603974} = \frac{27}{38405961} = \frac{36}{51207948}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{35029674} = \frac{21}{40867953} = \frac{42}{81735906}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39564270} = \frac{26}{57148390} = \frac{36}{79128540}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25637940} = \frac{27}{38456910} = \frac{54}{76913820}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{35076492} = \frac{36}{70152984} = \frac{45}{87691230}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39570264} = \frac{35}{76942180} = \frac{36}{79140528}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25639740} = \frac{27}{38459610} = \frac{36}{51279480}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{35927046} = \frac{23}{45906781} = \frac{36}{71854092}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39602574} = \frac{27}{59403861} = \frac{36}{79205148}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25740396} = \frac{27}{38610594} = \frac{36}{51480792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{36025974} = \frac{27}{54038961} = \frac{36}{72051948}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39625740} = \frac{27}{59438610} = \frac{36}{79251480}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25743960} = \frac{27}{38615940} = \frac{36}{51487920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{36259740} = \frac{27}{54389610} = \frac{36}{72519480}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39740256} = \frac{27}{59610384} = \frac{36}{79480512}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25960374} = \frac{27}{38940561} = \frac{36}{51920748}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{36429570} = \frac{36}{72859140} = \frac{43}{87026195}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39742560} = \frac{27}{59613840} = \frac{36}{79485120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25963740} = \frac{27}{38945610} = \frac{36}{51927480}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{36457029} = \frac{28}{56710934} = \frac{36}{72914058}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39760542} = \frac{27}{59640813} = \frac{36}{79521084}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25964370} = \frac{19}{27406835} = \frac{36}{51928740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37026459} = \frac{36}{74052918} = \frac{42}{86395071}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{39762054} = \frac{27}{59643081} = \frac{36}{79524108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25974036} = \frac{27}{38961054} = \frac{36}{51948072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37052946} = \frac{32}{65871904} = \frac{36}{74105892}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{40953726} = \frac{27}{61430589} = \frac{36}{81907452}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25974360} = \frac{27}{38961540} = \frac{36}{51948720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37095264} = \frac{36}{74190528} = \frac{45}{92738160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{45702936} = \frac{28}{71093456} = \frac{36}{91405872}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{25976034} = \frac{27}{38964051} = \frac{39}{56281407}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37402596} = \frac{27}{56103894} = \frac{36}{74805192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{46273590} = \frac{27}{69410385} = \frac{36}{92547180}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{26074395} = \frac{36}{52148790} = \frac{48}{69531720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37425960} = \frac{27}{56138940} = \frac{36}{74851920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{59403276} = \frac{19}{62703458} = \frac{23}{75904186}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{27039564} = \frac{26}{39057148} = \frac{36}{54079128}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37640952} = \frac{24}{50187936} = \frac{36}{75281904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{59432760} = \frac{19}{62734580} = \frac{23}{75941860}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{27359046} = \frac{27}{41038569} = \frac{36}{54718092}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37649052} = \frac{24}{50198736} = \frac{36}{75298104}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20348756} = \frac{38}{40697512} = \frac{76}{81395024}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{27395640} = \frac{26}{39571480} = \frac{36}{54791280}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37945602} = \frac{27}{56918403} = \frac{36}{75891204}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20357648} = \frac{38}{40715296} = \frac{76}{81430592}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{27450639} = \frac{36}{54901278} = \frac{52}{79301846}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18}{37945620} = \frac{27}{56918430} = \frac{36}{75891240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20364758} = \frac{38}{40729516} = \frac{76}{81459032}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20384756} = \frac{38}{40769512} = \frac{76}{81539024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23645780} = \frac{38}{47291560} = \frac{76}{94583120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24630785} = \frac{38}{49261570} = \frac{76}{98523140}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20458763} = \frac{28}{30149756} = \frac{38}{40917526}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23754608} = \frac{38}{47509216} = \frac{76}{95018432}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24635078} = \frac{38}{49270156} = \frac{76}{98540312}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20476358} = \frac{38}{40952716} = \frac{76}{81905432}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23758046} = \frac{38}{47516092} = \frac{76}{95032184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24635780} = \frac{38}{49271560} = \frac{76}{98543120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20483756} = \frac{38}{40967512} = \frac{76}{81935024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23760458} = \frac{38}{47520916} = \frac{76}{95041832}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{25604837} = \frac{37}{49862051} = \frac{38}{51209674}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20485763} = \frac{38}{40971526} = \frac{76}{81943052}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23784506} = \frac{38}{47569012} = \frac{76}{95138024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{25703846} = \frac{38}{51407692} = \frac{65}{87934210}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20534876} = \frac{38}{41069752} = \frac{76}{82139504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23784560} = \frac{38}{47569120} = \frac{76}{95138240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{26784053} = \frac{27}{38061549} = \frac{54}{76123098}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20538476} = \frac{38}{41076952} = \frac{76}{82153904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23784605} = \frac{38}{47569210} = \frac{76}{95138420}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{27456380} = \frac{38}{54912760} = \frac{57}{82369140}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20548376} = \frac{38}{41096752} = \frac{76}{82193504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23804576} = \frac{38}{47609152} = \frac{76}{95218304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{28547063} = \frac{36}{54089172} = \frac{38}{57094126}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20634785} = \frac{38}{41269570} = \frac{76}{82539140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23807546} = \frac{38}{47615092} = \frac{76}{95230184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{28560743} = \frac{27}{40586319} = \frac{56}{84179032}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20647835} = \frac{38}{41295670} = \frac{76}{82591340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24358760} = \frac{48}{61537920} = \frac{53}{67948120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{34705286} = \frac{38}{69410572} = \frac{45}{82196730}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20753648} = \frac{38}{41507296} = \frac{76}{83014592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24507863} = \frac{38}{49015726} = \frac{76}{98031452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{35478206} = \frac{27}{50416398} = \frac{38}{70956412}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20754863} = \frac{38}{41509726} = \frac{76}{83019452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24530876} = \frac{38}{49061752} = \frac{76}{98123504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{35846027} = \frac{37}{69805421} = \frac{38}{71692054}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20763548} = \frac{38}{41527096} = \frac{76}{83054192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24537608} = \frac{38}{49075216} = \frac{76}{98150432}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{47063285} = \frac{36}{89172540} = \frac{38}{94126570}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20764853} = \frac{38}{41529706} = \frac{76}{83059412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24538076} = \frac{38}{49076152} = \frac{76}{98152304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{13478569} = \frac{40}{26957138} = \frac{80}{53914276}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20854763} = \frac{38}{41709526} = \frac{76}{83419052}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24576038} = \frac{38}{49152076} = \frac{76}{98304152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{13485679} = \frac{40}{26971358} = \frac{80}{53942716}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{20864753} = \frac{38}{41729506} = \frac{76}{83459012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24578630} = \frac{38}{49157260} = \frac{76}{98314520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{13567849} = \frac{40}{27135698} = \frac{80}{54271396}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23045876} = \frac{38}{46091752} = \frac{76}{92183504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24580376} = \frac{38}{49160752} = \frac{76}{98321504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{13567984} = \frac{40}{27135968} = \frac{80}{54271936}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23078645} = \frac{38}{46157290} = \frac{76}{92314580}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24587603} = \frac{38}{49175206} = \frac{76}{98350412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{13568479} = \frac{40}{27136958} = \frac{80}{54273916}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23087546} = \frac{38}{46175092} = \frac{76}{92350184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24603758} = \frac{38}{49207516} = \frac{76}{98415032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{13569784} = \frac{40}{27139568} = \frac{80}{54279136}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23468705} = \frac{39}{48172605} = \frac{78}{96345210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24607538} = \frac{38}{49215076} = \frac{76}{98430152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{13657948} = \frac{40}{27315896} = \frac{80}{54631792}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{23645078} = \frac{38}{47290156} = \frac{76}{94580312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19}{24608753} = \frac{38}{49217506} = \frac{76}{98435012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20}{13659478} = \frac{40}{27318956} = \frac{80}{54637912}$

- ▶ $\frac{20}{13796584} = \frac{40}{27593168} = \frac{60}{41389752}$
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- ▶ $\frac{20}{14583976} = \frac{30}{21875964} = \frac{60}{43751928}$
- ▶ $\frac{20}{14598376} = \frac{30}{21897564} = \frac{60}{43795128}$
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- ▶ $\frac{20}{14835679} = \frac{40}{29671358} = \frac{80}{59342716}$
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- ▶ $\frac{20}{14936578} = \frac{40}{29873156} = \frac{80}{59746312}$
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- ▶ $\frac{20}{17835649} = \frac{40}{35671298} = \frac{80}{71342596}$
- ▶ $\frac{20}{17839456} = \frac{30}{26759184} = \frac{40}{35678912}$
- ▶ $\frac{20}{17856349} = \frac{40}{35712698} = \frac{80}{71425396}$
- ▶ $\frac{20}{17859634} = \frac{30}{26789451} = \frac{40}{35719268}$
- ▶ $\frac{20}{17945638} = \frac{30}{26918457} = \frac{40}{35891276}$
- ▶ $\frac{20}{17945836} = \frac{30}{26918754} = \frac{40}{35891672}$
- ▶ $\frac{20}{17983564} = \frac{40}{35967128} = \frac{80}{71934256}$
- ▶ $\frac{20}{18356479} = \frac{40}{36712958} = \frac{80}{73425916}$
- ▶ $\frac{20}{18394576} = \frac{30}{27591864} = \frac{40}{36789152}$

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|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{20}{18563479} = \frac{40}{37126958} = \frac{80}{74253916}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{36179458} = \frac{30}{54269187} = \frac{40}{72358916}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{34067985} = \frac{27}{43801695} = \frac{42}{68135970}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{18579634} = \frac{30}{27869451} = \frac{40}{37159268}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{36194578} = \frac{30}{54291867} = \frac{40}{72389156}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{35468097} = \frac{27}{45601839} = \frac{54}{91203678}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{18597634} = \frac{30}{27896451} = \frac{40}{37195268}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{36579814} = \frac{30}{54869721} = \frac{40}{73159628}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{35480697} = \frac{27}{45618039} = \frac{54}{91236078}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19376458} = \frac{40}{38752916} = \frac{60}{58129374}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{36597814} = \frac{30}{54896721} = \frac{40}{73195628}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{36457890} = \frac{38}{65971420} = \frac{47}{81596230}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19437658} = \frac{30}{29156487} = \frac{60}{58312974}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{37619458} = \frac{30}{56429187} = \frac{40}{75238916}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{37509864} = \frac{43}{76805912} = \frac{49}{87523016}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19456378} = \frac{30}{29184567} = \frac{40}{38912756}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{37659814} = \frac{30}{56489721} = \frac{40}{75319628}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{38047569} = \frac{42}{76095138} = \frac{53}{96024817}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19457836} = \frac{30}{29186754} = \frac{40}{38915672}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{37819456} = \frac{30}{56729184} = \frac{40}{75638912}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{38406795} = \frac{27}{49380165} = \frac{42}{76813590}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19458376} = \frac{30}{29187564} = \frac{40}{38916752}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{37945618} = \frac{30}{56918427} = \frac{40}{75891236}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{40968375} = \frac{39}{76084125} = \frac{42}{81936750}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19463758} = \frac{40}{38927516} = \frac{60}{58391274}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{37945816} = \frac{30}{56918724} = \frac{40}{75891632}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{43695078} = \frac{42}{87390156} = \frac{46}{95713028}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19576438} = \frac{40}{39152876} = \frac{60}{58729314}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{37965814} = \frac{30}{56948721} = \frac{40}{75931628}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{47693805} = \frac{28}{63591740} = \frac{42}{95387610}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19637458} = \frac{30}{29456187} = \frac{60}{58912374}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{38179456} = \frac{30}{57269184} = \frac{40}{76358912}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{47936805} = \frac{28}{63915740} = \frac{42}{95873610}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19643758} = \frac{40}{39287516} = \frac{60}{58931274}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{38194576} = \frac{30}{57291864} = \frac{40}{76389152}$ | ▶ $\frac{21}{47938065} = \frac{36}{82179540} = \frac{42}{95876130}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19657438} = \frac{30}{29486157} = \frac{60}{58972314}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{39456178} = \frac{30}{59184267} = \frac{40}{78912356}$ | ▶ $\frac{23}{10456789} = \frac{46}{20913578} = \frac{68}{30915724}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19783564} = \frac{40}{39567128} = \frac{80}{79134256}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{39457618} = \frac{30}{59186427} = \frac{40}{78915236}$ | ▶ $\frac{23}{10457689} = \frac{46}{20915378} = \frac{92}{41830756}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{19857634} = \frac{30}{29786451} = \frac{40}{39715268}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{39457816} = \frac{30}{59186724} = \frac{40}{78915632}$ | ▶ $\frac{23}{10458769} = \frac{46}{20917538} = \frac{92}{41835076}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{34178596} = \frac{30}{51267894} = \frac{40}{68357192}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{39458176} = \frac{30}{59187264} = \frac{40}{78916352}$ | ▶ $\frac{23}{10467589} = \frac{46}{20935178} = \frac{92}{41870356}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{34179856} = \frac{30}{51269784} = \frac{40}{68359712}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{39657814} = \frac{30}{59486721} = \frac{40}{79315628}$ | ▶ $\frac{23}{10468759} = \frac{46}{20937518} = \frac{92}{41875036}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{20}{34185796} = \frac{30}{51278694} = \frac{40}{68371592}$ | ▶ $\frac{20}{39765814} = \frac{30}{59648721} = \frac{40}{79531628}$ | ▶ $\frac{23}{10589476} = \frac{59}{27164308} = \frac{98}{45120376}$ |
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- ▶ $\frac{23}{10789465} = \frac{46}{21578930} = \frac{92}{43157860}$
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- ▶ $\frac{23}{18904576} = \frac{46}{37809152} = \frac{92}{75618304}$
- ▶ $\frac{23}{18907546} = \frac{46}{37815092} = \frac{92}{75630184}$
- ▶ $\frac{23}{18954076} = \frac{46}{37908152} = \frac{92}{75816304}$
- ▶ $\frac{23}{18957604} = \frac{46}{37915208} = \frac{92}{75830416}$
- ▶ $\frac{23}{18960754} = \frac{46}{37921508} = \frac{92}{75843016}$
- ▶ $\frac{23}{18964075} = \frac{46}{37928150} = \frac{78}{64312950}$
- ▶ $\frac{23}{19045876} = \frac{46}{38091752} = \frac{92}{76183504}$
- ▶ $\frac{23}{19078645} = \frac{46}{38157290} = \frac{92}{76314580}$
- ▶ $\frac{23}{19087546} = \frac{46}{38175092} = \frac{92}{76350184}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{19507864} = \frac{46}{39015728} = \frac{92}{78031456}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13079685} = \frac{48}{26159370} = \frac{96}{52318740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17390568} = \frac{37}{26810459} = \frac{74}{53620918}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{19540876} = \frac{46}{39081752} = \frac{92}{78163504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13086795} = \frac{48}{26173590} = \frac{96}{52347180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17530896} = \frac{48}{35061792} = \frac{96}{70123584}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{19578640} = \frac{46}{39157280} = \frac{92}{78314560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13089576} = \frac{53}{28906147} = \frac{79}{43086521}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17538096} = \frac{48}{35076192} = \frac{96}{70152384}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{19587604} = \frac{46}{39175208} = \frac{92}{78350416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13096785} = \frac{48}{26193570} = \frac{96}{52387140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17580396} = \frac{48}{35160792} = \frac{96}{70321584}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{19608754} = \frac{46}{39217508} = \frac{92}{78435016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13507968} = \frac{48}{27015936} = \frac{96}{54031872}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17589603} = \frac{48}{35179206} = \frac{96}{70358412}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23}{19640785} = \frac{46}{39281570} = \frac{92}{78563140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13509678} = \frac{48}{27019356} = \frac{96}{54038712}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17596038} = \frac{48}{35192076} = \frac{96}{70384152}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10376958} = \frac{48}{20753916} = \frac{96}{41507832}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13576980} = \frac{26}{14708395} = \frac{48}{27153960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17603958} = \frac{48}{35207916} = \frac{96}{70415832}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10395768} = \frac{48}{20791536} = \frac{96}{41583072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13579680} = \frac{48}{27159360} = \frac{96}{54318720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17608953} = \frac{48}{35217906} = \frac{96}{70435812}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10396758} = \frac{48}{20793516} = \frac{96}{41587032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13596780} = \frac{48}{27193560} = \frac{96}{54387120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17609538} = \frac{48}{35219076} = \frac{96}{70438152}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10678395} = \frac{48}{21356790} = \frac{96}{42713580}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13678095} = \frac{48}{27356190} = \frac{96}{54712380}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17635980} = \frac{48}{35271960} = \frac{84}{61725930}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10683795} = \frac{48}{21367590} = \frac{96}{42735180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13679508} = \frac{48}{27359016} = \frac{96}{54718032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17809635} = \frac{48}{35619270} = \frac{96}{71238540}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10753968} = \frac{48}{21507936} = \frac{96}{43015872}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13679580} = \frac{48}{27359160} = \frac{96}{54718320}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17839506} = \frac{48}{35679012} = \frac{96}{71358024}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10768953} = \frac{48}{21537906} = \frac{96}{43075812}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13680795} = \frac{48}{27361590} = \frac{96}{54723180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17839560} = \frac{48}{35679120} = \frac{96}{71358240}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10769538} = \frac{48}{21539076} = \frac{96}{43078152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13695078} = \frac{48}{27390156} = \frac{96}{54780312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17839605} = \frac{48}{35679210} = \frac{96}{71358420}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10876953} = \frac{48}{21753906} = \frac{96}{43507812}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13795680} = \frac{48}{27591360} = \frac{67}{38512940}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17850963} = \frac{48}{35701926} = \frac{96}{71403852}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10896753} = \frac{48}{21793506} = \frac{96}{43587012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13879650} = \frac{36}{20819475} = \frac{72}{41638950}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17859630} = \frac{48}{35719260} = \frac{96}{71438520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10953678} = \frac{48}{21907356} = \frac{60}{27384195}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{15378096} = \frac{48}{30756192} = \frac{67}{42930518}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17863095} = \frac{48}{35726190} = \frac{96}{71452380}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10953768} = \frac{48}{21907536} = \frac{96}{43815072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{15783096} = \frac{26}{17098354} = \frac{52}{34196708}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17950863} = \frac{48}{35901726} = \frac{96}{71803452}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10967538} = \frac{48}{21935076} = \frac{96}{43870152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{15793680} = \frac{78}{51329460} = \frac{82}{53961740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17953608} = \frac{48}{35907216} = \frac{81}{60593427}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{10968753} = \frac{48}{21937506} = \frac{96}{43875012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{15978036} = \frac{48}{31956072} = \frac{52}{34619078}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17956380} = \frac{48}{35912760} = \frac{72}{53869140}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{13078695} = \frac{48}{26157390} = \frac{96}{52314780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{15978360} = \frac{48}{31956720} = \frac{52}{34619780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24}{17958630} = \frac{48}{35917260} = \frac{96}{71834520}$

▶ $\frac{24}{17963085} = \frac{48}{35926170} = \frac{96}{71852340}$	▶ $\frac{24}{18953076} = \frac{48}{37906152} = \frac{96}{75812304}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19780356} = \frac{48}{39560712} = \frac{72}{59341068}$
▶ $\frac{24}{17963508} = \frac{48}{35927016} = \frac{96}{71854032}$	▶ $\frac{24}{18957603} = \frac{48}{37915206} = \frac{96}{75830412}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19780536} = \frac{48}{39561072} = \frac{72}{59341608}$
▶ $\frac{24}{17963580} = \frac{48}{35927160} = \frac{96}{71854320}$	▶ $\frac{24}{18960753} = \frac{48}{37921506} = \frac{96}{75843012}$	▶ $\frac{24}{30158976} = \frac{47}{59061328} = \frac{48}{60317952}$
▶ $\frac{24}{17980356} = \frac{48}{35960712} = \frac{72}{53941068}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19507863} = \frac{48}{39015726} = \frac{96}{78031452}$	▶ $\frac{24}{31589760} = \frac{48}{63179520} = \frac{58}{76341920}$
▶ $\frac{24}{17980536} = \frac{48}{35961072} = \frac{72}{53941608}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19508376} = \frac{48}{39016752} = \frac{63}{51209487}$	▶ $\frac{24}{31875096} = \frac{48}{63750192} = \frac{49}{65078321}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18037596} = \frac{48}{36075192} = \frac{96}{72150384}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19530876} = \frac{48}{39061752} = \frac{96}{78123504}$	▶ $\frac{24}{31976508} = \frac{38}{50629471} = \frac{70}{93264815}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18039576} = \frac{48}{36079152} = \frac{96}{72158304}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19537608} = \frac{48}{39075216} = \frac{96}{78150432}$	▶ $\frac{24}{35079816} = \frac{48}{70159632} = \frac{63}{92084517}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18075396} = \frac{48}{36150792} = \frac{96}{72301584}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19538076} = \frac{48}{39076152} = \frac{96}{78152304}$	▶ $\frac{24}{35198760} = \frac{36}{52798140} = \frac{42}{61597830}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18079635} = \frac{48}{36159270} = \frac{96}{72318540}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19563780} = \frac{48}{39127560} = \frac{72}{58691340}$	▶ $\frac{24}{36015978} = \frac{48}{72031956} = \frac{52}{78034619}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18095376} = \frac{48}{36190752} = \frac{96}{72381504}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19576038} = \frac{48}{39152076} = \frac{96}{78304152}$	▶ $\frac{24}{36159780} = \frac{48}{72319560} = \frac{52}{78346190}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18375096} = \frac{48}{36750192} = \frac{98}{75031642}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19578630} = \frac{48}{39157260} = \frac{96}{78314520}$	▶ $\frac{24}{37185096} = \frac{39}{60425781} = \frac{42}{65073918}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18375960} = \frac{48}{36751920} = \frac{93}{71206845}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19580376} = \frac{48}{39160752} = \frac{96}{78321504}$	▶ $\frac{24}{37809516} = \frac{30}{47261895} = \frac{48}{75619032}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18379506} = \frac{48}{36759012} = \frac{96}{73518024}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19587603} = \frac{48}{39175206} = \frac{96}{78350412}$	▶ $\frac{24}{38017596} = \frac{38}{60194527} = \frac{48}{76035192}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18379560} = \frac{48}{36759120} = \frac{96}{73518240}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19603758} = \frac{48}{39207516} = \frac{96}{78415032}$	▶ $\frac{24}{38097516} = \frac{30}{47621895} = \frac{48}{76195032}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18379605} = \frac{48}{36759210} = \frac{96}{73518420}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19607538} = \frac{48}{39215076} = \frac{96}{78430152}$	▶ $\frac{24}{38179560} = \frac{39}{62041785} = \frac{48}{76359120}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18507963} = \frac{48}{37015926} = \frac{96}{74031852}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19608753} = \frac{48}{39217506} = \frac{96}{78435012}$	▶ $\frac{24}{38751960} = \frac{36}{58127940} = \frac{42}{67815930}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18579630} = \frac{48}{37159260} = \frac{96}{74318520}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19630785} = \frac{48}{39261570} = \frac{96}{78523140}$	▶ $\frac{24}{38795160} = \frac{36}{58192740} = \frac{42}{67891530}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18630795} = \frac{48}{37261590} = \frac{96}{74523180}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19635078} = \frac{48}{39270156} = \frac{96}{78540312}$	▶ $\frac{24}{39518760} = \frac{36}{59278140} = \frac{42}{69157830}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18753096} = \frac{48}{37506192} = \frac{96}{75012384}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19635780} = \frac{48}{39271560} = \frac{96}{78543120}$	▶ $\frac{24}{39785016} = \frac{29}{48073561} = \frac{56}{92831704}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18759603} = \frac{48}{37519206} = \frac{96}{75038412}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19753086} = \frac{48}{39506172} = \frac{60}{49382715}$	▶ $\frac{24}{78501396} = \frac{26}{85043179} = \frac{30}{98126745}$
▶ $\frac{24}{18760953} = \frac{48}{37521906} = \frac{96}{75043812}$	▶ $\frac{24}{19763580} = \frac{48}{39527160} = \frac{84}{69172530}$	▶ $\frac{25}{10689473} = \frac{50}{21378946} = \frac{75}{32068419}$

- ▶ $\frac{25}{10694873} = \frac{50}{21389746} = \frac{75}{32084619}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{10869473} = \frac{50}{21738946} = \frac{75}{32608419}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{10894673} = \frac{50}{21789346} = \frac{75}{32684019}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{10946873} = \frac{50}{21893746} = \frac{75}{32840619}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{10948673} = \frac{50}{21897346} = \frac{75}{32846019}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{13068947} = \frac{50}{26137894} = \frac{75}{39206841}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{13069487} = \frac{50}{26138974} = \frac{75}{39208461}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{13086947} = \frac{50}{26173894} = \frac{75}{39260841}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{13089467} = \frac{50}{26178934} = \frac{75}{39268401}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{13094687} = \frac{50}{26189374} = \frac{75}{39284061}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{13094867} = \frac{50}{26189734} = \frac{75}{39284601}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{13764890} = \frac{35}{19270846} = \frac{70}{38541692}$
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- ▶ $\frac{25}{14973860} = \frac{40}{23958176} = \frac{80}{47916352}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{16378940} = \frac{30}{19654728} = \frac{75}{49136820}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{18647930} = \frac{90}{67132548} = \frac{95}{70862134}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{30689471} = \frac{50}{61378942} = \frac{75}{92068413}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{30694871} = \frac{50}{61389742} = \frac{75}{92084613}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{30869471} = \frac{50}{61738942} = \frac{75}{92608413}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{30894671} = \frac{50}{61789342} = \frac{75}{92684013}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{30946871} = \frac{50}{61893742} = \frac{75}{92840613}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{30948671} = \frac{50}{61897342} = \frac{75}{92846013}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{31068947} = \frac{50}{62137894} = \frac{75}{93206841}$
- ▶ $\frac{25}{31069487} = \frac{50}{62138974} = \frac{75}{93208461}$
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- ▶ $\frac{25}{31094867} = \frac{50}{62189734} = \frac{75}{93284601}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{10348975} = \frac{46}{18309725} = \frac{78}{31046925}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{13750984} = \frac{34}{17982056} = \frac{51}{26973084}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{13789450} = \frac{39}{20684175} = \frac{91}{48263075}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{13897450} = \frac{39}{20846175} = \frac{78}{41692350}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{14530789} = \frac{46}{25708319} = \frac{56}{31297084}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{15397084} = \frac{52}{30794168} = \frac{65}{38492710}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{15803749} = \frac{32}{19450768} = \frac{52}{31607498}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{15847039} = \frac{52}{31694078} = \frac{92}{56074138}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{17043598} = \frac{52}{34087196} = \frac{69}{45231087}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{17094538} = \frac{39}{25641807} = \frac{52}{34189076}$
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- ▶ $\frac{26}{17349085} = \frac{52}{34698170} = \frac{62}{41370895}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{17389450} = \frac{39}{26084175} = \frac{61}{40798325}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{17508439} = \frac{62}{41750893} = \frac{68}{45791302}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{18953740} = \frac{62}{45197380} = \frac{68}{49571320}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{19730854} = \frac{52}{39461708} = \frac{89}{67540231}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{31507489} = \frac{42}{50896713} = \frac{52}{63014978}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{37081954} = \frac{38}{54196702} = \frac{52}{74163908}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{38147590} = \frac{27}{39614805} = \frac{36}{52819740}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{38194507} = \frac{48}{70512936} = \frac{52}{76389014}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{39074815} = \frac{52}{78149630} = \frac{62}{93178405}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{39815074} = \frac{41}{62785309} = \frac{52}{79630148}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{43170985} = \frac{30}{49812675} = \frac{52}{86341970}$
- ▶ $\frac{26}{47091538} = \frac{28}{50713964} = \frac{52}{94183076}$
- ▶ $\frac{27}{10683954} = \frac{54}{21367908} = \frac{79}{31260458}$
- ▶ $\frac{27}{10685493} = \frac{54}{21370986} = \frac{81}{32056479}$
- ▶ $\frac{27}{10693485} = \frac{36}{14257980} = \frac{54}{21386970}$
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- ▶ $\frac{27}{10836549} = \frac{54}{21673098} = \frac{81}{32509647}$
- ▶ $\frac{27}{10854693} = \frac{54}{21709386} = \frac{81}{32564079}$
- ▶ $\frac{27}{10865349} = \frac{54}{21730698} = \frac{81}{32596047}$
- ▶ $\frac{27}{10934865} = \frac{36}{14579820} = \frac{54}{21869730}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13094865} = \frac{36}{17459820} = \frac{54}{26189730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14835069} = \frac{54}{29670138} = \frac{72}{39560184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{19064835} = \frac{36}{25419780} = \frac{54}{38129670}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13409685} = \frac{54}{26819370} = \frac{64}{31785920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14835690} = \frac{54}{29671380} = \frac{72}{39561840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{19348605} = \frac{36}{25798140} = \frac{54}{38697210}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13458690} = \frac{54}{26917380} = \frac{96}{47853120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14836905} = \frac{36}{19782540} = \frac{54}{29673810}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{19460385} = \frac{36}{25947180} = \frac{72}{51894360}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13458906} = \frac{36}{17945208} = \frac{72}{35890416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14839065} = \frac{36}{19785420} = \frac{54}{29678130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{19483605} = \frac{36}{25978140} = \frac{54}{38967210}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13465089} = \frac{54}{26930178} = \frac{81}{40395267}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14893065} = \frac{36}{19857420} = \frac{54}{29786130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{30598614} = \frac{36}{40798152} = \frac{72}{81596304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13485069} = \frac{54}{26970138} = \frac{72}{35960184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16093485} = \frac{36}{21457980} = \frac{54}{32186970}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{30685491} = \frac{54}{61370982} = \frac{81}{92056473}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13485690} = \frac{54}{26971380} = \frac{72}{35961840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16309485} = \frac{36}{21745980} = \frac{54}{32618970}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{30689145} = \frac{54}{61378290} = \frac{81}{92067435}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13486905} = \frac{36}{17982540} = \frac{54}{26973810}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16345089} = \frac{54}{32690178} = \frac{81}{49035267}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{30854691} = \frac{54}{61709382} = \frac{81}{92564073}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13805964} = \frac{36}{18407952} = \frac{72}{36815904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16394805} = \frac{36}{21859740} = \frac{54}{32789610}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{31068549} = \frac{54}{62137098} = \frac{81}{93205647}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13856940} = \frac{36}{18475920} = \frac{72}{36951840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16430985} = \frac{54}{32861970} = \frac{72}{43815960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{31085469} = \frac{54}{62170938} = \frac{81}{93256407}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{13948065} = \frac{36}{18597420} = \frac{54}{27896130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16480935} = \frac{36}{21974580} = \frac{54}{32961870}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{31450689} = \frac{54}{62901378} = \frac{81}{94352067}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14305896} = \frac{36}{19074528} = \frac{72}{38149056}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16483905} = \frac{36}{21978540} = \frac{54}{32967810}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{31450869} = \frac{54}{62901738} = \frac{81}{94352607}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14506893} = \frac{54}{29013786} = \frac{81}{43520679}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16489305} = \frac{36}{21985740} = \frac{54}{32978610}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{35064819} = \frac{54}{70129638} = \frac{72}{93506184}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14508693} = \frac{54}{29017386} = \frac{81}{43526079}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16493085} = \frac{54}{32986170} = \frac{72}{43981560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{35180649} = \frac{54}{70361298} = \frac{72}{93815064}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14530689} = \frac{54}{29061378} = \frac{81}{43592067}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{16954083} = \frac{49}{30768521} = \frac{98}{61537042}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{35198064} = \frac{54}{70396128} = \frac{72}{93861504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14530869} = \frac{54}{29061738} = \frac{81}{43592607}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{18039564} = \frac{39}{26057148} = \frac{54}{36079128}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{35648019} = \frac{54}{71296038} = \frac{72}{95061384}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14608539} = \frac{36}{19478052} = \frac{72}{38956104}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{18564930} = \frac{54}{37129860} = \frac{86}{59132740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{35861940} = \frac{36}{47815920} = \frac{72}{95631840}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14805396} = \frac{36}{19740528} = \frac{72}{39481056}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{18906345} = \frac{41}{28709635} = \frac{54}{37812690}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{35904681} = \frac{54}{71809362} = \frac{64}{85107392}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{14809365} = \frac{36}{19745820} = \frac{54}{29618730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{19063485} = \frac{36}{25417980} = \frac{54}{38126970}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{35918046} = \frac{54}{71836092} = \frac{64}{85139072}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{36594801} = \frac{28}{37950164} = \frac{54}{73189602}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{58619430} = \frac{36}{78159240} = \frac{39}{84672510}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{16943507} = \frac{36}{21784509} = \frac{72}{43569018}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{38194605} = \frac{54}{76389210} = \frac{63}{89120745}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{10435796} = \frac{52}{19380764} = \frac{82}{30561974}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{16943570} = \frac{36}{21784590} = \frac{72}{43569180}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{39564018} = \frac{39}{57148026} = \frac{54}{79128036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{10539674} = \frac{56}{21079348} = \frac{70}{26349185}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{17456390} = \frac{56}{34912780} = \frac{84}{52369170}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{39564180} = \frac{39}{57148260} = \frac{54}{79128360}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{10739654} = \frac{56}{21479308} = \frac{70}{26849135}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{19357046} = \frac{56}{38714092} = \frac{70}{48392615}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{27}{39841605} = \frac{42}{61975830} = \frac{54}{79683210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{10973564} = \frac{39}{15284607} = \frac{78}{30569214}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{28}{35071694} = \frac{36}{45092178} = \frac{72}{90184356}$
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- ▶ $\frac{32}{15789460} = \frac{40}{19736825} = \frac{64}{31578920}$
- ▶ $\frac{32}{15790486} = \frac{64}{31580972} = \frac{80}{39476215}$
- ▶ $\frac{32}{15967840} = \frac{48}{23951760} = \frac{86}{42913570}$
- ▶ $\frac{32}{16795804} = \frac{48}{25193706} = \frac{96}{50387412}$
- ▶ $\frac{32}{17589046} = \frac{64}{35178092} = \frac{80}{43972615}$

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|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{32}{17590486} = \frac{64}{35180972} = \frac{80}{43976215}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{18597602} = \frac{51}{27896403} = \frac{68}{37195204}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{27160985} = \frac{68}{54321970} = \frac{78}{62310495}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{32}{17894560} = \frac{64}{35789120} = \frac{73}{40821965}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{18597620} = \frac{51}{27896430} = \frac{68}{37195240}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{29158706} = \frac{42}{36019578} = \frac{84}{72039156}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{32}{17950864} = \frac{64}{35901728} = \frac{92}{51608734}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{19785602} = \frac{51}{29678403} = \frac{68}{39571204}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{29870615} = \frac{68}{59741230} = \frac{70}{61498325}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{32}{19478560} = \frac{47}{28609135} = \frac{64}{38957120}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{19785620} = \frac{51}{29678430} = \frac{68}{39571240}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{57012968} = \frac{41}{68750932} = \frac{52}{87196304}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{32}{19547680} = \frac{52}{31764980} = \frac{54}{32986710}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{19857602} = \frac{51}{29786403} = \frac{68}{39715204}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{10846297} = \frac{40}{12395768} = \frac{80}{24791536}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{32}{19567804} = \frac{48}{29351706} = \frac{96}{58703412}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{19857620} = \frac{51}{29786430} = \frac{68}{39715240}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{10846927} = \frac{60}{18594732} = \frac{70}{21693854}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{10259687} = \frac{68}{20519374} = \frac{94}{28365017}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{20178596} = \frac{51}{30267894} = \frac{68}{40357192}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{14829670} = \frac{49}{20761538} = \frac{98}{41523076}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{10789652} = \frac{68}{21579304} = \frac{85}{26974130}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{20179856} = \frac{51}{30269784} = \frac{68}{40359712}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{14962780} = \frac{45}{19237860} = \frac{84}{35910672}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{10965782} = \frac{49}{15803627} = \frac{98}{31607254}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{20185796} = \frac{51}{30278694} = \frac{68}{40371592}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{16208479} = \frac{40}{18523976} = \frac{70}{32416958}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{10967852} = \frac{68}{21935704} = \frac{85}{27419630}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{20185976} = \frac{51}{30278964} = \frac{68}{40371952}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{16807294} = \frac{45}{21609378} = \frac{90}{43218756}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{10987652} = \frac{68}{21975304} = \frac{85}{27469130}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{20197856} = \frac{51}{30296784} = \frac{68}{40395712}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{16829407} = \frac{45}{21637809} = \frac{90}{43275618}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{12698507} = \frac{68}{25397014} = \frac{70}{26143985}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{20198576} = \frac{51}{30297864} = \frac{68}{40397152}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{16940728} = \frac{45}{21780936} = \frac{90}{43561872}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{12705698} = \frac{54}{20179638} = \frac{81}{30269457}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{21785960} = \frac{51}{32678940} = \frac{68}{43571920}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{16942807} = \frac{45}{21783609} = \frac{90}{43567218}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{15692870} = \frac{47}{21693085} = \frac{67}{30924185}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{21798560} = \frac{51}{32697840} = \frac{68}{43597120}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{17986240} = \frac{49}{25180736} = \frac{98}{50361472}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{16025798} = \frac{51}{24038697} = \frac{67}{31580249}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{21857960} = \frac{51}{32786940} = \frac{68}{43715920}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{21476980} = \frac{82}{50317496} = \frac{94}{57681032}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{17859602} = \frac{51}{26789403} = \frac{68}{35719204}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{21859076} = \frac{47}{30216958} = \frac{49}{31502786}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{21748069} = \frac{45}{27961803} = \frac{65}{40389271}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{17859620} = \frac{51}{26789430} = \frac{68}{35719240}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{21859760} = \frac{51}{32789640} = \frac{68}{43719520}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{28071694} = \frac{45}{36092178} = \frac{90}{72184356}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{17985602} = \frac{51}{26978403} = \frac{68}{35971204}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{21875906} = \frac{71}{45682039} = \frac{89}{57263401}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{28169407} = \frac{45}{36217809} = \frac{90}{72435618}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{17985620} = \frac{51}{26978430} = \frac{68}{35971240}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{21978560} = \frac{51}{32967840} = \frac{68}{43957120}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{29407168} = \frac{45}{37809216} = \frac{90}{75618432}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{18579602} = \frac{51}{27869403} = \frac{68}{37159204}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{21985760} = \frac{51}{32978640} = \frac{68}{43971520}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{29416807} = \frac{45}{37821609} = \frac{90}{75643218}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{34}{18579620} = \frac{51}{27869430} = \frac{68}{37159240}$ | ▶ $\frac{34}{25871960} = \frac{68}{51743920} = \frac{94}{71528360}$ | ▶ $\frac{35}{29471680} = \frac{45}{37892160} = \frac{64}{53891072}$ |

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|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{35}{42176890} = \frac{61}{73508294} = \frac{63}{75918402}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{15790482} = \frac{48}{21053976} = \frac{72}{31580964}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19285470} = \frac{48}{25713960} = \frac{90}{48213675}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{35}{42971068} = \frac{65}{79803412} = \frac{70}{85942136}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{15794802} = \frac{48}{21059736} = \frac{72}{31589604}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19457802} = \frac{54}{29186703} = \frac{72}{38915604}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{35}{47062918} = \frac{40}{53786192} = \frac{70}{94125836}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{15978024} = \frac{72}{31956048} = \frac{78}{34619052}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19457820} = \frac{54}{29186730} = \frac{72}{38915640}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{35}{47129068} = \frac{40}{53861792} = \frac{70}{94258136}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{15978240} = \frac{72}{31956480} = \frac{78}{34619520}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19725084} = \frac{72}{39450168} = \frac{79}{43285601}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{35}{47806192} = \frac{60}{81953472} = \frac{70}{95612384}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17094825} = \frac{60}{28491375} = \frac{72}{34189650}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19725408} = \frac{68}{37259104} = \frac{72}{39450816}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{35}{48069217} = \frac{45}{61803279} = \frac{65}{89271403}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17095824} = \frac{39}{18520476} = \frac{45}{21369780}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19740258} = \frac{54}{29610387} = \frac{72}{39480516}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{35}{48107269} = \frac{65}{89342071} = \frac{70}{96214538}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17254098} = \frac{68}{32591074} = \frac{72}{34508196}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19780542} = \frac{54}{29670813} = \frac{72}{39561084}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{35}{48716920} = \frac{41}{57068392} = \frac{67}{93258104}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17402598} = \frac{54}{26103897} = \frac{72}{34805196}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19782054} = \frac{54}{29673081} = \frac{72}{39564108}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{12498750} = \frac{84}{29163750} = \frac{90}{31246875}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17459028} = \frac{59}{28613407} = \frac{72}{34918056}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19802574} = \frac{54}{29703861} = \frac{72}{39605148}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{14579802} = \frac{54}{21869703} = \frac{70}{28349615}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17480925} = \frac{60}{29134875} = \frac{72}{34961850}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19805274} = \frac{72}{39610548} = \frac{92}{50613478}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{14752980} = \frac{47}{19260835} = \frac{94}{38521670}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17508492} = \frac{51}{24803697} = \frac{72}{35016984}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{20179458} = \frac{54}{30269187} = \frac{72}{40358916}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{14958072} = \frac{39}{16204578} = \frac{78}{32409156}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17584902} = \frac{70}{34192865} = \frac{72}{35169804}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{20194578} = \frac{54}{30291867} = \frac{72}{40389156}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{15072849} = \frac{72}{30145698} = \frac{76}{31820459}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17945802} = \frac{54}{26918703} = \frac{72}{35891604}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{20541798} = \frac{54}{30812697} = \frac{72}{41083596}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{15072984} = \frac{72}{30145968} = \frac{84}{35170296}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17945820} = \frac{54}{26918730} = \frac{72}{35891640}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{20541978} = \frac{54}{30812967} = \frac{72}{41083956}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{15082974} = \frac{42}{17596803} = \frac{72}{30165948}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17980542} = \frac{54}{26970813} = \frac{72}{35961084}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{20951784} = \frac{45}{26189730} = \frac{72}{41903568}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{15279480} = \frac{46}{19523780} = \frac{87}{36925410}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{17982054} = \frac{54}{26973081} = \frac{72}{35964108}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{21475980} = \frac{64}{38179520} = \frac{78}{46531290}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{15490782} = \frac{72}{30981564} = \frac{96}{41308752}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{18025974} = \frac{54}{27038961} = \frac{72}{36051948}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{21579048} = \frac{45}{26973810} = \frac{72}{43158096}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{15702948} = \frac{63}{27480159} = \frac{72}{31405896}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{18075924} = \frac{43}{21590687} = \frac{78}{39164502}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{21759048} = \frac{72}{43518096} = \frac{93}{56210874}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{15702984} = \frac{45}{19628730} = \frac{72}{31405968}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{18457029} = \frac{56}{28710934} = \frac{72}{36914058}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{21794580} = \frac{54}{32691870} = \frac{72}{43589160}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{15729408} = \frac{42}{18350976} = \frac{84}{36701952}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19247508} = \frac{39}{20851467} = \frac{72}{38495016}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{21798054} = \frac{54}{32697081} = \frac{72}{43596108}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{36}{15729840} = \frac{72}{31459680} = \frac{79}{34518260}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{19247805} = \frac{72}{38495610} = \frac{96}{51327480}$ | ▶ $\frac{36}{21907548} = \frac{72}{43815096} = \frac{89}{54160327}$ |

- ▶ $\frac{36}{21978054} = \frac{54}{32967081} = \frac{72}{43956108}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{24015978} = \frac{72}{48031956} = \frac{78}{52034619}$
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- ▶ $\frac{36}{25781940} = \frac{37}{26498105} = \frac{54}{38672910}$
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- ▶ $\frac{36}{25974018} = \frac{54}{38961027} = \frac{72}{51948036}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{25980174} = \frac{54}{38970261} = \frac{72}{51960348}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{27154908} = \frac{63}{47521089} = \frac{72}{54309816}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{27194580} = \frac{72}{54389160} = \frac{89}{67231045}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{27415980} = \frac{72}{54831960} = \frac{93}{70824615}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{28170954} = \frac{52}{40691378} = \frac{72}{56341908}$
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- ▶ $\frac{36}{29705184} = \frac{63}{51984072} = \frac{72}{59410368}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{29815740} = \frac{47}{38926105} = \frac{72}{59631480}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{45091728} = \frac{63}{78910524} = \frac{72}{90183456}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{45702918} = \frac{56}{71093428} = \frac{72}{91405836}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{45820179} = \frac{48}{61093572} = \frac{72}{91640358}$
- ▶ $\frac{36}{48271590} = \frac{70}{93861425} = \frac{72}{96543180}$
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- ▶ $\frac{36}{57942180} = \frac{43}{69208715} = \frac{54}{86913270}$
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- ▶ $\frac{37}{12569048} = \frac{48}{16305792} = \frac{74}{25138096}$
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- ▶ $\frac{37}{14658290} = \frac{63}{24958710} = \frac{74}{29316580}$
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- ▶ $\frac{37}{26019584} = \frac{74}{52039168} = \frac{97}{68213504}$
- ▶ $\frac{37}{26198405} = \frac{74}{52396810} = \frac{76}{53812940}$
- ▶ $\frac{37}{29456810} = \frac{52}{41398760} = \frac{74}{58913620}$
- ▶ $\frac{37}{45682901} = \frac{47}{58029631} = \frac{74}{91365802}$
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- ▶ $\frac{38}{17945620} = \frac{57}{26918430} = \frac{76}{35891240}$
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▶ $\frac{38}{17962054} = \frac{57}{26943081} = \frac{76}{35924108}$	▶ $\frac{38}{21976054} = \frac{57}{32964081} = \frac{76}{43952108}$	▶ $\frac{39}{12640875} = \frac{63}{20419875} = \frac{98}{31764250}$
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▶ $\frac{38}{19457620} = \frac{57}{29186430} = \frac{76}{38915240}$	▶ $\frac{38}{25601974} = \frac{57}{38402961} = \frac{76}{51203948}$	▶ $\frac{39}{14762085} = \frac{42}{15897630} = \frac{84}{31795260}$
▶ $\frac{38}{19564072} = \frac{45}{23167980} = \frac{57}{29346108}$	▶ $\frac{38}{25619740} = \frac{57}{38429610} = \frac{76}{51239480}$	▶ $\frac{39}{15602478} = \frac{78}{31204956} = \frac{91}{36405782}$
▶ $\frac{38}{19602574} = \frac{57}{29403861} = \frac{76}{39205148}$	▶ $\frac{38}{25740196} = \frac{57}{38610294} = \frac{76}{51480392}$	▶ $\frac{39}{15624780} = \frac{78}{31249560} = \frac{91}{36457820}$
▶ $\frac{38}{19625740} = \frac{57}{29438610} = \frac{76}{39251480}$	▶ $\frac{38}{25741960} = \frac{57}{38612940} = \frac{76}{51483920}$	▶ $\frac{39}{15780246} = \frac{78}{31560492} = \frac{91}{36820574}$
▶ $\frac{38}{19740256} = \frac{57}{29610384} = \frac{76}{39480512}$	▶ $\frac{38}{25960174} = \frac{57}{38940261} = \frac{76}{51920348}$	▶ $\frac{39}{15782460} = \frac{78}{31564920} = \frac{91}{36825740}$
▶ $\frac{38}{19742560} = \frac{57}{29613840} = \frac{76}{39485120}$	▶ $\frac{38}{25961740} = \frac{57}{38942610} = \frac{76}{51923480}$	▶ $\frac{39}{16280745} = \frac{47}{19620385} = \frac{78}{32561490}$
▶ $\frac{38}{19760542} = \frac{57}{29640813} = \frac{76}{39521084}$	▶ $\frac{38}{25974016} = \frac{57}{38961024} = \frac{76}{51948032}$	▶ $\frac{39}{16458702} = \frac{61}{25743098} = \frac{96}{40513728}$
▶ $\frac{38}{19762054} = \frac{57}{29643081} = \frac{76}{39524108}$	▶ $\frac{38}{25974160} = \frac{57}{38961240} = \frac{76}{51948320}$	▶ $\frac{39}{16720548} = \frac{48}{20579136} = \frac{98}{42015736}$
▶ $\frac{38}{20179456} = \frac{57}{30269184} = \frac{76}{40358912}$	▶ $\frac{38}{26095417} = \frac{54}{37082961} = \frac{76}{52190834}$	▶ $\frac{39}{17284605} = \frac{61}{27034895} = \frac{78}{34569210}$
▶ $\frac{38}{20194576} = \frac{57}{30291864} = \frac{76}{40389152}$	▶ $\frac{38}{26914507} = \frac{46}{32580719} = \frac{76}{53829014}$	▶ $\frac{39}{17562480} = \frac{78}{35124960} = \frac{81}{36475920}$
▶ $\frac{38}{20541679} = \frac{56}{30271948} = \frac{94}{50813627}$	▶ $\frac{38}{27104659} = \frac{58}{41370269} = \frac{76}{54209318}$	▶ $\frac{39}{17624508} = \frac{65}{29374180} = \frac{78}{35249016}$
▶ $\frac{38}{20541796} = \frac{57}{30812694} = \frac{76}{41083592}$	▶ $\frac{38}{27164509} = \frac{54}{38602197} = \frac{76}{54329018}$	▶ $\frac{39}{21645780} = \frac{59}{32746180} = \frac{78}{43291560}$
▶ $\frac{38}{20541976} = \frac{57}{30812964} = \frac{76}{41083952}$	▶ $\frac{38}{29470615} = \frac{76}{58941230} = \frac{78}{60492315}$	▶ $\frac{39}{21750846} = \frac{78}{43501692} = \frac{93}{51867402}$
▶ $\frac{38}{21054679} = \frac{56}{31027948} = \frac{76}{42109358}$	▶ $\frac{38}{29741650} = \frac{41}{32089675} = \frac{82}{64179350}$	▶ $\frac{39}{24601578} = \frac{78}{49203156} = \frac{91}{57403682}$
▶ $\frac{38}{21750649} = \frac{62}{35487901} = \frac{76}{43501298}$	▶ $\frac{38}{41952076} = \frac{73}{80592146} = \frac{76}{83904152}$	▶ $\frac{39}{24615780} = \frac{78}{49231560} = \frac{91}{57436820}$
▶ $\frac{38}{21794560} = \frac{57}{32691840} = \frac{76}{43589120}$	▶ $\frac{38}{46791205} = \frac{70}{86194325} = \frac{76}{93582410}$	▶ $\frac{39}{24780156} = \frac{78}{49560312} = \frac{91}{57820364}$
▶ $\frac{38}{21796054} = \frac{57}{32694081} = \frac{76}{43592108}$	▶ $\frac{38}{46927150} = \frac{39}{48162075} = \frac{78}{96324150}$	▶ $\frac{39}{24781560} = \frac{78}{49563120} = \frac{91}{57823640}$
▶ $\frac{38}{21945076} = \frac{59}{34072618} = \frac{76}{43890152}$	▶ $\frac{38}{59617402} = \frac{48}{75306192} = \frac{57}{89426103}$	▶ $\frac{39}{25810746} = \frac{45}{29781630} = \frac{93}{61548702}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{26074815} = \frac{78}{52149630} = \frac{93}{62178405}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13079865} = \frac{56}{17439820} = \frac{84}{26159730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{31097586} = \frac{49}{36280517} = \frac{98}{72561034}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{26481507} = \frac{78}{52963014} = \frac{89}{60432157}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13509678} = \frac{81}{26054379} = \frac{84}{27019356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{31587906} = \frac{57}{42869301} = \frac{87}{65432091}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{26584701} = \frac{56}{38172904} = \frac{78}{53169402}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13679805} = \frac{56}{18239740} = \frac{84}{27359610}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{36015798} = \frac{58}{49736102} = \frac{84}{72031596}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{26745108} = \frac{48}{32917056} = \frac{78}{53490216}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13769805} = \frac{48}{15736920} = \frac{84}{27539610}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{36510978} = \frac{61}{53027849} = \frac{84}{73021956}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{28607514} = \frac{51}{37409826} = \frac{85}{62349710}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13798065} = \frac{56}{18397420} = \frac{84}{27596130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{37961805} = \frac{84}{75923610} = \frac{90}{81346725}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{45278610} = \frac{74}{85913260} = \frac{84}{97523160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13976508} = \frac{84}{27953016} = \frac{94}{31280756}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{38975160} = \frac{51}{47326980} = \frac{92}{85374160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{39}{47052681} = \frac{69}{83247051} = \frac{78}{94105362}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{15308769} = \frac{54}{19682703} = \frac{98}{35720461}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{39576180} = \frac{81}{76325490} = \frac{84}{79152360}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40}{19582376} = \frac{70}{34269158} = \frac{80}{39164752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{16079835} = \frac{56}{21439780} = \frac{84}{32159670}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{39780615} = \frac{72}{68195340} = \frac{84}{79561230}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40}{19675328} = \frac{65}{31972408} = \frac{75}{36891240}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{16307985} = \frac{56}{21743980} = \frac{84}{32615970}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{50187396} = \frac{63}{75281094} = \frac{78}{93205164}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40}{19823576} = \frac{70}{34691258} = \frac{80}{39647152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{16379805} = \frac{56}{21839740} = \frac{84}{32759610}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{51978360} = \frac{61}{75492380} = \frac{78}{96531240}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40}{19825736} = \frac{80}{39651472} = \frac{95}{47086123}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{16395078} = \frac{54}{21079386} = \frac{84}{32790156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43}{15098762} = \frac{47}{16503298} = \frac{86}{30197524}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{20763958} = \frac{65}{32918470} = \frac{78}{39502164}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{17950863} = \frac{54}{23079681} = \frac{84}{35901726}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43}{17092586} = \frac{79}{31402658} = \frac{92}{36570184}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{20968753} = \frac{82}{41937506} = \frac{92}{47051836}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{17980635} = \frac{56}{23974180} = \frac{84}{35961270}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43}{21096875} = \frac{81}{39740625} = \frac{86}{42193750}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{25836970} = \frac{78}{49153260} = \frac{82}{51673940}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{17983605} = \frac{56}{23978140} = \frac{84}{35967210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43}{27601958} = \frac{47}{30169582} = \frac{65}{41723890}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{29563870} = \frac{61}{43985270} = \frac{89}{64175230}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{17986305} = \frac{56}{23981740} = \frac{84}{35972610}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43}{29601587} = \frac{76}{52319084} = \frac{86}{59203174}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{32589670} = \frac{82}{65179340} = \frac{83}{65974210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{18795630} = \frac{84}{37591260} = \frac{91}{40723865}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43}{56798012} = \frac{61}{80573924} = \frac{72}{95103648}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41}{39268570} = \frac{61}{58423970} = \frac{62}{59381740}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{30187956} = \frac{84}{60375912} = \frac{91}{65407238}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{10238679} = \frac{65}{14789203} = \frac{70}{15926834}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{10679835} = \frac{56}{14239780} = \frac{84}{21359670}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{30518796} = \frac{45}{32698710} = \frac{84}{61037592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{10826739} = \frac{80}{19247536} = \frac{90}{21653478}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{10798365} = \frac{56}{14397820} = \frac{84}{21596730}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{30796185} = \frac{84}{61592370} = \frac{92}{67458310}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{10892673} = \frac{80}{19364752} = \frac{90}{21785346}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{10953768} = \frac{84}{21907536} = \frac{96}{25037184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{30965718} = \frac{68}{50134972} = \frac{71}{52346809}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{12869073} = \frac{90}{25738146} = \frac{95}{27168043}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{13067985} = \frac{56}{17423980} = \frac{84}{26135970}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{42}{31079685} = \frac{52}{38479610} = \frac{84}{62159370}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{16273908} = \frac{70}{25314968} = \frac{90}{32547816}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{16372809} = \frac{85}{30926417} = \frac{90}{32745618}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{23915078} = \frac{87}{45230691} = \frac{92}{47830156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{12375960} = \frac{72}{18563940} = \frac{84}{21657930}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{17263809} = \frac{85}{32609417} = \frac{90}{34527618}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{27358190} = \frac{69}{41037285} = \frac{92}{54716380}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{12395760} = \frac{72}{18593640} = \frac{93}{24016785}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{19062738} = \frac{70}{29653148} = \frac{90}{38125476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{27359018} = \frac{69}{41038527} = \frac{92}{54718036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{12397560} = \frac{72}{18596340} = \frac{84}{21695730}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{20631789} = \frac{65}{29801473} = \frac{90}{41263578}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{27381590} = \frac{69}{41072385} = \frac{92}{54763180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{13576920} = \frac{84}{23759610} = \frac{96}{27153840}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{20893176} = \frac{75}{34821960} = \frac{90}{41786352}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{27390158} = \frac{69}{41085237} = \frac{92}{54780316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{15209376} = \frac{96}{30418752} = \frac{98}{31052476}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{21368079} = \frac{85}{40361927} = \frac{90}{42736158}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{29570318} = \frac{81}{52069473} = \frac{97}{62354801}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{15927360} = \frac{96}{31854720} = \frac{97}{32186540}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{21793086} = \frac{65}{31478902} = \frac{90}{43586172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{38157920} = \frac{91}{75486320} = \frac{92}{76315840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{16739520} = \frac{94}{32781560} = \frac{98}{34176520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{26731089} = \frac{80}{47521936} = \frac{90}{53462178}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{57923108} = \frac{47}{59182306} = \frac{74}{93180652}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{17063952} = \frac{83}{29506417} = \frac{86}{30572914}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{26739108} = \frac{80}{47536192} = \frac{90}{53478216}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{58271903} = \frac{62}{78540391} = \frac{64}{81073952}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{17293560} = \frac{52}{18734690} = \frac{96}{34587120}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{26938071} = \frac{60}{35917428} = \frac{90}{53876142}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{70935128} = \frac{53}{81729604} = \frac{63}{97150284}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{17390256} = \frac{81}{29346057} = \frac{96}{34780512}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{29368071} = \frac{60}{39157428} = \frac{90}{58736142}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{15629380} = \frac{81}{26935740} = \frac{94}{31258760}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{17532096} = \frac{54}{19723608} = \frac{57}{20819364}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{32718690} = \frac{49}{35627018} = \frac{98}{71254036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{15902638} = \frac{74}{25038196} = \frac{94}{31805276}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{17906352} = \frac{69}{25740381} = \frac{96}{35812704}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{32968170} = \frac{81}{59342706} = \frac{89}{65203714}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{26318590} = \frac{53}{29678410} = \frac{94}{52637180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{19027356} = \frac{60}{23784195} = \frac{96}{38054712}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{37928610} = \frac{85}{71642930} = \frac{89}{75014362}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{26810539} = \frac{81}{46205397} = \frac{94}{53621078}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{19205376} = \frac{94}{37610528} = \frac{96}{38410752}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45}{38276910} = \frac{46}{39127508} = \frac{71}{60392458}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{29301586} = \frac{87}{54239106} = \frac{94}{58603172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{19360752} = \frac{63}{25410987} = \frac{96}{38721504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{15827390} = \frac{69}{23741085} = \frac{92}{31654780}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{30126859} = \frac{51}{32690847} = \frac{94}{60253718}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{21057936} = \frac{54}{23690178} = \frac{72}{31586904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{15902738} = \frac{69}{23854107} = \frac{92}{31805476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{31628509} = \frac{93}{62584071} = \frac{94}{63257018}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{21759360} = \frac{93}{42158760} = \frac{96}{43518720}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{17835902} = \frac{91}{35284067} = \frac{92}{35671804}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{47}{36810259} = \frac{72}{56390184} = \frac{94}{73620518}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{21790536} = \frac{78}{35409621} = \frac{96}{43581072}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{18273590} = \frac{69}{27410385} = \frac{92}{36547180}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{10357692} = \frac{56}{12083974} = \frac{96}{20715384}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{23790516} = \frac{60}{29738145} = \frac{96}{47581032}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{19027358} = \frac{69}{28541037} = \frac{92}{38054716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{12037596} = \frac{72}{18056394} = \frac{84}{21065793}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{25031976} = \frac{54}{28160973} = \frac{58}{30246971}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{46}{19203758} = \frac{71}{29640583} = \frac{92}{38407516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{12039756} = \frac{72}{18059634} = \frac{84}{21069573}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{25190736} = \frac{81}{42509367} = \frac{96}{50381472}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{25390617} = \frac{80}{42317695} = \frac{96}{50781234}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{13250867} = \frac{91}{24608753} = \frac{98}{26501734}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{20381976} = \frac{81}{30572964} = \frac{84}{31705296}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{25603917} = \frac{80}{42673195} = \frac{96}{51207834}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{15736028} = \frac{56}{17984032} = \frac{98}{31472056}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{29173068} = \frac{76}{41058392} = \frac{81}{43759602}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{25639017} = \frac{80}{42731695} = \frac{96}{51278034}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{15736280} = \frac{56}{17984320} = \frac{98}{31472560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{56}{17398024} = \frac{67}{20815493} = \frac{89}{27650431}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{25719036} = \frac{60}{32148795} = \frac{96}{51438072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{17258360} = \frac{56}{19723840} = \frac{98}{34516720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{56}{34809712} = \frac{81}{50349762} = \frac{82}{50971364}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{25903617} = \frac{80}{43172695} = \frac{96}{51807234}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{18352607} = \frac{67}{25094381} = \frac{98}{36705214}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{19243086} = \frac{61}{20593478} = \frac{65}{21943870}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{35601792} = \frac{51}{37826904} = \frac{96}{71203584}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{26507138} = \frac{78}{42195036} = \frac{98}{53014276}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{24960813} = \frac{78}{34156902} = \frac{81}{35470629}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{35617920} = \frac{73}{54168920} = \frac{96}{71235840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{28015736} = \frac{56}{32017984} = \frac{98}{56031472}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{26940138} = \frac{76}{35920184} = \frac{84}{39701256}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{36179520} = \frac{57}{42963180} = \frac{58}{43716920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{28650713} = \frac{91}{53208467} = \frac{98}{57301426}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{48219036} = \frac{69}{58370412} = \frac{84}{71059632}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{37596012} = \frac{72}{56394018} = \frac{84}{65793021}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{35708162} = \frac{85}{61942730} = \frac{94}{68501372}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{48329160} = \frac{73}{61895240} = \frac{89}{75461320}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{37596120} = \frac{72}{56394180} = \frac{84}{65793210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{37162580} = \frac{51}{38679420} = \frac{98}{74325160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57}{61340892} = \frac{79}{85016324} = \frac{85}{91473260}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{37659012} = \frac{84}{65903271} = \frac{96}{75318024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{38067512} = \frac{52}{40398176} = \frac{98}{76135024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{29460317} = \frac{82}{41650793} = \frac{92}{46730158}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{37691520} = \frac{83}{65174920} = \frac{94}{73812560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{38201576} = \frac{51}{39760824} = \frac{98}{76403152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{39671420} = \frac{71}{48563290} = \frac{76}{51983240}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{37910652} = \frac{52}{41069873} = \frac{96}{75821304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{51}{26374089} = \frac{89}{46025371} = \frac{97}{50162483}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58}{46031729} = \frac{82}{65079341} = \frac{92}{73015846}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{39106752} = \frac{89}{72510436} = \frac{96}{78213504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{51}{36948072} = \frac{58}{42019376} = \frac{74}{53610928}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59}{24036187} = \frac{61}{24850973} = \frac{92}{37480156}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{39756012} = \frac{72}{59634018} = \frac{84}{69573021}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{51}{39208647} = \frac{96}{73804512} = \frac{98}{75342106}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59}{32806714} = \frac{81}{45039726} = \frac{85}{47263910}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{39756120} = \frac{72}{59634180} = \frac{84}{69573210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{52}{18934760} = \frac{59}{21483670} = \frac{73}{26581490}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{62}{14579083} = \frac{72}{16930548} = \frac{84}{19752306}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{63905712} = \frac{49}{65237081} = \frac{74}{98521306}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{52}{19370468} = \frac{67}{24958103} = \frac{84}{31290756}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{62}{17390845} = \frac{70}{19634825} = \frac{84}{23561790}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{75219360} = \frac{62}{97158340} = \frac{63}{98725410}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{52}{19374680} = \frac{71}{26453890} = \frac{84}{31297560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{65}{24789310} = \frac{79}{30128546} = \frac{85}{32416790}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{76509312} = \frac{49}{78103256} = \frac{61}{97230584}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{52}{43697810} = \frac{64}{53781920} = \frac{68}{57143290}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{25843910} = \frac{76}{29315480} = \frac{92}{35487160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{48}{76530912} = \frac{49}{78125306} = \frac{61}{97258034}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{10268397} = \frac{68}{12930574} = \frac{84}{15973062}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67}{40132598} = \frac{68}{40731592} = \frac{83}{49716502}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{49}{10675238} = \frac{69}{15032478} = \frac{98}{21350476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{54}{20176398} = \frac{81}{30264597} = \frac{87}{32506419}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69}{78245310} = \frac{74}{83915260} = \frac{86}{97523140}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{70}{12346985} = \frac{76}{13405298} = \frac{94}{16580237}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{72}{54013968} = \frac{94}{70518236} = \frac{95}{71268430}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84}{29315706} = \frac{94}{32805671} = \frac{98}{34201657}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{70}{26894315} = \frac{82}{31504769} = \frac{98}{37652041}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{72}{61059348} = \frac{84}{71235906} = \frac{90}{76324185}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85}{23917640} = \frac{89}{25043176} = \frac{95}{26731480}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{70}{49832615} = \frac{74}{52680193} = \frac{76}{54103982}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{75}{68924310} = \frac{80}{73519264} = \frac{95}{87304126}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{15702439} = \frac{90}{16432785} = \frac{96}{17528304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{72}{19048536} = \frac{78}{20635914} = \frac{89}{23546107}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{79}{64521038} = \frac{85}{69421370} = \frac{96}{78405312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86}{39754102} = \frac{87}{40216359} = \frac{91}{42065387}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{72}{40195368} = \frac{92}{51360748} = \frac{98}{54710362}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{80}{15427936} = \frac{90}{17356428} = \frac{95}{18320674}$	

• **Single Digit Numerator**

$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{203475689} = \frac{2}{406951378} = \frac{4}{813902756}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{205347689} = \frac{2}{410695378} = \frac{4}{821390756}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206897534} = \frac{2}{413795068} = \frac{4}{827590136}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{203487569} = \frac{2}{406975138} = \frac{4}{813950276}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{205348769} = \frac{2}{410697538} = \frac{4}{821395076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206975384} = \frac{2}{413950768} = \frac{4}{827901536}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{203756849} = \frac{2}{407513698} = \frac{4}{815027396}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{205376849} = \frac{2}{410753698} = \frac{4}{821507396}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206983754} = \frac{2}{413967508} = \frac{4}{827935016}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{203756984} = \frac{2}{407513968} = \frac{4}{815027936}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{205376984} = \frac{2}{410753968} = \frac{4}{821507936}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206987534} = \frac{2}{413975068} = \frac{4}{827950136}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{203765948} = \frac{2}{407531896} = \frac{4}{815063792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{205384769} = \frac{2}{410769538} = \frac{4}{821539076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{207653948} = \frac{2}{415307896} = \frac{4}{830615792}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{203847569} = \frac{2}{407695138} = \frac{4}{815390276}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{205397684} = \frac{2}{410795368} = \frac{4}{821590736}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{207654398} = \frac{2}{415308796} = \frac{4}{830617592}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{203947658} = \frac{2}{407895316} = \frac{4}{815790632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{205476839} = \frac{2}{410953678} = \frac{4}{821907356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{207654893} = \frac{2}{415309786} = \frac{4}{830619572}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{203975684} = \frac{2}{407951368} = \frac{4}{815902736}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{205483769} = \frac{2}{410967538} = \frac{4}{821935076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{207654938} = \frac{2}{415309876} = \frac{4}{830619752}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{204376598} = \frac{2}{408753196} = \frac{4}{817506392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206753489} = \frac{2}{413506978} = \frac{4}{827013956}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{208765493} = \frac{2}{417530986} = \frac{4}{835061972}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{204397658} = \frac{2}{408795316} = \frac{4}{817590632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206753849} = \frac{2}{413507698} = \frac{4}{827015396}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{208947653} = \frac{2}{417895306} = \frac{4}{835790612}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{204756839} = \frac{2}{409513678} = \frac{4}{819027356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206753984} = \frac{2}{413507968} = \frac{4}{827015936}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{208976543} = \frac{2}{417953086} = \frac{4}{835906172}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{204765893} = \frac{2}{409531786} = \frac{4}{819063572}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206754839} = \frac{2}{413509678} = \frac{4}{827019356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{209376548} = \frac{2}{418753096} = \frac{4}{837506192}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{204765938} = \frac{2}{409531876} = \frac{4}{819063752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206837549} = \frac{2}{413675098} = \frac{4}{827350196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{209476538} = \frac{2}{418953076} = \frac{4}{837906152}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{204837569} = \frac{2}{409675138} = \frac{4}{819350276}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206839754} = \frac{2}{413679508} = \frac{4}{827359016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{209487653} = \frac{2}{418975306} = \frac{4}{837950612}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{204876593} = \frac{2}{409753186} = \frac{4}{819506372}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{206847539} = \frac{2}{413695078} = \frac{4}{827390156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{209765438} = \frac{2}{419530876} = \frac{4}{839061752}$
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- ▶ $\frac{1}{230457689} = \frac{2}{460915378} = \frac{4}{921830756}$
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- ▶ $\frac{1}{240395768} = \frac{2}{480791536} = \frac{4}{961583072}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{240396758} = \frac{2}{480793516} = \frac{4}{961587032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245376809} = \frac{2}{490753618} = \frac{4}{981507236}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246758039} = \frac{2}{493516078} = \frac{4}{987032156}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{240678395} = \frac{2}{481356790} = \frac{4}{962713580}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245376908} = \frac{2}{490753816} = \frac{4}{981507632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246758903} = \frac{2}{493517806} = \frac{4}{987035612}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{240753968} = \frac{2}{481507936} = \frac{4}{963015872}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245390768} = \frac{2}{490781536} = \frac{4}{981563072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246783905} = \frac{2}{493567810} = \frac{4}{987135620}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{240768953} = \frac{2}{481537906} = \frac{4}{963075812}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245678390} = \frac{2}{491356780} = \frac{4}{982713560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246803759} = \frac{2}{493607518} = \frac{4}{987215036}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{240769538} = \frac{2}{481539076} = \frac{4}{963078152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245683790} = \frac{2}{491367580} = \frac{4}{982735160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246807539} = \frac{2}{493615078} = \frac{4}{987230156}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{240876953} = \frac{2}{481753906} = \frac{4}{963507812}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245768039} = \frac{2}{491536078} = \frac{4}{983072156}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246837905} = \frac{2}{493675810} = \frac{4}{987351620}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{240896753} = \frac{2}{481793506} = \frac{4}{963587012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245768903} = \frac{2}{491537806} = \frac{4}{983075612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246875309} = \frac{2}{493750618} = \frac{4}{987501236}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{240953768} = \frac{2}{481907536} = \frac{4}{963815072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245769038} = \frac{2}{491538076} = \frac{4}{983076152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246875903} = \frac{2}{493751806} = \frac{4}{987503612}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{243078965} = \frac{2}{486157930} = \frac{4}{972315860}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245903768} = \frac{2}{491807536} = \frac{4}{983615072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246907538} = \frac{2}{493815076} = \frac{4}{987630152}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{243087965} = \frac{2}{486175930} = \frac{4}{972351860}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246507893} = \frac{2}{493015786} = \frac{4}{986031572}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246908753} = \frac{2}{493817506} = \frac{4}{987635012}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{243780965} = \frac{2}{487561930} = \frac{4}{975123860}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246507938} = \frac{2}{493015876} = \frac{4}{986031752}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{250689473} = \frac{2}{501378946} = \frac{3}{752068419}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{243796508} = \frac{2}{487593016} = \frac{4}{975186032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246508793} = \frac{2}{493017586} = \frac{4}{986035172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{250694873} = \frac{2}{501389746} = \frac{3}{752084619}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{243796580} = \frac{2}{487593160} = \frac{4}{975186320}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246509378} = \frac{2}{493018756} = \frac{4}{986037512}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{250869473} = \frac{2}{501738946} = \frac{3}{752608419}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{243807965} = \frac{2}{487615930} = \frac{4}{975231860}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246578930} = \frac{2}{493157860} = \frac{4}{986315720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{250894673} = \frac{2}{501789346} = \frac{3}{752684019}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{243965078} = \frac{2}{487930156} = \frac{4}{975860312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246579380} = \frac{2}{493158760} = \frac{4}{986317520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{250946873} = \frac{2}{501893746} = \frac{3}{752840619}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{243965780} = \frac{2}{487931560} = \frac{4}{975863120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246587930} = \frac{2}{493175860} = \frac{4}{986351720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{250948673} = \frac{2}{501897346} = \frac{3}{752846019}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245067839} = \frac{2}{490135678} = \frac{4}{980271356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246593780} = \frac{2}{493187560} = \frac{4}{986375120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{253068947} = \frac{2}{506137894} = \frac{3}{759206841}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245068379} = \frac{2}{490136758} = \frac{4}{980273516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246753089} = \frac{2}{493506178} = \frac{4}{987012356}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{253069487} = \frac{2}{506138974} = \frac{3}{759208461}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{245307689} = \frac{2}{490615378} = \frac{4}{981230756}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{246753809} = \frac{2}{493507618} = \frac{4}{987015236}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{1}{253086947} = \frac{2}{506173894} = \frac{3}{759260841}$
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- ▶ $\frac{1}{253094687} = \frac{2}{506189374} = \frac{3}{759284061}$
- ▶ $\frac{1}{253094867} = \frac{2}{506189734} = \frac{3}{759284601}$
- ▶ $\frac{1}{265089347} = \frac{2}{530178694} = \frac{3}{795268041}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{136904758} = \frac{4}{273809516} = \frac{8}{547619032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140579836} = \frac{3}{210869754} = \frac{6}{421739508}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147536809} = \frac{4}{295073618} = \frac{8}{590147236}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{136907548} = \frac{4}{273815096} = \frac{8}{547630192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140597836} = \frac{3}{210896754} = \frac{6}{421793508}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147536908} = \frac{4}{295073816} = \frac{8}{590147632}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{136975408} = \frac{4}{273950816} = \frac{8}{547901632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140679835} = \frac{4}{281359670} = \frac{8}{562719340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147569380} = \frac{4}{295138760} = \frac{7}{516492830}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{136975804} = \frac{4}{273951608} = \frac{8}{547903216}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140697835} = \frac{4}{281395670} = \frac{8}{562791340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147580369} = \frac{4}{295160738} = \frac{8}{590321476}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{136978405} = \frac{4}{273956810} = \frac{8}{547913620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140753698} = \frac{4}{281507396} = \frac{8}{563014792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147586903} = \frac{4}{295173806} = \frac{8}{590347612}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{136980754} = \frac{4}{273961508} = \frac{8}{547923016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140769853} = \frac{4}{281539706} = \frac{8}{563079412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147590368} = \frac{4}{295180736} = \frac{8}{590361472}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{137965840} = \frac{4}{275931680} = \frac{6}{413897520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140869753} = \frac{4}{281739506} = \frac{8}{563479012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147680359} = \frac{4}{295360718} = \frac{8}{590721436}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{139047568} = \frac{4}{278095136} = \frac{5}{347618920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140975368} = \frac{4}{281950736} = \frac{8}{563901472}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147685309} = \frac{4}{295370618} = \frac{8}{590741236}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{139476508} = \frac{4}{278953016} = \frac{5}{348691270}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140976853} = \frac{4}{281953706} = \frac{8}{563907412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147685903} = \frac{4}{295371806} = \frac{8}{590743612}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{139507684} = \frac{4}{279015368} = \frac{5}{348769210}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140986753} = \frac{4}{281973506} = \frac{8}{563947012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147690358} = \frac{4}{295380716} = \frac{8}{590761432}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{139657840} = \frac{4}{279315680} = \frac{6}{418973520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{143079865} = \frac{4}{286159730} = \frac{8}{572319460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147690853} = \frac{4}{295381706} = \frac{8}{590763412}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140357698} = \frac{4}{280715396} = \frac{8}{561430792}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{143097865} = \frac{4}{286195730} = \frac{8}{572391460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147809365} = \frac{4}{295618730} = \frac{8}{591237460}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140359768} = \frac{4}{280719536} = \frac{8}{561439072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{143650798} = \frac{4}{287301596} = \frac{8}{574603192}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147835069} = \frac{4}{295670138} = \frac{8}{591340276}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140365798} = \frac{3}{210548697} = \frac{4}{280731596}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{143650978} = \frac{4}{287301956} = \frac{8}{574603912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147835690} = \frac{4}{295671380} = \frac{8}{591342760}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140365978} = \frac{3}{210548967} = \frac{4}{280731956}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{143765980} = \frac{3}{215648970} = \frac{4}{287531960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147836905} = \frac{4}{295673810} = \frac{8}{591347620}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140367598} = \frac{4}{280735196} = \frac{8}{561470392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{143796580} = \frac{3}{215694870} = \frac{4}{287593160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147865093} = \frac{4}{295730186} = \frac{8}{591460372}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140369758} = \frac{4}{280739516} = \frac{8}{561479032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{143859760} = \frac{3}{215789640} = \frac{6}{431579280}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147865930} = \frac{4}{295731860} = \frac{8}{591463720}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{140376598} = \frac{3}{210564897} = \frac{4}{280753196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{143965780} = \frac{3}{215948670} = \frac{4}{287931560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147906835} = \frac{4}{295813670} = \frac{8}{591627340}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147930865} = \frac{4}{295861730} = \frac{8}{591723460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{149365078} = \frac{4}{298730156} = \frac{8}{597460312}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154760893} = \frac{4}{309521786} = \frac{8}{619043572}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{147936580} = \frac{4}{295873160} = \frac{8}{591746320}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{149365780} = \frac{4}{298731560} = \frac{8}{597463120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154760938} = \frac{4}{309521876} = \frac{8}{619043752}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148035769} = \frac{4}{296071538} = \frac{8}{592143076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{150786493} = \frac{4}{301572986} = \frac{8}{603145972}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154809376} = \frac{4}{309618752} = \frac{8}{619237504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148036759} = \frac{4}{296073518} = \frac{8}{592147036}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{150794863} = \frac{4}{301589726} = \frac{8}{603179452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154876093} = \frac{4}{309752186} = \frac{8}{619504372}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148075369} = \frac{4}{296150738} = \frac{8}{592301476}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{150798643} = \frac{4}{301597286} = \frac{8}{603194572}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154893076} = \frac{4}{309786152} = \frac{8}{619572304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148079365} = \frac{4}{296158730} = \frac{8}{592317460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{150864793} = \frac{4}{301729586} = \frac{8}{603459172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154930876} = \frac{4}{309861752} = \frac{8}{619723504}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148350679} = \frac{4}{296701358} = \frac{8}{593402716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{150936478} = \frac{4}{301872956} = \frac{8}{603745912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154937608} = \frac{4}{309875216} = \frac{8}{619750432}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148356790} = \frac{4}{296713580} = \frac{8}{593427160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{150947863} = \frac{4}{301895726} = \frac{8}{603791452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154938076} = \frac{4}{309876152} = \frac{8}{619752304}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148367905} = \frac{4}{296735810} = \frac{8}{593471620}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{150978643} = \frac{4}{301957286} = \frac{8}{603914572}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157603948} = \frac{4}{315207896} = \frac{8}{630415792}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148530769} = \frac{4}{297061538} = \frac{8}{594123076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{153078964} = \frac{4}{306157928} = \frac{5}{382697410}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157604398} = \frac{4}{315208796} = \frac{8}{630417592}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148576903} = \frac{4}{297153806} = \frac{8}{594307612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{153089476} = \frac{4}{306178952} = \frac{8}{612357904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157604893} = \frac{4}{315209786} = \frac{8}{630419572}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148650793} = \frac{4}{297301586} = \frac{8}{594603172}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{153094876} = \frac{4}{306189752} = \frac{8}{612379504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157604938} = \frac{4}{315209876} = \frac{8}{630419752}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148657930} = \frac{4}{297315860} = \frac{8}{594631720}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{153098764} = \frac{4}{306197528} = \frac{5}{382746910}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157839640} = \frac{4}{315679280} = \frac{6}{473518920}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148675903} = \frac{4}{297351806} = \frac{8}{594703612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{153809476} = \frac{4}{307618952} = \frac{8}{615237904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157936480} = \frac{4}{315872960} = \frac{8}{631745920}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{148690753} = \frac{4}{297381506} = \frac{8}{594763012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{153907648} = \frac{4}{307815296} = \frac{5}{384769120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157948630} = \frac{4}{315897260} = \frac{8}{631794520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{149035768} = \frac{4}{298071536} = \frac{8}{596143072}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{153947608} = \frac{4}{307895216} = \frac{8}{615790432}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157963840} = \frac{4}{315927680} = \frac{6}{473891520}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{149036758} = \frac{4}{298073516} = \frac{8}{596147032}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{153948076} = \frac{4}{307896152} = \frac{8}{615792304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157983604} = \frac{4}{315967208} = \frac{6}{473950812}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{149067835} = \frac{4}{298135670} = \frac{8}{596271340}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154308976} = \frac{4}{308617952} = \frac{8}{617235904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157984036} = \frac{4}{315968072} = \frac{6}{473952108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{149075368} = \frac{4}{298150736} = \frac{8}{596301472}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154309876} = \frac{4}{308619752} = \frac{8}{617239504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157986034} = \frac{4}{315972068} = \frac{6}{473958102}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{149076853} = \frac{4}{298153706} = \frac{8}{596307412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154376098} = \frac{4}{308752196} = \frac{8}{617504392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{157986430} = \frac{4}{315972860} = \frac{8}{631945720}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{149086753} = \frac{4}{298173506} = \frac{8}{596347012}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154380976} = \frac{4}{308761952} = \frac{8}{617523904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{158039476} = \frac{4}{316078952} = \frac{8}{632157904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{149307865} = \frac{4}{298615730} = \frac{8}{597231460}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{154398076} = \frac{4}{308796152} = \frac{8}{617592304}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{158043976} = \frac{4}{316087952} = \frac{8}{632175904}$

▶ $\frac{2}{158049376} = \frac{4}{316098752} = \frac{8}{632197504}$	▶ $\frac{2}{159843760} = \frac{4}{319687520} = \frac{6}{479531280}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160894753} = \frac{4}{321789506} = \frac{8}{643579012}$
▶ $\frac{2}{158379640} = \frac{4}{316759280} = \frac{6}{475138920}$	▶ $\frac{2}{159876043} = \frac{4}{319752086} = \frac{8}{639504172}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160897543} = \frac{4}{321795086} = \frac{8}{643590172}$
▶ $\frac{2}{158439760} = \frac{4}{316879520} = \frac{6}{475319280}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160357984} = \frac{4}{320715968} = \frac{6}{481073952}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160937548} = \frac{4}{321875096} = \frac{8}{643750192}$
▶ $\frac{2}{158647930} = \frac{4}{317295860} = \frac{8}{634591720}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160359784} = \frac{4}{320719568} = \frac{6}{481079352}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160947538} = \frac{4}{321895076} = \frac{8}{643790152}$
▶ $\frac{2}{158760493} = \frac{4}{317520986} = \frac{8}{635041972}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160375948} = \frac{4}{320751896} = \frac{8}{641503792}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160948753} = \frac{4}{321897506} = \frac{8}{643795012}$
▶ $\frac{2}{158930476} = \frac{4}{317860952} = \frac{8}{635721904}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160379458} = \frac{3}{240569187} = \frac{4}{320758916}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160975438} = \frac{4}{321950876} = \frac{8}{643901752}$
▶ $\frac{2}{158947603} = \frac{4}{317895206} = \frac{8}{635790412}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160394578} = \frac{3}{240591867} = \frac{4}{320789156}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160987543} = \frac{4}{321975086} = \frac{8}{643950172}$
▶ $\frac{2}{158976043} = \frac{4}{317952086} = \frac{8}{635904172}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160394758} = \frac{4}{320789516} = \frac{8}{641579032}$	▶ $\frac{2}{163079485} = \frac{4}{326158970} = \frac{8}{652317940}$
▶ $\frac{2}{159304876} = \frac{4}{318609752} = \frac{8}{637219504}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160437598} = \frac{4}{320875196} = \frac{8}{641750392}$	▶ $\frac{2}{163094785} = \frac{4}{326189570} = \frac{8}{652379140}$
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▶ $\frac{2}{159480376} = \frac{4}{318960752} = \frac{8}{637921504}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160543798} = \frac{3}{240815697} = \frac{4}{321087596}$	▶ $\frac{2}{163794580} = \frac{3}{245691870} = \frac{4}{327589160}$
▶ $\frac{2}{159487603} = \frac{4}{318975206} = \frac{8}{637950412}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160543978} = \frac{3}{240815967} = \frac{4}{321087956}$	▶ $\frac{2}{163795840} = \frac{4}{327591680} = \frac{6}{491387520}$
▶ $\frac{2}{159637840} = \frac{4}{319275680} = \frac{6}{478913520}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160579834} = \frac{3}{240869751} = \frac{6}{481739502}$	▶ $\frac{2}{163798054} = \frac{3}{245697081} = \frac{4}{327596108}$
▶ $\frac{2}{159760438} = \frac{4}{319520876} = \frac{8}{639041752}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160597834} = \frac{3}{240896751} = \frac{6}{481793502}$	▶ $\frac{2}{163857940} = \frac{3}{245786910} = \frac{6}{491573820}$
▶ $\frac{2}{159783604} = \frac{4}{319567208} = \frac{6}{479350812}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160753948} = \frac{4}{321507896} = \frac{8}{643015792}$	▶ $\frac{2}{163945780} = \frac{3}{245918670} = \frac{4}{327891560}$
▶ $\frac{2}{159784036} = \frac{4}{319568072} = \frac{6}{479352108}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160754398} = \frac{4}{321508796} = \frac{8}{643017592}$	▶ $\frac{2}{163957840} = \frac{4}{327915680} = \frac{6}{491873520}$
▶ $\frac{2}{159786034} = \frac{4}{319572068} = \frac{6}{479358102}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160754893} = \frac{4}{321509786} = \frac{8}{643019572}$	▶ $\frac{2}{163978054} = \frac{3}{245967081} = \frac{4}{327956108}$
▶ $\frac{2}{159786430} = \frac{4}{319572860} = \frac{8}{639145720}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160754938} = \frac{4}{321509876} = \frac{8}{643019752}$	▶ $\frac{2}{164307985} = \frac{4}{328615970} = \frac{8}{657231940}$
▶ $\frac{2}{159804376} = \frac{4}{319608752} = \frac{8}{639217504}$	▶ $\frac{2}{160875493} = \frac{4}{321750986} = \frac{8}{643501972}$	▶ $\frac{2}{164309785} = \frac{4}{328619570} = \frac{8}{657239140}$

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|---|---|---|
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164350798} = \frac{4}{328701596} = \frac{8}{657403192}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{174596380} = \frac{3}{261894570} = \frac{6}{523789140}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175946380} = \frac{4}{351892760} = \frac{6}{527839140}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164350978} = \frac{4}{328701956} = \frac{8}{657403912}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{174598036} = \frac{3}{261897054} = \frac{6}{523794108}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175964380} = \frac{4}{351928760} = \frac{6}{527893140}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164357980} = \frac{4}{328715960} = \frac{8}{657431920}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175308649} = \frac{4}{350617298} = \frac{8}{701234596}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175980364} = \frac{4}{351960728} = \frac{8}{703921456}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164359780} = \frac{4}{328719560} = \frac{8}{657439120}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175309864} = \frac{4}{350619728} = \frac{8}{701239456}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175980436} = \frac{4}{351960872} = \frac{6}{527941308}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164780935} = \frac{4}{329561870} = \frac{8}{659123740}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175348906} = \frac{4}{350697812} = \frac{8}{701395624}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175986304} = \frac{4}{351972608} = \frac{8}{703945216}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164785093} = \frac{4}{329570186} = \frac{8}{659140372}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175364098} = \frac{4}{350728196} = \frac{8}{701456392}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175986403} = \frac{4}{351972806} = \frac{8}{703945612}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164785930} = \frac{4}{329571860} = \frac{8}{659143720}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175364809} = \frac{4}{350729618} = \frac{8}{701459236}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176034598} = \frac{3}{264051897} = \frac{6}{528103794}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164793085} = \frac{4}{329586170} = \frac{8}{659172340}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175364908} = \frac{4}{350729816} = \frac{8}{701459632}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176039458} = \frac{3}{264059187} = \frac{4}{352078916}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164793508} = \frac{4}{329587016} = \frac{8}{659174032}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175384906} = \frac{4}{350769812} = \frac{8}{701539624}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176043598} = \frac{4}{352087196} = \frac{6}{528130794}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164793580} = \frac{4}{329587160} = \frac{8}{659174320}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175398406} = \frac{4}{350796812} = \frac{8}{701593624}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176053489} = \frac{4}{352106978} = \frac{8}{704213956}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164807935} = \frac{4}{329615870} = \frac{8}{659231740}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175409863} = \frac{4}{350819726} = \frac{8}{701639452}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176053849} = \frac{4}{352107698} = \frac{8}{704215396}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164850793} = \frac{4}{329701586} = \frac{8}{659403172}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175483906} = \frac{4}{350967812} = \frac{8}{701935624}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176053984} = \frac{4}{352107968} = \frac{8}{704215936}$ |
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| ▶ $\frac{2}{164930785} = \frac{4}{329861570} = \frac{8}{659723140}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175490863} = \frac{4}{350981726} = \frac{8}{701963452}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176054839} = \frac{4}{352109678} = \frac{8}{704219356}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{164935078} = \frac{4}{329870156} = \frac{8}{659740312}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175603489} = \frac{4}{351206978} = \frac{8}{702413956}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176304859} = \frac{4}{352609718} = \frac{8}{705219436}$ |
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| ▶ $\frac{2}{165837940} = \frac{3}{248756910} = \frac{6}{497513820}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175604839} = \frac{4}{351209678} = \frac{8}{702419356}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176354098} = \frac{4}{352708196} = \frac{8}{705416392}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{167309458} = \frac{3}{250964187} = \frac{6}{501928374}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175803649} = \frac{4}{351607298} = \frac{8}{703214596}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176354809} = \frac{4}{352709618} = \frac{8}{705419236}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{170934658} = \frac{3}{256401987} = \frac{6}{512803974}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175863049} = \frac{4}{351726098} = \frac{8}{703452196}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176354908} = \frac{4}{352709816} = \frac{8}{705419632}$ |
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| ▶ $\frac{2}{174360598} = \frac{3}{261540897} = \frac{6}{523081794}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175903648} = \frac{4}{351807296} = \frac{8}{703614592}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176359048} = \frac{4}{352718096} = \frac{8}{705436192}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{174396580} = \frac{3}{261594870} = \frac{6}{523189740}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{175904863} = \frac{4}{351809726} = \frac{8}{703619452}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{176359804} = \frac{4}{352719608} = \frac{8}{705439216}$ |

$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{176398054} = \frac{3}{264597081} = \frac{4}{352796108}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{178563490} = \frac{4}{357126980} = \frac{8}{714253960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{179836054} = \frac{3}{269754081} = \frac{4}{359672108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{176403598} = \frac{4}{352807196} = \frac{8}{705614392}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{178596034} = \frac{3}{267894051} = \frac{4}{357192068}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{179836405} = \frac{4}{359672810} = \frac{8}{719345620}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{176409853} = \frac{4}{352819706} = \frac{8}{705639412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{178596340} = \frac{3}{267894510} = \frac{4}{357192680}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{179840635} = \frac{4}{359681270} = \frac{8}{719362540}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{176480359} = \frac{4}{352960718} = \frac{8}{705921436}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{179063485} = \frac{4}{358126970} = \frac{8}{716253940}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{179863405} = \frac{4}{359726810} = \frac{8}{719453620}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{176485903} = \frac{4}{352971806} = \frac{8}{705943612}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{179403658} = \frac{3}{269105487} = \frac{6}{538210974}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{180357649} = \frac{4}{360715298} = \frac{8}{721430596}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{176490358} = \frac{4}{352980716} = \frac{8}{705961432}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{179453608} = \frac{4}{358907216} = \frac{9}{807541236}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{180357964} = \frac{4}{360715928} = \frac{6}{541073892}$
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- ▶ $\frac{2}{180976354} = \frac{4}{361952708} = \frac{8}{723905416}$
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| ▶ $\frac{2}{190764853} = \frac{4}{381529706} = \frac{8}{763059412}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{196054378} = \frac{3}{294081567} = \frac{4}{392108756}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197630854} = \frac{4}{395261708} = \frac{8}{790523416}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{190854763} = \frac{4}{381709526} = \frac{8}{763419052}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{196340578} = \frac{3}{294510867} = \frac{6}{589021734}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197635408} = \frac{4}{395270816} = \frac{8}{790541632}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{190864753} = \frac{4}{381729506} = \frac{8}{763459012}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{196357804} = \frac{4}{392715608} = \frac{6}{589073412}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197635804} = \frac{4}{395271608} = \frac{8}{790543216}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{193054876} = \frac{4}{386109752} = \frac{5}{482637190}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{196374580} = \frac{3}{294561870} = \frac{6}{589123740}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197638054} = \frac{3}{296457081} = \frac{4}{395276108}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{193085476} = \frac{4}{386170952} = \frac{5}{482713690}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{196378054} = \frac{3}{294567081} = \frac{4}{392756108}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197640358} = \frac{4}{395280716} = \frac{8}{790561432}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{193450876} = \frac{4}{386901752} = \frac{5}{483627190}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{196403578} = \frac{4}{392807156} = \frac{6}{589210734}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197640853} = \frac{4}{395281706} = \frac{8}{790563412}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{193485076} = \frac{4}{386970152} = \frac{5}{483712690}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{196437580} = \frac{4}{392875160} = \frac{6}{589312740}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197805436} = \frac{3}{296708154} = \frac{4}{395610872}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{193507648} = \frac{4}{387015296} = \frac{5}{483769120}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{196574380} = \frac{3}{294861570} = \frac{6}{589723140}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197835064} = \frac{4}{395670128} = \frac{8}{791340256}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{193764580} = \frac{4}{387529160} = \frac{6}{581293740}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{196578034} = \frac{3}{294867051} = \frac{6}{589734102}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197835640} = \frac{4}{395671280} = \frac{8}{791342560}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194036578} = \frac{3}{291054867} = \frac{6}{582109734}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197436058} = \frac{3}{296154087} = \frac{6}{592308174}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197836054} = \frac{3}{296754081} = \frac{4}{395672108}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194376580} = \frac{3}{291564870} = \frac{6}{583129740}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197458036} = \frac{3}{296187054} = \frac{6}{592374108}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197836405} = \frac{4}{395672810} = \frac{8}{791345620}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194530876} = \frac{4}{389061752} = \frac{5}{486327190}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197536408} = \frac{4}{395072816} = \frac{8}{790145632}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197840635} = \frac{4}{395681270} = \frac{8}{791362540}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194560378} = \frac{3}{291840567} = \frac{4}{389120756}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197538406} = \frac{4}{395076812} = \frac{8}{790153624}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197850634} = \frac{4}{395701268} = \frac{8}{791402536}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194563780} = \frac{3}{291845670} = \frac{4}{389127560}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197540863} = \frac{4}{395081726} = \frac{8}{790163452}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197856034} = \frac{3}{296784051} = \frac{4}{395712068}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194576038} = \frac{3}{291864057} = \frac{4}{389152076}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197560384} = \frac{4}{395120768} = \frac{8}{790241536}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197863405} = \frac{4}{395726810} = \frac{8}{791453620}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194578036} = \frac{3}{291867054} = \frac{4}{389156072}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197580364} = \frac{4}{395160728} = \frac{8}{790321456}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{198034576} = \frac{3}{297051864} = \frac{6}{594103728}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194578360} = \frac{3}{291867540} = \frac{4}{389156720}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197580436} = \frac{4}{395160872} = \frac{6}{592741308}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{198035764} = \frac{4}{396071528} = \frac{8}{792143056}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194580376} = \frac{3}{291870564} = \frac{4}{389160752}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197586304} = \frac{4}{395172608} = \frac{8}{790345216}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{198043576} = \frac{4}{396087152} = \frac{6}{594130728}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194583760} = \frac{3}{291875640} = \frac{4}{389167520}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197586403} = \frac{4}{395172806} = \frac{8}{790345612}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{198054376} = \frac{3}{297081564} = \frac{4}{396108752}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194637580} = \frac{4}{389275160} = \frac{6}{583912740}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197603458} = \frac{3}{296405187} = \frac{6}{592810374}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{198057436} = \frac{3}{297086154} = \frac{6}{594172308}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{194853076} = \frac{4}{389706152} = \frac{5}{487132690}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197604358} = \frac{4}{395208716} = \frac{6}{592813074}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{198075364} = \frac{4}{396150728} = \frac{8}{792301456}$ |
| ▶ $\frac{2}{195764380} = \frac{4}{391528760} = \frac{6}{587293140}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{197605384} = \frac{4}{395210768} = \frac{8}{790421536}$ | ▶ $\frac{2}{198076354} = \frac{4}{396152708} = \frac{8}{792305416}$ |

$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198375406} = \frac{4}{396750812} = \frac{8}{793501624}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{340179856} = \frac{3}{510269784} = \frac{4}{680359712}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{376019458} = \frac{3}{564029187} = \frac{4}{752038916}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198375604} = \frac{4}{396751208} = \frac{8}{793502416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{340185796} = \frac{3}{510278694} = \frac{4}{680371592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{376054198} = \frac{3}{564081297} = \frac{4}{752108396}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198403756} = \frac{4}{396807512} = \frac{8}{793615024}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{340185976} = \frac{3}{510278964} = \frac{4}{680371952}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{376194580} = \frac{3}{564291870} = \frac{4}{752389160}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198405376} = \frac{4}{396810752} = \frac{8}{793621504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{340197856} = \frac{3}{510296784} = \frac{4}{680395712}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{376198054} = \frac{3}{564297081} = \frac{4}{752396108}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198530764} = \frac{4}{397061528} = \frac{8}{794123056}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{340198576} = \frac{3}{510297864} = \frac{4}{680397152}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{376598014} = \frac{3}{564897021} = \frac{4}{753196028}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198540763} = \frac{4}{397081526} = \frac{8}{794163052}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{341785960} = \frac{3}{512678940} = \frac{4}{683571920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{376598140} = \frac{3}{564897210} = \frac{4}{753196280}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198576034} = \frac{3}{297864051} = \frac{4}{397152068}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{341798560} = \frac{3}{512697840} = \frac{4}{683597120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{378019456} = \frac{3}{567029184} = \frac{4}{756038912}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198576304} = \frac{4}{397152608} = \frac{8}{794305216}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{341857960} = \frac{3}{512786940} = \frac{4}{683715920}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{378054196} = \frac{3}{567081294} = \frac{4}{756108392}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198576340} = \frac{3}{297864510} = \frac{4}{397152680}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{341859760} = \frac{3}{512789640} = \frac{4}{683719520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{378194560} = \frac{3}{567291840} = \frac{4}{756389120}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{198630754} = \frac{4}{397261508} = \frac{8}{794523016}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{341985760} = \frac{3}{512978640} = \frac{4}{683971520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{379456018} = \frac{3}{569184027} = \frac{4}{758912036}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{317680594} = \frac{3}{476520891} = \frac{6}{953041782}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{361945780} = \frac{3}{542918670} = \frac{4}{723891560}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2}{379658140} = \frac{3}{569487210} = \frac{4}{759316280}$
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- ▶ $\frac{2}{380541976} = \frac{3}{570812964} = \frac{4}{761083952}$
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- ▶ $\frac{3}{102456789} = \frac{6}{204913578} = \frac{7}{239065841}$
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$\triangleright \frac{3}{127468905} = \frac{6}{254937810} = \frac{9}{382406715}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{145267089} = \frac{6}{290534178} = \frac{9}{435801267}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{192854760} = \frac{4}{257139680} = \frac{8}{514279360}$
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$\triangleright \frac{3}{128546709} = \frac{6}{257093418} = \frac{9}{385640127}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{145268907} = \frac{6}{290537814} = \frac{9}{435806721}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{194785206} = \frac{4}{259713608} = \frac{6}{389570412}$
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$\triangleright \frac{3}{128547069} = \frac{6}{257094138} = \frac{9}{385641207}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{145270689} = \frac{6}{290541378} = \frac{9}{435812067}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{210786945} = \frac{6}{421573890} = \frac{7}{491836205}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{128549067} = \frac{6}{257098134} = \frac{9}{385647201}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{145270869} = \frac{6}{290541738} = \frac{9}{435812607}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{250689471} = \frac{6}{501378942} = \frac{9}{752068413}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{128674905} = \frac{6}{257349810} = \frac{9}{386024715}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{145286709} = \frac{6}{290573418} = \frac{9}{435860127}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{250694871} = \frac{6}{501389742} = \frac{9}{752084613}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{128746905} = \frac{6}{257493810} = \frac{9}{386240715}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{145286907} = \frac{6}{290573814} = \frac{9}{435860721}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{250869471} = \frac{6}{501738942} = \frac{9}{752608413}$
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$\triangleright \frac{3}{129085467} = \frac{6}{258170934} = \frac{9}{387256401}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{145289067} = \frac{6}{290578134} = \frac{9}{435867201}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{250946871} = \frac{6}{501893742} = \frac{9}{752840613}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{140526789} = \frac{4}{187369052} = \frac{9}{421580367}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{145290687} = \frac{6}{290581374} = \frac{9}{435872061}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{250948671} = \frac{6}{501897342} = \frac{9}{752846013}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145067289} = \frac{6}{290134578} = \frac{9}{435201867}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{145290867} = \frac{6}{290581734} = \frac{9}{435872601}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{251068947} = \frac{6}{502137894} = \frac{9}{753206841}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145068729} = \frac{6}{290137458} = \frac{9}{435206187}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{156402897} = \frac{4}{208537196} = \frac{6}{312805794}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{251069487} = \frac{6}{502138974} = \frac{9}{753208461}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145068927} = \frac{6}{290137854} = \frac{9}{435206781}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{157904826} = \frac{4}{210539768} = \frac{8}{421079536}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{251086947} = \frac{6}{502173894} = \frac{9}{753260841}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145069287} = \frac{6}{290138574} = \frac{9}{435207861}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{158902746} = \frac{5}{264837910} = \frac{6}{317805492}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{251089467} = \frac{6}{502178934} = \frac{9}{753268401}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145072689} = \frac{6}{290145378} = \frac{9}{435218067}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{169458072} = \frac{7}{395402168} = \frac{9}{508374216}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{251094687} = \frac{6}{502189374} = \frac{9}{753284061}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145072869} = \frac{6}{290145738} = \frac{9}{435218607}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{170258946} = \frac{5}{283764910} = \frac{6}{340517892}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{251094867} = \frac{6}{502189734} = \frac{9}{753284601}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145086729} = \frac{6}{290173458} = \frac{9}{435260187}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{174890256} = \frac{5}{291483760} = \frac{6}{349780512}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{261570489} = \frac{6}{523140978} = \frac{8}{697521304}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145086927} = \frac{6}{290173854} = \frac{9}{435260781}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{176089245} = \frac{6}{352178490} = \frac{8}{469571320}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{267085491} = \frac{6}{534170982} = \frac{9}{801256473}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145087269} = \frac{6}{290174538} = \frac{9}{435261807}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{179204586} = \frac{5}{298674310} = \frac{6}{358409172}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{267089145} = \frac{6}{534178290} = \frac{9}{801267435}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145089267} = \frac{6}{290178534} = \frac{9}{435267801}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{187640952} = \frac{4}{250187936} = \frac{6}{375281904}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{267108549} = \frac{6}{534217098} = \frac{9}{801325647}$
$\triangleright \frac{3}{145092687} = \frac{6}{290185374} = \frac{9}{435278061}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{187649052} = \frac{4}{250198736} = \frac{6}{375298104}$	$\triangleright \frac{3}{267145089} = \frac{6}{534290178} = \frac{9}{801435267}$

- ▶ $\frac{3}{267489051} = \frac{6}{534978102} = \frac{9}{802467153}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{267489105} = \frac{6}{534978210} = \frac{9}{802467315}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268547091} = \frac{6}{537094182} = \frac{9}{805641273}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268547109} = \frac{6}{537094218} = \frac{9}{805641327}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268549071} = \frac{6}{537098142} = \frac{9}{805647213}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268549107} = \frac{6}{537098214} = \frac{9}{805647321}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268709145} = \frac{6}{537418290} = \frac{9}{806127435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268714509} = \frac{6}{537429018} = \frac{9}{806143527}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268749051} = \frac{6}{537498102} = \frac{9}{806247153}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268749105} = \frac{6}{537498210} = \frac{9}{806247315}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268907145} = \frac{6}{537814290} = \frac{9}{806721435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{268914507} = \frac{6}{537829014} = \frac{9}{806743521}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{269085471} = \frac{6}{538170942} = \frac{9}{807256413}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{269087145} = \frac{6}{538174290} = \frac{9}{807261435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{269108547} = \frac{6}{538217094} = \frac{9}{807325641}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{269145087} = \frac{6}{538290174} = \frac{9}{807435261}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{270598614} = \frac{4}{360798152} = \frac{8}{721596304}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{270685491} = \frac{6}{541370982} = \frac{9}{812056473}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{270689145} = \frac{6}{541378290} = \frac{9}{812067435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{270854691} = \frac{6}{541709382} = \frac{9}{812564073}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{270869145} = \frac{6}{541738290} = \frac{9}{812607435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{271068549} = \frac{6}{542137098} = \frac{9}{813205647}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{271085469} = \frac{6}{542170938} = \frac{9}{813256407}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{271450689} = \frac{6}{542901378} = \frac{9}{814352067}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{271450869} = \frac{6}{542901738} = \frac{9}{814352607}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{274689051} = \frac{6}{549378102} = \frac{9}{824067153}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{274689105} = \frac{6}{549378210} = \frac{9}{824067315}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{274869051} = \frac{6}{549738102} = \frac{9}{824607153}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{274869105} = \frac{6}{549738210} = \frac{9}{824607315}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{274869105} = \frac{6}{549738210} = \frac{9}{824607315}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{274869105} = \frac{6}{549738210} = \frac{9}{824607315}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{285467091} = \frac{6}{570934182} = \frac{9}{856401273}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{285467109} = \frac{6}{570934218} = \frac{9}{856401327}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{285469071} = \frac{6}{570938142} = \frac{9}{856407213}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{285469107} = \frac{6}{570938214} = \frac{9}{856407321}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{285470691} = \frac{6}{570941382} = \frac{9}{856412073}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{285471069} = \frac{6}{570942138} = \frac{9}{856413207}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{285490671} = \frac{6}{570981342} = \frac{9}{856472013}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{285491067} = \frac{6}{570982134} = \frac{9}{856473201}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286140597} = \frac{4}{381520796} = \frac{8}{763041592}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286194570} = \frac{4}{381592760} = \frac{6}{572389140}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286197054} = \frac{4}{381596072} = \frac{6}{572394108}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286549107} = \frac{6}{573098214} = \frac{8}{764130952}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286709145} = \frac{6}{573418290} = \frac{9}{860127435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286714509} = \frac{6}{573429018} = \frac{9}{860143527}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286749051} = \frac{6}{573498102} = \frac{9}{860247153}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286749105} = \frac{6}{573498210} = \frac{9}{860247315}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286907145} = \frac{6}{573814290} = \frac{9}{860721435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{286914507} = \frac{6}{573829014} = \frac{9}{860743521}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{287069145} = \frac{6}{574138290} = \frac{9}{861207435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{287145069} = \frac{6}{574290138} = \frac{9}{861435207}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{287469051} = \frac{6}{574938102} = \frac{9}{862407153}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{287469105} = \frac{6}{574938210} = \frac{9}{862407315}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{289067145} = \frac{6}{578134290} = \frac{9}{867201435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{289145067} = \frac{6}{578290134} = \frac{9}{867435201}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{290685471} = \frac{6}{581370942} = \frac{9}{872056413}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{290687145} = \frac{6}{581374290} = \frac{9}{872061435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{290854671} = \frac{6}{581709342} = \frac{9}{872564013}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{290867145} = \frac{6}{581734290} = \frac{9}{872601435}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{291068547} = \frac{6}{582137094} = \frac{9}{873205641}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{291085467} = \frac{6}{582170934} = \frac{9}{873256401}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{291450687} = \frac{6}{582901374} = \frac{9}{874352061}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{291450867} = \frac{6}{582901734} = \frac{9}{874352601}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{294586170} = \frac{4}{392781560} = \frac{6}{589172340}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{297058614} = \frac{4}{396078152} = \frac{8}{792156304}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{298614057} = \frac{4}{398152076} = \frac{8}{796304152}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{298617054} = \frac{4}{398156072} = \frac{6}{597234108}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{402897156} = \frac{4}{537196208} = \frac{6}{805794312}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{428957016} = \frac{5}{714928360} = \frac{6}{857914032}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{457018629} = \frac{4}{609358172} = \frac{6}{914037258}$
- ▶ $\frac{3}{457186029} = \frac{4}{609581372} = \frac{6}{914372058}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{460185729} = \frac{4}{613580972} = \frac{6}{920371458}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{163780952} = \frac{8}{327561904} = \frac{9}{368507142}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{239580176} = \frac{7}{419265308} = \frac{8}{479160352}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{461857029} = \frac{4}{615809372} = \frac{6}{923714058}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{172609538} = \frac{6}{258914307} = \frac{8}{345219076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{253719608} = \frac{6}{380579412} = \frac{8}{507439216}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{476185092} = \frac{5}{793641820} = \frac{6}{952370184}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{173805296} = \frac{7}{304159268} = \frac{8}{347610592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{253971608} = \frac{6}{380957412} = \frac{8}{507943216}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3}{490761852} = \frac{5}{817936420} = \frac{6}{981523704}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{176235980} = \frac{7}{308412965} = \frac{8}{352471960}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{290315768} = \frac{5}{362894710} = \frac{9}{653210478}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{102957368} = \frac{8}{205914736} = \frac{9}{231654078}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{176239580} = \frac{7}{308419265} = \frac{8}{352479160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{328957016} = \frac{8}{657914032} = \frac{9}{740153286}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{136579820} = \frac{7}{239014685} = \frac{8}{273159640}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{180537296} = \frac{7}{315940268} = \frac{8}{361074592}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{378095216} = \frac{8}{756190432} = \frac{9}{850714236}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{136597820} = \frac{7}{239046185} = \frac{8}{273195640}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{180953726} = \frac{6}{271430589} = \frac{8}{361907452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{378096152} = \frac{8}{756192304} = \frac{9}{850716342}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{152378096} = \frac{8}{304756192} = \frac{9}{342850716}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{195823760} = \frac{7}{342691580} = \frac{8}{391647520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{397102568} = \frac{5}{496378210} = \frac{8}{794205136}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{153726098} = \frac{6}{230589147} = \frac{8}{307452196}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{198235760} = \frac{7}{346912580} = \frac{8}{396471520}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{536091728} = \frac{6}{804137592} = \frac{7}{938160524}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{153809726} = \frac{6}{230714589} = \frac{8}{307619452}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{231570968} = \frac{5}{289463710} = \frac{9}{521034678}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{7}{134286509} = \frac{8}{153470296} = \frac{9}{172654083}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{158703296} = \frac{8}{317406592} = \frac{9}{357082416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{231785096} = \frac{7}{405623918} = \frac{8}{463570192}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{163087952} = \frac{7}{285403916} = \frac{8}{326175904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4}{235980176} = \frac{7}{412965308} = \frac{8}{471960352}$	

2.25 2 Equivalent Expressions

In this case, we have more than 300.000 possibilities to write pandigital equivalent fractions of 2 expressions. We have selected below only few. There are with 4 and 5 digits numerators starting from 5 onwards. These are around 3971 values.

• 5-Digits Numerator

$\blacktriangleright \frac{50127}{83496} = \frac{52173}{86904}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50192}{73468} = \frac{62740}{91835}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50328}{67149} = \frac{67104}{89532}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50439}{82671} = \frac{57362}{94018}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{50142}{67893} = \frac{63294}{85701}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50271}{64389} = \frac{65739}{84201}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50348}{69712} = \frac{62935}{87140}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50439}{87261} = \frac{52417}{90683}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{50143}{78269} = \frac{58704}{91632}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50296}{73148} = \frac{62870}{91435}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50348}{76219} = \frac{54032}{81796}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50463}{71289} = \frac{63504}{89712}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{50182}{73964} = \frac{59306}{87412}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50314}{69278} = \frac{61749}{85023}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50349}{67128} = \frac{67132}{89504}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50482}{79163} = \frac{61048}{95732}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{50183}{79462} = \frac{53179}{84206}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50314}{89672} = \frac{52601}{93748}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50349}{71286} = \frac{67132}{95048}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50496}{71328} = \frac{67328}{95104}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{50184}{67932} = \frac{62730}{84915}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50317}{82946} = \frac{54072}{89136}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50394}{67821} = \frac{70824}{95316}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{50691}{72834} = \frac{56231}{80794}$

▶ $\frac{50894}{61372} = \frac{76341}{92058}$	▶ $\frac{51837}{69042} = \frac{72385}{96410}$	▶ $\frac{52863}{70149} = \frac{53126}{70498}$	▶ $\frac{53280}{71946} = \frac{65120}{87934}$
▶ $\frac{50897}{62134} = \frac{75614}{92308}$	▶ $\frac{51870}{64239} = \frac{59280}{73416}$	▶ $\frac{52864}{71390} = \frac{73024}{98615}$	▶ $\frac{53298}{64071} = \frac{65142}{78309}$
▶ $\frac{50917}{63248} = \frac{75081}{93264}$	▶ $\frac{51903}{86724} = \frac{58302}{97416}$	▶ $\frac{52893}{61047} = \frac{70524}{81396}$	▶ $\frac{53298}{67014} = \frac{71064}{89352}$
▶ $\frac{51072}{69384} = \frac{51984}{70623}$	▶ $\frac{51920}{76384} = \frac{57230}{84196}$	▶ $\frac{52931}{64780} = \frac{69714}{85320}$	▶ $\frac{53298}{70146} = \frac{71064}{93528}$
▶ $\frac{51093}{62874} = \frac{51904}{63872}$	▶ $\frac{51947}{62083} = \frac{70561}{84329}$	▶ $\frac{52984}{73016} = \frac{59607}{82143}$	▶ $\frac{53412}{76890} = \frac{62314}{89705}$
▶ $\frac{51096}{74832} = \frac{59612}{87304}$	▶ $\frac{51948}{63270} = \frac{75816}{92340}$	▶ $\frac{52986}{70134} = \frac{70648}{93512}$	▶ $\frac{53416}{80729} = \frac{63128}{95407}$
▶ $\frac{51296}{70348} = \frac{64120}{87935}$	▶ $\frac{52104}{78936} = \frac{54609}{82731}$	▶ $\frac{53016}{72984} = \frac{59643}{82107}$	▶ $\frac{53417}{68092} = \frac{56329}{71804}$
▶ $\frac{51304}{87692} = \frac{54802}{93671}$	▶ $\frac{52173}{60984} = \frac{76415}{89320}$	▶ $\frac{53018}{67942} = \frac{64379}{82501}$	▶ $\frac{53478}{62910} = \frac{80217}{94365}$
▶ $\frac{51308}{74296} = \frac{64135}{92870}$	▶ $\frac{52193}{68470} = \frac{64923}{85170}$	▶ $\frac{53086}{72941} = \frac{67310}{92485}$	▶ $\frac{53478}{69210} = \frac{62391}{80745}$
▶ $\frac{51328}{70496} = \frac{60952}{83714}$	▶ $\frac{52319}{74806} = \frac{64357}{92018}$	▶ $\frac{53092}{68471} = \frac{73512}{94806}$	▶ $\frac{53481}{70692} = \frac{71308}{94256}$
▶ $\frac{51342}{78690} = \frac{56914}{87230}$	▶ $\frac{52374}{96180} = \frac{53621}{98470}$	▶ $\frac{53109}{84672} = \frac{60134}{95872}$	▶ $\frac{53497}{82106} = \frac{60513}{92874}$
▶ $\frac{51423}{78690} = \frac{61258}{93740}$	▶ $\frac{52403}{67918} = \frac{63245}{81970}$	▶ $\frac{53128}{79460} = \frac{61830}{92475}$	▶ $\frac{53679}{80214} = \frac{56147}{83902}$
▶ $\frac{51428}{73096} = \frac{64285}{91370}$	▶ $\frac{52460}{89731} = \frac{54180}{92673}$	▶ $\frac{53148}{67209} = \frac{58092}{73461}$	▶ $\frac{53690}{87412} = \frac{57820}{94136}$
▶ $\frac{51432}{69708} = \frac{64290}{87135}$	▶ $\frac{52461}{78039} = \frac{56079}{83421}$	▶ $\frac{53169}{87024} = \frac{56043}{91728}$	▶ $\frac{53708}{62914} = \frac{80562}{94371}$
▶ $\frac{51460}{73289} = \frac{53940}{76821}$	▶ $\frac{52461}{78390} = \frac{61857}{92430}$	▶ $\frac{53172}{90684} = \frac{57603}{98241}$	▶ $\frac{53714}{62908} = \frac{80571}{94362}$
▶ $\frac{51496}{73028} = \frac{64370}{91285}$	▶ $\frac{52481}{69730} = \frac{72358}{96140}$	▶ $\frac{53184}{67920} = \frac{59832}{76410}$	▶ $\frac{53721}{60489} = \frac{64389}{72501}$
▶ $\frac{51649}{70382} = \frac{67541}{92038}$	▶ $\frac{52614}{70398} = \frac{70152}{93864}$	▶ $\frac{53184}{69072} = \frac{65372}{84901}$	▶ $\frac{53746}{89012} = \frac{58632}{97104}$
▶ $\frac{51723}{89460} = \frac{54186}{93720}$	▶ $\frac{52781}{64390} = \frac{58396}{71240}$	▶ $\frac{53192}{67840} = \frac{59841}{76320}$	▶ $\frac{53912}{67804} = \frac{58014}{72963}$
▶ $\frac{51807}{64239} = \frac{59208}{73416}$	▶ $\frac{52839}{61047} = \frac{70452}{81396}$	▶ $\frac{53271}{64098} = \frac{65109}{78342}$	▶ $\frac{53928}{64170} = \frac{65912}{78430}$

▶ $\frac{53928}{67140} = \frac{67410}{83925}$	▶ $\frac{54102}{67938} = \frac{72136}{90584}$	▶ $\frac{54782}{91630} = \frac{58136}{97240}$	▶ $\frac{56493}{72081} = \frac{75324}{96108}$
▶ $\frac{53940}{67128} = \frac{67425}{83910}$	▶ $\frac{54126}{73098} = \frac{59364}{80172}$	▶ $\frac{54831}{70692} = \frac{73108}{94256}$	▶ $\frac{56704}{89312} = \frac{58476}{92103}$
▶ $\frac{53940}{72168} = \frac{63510}{84972}$	▶ $\frac{54126}{78930} = \frac{63147}{92085}$	▶ $\frac{54861}{72039} = \frac{73148}{96052}$	▶ $\frac{56712}{93840} = \frac{58241}{96370}$
▶ $\frac{53946}{71280} = \frac{65934}{87120}$	▶ $\frac{54138}{67902} = \frac{72184}{90536}$	▶ $\frac{54861}{72390} = \frac{73148}{96520}$	▶ $\frac{56732}{81094} = \frac{63278}{90451}$
▶ $\frac{54018}{73692} = \frac{63021}{85974}$	▶ $\frac{54180}{69237} = \frac{74820}{95613}$	▶ $\frac{54873}{62109} = \frac{71253}{80649}$	▶ $\frac{56814}{70329} = \frac{72410}{89635}$
▶ $\frac{54018}{76932} = \frac{63021}{89754}$	▶ $\frac{54180}{76932} = \frac{63210}{89754}$	▶ $\frac{54902}{67318} = \frac{73014}{89526}$	▶ $\frac{56938}{71204} = \frac{73206}{91548}$
▶ $\frac{54019}{62783} = \frac{69453}{80721}$	▶ $\frac{54180}{79632} = \frac{59340}{87216}$	▶ $\frac{54903}{71862} = \frac{73204}{95816}$	▶ $\frac{57024}{83916} = \frac{59136}{87024}$
▶ $\frac{54019}{67823} = \frac{69453}{87201}$	▶ $\frac{54201}{73689} = \frac{58206}{79134}$	▶ $\frac{54918}{73062} = \frac{64071}{85239}$	▶ $\frac{57032}{69148} = \frac{71290}{86435}$
▶ $\frac{54026}{87193} = \frac{60382}{97451}$	▶ $\frac{54208}{63917} = \frac{61952}{73048}$	▶ $\frac{54928}{73160} = \frac{61794}{82305}$	▶ $\frac{57104}{68392} = \frac{74562}{89301}$
▶ $\frac{54028}{63791} = \frac{70652}{83419}$	▶ $\frac{54208}{76391} = \frac{61952}{87304}$	▶ $\frac{54930}{71862} = \frac{73240}{95816}$	▶ $\frac{57123}{68904} = \frac{67509}{81432}$
▶ $\frac{54028}{69173} = \frac{62340}{79815}$	▶ $\frac{54230}{71896} = \frac{59160}{78432}$	▶ $\frac{54938}{67210} = \frac{59164}{72380}$	▶ $\frac{57134}{62908} = \frac{85701}{94362}$
▶ $\frac{54028}{76193} = \frac{62340}{87915}$	▶ $\frac{54360}{89172} = \frac{57380}{94126}$	▶ $\frac{54981}{63027} = \frac{74169}{85023}$	▶ $\frac{57148}{62309} = \frac{83524}{91067}$
▶ $\frac{54029}{67318} = \frac{73524}{91608}$	▶ $\frac{54378}{60192} = \frac{64395}{71280}$	▶ $\frac{56018}{73429} = \frac{60384}{79152}$	▶ $\frac{57148}{69032} = \frac{71435}{86290}$
▶ $\frac{54029}{71683} = \frac{62941}{83507}$	▶ $\frac{54397}{81206} = \frac{60123}{89754}$	▶ $\frac{56120}{78934} = \frac{65320}{91874}$	▶ $\frac{57183}{64092} = \frac{72354}{81096}$
▶ $\frac{54082}{63791} = \frac{69534}{82017}$	▶ $\frac{54612}{78930} = \frac{63714}{92085}$	▶ $\frac{56192}{73408} = \frac{60582}{79143}$	▶ $\frac{57192}{68304} = \frac{69107}{82534}$
▶ $\frac{54093}{62871} = \frac{83512}{97064}$	▶ $\frac{54621}{83079} = \frac{61047}{92853}$	▶ $\frac{56481}{72093} = \frac{75308}{96124}$	▶ $\frac{57213}{68904} = \frac{74165}{89320}$
▶ $\frac{54093}{68172} = \frac{65043}{81972}$	▶ $\frac{54738}{62910} = \frac{82107}{94365}$	▶ $\frac{56481}{72309} = \frac{75308}{96412}$	▶ $\frac{57321}{64908} = \frac{80674}{91352}$
▶ $\frac{54093}{72618} = \frac{62415}{83790}$	▶ $\frac{54739}{61028} = \frac{74906}{83512}$	▶ $\frac{56490}{72138} = \frac{75320}{96184}$	▶ $\frac{57348}{92016} = \frac{60534}{97128}$
▶ $\frac{54093}{81276} = \frac{62415}{93780}$	▶ $\frac{54780}{63921} = \frac{69720}{81354}$	▶ $\frac{56490}{73812} = \frac{75320}{98416}$	▶ $\frac{57408}{61932} = \frac{85376}{92104}$

▶ $\frac{57426}{81039} = \frac{64182}{90573}$	▶ $\frac{58912}{76304} = \frac{62594}{81073}$	▶ $\frac{59328}{71460} = \frac{74160}{89325}$	▶ $\frac{59840}{63712} = \frac{68510}{72943}$
▶ $\frac{57491}{86023} = \frac{65704}{98312}$	▶ $\frac{58916}{73024} = \frac{73645}{91280}$	▶ $\frac{59406}{73218} = \frac{69307}{85421}$	▶ $\frac{59864}{73012} = \frac{74830}{91265}$
▶ $\frac{57921}{86043} = \frac{64207}{95381}$	▶ $\frac{58927}{64130} = \frac{76459}{83210}$	▶ $\frac{59408}{67132} = \frac{74260}{83915}$	▶ $\frac{59874}{61032} = \frac{69853}{71204}$
▶ $\frac{57981}{60423} = \frac{68523}{71409}$	▶ $\frac{58942}{71630} = \frac{61209}{74385}$	▶ $\frac{59410}{72683} = \frac{73120}{89456}$	▶ $\frac{60129}{85374} = \frac{67203}{95418}$
▶ $\frac{57983}{61042} = \frac{85714}{90236}$	▶ $\frac{59013}{68724} = \frac{71495}{83260}$	▶ $\frac{59413}{70682} = \frac{76532}{91048}$	▶ $\frac{60198}{73452} = \frac{70231}{85694}$
▶ $\frac{58023}{64197} = \frac{74601}{82539}$	▶ $\frac{59024}{81736} = \frac{62930}{87145}$	▶ $\frac{59418}{60732} = \frac{69321}{70854}$	▶ $\frac{60198}{74532} = \frac{70231}{86954}$
▶ $\frac{58023}{76419} = \frac{74601}{98253}$	▶ $\frac{59048}{73216} = \frac{75823}{94016}$	▶ $\frac{59418}{67320} = \frac{69321}{78540}$	▶ $\frac{60354}{72891} = \frac{75682}{91403}$
▶ $\frac{58037}{62419} = \frac{74619}{80253}$	▶ $\frac{59073}{62814} = \frac{75369}{80142}$	▶ $\frac{59418}{73206} = \frac{69321}{85407}$	▶ $\frac{60384}{71592} = \frac{67932}{80541}$
▶ $\frac{58092}{71346} = \frac{60358}{74129}$	▶ $\frac{59103}{62478} = \frac{85371}{90246}$	▶ $\frac{59418}{73260} = \frac{69321}{85470}$	▶ $\frac{60384}{75912} = \frac{67932}{85401}$
▶ $\frac{58104}{67932} = \frac{72630}{84915}$	▶ $\frac{59132}{67408} = \frac{73915}{84260}$	▶ $\frac{59428}{71063} = \frac{81340}{97265}$	▶ $\frac{60392}{71584} = \frac{67941}{80532}$
▶ $\frac{58124}{60973} = \frac{79260}{83145}$	▶ $\frac{59140}{67328} = \frac{73925}{84160}$	▶ $\frac{59460}{71328} = \frac{74325}{89160}$	▶ $\frac{60398}{72514} = \frac{72013}{86459}$
▶ $\frac{58176}{90324} = \frac{63024}{97851}$	▶ $\frac{59178}{62430} = \frac{69041}{72835}$	▶ $\frac{59460}{73218} = \frac{69370}{85421}$	▶ $\frac{60592}{78134} = \frac{64920}{83715}$
▶ $\frac{58194}{76320} = \frac{75213}{98640}$	▶ $\frac{59178}{63024} = \frac{69041}{73528}$	▶ $\frac{59472}{68103} = \frac{64192}{73508}$	▶ $\frac{60594}{73218} = \frac{70693}{85421}$
▶ $\frac{58620}{71493} = \frac{78160}{95324}$	▶ $\frac{5918}{720346} = \frac{7532}{916804}$	▶ $\frac{59602}{87431} = \frac{63108}{92574}$	▶ $\frac{60723}{84591} = \frac{67124}{93508}$
▶ $\frac{58623}{71490} = \frac{78164}{95320}$	▶ $\frac{59203}{74168} = \frac{73801}{92456}$	▶ $\frac{59683}{72410} = \frac{73456}{89120}$	▶ $\frac{60835}{91724} = \frac{63480}{95712}$
▶ $\frac{58640}{73192} = \frac{65970}{82341}$	▶ $\frac{59248}{67130} = \frac{63480}{71925}$	▶ $\frac{59712}{63840} = \frac{69042}{73815}$	▶ $\frac{60927}{83145} = \frac{65342}{89170}$
▶ $\frac{58740}{63921} = \frac{76540}{83291}$	▶ $\frac{59304}{78612} = \frac{74130}{98265}$	▶ $\frac{59814}{73026} = \frac{73106}{89254}$	▶ $\frac{60931}{72485} = \frac{62049}{73815}$
▶ $\frac{58794}{61032} = \frac{68593}{71204}$	▶ $\frac{59328}{67140} = \frac{74160}{83925}$	▶ $\frac{59832}{61074} = \frac{69804}{71253}$	▶ $\frac{61052}{73984} = \frac{76315}{92480}$
▶ $\frac{58912}{73460} = \frac{73640}{91825}$	▶ $\frac{59328}{70416} = \frac{70452}{83619}$	▶ $\frac{59832}{70416} = \frac{70912}{83456}$	▶ $\frac{61230}{75894} = \frac{65940}{81732}$

▶ $\frac{61230}{79548} = \frac{71435}{92806}$	▶ $\frac{61980}{74532} = \frac{72310}{86954}$	▶ $\frac{63258}{79410} = \frac{73801}{92645}$	▶ $\frac{64592}{70831} = \frac{74096}{81253}$
▶ $\frac{61254}{78930} = \frac{71463}{92085}$	▶ $\frac{62153}{74809} = \frac{71032}{85496}$	▶ $\frac{63294}{78501} = \frac{65142}{80793}$	▶ $\frac{64710}{83925} = \frac{70462}{91385}$
▶ $\frac{61275}{84930} = \frac{63425}{87910}$	▶ $\frac{62190}{78345} = \frac{71864}{90532}$	▶ $\frac{63410}{87295} = \frac{70124}{96538}$	▶ $\frac{64790}{81235} = \frac{69502}{87143}$
▶ $\frac{61295}{87043} = \frac{65780}{93412}$	▶ $\frac{62370}{84159} = \frac{68530}{92471}$	▶ $\frac{63450}{71928} = \frac{74025}{83916}$	▶ $\frac{64801}{75293} = \frac{78364}{91052}$
▶ $\frac{61340}{79285} = \frac{73608}{95142}$	▶ $\frac{62419}{75803} = \frac{80253}{97461}$	▶ $\frac{63480}{72519} = \frac{83720}{95641}$	▶ $\frac{64812}{79530} = \frac{74632}{91580}$
▶ $\frac{61358}{79420} = \frac{72514}{93860}$	▶ $\frac{62419}{80735} = \frac{62937}{81405}$	▶ $\frac{63491}{75082} = \frac{71932}{85064}$	▶ $\frac{65028}{71349} = \frac{86704}{95132}$
▶ $\frac{61374}{80295} = \frac{70638}{92415}$	▶ $\frac{62481}{70953} = \frac{85432}{97016}$	▶ $\frac{63492}{70158} = \frac{75036}{82914}$	▶ $\frac{65042}{71893} = \frac{72694}{80351}$
▶ $\frac{61490}{72358} = \frac{81270}{95634}$	▶ $\frac{62490}{71538} = \frac{72905}{83461}$	▶ $\frac{63497}{82015} = \frac{71603}{92485}$	▶ $\frac{65049}{71328} = \frac{86732}{95104}$
▶ $\frac{61523}{74809} = \frac{70312}{85496}$	▶ $\frac{62510}{73948} = \frac{67915}{80342}$	▶ $\frac{63510}{74298} = \frac{71540}{83692}$	▶ $\frac{65124}{78390} = \frac{76302}{91845}$
▶ $\frac{61538}{79402} = \frac{64721}{83509}$	▶ $\frac{62537}{80914} = \frac{76132}{98504}$	▶ $\frac{63720}{85491} = \frac{71280}{95634}$	▶ $\frac{65142}{70938} = \frac{83754}{91206}$
▶ $\frac{61548}{79230} = \frac{71806}{92435}$	▶ $\frac{62538}{71490} = \frac{72961}{83405}$	▶ $\frac{63910}{74285} = \frac{80542}{93617}$	▶ $\frac{65279}{84013} = \frac{74283}{95601}$
▶ $\frac{61745}{93280} = \frac{64308}{97152}$	▶ $\frac{62580}{74319} = \frac{71520}{84936}$	▶ $\frac{63921}{78045} = \frac{69732}{85140}$	▶ $\frac{65298}{70134} = \frac{87064}{93512}$
▶ $\frac{61803}{72954} = \frac{76518}{90324}$	▶ $\frac{62930}{71548} = \frac{72065}{81934}$	▶ $\frac{63954}{87210} = \frac{68013}{92745}$	▶ $\frac{65308}{74192} = \frac{81635}{92740}$
▶ $\frac{61829}{74035} = \frac{69103}{82745}$	▶ $\frac{63012}{79548} = \frac{73514}{92806}$	▶ $\frac{64092}{78153} = \frac{78204}{95361}$	▶ $\frac{65312}{74980} = \frac{81640}{93725}$
▶ $\frac{61893}{72450} = \frac{83421}{97650}$	▶ $\frac{63124}{85097} = \frac{67528}{91034}$	▶ $\frac{64130}{78529} = \frac{73140}{89562}$	▶ $\frac{65340}{91278} = \frac{68310}{95427}$
▶ $\frac{61925}{74380} = \frac{74310}{89256}$	▶ $\frac{63129}{74085} = \frac{72694}{85310}$	▶ $\frac{64239}{70518} = \frac{73416}{80592}$	▶ $\frac{65348}{71920} = \frac{75361}{82940}$
▶ $\frac{61932}{80457} = \frac{71460}{92835}$	▶ $\frac{63180}{74925} = \frac{81432}{96570}$	▶ $\frac{64239}{75180} = \frac{73416}{85920}$	▶ $\frac{65392}{74108} = \frac{81740}{92635}$
▶ $\frac{61952}{73084} = \frac{70912}{83654}$	▶ $\frac{63189}{74025} = \frac{78234}{91650}$	▶ $\frac{64372}{80591} = \frac{73568}{92104}$	▶ $\frac{65412}{78930} = \frac{76314}{92085}$
▶ $\frac{61980}{73452} = \frac{72310}{85694}$	▶ $\frac{63249}{75081} = \frac{78516}{93204}$	▶ $\frac{64389}{70512} = \frac{74295}{81360}$	▶ $\frac{65493}{80712} = \frac{74302}{91568}$

▶ $\frac{65814}{73290} = \frac{73649}{82015}$	▶ $\frac{68203}{74951} = \frac{84051}{92367}$	▶ $\frac{69432}{80157} = \frac{82056}{94731}$	▶ $\frac{73501}{84692} = \frac{78243}{90156}$
▶ $\frac{65840}{71392} = \frac{86415}{93702}$	▶ $\frac{68241}{79350} = \frac{72369}{84150}$	▶ $\frac{69483}{72105} = \frac{69801}{72435}$	▶ $\frac{73602}{81954} = \frac{85023}{94671}$
▶ $\frac{65894}{70312} = \frac{76409}{81532}$	▶ $\frac{68490}{71235} = \frac{86754}{90231}$	▶ $\frac{69812}{75304} = \frac{87265}{94130}$	▶ $\frac{73602}{84591} = \frac{84506}{97123}$
▶ $\frac{65930}{71482} = \frac{68210}{73954}$	▶ $\frac{68514}{79230} = \frac{81736}{94520}$	▶ $\frac{6984}{103572} = \frac{8730}{129465}$	▶ $\frac{73920}{81546} = \frac{86240}{95137}$
▶ $\frac{65932}{74018} = \frac{72504}{81396}$	▶ $\frac{68925}{74310} = \frac{87305}{94126}$	▶ $\frac{70136}{85294} = \frac{76512}{93048}$	▶ $\frac{73926}{81540} = \frac{86247}{95130}$
▶ $\frac{65932}{78104} = \frac{82415}{97630}$	▶ $\frac{68935}{74120} = \frac{75423}{81096}$	▶ $\frac{70326}{81954} = \frac{82047}{95613}$	▶ $\frac{73960}{84152} = \frac{83205}{94671}$
▶ $\frac{65940}{73218} = \frac{76930}{85421}$	▶ $\frac{69023}{84157} = \frac{78026}{95134}$	▶ $\frac{70328}{94615} = \frac{73160}{98425}$	▶ $\frac{74025}{81639} = \frac{83475}{92061}$
▶ $\frac{65941}{72380} = \frac{74359}{81620}$	▶ $\frac{69138}{74520} = \frac{85671}{92340}$	▶ $\frac{70346}{95812} = \frac{72415}{98630}$	▶ $\frac{74096}{83512} = \frac{81674}{92053}$
▶ $\frac{67032}{81954} = \frac{78204}{95613}$	▶ $\frac{69153}{87024} = \frac{73158}{92064}$	▶ $\frac{70649}{85312} = \frac{70914}{85632}$	▶ $\frac{74295}{81630} = \frac{87503}{96142}$
▶ $\frac{67039}{84152} = \frac{72163}{90584}$	▶ $\frac{69201}{73458} = \frac{75492}{80136}$	▶ $\frac{71085}{93426} = \frac{72135}{94806}$	▶ $\frac{74529}{86310} = \frac{81627}{94530}$
▶ $\frac{67150}{84932} = \frac{69125}{87430}$	▶ $\frac{69207}{83145} = \frac{81243}{97605}$	▶ $\frac{71328}{94560} = \frac{72814}{96530}$	▶ $\frac{74612}{93058} = \frac{76234}{95081}$
▶ $\frac{67392}{81540} = \frac{78624}{95130}$	▶ $\frac{69210}{78534} = \frac{80745}{91623}$	▶ $\frac{71463}{80925} = \frac{80647}{91325}$	▶ $\frac{74952}{83160} = \frac{85362}{94710}$
▶ $\frac{67925}{80314} = \frac{73150}{86492}$	▶ $\frac{69230}{84157} = \frac{78260}{95134}$	▶ $\frac{71496}{82350} = \frac{83412}{96075}$	▶ $\frac{75096}{83142} = \frac{85176}{94302}$
▶ $\frac{67942}{81305} = \frac{76382}{91405}$	▶ $\frac{69270}{83145} = \frac{78506}{94231}$	▶ $\frac{72150}{84693} = \frac{73450}{86219}$	▶ $\frac{75632}{81490} = \frac{84760}{91325}$
▶ $\frac{67952}{81034} = \frac{75624}{90183}$	▶ $\frac{69312}{75840} = \frac{83752}{91640}$	▶ $\frac{72345}{86190} = \frac{80136}{95472}$	▶ $\frac{75806}{91234} = \frac{81034}{97526}$
▶ $\frac{68135}{79420} = \frac{81762}{95304}$	▶ $\frac{69321}{74508} = \frac{75923}{81604}$	▶ $\frac{72561}{84930} = \frac{81472}{95360}$	▶ $\frac{76051}{83249} = \frac{85074}{93126}$
▶ $\frac{68145}{70329} = \frac{87615}{90423}$	▶ $\frac{69324}{81750} = \frac{70914}{83625}$	▶ $\frac{72954}{80136} = \frac{87043}{95612}$	▶ $\frac{76059}{82134} = \frac{83571}{90246}$
▶ $\frac{68145}{73290} = \frac{87615}{94230}$	▶ $\frac{69380}{74512} = \frac{86725}{93140}$	▶ $\frac{73014}{85269} = \frac{76410}{89235}$	▶ $\frac{76302}{81954} = \frac{84321}{90567}$
▶ $\frac{68154}{73920} = \frac{79513}{86240}$	▶ $\frac{69402}{71853} = \frac{87156}{90234}$	▶ $\frac{73024}{95168} = \frac{75306}{98142}$	▶ $\frac{76482}{91350} = \frac{80731}{96425}$

$\triangleright \frac{76529}{80134} = \frac{79501}{83246}$	$\triangleright \frac{81072}{93456} = \frac{82761}{95403}$	$\triangleright \frac{82467}{91035} = \frac{87241}{96305}$	$\triangleright \frac{85140}{93267} = \frac{87120}{95436}$
$\triangleright \frac{76950}{81243} = \frac{86450}{91273}$	$\triangleright \frac{81536}{94720} = \frac{82173}{95460}$	$\triangleright \frac{83725}{91460} = \frac{84710}{92536}$	$\triangleright \frac{86730}{94521} = \frac{87320}{95164}$
$\triangleright \frac{79164}{85320} = \frac{85761}{92430}$	$\triangleright \frac{81756}{93204} = \frac{82513}{94067}$	$\triangleright \frac{83740}{95612} = \frac{85320}{97416}$	
$\triangleright \frac{80615}{93472} = \frac{84120}{97536}$	$\triangleright \frac{82017}{94635} = \frac{84123}{97065}$	$\triangleright \frac{84726}{93150} = \frac{87341}{96025}$	

• **4-Digits Numerator**

$\triangleright \frac{5016}{283749} = \frac{8360}{472915}$	$\triangleright \frac{5019}{438627} = \frac{8604}{751932}$	$\triangleright \frac{5028}{137694} = \frac{6704}{183592}$	$\triangleright \frac{5034}{162879} = \frac{8390}{271465}$
$\triangleright \frac{5016}{342798} = \frac{7348}{502169}$	$\triangleright \frac{5019}{463827} = \frac{8604}{795132}$	$\triangleright \frac{5028}{137964} = \frac{6704}{183952}$	$\triangleright \frac{5034}{162987} = \frac{8390}{271645}$
$\triangleright \frac{5016}{372894} = \frac{6072}{451398}$	$\triangleright \frac{5024}{139876} = \frac{7536}{209814}$	$\triangleright \frac{5028}{193476} = \frac{9218}{354706}$	$\triangleright \frac{5034}{179268} = \frac{5873}{209146}$
$\triangleright \frac{5016}{372984} = \frac{7106}{528394}$	$\triangleright \frac{5024}{187396} = \frac{7536}{281094}$	$\triangleright \frac{5028}{671349} = \frac{6704}{895132}$	$\triangleright \frac{5034}{269178} = \frac{6712}{358904}$
$\triangleright \frac{5016}{387429} = \frac{9240}{713685}$	$\triangleright \frac{5024}{193876} = \frac{7536}{290814}$	$\triangleright \frac{5028}{713496} = \frac{6704}{951328}$	$\triangleright \frac{5036}{149872} = \frac{6295}{187340}$
$\triangleright \frac{5016}{387942} = \frac{6908}{534271}$	$\triangleright \frac{5026}{137894} = \frac{7539}{206841}$	$\triangleright \frac{5028}{731496} = \frac{6285}{914370}$	$\triangleright \frac{5036}{297184} = \frac{6295}{371480}$
$\triangleright \frac{5016}{432897} = \frac{8360}{721495}$	$\triangleright \frac{5026}{138974} = \frac{7539}{208461}$	$\triangleright \frac{5028}{736149} = \frac{6704}{981532}$	$\triangleright \frac{5037}{148296} = \frac{8395}{247160}$
$\triangleright \frac{5016}{438729} = \frac{9504}{831276}$	$\triangleright \frac{5026}{173894} = \frac{7539}{260841}$	$\triangleright \frac{5029}{348176} = \frac{8239}{570416}$	$\triangleright \frac{5037}{162984} = \frac{8395}{271640}$
$\triangleright \frac{5016}{823479} = \frac{5104}{837926}$	$\triangleright \frac{5026}{178934} = \frac{7539}{268401}$	$\triangleright \frac{5029}{371864} = \frac{9523}{704168}$	$\triangleright \frac{5037}{689241} = \frac{5402}{739186}$
$\triangleright \frac{5016}{847932} = \frac{5478}{926031}$	$\triangleright \frac{5026}{189374} = \frac{7539}{284061}$	$\triangleright \frac{5031}{469872} = \frac{6192}{578304}$	$\triangleright \frac{5037}{924618} = \frac{5106}{937284}$
$\triangleright \frac{5017}{398246} = \frac{7598}{603124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5026}{189734} = \frac{7539}{284601}$	$\triangleright \frac{5032}{149876} = \frac{6290}{187345}$	$\triangleright \frac{5038}{174269} = \frac{9416}{325708}$
$\triangleright \frac{5018}{463972} = \frac{5109}{472386}$	$\triangleright \frac{5026}{397418} = \frac{6103}{482579}$	$\triangleright \frac{5032}{647981} = \frac{7480}{963215}$	$\triangleright \frac{5038}{241967} = \frac{6412}{307958}$
$\triangleright \frac{5018}{743629} = \frac{5902}{874631}$	$\triangleright \frac{5026}{398174} = \frac{6821}{540379}$	$\triangleright \frac{5032}{697148} = \frac{6290}{871435}$	$\triangleright \frac{5041}{263978} = \frac{7526}{394108}$
$\triangleright \frac{5019}{283746} = \frac{8365}{472910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5027}{391468} = \frac{7312}{569408}$	$\triangleright \frac{5032}{746198} = \frac{5476}{812039}$	$\triangleright \frac{5041}{679328} = \frac{5964}{803712}$

$\triangleright \frac{5042}{138796} = \frac{7563}{208194}$	$\triangleright \frac{5049}{712638} = \frac{6732}{950184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5063}{219784} = \frac{6954}{301872}$	$\triangleright \frac{5074}{369281} = \frac{9804}{713526}$
$\triangleright \frac{5042}{139876} = \frac{7563}{209814}$	$\triangleright \frac{5049}{726381} = \frac{6358}{914702}$	$\triangleright \frac{5063}{428197} = \frac{8906}{753214}$	$\triangleright \frac{5074}{619382} = \frac{6751}{824093}$
$\triangleright \frac{5042}{187396} = \frac{7563}{281094}$	$\triangleright \frac{5049}{736128} = \frac{6732}{981504}$	$\triangleright \frac{5064}{137928} = \frac{6752}{183904}$	$\triangleright \frac{5076}{129438} = \frac{9846}{251073}$
$\triangleright \frac{5042}{187936} = \frac{7563}{281904}$	$\triangleright \frac{5049}{762831} = \frac{5236}{791084}$	$\triangleright \frac{5064}{239178} = \frac{6752}{318904}$	$\triangleright \frac{5076}{143829} = \frac{8460}{239715}$
$\triangleright \frac{5042}{193876} = \frac{7563}{290814}$	$\triangleright \frac{5049}{832167} = \frac{5841}{962703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5064}{293718} = \frac{5908}{342671}$	$\triangleright \frac{5076}{149832} = \frac{6345}{187290}$
$\triangleright \frac{5042}{198736} = \frac{7563}{298104}$	$\triangleright \frac{5061}{238749} = \frac{8917}{420653}$	$\triangleright \frac{5067}{328491} = \frac{9571}{620483}$	$\triangleright \frac{5076}{314289} = \frac{5184}{320976}$
$\triangleright \frac{50421}{63798} = \frac{65709}{83142}$	$\triangleright \frac{5061}{293874} = \frac{7953}{461802}$	$\triangleright \frac{5068}{172493} = \frac{6804}{231579}$	$\triangleright \frac{5076}{482139} = \frac{9024}{857136}$
$\triangleright \frac{5043}{198276} = \frac{9102}{357864}$	$\triangleright \frac{5061}{297843} = \frac{6507}{382941}$	$\triangleright \frac{5068}{273491} = \frac{9604}{518273}$	$\triangleright \frac{5076}{483192} = \frac{9165}{872430}$
$\triangleright \frac{5043}{681297} = \frac{6847}{925013}$	$\triangleright \frac{5061}{374829} = \frac{6507}{481923}$	$\triangleright \frac{5069}{147823} = \frac{6327}{184509}$	$\triangleright \frac{5079}{143826} = \frac{8465}{239710}$
$\triangleright \frac{5043}{698271} = \frac{6027}{834519}$	$\triangleright \frac{5061}{382794} = \frac{6748}{510392}$	$\triangleright \frac{5069}{427831} = \frac{9042}{763158}$	$\triangleright \frac{5079}{162834} = \frac{8465}{271390}$
$\triangleright \frac{50439}{62178} = \frac{69207}{85314}$	$\triangleright \frac{5061}{387429} = \frac{6507}{498123}$	$\triangleright \frac{5069}{817342} = \frac{6031}{972458}$	$\triangleright \frac{5082}{143769} = \frac{8470}{239615}$
$\triangleright \frac{5046}{137982} = \frac{8961}{245037}$	$\triangleright \frac{5061}{389274} = \frac{6748}{519032}$	$\triangleright \frac{5071}{326849} = \frac{5104}{328976}$	$\triangleright \frac{5082}{163947} = \frac{6534}{210789}$
$\triangleright \frac{5047}{291683} = \frac{6489}{375021}$	$\triangleright \frac{5061}{749238} = \frac{5302}{784916}$	$\triangleright \frac{5072}{149368} = \frac{6974}{205381}$	$\triangleright \frac{5082}{314769} = \frac{8712}{539604}$
$\triangleright \frac{5047}{326819} = \frac{7938}{514026}$	$\triangleright \frac{5062}{137894} = \frac{7593}{206841}$	$\triangleright \frac{5072}{149836} = \frac{6340}{187295}$	$\triangleright \frac{5082}{716394} = \frac{6534}{921078}$
$\triangleright \frac{5048}{231796} = \frac{6310}{289745}$	$\triangleright \frac{5062}{138974} = \frac{7593}{208461}$	$\triangleright \frac{5072}{413968} = \frac{6023}{491587}$	$\triangleright \frac{5083}{129674} = \frac{7293}{186054}$
$\triangleright \frac{5048}{279136} = \frac{5679}{314028}$	$\triangleright \frac{5062}{173894} = \frac{7593}{260841}$	$\triangleright \frac{5074}{182369} = \frac{8170}{293645}$	$\triangleright \frac{5083}{162794} = \frac{5304}{169872}$
$\triangleright \frac{5048}{319672} = \frac{8203}{519467}$	$\triangleright \frac{5062}{178934} = \frac{7593}{268401}$	$\triangleright \frac{5074}{289631} = \frac{5418}{309267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5083}{264197} = \frac{6578}{341902}$
$\triangleright \frac{5049}{127386} = \frac{9537}{240618}$	$\triangleright \frac{5062}{189374} = \frac{7593}{284061}$	$\triangleright \frac{5074}{291368} = \frac{9027}{518364}$	$\triangleright \frac{5083}{716924} = \frac{6049}{853172}$
$\triangleright \frac{5049}{671328} = \frac{6732}{895104}$	$\triangleright \frac{5062}{189734} = \frac{7593}{284601}$	$\triangleright \frac{5074}{362189} = \frac{6018}{429573}$	$\triangleright \frac{5084}{312976} = \frac{7503}{461892}$

▶ $\frac{5084}{371296} = \frac{6913}{504872}$	▶ $\frac{5096}{741328} = \frac{5369}{781042}$	▶ $\frac{5106}{473892} = \frac{7104}{659328}$	▶ $\frac{5146}{327980} = \frac{8964}{571320}$
▶ $\frac{5084}{732916} = \frac{6417}{925083}$	▶ $\frac{5097}{432816} = \frac{8495}{721360}$	▶ $\frac{5120}{367984} = \frac{5760}{413982}$	▶ $\frac{5146}{920387} = \frac{5208}{931476}$
▶ $\frac{5084}{961372} = \frac{5207}{984631}$	▶ $\frac{5103}{264789} = \frac{7614}{395082}$	▶ $\frac{5120}{374968} = \frac{5760}{421839}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{230967} = \frac{7592}{340618}$
▶ $\frac{5092}{134786} = \frac{7504}{198632}$	▶ $\frac{5103}{298647} = \frac{5481}{320769}$	▶ $\frac{5120}{837496} = \frac{5760}{942183}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{267930} = \frac{8910}{463725}$
▶ $\frac{5092}{184376} = \frac{8107}{293546}$	▶ $\frac{5103}{467289} = \frac{7581}{694203}$	▶ $\frac{5123}{406897} = \frac{6157}{489023}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{270369} = \frac{6084}{319527}$
▶ $\frac{5092}{314678} = \frac{9782}{604513}$	▶ $\frac{5103}{649782} = \frac{5427}{691038}$	▶ $\frac{5124}{609378} = \frac{6954}{827013}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{297063} = \frac{7260}{418935}$
▶ $\frac{5092}{364781} = \frac{5628}{403179}$	▶ $\frac{5103}{728649} = \frac{6804}{971532}$	▶ $\frac{5124}{637098} = \frac{6710}{834295}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{302796} = \frac{5247}{308619}$
▶ $\frac{5093}{127468} = \frac{6945}{173820}$	▶ $\frac{5103}{729864} = \frac{6804}{973152}$	▶ $\frac{5128}{374960} = \frac{5769}{421830}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{327096} = \frac{8073}{512946}$
▶ $\frac{5094}{137628} = \frac{6792}{183504}$	▶ $\frac{51039}{62487} = \frac{54891}{67203}$	▶ $\frac{5128}{396704} = \frac{9615}{743820}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{367290} = \frac{5876}{419230}$
▶ $\frac{5094}{168732} = \frac{7641}{253098}$	▶ $\frac{5104}{297638} = \frac{9048}{527631}$	▶ $\frac{5129}{364780} = \frac{5798}{412360}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{396207} = \frac{9152}{704368}$
▶ $\frac{5094}{213768} = \frac{6509}{273148}$	▶ $\frac{5104}{368972} = \frac{8932}{645701}$	▶ $\frac{5129}{407836} = \frac{5798}{461032}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{697032} = \frac{6435}{871290}$
▶ $\frac{5094}{376281} = \frac{8490}{627135}$	▶ $\frac{5104}{639827} = \frac{7216}{904583}$	▶ $\frac{5130}{724869} = \frac{6570}{928341}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{703296} = \frac{6435}{879120}$
▶ $\frac{5094}{382761} = \frac{6792}{510348}$	▶ $\frac{5106}{287934} = \frac{6279}{354081}$	▶ $\frac{5130}{728649} = \frac{6840}{971532}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{730296} = \frac{6435}{912870}$
▶ $\frac{5096}{123487} = \frac{8904}{215763}$	▶ $\frac{5106}{327894} = \frac{7038}{451962}$	▶ $\frac{5130}{729864} = \frac{6840}{973152}$	▶ $\frac{5148}{903672} = \frac{5174}{908236}$
▶ $\frac{5096}{132847} = \frac{7056}{183942}$	▶ $\frac{5106}{392748} = \frac{9213}{708654}$	▶ $\frac{5134}{679082} = \frac{5436}{719028}$	▶ $\frac{5149}{680732} = \frac{7046}{931528}$
▶ $\frac{5096}{238147} = \frac{8120}{379465}$	▶ $\frac{5106}{397824} = \frac{7935}{618240}$	▶ $\frac{5134}{679802} = \frac{5423}{718069}$	▶ $\frac{5160}{247938} = \frac{7580}{364219}$
▶ $\frac{5096}{284713} = \frac{7056}{394218}$	▶ $\frac{5106}{428973} = \frac{7104}{596832}$	▶ $\frac{5136}{478290} = \frac{5328}{496170}$	▶ $\frac{5160}{427893} = \frac{6920}{573841}$
▶ $\frac{5096}{731428} = \frac{6370}{914285}$	▶ $\frac{5106}{429387} = \frac{8214}{690753}$	▶ $\frac{5139}{482076} = \frac{9136}{857024}$	▶ $\frac{5160}{438729} = \frac{9240}{785631}$
▶ $\frac{5096}{734812} = \frac{6174}{890253}$	▶ $\frac{5106}{439782} = \frac{6279}{540813}$	▶ $\frac{5146}{278039} = \frac{7968}{430512}$	▶ $\frac{5162}{490738} = \frac{7209}{685341}$

▶ $\frac{5168}{293740} = \frac{8296}{471530}$	▶ $\frac{5178}{269034} = \frac{6904}{358712}$	▶ $\frac{5187}{642390} = \frac{5928}{734160}$	▶ $\frac{52049}{73186} = \frac{70153}{98642}$
▶ $\frac{5168}{347092} = \frac{9724}{653081}$	▶ $\frac{5178}{290364} = \frac{6904}{387152}$	▶ $\frac{5187}{694203} = \frac{6279}{840351}$	▶ $\frac{5206}{318497} = \frac{7398}{452601}$
▶ $\frac{5168}{349072} = \frac{5814}{392706}$	▶ $\frac{5178}{290634} = \frac{6904}{387512}$	▶ $\frac{5192}{378640} = \frac{8437}{615290}$	▶ $\frac{5206}{397841} = \frac{6302}{481597}$
▶ $\frac{5168}{430729} = \frac{8512}{709436}$	▶ $\frac{5178}{403629} = \frac{6904}{538172}$	▶ $\frac{5192}{387046} = \frac{8732}{650941}$	▶ $\frac{5206}{419387} = \frac{9316}{750482}$
▶ $\frac{5168}{437920} = \frac{7581}{642390}$	▶ $\frac{5178}{436029} = \frac{6904}{581372}$	▶ $\frac{5192}{630784} = \frac{5841}{709632}$	▶ $\frac{5206}{719834} = \frac{7124}{985036}$
▶ $\frac{5168}{723904} = \frac{6783}{950124}$	▶ $\frac{5180}{276493} = \frac{9620}{513487}$	▶ $\frac{5192}{763840} = \frac{5723}{841960}$	▶ $\frac{5208}{174936} = \frac{9548}{320716}$
▶ $\frac{5169}{208374} = \frac{8615}{347290}$	▶ $\frac{5180}{294637} = \frac{9620}{547183}$	▶ $\frac{5193}{480726} = \frac{7501}{694382}$	▶ $\frac{5208}{197346} = \frac{5236}{198407}$
▶ $\frac{5170}{238964} = \frac{8930}{412756}$	▶ $\frac{5180}{327964} = \frac{5920}{374816}$	▶ $\frac{5194}{208376} = \frac{8904}{357216}$	▶ $\frac{5208}{491736} = \frac{6324}{597108}$
▶ $\frac{5170}{246938} = \frac{5940}{283716}$	▶ $\frac{5180}{642397} = \frac{5920}{734168}$	▶ $\frac{5194}{237860} = \frac{5936}{271840}$	▶ $\frac{5208}{496713} = \frac{7320}{698145}$
▶ $\frac{5170}{268934} = \frac{7865}{409123}$	▶ $\frac{5180}{764239} = \frac{5920}{873416}$	▶ $\frac{5194}{306287} = \frac{5782}{340961}$	▶ $\frac{5213}{640798} = \frac{5941}{730286}$
▶ $\frac{5170}{846329} = \frac{5310}{869247}$	▶ $\frac{5184}{203796} = \frac{6384}{250971}$	▶ $\frac{5194}{367820} = \frac{7938}{562140}$	▶ $\frac{5214}{360987} = \frac{7268}{503194}$
▶ $\frac{5172}{396804} = \frac{5603}{429871}$	▶ $\frac{5184}{297036} = \frac{6480}{371295}$	▶ $\frac{5194}{632078} = \frac{7546}{918302}$	▶ $\frac{5217}{398046} = \frac{7614}{580932}$
▶ $\frac{5172}{804396} = \frac{5603}{871429}$	▶ $\frac{5184}{307692} = \frac{9072}{538461}$	▶ $\frac{5194}{670238} = \frac{5341}{689207}$	▶ $\frac{5217}{408369} = \frac{6251}{489307}$
▶ $\frac{5176}{409328} = \frac{9058}{716324}$	▶ $\frac{5184}{607392} = \frac{6318}{740259}$	▶ $\frac{5196}{372804} = \frac{5629}{403871}$	▶ $\frac{5217}{836940} = \frac{5687}{912340}$
▶ $\frac{5178}{203964} = \frac{6041}{237958}$	▶ $\frac{5184}{630792} = \frac{5832}{709641}$	▶ $\frac{5196}{804372} = \frac{5629}{871403}$	▶ $\frac{5219}{374680} = \frac{9517}{683240}$
▶ $\frac{5178}{236904} = \frac{6904}{315872}$	▶ $\frac{5184}{679320} = \frac{7128}{934065}$	▶ $\frac{5198}{273460} = \frac{6187}{325490}$	▶ $\frac{5236}{140987} = \frac{9316}{250847}$
▶ $\frac{5178}{239064} = \frac{6904}{318752}$	▶ $\frac{5184}{730296} = \frac{5904}{831726}$	▶ $\frac{5198}{623047} = \frac{8136}{975204}$	▶ $\frac{5236}{178904} = \frac{6307}{215498}$
▶ $\frac{5178}{239604} = \frac{6041}{279538}$	▶ $\frac{5187}{249603} = \frac{7098}{341562}$	▶ $\frac{5201}{437689} = \frac{8916}{750324}$	▶ $\frac{5236}{179480} = \frac{6358}{217940}$
▶ $\frac{5178}{263904} = \frac{6904}{351872}$	▶ $\frac{5187}{349206} = \frac{8379}{564102}$	▶ $\frac{5203}{497816} = \frac{8041}{769352}$	▶ $\frac{5236}{184079} = \frac{5984}{210376}$

▶ $\frac{5236}{409178} = \frac{5372}{419806}$	▶ $\frac{5268}{103947} = \frac{7024}{138596}$	▶ $\frac{5287}{193460} = \frac{9641}{352780}$	▶ $\frac{5291}{306748} = \frac{9361}{542708}$
▶ $\frac{5238}{461079} = \frac{6014}{529387}$	▶ $\frac{5268}{139047} = \frac{7024}{185396}$	▶ $\frac{5287}{490136} = \frac{5372}{498016}$	▶ $\frac{5291}{364780} = \frac{8954}{617320}$
▶ $\frac{5239}{170846} = \frac{9672}{315408}$	▶ $\frac{5270}{391468} = \frac{9605}{713482}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{104736} = \frac{7052}{139648}$	▶ $\frac{5291}{376480} = \frac{8954}{637120}$
▶ $\frac{5239}{186407} = \frac{5673}{201849}$	▶ $\frac{5270}{398164} = \frac{8925}{674310}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{104763} = \frac{7052}{139684}$	▶ $\frac{5291}{487630} = \frac{8621}{794530}$
▶ $\frac{5239}{678041} = \frac{5642}{730198}$	▶ $\frac{5274}{389601} = \frac{7032}{519468}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{136407} = \frac{9718}{250634}$	▶ $\frac{5291}{678403} = \frac{6253}{801749}$
▶ $\frac{5240}{179863} = \frac{9560}{328147}$	▶ $\frac{5276}{138904} = \frac{7914}{208356}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{167403} = \frac{6794}{215038}$	▶ $\frac{5291}{763048} = \frac{6253}{901784}$
▶ $\frac{5240}{319768} = \frac{7205}{439681}$	▶ $\frac{5276}{413890} = \frac{7914}{620835}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{310476} = \frac{7052}{413968}$	▶ $\frac{5293}{714086} = \frac{7031}{948562}$
▶ $\frac{5243}{168097} = \frac{6517}{208943}$	▶ $\frac{5278}{103649} = \frac{8932}{175406}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{361047} = \frac{7052}{481396}$	▶ $\frac{5296}{173804} = \frac{9268}{304157}$
▶ $\frac{5243}{871906} = \frac{5671}{943082}$	▶ $\frac{5278}{104936} = \frac{7308}{145296}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{463710} = \frac{9417}{825630}$	▶ $\frac{5296}{417380} = \frac{9268}{730415}$
▶ $\frac{5246}{170983} = \frac{7396}{241058}$	▶ $\frac{5278}{149630} = \frac{6293}{178405}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{610473} = \frac{7052}{813964}$	▶ $\frac{5298}{134076} = \frac{9713}{245806}$
▶ $\frac{5246}{897310} = \frac{5418}{926730}$	▶ $\frac{5278}{463190} = \frac{9512}{834760}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{631047} = \frac{7052}{841396}$	▶ $\frac{5298}{316704} = \frac{9713}{580624}$
▶ $\frac{5247}{381690} = \frac{8162}{593740}$	▶ $\frac{5280}{413976} = \frac{6820}{534719}$	▶ $\frac{5289}{647103} = \frac{5934}{726018}$	▶ $\frac{5298}{670134} = \frac{7064}{893512}$
▶ $\frac{5248}{103976} = \frac{8432}{167059}$	▶ $\frac{5280}{419376} = \frac{9460}{751382}$	▶ $\frac{5290}{138764} = \frac{7935}{208146}$	▶ $\frac{5298}{701346} = \frac{7064}{935128}$
▶ $\frac{5248}{173960} = \frac{9840}{326175}$	▶ $\frac{5283}{149670} = \frac{6457}{182930}$	▶ $\frac{5290}{184736} = \frac{9085}{317264}$	▶ $\frac{5298}{736014} = \frac{7064}{981352}$
▶ $\frac{5248}{709136} = \frac{7048}{952361}$	▶ $\frac{5283}{179640} = \frac{7631}{259480}$	▶ $\frac{5290}{187364} = \frac{7935}{281046}$	▶ $\frac{5301}{428697} = \frac{8091}{654327}$
▶ $\frac{5264}{301798} = \frac{9024}{517368}$	▶ $\frac{5286}{104739} = \frac{7048}{139652}$	▶ $\frac{5290}{413876} = \frac{7935}{620814}$	▶ $\frac{5301}{469278} = \frac{8094}{716532}$
▶ $\frac{5264}{317908} = \frac{9632}{581704}$	▶ $\frac{5286}{190437} = \frac{7048}{253916}$	▶ $\frac{5290}{418736} = \frac{7935}{628104}$	▶ $\frac{5301}{486297} = \frac{6327}{580419}$
▶ $\frac{5267}{139840} = \frac{7328}{194560}$	▶ $\frac{5286}{391047} = \frac{7048}{521396}$	▶ $\frac{5290}{476813} = \frac{7590}{684123}$	▶ $\frac{5301}{748296} = \frac{6417}{905832}$
▶ $\frac{5267}{149308} = \frac{6785}{192340}$	▶ $\frac{5287}{190643} = \frac{6851}{247039}$	▶ $\frac{5290}{681743} = \frac{7360}{948512}$	▶ $\frac{5301}{796824} = \frac{6327}{951048}$

$\triangleright \frac{5302}{167948} = \frac{8435}{267190}$	$\triangleright \frac{5316}{297084} = \frac{7531}{420869}$	$\triangleright \frac{5328}{714960} = \frac{6327}{849015}$	$\triangleright \frac{5348}{216097} = \frac{9168}{370452}$
$\triangleright \frac{5302}{178694} = \frac{7953}{268041}$	$\triangleright \frac{5317}{204698} = \frac{9407}{362158}$	$\triangleright \frac{5328}{719460} = \frac{6512}{879340}$	$\triangleright \frac{5360}{428197} = \frac{9280}{741356}$
$\triangleright \frac{5302}{186974} = \frac{7953}{280461}$	$\triangleright \frac{5317}{289640} = \frac{9816}{534720}$	$\triangleright \frac{5329}{486107} = \frac{7081}{645923}$	$\triangleright \frac{5360}{492718} = \frac{9320}{856741}$
$\triangleright \frac{5302}{197846} = \frac{8194}{305762}$	$\triangleright \frac{5320}{168974} = \frac{7980}{253461}$	$\triangleright \frac{5340}{167892} = \frac{6230}{195874}$	$\triangleright \frac{5364}{290178} = \frac{7152}{386904}$
$\triangleright \frac{5304}{167892} = \frac{5694}{180237}$	$\triangleright \frac{5320}{176894} = \frac{7980}{265341}$	$\triangleright \frac{5342}{170986} = \frac{8013}{256479}$	$\triangleright \frac{5368}{270149} = \frac{8296}{417503}$
$\triangleright \frac{5304}{729168} = \frac{5967}{820314}$	$\triangleright \frac{5320}{179648} = \frac{8740}{295136}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{107892} = \frac{6435}{129870}$	$\triangleright \frac{5368}{419720} = \frac{6039}{472185}$
$\triangleright \frac{5304}{729816} = \frac{5967}{821043}$	$\triangleright \frac{5320}{418796} = \frac{6270}{493581}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{120879} = \frac{7290}{164835}$	$\triangleright \frac{5369}{180427} = \frac{5782}{194306}$
$\triangleright \frac{5304}{761982} = \frac{6324}{908517}$	$\triangleright \frac{5320}{468179} = \frac{6720}{591384}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{120978} = \frac{6804}{153972}$	$\triangleright \frac{5369}{182074} = \frac{8645}{293170}$
$\triangleright \frac{5304}{819672} = \frac{6357}{982401}$	$\triangleright \frac{5320}{497861} = \frac{9120}{853476}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{128790} = \frac{8613}{207495}$	$\triangleright \frac{5369}{870142} = \frac{6018}{975324}$
$\triangleright \frac{5307}{184962} = \frac{7503}{261498}$	$\triangleright \frac{5320}{687914} = \frac{7280}{941356}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{170829} = \frac{6534}{208791}$	$\triangleright \frac{5369}{874120} = \frac{5782}{941360}$
$\triangleright \frac{5307}{246819} = \frac{8723}{405691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5320}{716984} = \frac{5390}{726418}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{170982} = \frac{8019}{256473}$	$\triangleright \frac{5370}{196482} = \frac{9845}{360217}$
$\triangleright \frac{5307}{249168} = \frac{7259}{340816}$	$\triangleright \frac{5320}{948176} = \frac{5460}{973128}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{178290} = \frac{8019}{267435}$	$\triangleright \frac{5371}{462890} = \frac{9563}{824170}$
$\triangleright \frac{5307}{461892} = \frac{8265}{719340}$	$\triangleright \frac{5324}{180796} = \frac{7381}{250649}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{179820} = \frac{6534}{219780}$	$\triangleright \frac{5372}{691408} = \frac{6103}{785492}$
$\triangleright \frac{5310}{426987} = \frac{6490}{521873}$	$\triangleright \frac{5327}{498610} = \frac{9132}{854760}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{219780} = \frac{6318}{259740}$	$\triangleright \frac{5374}{182906} = \frac{8061}{274359}$
$\triangleright \frac{5310}{427986} = \frac{7485}{603291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5328}{196470} = \frac{5376}{198240}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{291708} = \frac{8019}{437562}$	$\triangleright \frac{5374}{186290} = \frac{8061}{279435}$
$\triangleright \frac{5310}{842697} = \frac{5490}{871263}$	$\triangleright \frac{5328}{409176} = \frac{9324}{716058}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{701298} = \frac{7128}{935064}$	$\triangleright \frac{5376}{104928} = \frac{8064}{157392}$
$\triangleright \frac{5312}{649807} = \frac{6208}{759413}$	$\triangleright \frac{5328}{619047} = \frac{7104}{825396}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{719280} = \frac{6534}{879120}$	$\triangleright \frac{5376}{109248} = \frac{9072}{184356}$
$\triangleright \frac{5312}{897064} = \frac{5408}{913276}$	$\triangleright \frac{5328}{640971} = \frac{6512}{783409}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{720918} = \frac{6804}{917532}$	$\triangleright \frac{5376}{128490} = \frac{8064}{192735}$
$\triangleright \frac{5312}{907648} = \frac{5478}{936012}$	$\triangleright \frac{5328}{649017} = \frac{7824}{953061}$	$\triangleright \frac{5346}{912708} = \frac{5742}{980316}$	$\triangleright \frac{5376}{129048} = \frac{8064}{193572}$

▶ $\frac{5376}{140829} = \frac{8960}{234715}$	▶ $\frac{5382}{170946} = \frac{8073}{256419}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{163798} = \frac{8103}{245697}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{379618} = \frac{8103}{569427}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{190428} = \frac{7168}{253904}$	▶ $\frac{5382}{179460} = \frac{6578}{219340}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{163978} = \frac{8103}{245967}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{379816} = \frac{8103}{569724}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{214980} = \frac{9408}{376215}$	▶ $\frac{5382}{619047} = \frac{8142}{936507}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{176398} = \frac{8103}{264597}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{381796} = \frac{8103}{572694}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{481290} = \frac{8064}{721935}$	▶ $\frac{5384}{102796} = \frac{6730}{128495}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{178396} = \frac{8103}{267594}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{381976} = \frac{8103}{572964}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{490128} = \frac{8064}{735192}$	▶ $\frac{5384}{170269} = \frac{9576}{302841}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{179638} = \frac{8103}{269457}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{396178} = \frac{8103}{594267}$
▶ $\frac{5376}{492810} = \frac{8064}{739215}$	▶ $\frac{5386}{170942} = \frac{8079}{256413}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{179836} = \frac{8103}{269754}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{397618} = \frac{8103}{596427}$
▶ $\frac{5378}{142906} = \frac{8067}{214359}$	▶ $\frac{5386}{174290} = \frac{8079}{261435}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{183796} = \frac{8103}{275694}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{397816} = \frac{8103}{596724}$
▶ $\frac{5378}{146290} = \frac{8067}{219435}$	▶ $\frac{5386}{274910} = \frac{8079}{412365}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{183976} = \frac{8103}{275964}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{398176} = \frac{8103}{597264}$
▶ $\frac{5379}{140826} = \frac{8965}{234710}$	▶ $\frac{5390}{127468} = \frac{9065}{214378}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{189736} = \frac{5913}{207684}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{673918} = \frac{6497}{810523}$
▶ $\frac{5379}{162804} = \frac{8965}{271340}$	▶ $\frac{5390}{167482} = \frac{6985}{217043}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{196378} = \frac{8103}{294567}$	▶ $\frac{5403}{286197} = \frac{7204}{381596}$
▶ $\frac{5380}{146792} = \frac{6725}{183490}$	▶ $\frac{5390}{182476} = \frac{5720}{193648}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{197638} = \frac{8103}{296457}$	▶ $\frac{5403}{298617} = \frac{7204}{398156}$
▶ $\frac{5380}{172964} = \frac{9415}{302687}$	▶ $\frac{5390}{278614} = \frac{8195}{423607}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{197836} = \frac{8103}{296754}$	▶ $\frac{5408}{327691} = \frac{9248}{560371}$
▶ $\frac{5380}{214976} = \frac{9415}{376208}$	▶ $\frac{5392}{187640} = \frac{8762}{304915}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{198376} = \frac{8103}{297564}$	▶ $\frac{5408}{397216} = \frac{7098}{521346}$
▶ $\frac{5380}{417296} = \frac{9415}{730268}$	▶ $\frac{5394}{687210} = \frac{6293}{801745}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{317968} = \frac{8103}{476952}$	▶ $\frac{5408}{726193} = \frac{6240}{837915}$
▶ $\frac{5380}{472916} = \frac{9415}{827603}$	▶ $\frac{5394}{721680} = \frac{6351}{849720}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{319768} = \frac{8103}{479652}$	▶ $\frac{5409}{281736} = \frac{7813}{406952}$
▶ $\frac{5380}{674921} = \frac{6520}{817934}$	▶ $\frac{5396}{147820} = \frac{6532}{178940}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{361798} = \frac{8103}{542697}$	▶ $\frac{5409}{362817} = \frac{7813}{524069}$
▶ $\frac{5382}{140769} = \frac{8970}{234615}$	▶ $\frac{5396}{184072} = \frac{8946}{305172}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{361978} = \frac{8103}{542967}$	▶ $\frac{5412}{368907} = \frac{8364}{570129}$
▶ $\frac{5382}{146970} = \frac{7839}{214065}$	▶ $\frac{5396}{284710} = \frac{6042}{318795}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{376198} = \frac{8103}{564297}$	▶ $\frac{5412}{678930} = \frac{6314}{792085}$
▶ $\frac{5382}{170469} = \frac{6854}{217093}$	▶ $\frac{5401}{367928} = \frac{5892}{401376}$	▶ $\frac{5402}{378196} = \frac{8103}{567294}$	▶ $\frac{5412}{679038} = \frac{7216}{905384}$

$\triangleright \frac{5412}{789063} = \frac{6724}{980351}$	$\triangleright \frac{5418}{397602} = \frac{8127}{596403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{361798} = \frac{8130}{542697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5428}{179360} = \frac{7843}{259160}$
$\triangleright \frac{5412}{789306} = \frac{6314}{920857}$	$\triangleright \frac{5418}{397620} = \frac{8127}{596430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{361978} = \frac{8130}{542967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5428}{317906} = \frac{9086}{532147}$
$\triangleright \frac{5412}{897360} = \frac{5863}{972140}$	$\triangleright \frac{5418}{736029} = \frac{5934}{806127}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{376198} = \frac{8130}{564297}$	$\triangleright \frac{5429}{108763} = \frac{7832}{156904}$
$\triangleright \frac{5416}{203798} = \frac{8124}{305697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5418}{736920} = \frac{6321}{859740}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{378196} = \frac{8130}{567294}$	$\triangleright \frac{5429}{673018} = \frac{6527}{809134}$
$\triangleright \frac{5416}{203978} = \frac{8124}{305967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5418}{769320} = \frac{6321}{897540}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{379618} = \frac{8130}{569427}$	$\triangleright \frac{5430}{286197} = \frac{7240}{381596}$
$\triangleright \frac{5416}{237980} = \frac{8124}{356970}$	$\triangleright \frac{5418}{796320} = \frac{5934}{872160}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{379816} = \frac{8130}{569724}$	$\triangleright \frac{5430}{298617} = \frac{7240}{398156}$
$\triangleright \frac{5416}{379802} = \frac{8124}{569703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{163798} = \frac{8130}{245697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{381796} = \frac{8130}{572694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5432}{170968} = \frac{7469}{235081}$
$\triangleright \frac{5416}{379820} = \frac{8124}{569730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{163978} = \frac{8130}{245967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{381976} = \frac{8130}{572964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5432}{186970} = \frac{8924}{307165}$
$\triangleright \frac{5416}{397802} = \frac{8124}{596703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{176398} = \frac{8130}{264597}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{396178} = \frac{8130}{594267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5432}{187096} = \frac{9506}{327418}$
$\triangleright \frac{5416}{397820} = \frac{8124}{596730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{178396} = \frac{8130}{267594}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{397618} = \frac{8130}{596427}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{179802} = \frac{8154}{269703}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{203796} = \frac{8127}{305694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{179638} = \frac{8130}{269457}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{397816} = \frac{8130}{596724}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{179820} = \frac{8154}{269730}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{203976} = \frac{8127}{305964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{179836} = \frac{8130}{269754}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{398176} = \frac{8130}{597264}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{190728} = \frac{6795}{238410}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{209367} = \frac{7896}{305124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{183796} = \frac{8130}{275694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5423}{607981} = \frac{6409}{718523}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{197802} = \frac{8154}{296703}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{237069} = \frac{6708}{293514}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{196378} = \frac{8130}{294567}$	$\triangleright \frac{5423}{718960} = \frac{5916}{784320}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{197820} = \frac{8154}{296730}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{237960} = \frac{8127}{356940}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{197638} = \frac{8130}{296457}$	$\triangleright \frac{5426}{137098} = \frac{8139}{205647}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{201798} = \frac{8154}{302697}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{239760} = \frac{8127}{359640}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{197836} = \frac{8130}{296754}$	$\triangleright \frac{5426}{170938} = \frac{8139}{256407}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{201978} = \frac{8154}{302967}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{379602} = \frac{8127}{569403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{198376} = \frac{8130}{297564}$	$\triangleright \frac{54273}{60198} = \frac{84501}{93726}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{217980} = \frac{8154}{326970}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{379620} = \frac{8127}{569430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{317968} = \frac{8130}{476952}$	$\triangleright \frac{5428}{107936} = \frac{6785}{134920}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{219780} = \frac{8154}{329670}$
$\triangleright \frac{5418}{397026} = \frac{6579}{482103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5420}{319768} = \frac{8130}{479652}$	$\triangleright \frac{5428}{170936} = \frac{9617}{302854}$	$\triangleright \frac{5436}{281709} = \frac{7852}{406913}$

$\triangleright \frac{5436}{891720} = \frac{5738}{941260}$	$\triangleright \frac{5460}{891723} = \frac{5720}{934186}$	$\triangleright \frac{5478}{269310} = \frac{8217}{403965}$	$\triangleright \frac{5490}{836127} = \frac{6210}{945783}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{179602} = \frac{8157}{269403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5460}{897312} = \frac{5670}{931824}$	$\triangleright \frac{5478}{312609} = \frac{5976}{341028}$	$\triangleright \frac{5491}{267308} = \frac{7106}{345928}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{179620} = \frac{8157}{269430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5462}{137098} = \frac{8193}{205647}$	$\triangleright \frac{5478}{312690} = \frac{8217}{469035}$	$\triangleright \frac{5491}{280763} = \frac{8092}{413756}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{197602} = \frac{8157}{296403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5462}{170938} = \frac{8193}{256407}$	$\triangleright \frac{5478}{326910} = \frac{8217}{490365}$	$\triangleright \frac{5491}{387260} = \frac{8417}{593620}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{197620} = \frac{8157}{296430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5467}{238091} = \frac{9372}{408156}$	$\triangleright \frac{5478}{639210} = \frac{6972}{813540}$	$\triangleright \frac{5491}{602837} = \frac{7429}{815603}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{201796} = \frac{8157}{302694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5467}{291830} = \frac{6958}{371420}$	$\triangleright \frac{5481}{376029} = \frac{6902}{473518}$	$\triangleright \frac{5493}{608217} = \frac{7324}{810956}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{201976} = \frac{8157}{302964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5467}{308921} = \frac{8932}{504716}$	$\triangleright \frac{5481}{397062} = \frac{7308}{529416}$	$\triangleright \frac{5493}{718620} = \frac{7324}{958160}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{217960} = \frac{8157}{326940}$	$\triangleright \frac{5467}{380219} = \frac{9372}{651804}$	$\triangleright \frac{5481}{706239} = \frac{7308}{941652}$	$\triangleright \frac{5496}{208371} = \frac{9160}{347285}$
$\triangleright \frac{5438}{219760} = \frac{8157}{329640}$	$\triangleright \frac{5468}{103792} = \frac{6835}{129740}$	$\triangleright \frac{5486}{309712} = \frac{7385}{416920}$	$\triangleright \frac{5496}{283701} = \frac{9160}{472835}$
$\triangleright \frac{5439}{106782} = \frac{8379}{164502}$	$\triangleright \frac{5468}{730192} = \frac{6835}{912740}$	$\triangleright \frac{5487}{136290} = \frac{9548}{237160}$	$\triangleright \frac{5496}{308217} = \frac{7328}{410956}$
$\triangleright \frac{5439}{270186} = \frac{7104}{352896}$	$\triangleright \frac{5472}{109836} = \frac{6840}{137295}$	$\triangleright \frac{5487}{203196} = \frac{9641}{357028}$	$\triangleright \frac{5497}{163208} = \frac{6931}{205784}$
$\triangleright \frac{5439}{620781} = \frac{8214}{937506}$	$\triangleright \frac{5472}{138960} = \frac{9576}{243180}$	$\triangleright \frac{5489}{173206} = \frac{7485}{236190}$	$\triangleright \frac{5601}{382794} = \frac{7468}{510392}$
$\triangleright \frac{5439}{817026} = \frac{6327}{950418}$	$\triangleright \frac{5472}{183096} = \frac{9576}{320418}$	$\triangleright \frac{5490}{126378} = \frac{7930}{182546}$	$\triangleright \frac{5601}{389274} = \frac{7468}{519032}$
$\triangleright \frac{5460}{137982} = \frac{5670}{143289}$	$\triangleright \frac{5472}{190836} = \frac{5976}{208413}$	$\triangleright \frac{5490}{127836} = \frac{7930}{184652}$	$\triangleright \frac{5602}{143798} = \frac{8403}{215697}$
$\triangleright \frac{5460}{138792} = \frac{6825}{173490}$	$\triangleright \frac{5472}{360981} = \frac{8064}{531972}$	$\triangleright \frac{5490}{312678} = \frac{8235}{469017}$	$\triangleright \frac{5602}{143978} = \frac{8403}{215967}$
$\triangleright \frac{5460}{183729} = \frac{5760}{193824}$	$\triangleright \frac{5472}{398610} = \frac{7296}{531480}$	$\triangleright \frac{5490}{371862} = \frac{7320}{495816}$	$\triangleright \frac{5602}{174398} = \frac{8403}{261597}$
$\triangleright \frac{5460}{192738} = \frac{8370}{295461}$	$\triangleright \frac{5476}{109832} = \frac{6845}{137290}$	$\triangleright \frac{5490}{718623} = \frac{7320}{958164}$	$\triangleright \frac{5602}{178394} = \frac{8403}{267591}$
$\triangleright \frac{5460}{312897} = \frac{8960}{513472}$	$\triangleright \frac{5478}{106392} = \frac{6972}{135408}$	$\triangleright \frac{5490}{721386} = \frac{7065}{928341}$	$\triangleright \frac{5602}{179438} = \frac{8403}{269157}$
$\triangleright \frac{5460}{387192} = \frac{9135}{647802}$	$\triangleright \frac{5478}{269130} = \frac{8217}{403695}$	$\triangleright \frac{5490}{723861} = \frac{7320}{965148}$	$\triangleright \frac{5602}{179834} = \frac{8403}{269751}$

$\triangleright \frac{5602}{183794} = \frac{8403}{275691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5609}{472183} = \frac{8946}{753102}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{397820} = \frac{8421}{596730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{194378} = \frac{8430}{291567}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{183974} = \frac{8403}{275961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5610}{274839} = \frac{8690}{425731}$	$\triangleright \frac{5617}{280439} = \frac{9061}{452387}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{197438} = \frac{8430}{296157}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{194378} = \frac{8403}{291567}$	$\triangleright \frac{5610}{284937} = \frac{6270}{318459}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{203794} = \frac{8427}{305691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{197834} = \frac{8430}{296751}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{197438} = \frac{8403}{296157}$	$\triangleright \frac{5610}{384972} = \frac{7480}{513296}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{203974} = \frac{8427}{305961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{198374} = \frac{8430}{297561}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{197834} = \frac{8403}{296751}$	$\triangleright \frac{5610}{398472} = \frac{7480}{531296}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{230974} = \frac{7526}{309418}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{341798} = \frac{8430}{512697}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{198374} = \frac{8403}{297561}$	$\triangleright \frac{5610}{493782} = \frac{6490}{571238}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{237940} = \frac{8427}{356910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{341978} = \frac{8430}{512967}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{341798} = \frac{8403}{512697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5610}{723849} = \frac{7480}{965132}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{239740} = \frac{8427}{359610}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{374198} = \frac{8430}{561297}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{341978} = \frac{8403}{512967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5610}{723984} = \frac{7480}{965312}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{379402} = \frac{8427}{569103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{378194} = \frac{8430}{567291}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{374198} = \frac{8403}{561297}$	$\triangleright \frac{5610}{874293} = \frac{5720}{891436}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{379420} = \frac{8427}{569130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{379418} = \frac{8430}{569127}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{378194} = \frac{8403}{567291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5612}{437980} = \frac{7843}{612095}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{397402} = \frac{8427}{596103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{379814} = \frac{8430}{569721}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{379418} = \frac{8403}{569127}$	$\triangleright \frac{5612}{789340} = \frac{6532}{918740}$	$\triangleright \frac{5618}{397420} = \frac{8427}{596130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{381794} = \frac{8430}{572691}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{379814} = \frac{8403}{569721}$	$\triangleright \frac{5612}{940378} = \frac{5734}{960821}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{143798} = \frac{8430}{215697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{381974} = \frac{8430}{572961}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{381794} = \frac{8403}{572691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{203798} = \frac{8421}{305697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{143978} = \frac{8430}{215967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{394178} = \frac{8430}{591267}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{381974} = \frac{8403}{572961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{203978} = \frac{8421}{305967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{174398} = \frac{8430}{261597}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{397418} = \frac{8430}{596127}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{394178} = \frac{8403}{591267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{237980} = \frac{8421}{356970}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{178394} = \frac{8430}{267591}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{397814} = \frac{8430}{596721}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{397418} = \frac{8403}{596127}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{239780} = \frac{8421}{359670}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{179438} = \frac{8430}{269157}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{398174} = \frac{8430}{597261}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{397814} = \frac{8403}{596721}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{379802} = \frac{8421}{569703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{179834} = \frac{8430}{269751}$	$\triangleright \frac{5621}{408397} = \frac{8176}{594032}$
$\triangleright \frac{5602}{398174} = \frac{8403}{597261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{379820} = \frac{8421}{569730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{183794} = \frac{8430}{275691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5621}{793408} = \frac{5694}{803712}$
$\triangleright \frac{5604}{239178} = \frac{6538}{279041}$	$\triangleright \frac{5614}{397802} = \frac{8421}{596703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5620}{183974} = \frac{8430}{275961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5621}{809347} = \frac{6059}{872413}$

$\triangleright \frac{5624}{379810} = \frac{6512}{439780}$	$\triangleright \frac{5634}{912708} = \frac{6057}{981234}$	$\triangleright \frac{5642}{870139} = \frac{6370}{982415}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{738012} = \frac{7532}{984016}$
$\triangleright \frac{5624}{391780} = \frac{6290}{438175}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{179402} = \frac{8457}{269103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5643}{127908} = \frac{9153}{207468}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{738120} = \frac{7532}{984160}$
$\triangleright \frac{5628}{103479} = \frac{9380}{172465}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{179420} = \frac{8457}{269130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5643}{271890} = \frac{6138}{295740}$	$\triangleright \frac{5670}{138294} = \frac{7560}{184392}$
$\triangleright \frac{5628}{109347} = \frac{7236}{140589}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{197402} = \frac{8457}{296103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5643}{720981} = \frac{7524}{961308}$	$\triangleright \frac{5670}{149283} = \frac{6930}{182457}$
$\triangleright \frac{5628}{130479} = \frac{9380}{217465}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{197420} = \frac{8457}{296130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5648}{197320} = \frac{9178}{320645}$	$\triangleright \frac{5670}{381429} = \frac{6370}{428519}$
$\triangleright \frac{5628}{304917} = \frac{5712}{309468}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{201794} = \frac{8457}{302691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5648}{397120} = \frac{9178}{645320}$	$\triangleright \frac{5670}{489321} = \frac{9670}{834521}$
$\triangleright \frac{5628}{470139} = \frac{7420}{619835}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{201974} = \frac{8457}{302961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{120738} = \frac{7532}{160984}$	$\triangleright \frac{5670}{839241} = \frac{6370}{942851}$
$\triangleright \frac{5629}{107384} = \frac{8437}{160952}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{217940} = \frac{8457}{326910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{127380} = \frac{7532}{169840}$	$\triangleright \frac{5671}{240938} = \frac{7169}{304582}$
$\triangleright \frac{5629}{301847} = \frac{6928}{371504}$	$\triangleright \frac{5638}{219740} = \frac{8457}{329610}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{138072} = \frac{7532}{184096}$	$\triangleright \frac{5671}{324890} = \frac{7918}{453620}$
$\triangleright \frac{5632}{871904} = \frac{6320}{978415}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{138297} = \frac{7520}{184396}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{138720} = \frac{7532}{184960}$	$\triangleright \frac{5673}{129084} = \frac{5978}{136024}$
$\triangleright \frac{5634}{179802} = \frac{8451}{269703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{139872} = \frac{6390}{158472}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{172038} = \frac{9415}{286730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5673}{480192} = \frac{9021}{763584}$
$\triangleright \frac{5634}{179820} = \frac{8451}{269730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{197832} = \frac{6815}{239047}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{217083} = \frac{7014}{269538}$	$\triangleright \frac{5678}{403291} = \frac{7348}{521906}$
$\triangleright \frac{5634}{197802} = \frac{8451}{296703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{297138} = \frac{7520}{396184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{308172} = \frac{7532}{410896}$	$\triangleright \frac{5678}{439210} = \frac{9248}{715360}$
$\triangleright \frac{5634}{197820} = \frac{8451}{296730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{318792} = \frac{6580}{371924}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{327180} = \frac{5918}{342760}$	$\triangleright \frac{5679}{103428} = \frac{9465}{172380}$
$\triangleright \frac{5634}{201798} = \frac{8451}{302697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{319278} = \frac{6580}{372491}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{372081} = \frac{7532}{496108}$	$\triangleright \frac{5679}{130428} = \frac{9465}{217380}$
$\triangleright \frac{5634}{201978} = \frac{8451}{302967}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{783192} = \frac{6580}{913724}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{720138} = \frac{7532}{960184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5679}{142308} = \frac{9465}{237180}$
$\triangleright \frac{5634}{217980} = \frac{8451}{326970}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{792318} = \frac{6580}{924371}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{720813} = \frac{7532}{961084}$	$\triangleright \frac{5679}{324801} = \frac{8203}{469157}$
$\triangleright \frac{5634}{219780} = \frac{8451}{329670}$	$\triangleright \frac{5640}{871239} = \frac{6120}{945387}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{721380} = \frac{7532}{961840}$	$\triangleright \frac{5680}{213497} = \frac{8560}{321749}$
$\triangleright \frac{5634}{290178} = \frac{7512}{386904}$	$\triangleright \frac{5642}{109837} = \frac{8370}{162945}$	$\triangleright \frac{5649}{723081} = \frac{7532}{964108}$	$\triangleright \frac{5680}{231794} = \frac{8520}{347691}$

▶ $\frac{5680}{231974} = \frac{8520}{347961}$	▶ $\frac{5687}{390241} = \frac{9801}{672543}$	▶ $\frac{5698}{123704} = \frac{7326}{159048}$	▶ $\frac{5712}{309648} = \frac{6902}{374158}$
▶ $\frac{5680}{293174} = \frac{8520}{439761}$	▶ $\frac{5687}{409123} = \frac{6721}{483509}$	▶ $\frac{5698}{170324} = \frac{5809}{173642}$	▶ $\frac{5712}{348096} = \frac{8364}{509712}$
▶ $\frac{5680}{317942} = \frac{8520}{476913}$	▶ $\frac{5687}{432190} = \frac{9823}{746510}$	▶ $\frac{5698}{230174} = \frac{8954}{361702}$	▶ $\frac{5712}{463890} = \frac{9384}{762105}$
▶ $\frac{5680}{319742} = \frac{8520}{479613}$	▶ $\frac{5691}{247380} = \frac{7859}{341620}$	▶ $\frac{5698}{703241} = \frac{6142}{758039}$	▶ $\frac{5712}{480396} = \frac{8432}{709156}$
▶ $\frac{5680}{329174} = \frac{8520}{493761}$	▶ $\frac{5691}{402738} = \frac{9485}{671230}$	▶ $\frac{5703}{286194} = \frac{7604}{381592}$	▶ $\frac{5712}{483096} = \frac{6902}{583741}$
▶ $\frac{5680}{497213} = \frac{8560}{749321}$	▶ $\frac{5691}{403278} = \frac{9485}{672130}$	▶ $\frac{5703}{298614} = \frac{7604}{398152}$	▶ $\frac{5712}{690348} = \frac{7140}{862935}$
▶ $\frac{5681}{239704} = \frac{9568}{403712}$	▶ $\frac{5691}{403872} = \frac{9485}{673120}$	▶ $\frac{5704}{132986} = \frac{7936}{185024}$	▶ $\frac{5713}{642089} = \frac{8471}{952063}$
▶ $\frac{5681}{379240} = \frac{6578}{439120}$	▶ $\frac{5691}{743082} = \frac{7308}{954216}$	▶ $\frac{5704}{168392} = \frac{9637}{284501}$	▶ $\frac{5714}{269308} = \frac{8571}{403962}$
▶ $\frac{5681}{397024} = \frac{8073}{564192}$	▶ $\frac{5694}{123078} = \frac{7098}{153426}$	▶ $\frac{5704}{169832} = \frac{9641}{287053}$	▶ $\frac{5714}{293068} = \frac{8571}{439602}$
▶ $\frac{5681}{497302} = \frac{7429}{650318}$	▶ $\frac{5694}{138027} = \frac{7592}{184036}$	▶ $\frac{5704}{238916} = \frac{7130}{298645}$	▶ $\frac{5714}{306928} = \frac{8571}{460392}$
▶ $\frac{5681}{739024} = \frac{7084}{921536}$	▶ $\frac{5694}{138270} = \frac{7592}{184360}$	▶ $\frac{5704}{293618} = \frac{7936}{408512}$	▶ $\frac{5714}{309268} = \frac{8571}{463902}$
▶ $\frac{5682}{307194} = \frac{8523}{460791}$	▶ $\frac{5694}{170382} = \frac{8073}{241569}$	▶ $\frac{5704}{312968} = \frac{6417}{352089}$	▶ $\frac{5714}{326908} = \frac{8571}{490362}$
▶ $\frac{5682}{317940} = \frac{8523}{476910}$	▶ $\frac{5694}{271830} = \frac{6789}{324105}$	▶ $\frac{5704}{398612} = \frac{7130}{498265}$	▶ $\frac{5714}{329068} = \frac{8571}{493602}$
▶ $\frac{5682}{319740} = \frac{8523}{479610}$	▶ $\frac{5694}{370812} = \frac{8103}{527694}$	▶ $\frac{5708}{269314} = \frac{8562}{403971}$	▶ $\frac{5716}{238904} = \frac{7145}{298630}$
▶ $\frac{5682}{370941} = \frac{9470}{618235}$	▶ $\frac{5694}{810732} = \frac{6351}{904278}$	▶ $\frac{5708}{291346} = \frac{8562}{437019}$	▶ $\frac{5716}{290384} = \frac{7145}{362980}$
▶ $\frac{5684}{120379} = \frac{8260}{174935}$	▶ $\frac{5697}{138024} = \frac{7596}{184032}$	▶ $\frac{5708}{326914} = \frac{8562}{490371}$	▶ $\frac{5720}{138496} = \frac{7865}{190432}$
▶ $\frac{5684}{190327} = \frac{9604}{321587}$	▶ $\frac{5697}{138240} = \frac{7596}{184320}$	▶ $\frac{5708}{629134} = \frac{8562}{943701}$	▶ $\frac{5720}{143968} = \frac{9815}{247036}$
▶ $\frac{5684}{273910} = \frac{7192}{346580}$	▶ $\frac{5697}{240138} = \frac{7596}{320184}$	▶ $\frac{5708}{691432} = \frac{7135}{864290}$	▶ $\frac{5720}{391864} = \frac{9815}{672403}$
▶ $\frac{5684}{739210} = \frac{6174}{802935}$	▶ $\frac{5697}{241380} = \frac{7596}{321840}$	▶ $\frac{5709}{132864} = \frac{7029}{163584}$	▶ $\frac{5720}{439816} = \frac{9185}{706243}$

$\triangleright \frac{5720}{468391} = \frac{7280}{596134}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{129048} = \frac{8604}{193572}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{198362} = \frac{8610}{297543}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{160398} = \frac{8613}{240597}$
$\triangleright \frac{5720}{483691} = \frac{7480}{632519}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{481290} = \frac{8604}{721935}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{218396} = \frac{8610}{327594}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{163980} = \frac{8613}{245970}$
$\triangleright \frac{5720}{631984} = \frac{6435}{710982}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{490128} = \frac{8604}{735192}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{219638} = \frac{8610}{329457}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{180396} = \frac{8613}{270594}$
$\triangleright \frac{5720}{639184} = \frac{6435}{719082}$	$\triangleright \frac{5736}{492810} = \frac{8604}{739215}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{219836} = \frac{8610}{329754}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{183960} = \frac{8613}{275940}$
$\triangleright \frac{5723}{416809} = \frac{8791}{640253}$	$\triangleright \frac{5738}{142906} = \frac{8607}{214359}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{231968} = \frac{8610}{347952}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{196038} = \frac{8613}{294057}$
$\triangleright \frac{5724}{193860} = \frac{8109}{274635}$	$\triangleright \frac{5738}{146290} = \frac{8607}{219435}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{236198} = \frac{8610}{354297}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{196380} = \frac{8613}{294570}$
$\triangleright \frac{5724}{380169} = \frac{7236}{480591}$	$\triangleright \frac{5738}{269401} = \frac{8456}{397012}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{238196} = \frac{8610}{357294}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{198036} = \frac{8613}{297054}$
$\triangleright \frac{5724}{689013} = \frac{7420}{893165}$	$\triangleright \frac{5738}{401962} = \frac{7068}{495132}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{239618} = \frac{8610}{359427}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{198360} = \frac{8613}{297540}$
$\triangleright \frac{5726}{193048} = \frac{6398}{215704}$	$\triangleright \frac{5738}{619402} = \frac{7904}{853216}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{316928} = \frac{8610}{475392}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{319680} = \frac{8613}{479520}$
$\triangleright \frac{5728}{306914} = \frac{8592}{460371}$	$\triangleright \frac{5739}{104286} = \frac{7652}{139048}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{319682} = \frac{8610}{479523}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{360198} = \frac{8613}{540297}$
$\triangleright \frac{5728}{409136} = \frac{8592}{613704}$	$\triangleright \frac{5739}{610428} = \frac{7652}{813904}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{329168} = \frac{8610}{493752}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{361980} = \frac{8613}{542970}$
$\triangleright \frac{5729}{430168} = \frac{9436}{708512}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{162398} = \frac{8610}{243597}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{361982} = \frac{8610}{542973}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{380196} = \frac{8613}{570294}$
$\triangleright \frac{5729}{608413} = \frac{8762}{930514}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{163982} = \frac{8610}{245973}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{362198} = \frac{8610}{543297}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{381960} = \frac{8613}{572940}$
$\triangleright \frac{5730}{692184} = \frac{7560}{913248}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{182396} = \frac{8610}{273594}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{381962} = \frac{8610}{572943}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{396018} = \frac{8613}{594027}$
$\triangleright \frac{5734}{182906} = \frac{8601}{274359}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{183962} = \frac{8610}{275943}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{382196} = \frac{8610}{573294}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{396180} = \frac{8613}{594270}$
$\triangleright \frac{5734}{186290} = \frac{8601}{279435}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{192836} = \frac{6970}{234158}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{396182} = \frac{8610}{594273}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{398016} = \frac{8613}{597024}$
$\triangleright \frac{5736}{104289} = \frac{7648}{139052}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{196238} = \frac{8610}{294357}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{396218} = \frac{8610}{594327}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{398160} = \frac{8613}{597240}$
$\triangleright \frac{5736}{104928} = \frac{8604}{157392}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{196382} = \frac{8610}{294573}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{398162} = \frac{8610}{597243}$	$\triangleright \frac{5742}{631098} = \frac{7326}{805194}$
$\triangleright \frac{5736}{128490} = \frac{8604}{192735}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{198236} = \frac{8610}{297354}$	$\triangleright \frac{5740}{398216} = \frac{8610}{597324}$	$\triangleright \frac{5746}{103298} = \frac{7956}{143028}$

$\triangleright \frac{5746}{138290} = \frac{8619}{207435}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{342198} = \frac{8640}{513297}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{198340} = \frac{8643}{297510}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{304192} = \frac{8652}{479103}$
$\triangleright \frac{5746}{231098} = \frac{8957}{360241}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{349182} = \frac{8960}{543172}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{340198} = \frac{8643}{510297}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{312904} = \frac{6489}{352017}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{142398} = \frac{8640}{213597}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{381942} = \frac{8640}{572913}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{341980} = \frac{8643}{512970}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{319402} = \frac{8652}{479103}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{143982} = \frac{8640}{215973}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{382194} = \frac{8640}{573291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{380194} = \frac{8643}{570291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{319420} = \frac{8652}{479130}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{182394} = \frac{8640}{273591}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{394182} = \frac{8640}{591273}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{381940} = \frac{8643}{572910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{329140} = \frac{8652}{493710}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{183942} = \frac{8640}{275913}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{394218} = \frac{8640}{591327}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{394018} = \frac{8643}{591027}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{409312} = \frac{7931}{562804}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{194238} = \frac{8640}{291357}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{398142} = \frac{8640}{597213}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{394180} = \frac{8643}{591270}$	$\triangleright \frac{5769}{143082} = \frac{9615}{238470}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{194382} = \frac{8640}{291573}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{398214} = \frac{8640}{597321}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{398014} = \frac{8643}{597021}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{142396} = \frac{8670}{213594}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{198234} = \frac{8640}{297351}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{482913} = \frac{8320}{697541}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{398140} = \frac{8643}{597210}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{143962} = \frac{8670}{215943}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{198342} = \frac{8640}{297513}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{489312} = \frac{7580}{643921}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{418390} = \frac{6298}{457310}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{162394} = \frac{8670}{243591}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{214398} = \frac{8640}{321597}$	$\triangleright \frac{5760}{918432} = \frac{6120}{975834}$	$\triangleright \frac{5763}{104289} = \frac{7684}{139052}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{163942} = \frac{8670}{245913}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{218394} = \frac{8640}{327591}$	$\triangleright \frac{5761}{849023} = \frac{6584}{970312}$	$\triangleright \frac{5763}{819024} = \frac{6273}{891504}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{194236} = \frac{8670}{291354}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{219438} = \frac{8640}{329157}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{140398} = \frac{8643}{210597}$	$\triangleright \frac{57632}{91840} = \frac{61234}{97580}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{194362} = \frac{8670}{291543}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{219834} = \frac{8640}{329751}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{143980} = \frac{8643}{215970}$	$\triangleright \frac{5764}{198203} = \frac{6908}{237541}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{196234} = \frac{8670}{294351}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{234198} = \frac{8640}{351297}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{180394} = \frac{8643}{270591}$	$\triangleright \frac{5764}{302819} = \frac{7860}{412935}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{196342} = \frac{8670}{294513}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{238194} = \frac{8640}{357291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{183940} = \frac{8643}{275910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{193024} = \frac{7931}{265408}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{214396} = \frac{8670}{321594}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{239418} = \frac{8640}{359127}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{194038} = \frac{8643}{291057}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{203194} = \frac{8652}{304791}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{216394} = \frac{8670}{324591}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{239814} = \frac{8640}{359721}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{194380} = \frac{8643}{291570}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{231940} = \frac{8652}{347910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{219436} = \frac{8670}{329154}$
$\triangleright \frac{5760}{341982} = \frac{8640}{512973}$	$\triangleright \frac{5762}{198034} = \frac{8643}{297051}$	$\triangleright \frac{5768}{293140} = \frac{8652}{439710}$	$\triangleright \frac{5780}{219634} = \frac{8670}{329451}$

$\triangleright \frac{5780}{234196} = \frac{8670}{351294}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{196340} = \frac{8673}{294510}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{163820} = \frac{8691}{245730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{238016} = \frac{8691}{357024}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{236194} = \frac{8670}{354291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{340196} = \frac{8673}{510294}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{180236} = \frac{8691}{270354}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{238160} = \frac{8691}{357240}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{239416} = \frac{8670}{359124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{341960} = \frac{8673}{512940}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{180362} = \frac{8691}{270543}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{316802} = \frac{8691}{475203}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{239614} = \frac{8670}{359421}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{360194} = \frac{8673}{540291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{182036} = \frac{8691}{273054}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{316820} = \frac{8691}{475230}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{341962} = \frac{8670}{512943}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{361940} = \frac{8673}{542910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{182360} = \frac{8691}{273540}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{360182} = \frac{8691}{540273}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{342196} = \frac{8670}{513294}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{394016} = \frac{8673}{591024}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{183602} = \frac{8691}{275403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{360218} = \frac{8691}{540327}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{361942} = \frac{8670}{542913}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{394160} = \frac{8673}{591240}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{183620} = \frac{8691}{275430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{361802} = \frac{8691}{542703}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{362194} = \frac{8670}{543291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{396014} = \frac{8673}{594021}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{201638} = \frac{8691}{302457}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{361820} = \frac{8691}{542730}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{394162} = \frac{8670}{591243}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{396140} = \frac{8673}{594210}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{201836} = \frac{8691}{302754}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{362018} = \frac{8691}{543027}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{394216} = \frac{8670}{591324}$	$\triangleright \frac{5782}{496013} = \frac{8526}{731409}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{203168} = \frac{8691}{304752}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{362180} = \frac{8691}{543270}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{396142} = \frac{8670}{594213}$	$\triangleright \frac{57823}{61904} = \frac{58914}{63072}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{203618} = \frac{8691}{305427}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{380162} = \frac{8691}{570243}$
$\triangleright \frac{5780}{396214} = \frac{8670}{594321}$	$\triangleright \frac{5786}{120439} = \frac{7890}{164235}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{203816} = \frac{8691}{305724}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{380216} = \frac{8691}{570324}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{136409} = \frac{9086}{214357}$	$\triangleright \frac{5786}{134290} = \frac{8679}{201435}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{216038} = \frac{8691}{324057}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{381602} = \frac{8691}{572403}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{140396} = \frac{8673}{210594}$	$\triangleright \frac{5792}{361048} = \frac{9412}{586703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{216380} = \frac{8691}{324570}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{381620} = \frac{8691}{572430}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{160394} = \frac{8673}{240591}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{160238} = \frac{8691}{240357}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{218036} = \frac{8691}{327054}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{382016} = \frac{8691}{573024}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{163940} = \frac{8673}{245910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{160382} = \frac{8691}{240573}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{218360} = \frac{8691}{327540}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{382160} = \frac{8691}{573240}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{194036} = \frac{8673}{291054}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{162038} = \frac{8691}{243057}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{231680} = \frac{8691}{347520}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{130284} = \frac{7084}{159236}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{194360} = \frac{8673}{291540}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{162380} = \frac{8691}{243570}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{236018} = \frac{8691}{354027}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{130824} = \frac{7308}{164952}$
$\triangleright \frac{5782}{196034} = \frac{8673}{294051}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{163802} = \frac{8691}{245703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5794}{236180} = \frac{8691}{354270}$	$\triangleright \frac{5796}{132480} = \frac{9387}{214560}$

▶ $\frac{5796}{140238} = \frac{8694}{210357}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{218034} = \frac{8694}{327051}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{438012} = \frac{7812}{590364}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{216034} = \frac{8697}{324051}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{140382} = \frac{8694}{210573}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{218340} = \frac{8694}{327510}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{481320} = \frac{6417}{532890}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{216340} = \frac{8697}{324510}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{142038} = \frac{8694}{213057}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{234018} = \frac{8694}{351027}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{140236} = \frac{8697}{210354}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{234016} = \frac{8697}{351024}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{142380} = \frac{8694}{213570}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{234180} = \frac{8694}{351270}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{140362} = \frac{8697}{210543}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{234160} = \frac{8697}{351240}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{143802} = \frac{8694}{215703}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{238014} = \frac{8694}{357021}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{142036} = \frac{8697}{213054}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{236014} = \frac{8697}{354021}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{143820} = \frac{8694}{215730}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{238140} = \frac{8694}{357210}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{142360} = \frac{8697}{213540}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{236140} = \frac{8697}{354210}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{180234} = \frac{8694}{270351}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{318024} = \frac{6417}{352098}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{143602} = \frac{8697}{215403}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{263140} = \frac{5837}{264910}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{180342} = \frac{8694}{270513}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{340182} = \frac{8694}{510273}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{143620} = \frac{8697}{215430}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{340162} = \frac{8697}{510243}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{182034} = \frac{8694}{273051}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{340218} = \frac{8694}{510327}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{160234} = \frac{8697}{240351}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{340216} = \frac{8697}{510324}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{182340} = \frac{8694}{273510}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{341802} = \frac{8694}{512703}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{162034} = \frac{8697}{243051}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{341602} = \frac{8697}{512403}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{183402} = \frac{8694}{275103}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{341820} = \frac{8694}{512730}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{162340} = \frac{8697}{243510}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{341620} = \frac{8697}{512430}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{183420} = \frac{8694}{275130}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{342018} = \frac{8694}{513027}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{163402} = \frac{8697}{245103}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{342016} = \frac{8697}{513024}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{184230} = \frac{9478}{301265}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{380142} = \frac{8694}{570213}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{163420} = \frac{8697}{245130}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{342160} = \frac{8697}{513240}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{201438} = \frac{8694}{302157}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{380214} = \frac{8694}{570321}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{201436} = \frac{8697}{302154}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{360142} = \frac{8697}{540213}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{201834} = \frac{8694}{302751}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{381402} = \frac{8694}{572103}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{201634} = \frac{8697}{302451}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{360214} = \frac{8697}{540321}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{203418} = \frac{8694}{305127}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{381420} = \frac{8694}{572130}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{203416} = \frac{8697}{305124}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{361402} = \frac{8697}{542103}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{203814} = \frac{8694}{305721}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{382014} = \frac{8694}{573021}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{203614} = \frac{8697}{305421}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{361420} = \frac{8697}{542130}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{214038} = \frac{8694}{321057}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{382140} = \frac{8694}{573210}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{214036} = \frac{8697}{321054}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{362014} = \frac{8697}{543021}$
▶ $\frac{5796}{214380} = \frac{8694}{321570}$	▶ $\frac{5796}{412083} = \frac{8740}{621395}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{214360} = \frac{8697}{321540}$	▶ $\frac{5798}{362140} = \frac{8697}{543210}$

$\triangleright \frac{5802}{143796} = \frac{8703}{215694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5802}{379614} = \frac{8703}{569421}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{379602} = \frac{8721}{569403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{143796} = \frac{8730}{215694}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{143976} = \frac{8703}{215964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5802}{394176} = \frac{8703}{591264}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{379620} = \frac{8721}{569430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{163794} = \frac{8730}{245691}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{163794} = \frac{8703}{245691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5802}{396174} = \frac{8703}{594261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{397602} = \frac{8721}{596403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{163974} = \frac{8730}{245961}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{163974} = \frac{8703}{245961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5802}{397416} = \frac{8703}{596124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{397620} = \frac{8721}{596430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{174396} = \frac{8730}{261594}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{174396} = \frac{8703}{261594}$	$\triangleright \frac{5802}{397614} = \frac{8703}{596421}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{670293} = \frac{6954}{801723}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{176394} = \frac{8730}{264591}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{176394} = \frac{8703}{264591}$	$\triangleright \frac{5803}{162974} = \frac{7461}{209538}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{673290} = \frac{7429}{860315}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{179436} = \frac{8730}{269154}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{179436} = \frac{8703}{269154}$	$\triangleright \frac{5803}{279146} = \frac{7461}{358902}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{690327} = \frac{5916}{702438}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{179634} = \frac{8730}{269451}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{179634} = \frac{8703}{269451}$	$\triangleright \frac{5803}{624197} = \frac{7461}{802539}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{203794} = \frac{8724}{305691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{194376} = \frac{8730}{291564}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{194376} = \frac{8703}{291564}$	$\triangleright \frac{5803}{762419} = \frac{7461}{980253}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{203974} = \frac{8724}{305961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{196374} = \frac{8730}{294561}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{196374} = \frac{8703}{294561}$	$\triangleright \frac{5809}{176342} = \frac{6751}{204938}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{237940} = \frac{8724}{356910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{197436} = \frac{8730}{296154}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{197436} = \frac{8703}{296154}$	$\triangleright \frac{5809}{371462} = \frac{7918}{506324}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{379402} = \frac{8724}{569103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{197634} = \frac{8730}{296451}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{197634} = \frac{8703}{296451}$	$\triangleright \frac{5809}{637214} = \frac{8635}{947210}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{379420} = \frac{8724}{569130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{341796} = \frac{8730}{512694}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{341796} = \frac{8703}{512694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5810}{379642} = \frac{7980}{521436}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{397402} = \frac{8724}{596103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{341976} = \frac{8730}{512964}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{341976} = \frac{8703}{512964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5812}{679304} = \frac{7265}{849130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5816}{397420} = \frac{8724}{596130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{361794} = \frac{8730}{542691}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{361794} = \frac{8703}{542691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{203976} = \frac{8721}{305964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5819}{264730} = \frac{9361}{425870}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{361974} = \frac{8730}{542961}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{361974} = \frac{8703}{542961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{207936} = \frac{5967}{213408}$	$\triangleright \frac{5819}{302764} = \frac{7935}{412860}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{374196} = \frac{8730}{561294}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{374196} = \frac{8703}{561294}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{237960} = \frac{8721}{356940}$	$\triangleright \frac{5819}{306724} = \frac{7935}{418260}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{376194} = \frac{8730}{564291}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{376194} = \frac{8703}{564291}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{239760} = \frac{8721}{359640}$	$\triangleright \frac{5819}{724306} = \frac{6348}{790152}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{379416} = \frac{8730}{569124}$
$\triangleright \frac{5802}{379416} = \frac{8703}{569124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5814}{270963} = \frac{8512}{396704}$	$\triangleright \frac{5819}{734206} = \frac{6302}{795148}$	$\triangleright \frac{5820}{379614} = \frac{8730}{569421}$

$\triangleright \frac{5820}{394176} = \frac{8730}{591264}$	$\triangleright \frac{5826}{374901} = \frac{9710}{624835}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{201796} = \frac{8751}{302694}$	$\triangleright \frac{5860}{734912} = \frac{7325}{918640}$
$\triangleright \frac{5820}{396174} = \frac{8730}{594261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5829}{143076} = \frac{9715}{238460}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{201976} = \frac{8751}{302964}$	$\triangleright \frac{5862}{137094} = \frac{8793}{205641}$
$\triangleright \frac{5820}{397416} = \frac{8730}{596124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5829}{371046} = \frac{7308}{465192}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{217960} = \frac{8751}{326940}$	$\triangleright \frac{5862}{170934} = \frac{8793}{256401}$
$\triangleright \frac{5820}{397614} = \frac{8730}{596421}$	$\triangleright \frac{5829}{436170} = \frac{6873}{514290}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{219760} = \frac{8751}{329640}$	$\triangleright \frac{5862}{307149} = \frac{7816}{409532}$
$\triangleright \frac{5820}{436791} = \frac{8340}{625917}$	$\triangleright \frac{5831}{496027} = \frac{6902}{587134}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{109472} = \frac{7295}{136840}$	$\triangleright \frac{5862}{371490} = \frac{7816}{495320}$
$\triangleright \frac{5820}{479316} = \frac{8245}{679031}$	$\triangleright \frac{5831}{602749} = \frac{6902}{713458}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{149072} = \frac{7295}{186340}$	$\triangleright \frac{5862}{714903} = \frac{7816}{953204}$
$\triangleright \frac{5823}{174690} = \frac{5832}{174960}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{107946} = \frac{6804}{125937}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{179402} = \frac{8754}{269103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5862}{714930} = \frac{7816}{953240}$
$\triangleright \frac{5824}{107936} = \frac{7826}{145039}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{109476} = \frac{7290}{136845}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{179420} = \frac{8754}{269130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5863}{174209} = \frac{8437}{250691}$
$\triangleright \frac{5824}{130796} = \frac{7280}{163495}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{109674} = \frac{6804}{127953}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{197402} = \frac{8754}{296103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5863}{472901} = \frac{6314}{509278}$
$\triangleright \frac{5824}{301769} = \frac{6720}{348195}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{149076} = \frac{7290}{186345}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{197420} = \frac{8754}{296130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5863}{729014} = \frac{6314}{785092}$
$\triangleright \frac{5824}{637091} = \frac{8704}{952136}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{169074} = \frac{6804}{197253}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{201794} = \frac{8754}{302691}$	$\triangleright \frac{5864}{731920} = \frac{6597}{823410}$
$\triangleright \frac{5824}{730916} = \frac{7280}{913645}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{417960} = \frac{6318}{452790}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{201974} = \frac{8754}{302961}$	$\triangleright \frac{5871}{294063} = \frac{6489}{325017}$
$\triangleright \frac{5824}{761930} = \frac{6048}{791235}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{460971} = \frac{7128}{563409}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{217940} = \frac{8754}{326910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5871}{360294} = \frac{8379}{514206}$
$\triangleright \frac{5824}{917630} = \frac{6240}{983175}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{491076} = \frac{7290}{613845}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{219740} = \frac{8754}{329610}$	$\triangleright \frac{5871}{426930} = \frac{7416}{539280}$
$\triangleright \frac{5824}{930176} = \frac{6083}{971542}$	$\triangleright \frac{5832}{610794} = \frac{6804}{712593}$	$\triangleright \frac{5836}{491072} = \frac{7295}{613840}$	$\triangleright \frac{5871}{493620} = \frac{8961}{753420}$
$\triangleright \frac{5826}{137094} = \frac{8739}{205641}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{179602} = \frac{8751}{269403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5837}{129064} = \frac{6735}{148920}$	$\triangleright \frac{5872}{149036} = \frac{7340}{186295}$
$\triangleright \frac{5826}{143079} = \frac{9710}{238465}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{179620} = \frac{8751}{269430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5837}{249106} = \frac{7184}{306592}$	$\triangleright \frac{5872}{490316} = \frac{7340}{612895}$
$\triangleright \frac{5826}{170934} = \frac{8739}{256401}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{197602} = \frac{8751}{296403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5860}{134792} = \frac{7325}{168490}$	$\triangleright \frac{5873}{160249} = \frac{9037}{246581}$
$\triangleright \frac{5826}{374091} = \frac{9710}{623485}$	$\triangleright \frac{5834}{197620} = \frac{8751}{296430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5860}{149723} = \frac{7260}{185493}$	$\triangleright \frac{5874}{103692} = \frac{6853}{120974}$

$\triangleright \frac{5874}{109632} = \frac{6853}{127904}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{364728} = \frac{8149}{503672}$	$\triangleright \frac{5913}{470286} = \frac{8541}{679302}$	$\triangleright \frac{5928}{340176} = \frac{7293}{418506}$
$\triangleright \frac{5874}{163092} = \frac{6853}{190274}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{367482} = \frac{9835}{612470}$	$\triangleright \frac{5913}{482760} = \frac{8541}{697320}$	$\triangleright \frac{5928}{401736} = \frac{8931}{605247}$
$\triangleright \frac{5874}{169032} = \frac{6853}{197204}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{374826} = \frac{9835}{624710}$	$\triangleright \frac{5913}{674082} = \frac{8136}{927504}$	$\triangleright \frac{5928}{413706} = \frac{9152}{638704}$
$\triangleright \frac{5874}{639210} = \frac{7654}{832910}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{376284} = \frac{9835}{627140}$	$\triangleright \frac{5913}{684207} = \frac{6132}{709548}$	$\triangleright \frac{5932}{671408} = \frac{7415}{839260}$
$\triangleright \frac{5876}{123409} = \frac{6780}{142395}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{376824} = \frac{8149}{520376}$	$\triangleright \frac{5916}{248370} = \frac{7018}{294635}$	$\triangleright \frac{5932}{714608} = \frac{7415}{893260}$
$\triangleright \frac{5876}{149032} = \frac{7345}{186290}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{382746} = \frac{9273}{601458}$	$\triangleright \frac{5916}{270348} = \frac{9367}{428051}$	$\triangleright \frac{5932}{786104} = \frac{7415}{982630}$
$\triangleright \frac{5876}{490312} = \frac{7345}{612890}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{384762} = \frac{9835}{641270}$	$\triangleright \frac{5916}{370248} = \frac{7395}{462810}$	$\triangleright \frac{5934}{210786} = \frac{7314}{259806}$
$\triangleright \frac{5876}{493012} = \frac{8362}{701594}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{432876} = \frac{9835}{721460}$	$\triangleright \frac{5916}{387204} = \frac{6902}{451738}$	$\triangleright \frac{5934}{687210} = \frac{6923}{801745}$
$\triangleright \frac{5890}{172634} = \frac{9145}{268037}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{437682} = \frac{7306}{541892}$	$\triangleright \frac{5916}{432807} = \frac{9860}{721345}$	$\triangleright \frac{5936}{104728} = \frac{9534}{168207}$
$\triangleright \frac{5890}{174623} = \frac{8930}{264751}$	$\triangleright \frac{5901}{438627} = \frac{8149}{605723}$	$\triangleright \frac{5916}{438702} = \frac{7308}{541926}$	$\triangleright \frac{5936}{108472} = \frac{9328}{170456}$
$\triangleright \frac{5891}{260437} = \frac{6493}{287051}$	$\triangleright \frac{5904}{137628} = \frac{7052}{164389}$	$\triangleright \frac{5916}{473802} = \frac{7854}{629013}$	$\triangleright \frac{5936}{128704} = \frac{7049}{152836}$
$\triangleright \frac{5892}{103674} = \frac{6874}{120953}$	$\triangleright \frac{5904}{286713} = \frac{7920}{384615}$	$\triangleright \frac{5916}{480327} = \frac{7820}{634915}$	$\triangleright \frac{5936}{184072} = \frac{6042}{187359}$
$\triangleright \frac{5892}{163074} = \frac{6874}{190253}$	$\triangleright \frac{5904}{376281} = \frac{9840}{627135}$	$\triangleright \frac{5916}{703482} = \frac{7310}{869245}$	$\triangleright \frac{5936}{412870} = \frac{6832}{475190}$
$\triangleright \frac{5892}{167340} = \frac{6874}{195230}$	$\triangleright \frac{5907}{248631} = \frac{6039}{254187}$	$\triangleright \frac{5917}{304268} = \frac{9215}{473860}$	$\triangleright \frac{5936}{702184} = \frac{6254}{739801}$
$\triangleright \frac{5892}{370461} = \frac{9820}{617435}$	$\triangleright \frac{5907}{432816} = \frac{9845}{721360}$	$\triangleright \frac{5920}{174368} = \frac{8140}{239756}$	$\triangleright \frac{5936}{704128} = \frac{7049}{836152}$
$\triangleright \frac{5892}{417360} = \frac{8347}{591260}$	$\triangleright \frac{5907}{634821} = \frac{6981}{750243}$	$\triangleright \frac{5920}{387416} = \frac{8140}{532697}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{138267} = \frac{7920}{184356}$
$\triangleright \frac{5896}{103247} = \frac{9064}{158723}$	$\triangleright \frac{5908}{271346} = \frac{8092}{371654}$	$\triangleright \frac{5920}{834176} = \frac{6475}{912380}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{162378} = \frac{8910}{243567}$
$\triangleright \frac{5896}{132704} = \frac{8576}{193024}$	$\triangleright \frac{5908}{342167} = \frac{6752}{391048}$	$\triangleright \frac{5928}{137046} = \frac{8436}{195027}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{163782} = \frac{8910}{245673}$
$\triangleright \frac{5896}{403172} = \frac{7102}{485639}$	$\triangleright \frac{5913}{420876} = \frac{8541}{607932}$	$\triangleright \frac{5928}{307164} = \frac{8930}{462715}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{176238} = \frac{8910}{264357}$

$\triangleright \frac{5940}{176382} = \frac{8910}{264573}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{361782} = \frac{8910}{542673}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{178360} = \frac{8913}{267540}$	$\triangleright \frac{5946}{187320} = \frac{6937}{218540}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{178236} = \frac{8910}{267354}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{362178} = \frac{8910}{543267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{180376} = \frac{8913}{270564}$	$\triangleright \frac{5946}{378102} = \frac{7928}{504136}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{178362} = \frac{8910}{267543}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{376182} = \frac{8910}{564273}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{183760} = \frac{8913}{275640}$	$\triangleright \frac{5946}{732018} = \frac{6937}{854021}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{182376} = \frac{8910}{273564}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{376218} = \frac{8910}{564327}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{307168} = \frac{8913}{460752}$	$\triangleright \frac{5946}{732180} = \frac{6937}{854210}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{183762} = \frac{8910}{275643}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{378162} = \frac{8910}{567243}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{316708} = \frac{8913}{475062}$	$\triangleright \frac{5947}{230681} = \frac{7581}{294063}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{187326} = \frac{6930}{218547}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{378216} = \frac{8910}{567324}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{317068} = \frac{8913}{475602}$	$\triangleright \frac{5947}{260813} = \frac{8451}{370629}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{216378} = \frac{8910}{324567}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{381762} = \frac{8910}{572643}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{317680} = \frac{8913}{476520}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{132784} = \frac{6705}{149382}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{217638} = \frac{8910}{326457}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{382176} = \frac{8910}{573264}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{360178} = \frac{8913}{540267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{142378} = \frac{8940}{213567}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{217836} = \frac{8910}{326754}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{618732} = \frac{6930}{721854}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{361780} = \frac{8913}{542670}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{143782} = \frac{8940}{215673}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{218376} = \frac{8910}{327564}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{671328} = \frac{7425}{839160}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{376018} = \frac{8913}{564027}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{174238} = \frac{8940}{261357}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{231768} = \frac{8910}{347652}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{673218} = \frac{6930}{785421}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{376180} = \frac{8913}{564270}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{174382} = \frac{8940}{261573}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{236178} = \frac{8910}{354267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{732186} = \frac{6930}{854217}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{378016} = \frac{8913}{567024}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{178234} = \frac{8940}{267351}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{237618} = \frac{8910}{356427}$	$\triangleright \frac{5940}{732618} = \frac{6930}{854721}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{378160} = \frac{8913}{567240}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{178342} = \frac{8940}{267513}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{237816} = \frac{8910}{356724}$	$\triangleright \frac{5941}{726830} = \frac{7312}{894560}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{380176} = \frac{8913}{570264}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{182374} = \frac{8940}{273561}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{238176} = \frac{8910}{357264}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{160378} = \frac{8913}{240567}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{381760} = \frac{8913}{572640}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{183742} = \frac{8940}{275613}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{267138} = \frac{7920}{356184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{163780} = \frac{8913}{245670}$	$\triangleright \frac{5943}{286170} = \frac{7924}{381560}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{214378} = \frac{8940}{321567}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{286173} = \frac{7920}{381564}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{176038} = \frac{8913}{264057}$	$\triangleright \frac{5946}{102378} = \frac{7928}{136504}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{217438} = \frac{8940}{326157}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{317682} = \frac{8910}{476523}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{176380} = \frac{8913}{264570}$	$\triangleright \frac{5946}{107832} = \frac{6937}{125804}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{217834} = \frac{8940}{326751}$
$\triangleright \frac{5940}{328617} = \frac{7920}{438156}$	$\triangleright \frac{5942}{178036} = \frac{8913}{267054}$	$\triangleright \frac{5946}{180732} = \frac{6937}{210854}$	$\triangleright \frac{5960}{218374} = \frac{8940}{327561}$

$\triangleright \frac{5960}{234178} = \frac{8940}{351267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{180374} = \frac{8943}{270561}$	$\triangleright \frac{5967}{240138} = \frac{7956}{320184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5973}{286140} = \frac{7964}{381520}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{237418} = \frac{8940}{356127}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{183740} = \frac{8943}{275610}$	$\triangleright \frac{5967}{241380} = \frac{7956}{321840}$	$\triangleright \frac{5973}{461802} = \frac{8145}{629730}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{237814} = \frac{8940}{356721}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{340178} = \frac{8943}{510267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5967}{310284} = \frac{6579}{342108}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{138620} = \frac{6283}{145790}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{238174} = \frac{8940}{357261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{341780} = \frac{8943}{512670}$	$\triangleright \frac{5967}{320814} = \frac{7803}{419526}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{160238} = \frac{8961}{240357}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{341782} = \frac{8940}{512673}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{374018} = \frac{8943}{561027}$	$\triangleright \frac{5968}{203174} = \frac{8952}{304761}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{160382} = \frac{8961}{240573}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{342178} = \frac{8940}{513267}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{374180} = \frac{8943}{561270}$	$\triangleright \frac{5968}{230714} = \frac{8952}{346071}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{162038} = \frac{8961}{243057}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{374182} = \frac{8940}{561273}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{378014} = \frac{8943}{567021}$	$\triangleright \frac{5968}{231740} = \frac{8952}{347610}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{162380} = \frac{8961}{243570}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{374218} = \frac{8940}{561327}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{378140} = \frac{8943}{567210}$	$\triangleright \frac{5968}{307142} = \frac{8952}{460713}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{163802} = \frac{8961}{245703}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{378142} = \frac{8940}{567213}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{380174} = \frac{8943}{570261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5968}{317402} = \frac{8952}{476103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{163820} = \frac{8961}{245730}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{378214} = \frac{8940}{567321}$	$\triangleright \frac{5962}{381740} = \frac{8943}{572610}$	$\triangleright \frac{5968}{317420} = \frac{8952}{476130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{180236} = \frac{8961}{270354}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{381742} = \frac{8940}{572613}$	$\triangleright \frac{5964}{130782} = \frac{9870}{216435}$	$\triangleright \frac{5968}{417032} = \frac{8206}{573419}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{180362} = \frac{8961}{270543}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{382174} = \frac{8940}{573261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5964}{138027} = \frac{7952}{184036}$	$\triangleright \frac{5968}{713240} = \frac{6714}{802395}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{182036} = \frac{8961}{273054}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{384271} = \frac{6120}{394587}$	$\triangleright \frac{5964}{138270} = \frac{7952}{184360}$	$\triangleright \frac{5970}{138264} = \frac{7960}{184352}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{182360} = \frac{8961}{273540}$
$\triangleright \frac{5960}{814732} = \frac{6740}{921358}$	$\triangleright \frac{5964}{203178} = \frac{6958}{237041}$	$\triangleright \frac{5970}{264138} = \frac{7960}{352184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{183602} = \frac{8961}{275403}$
$\triangleright \frac{5962}{143780} = \frac{8943}{215670}$	$\triangleright \frac{5964}{270138} = \frac{7952}{360184}$	$\triangleright \frac{5970}{286143} = \frac{7960}{381524}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{183620} = \frac{8961}{275430}$
$\triangleright \frac{5962}{174038} = \frac{8943}{261057}$	$\triangleright \frac{5964}{271380} = \frac{7952}{361840}$	$\triangleright \frac{5972}{103864} = \frac{7465}{129830}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{201638} = \frac{8961}{302457}$
$\triangleright \frac{5962}{174380} = \frac{8943}{261570}$	$\triangleright \frac{5967}{134082} = \frac{6273}{140958}$	$\triangleright \frac{5972}{106384} = \frac{7465}{132980}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{201836} = \frac{8961}{302754}$
$\triangleright \frac{5962}{178034} = \frac{8943}{267051}$	$\triangleright \frac{5967}{138024} = \frac{7956}{184032}$	$\triangleright \frac{5973}{180642} = \frac{7059}{213486}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{203168} = \frac{8961}{304752}$
$\triangleright \frac{5962}{178340} = \frac{8943}{267510}$	$\triangleright \frac{5967}{138240} = \frac{7956}{184320}$	$\triangleright \frac{5973}{218064} = \frac{8145}{297360}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{203618} = \frac{8961}{305427}$

$\triangleright \frac{5974}{203816} = \frac{8961}{305724}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{380216} = \frac{8961}{570324}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{201834} = \frac{8964}{302751}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{342810} = \frac{8632}{495170}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{208163} = \frac{9048}{315276}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{381602} = \frac{8961}{572403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{203418} = \frac{8964}{305127}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{348102} = \frac{7308}{425691}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{216038} = \frac{8961}{324057}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{381620} = \frac{8961}{572430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{203814} = \frac{8964}{305721}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{380142} = \frac{8964}{570213}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{216380} = \frac{8961}{324570}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{382016} = \frac{8961}{573024}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{204138} = \frac{6308}{215479}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{380214} = \frac{8964}{570321}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{218036} = \frac{8961}{327054}$	$\triangleright \frac{5974}{382160} = \frac{8961}{573240}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{214038} = \frac{8964}{321057}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{381402} = \frac{8964}{572103}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{231680} = \frac{8961}{347520}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{134208} = \frac{6723}{150984}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{214380} = \frac{8964}{321570}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{381420} = \frac{8964}{572130}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{236018} = \frac{8961}{354027}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{140238} = \frac{8964}{210357}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{218034} = \frac{8964}{327051}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{382014} = \frac{8964}{573021}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{236180} = \frac{8961}{354270}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{140382} = \frac{8964}{210573}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{218340} = \frac{8964}{327510}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{382140} = \frac{8964}{573210}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{238016} = \frac{8961}{357024}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{142038} = \frac{8964}{213057}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{234018} = \frac{8964}{351027}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{431208} = \frac{6723}{485109}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{238160} = \frac{8961}{357240}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{142380} = \frac{8964}{213570}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{234180} = \frac{8964}{351270}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{431280} = \frac{6723}{485190}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{316802} = \frac{8961}{475203}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{143802} = \frac{8964}{215703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{238014} = \frac{8964}{357021}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{804312} = \frac{6723}{904851}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{316820} = \frac{8961}{475230}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{143820} = \frac{8964}{215730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{238140} = \frac{8964}{357210}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{843120} = \frac{6723}{948510}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{360182} = \frac{8961}{540273}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{180234} = \frac{8964}{270351}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{243180} = \frac{7138}{290465}$	$\triangleright \frac{59760}{84312} = \frac{67230}{94851}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{360218} = \frac{8961}{540327}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{180342} = \frac{8964}{270513}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{340182} = \frac{8964}{510273}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{140236} = \frac{8967}{210354}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{361802} = \frac{8961}{542703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{182034} = \frac{8964}{273051}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{340218} = \frac{8964}{510327}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{140362} = \frac{8967}{210543}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{361820} = \frac{8961}{542730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{182340} = \frac{8964}{273510}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{341802} = \frac{8964}{512703}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{142036} = \frac{8967}{213054}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{362018} = \frac{8961}{543027}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{183402} = \frac{8964}{275103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{341820} = \frac{8964}{512730}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{142360} = \frac{8967}{213540}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{362180} = \frac{8961}{543270}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{183420} = \frac{8964}{275130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{342018} = \frac{8964}{513027}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{143602} = \frac{8967}{215403}$
$\triangleright \frac{5974}{380162} = \frac{8961}{570243}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{201438} = \frac{8964}{302157}$	$\triangleright \frac{5976}{342180} = \frac{8964}{513270}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{143620} = \frac{8967}{215430}$

$\triangleright \frac{5978}{160234} = \frac{8967}{240351}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{340162} = \frac{8967}{510243}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{174236} = \frac{8970}{261354}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{372416} = \frac{9230}{574816}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{160342} = \frac{8967}{240513}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{340216} = \frac{8967}{510324}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{174362} = \frac{8970}{261543}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{374162} = \frac{8970}{561243}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{162034} = \frac{8967}{243051}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{341602} = \frac{8967}{512403}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{176234} = \frac{8970}{264351}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{374216} = \frac{8970}{561324}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{162340} = \frac{8967}{243510}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{341620} = \frac{8967}{512430}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{176342} = \frac{8970}{264513}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{376214} = \frac{8970}{564321}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{163402} = \frac{8967}{245103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{342016} = \frac{8967}{513024}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{213647} = \frac{7540}{269381}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{436172} = \frac{8710}{635294}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{163420} = \frac{8967}{245130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{342160} = \frac{8967}{513240}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{214376} = \frac{8970}{321564}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{140376} = \frac{8973}{210564}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{201436} = \frac{8967}{302154}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{360142} = \frac{8967}{540213}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{216374} = \frac{8970}{324561}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{143760} = \frac{8973}{215640}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{201634} = \frac{8967}{302451}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{360214} = \frac{8967}{540321}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{217436} = \frac{8970}{326154}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{160374} = \frac{8973}{240561}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{203416} = \frac{8967}{305124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{361402} = \frac{8967}{542103}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{217634} = \frac{8970}{326451}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{163740} = \frac{8973}{245610}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{203614} = \frac{8967}{305421}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{361420} = \frac{8967}{542130}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{234176} = \frac{8970}{351264}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{174036} = \frac{8973}{261054}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{214036} = \frac{8967}{321054}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{362014} = \frac{8967}{543021}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{236174} = \frac{8970}{354261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{174360} = \frac{8973}{261540}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{214360} = \frac{8967}{321540}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{362140} = \frac{8967}{543210}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{237416} = \frac{8970}{356124}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{176034} = \frac{8973}{264051}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{216034} = \frac{8967}{324051}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{364021} = \frac{8906}{542317}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{237614} = \frac{8970}{356421}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{176340} = \frac{8973}{264510}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{216340} = \frac{8967}{324510}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{410326} = \frac{7869}{540123}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{341762} = \frac{8970}{512643}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{340176} = \frac{8973}{510264}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{234016} = \frac{8967}{351024}$	$\triangleright \frac{5978}{431026} = \frac{8036}{579412}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{342176} = \frac{8970}{513264}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{341760} = \frac{8973}{512640}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{234160} = \frac{8967}{351240}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{142376} = \frac{8970}{213564}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{361742} = \frac{8970}{542613}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{360174} = \frac{8973}{540261}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{236014} = \frac{8967}{354021}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{143762} = \frac{8970}{215643}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{362174} = \frac{8970}{543261}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{361740} = \frac{8973}{542610}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{236140} = \frac{8967}{354210}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{162374} = \frac{8970}{243561}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{367241} = \frac{9360}{574812}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{374016} = \frac{8973}{561024}$
$\triangleright \frac{5978}{301462} = \frac{9352}{471608}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{163742} = \frac{8970}{245613}$	$\triangleright \frac{5980}{371462} = \frac{6210}{385749}$	$\triangleright \frac{5982}{374160} = \frac{8973}{561240}$

▶ $\frac{5982}{376014} = \frac{8973}{564021}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{498375} = \frac{7348}{609125}$	▶ $\frac{6019}{734825} = \frac{6482}{791350}$	▶ $\frac{6035}{128794} = \frac{7480}{159632}$
▶ $\frac{5982}{376140} = \frac{8973}{564210}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{538794} = \frac{7014}{628593}$	▶ $\frac{6023}{158479} = \frac{6974}{183502}$	▶ $\frac{6035}{214897} = \frac{8165}{290743}$
▶ $\frac{5983}{240671} = \frac{8091}{325467}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{539874} = \frac{7014}{629853}$	▶ $\frac{6025}{314987} = \frac{9150}{478362}$	▶ $\frac{6035}{498712} = \frac{7810}{645392}$
▶ $\frac{5984}{106372} = \frac{7480}{132965}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{587394} = \frac{7014}{685293}$	▶ $\frac{6027}{134589} = \frac{8036}{179452}$	▶ $\frac{6035}{741829} = \frac{6745}{829103}$
▶ $\frac{5984}{120736} = \frac{6953}{140287}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{587934} = \frac{7014}{685923}$	▶ $\frac{6027}{348951} = \frac{8673}{502149}$	▶ $\frac{6039}{142758} = \frac{8235}{194670}$
▶ $\frac{5984}{173206} = \frac{8704}{251936}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{593874} = \frac{7014}{692853}$	▶ $\frac{6027}{395814} = \frac{9751}{640382}$	▶ $\frac{6039}{145782} = \frac{8052}{194376}$
▶ $\frac{5984}{361702} = \frac{8432}{509671}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{598734} = \frac{7014}{698523}$	▶ $\frac{6027}{419538} = \frac{9348}{650712}$	▶ $\frac{6039}{257481} = \frac{9702}{413658}$
▶ $\frac{5984}{637120} = \frac{6851}{729430}$	▶ $\frac{6012}{738459} = \frac{7348}{902561}$	▶ $\frac{6027}{495813} = \frac{8526}{701394}$	▶ $\frac{6039}{582714} = \frac{8235}{794610}$
▶ $\frac{5984}{730612} = \frac{7480}{913265}$	▶ $\frac{6014}{235879} = \frac{9506}{372841}$	▶ $\frac{6027}{495831} = \frac{7134}{586902}$	▶ $\frac{6039}{758142} = \frac{6954}{873012}$
▶ $\frac{5986}{137240} = \frac{7954}{182360}$	▶ $\frac{6014}{527389} = \frac{9610}{842735}$	▶ $\frac{6027}{549318} = \frac{9513}{867042}$	▶ $\frac{6042}{137598} = \frac{9487}{216053}$
▶ $\frac{5986}{432017} = \frac{6278}{453091}$	▶ $\frac{6014}{739528} = \frac{7564}{930128}$	▶ $\frac{6027}{583149} = \frac{7134}{690258}$	▶ $\frac{6042}{378195} = \frac{6890}{431275}$
▶ $\frac{5986}{472310} = \frac{7134}{562890}$	▶ $\frac{6017}{243958} = \frac{7658}{310492}$	▶ $\frac{6028}{193754} = \frac{9864}{317052}$	▶ $\frac{6042}{379851} = \frac{6270}{394185}$
▶ $\frac{6012}{349578} = \frac{9018}{524367}$	▶ $\frac{6018}{245973} = \frac{8614}{352079}$	▶ $\frac{6028}{195734} = \frac{7946}{258013}$	▶ $\frac{6042}{715938} = \frac{7049}{835261}$
▶ $\frac{6012}{349758} = \frac{9018}{524637}$	▶ $\frac{6018}{275349} = \frac{9086}{415723}$	▶ $\frac{6028}{357914} = \frac{9042}{536871}$	▶ $\frac{6042}{739158} = \frac{7049}{862351}$
▶ $\frac{6012}{354978} = \frac{9018}{532467}$	▶ $\frac{6018}{379542} = \frac{9853}{621407}$	▶ $\frac{6028}{359174} = \frac{9042}{538761}$	▶ $\frac{6042}{739518} = \frac{7314}{895206}$
▶ $\frac{6012}{357498} = \frac{9018}{536247}$	▶ $\frac{6018}{397542} = \frac{9843}{650217}$	▶ $\frac{6028}{375914} = \frac{9042}{563871}$	▶ $\frac{6042}{753198} = \frac{7632}{951408}$
▶ $\frac{6012}{374958} = \frac{9018}{562437}$	▶ $\frac{6018}{594732} = \frac{7021}{693854}$	▶ $\frac{6028}{379154} = \frac{9042}{568731}$	▶ $\frac{6042}{753819} = \frac{6574}{820193}$
▶ $\frac{6012}{375498} = \frac{9018}{563247}$	▶ $\frac{6018}{732594} = \frac{7021}{854693}$	▶ $\frac{6028}{391574} = \frac{9042}{587361}$	▶ $\frac{6045}{128973} = \frac{9765}{208341}$
▶ $\frac{6012}{479583} = \frac{9352}{746018}$	▶ $\frac{6019}{275834} = \frac{6945}{318270}$	▶ $\frac{6028}{719543} = \frac{7124}{850369}$	▶ $\frac{6045}{328197} = \frac{7605}{412893}$

$\triangleright \frac{6045}{819237} = \frac{6435}{872091}$	$\triangleright \frac{6075}{439182} = \frac{9450}{683172}$	$\triangleright \frac{6098}{153724} = \frac{9147}{230586}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{354978} = \frac{9180}{532467}$
$\triangleright \frac{6048}{139752} = \frac{9380}{216745}$	$\triangleright \frac{6078}{193452} = \frac{8104}{257936}$	$\triangleright \frac{6098}{354712} = \frac{9147}{532068}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{357498} = \frac{9180}{536247}$
$\triangleright \frac{6048}{153792} = \frac{9765}{248310}$	$\triangleright \frac{6078}{194532} = \frac{8104}{259376}$	$\triangleright \frac{6098}{413572} = \frac{9147}{620358}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{374958} = \frac{9180}{562437}$
$\triangleright \frac{6048}{172395} = \frac{8736}{249015}$	$\triangleright \frac{6078}{523149} = \frac{8104}{697532}$	$\triangleright \frac{6098}{415372} = \frac{9147}{623058}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{375498} = \frac{9180}{563247}$
$\triangleright \frac{6048}{173529} = \frac{9184}{263507}$	$\triangleright \frac{6083}{129745} = \frac{7426}{158390}$	$\triangleright \frac{6102}{378594} = \frac{8136}{504792}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{398475} = \frac{7208}{469315}$
$\triangleright \frac{6048}{312795} = \frac{6912}{357480}$	$\triangleright \frac{6083}{271495} = \frac{7821}{349065}$	$\triangleright \frac{6102}{594378} = \frac{8136}{792504}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{435897} = \frac{9480}{675213}$
$\triangleright \frac{6048}{375219} = \frac{7392}{458601}$	$\triangleright \frac{6083}{417592} = \frac{7821}{536904}$	$\triangleright \frac{6104}{398572} = \frac{7630}{498215}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{538794} = \frac{7140}{628593}$
$\triangleright \frac{6048}{713529} = \frac{8064}{951372}$	$\triangleright \frac{6083}{451297} = \frac{9638}{715042}$	$\triangleright \frac{6104}{739852} = \frac{7630}{924815}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{539874} = \frac{7140}{629853}$
$\triangleright \frac{6048}{795123} = \frac{7456}{980231}$	$\triangleright \frac{6083}{459172} = \frac{7821}{590364}$	$\triangleright \frac{6104}{785932} = \frac{7630}{982415}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{587394} = \frac{7140}{685293}$
$\triangleright \frac{6052}{794138} = \frac{6230}{817495}$	$\triangleright \frac{6083}{471295} = \frac{9401}{728365}$	$\triangleright \frac{6105}{284739} = \frac{8140}{379652}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{587934} = \frac{7140}{685923}$
$\triangleright \frac{6059}{782341} = \frac{6142}{793058}$	$\triangleright \frac{6084}{153972} = \frac{7956}{201348}$	$\triangleright \frac{6105}{392847} = \frac{8140}{523796}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{593874} = \frac{7140}{692853}$
$\triangleright \frac{6071}{548392} = \frac{8406}{759312}$	$\triangleright \frac{6092}{715384} = \frac{7615}{894230}$	$\triangleright \frac{6105}{394827} = \frac{8910}{576234}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{598734} = \frac{7140}{698523}$
$\triangleright \frac{6072}{149385} = \frac{9768}{240315}$	$\triangleright \frac{6093}{548217} = \frac{8124}{730956}$	$\triangleright \frac{6105}{493728} = \frac{7590}{613824}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{748935} = \frac{7104}{869352}$
$\triangleright \frac{6072}{183954} = \frac{6204}{187953}$	$\triangleright \frac{6094}{581273} = \frac{8310}{792645}$	$\triangleright \frac{6107}{259843} = \frac{6541}{278309}$	$\triangleright \frac{6123}{758940} = \frac{6594}{817320}$
$\triangleright \frac{6072}{189543} = \frac{6248}{195037}$	$\triangleright \frac{6095}{274381} = \frac{7590}{341682}$	$\triangleright \frac{6108}{493572} = \frac{9162}{740358}$	$\triangleright \frac{6123}{940587} = \frac{6318}{970542}$
$\triangleright \frac{6072}{534819} = \frac{7392}{651084}$	$\triangleright \frac{6095}{328417} = \frac{6890}{371254}$	$\triangleright \frac{6108}{495372} = \frac{9162}{743058}$	$\triangleright \frac{6125}{784390} = \frac{7350}{941268}$
$\triangleright \frac{6072}{819534} = \frac{7084}{956123}$	$\triangleright \frac{6095}{471382} = \frac{6325}{489170}$	$\triangleright \frac{6108}{734592} = \frac{7635}{918240}$	$\triangleright \frac{6127}{580394} = \frac{6237}{590814}$
$\triangleright \frac{6075}{413829} = \frac{9025}{614783}$	$\triangleright \frac{6095}{487123} = \frac{7130}{569842}$	$\triangleright \frac{6109}{472853} = \frac{9238}{715046}$	$\triangleright \frac{6128}{703954} = \frac{7240}{831695}$
$\triangleright \frac{6075}{431892} = \frac{9450}{671832}$	$\triangleright \frac{6098}{135724} = \frac{9147}{203586}$	$\triangleright \frac{6120}{349578} = \frac{9180}{524367}$	$\triangleright \frac{6129}{458730} = \frac{6583}{492710}$

$\triangleright \frac{6132}{549780} = \frac{8103}{726495}$	$\triangleright \frac{6147}{392805} = \frac{8196}{523740}$	$\triangleright \frac{6174}{532098} = \frac{9702}{836154}$	$\triangleright \frac{6184}{503792} = \frac{8503}{692714}$
$\triangleright \frac{6134}{508972} = \frac{9201}{763458}$	$\triangleright \frac{6148}{295307} = \frac{8692}{417503}$	$\triangleright \frac{6175}{203984} = \frac{8450}{279136}$	$\triangleright \frac{6185}{247930} = \frac{8659}{347102}$
$\triangleright \frac{6135}{792840} = \frac{7362}{951408}$	$\triangleright \frac{6148}{530729} = \frac{8692}{750341}$	$\triangleright \frac{6175}{283049} = \frac{9025}{413687}$	$\triangleright \frac{6190}{273584} = \frac{9285}{410376}$
$\triangleright \frac{6137}{240958} = \frac{9462}{371508}$	$\triangleright \frac{6148}{730592} = \frac{7685}{913240}$	$\triangleright \frac{6175}{423098} = \frac{9025}{618374}$	$\triangleright \frac{6190}{275384} = \frac{9285}{413076}$
$\triangleright \frac{6137}{504298} = \frac{7106}{583924}$	$\triangleright \frac{6149}{270358} = \frac{9503}{417826}$	$\triangleright \frac{6175}{439280} = \frac{7930}{564128}$	$\triangleright \frac{6190}{427358} = \frac{9285}{641037}$
$\triangleright \frac{6138}{249705} = \frac{8910}{362475}$	$\triangleright \frac{6149}{723580} = \frac{8127}{956340}$	$\triangleright \frac{6175}{832409} = \frac{7150}{963842}$	$\triangleright \frac{6190}{427538} = \frac{9285}{641307}$
$\triangleright \frac{6138}{275094} = \frac{8712}{390456}$	$\triangleright \frac{6150}{238497} = \frac{8450}{327691}$	$\triangleright \frac{6179}{230584} = \frac{9185}{342760}$	$\triangleright \frac{6192}{503487} = \frac{8304}{675219}$
$\triangleright \frac{6138}{275904} = \frac{9207}{413856}$	$\triangleright \frac{6150}{387942} = \frac{7825}{493601}$	$\triangleright \frac{6179}{284530} = \frac{6847}{315290}$	$\triangleright \frac{6192}{503784} = \frac{8514}{692703}$
$\triangleright \frac{6138}{402597} = \frac{7326}{480519}$	$\triangleright \frac{6153}{402897} = \frac{8204}{537196}$	$\triangleright \frac{6179}{453028} = \frac{9185}{673420}$	$\triangleright \frac{6192}{730584} = \frac{7310}{862495}$
$\triangleright \frac{6138}{409572} = \frac{9207}{614358}$	$\triangleright \frac{6153}{420987} = \frac{9083}{621457}$	$\triangleright \frac{6180}{247935} = \frac{8652}{347109}$	$\triangleright \frac{6194}{203587} = \frac{7638}{251049}$
$\triangleright \frac{6138}{427590} = \frac{9207}{641385}$	$\triangleright \frac{6154}{203987} = \frac{6358}{210749}$	$\triangleright \frac{6180}{495327} = \frac{6480}{519372}$	$\triangleright \frac{6194}{372058} = \frac{8476}{509132}$
$\triangleright \frac{6139}{204785} = \frac{9647}{321805}$	$\triangleright \frac{6158}{273904} = \frac{9237}{410856}$	$\triangleright \frac{6180}{594732} = \frac{7210}{693854}$	$\triangleright \frac{6194}{375820} = \frac{8639}{524170}$
$\triangleright \frac{6139}{478520} = \frac{7893}{615240}$	$\triangleright \frac{6158}{409372} = \frac{9237}{614058}$	$\triangleright \frac{6180}{732594} = \frac{7210}{854693}$	$\triangleright \frac{6195}{302847} = \frac{8715}{426039}$
$\triangleright \frac{6140}{792835} = \frac{7368}{951402}$	$\triangleright \frac{6158}{427390} = \frac{9237}{641085}$	$\triangleright \frac{6180}{794235} = \frac{7416}{953082}$	$\triangleright \frac{6195}{324087} = \frac{9870}{516342}$
$\triangleright \frac{6142}{809375} = \frac{7138}{940625}$	$\triangleright \frac{6172}{409358} = \frac{9258}{614037}$	$\triangleright \frac{6182}{704935} = \frac{8430}{961275}$	$\triangleright \frac{6195}{387240} = \frac{8496}{531072}$
$\triangleright \frac{6145}{327980} = \frac{8603}{459172}$	$\triangleright \frac{6172}{409538} = \frac{9258}{614307}$	$\triangleright \frac{6184}{273590} = \frac{9276}{410385}$	$\triangleright \frac{6195}{423780} = \frac{9853}{674012}$
$\triangleright \frac{6147}{280539} = \frac{8196}{374052}$	$\triangleright \frac{6172}{508934} = \frac{9258}{763401}$	$\triangleright \frac{6184}{275390} = \frac{9276}{413085}$	
$\triangleright \frac{6198}{734520} = \frac{7231}{856940}$	$\triangleright \frac{6201}{479385} = \frac{8307}{642195}$	$\triangleright \frac{6204}{183975} = \frac{7896}{234150}$	$\triangleright \frac{6204}{539781} = \frac{9024}{785136}$
$\triangleright \frac{6198}{745320} = \frac{7231}{869540}$	$\triangleright \frac{6201}{834795} = \frac{6837}{920415}$	$\triangleright \frac{6204}{519378} = \frac{7238}{605941}$	$\triangleright \frac{6205}{479318} = \frac{6970}{538412}$

$\triangleright \frac{6208}{534179} = \frac{9472}{815036}$	$\triangleright \frac{6237}{580419} = \frac{8019}{746253}$	$\triangleright \frac{6258}{431907} = \frac{7152}{493608}$	$\triangleright \frac{6275}{384910} = \frac{7530}{461892}$
$\triangleright \frac{6209}{135478} = \frac{7096}{154832}$	$\triangleright \frac{6237}{841590} = \frac{6853}{924710}$	$\triangleright \frac{6258}{431970} = \frac{7152}{493680}$	$\triangleright \frac{6278}{135904} = \frac{9417}{203856}$
$\triangleright \frac{6210}{473958} = \frac{8395}{640721}$	$\triangleright \frac{6239}{750148} = \frac{7106}{854392}$	$\triangleright \frac{6258}{704319} = \frac{7152}{804936}$	$\triangleright \frac{6278}{153904} = \frac{9417}{230856}$
$\triangleright \frac{6210}{583794} = \frac{7245}{681093}$	$\triangleright \frac{6240}{315978} = \frac{8960}{453712}$	$\triangleright \frac{6258}{743190} = \frac{7152}{849360}$	$\triangleright \frac{6278}{413590} = \frac{9417}{620385}$
$\triangleright \frac{6210}{598374} = \frac{7245}{698103}$	$\triangleright \frac{6240}{318975} = \frac{9152}{467830}$	$\triangleright \frac{6258}{794130} = \frac{7301}{926485}$	$\triangleright \frac{6278}{415390} = \frac{9417}{623085}$
$\triangleright \frac{6213}{498750} = \frac{9483}{761250}$	$\triangleright \frac{6240}{389571} = \frac{6720}{419538}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{134589} = \frac{8360}{179452}$	$\triangleright \frac{6278}{534910} = \frac{9417}{802365}$
$\triangleright \frac{6215}{409738} = \frac{9735}{641802}$	$\triangleright \frac{6250}{137894} = \frac{9375}{206841}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{185934} = \frac{6435}{190827}$	$\triangleright \frac{6279}{304815} = \frac{8671}{420935}$
$\triangleright \frac{6215}{439780} = \frac{8362}{591704}$	$\triangleright \frac{6250}{138974} = \frac{9375}{208461}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{319485} = \frac{7062}{359841}$	$\triangleright \frac{6279}{310485} = \frac{9568}{473120}$
$\triangleright \frac{6215}{839047} = \frac{6780}{915324}$	$\triangleright \frac{6250}{173894} = \frac{9375}{260841}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{481593} = \frac{9680}{743512}$	$\triangleright \frac{6279}{540183} = \frac{8073}{694521}$
$\triangleright \frac{6219}{375048} = \frac{7601}{458392}$	$\triangleright \frac{6250}{178934} = \frac{9375}{268401}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{489315} = \frac{9614}{750283}$	$\triangleright \frac{6280}{357914} = \frac{9420}{536871}$
$\triangleright \frac{6230}{415897} = \frac{6790}{453281}$	$\triangleright \frac{6250}{189374} = \frac{9375}{284061}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{498135} = \frac{6384}{507192}$	$\triangleright \frac{6280}{359174} = \frac{9420}{538761}$
$\triangleright \frac{6234}{718095} = \frac{8312}{957460}$	$\triangleright \frac{6250}{189734} = \frac{9375}{284601}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{519384} = \frac{9735}{806412}$	$\triangleright \frac{6280}{375914} = \frac{9420}{563871}$
$\triangleright \frac{62349}{75810} = \frac{65318}{79420}$	$\triangleright \frac{6251}{380794} = \frac{8379}{510426}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{539184} = \frac{7315}{629048}$	$\triangleright \frac{6280}{379154} = \frac{9420}{568731}$
$\triangleright \frac{6235}{794180} = \frac{7482}{953016}$	$\triangleright \frac{6254}{137098} = \frac{9381}{205647}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{593184} = \frac{7315}{692048}$	$\triangleright \frac{6280}{391574} = \frac{9420}{587361}$
$\triangleright \frac{6237}{185409} = \frac{9603}{285471}$	$\triangleright \frac{6254}{139708} = \frac{8732}{195064}$	$\triangleright \frac{6270}{853941} = \frac{6840}{931572}$	$\triangleright \frac{6280}{391754} = \frac{9420}{587631}$
$\triangleright \frac{6237}{194805} = \frac{8316}{259740}$	$\triangleright \frac{6254}{170938} = \frac{9381}{256407}$	$\triangleright \frac{6273}{450891} = \frac{9512}{683704}$	$\triangleright \frac{6280}{431795} = \frac{8792}{604513}$
$\triangleright \frac{6237}{405891} = \frac{7392}{481056}$	$\triangleright \frac{6258}{137094} = \frac{9387}{205641}$	$\triangleright \frac{6273}{450918} = \frac{9435}{678210}$	$\triangleright \frac{6281}{397540} = \frac{9136}{578240}$
$\triangleright \frac{6237}{450198} = \frac{9108}{657432}$	$\triangleright \frac{6258}{170934} = \frac{9387}{256401}$	$\triangleright \frac{6275}{108934} = \frac{8625}{149730}$	$\triangleright \frac{6281}{403579} = \frac{9136}{587024}$
$\triangleright \frac{6237}{481950} = \frac{8217}{634950}$	$\triangleright \frac{6258}{413970} = \frac{7301}{482965}$	$\triangleright \frac{6275}{348910} = \frac{7530}{418692}$	$\triangleright \frac{6281}{539704} = \frac{9136}{785024}$

$\triangleright \frac{6283}{175409} = \frac{8967}{250341}$	$\triangleright \frac{6290}{471835} = \frac{7104}{532896}$	$\triangleright \frac{6309}{241875} = \frac{9814}{376250}$	$\triangleright \frac{6327}{850149} = \frac{7182}{965034}$
$\triangleright \frac{6283}{407159} = \frac{7503}{486219}$	$\triangleright \frac{6290}{534871} = \frac{8510}{723649}$	$\triangleright \frac{6309}{548217} = \frac{8412}{730956}$	$\triangleright \frac{6328}{175490} = \frac{7684}{213095}$
$\triangleright \frac{6285}{149370} = \frac{6704}{159328}$	$\triangleright \frac{6293}{157480} = \frac{9541}{238760}$	$\triangleright \frac{6312}{507498} = \frac{7364}{592081}$	$\triangleright \frac{6340}{178295} = \frac{7608}{213954}$
$\triangleright \frac{6285}{741930} = \frac{7542}{890316}$	$\triangleright \frac{6293}{501487} = \frac{8439}{672501}$	$\triangleright \frac{6314}{250879} = \frac{7854}{312069}$	$\triangleright \frac{6340}{182795} = \frac{7608}{219354}$
$\triangleright \frac{6289}{130745} = \frac{7809}{162345}$	$\triangleright \frac{6298}{105374} = \frac{8509}{142367}$	$\triangleright \frac{6314}{250987} = \frac{9184}{365072}$	$\triangleright \frac{6340}{287519} = \frac{8260}{374591}$
$\triangleright \frac{6289}{470351} = \frac{8417}{629503}$	$\triangleright \frac{6298}{350714} = \frac{7102}{395486}$	$\triangleright \frac{6314}{258907} = \frac{7462}{305981}$	$\triangleright \frac{6340}{572819} = \frac{7540}{681239}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{134578} = \frac{9435}{201867}$	$\triangleright \frac{6298}{410375} = \frac{9870}{643125}$	$\triangleright \frac{6315}{489270} = \frac{9683}{750214}$	$\triangleright \frac{6342}{179508} = \frac{8154}{230796}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{137458} = \frac{9435}{206187}$	$\triangleright \frac{6298}{431507} = \frac{7102}{486593}$	$\triangleright \frac{6318}{240975} = \frac{9126}{348075}$	$\triangleright \frac{6345}{182709} = \frac{8930}{257146}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{137854} = \frac{9435}{206781}$	$\triangleright \frac{6298}{437510} = \frac{7614}{528930}$	$\triangleright \frac{6320}{745918} = \frac{7840}{925316}$	$\triangleright \frac{6345}{189027} = \frac{9635}{287041}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{138574} = \frac{9435}{207861}$	$\triangleright \frac{6298}{510473} = \frac{9306}{754281}$	$\triangleright \frac{6321}{498057} = \frac{8127}{640359}$	$\triangleright \frac{6345}{189270} = \frac{9635}{287410}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{145378} = \frac{9435}{218067}$	$\triangleright \frac{6302}{189745} = \frac{9476}{285310}$	$\triangleright \frac{6321}{570948} = \frac{8514}{769032}$	$\triangleright \frac{6345}{270189} = \frac{9635}{410287}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{145738} = \frac{9435}{218607}$	$\triangleright \frac{6304}{518792} = \frac{7092}{583641}$	$\triangleright \frac{6321}{749805} = \frac{8127}{964035}$	$\triangleright \frac{6345}{271890} = \frac{9635}{412870}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{173458} = \frac{9435}{260187}$	$\triangleright \frac{6305}{142978} = \frac{9165}{207834}$	$\triangleright \frac{6325}{147890} = \frac{8360}{195472}$	$\triangleright \frac{6347}{590821} = \frac{7501}{698243}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{173485} = \frac{9176}{253084}$	$\triangleright \frac{6305}{278941} = \frac{9215}{407683}$	$\triangleright \frac{6325}{198470} = \frac{7590}{238164}$	$\triangleright \frac{6348}{107295} = \frac{9752}{164830}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{173854} = \frac{9435}{260781}$	$\triangleright \frac{63052}{91784} = \frac{67351}{98042}$	$\triangleright \frac{6327}{195804} = \frac{7695}{238140}$	$\triangleright \frac{6348}{195270} = \frac{7038}{216495}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{174538} = \frac{9435}{261807}$	$\triangleright \frac{6308}{142975} = \frac{8964}{203175}$	$\triangleright \frac{6327}{458109} = \frac{9324}{675108}$	$\triangleright \frac{6348}{215970} = \frac{9614}{327085}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{178534} = \frac{9435}{267801}$	$\triangleright \frac{6308}{174952} = \frac{8549}{237106}$	$\triangleright \frac{6327}{508491} = \frac{8037}{645921}$	$\triangleright \frac{6348}{275910} = \frac{7406}{321895}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{185374} = \frac{9435}{278061}$	$\triangleright \frac{6308}{517294} = \frac{8964}{735102}$	$\triangleright \frac{6327}{519480} = \frac{9234}{758160}$	$\triangleright \frac{6348}{527091} = \frac{7820}{649315}$
$\triangleright \frac{6290}{185734} = \frac{9435}{278601}$	$\triangleright \frac{6308}{715294} = \frac{8170}{926435}$	$\triangleright \frac{6327}{591408} = \frac{9063}{847152}$	$\triangleright \frac{6348}{592710} = \frac{7314}{682905}$

$\triangleright \frac{6348}{715902} = \frac{7406}{835219}$	$\triangleright \frac{6370}{129584} = \frac{7490}{152368}$	$\triangleright \frac{6380}{459712} = \frac{7830}{564192}$	$\triangleright \frac{6391}{487520} = \frac{6972}{531840}$
$\triangleright \frac{6348}{719250} = \frac{7406}{839125}$	$\triangleright \frac{6370}{148295} = \frac{7098}{165243}$	$\triangleright \frac{6380}{547921} = \frac{8120}{697354}$	$\triangleright \frac{6391}{542087} = \frac{7304}{619528}$
$\triangleright \frac{6348}{725190} = \frac{8372}{956410}$	$\triangleright \frac{6370}{198254} = \frac{9685}{301427}$	$\triangleright \frac{6380}{792154} = \frac{7540}{936182}$	$\triangleright \frac{6391}{754208} = \frac{7304}{861952}$
$\triangleright \frac{6351}{247908} = \frac{6931}{270548}$	$\triangleright \frac{6370}{514892} = \frac{9425}{761830}$	$\triangleright \frac{6384}{105972} = \frac{7980}{132465}$	$\triangleright \frac{6391}{782045} = \frac{6972}{853140}$
$\triangleright \frac{6351}{740892} = \frac{8103}{945276}$	$\triangleright \frac{6372}{105984} = \frac{7965}{132480}$	$\triangleright \frac{6384}{125970} = \frac{7392}{145860}$	$\triangleright \frac{6392}{147580} = \frac{7038}{162495}$
$\triangleright \frac{6351}{742980} = \frac{7154}{836920}$	$\triangleright \frac{6372}{154980} = \frac{8673}{210945}$	$\triangleright \frac{6384}{197052} = \frac{7980}{246315}$	$\triangleright \frac{6392}{450871} = \frac{8704}{613952}$
$\triangleright \frac{6351}{847902} = \frac{7081}{945362}$	$\triangleright \frac{6372}{159840} = \frac{9853}{247160}$	$\triangleright \frac{6384}{271950} = \frac{6840}{291375}$	$\triangleright \frac{6392}{471580} = \frac{9682}{714305}$
$\triangleright \frac{6352}{170948} = \frac{7940}{213685}$	$\triangleright \frac{6372}{195048} = \frac{7965}{243810}$	$\triangleright \frac{6384}{570912} = \frac{8169}{730542}$	$\triangleright \frac{6392}{518704} = \frac{8037}{652194}$
$\triangleright \frac{6352}{174908} = \frac{7940}{218635}$	$\triangleright \frac{6372}{198504} = \frac{7965}{248130}$	$\triangleright \frac{6390}{128475} = \frac{8094}{162735}$	$\triangleright \frac{6398}{402157} = \frac{7312}{459608}$
$\triangleright \frac{6352}{497108} = \frac{7940}{621385}$	$\triangleright \frac{6372}{501984} = \frac{7139}{562408}$	$\triangleright \frac{6390}{145782} = \frac{8520}{194376}$	$\triangleright \frac{6398}{740215} = \frac{7312}{845960}$
$\triangleright \frac{6352}{890471} = \frac{6784}{951032}$	$\triangleright \frac{6375}{298401} = \frac{8625}{403719}$	$\triangleright \frac{6390}{172458} = \frac{6745}{182039}$	$\triangleright \frac{6401}{397528} = \frac{9342}{580176}$
$\triangleright \frac{6354}{271908} = \frac{9531}{407862}$	$\triangleright \frac{6375}{429810} = \frac{8925}{601734}$	$\triangleright \frac{6390}{182754} = \frac{9630}{275418}$	$\triangleright \frac{6402}{378591} = \frac{9482}{560731}$
$\triangleright \frac{6357}{104289} = \frac{8476}{139052}$	$\triangleright \frac{6375}{492180} = \frac{9350}{721864}$	$\triangleright \frac{6390}{248571} = \frac{9120}{354768}$	$\triangleright \frac{6402}{395178} = \frac{7062}{435918}$
$\triangleright \frac{6357}{129480} = \frac{7824}{159360}$	$\triangleright \frac{6378}{102594} = \frac{8504}{136792}$	$\triangleright \frac{6390}{412785} = \frac{9372}{605418}$	$\triangleright \frac{6402}{397815} = \frac{9312}{578640}$
$\triangleright \frac{6357}{421980} = \frac{7824}{519360}$	$\triangleright \frac{6378}{594102} = \frac{8504}{792136}$	$\triangleright \frac{6390}{428175} = \frac{9230}{618475}$	$\triangleright \frac{6402}{518793} = \frac{9312}{754608}$
$\triangleright \frac{6358}{109472} = \frac{9537}{164208}$	$\triangleright \frac{6380}{125947} = \frac{7920}{156348}$	$\triangleright \frac{6390}{512478} = \frac{7920}{635184}$	$\triangleright \frac{6402}{519783} = \frac{9312}{756048}$
$\triangleright \frac{6358}{129047} = \frac{8602}{174593}$	$\triangleright \frac{6380}{154792} = \frac{7540}{182936}$	$\triangleright \frac{6390}{527814} = \frac{6930}{572418}$	$\triangleright \frac{6402}{783915} = \frac{6790}{831425}$
$\triangleright \frac{6358}{270149} = \frac{9826}{417503}$	$\triangleright \frac{6380}{179452} = \frac{7590}{213486}$	$\triangleright \frac{6391}{240758} = \frac{8217}{309546}$	$\triangleright \frac{6405}{173982} = \frac{8540}{231976}$
$\triangleright \frac{6358}{701492} = \frac{7514}{829036}$	$\triangleright \frac{6380}{452197} = \frac{7920}{561348}$	$\triangleright \frac{6391}{275408} = \frac{8217}{354096}$	$\triangleright \frac{6405}{179382} = \frac{8540}{239176}$

$\triangleright \frac{6405}{197823} = \frac{9310}{287546}$	$\triangleright \frac{6419}{580237} = \frac{8253}{746019}$	$\triangleright \frac{64530}{79812} = \frac{69310}{85724}$	$\triangleright \frac{6490}{123875} = \frac{9086}{173425}$
$\triangleright \frac{6405}{217938} = \frac{7015}{238694}$	$\triangleright \frac{6419}{758023} = \frac{8253}{974601}$	$\triangleright \frac{64582}{79310} = \frac{78421}{96305}$	$\triangleright \frac{6490}{187325} = \frac{9746}{281305}$
$\triangleright \frac{6405}{271389} = \frac{7245}{306981}$	$\triangleright \frac{6420}{597381} = \frac{9420}{876531}$	$\triangleright \frac{6459}{703128} = \frac{8612}{937504}$	$\triangleright \frac{6490}{315827} = \frac{7920}{385416}$
$\triangleright \frac{6405}{793821} = \frac{7015}{869423}$	$\triangleright \frac{6420}{715938} = \frac{7490}{835261}$	$\triangleright \frac{6459}{730128} = \frac{8612}{973504}$	$\triangleright \frac{6490}{328571} = \frac{7590}{384261}$
$\triangleright \frac{6408}{532971} = \frac{7832}{651409}$	$\triangleright \frac{6420}{739158} = \frac{7490}{862351}$	$\triangleright \frac{6475}{193820} = \frac{9065}{271348}$	$\triangleright \frac{6490}{873125} = \frac{7316}{984250}$
$\triangleright \frac{6408}{739152} = \frac{7209}{831546}$	$\triangleright \frac{6432}{579081} = \frac{7104}{639582}$	$\triangleright \frac{6475}{298130} = \frac{9065}{417382}$	$\triangleright \frac{6493}{107285} = \frac{8456}{139720}$
$\triangleright \frac{6408}{751392} = \frac{7209}{845316}$	$\triangleright \frac{6435}{120879} = \frac{9360}{175824}$	$\triangleright \frac{6475}{312980} = \frac{9065}{438172}$	$\triangleright \frac{6493}{157208} = \frac{9815}{237640}$
$\triangleright \frac{6409}{357812} = \frac{7395}{412860}$	$\triangleright \frac{6435}{287190} = \frac{8294}{370156}$	$\triangleright \frac{6478}{352190} = \frac{7268}{395140}$	$\triangleright \frac{6493}{752801} = \frac{7852}{910364}$
$\triangleright \frac{6409}{712385} = \frac{7293}{810645}$	$\triangleright \frac{6435}{812097} = \frac{6570}{829134}$	$\triangleright \frac{6479}{120835} = \frac{8246}{153790}$	$\triangleright \frac{6498}{157320} = \frac{9576}{231840}$
$\triangleright \frac{6413}{298507} = \frac{9063}{421857}$	$\triangleright \frac{6437}{592081} = \frac{8164}{750932}$	$\triangleright \frac{6479}{183502} = \frac{9641}{273058}$	$\triangleright \frac{6498}{312075} = \frac{9082}{436175}$
$\triangleright \frac{6413}{587092} = \frac{8109}{742356}$	$\triangleright \frac{6438}{250971} = \frac{9048}{352716}$	$\triangleright \frac{6479}{251038} = \frac{9614}{372508}$	$\triangleright \frac{6502}{137894} = \frac{9753}{206841}$
$\triangleright \frac{6413}{589270} = \frac{8321}{764590}$	$\triangleright \frac{6438}{297105} = \frac{8214}{379065}$	$\triangleright \frac{6480}{195372} = \frac{9540}{287631}$	$\triangleright \frac{6502}{138974} = \frac{9753}{208461}$
$\triangleright \frac{6413}{785290} = \frac{7314}{895620}$	$\triangleright \frac{6438}{509712} = \frac{9048}{716352}$	$\triangleright \frac{6480}{312975} = \frac{9072}{438165}$	$\triangleright \frac{6502}{173894} = \frac{9753}{260841}$
$\triangleright \frac{6417}{308295} = \frac{8901}{427635}$	$\triangleright \frac{6438}{710529} = \frac{8214}{906537}$	$\triangleright \frac{6480}{357291} = \frac{9760}{538142}$	$\triangleright \frac{6502}{178934} = \frac{9753}{268401}$
$\triangleright \frac{6417}{382509} = \frac{7038}{419526}$	$\triangleright \frac{6439}{527810} = \frac{7124}{583960}$	$\triangleright \frac{6480}{572913} = \frac{9360}{827541}$	$\triangleright \frac{6502}{189374} = \frac{9753}{284061}$
$\triangleright \frac{6417}{389205} = \frac{8694}{527310}$	$\triangleright \frac{6450}{712983} = \frac{7350}{812469}$	$\triangleright \frac{6480}{713529} = \frac{8640}{951372}$	$\triangleright \frac{6502}{189734} = \frac{9753}{284601}$
$\triangleright \frac{6417}{539280} = \frac{7843}{659120}$	$\triangleright \frac{6450}{798123} = \frac{7450}{921863}$	$\triangleright \frac{6480}{739152} = \frac{7290}{831546}$	$\triangleright \frac{6504}{178392} = \frac{7046}{193258}$
$\triangleright \frac{6418}{273590} = \frac{9627}{410385}$	$\triangleright \frac{6453}{129870} = \frac{7648}{153920}$	$\triangleright \frac{6480}{751392} = \frac{7290}{845316}$	$\triangleright \frac{6504}{273981} = \frac{9528}{401367}$
$\triangleright \frac{6418}{275390} = \frac{9627}{413085}$	$\triangleright \frac{6453}{798120} = \frac{6931}{857240}$	$\triangleright \frac{6489}{275310} = \frac{8549}{362710}$	$\triangleright \frac{6504}{379812} = \frac{9214}{538067}$

$\triangleright \frac{6504}{397812} = \frac{8130}{497265}$	$\triangleright \frac{6520}{197384} = \frac{8965}{271403}$	$\triangleright \frac{6538}{274910} = \frac{9807}{412365}$	$\triangleright \frac{6573}{819420} = \frac{7512}{936480}$
$\triangleright \frac{6504}{739812} = \frac{8130}{924765}$	$\triangleright \frac{6527}{384910} = \frac{8132}{479560}$	$\triangleright \frac{65380}{74912} = \frac{81725}{93640}$	$\triangleright \frac{6574}{138290} = \frac{9861}{207435}$
$\triangleright \frac{6507}{391284} = \frac{8917}{536204}$	$\triangleright \frac{6528}{104739} = \frac{8704}{139652}$	$\triangleright \frac{6539}{147082} = \frac{7042}{158396}$	$\triangleright \frac{6574}{139802} = \frac{8304}{176592}$
$\triangleright \frac{6508}{197432} = \frac{8135}{246790}$	$\triangleright \frac{6528}{190437} = \frac{8704}{253916}$	$\triangleright \frac{6539}{170482} = \frac{7042}{183596}$	$\triangleright \frac{6574}{290813} = \frac{9386}{415207}$
$\triangleright \frac{6508}{741392} = \frac{8135}{926740}$	$\triangleright \frac{6528}{391047} = \frac{8704}{521396}$	$\triangleright \frac{6540}{738912} = \frac{8175}{923640}$	$\triangleright \frac{6574}{392018} = \frac{8607}{513249}$
$\triangleright \frac{6509}{178342} = \frac{7641}{209358}$	$\triangleright \frac{6528}{431970} = \frac{6912}{457380}$	$\triangleright \frac{6542}{137098} = \frac{9813}{205647}$	$\triangleright \frac{6578}{120439} = \frac{8970}{164235}$
$\triangleright \frac{6510}{823794} = \frac{7245}{916803}$	$\triangleright \frac{6528}{493170} = \frac{9024}{681735}$	$\triangleright \frac{6542}{170938} = \frac{9813}{256407}$	$\triangleright \frac{6578}{134290} = \frac{9867}{201435}$
$\triangleright \frac{6512}{394087} = \frac{8976}{543201}$	$\triangleright \frac{6531}{420798} = \frac{8397}{541026}$	$\triangleright \frac{6549}{308217} = \frac{8732}{410956}$	$\triangleright \frac{6578}{302419} = \frac{8602}{395471}$
$\triangleright \frac{6512}{409738} = \frac{7392}{465108}$	$\triangleright \frac{6534}{120798} = \frac{7502}{138694}$	$\triangleright \frac{6570}{398142} = \frac{7065}{428139}$	$\triangleright \frac{6578}{304291} = \frac{8096}{374512}$
$\triangleright \frac{6512}{738940} = \frac{8140}{923675}$	$\triangleright \frac{6534}{170982} = \frac{9801}{256473}$	$\triangleright \frac{6570}{419823} = \frac{7290}{465831}$	$\triangleright \frac{6578}{392104} = \frac{8437}{502916}$
$\triangleright \frac{6512}{749380} = \frac{8140}{936725}$	$\triangleright \frac{6534}{178290} = \frac{9801}{267435}$	$\triangleright \frac{6572}{148930} = \frac{9548}{216370}$	$\triangleright \frac{6578}{409123} = \frac{8142}{506397}$
$\triangleright \frac{6512}{783904} = \frac{8103}{975426}$	$\triangleright \frac{6534}{219087} = \frac{9504}{318672}$	$\triangleright \frac{6572}{398104} = \frac{8215}{497630}$	$\triangleright \frac{6579}{280143} = \frac{8127}{346059}$
$\triangleright \frac{6517}{329840} = \frac{7546}{381920}$	$\triangleright \frac{6534}{291708} = \frac{9801}{437562}$	$\triangleright \frac{6572}{493801} = \frac{7192}{540386}$	$\triangleright \frac{6579}{421830} = \frac{6851}{439270}$
$\triangleright \frac{6517}{420938} = \frac{8379}{541206}$	$\triangleright \frac{6534}{701298} = \frac{8712}{935064}$	$\triangleright \frac{6572}{813409} = \frac{7420}{918365}$	$\triangleright \frac{6580}{723941} = \frac{7420}{816359}$
$\triangleright \frac{6517}{490238} = \frac{6713}{504982}$	$\triangleright \frac{6534}{781902} = \frac{6723}{804519}$	$\triangleright \frac{6572}{908314} = \frac{6758}{934021}$	$\triangleright \frac{6582}{137094} = \frac{9873}{205641}$
$\triangleright \frac{6517}{809324} = \frac{7203}{894516}$	$\triangleright \frac{6534}{912780} = \frac{6831}{954270}$	$\triangleright \frac{6573}{104289} = \frac{8764}{139052}$	$\triangleright \frac{6582}{170934} = \frac{9873}{256401}$
$\triangleright \frac{6519}{378420} = \frac{8159}{473620}$	$\triangleright \frac{6537}{190428} = \frac{8716}{253904}$	$\triangleright \frac{6573}{420819} = \frac{7512}{480936}$	$\triangleright \frac{6583}{174029} = \frac{9761}{258043}$
$\triangleright \frac{6519}{420873} = \frac{9102}{587634}$	$\triangleright \frac{6538}{170942} = \frac{9807}{256413}$	$\triangleright \frac{6573}{428190} = \frac{7512}{489360}$	$\triangleright \frac{6583}{174290} = \frac{9761}{258430}$
$\triangleright \frac{6519}{487203} = \frac{7049}{526813}$	$\triangleright \frac{6538}{174290} = \frac{9807}{261435}$	$\triangleright \frac{6573}{819042} = \frac{7512}{936048}$	$\triangleright \frac{6583}{271904} = \frac{7945}{328160}$

▶ $\frac{6583}{290174} = \frac{9761}{430258}$	▶ $\frac{6702}{531894} = \frac{7819}{620543}$	▶ $\frac{6728}{194503} = \frac{9048}{261573}$	▶ $\frac{6740}{539128} = \frac{8425}{673910}$
▶ $\frac{6583}{291740} = \frac{9761}{432580}$	▶ $\frac{6708}{319254} = \frac{7482}{356091}$	▶ $\frac{6728}{539140} = \frac{8410}{673925}$	▶ $\frac{6740}{591328} = \frac{8425}{739160}$
▶ $\frac{6591}{347802} = \frac{9672}{510384}$	▶ $\frac{6708}{351429} = \frac{9804}{513627}$	▶ $\frac{6730}{182945} = \frac{8076}{219534}$	▶ $\frac{6741}{298530} = \frac{7812}{345960}$
▶ $\frac{6592}{143708} = \frac{8240}{179635}$	▶ $\frac{6708}{394251} = \frac{9804}{576213}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{180594} = \frac{7854}{210693}$	▶ $\frac{6741}{598023} = \frac{8064}{715392}$
▶ $\frac{6592}{307184} = \frac{8652}{403179}$	▶ $\frac{6708}{425139} = \frac{9804}{621357}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{415089} = \frac{7128}{439506}$	▶ $\frac{6745}{813092} = \frac{7410}{893256}$
▶ $\frac{6592}{310784} = \frac{9785}{461320}$	▶ $\frac{6708}{429351} = \frac{9804}{627513}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{501948} = \frac{7106}{529834}$	▶ $\frac{6748}{153902} = \frac{7230}{164895}$
▶ $\frac{6592}{470813} = \frac{8512}{607943}$	▶ $\frac{6708}{431925} = \frac{9804}{631275}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{580194} = \frac{8602}{741359}$	▶ $\frac{6748}{195230} = \frac{8194}{237065}$
▶ $\frac{6592}{734108} = \frac{8240}{917635}$	▶ $\frac{6708}{521934} = \frac{8190}{637245}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{591408} = \frac{8415}{739260}$	▶ $\frac{6749}{218350} = \frac{6783}{219450}$
▶ $\frac{6593}{714820} = \frac{6821}{739540}$	▶ $\frac{6708}{532194} = \frac{7482}{593601}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{594018} = \frac{7854}{693021}$	▶ $\frac{6750}{198342} = \frac{8375}{246091}$
▶ $\frac{6594}{102378} = \frac{8792}{136504}$	▶ $\frac{6708}{914352} = \frac{7215}{983460}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{594180} = \frac{7854}{693210}$	▶ $\frac{6750}{428139} = \frac{9750}{618423}$
▶ $\frac{6594}{107832} = \frac{7693}{125804}$	▶ $\frac{6710}{429385} = \frac{8174}{523069}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{849150} = \frac{6930}{874125}$	▶ $\frac{6750}{894132} = \frac{7125}{943806}$
▶ $\frac{6594}{180732} = \frac{7693}{210854}$	▶ $\frac{6710}{839542} = \frac{7320}{915864}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{894150} = \frac{7106}{943825}$	▶ $\frac{6751}{423980} = \frac{9263}{581740}$
▶ $\frac{6594}{187320} = \frac{7693}{218540}$	▶ $\frac{6713}{582904} = \frac{9042}{785136}$	▶ $\frac{6732}{905148} = \frac{7326}{985014}$	▶ $\frac{6754}{291038} = \frac{8596}{370412}$
▶ $\frac{6594}{218073} = \frac{9870}{326415}$	▶ $\frac{6714}{238095} = \frac{8952}{317460}$	▶ $\frac{6738}{215094} = \frac{7861}{250943}$	▶ $\frac{6754}{291830} = \frac{8596}{371420}$
▶ $\frac{6594}{287310} = \frac{8526}{371490}$	▶ $\frac{6714}{358029} = \frac{8206}{437591}$	▶ $\frac{6738}{251490} = \frac{7861}{293405}$	▶ $\frac{6754}{381920} = \frac{7982}{451360}$
▶ $\frac{6594}{378102} = \frac{8792}{504136}$	▶ $\frac{6720}{195384} = \frac{9480}{275631}$	▶ $\frac{6739}{124085} = \frac{9083}{167245}$	▶ $\frac{6754}{392810} = \frac{9824}{571360}$
▶ $\frac{6594}{732018} = \frac{7693}{854021}$	▶ $\frac{6720}{531984} = \frac{9380}{742561}$	▶ $\frac{6739}{201584} = \frac{9315}{278640}$	▶ $\frac{6758}{309124} = \frac{6789}{310542}$
▶ $\frac{6594}{732180} = \frac{7693}{854210}$	▶ $\frac{6720}{819534} = \frac{7840}{956123}$	▶ $\frac{6739}{480125} = \frac{9083}{647125}$	▶ $\frac{6758}{423901} = \frac{7316}{458902}$
▶ $\frac{6702}{518934} = \frac{7819}{605423}$	▶ $\frac{6721}{549380} = \frac{7238}{591640}$	▶ $\frac{6740}{138952} = \frac{8425}{173690}$	▶ $\frac{6759}{348102} = \frac{9763}{502814}$

$\triangleright \frac{6780}{132549} = \frac{7920}{154836}$	$\triangleright \frac{6792}{351840} = \frac{7641}{395820}$	$\triangleright \frac{6812}{409375} = \frac{8216}{493750}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{192375} = \frac{9648}{271350}$
$\triangleright \frac{6780}{215943} = \frac{7980}{254163}$	$\triangleright \frac{6792}{518304} = \frac{7641}{583092}$	$\triangleright \frac{6815}{234790} = \frac{9541}{328706}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{193572} = \frac{7560}{213948}$
$\triangleright \frac{6780}{394125} = \frac{8136}{472950}$	$\triangleright \frac{6792}{531840} = \frac{7641}{598320}$	$\triangleright \frac{6817}{249305} = \frac{8421}{307965}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{217935} = \frac{7904}{251836}$
$\triangleright \frac{6783}{102459} = \frac{7258}{109634}$	$\triangleright \frac{6792}{540813} = \frac{9024}{718536}$	$\triangleright \frac{6817}{942350} = \frac{7123}{984650}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{319257} = \frac{9720}{453681}$
$\triangleright \frac{6783}{519204} = \frac{7106}{543928}$	$\triangleright \frac{6792}{541038} = \frac{9056}{721384}$	$\triangleright \frac{6820}{195734} = \frac{7540}{216398}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{329517} = \frac{7920}{381546}$
$\triangleright \frac{6784}{519320} = \frac{9328}{714065}$	$\triangleright \frac{6795}{148320} = \frac{9513}{207648}$	$\triangleright \frac{6820}{437195} = \frac{9548}{612073}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{357219} = \frac{7560}{394821}$
$\triangleright \frac{6784}{531920} = \frac{7632}{598410}$	$\triangleright \frac{6795}{431820} = \frac{9815}{623740}$	$\triangleright \frac{6825}{394170} = \frac{7605}{439218}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{527193} = \frac{7320}{564189}$
$\triangleright \frac{6785}{143290} = \frac{6903}{145782}$	$\triangleright \frac{6798}{410352} = \frac{9317}{562408}$	$\triangleright \frac{6825}{394710} = \frac{8190}{473652}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{573192} = \frac{9720}{814536}$
$\triangleright \frac{6785}{193402} = \frac{7590}{216348}$	$\triangleright \frac{6798}{453120} = \frac{7931}{528640}$	$\triangleright \frac{6825}{419370} = \frac{9230}{567148}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{713925} = \frac{8760}{914325}$
$\triangleright \frac{6789}{120435} = \frac{7592}{134680}$	$\triangleright \frac{6798}{540132} = \frac{8943}{710562}$	$\triangleright \frac{6825}{473109} = \frac{9150}{634278}$	$\triangleright \frac{6840}{731592} = \frac{7695}{823041}$
$\triangleright \frac{6789}{140523} = \frac{9052}{187364}$	$\triangleright \frac{6802}{139574} = \frac{8592}{176304}$	$\triangleright \frac{6825}{739410} = \frac{7605}{823914}$	$\triangleright \frac{6845}{217930} = \frac{9472}{301568}$
$\triangleright \frac{6789}{314052} = \frac{9052}{418736}$	$\triangleright \frac{6802}{345971} = \frac{8592}{437016}$	$\triangleright \frac{6830}{172945} = \frac{8196}{207534}$	$\triangleright \frac{6847}{352190} = \frac{7682}{395140}$
$\triangleright \frac{6790}{234815} = \frac{9506}{328741}$	$\triangleright \frac{6802}{475931} = \frac{9308}{651274}$	$\triangleright \frac{6830}{247915} = \frac{9562}{347081}$	$\triangleright \frac{6847}{521930} = \frac{8517}{649230}$
$\triangleright \frac{6790}{358124} = \frac{9170}{483652}$	$\triangleright \frac{6802}{497135} = \frac{8234}{601795}$	$\triangleright \frac{6831}{405927} = \frac{8019}{476523}$	$\triangleright \frac{6850}{132479} = \frac{9450}{182763}$
$\triangleright \frac{6790}{421853} = \frac{8610}{534927}$	$\triangleright \frac{6809}{143275} = \frac{8047}{169325}$	$\triangleright \frac{6831}{452709} = \frac{7029}{465831}$	$\triangleright \frac{6850}{372914} = \frac{7150}{389246}$
$\triangleright \frac{6792}{103854} = \frac{9056}{138472}$	$\triangleright \frac{6809}{275143} = \frac{8047}{325169}$	$\triangleright \frac{6832}{715904} = \frac{8723}{914056}$	$\triangleright \frac{6851}{249730} = \frac{8649}{315270}$
$\triangleright \frac{6792}{154830} = \frac{7924}{180635}$	$\triangleright \frac{6810}{529734} = \frac{7945}{618023}$	$\triangleright \frac{6834}{705912} = \frac{6953}{718204}$	$\triangleright \frac{6851}{709342} = \frac{8736}{904512}$
$\triangleright \frac{6792}{185340} = \frac{8490}{231675}$	$\triangleright \frac{6810}{532974} = \frac{7945}{621803}$	$\triangleright \frac{6834}{925701} = \frac{7236}{980154}$	$\triangleright \frac{6853}{271094} = \frac{7854}{310692}$
$\triangleright \frac{6792}{301548} = \frac{7924}{351806}$	$\triangleright \frac{6812}{357409} = \frac{7860}{412395}$	$\triangleright \frac{6837}{294150} = \frac{8127}{349650}$	$\triangleright \frac{6854}{123970} = \frac{9536}{172480}$

$\triangleright \frac{6854}{190273} = \frac{9430}{261785}$	$\triangleright \frac{6902}{138754} = \frac{8352}{167904}$	$\triangleright \frac{6912}{745380} = \frac{8640}{931725}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{481257} = \frac{7810}{542369}$
$\triangleright \frac{6859}{273410} = \frac{7942}{316580}$	$\triangleright \frac{6902}{153874} = \frac{7582}{169034}$	$\triangleright \frac{6912}{750384} = \frac{8352}{906714}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{482715} = \frac{7238}{504169}$
$\triangleright \frac{6870}{193245} = \frac{9618}{270543}$	$\triangleright \frac{6902}{873154} = \frac{7308}{924516}$	$\triangleright \frac{6913}{280457} = \frac{7136}{289504}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{571248} = \frac{7315}{602984}$
$\triangleright \frac{6870}{319452} = \frac{8015}{372694}$	$\triangleright \frac{6903}{125847} = \frac{9243}{168507}$	$\triangleright \frac{6913}{405728} = \frac{8697}{510432}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{571284} = \frac{8415}{693702}$
$\triangleright \frac{6870}{321945} = \frac{9618}{450723}$	$\triangleright \frac{6903}{184257} = \frac{7358}{196402}$	$\triangleright \frac{6915}{237840} = \frac{8759}{301264}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{785412} = \frac{7315}{829046}$
$\triangleright \frac{6873}{120495} = \frac{7584}{132960}$	$\triangleright \frac{6903}{245817} = \frac{7906}{281534}$	$\triangleright \frac{6915}{248370} = \frac{8759}{314602}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{817245} = \frac{7126}{840359}$
$\triangleright \frac{6873}{519042} = \frac{7821}{590634}$	$\triangleright \frac{69034}{78512} = \frac{73965}{84120}$	$\triangleright \frac{6915}{748203} = \frac{8460}{915372}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{845271} = \frac{7480}{912356}$
$\triangleright \frac{6874}{125930} = \frac{7856}{143920}$	$\triangleright \frac{6908}{123475} = \frac{9420}{168375}$	$\triangleright \frac{6921}{504837} = \frac{8459}{617023}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{857142} = \frac{7245}{896103}$
$\triangleright \frac{6875}{291430} = \frac{8250}{349716}$	$\triangleright \frac{6908}{174352} = \frac{8635}{217940}$	$\triangleright \frac{6923}{748501} = \frac{8372}{905164}$	$\triangleright \frac{6931}{240758} = \frac{9082}{315476}$
$\triangleright \frac{6890}{125437} = \frac{9540}{173682}$	$\triangleright \frac{6908}{325147} = \frac{9152}{430768}$	$\triangleright \frac{6923}{841570} = \frac{7826}{951340}$	$\triangleright \frac{6931}{274850} = \frac{8729}{346150}$
$\triangleright \frac{6890}{145273} = \frac{7280}{153496}$	$\triangleright \frac{6908}{341572} = \frac{9263}{458017}$	$\triangleright \frac{6925}{481703} = \frac{8975}{624301}$	$\triangleright \frac{6931}{548027} = \frac{7859}{621403}$
$\triangleright \frac{6890}{175324} = \frac{7345}{186902}$	$\triangleright \frac{6908}{341752} = \frac{8635}{427190}$	$\triangleright \frac{6927}{430581} = \frac{9236}{574108}$	$\triangleright \frac{6931}{582407} = \frac{9082}{763154}$
$\triangleright \frac{6890}{415732} = \frac{8970}{541236}$	$\triangleright \frac{6908}{571432} = \frac{8635}{714290}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{125748} = \frac{8470}{153692}$	$\triangleright \frac{6935}{102784} = \frac{8740}{129536}$
$\triangleright \frac{6893}{517402} = \frac{9153}{687042}$	$\triangleright \frac{6908}{574321} = \frac{9420}{783165}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{125874} = \frac{7920}{143856}$	$\triangleright \frac{6935}{128407} = \frac{8360}{154792}$
$\triangleright \frac{6895}{127430} = \frac{9653}{178402}$	$\triangleright \frac{6912}{407835} = \frac{9216}{543780}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{148725} = \frac{7392}{158640}$	$\triangleright \frac{6935}{248710} = \frac{7081}{253946}$
$\triangleright \frac{6895}{142730} = \frac{7683}{159042}$	$\triangleright \frac{6912}{430785} = \frac{9216}{574380}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{184275} = \frac{7326}{194805}$	$\triangleright \frac{6940}{153872} = \frac{8675}{192340}$
$\triangleright \frac{6897}{215403} = \frac{8349}{260751}$	$\triangleright \frac{6912}{437805} = \frac{9216}{583740}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{185724} = \frac{7065}{189342}$	$\triangleright \frac{6940}{187352} = \frac{8675}{234190}$
$\triangleright \frac{6897}{415302} = \frac{7623}{459018}$	$\triangleright \frac{6912}{570348} = \frac{8640}{712935}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{278145} = \frac{7524}{301986}$	$\triangleright \frac{6940}{312875} = \frac{9716}{438025}$
$\triangleright \frac{6897}{530214} = \frac{9801}{753462}$	$\triangleright \frac{6912}{738540} = \frac{8640}{923175}$	$\triangleright \frac{6930}{427581} = \frac{8370}{516429}$	$\triangleright \frac{6940}{738512} = \frac{8675}{923140}$

$\triangleright \frac{6942}{107835} = \frac{9256}{143780}$	$\triangleright \frac{6970}{143825} = \frac{8364}{172590}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{310248} = \frac{9825}{437016}$	$\triangleright \frac{7026}{518934} = \frac{8197}{605423}$
$\triangleright \frac{6942}{130785} = \frac{9256}{174380}$	$\triangleright \frac{6970}{152438} = \frac{7480}{163592}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{312480} = \frac{7920}{354816}$	$\triangleright \frac{7026}{531894} = \frac{8197}{620543}$
$\triangleright \frac{6942}{137805} = \frac{9256}{183740}$	$\triangleright \frac{6970}{431528} = \frac{7380}{456912}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{402318} = \frac{7625}{439810}$	$\triangleright \frac{7028}{169435} = \frac{9036}{217845}$
$\triangleright \frac{6942}{158730} = \frac{7209}{164835}$	$\triangleright \frac{6972}{134085} = \frac{7968}{153240}$	$\triangleright \frac{6980}{124375} = \frac{8376}{149250}$	$\triangleright \frac{7028}{351694} = \frac{9036}{452178}$
$\triangleright \frac{6942}{783510} = \frac{7209}{813645}$	$\triangleright \frac{6972}{183540} = \frac{9047}{238165}$	$\triangleright \frac{6980}{135472} = \frac{8725}{169340}$	$\triangleright \frac{7029}{346185} = \frac{9372}{461580}$
$\triangleright \frac{6943}{517280} = \frac{9563}{712480}$	$\triangleright \frac{6972}{315408} = \frac{8715}{394260}$	$\triangleright \frac{6980}{745312} = \frac{8725}{931640}$	$\triangleright \frac{7029}{386145} = \frac{9372}{514860}$
$\triangleright \frac{6945}{321870} = \frac{9723}{450618}$	$\triangleright \frac{6972}{351408} = \frac{8715}{439260}$	$\triangleright \frac{6984}{135072} = \frac{9603}{185724}$	$\triangleright \frac{7029}{453861} = \frac{9372}{605148}$
$\triangleright \frac{6948}{125730} = \frac{8492}{153670}$	$\triangleright \frac{6972}{401835} = \frac{8632}{497510}$	$\triangleright \frac{6984}{170235} = \frac{9648}{235170}$	$\triangleright \frac{7029}{461853} = \frac{9372}{615804}$
$\triangleright \frac{6948}{130275} = \frac{9432}{176850}$	$\triangleright \frac{6972}{415083} = \frac{7812}{465093}$	$\triangleright \frac{6984}{315072} = \frac{8245}{371960}$	$\triangleright \frac{70296}{81345} = \frac{82416}{95370}$
$\triangleright \frac{6948}{173520} = \frac{9457}{236180}$	$\triangleright \frac{6972}{830415} = \frac{7812}{930465}$	$\triangleright \frac{6984}{753012} = \frac{8730}{941265}$	$\triangleright \frac{703}{2985641} = \frac{901}{3826547}$
$\triangleright \frac{6948}{213750} = \frac{8106}{249375}$	$\triangleright \frac{6972}{834150} = \frac{7812}{934650}$	$\triangleright \frac{6987}{214305} = \frac{9316}{285740}$	$\triangleright \frac{703}{6195428} = \frac{931}{8204756}$
$\triangleright \frac{6948}{573210} = \frac{9234}{761805}$	$\triangleright \frac{6973}{524810} = \frac{9614}{723580}$	$\triangleright \frac{6987}{231540} = \frac{7398}{245160}$	$\triangleright \frac{703}{8169452} = \frac{836}{9715024}$
$\triangleright \frac{6950}{832471} = \frac{7450}{892361}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{124380} = \frac{8370}{149256}$	$\triangleright \frac{6987}{430521} = \frac{9316}{574028}$	$\triangleright \frac{7031}{485692} = \frac{7298}{504136}$
$\triangleright \frac{6952}{138740} = \frac{8690}{173425}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{143280} = \frac{7905}{162384}$	$\triangleright \frac{7014}{526398} = \frac{9352}{701864}$	$\triangleright \frac{7032}{498516} = \frac{8790}{623145}$
$\triangleright \frac{6952}{187340} = \frac{8690}{234175}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{143820} = \frac{9765}{201348}$	$\triangleright \frac{7014}{532986} = \frac{9352}{710648}$	$\triangleright \frac{7032}{681954} = \frac{8204}{795613}$
$\triangleright \frac{6952}{341708} = \frac{8690}{427135}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{183024} = \frac{7350}{192864}$	$\triangleright \frac{7014}{653298} = \frac{9352}{871064}$	$\triangleright \frac{7032}{819546} = \frac{8204}{956137}$
$\triangleright \frac{6954}{308721} = \frac{7410}{328965}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{201438} = \frac{8175}{236094}$	$\triangleright \frac{7018}{453629} = \frac{8294}{536107}$	$\triangleright \frac{7035}{168294} = \frac{9045}{216378}$
$\triangleright \frac{69542}{83710} = \frac{75864}{91320}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{234810} = \frac{9145}{307862}$	$\triangleright \frac{7024}{851936} = \frac{7463}{905182}$	$\triangleright \frac{7035}{169428} = \frac{9045}{217836}$
$\triangleright \frac{6958}{130427} = \frac{9408}{176352}$	$\triangleright \frac{6975}{284301} = \frac{9475}{386201}$	$\triangleright \frac{7024}{895136} = \frac{7463}{951082}$	$\triangleright \frac{7035}{281694} = \frac{9045}{362178}$

$\triangleright \frac{7035}{294168} = \frac{9045}{378216}$	$\triangleright \frac{7062}{594813} = \frac{9042}{761583}$	$\triangleright \frac{7095}{283614} = \frac{9460}{378152}$	$\triangleright \frac{7104}{293568} = \frac{8251}{340967}$
$\triangleright \frac{7035}{468129} = \frac{8610}{572934}$	$\triangleright \frac{7062}{851934} = \frac{8052}{971364}$	$\triangleright \frac{7095}{286314} = \frac{9460}{381752}$	$\triangleright \frac{7104}{528693} = \frac{9024}{671583}$
$\triangleright \frac{7035}{681429} = \frac{9045}{876123}$	$\triangleright \frac{7068}{359214} = \frac{9362}{475801}$	$\triangleright \frac{7095}{623814} = \frac{9460}{831752}$	$\triangleright \frac{7104}{593628} = \frac{9360}{782145}$
$\triangleright \frac{7036}{194528} = \frac{8795}{243160}$	$\triangleright \frac{7068}{395124} = \frac{7502}{419386}$	$\triangleright \frac{7095}{628134} = \frac{9460}{837512}$	$\triangleright \frac{7104}{658392} = \frac{9176}{850423}$
$\triangleright \frac{7036}{498512} = \frac{8795}{623140}$	$\triangleright \frac{7068}{534192} = \frac{9348}{706512}$	$\triangleright \frac{7095}{638421} = \frac{7205}{648319}$	$\triangleright \frac{7105}{284396} = \frac{9280}{371456}$
$\triangleright \frac{7036}{512984} = \frac{8795}{641230}$	$\triangleright \frac{7068}{593142} = \frac{7192}{603548}$	$\triangleright \frac{7098}{134652} = \frac{7943}{150682}$	$\triangleright \frac{7105}{296438} = \frac{9065}{378214}$
$\triangleright \frac{7038}{125649} = \frac{7956}{142038}$	$\triangleright \frac{7084}{125396} = \frac{7854}{139026}$	$\triangleright \frac{7098}{145236} = \frac{8502}{173964}$	$\triangleright \frac{7105}{384629} = \frac{8120}{439576}$
$\triangleright \frac{7038}{152694} = \frac{7084}{153692}$	$\triangleright \frac{7084}{236159} = \frac{8740}{291365}$	$\triangleright \frac{7098}{162435} = \frac{8632}{197540}$	$\triangleright \frac{7105}{643829} = \frac{9065}{821437}$
$\triangleright \frac{7038}{269514} = \frac{9027}{345681}$	$\triangleright \frac{7085}{341692} = \frac{8175}{394260}$	$\triangleright \frac{7098}{261534} = \frac{8697}{320451}$	$\triangleright \frac{7106}{589342} = \frac{7293}{604851}$
$\triangleright \frac{7038}{491625} = \frac{9078}{634125}$	$\triangleright \frac{7089}{152643} = \frac{8062}{173594}$	$\triangleright \frac{7098}{325164} = \frac{8957}{410326}$	$\triangleright \frac{7106}{592348} = \frac{8569}{714302}$
$\triangleright \frac{7056}{213984} = \frac{8379}{254106}$	$\triangleright \frac{7089}{245613} = \frac{9078}{314526}$	$\triangleright \frac{7098}{624351} = \frac{9516}{837042}$	$\triangleright \frac{7120}{368549} = \frac{8720}{451369}$
$\triangleright \frac{7061}{358294} = \frac{8903}{451762}$	$\triangleright \frac{7089}{546312} = \frac{7923}{610584}$	$\triangleright \frac{7102}{356849} = \frac{8576}{430912}$	$\triangleright \frac{7120}{459863} = \frac{9520}{614873}$
$\triangleright \frac{7062}{381549} = \frac{9416}{508732}$	$\triangleright \frac{7089}{623415} = \frac{9401}{826735}$	$\triangleright \frac{7102}{364958} = \frac{8509}{437261}$	$\triangleright \frac{7123}{485690} = \frac{7961}{542830}$
$\triangleright \frac{7062}{391458} = \frac{8239}{456701}$	$\triangleright \frac{7092}{136548} = \frac{8274}{159306}$	$\triangleright \frac{7102}{385469} = \frac{9246}{501837}$	$\triangleright \frac{7123}{490586} = \frac{7961}{548302}$
$\triangleright \frac{7062}{395481} = \frac{9416}{527308}$	$\triangleright \frac{7092}{145386} = \frac{8532}{174906}$	$\triangleright \frac{7102}{856394} = \frac{8056}{971432}$	$\triangleright \frac{7125}{689340} = \frac{9025}{873164}$
$\triangleright \frac{7062}{398154} = \frac{9416}{530872}$	$\triangleright \frac{7092}{381546} = \frac{9062}{487531}$	$\triangleright \frac{71024}{83569} = \frac{72496}{85301}$	$\triangleright \frac{7128}{349650} = \frac{8316}{407925}$
$\triangleright \frac{7062}{543981} = \frac{9416}{725308}$	$\triangleright \frac{7092}{613458} = \frac{8694}{752031}$	$\triangleright \frac{7104}{235968} = \frac{9546}{317082}$	$\triangleright \frac{7128}{650349} = \frac{9504}{867132}$
$\triangleright \frac{7062}{548139} = \frac{9416}{730852}$	$\triangleright \frac{7095}{238146} = \frac{9460}{317528}$	$\triangleright \frac{7104}{236895} = \frac{9472}{315860}$	$\triangleright \frac{7128}{653904} = \frac{8019}{735642}$
$\triangleright \frac{7062}{549381} = \frac{9416}{732508}$	$\triangleright \frac{7095}{281346} = \frac{9460}{375128}$	$\triangleright \frac{7104}{263895} = \frac{9472}{351860}$	$\triangleright \frac{7130}{268594} = \frac{8215}{309467}$

$\triangleright \frac{7130}{562948} = \frac{7905}{624138}$	$\triangleright \frac{7149}{650328} = \frac{9532}{867104}$	$\triangleright \frac{7182}{493506} = \frac{9387}{645021}$	$\triangleright \frac{7206}{819534} = \frac{8407}{956123}$
$\triangleright \frac{7130}{629548} = \frac{8165}{720934}$	$\triangleright \frac{7150}{489632} = \frac{9175}{628304}$	$\triangleright \frac{7182}{506394} = \frac{9234}{651078}$	$\triangleright \frac{7208}{493165} = \frac{8432}{576910}$
$\triangleright \frac{7132}{594608} = \frac{8915}{743260}$	$\triangleright \frac{7150}{628394} = \frac{9350}{821746}$	$\triangleright \frac{7183}{450692} = \frac{9142}{573608}$	$\triangleright \frac{7208}{531964} = \frac{8904}{657132}$
$\triangleright \frac{7134}{260895} = \frac{9512}{347860}$	$\triangleright \frac{7152}{349680} = \frac{9238}{451670}$	$\triangleright \frac{7184}{530269} = \frac{9840}{726315}$	$\triangleright \frac{7209}{146583} = \frac{7398}{150426}$
$\triangleright \frac{7134}{280956} = \frac{9512}{374608}$	$\triangleright \frac{7152}{368904} = \frac{9238}{476501}$	$\triangleright \frac{7185}{346029} = \frac{9580}{461372}$	$\triangleright \frac{7209}{356481} = \frac{9612}{475308}$
$\triangleright \frac{7134}{628095} = \frac{9512}{837460}$	$\triangleright \frac{7152}{493860} = \frac{8940}{617325}$	$\triangleright \frac{7185}{460293} = \frac{9580}{613724}$	$\triangleright \frac{7209}{531864} = \frac{9315}{687240}$
$\triangleright \frac{7136}{205984} = \frac{8697}{251043}$	$\triangleright \frac{7154}{826903} = \frac{8176}{945032}$	$\triangleright \frac{7192}{503846} = \frac{8432}{590716}$	$\triangleright \frac{7209}{564813} = \frac{9612}{753084}$
$\triangleright \frac{7138}{294650} = \frac{8901}{367425}$	$\triangleright \frac{7160}{389425} = \frac{8592}{467310}$	$\triangleright \frac{7192}{534068} = \frac{9512}{706348}$	$\triangleright \frac{7210}{639485} = \frac{8034}{712569}$
$\triangleright \frac{7138}{402695} = \frac{9628}{543170}$	$\triangleright \frac{7164}{293508} = \frac{7562}{309814}$	$\triangleright \frac{7192}{653480} = \frac{8294}{753610}$	$\triangleright \frac{7215}{643890} = \frac{8029}{716534}$
$\triangleright \frac{7139}{260485} = \frac{8954}{326710}$	$\triangleright \frac{7168}{293504} = \frac{9184}{376052}$	$\triangleright \frac{7198}{402356} = \frac{7316}{408952}$	$\triangleright \frac{7215}{684093} = \frac{9230}{875146}$
$\triangleright \frac{7146}{205398} = \frac{7543}{216809}$	$\triangleright \frac{7168}{294035} = \frac{9216}{378045}$	$\triangleright \frac{7198}{562034} = \frac{9516}{743028}$	$\triangleright \frac{7215}{694083} = \frac{9015}{867243}$
$\triangleright \frac{7146}{238095} = \frac{9528}{317460}$	$\triangleright \frac{7168}{294350} = \frac{9216}{378450}$	$\triangleright \frac{7201}{364598} = \frac{8512}{430976}$	$\triangleright \frac{7042}{395861} = \frac{7630}{428915}$
$\triangleright \frac{7146}{539280} = \frac{8734}{659120}$	$\triangleright \frac{7168}{350294} = \frac{9216}{450378}$	$\triangleright \frac{7203}{419685} = \frac{7938}{462510}$	$\triangleright \frac{7046}{153928} = \frac{8723}{190564}$
$\triangleright \frac{7149}{305862} = \frac{9532}{407816}$	$\triangleright \frac{7168}{352940} = \frac{9216}{453780}$	$\triangleright \frac{7203}{451689} = \frac{9261}{580743}$	$\triangleright \frac{7046}{583219} = \frac{8130}{672945}$
$\triangleright \frac{7149}{358620} = \frac{9532}{478160}$	$\triangleright \frac{7168}{395024} = \frac{9728}{536104}$	$\triangleright \frac{7203}{491568} = \frac{7301}{498256}$	$\triangleright \frac{7216}{359480} = \frac{9512}{473860}$
$\triangleright \frac{7149}{502638} = \frac{9532}{670184}$	$\triangleright \frac{7168}{453920} = \frac{7392}{468105}$	$\triangleright \frac{7203}{586149} = \frac{9604}{781532}$	$\triangleright \frac{7216}{359840} = \frac{8569}{427310}$
$\triangleright \frac{7149}{503286} = \frac{9532}{671048}$	$\triangleright \frac{7182}{354690} = \frac{8721}{430695}$	$\triangleright \frac{7203}{645981} = \frac{9261}{830547}$	$\triangleright \frac{7230}{145968} = \frac{8435}{170296}$
$\triangleright \frac{7149}{586203} = \frac{9532}{781604}$	$\triangleright \frac{7182}{403956} = \frac{7695}{432810}$	$\triangleright \frac{7203}{895461} = \frac{7546}{938102}$	$\triangleright \frac{7230}{586149} = \frac{9640}{781532}$
$\triangleright \frac{7149}{586230} = \frac{9532}{781640}$	$\triangleright \frac{7182}{436905} = \frac{9612}{584730}$	$\triangleright \frac{7205}{839146} = \frac{7860}{915432}$	$\triangleright \frac{7236}{149580} = \frac{7839}{162045}$

$\triangleright \frac{7236}{198504} = \frac{7839}{215046}$	$\triangleright \frac{7280}{169435} = \frac{9360}{217845}$	$\triangleright \frac{7301}{584962} = \frac{9238}{740156}$	$\triangleright \frac{7312}{589460} = \frac{9140}{736825}$
$\triangleright \frac{7236}{548910} = \frac{9246}{701385}$	$\triangleright \frac{7280}{351694} = \frac{9360}{452178}$	$\triangleright \frac{7304}{529816} = \frac{8217}{596043}$	$\triangleright \frac{7312}{658940} = \frac{9140}{823675}$
$\triangleright \frac{7238}{150964} = \frac{9863}{205714}$	$\triangleright \frac{7289}{435601} = \frac{8471}{506239}$	$\triangleright \frac{7304}{582916} = \frac{9130}{728645}$	$\triangleright \frac{7314}{286095} = \frac{9752}{381460}$
$\triangleright \frac{7238}{465091} = \frac{9870}{634215}$	$\triangleright \frac{7289}{560143} = \frac{7683}{590421}$	$\triangleright \frac{7304}{598612} = \frac{9130}{748265}$	$\triangleright \frac{7314}{289605} = \frac{9752}{386140}$
$\triangleright \frac{7238}{491056} = \frac{7315}{496280}$	$\triangleright \frac{7290}{461538} = \frac{9720}{615384}$	$\triangleright \frac{7304}{659812} = \frac{9130}{824765}$	$\triangleright \frac{7314}{528609} = \frac{8374}{605219}$
$\triangleright \frac{7238}{659410} = \frac{8162}{743590}$	$\triangleright \frac{7290}{463185} = \frac{9234}{586701}$	$\triangleright \frac{7305}{289614} = \frac{9740}{386152}$	$\triangleright \frac{7315}{624890} = \frac{8569}{732014}$
$\triangleright \frac{7239}{548610} = \frac{9652}{731480}$	$\triangleright \frac{7293}{108654} = \frac{9537}{142086}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{129465} = \frac{8352}{147960}$	$\triangleright \frac{7315}{649208} = \frac{8360}{741952}$
$\triangleright \frac{7240}{539816} = \frac{8145}{607293}$	$\triangleright \frac{7293}{460185} = \frac{9724}{613580}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{165492} = \frac{8526}{193074}$	$\triangleright \frac{7315}{862904} = \frac{7645}{901832}$
$\triangleright \frac{7240}{598136} = \frac{8145}{672903}$	$\triangleright \frac{7293}{540618} = \frac{8415}{623790}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{214956} = \frac{9541}{280637}$	$\triangleright \frac{7316}{425980} = \frac{9176}{534280}$
$\triangleright \frac{7241}{596830} = \frac{8912}{734560}$	$\triangleright \frac{7293}{586014} = \frac{7854}{631092}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{415296} = \frac{7569}{430128}$	$\triangleright \frac{7316}{502984} = \frac{9145}{628730}$
$\triangleright \frac{7245}{138069} = \frac{9730}{185426}$	$\triangleright \frac{7294}{168035} = \frac{9378}{216045}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{451269} = \frac{8604}{531297}$	$\triangleright \frac{7316}{509824} = \frac{9145}{637280}$
$\triangleright \frac{7245}{381960} = \frac{9016}{475328}$	$\triangleright \frac{7294}{168350} = \frac{9378}{216450}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{514296} = \frac{9135}{642870}$	$\triangleright \frac{7316}{582490} = \frac{9086}{723415}$
$\triangleright \frac{7245}{389160} = \frac{9387}{504216}$	$\triangleright \frac{7294}{350168} = \frac{9378}{450216}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{519246} = \frac{7482}{531609}$	$\triangleright \frac{7316}{582904} = \frac{9145}{728630}$
$\triangleright \frac{7245}{618930} = \frac{9765}{834210}$	$\triangleright \frac{7294}{351680} = \frac{9378}{452160}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{546192} = \frac{9135}{682740}$	$\triangleright \frac{7316}{589024} = \frac{9145}{736280}$
$\triangleright \frac{7249}{130658} = \frac{7908}{142536}$	$\triangleright \frac{7294}{501683} = \frac{9378}{645021}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{614592} = \frac{9135}{768240}$	$\triangleright \frac{7320}{148596} = \frac{8640}{175392}$
$\triangleright \frac{7249}{581306} = \frac{7908}{634152}$	$\triangleright \frac{7296}{104538} = \frac{8640}{123795}$	$\triangleright \frac{7308}{649215} = \frac{8352}{741960}$	$\triangleright \frac{7320}{159648} = \frac{8235}{179604}$
$\triangleright \frac{7254}{106938} = \frac{8649}{127503}$	$\triangleright \frac{7296}{350148} = \frac{9120}{437685}$	$\triangleright \frac{7310}{594862} = \frac{7905}{643281}$	$\triangleright \frac{7320}{185946} = \frac{8540}{216937}$
$\triangleright \frac{7254}{186930} = \frac{9087}{234165}$	$\triangleright \frac{7296}{510834} = \frac{9152}{640783}$	$\triangleright \frac{7312}{546980} = \frac{9140}{683725}$	$\triangleright \frac{7320}{186594} = \frac{8540}{217693}$
$\triangleright \frac{7254}{398610} = \frac{9672}{531480}$	$\triangleright \frac{7298}{431650} = \frac{7913}{468025}$	$\triangleright \frac{7312}{549860} = \frac{9140}{687325}$	$\triangleright \frac{7320}{541968} = \frac{8235}{609714}$

$\triangleright \frac{7320}{594186} = \frac{8540}{693217}$	$\triangleright \frac{7350}{142968} = \frac{8925}{173604}$	$\triangleright \frac{7380}{461529} = \frac{9840}{615372}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{614508} = \frac{9240}{768135}$
$\triangleright \frac{7320}{594618} = \frac{8540}{693721}$	$\triangleright \frac{7350}{168294} = \frac{9450}{216378}$	$\triangleright \frac{7380}{529146} = \frac{8730}{625941}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{654108} = \frac{9240}{817635}$
$\triangleright \frac{7320}{618594} = \frac{8540}{721693}$	$\triangleright \frac{7350}{169428} = \frac{9450}{217836}$	$\triangleright \frac{7380}{564912} = \frac{9840}{753216}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{681540} = \frac{8624}{795130}$
$\triangleright \frac{7320}{659418} = \frac{8540}{769321}$	$\triangleright \frac{7350}{281694} = \frac{9450}{362178}$	$\triangleright \frac{7384}{152906} = \frac{8236}{170549}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{685104} = \frac{9174}{850263}$
$\triangleright \frac{7326}{180594} = \frac{8547}{210693}$	$\triangleright \frac{7350}{291648} = \frac{7825}{310496}$	$\triangleright \frac{7384}{512096} = \frac{9017}{625348}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{815406} = \frac{8624}{951307}$
$\triangleright \frac{7326}{185940} = \frac{8547}{216930}$	$\triangleright \frac{7350}{294168} = \frac{9450}{378216}$	$\triangleright \frac{7385}{192640} = \frac{9706}{253184}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{815460} = \frac{8624}{951370}$
$\triangleright \frac{7326}{401598} = \frac{9702}{531846}$	$\triangleright \frac{7350}{296814} = \frac{8925}{360417}$	$\triangleright \frac{7385}{416092} = \frac{9730}{548216}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{854106} = \frac{8064}{931752}$
$\triangleright \frac{7326}{594018} = \frac{8547}{693021}$	$\triangleright \frac{7350}{681429} = \frac{9450}{876123}$	$\triangleright \frac{7386}{215094} = \frac{8617}{250943}$	$\triangleright \frac{7395}{128064} = \frac{7480}{129536}$
$\triangleright \frac{7326}{594180} = \frac{8547}{693210}$	$\triangleright \frac{7358}{129064} = \frac{8207}{143956}$	$\triangleright \frac{7386}{251490} = \frac{8617}{293405}$	$\triangleright \frac{7395}{148206} = \frac{7830}{156924}$
$\triangleright \frac{7326}{804195} = \frac{8712}{956340}$	$\triangleright \frac{7359}{428160} = \frac{9834}{572160}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{150864} = \frac{7854}{160293}$	$\triangleright \frac{7395}{240816} = \frac{9605}{312784}$
$\triangleright \frac{7328}{194650} = \frac{9840}{261375}$	$\triangleright \frac{7360}{154928} = \frac{8520}{179346}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{185640} = \frac{9768}{245310}$	$\triangleright \frac{7395}{280614} = \frac{9860}{374152}$
$\triangleright \frac{7328}{510496} = \frac{8473}{590261}$	$\triangleright \frac{7360}{482195} = \frac{8192}{536704}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{401856} = \frac{9768}{531024}$	$\triangleright \frac{7396}{152048} = \frac{9073}{186524}$
$\triangleright \frac{7329}{681450} = \frac{9423}{876150}$	$\triangleright \frac{7360}{591284} = \frac{9520}{764813}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{418560} = \frac{9471}{536280}$	$\triangleright \frac{7396}{450812} = \frac{9632}{587104}$
$\triangleright \frac{7340}{658912} = \frac{9175}{823640}$	$\triangleright \frac{7364}{185920} = \frac{9731}{245680}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{461058} = \frac{8624}{537901}$	$\triangleright \frac{7396}{510248} = \frac{9245}{637810}$
$\triangleright \frac{7348}{190652} = \frac{7849}{203651}$	$\triangleright \frac{7368}{105492} = \frac{8596}{123074}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{501468} = \frac{9072}{615438}$	$\triangleright \frac{7398}{145206} = \frac{8357}{164029}$
$\triangleright \frac{7348}{201569} = \frac{8756}{240193}$	$\triangleright \frac{7368}{519024} = \frac{8903}{627154}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{501648} = \frac{9702}{658413}$	$\triangleright \frac{7398}{205146} = \frac{7809}{216543}$
$\triangleright \frac{7348}{219605} = \frac{7964}{238015}$	$\triangleright \frac{7368}{519240} = \frac{8903}{627415}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{548016} = \frac{9108}{675234}$	$\triangleright \frac{7398}{254610} = \frac{8631}{297045}$
$\triangleright \frac{7348}{506192} = \frac{9185}{632740}$	$\triangleright \frac{7380}{125649} = \frac{9840}{167532}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{608154} = \frac{8624}{709513}$	$\triangleright \frac{7398}{506142} = \frac{7809}{534261}$
$\triangleright \frac{7348}{610592} = \frac{9185}{763240}$	$\triangleright \frac{7380}{146925} = \frac{8692}{173045}$	$\triangleright \frac{7392}{610548} = \frac{9240}{763185}$	$\triangleright \frac{7398}{526014} = \frac{9864}{701352}$

$\triangleright \frac{7398}{560412} = \frac{9453}{716082}$	$\triangleright \frac{7428}{513096} = \frac{9285}{641370}$	$\triangleright \frac{7490}{186235} = \frac{8346}{207519}$	$\triangleright \frac{7518}{632049} = \frac{8946}{752103}$
$\triangleright \frac{7408}{521936} = \frac{9723}{685041}$	$\triangleright \frac{7436}{295108} = \frac{8619}{342057}$	$\triangleright \frac{7490}{826315} = \frac{8346}{920751}$	$\triangleright \frac{7518}{642390} = \frac{8592}{734160}$
$\triangleright \frac{7410}{298365} = \frac{7904}{318256}$	$\triangleright \frac{7436}{821509} = \frac{7612}{840953}$	$\triangleright \frac{7493}{510286} = \frac{7906}{538412}$	$\triangleright \frac{7519}{286340} = \frac{9417}{358620}$
$\triangleright \frac{7410}{639825} = \frac{9672}{835140}$	$\triangleright \frac{7439}{268150} = \frac{8729}{314650}$	$\triangleright \frac{7496}{513028} = \frac{9370}{641285}$	$\triangleright \frac{7520}{139684} = \frac{9520}{176834}$
$\triangleright \frac{7410}{689325} = \frac{8132}{756490}$	$\triangleright \frac{7450}{123968} = \frac{9875}{164320}$	$\triangleright \frac{7498}{123065} = \frac{9062}{148735}$	$\triangleright \frac{7520}{193648} = \frac{9870}{254163}$
$\triangleright \frac{7410}{692835} = \frac{8134}{760529}$	$\triangleright \frac{7452}{691380} = \frac{9234}{856710}$	$\triangleright \frac{7502}{396418} = \frac{9207}{486513}$	$\triangleright \frac{7520}{481936} = \frac{9870}{632541}$
$\triangleright \frac{7412}{350968} = \frac{9265}{438710}$	$\triangleright \frac{7458}{391062} = \frac{8701}{456239}$	$\triangleright \frac{7502}{418396} = \frac{9207}{513486}$	$\triangleright \frac{7520}{813946} = \frac{8640}{935172}$
$\triangleright \frac{7416}{350892} = \frac{9270}{438615}$	$\triangleright \frac{7462}{531089} = \frac{8036}{571942}$	$\triangleright \frac{7502}{438619} = \frac{8712}{509364}$	$\triangleright \frac{7524}{309168} = \frac{9108}{374256}$
$\triangleright \frac{7416}{598302} = \frac{9064}{731258}$	$\triangleright \frac{7463}{905218} = \frac{8041}{975326}$	$\triangleright \frac{7502}{891436} = \frac{7623}{905814}$	$\triangleright \frac{7526}{104938} = \frac{8639}{120457}$
$\triangleright \frac{7420}{896315} = \frac{8056}{973142}$	$\triangleright \frac{7480}{123596} = \frac{8670}{143259}$	$\triangleright \frac{7504}{139628} = \frac{8036}{149527}$	$\triangleright \frac{7526}{148930} = \frac{9372}{185460}$
$\triangleright \frac{7421}{539068} = \frac{9231}{670548}$	$\triangleright \frac{7480}{329516} = \frac{8160}{359472}$	$\triangleright \frac{7504}{291683} = \frac{9648}{375021}$	$\triangleright \frac{7532}{690184} = \frac{9415}{862730}$
$\triangleright \frac{7421}{560839} = \frac{8507}{642913}$	$\triangleright \frac{7480}{359216} = \frac{9860}{473512}$	$\triangleright \frac{7506}{123849} = \frac{8046}{132759}$	$\triangleright \frac{7532}{698104} = \frac{9415}{872630}$
$\triangleright \frac{7421}{806593} = \frac{8507}{924631}$	$\triangleright \frac{7480}{392615} = \frac{9152}{480376}$	$\triangleright \frac{7506}{189324} = \frac{7645}{192830}$	$\triangleright \frac{7536}{109428} = \frac{9420}{136785}$
$\triangleright \frac{7425}{389610} = \frac{8910}{467532}$	$\triangleright \frac{7480}{532961} = \frac{9520}{678314}$	$\triangleright \frac{7514}{286039} = \frac{9826}{374051}$	$\triangleright \frac{7536}{142908} = \frac{9420}{178635}$
$\triangleright \frac{7425}{619380} = \frac{8910}{743256}$	$\triangleright \frac{7480}{615329} = \frac{9520}{783146}$	$\triangleright \frac{7514}{286390} = \frac{9826}{374510}$	$\triangleright \frac{7536}{419280} = \frac{7693}{428015}$
$\triangleright \frac{7425}{683910} = \frac{9460}{871352}$	$\triangleright \frac{7480}{631295} = \frac{8536}{720419}$	$\triangleright \frac{7514}{362089} = \frac{9826}{473501}$	$\triangleright \frac{7536}{490128} = \frac{8164}{530972}$
$\triangleright \frac{7425}{689310} = \frac{9405}{873126}$	$\triangleright \frac{7482}{136590} = \frac{9632}{175840}$	$\triangleright \frac{7514}{620398} = \frac{9503}{784621}$	$\triangleright \frac{7536}{491028} = \frac{9420}{613785}$
$\triangleright \frac{7426}{185039} = \frac{9638}{240157}$	$\triangleright \frac{7486}{109532} = \frac{8607}{125934}$	$\triangleright \frac{7514}{902836} = \frac{8021}{963754}$	$\triangleright \frac{7536}{804192} = \frac{8635}{921470}$
$\triangleright \frac{7426}{589103} = \frac{8742}{693501}$	$\triangleright \frac{7486}{302195} = \frac{9456}{381720}$	$\triangleright \frac{7518}{463092} = \frac{8234}{507196}$	$\triangleright \frac{7540}{263198} = \frac{8410}{293567}$

$\triangleright \frac{7540}{319826} = \frac{8410}{356729}$	$\triangleright \frac{7569}{214803} = \frac{8961}{254307}$	$\triangleright \frac{7605}{321984} = \frac{8190}{346752}$	$\triangleright \frac{7650}{913482} = \frac{8075}{964231}$
$\triangleright \frac{7540}{391268} = \frac{9360}{485712}$	$\triangleright \frac{7581}{309624} = \frac{7695}{314280}$	$\triangleright \frac{7605}{341289} = \frac{8190}{367542}$	$\triangleright \frac{7651}{420938} = \frac{9837}{541206}$
$\triangleright \frac{7543}{189620} = \frac{8734}{219560}$	$\triangleright \frac{7581}{623490} = \frac{7942}{653180}$	$\triangleright \frac{7610}{423895} = \frac{9132}{508674}$	$\triangleright \frac{7654}{192038} = \frac{7832}{196504}$
$\triangleright \frac{7546}{301928} = \frac{9261}{370548}$	$\triangleright \frac{7584}{120396} = \frac{9472}{150368}$	$\triangleright \frac{7615}{438920} = \frac{9138}{526704}$	$\triangleright \frac{7659}{482310} = \frac{9324}{587160}$
$\triangleright \frac{7546}{821093} = \frac{8470}{921635}$	$\triangleright \frac{7584}{306912} = \frac{9164}{370852}$	$\triangleright \frac{7618}{540293} = \frac{8790}{623415}$	$\triangleright \frac{7680}{149325} = \frac{8704}{169235}$
$\triangleright \frac{7548}{102936} = \frac{9435}{128670}$	$\triangleright \frac{7584}{321609} = \frac{9120}{386745}$	$\triangleright \frac{7620}{193548} = \frac{9765}{248031}$	$\triangleright \frac{7680}{241935} = \frac{9728}{306451}$
$\triangleright \frac{7548}{130296} = \frac{9435}{162870}$	$\triangleright \frac{7584}{603912} = \frac{8532}{679401}$	$\triangleright \frac{7623}{580419} = \frac{9801}{746253}$	$\triangleright \frac{7680}{394215} = \frac{9216}{473058}$
$\triangleright \frac{7548}{210936} = \frac{7659}{214038}$	$\triangleright \frac{7584}{693120} = \frac{9164}{837520}$	$\triangleright \frac{7625}{384910} = \frac{9650}{487132}$	$\triangleright \frac{7680}{493152} = \frac{8160}{523974}$
$\triangleright \frac{7548}{310692} = \frac{9102}{374658}$	$\triangleright \frac{7590}{124683} = \frac{8690}{142753}$	$\triangleright \frac{7630}{294518} = \frac{8095}{312467}$	$\triangleright \frac{7682}{309451} = \frac{8694}{350217}$
$\triangleright \frac{7548}{630921} = \frac{9028}{754631}$	$\triangleright \frac{7590}{368214} = \frac{8970}{435162}$	$\triangleright \frac{7630}{581924} = \frac{8175}{623490}$	$\triangleright \frac{7683}{912504} = \frac{7865}{934120}$
$\triangleright \frac{7560}{123984} = \frac{8925}{146370}$	$\triangleright \frac{7590}{386124} = \frac{8910}{453276}$	$\triangleright \frac{7632}{105894} = \frac{9720}{134865}$	$\triangleright \frac{7684}{930512} = \frac{8023}{971564}$
$\triangleright \frac{7560}{132489} = \frac{7680}{134592}$	$\triangleright \frac{7590}{436821} = \frac{8970}{516243}$	$\triangleright \frac{7635}{849012} = \frac{8610}{957432}$	$\triangleright \frac{7685}{314290} = \frac{7859}{321406}$
$\triangleright \frac{7560}{132894} = \frac{9520}{167348}$	$\triangleright \frac{7590}{463128} = \frac{8910}{543672}$	$\triangleright \frac{7641}{592083} = \frac{8207}{635941}$	$\triangleright \frac{7692}{130548} = \frac{8974}{152306}$
$\triangleright \frac{7560}{398412} = \frac{9210}{485367}$	$\triangleright \frac{7590}{612348} = \frac{7935}{640182}$	$\triangleright \frac{7645}{192380} = \frac{9174}{230856}$	$\triangleright \frac{7695}{103842} = \frac{9785}{132046}$
$\triangleright \frac{7562}{189430} = \frac{8756}{219340}$	$\triangleright \frac{7592}{146803} = \frac{7904}{152836}$	$\triangleright \frac{7648}{159320} = \frac{8604}{179235}$	$\triangleright \frac{7695}{123804} = \frac{9720}{156384}$
$\triangleright \frac{7564}{132980} = \frac{8742}{153690}$	$\triangleright \frac{7596}{120384} = \frac{9706}{153824}$	$\triangleright \frac{7648}{195320} = \frac{8604}{219735}$	$\triangleright \frac{7695}{142380} = \frac{9234}{170856}$
$\triangleright \frac{7564}{381920} = \frac{8357}{421960}$	$\triangleright \frac{7605}{142389} = \frac{9360}{175248}$	$\triangleright \frac{7648}{502139} = \frac{7936}{521048}$	$\triangleright \frac{7695}{148230} = \frac{9063}{174582}$
$\triangleright \frac{7568}{129430} = \frac{8360}{142975}$	$\triangleright \frac{7605}{219843} = \frac{8190}{236754}$	$\triangleright \frac{7650}{231948} = \frac{8950}{271364}$	$\triangleright \frac{7695}{184032} = \frac{9785}{234016}$
$\triangleright \frac{7568}{302419} = \frac{7920}{316485}$	$\triangleright \frac{7605}{241839} = \frac{9045}{287631}$	$\triangleright \frac{7650}{349128} = \frac{8925}{407316}$	$\triangleright \frac{7695}{243081} = \frac{8645}{273091}$

$\triangleright \frac{7695}{810243} = \frac{8645}{910273}$	$\triangleright \frac{7830}{612549} = \frac{8410}{657923}$	$\triangleright \frac{7903}{452186} = \frac{9032}{516784}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{648153} = \frac{9120}{746358}$
$\triangleright \frac{7695}{812430} = \frac{8645}{912730}$	$\triangleright \frac{7830}{694521} = \frac{8190}{726453}$	$\triangleright \frac{7904}{168532} = \frac{9576}{204183}$	$\triangleright \frac{7923}{685140} = \frac{9452}{817360}$
$\triangleright \frac{7801}{536924} = \frac{9135}{628740}$	$\triangleright \frac{7831}{695240} = \frac{8159}{724360}$	$\triangleright \frac{7904}{635128} = \frac{7980}{641235}$	$\triangleright \frac{7924}{150836} = \frac{9056}{172384}$
$\triangleright \frac{7802}{615943} = \frac{8742}{690153}$	$\triangleright \frac{7839}{524610} = \frac{9243}{618570}$	$\triangleright \frac{7904}{651328} = \frac{8645}{712390}$	$\triangleright \frac{7924}{160538} = \frac{9056}{183472}$
$\triangleright \frac{7803}{295461} = \frac{9248}{350176}$	$\triangleright \frac{7852}{149630} = \frac{9362}{178405}$	$\triangleright \frac{7906}{321845} = \frac{8576}{349120}$	$\triangleright \frac{7924}{581630} = \frac{8490}{623175}$
$\triangleright \frac{7805}{134692} = \frac{7840}{135296}$	$\triangleright \frac{7854}{126903} = \frac{8976}{145032}$	$\triangleright \frac{7908}{316524} = \frac{8567}{342901}$	$\triangleright \frac{7924}{613508} = \frac{8207}{635419}$
$\triangleright \frac{7810}{462935} = \frac{8946}{530271}$	$\triangleright \frac{7854}{129360} = \frac{9367}{154280}$	$\triangleright \frac{7910}{356482} = \frac{9605}{432871}$	$\triangleright \frac{7926}{154830} = \frac{9247}{180635}$
$\triangleright \frac{7812}{605934} = \frac{8370}{649215}$	$\triangleright \frac{7854}{690312} = \frac{8415}{739620}$	$\triangleright \frac{7912}{304658} = \frac{8256}{317904}$	$\triangleright \frac{7926}{301548} = \frac{9247}{351806}$
$\triangleright \frac{7812}{659304} = \frac{9765}{824130}$	$\triangleright \frac{7856}{194032} = \frac{8347}{206159}$	$\triangleright \frac{7912}{653084} = \frac{8372}{691054}$	$\triangleright \frac{7930}{452681} = \frac{8190}{467523}$
$\triangleright \frac{7816}{409352} = \frac{8793}{460521}$	$\triangleright \frac{7859}{160432} = \frac{8352}{170496}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{136485} = \frac{9504}{163782}$	$\triangleright \frac{7930}{865124} = \frac{8540}{931672}$
$\triangleright \frac{7820}{136459} = \frac{8560}{149372}$	$\triangleright \frac{7864}{501932} = \frac{9830}{627415}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{143865} = \frac{9504}{172638}$	$\triangleright \frac{7931}{462058} = \frac{9317}{542806}$
$\triangleright \frac{7820}{395416} = \frac{9520}{481376}$	$\triangleright \frac{7864}{593012} = \frac{9830}{741265}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{148635} = \frac{9504}{178362}$	$\triangleright \frac{7931}{562408} = \frac{8034}{569712}$
$\triangleright \frac{7820}{593164} = \frac{9430}{715286}$	$\triangleright \frac{7865}{140239} = \frac{9230}{164578}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{154638} = \frac{9360}{182754}$	$\triangleright \frac{7931}{624085} = \frac{8137}{640295}$
$\triangleright \frac{7821}{634095} = \frac{8532}{691740}$	$\triangleright \frac{7865}{304291} = \frac{9680}{374512}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{184635} = \frac{8352}{194706}$	$\triangleright \frac{7931}{658042} = \frac{8961}{743502}$
$\triangleright \frac{7824}{130596} = \frac{9780}{163245}$	$\triangleright \frac{7869}{341205} = \frac{8601}{372945}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{318564} = \frac{9240}{371658}$	$\triangleright \frac{7931}{854062} = \frac{8652}{931704}$
$\triangleright \frac{7824}{369150} = \frac{9128}{430675}$	$\triangleright \frac{7869}{420153} = \frac{8601}{459237}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{564318} = \frac{9240}{658371}$	$\triangleright \frac{7932}{154608} = \frac{9254}{180376}$
$\triangleright \frac{7826}{319540} = \frac{8729}{356410}$	$\triangleright \frac{7869}{513420} = \frac{8723}{569140}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{613584} = \frac{9405}{728631}$	$\triangleright \frac{7932}{160548} = \frac{9254}{187306}$
$\triangleright \frac{7830}{129465} = \frac{8526}{140973}$	$\triangleright \frac{7869}{514230} = \frac{9374}{612580}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{615384} = \frac{9630}{748251}$	$\triangleright \frac{7936}{218054} = \frac{8704}{239156}$
$\triangleright \frac{7830}{415962} = \frac{8265}{439071}$	$\triangleright \frac{7890}{143625} = \frac{9468}{172350}$	$\triangleright \frac{7920}{638154} = \frac{9360}{754182}$	$\triangleright \frac{7936}{450182} = \frac{8320}{471965}$

$\triangleright \frac{7936}{485120} = \frac{9238}{564710}$	$\triangleright \frac{7953}{120648} = \frac{8435}{127960}$	$\triangleright \frac{7986}{453120} = \frac{9317}{528640}$	$\triangleright \frac{8052}{697413} = \frac{9504}{823176}$
$\triangleright \frac{7936}{501824} = \frac{9176}{580234}$	$\triangleright \frac{7953}{184206} = \frac{8917}{206534}$	$\triangleright \frac{8016}{435792} = \frac{8517}{463029}$	$\triangleright \frac{8052}{734196} = \frac{9174}{836502}$
$\triangleright \frac{7936}{804512} = \frac{7952}{806134}$	$\triangleright \frac{7953}{648120} = \frac{9158}{746320}$	$\triangleright \frac{8023}{491675} = \frac{9831}{602475}$	$\triangleright \frac{8063}{479512} = \frac{8796}{523104}$
$\triangleright \frac{7938}{105462} = \frac{8253}{109647}$	$\triangleright \frac{7956}{423810} = \frac{8190}{436275}$	$\triangleright \frac{8023}{759416} = \frac{8362}{791504}$	$\triangleright \frac{8064}{251379} = \frac{9856}{307241}$
$\triangleright \frac{7938}{216405} = \frac{8694}{237015}$	$\triangleright \frac{7961}{380452} = \frac{8531}{407692}$	$\triangleright \frac{8027}{341596} = \frac{9074}{386152}$	$\triangleright \frac{8064}{312795} = \frac{9216}{357480}$
$\triangleright \frac{7938}{640521} = \frac{8694}{701523}$	$\triangleright \frac{7965}{108324} = \frac{9765}{132804}$	$\triangleright \frac{8027}{914365} = \frac{8376}{954120}$	$\triangleright \frac{8064}{513792} = \frac{8904}{567312}$
$\triangleright \frac{7942}{306185} = \frac{8246}{317905}$	$\triangleright \frac{7965}{314280} = \frac{9027}{356184}$	$\triangleright \frac{8032}{179456} = \frac{8534}{190672}$	$\triangleright \frac{8064}{571392} = \frac{9135}{647280}$
$\triangleright \frac{7942}{365180} = \frac{9823}{451670}$	$\triangleright \frac{7965}{421083} = \frac{9720}{513864}$	$\triangleright \frac{8034}{276159} = \frac{9270}{318645}$	$\triangleright \frac{8064}{739152} = \frac{9072}{831546}$
$\triangleright \frac{7942}{613580} = \frac{9386}{725140}$	$\triangleright \frac{7968}{402135} = \frac{9536}{481270}$	$\triangleright \frac{8034}{652197} = \frac{9064}{735812}$	$\triangleright \frac{8073}{412965} = \frac{9321}{476805}$
$\triangleright \frac{7943}{168025} = \frac{8463}{179025}$	$\triangleright \frac{7980}{142653} = \frac{8740}{156239}$	$\triangleright \frac{8034}{721695} = \frac{9476}{851230}$	$\triangleright \frac{8073}{496152} = \frac{8671}{532904}$
$\triangleright \frac{7943}{205816} = \frac{9165}{237480}$	$\triangleright \frac{7980}{234156} = \frac{9135}{268047}$	$\triangleright \frac{8037}{269451} = \frac{9576}{321048}$	$\triangleright \frac{8073}{549612} = \frac{8671}{590324}$
$\triangleright \frac{7943}{516802} = \frac{9024}{587136}$	$\triangleright \frac{7980}{365142} = \frac{9870}{451623}$	$\triangleright \frac{8041}{295367} = \frac{8602}{315974}$	$\triangleright \frac{8075}{291346} = \frac{9650}{348172}$
$\triangleright \frac{7945}{168230} = \frac{9534}{201876}$	$\triangleright \frac{7980}{431256} = \frac{8360}{451792}$	$\triangleright \frac{8041}{356972} = \frac{9503}{421876}$	$\triangleright \frac{8092}{145367} = \frac{8932}{160457}$
$\triangleright \frac{7945}{231680} = \frac{9534}{278016}$	$\triangleright \frac{7980}{453126} = \frac{9310}{528647}$	$\triangleright \frac{8041}{526793} = \frac{9537}{624801}$	$\triangleright \frac{8094}{536712} = \frac{9514}{630872}$
$\triangleright \frac{7946}{105328} = \frac{9864}{130752}$	$\triangleright \frac{7980}{536124} = \frac{9310}{625478}$	$\triangleright \frac{8041}{569327} = \frac{9503}{672841}$	$\triangleright \frac{8096}{271354} = \frac{9152}{306748}$
$\triangleright \frac{7946}{250183} = \frac{9864}{310572}$	$\triangleright \frac{7980}{541632} = \frac{8740}{593216}$	$\triangleright \frac{8046}{137592} = \frac{9387}{160524}$	$\triangleright \frac{8096}{341527} = \frac{9152}{386074}$
$\triangleright \frac{7950}{346128} = \frac{9275}{403816}$	$\triangleright \frac{7980}{645312} = \frac{9310}{752864}$	$\triangleright \frac{8052}{361974} = \frac{8976}{403512}$	$\triangleright \frac{8096}{473152} = \frac{9361}{547082}$
$\triangleright \frac{7952}{108346} = \frac{9872}{134506}$	$\triangleright \frac{7981}{205643} = \frac{9716}{250348}$	$\triangleright \frac{8052}{374916} = \frac{8723}{406159}$	$\triangleright \frac{8096}{475312} = \frac{9108}{534726}$
$\triangleright \frac{7952}{186304} = \frac{8435}{197620}$	$\triangleright \frac{7985}{136420} = \frac{9582}{163704}$	$\triangleright \frac{8052}{479136} = \frac{8723}{519064}$	$\triangleright \frac{8103}{567429} = \frac{9287}{650341}$

$\triangleright \frac{8103}{694527} = \frac{8541}{732069}$	$\triangleright \frac{8140}{723965} = \frac{8436}{750291}$	$\triangleright \frac{8172}{403956} = \frac{9761}{482503}$	$\triangleright \frac{8214}{395760} = \frac{9583}{461720}$
$\triangleright \frac{8106}{243759} = \frac{9534}{286701}$	$\triangleright \frac{8142}{537096} = \frac{9735}{642180}$	$\triangleright \frac{8174}{205936} = \frac{8509}{214376}$	$\triangleright \frac{8215}{693470} = \frac{8904}{751632}$
$\triangleright \frac{8106}{354927} = \frac{9870}{432165}$	$\triangleright \frac{8142}{650739} = \frac{9204}{735618}$	$\triangleright \frac{8174}{239056} = \frac{9516}{278304}$	$\triangleright \frac{8230}{167945} = \frac{9876}{201534}$
$\triangleright \frac{8106}{529734} = \frac{9457}{618023}$	$\triangleright \frac{8142}{673509} = \frac{9204}{761358}$	$\triangleright \frac{8174}{692350} = \frac{9246}{783150}$	$\triangleright \frac{8234}{167095} = \frac{8592}{174360}$
$\triangleright \frac{8106}{532974} = \frac{9457}{621803}$	$\triangleright \frac{8145}{623907} = \frac{8190}{627354}$	$\triangleright \frac{8175}{423690} = \frac{8720}{451936}$	$\triangleright \frac{8236}{759104} = \frac{9301}{857264}$
$\triangleright \frac{8107}{453629} = \frac{8509}{476123}$	$\triangleright \frac{8154}{607392} = \frac{9513}{708624}$	$\triangleright \frac{8190}{423675} = \frac{8736}{451920}$	$\triangleright \frac{8241}{563709} = \frac{8643}{591207}$
$\triangleright \frac{8109}{342567} = \frac{8904}{376152}$	$\triangleright \frac{8154}{673920} = \frac{9513}{786240}$	$\triangleright \frac{8190}{426573} = \frac{9360}{487512}$	$\triangleright \frac{8245}{691730} = \frac{9021}{756834}$
$\triangleright \frac{8120}{675439} = \frac{8960}{745312}$	$\triangleright \frac{8154}{739206} = \frac{9513}{862407}$	$\triangleright \frac{8190}{763245} = \frac{9126}{850473}$	$\triangleright \frac{8251}{709364} = \frac{9143}{786052}$
$\triangleright \frac{8125}{693470} = \frac{9750}{832164}$	$\triangleright \frac{8154}{739260} = \frac{9513}{862470}$	$\triangleright \frac{8192}{475360} = \frac{9216}{534780}$	$\triangleright \frac{8260}{157943} = \frac{8540}{163297}$
$\triangleright \frac{8126}{390745} = \frac{9082}{436715}$	$\triangleright \frac{8159}{264073} = \frac{9512}{307864}$	$\triangleright \frac{8192}{504736} = \frac{9472}{583601}$	$\triangleright \frac{8260}{453179} = \frac{9380}{514627}$
$\triangleright \frac{8126}{574039} = \frac{9082}{641573}$	$\triangleright \frac{8160}{342975} = \frac{9152}{384670}$	$\triangleright \frac{8195}{246730} = \frac{9536}{287104}$	$\triangleright \frac{8261}{407935} = \frac{9763}{482105}$
$\triangleright \frac{8127}{304956} = \frac{9261}{347508}$	$\triangleright \frac{8160}{497352} = \frac{9240}{563178}$	$\triangleright \frac{8195}{620734} = \frac{9405}{712386}$	$\triangleright \frac{8265}{714930} = \frac{9367}{810254}$
$\triangleright \frac{8127}{405963} = \frac{9072}{453168}$	$\triangleright \frac{8160}{524739} = \frac{9120}{586473}$	$\triangleright \frac{8204}{159376} = \frac{9083}{176452}$	$\triangleright \frac{8274}{163905} = \frac{9456}{187320}$
$\triangleright \frac{8127}{563409} = \frac{8729}{605143}$	$\triangleright \frac{8162}{457390} = \frac{8239}{461705}$	$\triangleright \frac{8204}{179536} = \frac{9376}{205184}$	$\triangleright \frac{8279}{615043} = \frac{9253}{687401}$
$\triangleright \frac{8132}{695704} = \frac{9523}{814706}$	$\triangleright \frac{8162}{590473} = \frac{9856}{713024}$	$\triangleright \frac{8206}{149573} = \frac{8954}{163207}$	$\triangleright \frac{8294}{137605} = \frac{9328}{154760}$
$\triangleright \frac{8135}{679420} = \frac{9762}{815304}$	$\triangleright \frac{8170}{364952} = \frac{9675}{432180}$	$\triangleright \frac{8206}{195734} = \frac{8579}{204631}$	$\triangleright \frac{8294}{701536} = \frac{9048}{765312}$
$\triangleright \frac{8136}{529704} = \frac{8249}{537061}$	$\triangleright \frac{8170}{369542} = \frac{8645}{391027}$	$\triangleright \frac{8210}{346975} = \frac{9852}{416370}$	$\triangleright \frac{8295}{137046} = \frac{8690}{143572}$
$\triangleright \frac{8140}{293675} = \frac{9768}{352410}$	$\triangleright \frac{8170}{695324} = \frac{9675}{823410}$	$\triangleright \frac{8210}{394675} = \frac{9852}{473610}$	$\triangleright \frac{8295}{146307} = \frac{8690}{153274}$
$\triangleright \frac{8140}{376925} = \frac{9768}{452310}$	$\triangleright \frac{8170}{952364} = \frac{8360}{974512}$	$\triangleright \frac{8214}{357960} = \frac{9583}{417620}$	$\triangleright \frac{8295}{314760} = \frac{9401}{356728}$

$\triangleright \frac{8304}{716952} = \frac{9342}{806571}$	$\triangleright \frac{8360}{471295} = \frac{9416}{530827}$	$\triangleright \frac{8432}{179056} = \frac{9741}{206853}$	$\triangleright \frac{8512}{304976} = \frac{9804}{351267}$
$\triangleright \frac{8304}{769512} = \frac{9342}{865701}$	$\triangleright \frac{8360}{512974} = \frac{8740}{536291}$	$\triangleright \frac{8436}{127509} = \frac{9028}{136457}$	$\triangleright \frac{8512}{309764} = \frac{9728}{354016}$
$\triangleright \frac{8305}{641297} = \frac{9845}{760213}$	$\triangleright \frac{8370}{269514} = \frac{8415}{270963}$	$\triangleright \frac{8437}{125906} = \frac{8749}{130562}$	$\triangleright \frac{8512}{349706} = \frac{9120}{374685}$
$\triangleright \frac{8310}{472965} = \frac{9418}{536027}$	$\triangleright \frac{8371}{695420} = \frac{9132}{758640}$	$\triangleright \frac{8437}{619205} = \frac{8723}{640195}$	$\triangleright \frac{8512}{374960} = \frac{9576}{421830}$
$\triangleright \frac{8316}{749520} = \frac{9471}{853620}$	$\triangleright \frac{8372}{549016} = \frac{8694}{570132}$	$\triangleright \frac{8456}{907312} = \frac{8607}{923514}$	$\triangleright \frac{8512}{467390} = \frac{9728}{534160}$
$\triangleright \frac{8316}{945702} = \frac{8470}{963215}$	$\triangleright \frac{8372}{640591} = \frac{9568}{732104}$	$\triangleright \frac{8460}{793125} = \frac{9036}{847125}$	$\triangleright \frac{8512}{473690} = \frac{9728}{541360}$
$\triangleright \frac{8319}{657024} = \frac{9165}{723840}$	$\triangleright \frac{8374}{610295} = \frac{9638}{702415}$	$\triangleright \frac{8470}{635129} = \frac{9520}{713864}$	$\triangleright \frac{8512}{697034} = \frac{9184}{752063}$
$\triangleright \frac{8319}{726054} = \frac{9541}{832706}$	$\triangleright \frac{8374}{691250} = \frac{9063}{748125}$	$\triangleright \frac{8476}{135290} = \frac{9672}{154380}$	$\triangleright \frac{8514}{703296} = \frac{8901}{735264}$
$\triangleright \frac{8325}{190476} = \frac{8625}{197340}$	$\triangleright \frac{8374}{695201} = \frac{8690}{721435}$	$\triangleright \frac{8490}{567132} = \frac{9840}{657312}$	$\triangleright \frac{8514}{730269} = \frac{8910}{764235}$
$\triangleright \frac{8325}{701964} = \frac{8425}{710396}$	$\triangleright \frac{8374}{956120} = \frac{8532}{974160}$	$\triangleright \frac{8491}{576023} = \frac{9704}{658312}$	$\triangleright \frac{8514}{932670} = \frac{8712}{954360}$
$\triangleright \frac{8325}{719460} = \frac{9065}{783412}$	$\triangleright \frac{8379}{126540} = \frac{8967}{135420}$	$\triangleright \frac{8492}{351067} = \frac{9812}{405637}$	$\triangleright \frac{8519}{473620} = \frac{9736}{541280}$
$\triangleright \frac{8325}{904761} = \frac{8475}{921063}$	$\triangleright \frac{8379}{401562} = \frac{8512}{407936}$	$\triangleright \frac{8493}{152076} = \frac{9685}{173420}$	$\triangleright \frac{8520}{471369} = \frac{9360}{517842}$
$\triangleright \frac{8326}{714950} = \frac{8901}{764325}$	$\triangleright \frac{8405}{219637} = \frac{9840}{257136}$	$\triangleright \frac{8493}{612750} = \frac{8791}{634250}$	$\triangleright \frac{8532}{791640} = \frac{9243}{857610}$
$\triangleright \frac{8327}{564091} = \frac{9084}{615372}$	$\triangleright \frac{8406}{239571} = \frac{9486}{270351}$	$\triangleright \frac{8493}{725610} = \frac{9536}{814720}$	$\triangleright \frac{8536}{419720} = \frac{9603}{472185}$
$\triangleright \frac{8327}{569041} = \frac{9841}{672503}$	$\triangleright \frac{8410}{679325} = \frac{9512}{768340}$	$\triangleright \frac{8496}{173520} = \frac{9027}{184365}$	$\triangleright \frac{8536}{701294} = \frac{9312}{765048}$
$\triangleright \frac{8341}{607259} = \frac{9658}{703142}$	$\triangleright \frac{8412}{537690} = \frac{9814}{627305}$	$\triangleright \frac{8496}{537012} = \frac{9204}{581763}$	$\triangleright \frac{8536}{749012} = \frac{9506}{834127}$
$\triangleright \frac{8346}{729105} = \frac{9630}{841275}$	$\triangleright \frac{8415}{276930} = \frac{9504}{312768}$	$\triangleright \frac{8496}{753012} = \frac{9204}{815763}$	$\triangleright \frac{8547}{126903} = \frac{9768}{145032}$
$\triangleright \frac{8352}{647019} = \frac{9824}{761053}$	$\triangleright \frac{8415}{329760} = \frac{9724}{381056}$	$\triangleright \frac{8503}{276419} = \frac{9276}{301548}$	$\triangleright \frac{8560}{134927} = \frac{9760}{153842}$
$\triangleright \frac{8352}{740196} = \frac{9720}{861435}$	$\triangleright \frac{8415}{372096} = \frac{9570}{423168}$	$\triangleright \frac{8504}{279136} = \frac{9567}{314028}$	$\triangleright \frac{8561}{273049} = \frac{9784}{312056}$

$\triangleright \frac{8561}{273490} = \frac{9784}{312560}$	$\triangleright \frac{8639}{740251} = \frac{9617}{824053}$	$\triangleright \frac{8712}{653904} = \frac{9801}{735642}$	$\triangleright \frac{8930}{715246} = \frac{9310}{745682}$
$\triangleright \frac{8561}{490273} = \frac{9784}{560312}$	$\triangleright \frac{8640}{735912} = \frac{9560}{814273}$	$\triangleright \frac{8715}{406329} = \frac{9130}{425678}$	$\triangleright \frac{8930}{754162} = \frac{9310}{786254}$
$\triangleright \frac{8561}{492730} = \frac{9784}{563120}$	$\triangleright \frac{8640}{739152} = \frac{9720}{831546}$	$\triangleright \frac{8721}{469503} = \frac{9367}{504281}$	$\triangleright \frac{8942}{307615} = \frac{9468}{325710}$
$\triangleright \frac{8576}{312904} = \frac{9648}{352017}$	$\triangleright \frac{8640}{751392} = \frac{9720}{845316}$	$\triangleright \frac{8721}{560439} = \frac{9063}{582417}$	$\triangleright \frac{8946}{517230} = \frac{9372}{541860}$
$\triangleright \frac{8596}{312704} = \frac{9517}{346208}$	$\triangleright \frac{8642}{309175} = \frac{9164}{327850}$	$\triangleright \frac{8730}{291456} = \frac{9215}{307648}$	$\triangleright \frac{8965}{230417} = \frac{9780}{251364}$
$\triangleright \frac{8602}{597431} = \frac{9108}{632574}$	$\triangleright \frac{8649}{370512} = \frac{9765}{418320}$	$\triangleright \frac{8732}{156940} = \frac{9324}{167580}$	$\triangleright \frac{8965}{423071} = \frac{9780}{461532}$
$\triangleright \frac{8610}{349275} = \frac{9184}{372560}$	$\triangleright \frac{8649}{705312} = \frac{9021}{735648}$	$\triangleright \frac{8732}{164905} = \frac{9324}{176085}$	$\triangleright \frac{8967}{150243} = \frac{9408}{157632}$
$\triangleright \frac{8610}{473529} = \frac{9430}{518627}$	$\triangleright \frac{8652}{319074} = \frac{9270}{341865}$	$\triangleright \frac{8745}{632910} = \frac{9328}{675104}$	$\triangleright \frac{8967}{512034} = \frac{9408}{537216}$
$\triangleright \frac{8610}{743925} = \frac{9102}{786435}$	$\triangleright \frac{8653}{217940} = \frac{9671}{243580}$	$\triangleright \frac{8750}{436912} = \frac{9375}{468120}$	$\triangleright \frac{8970}{163425} = \frac{9568}{174320}$
$\triangleright \frac{8614}{203597} = \frac{9086}{214753}$	$\triangleright \frac{8670}{152439} = \frac{9520}{167384}$	$\triangleright \frac{8791}{542360} = \frac{9263}{571480}$	$\triangleright \frac{8970}{351624} = \frac{9465}{371028}$
$\triangleright \frac{8614}{235790} = \frac{8791}{240635}$	$\triangleright \frac{8673}{945210} = \frac{8732}{951640}$	$\triangleright \frac{8904}{361725} = \frac{9168}{372450}$	$\triangleright \frac{8976}{142035} = \frac{9328}{147605}$
$\triangleright \frac{8619}{253470} = \frac{8957}{263410}$	$\triangleright \frac{8690}{351274} = \frac{9085}{367241}$	$\triangleright \frac{8904}{536172} = \frac{9328}{561704}$	$\triangleright \frac{8976}{531024} = \frac{9163}{542087}$
$\triangleright \frac{8621}{704359} = \frac{9102}{743658}$	$\triangleright \frac{8690}{451327} = \frac{8910}{462753}$	$\triangleright \frac{8905}{172346} = \frac{9035}{174862}$	$\triangleright \frac{9016}{573482} = \frac{9548}{607321}$
$\triangleright \frac{8624}{173950} = \frac{9240}{186375}$	$\triangleright \frac{8692}{305174} = \frac{9758}{342601}$	$\triangleright \frac{8906}{751243} = \frac{9028}{761534}$	$\triangleright \frac{9024}{735168} = \frac{9306}{758142}$
$\triangleright \frac{8624}{513079} = \frac{8976}{534021}$	$\triangleright \frac{8702}{134596} = \frac{9847}{152306}$	$\triangleright \frac{8910}{753624} = \frac{9240}{781536}$	$\triangleright \frac{9027}{841635} = \frac{9146}{852730}$
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$\triangleright \frac{8625}{193407} = \frac{9750}{218634}$	$\triangleright \frac{8710}{354296} = \frac{9165}{372804}$	$\triangleright \frac{8925}{163470} = \frac{9520}{174368}$	$\triangleright \frac{9028}{763415} = \frac{9620}{813475}$
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$\triangleright \frac{8631}{745290} = \frac{9453}{816270}$	$\triangleright \frac{8712}{340659} = \frac{9504}{371628}$	$\triangleright \frac{8930}{265174} = \frac{9310}{276458}$	$\triangleright \frac{9048}{361572} = \frac{9516}{380274}$

$\triangleright \frac{9053}{412786} = \frac{9876}{450312}$	$\triangleright \frac{9207}{145638} = \frac{9702}{153468}$	$\triangleright \frac{9412}{780653} = \frac{9724}{806531}$	$\triangleright \frac{7263}{519804} = \frac{9415}{673820}$
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$\triangleright \frac{9108}{362457} = \frac{9504}{378216}$	$\triangleright \frac{9210}{347865} = \frac{9824}{371056}$	$\triangleright \frac{9456}{713280} = \frac{9653}{728140}$	$\triangleright \frac{7843}{256910} = \frac{9548}{312760}$
$\triangleright \frac{9108}{574632} = \frac{9306}{587124}$	$\triangleright \frac{9215}{463078} = \frac{9310}{467852}$	$\triangleright \frac{9460}{135278} = \frac{9640}{137852}$	$\triangleright \frac{7843}{291065} = \frac{9207}{341685}$
$\triangleright \frac{9126}{534708} = \frac{9802}{574316}$	$\triangleright \frac{9234}{716850} = \frac{9481}{736025}$	$\triangleright \frac{9472}{815360} = \frac{9546}{821730}$	$\triangleright \frac{9072}{143856} = \frac{9702}{153846}$
$\triangleright \frac{9130}{678425} = \frac{9628}{715430}$	$\triangleright \frac{9238}{170456} = \frac{9486}{175032}$	$\triangleright \frac{9486}{503217} = \frac{9672}{513084}$	$\triangleright \frac{9072}{153846} = \frac{9720}{164835}$
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$\triangleright \frac{9152}{374608} = \frac{9460}{387215}$	$\triangleright \frac{9270}{134586} = \frac{9785}{142063}$	$\triangleright \frac{9548}{120736} = \frac{9765}{123480}$	$\triangleright \frac{9072}{681534} = \frac{9456}{710382}$
$\triangleright \frac{9152}{703648} = \frac{9308}{715642}$	$\triangleright \frac{9275}{134680} = \frac{9805}{142376}$	$\triangleright \frac{9618}{523740} = \frac{9847}{536210}$	$\triangleright \frac{9075}{143286} = \frac{9350}{147628}$
$\triangleright \frac{9156}{230874} = \frac{9810}{247365}$	$\triangleright \frac{9275}{138460} = \frac{9805}{146372}$	$\triangleright \frac{9718}{362504} = \frac{9804}{365712}$	$\triangleright \frac{9075}{168234} = \frac{9625}{178430}$
$\triangleright \frac{9156}{347802} = \frac{9810}{372645}$	$\triangleright \frac{9284}{301576} = \frac{9706}{315284}$	$\triangleright \frac{9718}{452360} = \frac{9831}{457620}$	$\triangleright \frac{9075}{821634} = \frac{9625}{871430}$
$\triangleright \frac{9163}{547820} = \frac{9724}{581360}$	$\triangleright \frac{9284}{367510} = \frac{9706}{384215}$	$\triangleright \frac{9724}{308165} = \frac{9860}{312475}$	$\triangleright \frac{9078}{462315} = \frac{9256}{471380}$
$\triangleright \frac{9170}{326845} = \frac{9562}{340817}$	$\triangleright \frac{9305}{124687} = \frac{9540}{127836}$	$\triangleright \frac{9724}{308516} = \frac{9856}{312704}$	$\triangleright \frac{9085}{146372} = \frac{9480}{152736}$
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$\triangleright \frac{9184}{576320} = \frac{9758}{612340}$	$\triangleright \frac{9408}{635712} = \frac{9513}{642807}$	$\triangleright \frac{7261}{804593} = \frac{8357}{926041}$	

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